

UNIVERSIDAD DE GRANADA
FACULTAD DE FILOSOFÍA Y LETRAS
DEPARTAMENTO DE HISTORIA Y CIENCIAS DE LA MÚSICA

**UNIVERSIDAD
DE GRANADA**

ANALYSIS OF TWO TERMS RELATED TO MUSIC
IN ANCIENT MESOPOTAMIA:
NAM-NAR AND *NĀRŪTU(M)*

A Dissertation written by

DANIEL SÁNCHEZ MUÑOZ

under the supervision of

PROF. ANTONIO MARTÍN MORENO (UGR)

and presented in order to obtain the

PH.D. DEGREE IN HISTORY AND ARTS

by the

UNIVERSITY OF GRANADA

October 2019

Editor: Universidad de Granada. Tesis Doctorales
Autor: Daniel Sánchez Muñoz
ISBN: 978-84-1306-406-2
URI: <http://hdl.handle.net/10481/58701>

To Juan Manuel Fernández Soler, *amicissimo historico*.

To José Andrés Morales Prados, *amicissimo tibicini*.

To my beloved grandparents José María Muñoz Cañadas and Carmen Díaz Arenas.

Sadly, all of you have already left this world, but your love and my good memories of
you will always be with me.

Ohne Musik wäre das Leben ein Irrtum

*Götzen-Dämmerung oder Wie
man mit dem Hammer philosophiert*

Friedrich Wilhelm Nietzsche

TABLE OF CONTENTS

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS	xi
ABBREVIATIONS AND WRITING CONVENTIONS	xviii
1. Index of abbreviations	xviii
1.1. Bibliographical abbreviations	xviii
1.2. Grammatical abbreviations	xxiv
2. About terms in ancient languages.....	xxv
1. INTRODUCTION	1
1.1. Approach to the topic of this study.....	1
1.2. Previous Research.....	3
1.2.1. About a Word for “Music” in Mesopotamia	3
1.2.1.1. Introduction	3
1.2.1.2. Main Positions for this Question.....	3
1.2.1.2.1. Anne Draffkorn Kilmer	3
1.2.1.2.2. Konrad Volk	4
1.2.1.2.3. Dahlia Shehata.....	6
1.2.1.2.4. Piotr Michalowski	8
1.2.1.2.5. Sam Mirelman	10
1.2.1.2.6. Nele Ziegler	11
1.2.1.3. Conclusions	13
1.2.2. Comprehensive Definitions of nam-nar and <i>nārūtu(m)</i>	13
1.2.2.1. Presentations and Specific Remarks	13
1.2.2.1.1. AHw II, p. 789 and CAD 1, p. 382.....	13
1.2.2.1.2. Theo J. H. Krispijn’s Definition of nam-nar	14
1.2.2.1.3. Review of Some Recent Contributions	16

1.2.2.2.	General Remarks	17
1.2.2.2.1.	Short Introduction.....	17
1.2.2.2.2.	About Chronological Variations in the Musical Lexicon.....	18
1.2.2.2.3.	Geographical Changes in Sumero-Akkadian Music terms?.....	18
1.2.2.2.4.	Musical Terms vs. Textual Typologies	21
1.2.3.	General Conclusions.....	21
1.3.	Hypothesis to be proved	21
1.3.1.	Exposition of the hypothesis	21
1.3.2.	About the definition of “Music” used in this study.....	22
1.3.3.	Justification <i>A Priori</i> of our hypothesis.....	23
1.3.3.1.	About terms for “Music” in Ancient Cultures	23
1.3.3.2.	About the condition of the nar/nāru(m)	25
1.4.	Objectives of this study.....	30
1.5.	Methodology.....	31
1.5.1.	General Definition	31
1.5.2.	About the Textual Editions.....	32
1.5.2.1.	Main texts of this study	32
1.5.2.2.	Secondary texts	36
1.5.3.	About the Commentary of these Edited Texts.....	36
1.6.	Expected Results of this study	37
2.	THE THIRD MILLENNIUM	38
2.1.	The Old Akkadian Period	38
2.2.	The 2 nd Dynasty of Lagaš	41
2.2.1.	Introduction	41
2.2.2.	Lexicographical analysis of some terminology pertaining to this excerpt	43
2.2.2.1.	se-em-(da)	43

2.2.2.2.	a₂-la₂	45
2.2.2.3.	bala_ḡ	47
2.2.2.4.	šu du₇-a	51
2.2.3.	Discussion of the previous translations of nam-nar in this excerpt	52
2.3.	The Ur III Period.....	54
2.3.1.	Music and Weaving in a text from Šulgi's reign.....	54
2.3.1.1.	Introduction	54
2.3.1.2.	Biographical outline of the females mentioned in this text.....	56
2.3.1.2.1.	Nin-Ezem (Pn_{in}-ezem) (r. i 3).....	56
2.3.1.2.2.	Geme-Dumuzida (Pg_{eme}₂-^ddumu-zi-da) (r. i 4)	57
2.3.1.2.3.	Pāpā (Ppa₄-a-pa₄-a) and Tablazu (Ptab-la-zu) (r. i 7–8).....	58
2.3.1.3.	Lexicographical approach to some complex expressions/terms	59
2.3.1.3.1.	lu₂ šu nu-BAD/UŠ₂-a-me	59
2.3.1.3.2.	uš-bar	61
2.3.1.4.	Sense of nam-nar in this excerpt.....	62
2.3.2.	A reference to nam-nar in TRU 41 [ICP 41] (Šulgi 41-00-00), r. 5?.....	65
2.4.	The transition to the Old Babylonian Period	67
2.5.	Conclusions.....	72

3.	NAM-NAR IN THE TEXTS OF THE OLD BABYLONIAN ELEMENTARY SCRIBAL CURRICULUM AND ADMINISTRATION	73
3.1.	General Introduction to the Old Babylonian Sumerian Texts	73
3.2.	The Elementary Scribal <i>Curriculum</i>	74
3.2.1.	Lexical texts.....	74
3.2.1.1.	About a type of song	74
3.2.1.2.	About a type of music	76
3.2.1.3.	About <i>nārūtum</i> and <i>narūtum</i>	79
3.2.2.	Model contracts	82

3.2.2.1.	A text about musical teaching	82
3.2.2.2.	A text about the construction of an instrument?	87
3.2.3.	Elementary literary texts.....	89
3.3.	Legal and Administrative Texts.....	90
3.3.1.	Introduction	90
3.3.2.	About musicians and anointed priests	91
3.3.3.	Some comments about several recently published texts	94
3.3.3.1.	Introduction	94
3.3.3.2.	Musicians and bur-šu-ma officials	95
3.3.3.3.	About the term nam-nar-sa	99
3.4.	Conclusions.....	100

4. NAM-NAR IN THE OLD BABYLONIAN SUMERIAN LITERARY TEXTS

102

4.1.	Introduction to this Chapter	102
4.2.	Debates.....	103
4.2.1.	Music at school according to two excerpts of <i>Enkihegal and Enkitalu</i> ..	103
4.2.1.1.	<i>Enkihegal and Enkitalu</i> , 94–99	103
4.2.1.1.1.	Introduction	103
4.2.1.1.2.	Terms only referred to singing?	105
4.2.1.1.3.	Identification of the za₃-mi₂/sammû(m)	106
4.2.1.1.4.	The musical role of the za₃-mi₂/sammû(m) and conclusions	111
4.2.1.2.	<i>Enkihegal and Enkitalu</i> , 110–113: music and morality	112
4.2.2.	<i>The Father and his rude Son</i> , 107–112	116
4.3.	Mythological Narrations	121
4.3.1.	Introduction: about a master of the music (lugal nam-nar-ra)	121
4.3.2.	Music as destiny: nam-nar in <i>Enki and Ninmah</i> , b 26–29	123
4.3.3.	About <i>Inanna and Enki</i> I v 33–34 and II v 47–52.....	128

4.3.3.1.	Introduction	128
4.3.3.2.	Lexicographical approach to the terms of this excerpt	129
4.3.3.2.1.	ḡeš-gu₃-di	129
4.3.3.2.2.	nam-ab-ba	131
4.3.3.3.	Conclusions	132
4.4.	Royal Praise Poetry	133
4.4.1.	Introduction	133
4.4.2.	About a musical room in <i>Ur-Namma A</i> , 187–188	133
4.4.2.1.	Introduction	133
4.4.2.2.	Lexicographical analysis of this excerpt	135
4.4.2.2.1.	tige₂, a-da-ab, gi-gid₂, and za-am-za-am	135
4.4.2.2.2.	ḡeš-gu₃-di and zag e₂-ḡars-e us₂	136
4.4.2.2.3.	e₂ and e₂-gal	138
4.4.2.3.	Towards a new definition of e₂ nam-nar-ra	138
4.4.3.	Šulgi and nam-nar	141
4.4.3.1.	Introduction: a king devoted to music	141
4.4.3.2.	<i>Šulgi B</i> , 157: nam-nar as musical sound	143
4.4.3.2.1.	Introduction	143
4.4.3.2.2.	Approach to some terms in this excerpt	147
4.4.3.2.2.1.	buru₃	147
4.4.3.2.2.2.	daḡal	148
4.4.3.2.2.3.	šu du₇-a	148
4.4.3.2.2.4.	Conclusions	149
4.4.3.2.3.	tige₂ as musical instrument in <i>Šulgi B</i> , 157	149
4.4.3.2.3.1.	Introduction	149
4.4.3.2.3.2.	A supposed connection between tige₂ and tigidla	149
4.4.3.2.3.3.	balan during the Old Babylonian Period	150

4.4.3.2.3.4. tige₂ : the balan instrument of the nar	152
4.4.3.2.4. a-da-ab as musical instrument in <i>Šulgi B</i> , 157	154
4.4.3.2.5. Conclusions	154
4.4.3.3. <i>Šulgi B</i> , 162: about Šulgi’s musical limits	155
4.4.3.4. <i>Šulgi B</i> , 277–279: study of šu nam-nar-ra	157
4.4.3.5. <i>Šulgi CC</i> and the term ser₃ nam-nar	159
4.4.4. Išmē-Dagān and nam-nar	161
4.4.4.1. <i>Išmē-Dagān A + V</i> , 367: devotion to the music	161
4.4.4.2. <i>Išmē-Dagān A + V</i> , A 373–374: the difficulties of music	163
4.5. A last (and uncertain) literary text	165
4.6. Conclusions about nam-nar in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts	168
5. NĀRŪTUM IN THE OLD BABYLONIAN TEXTS FROM MARI	171
5.1. Introduction	171
5.2. Texts from the reign of Šamšī-Addu (1795–1776 BCE)	172
5.2.1. Texts with <i>nārūtum</i> as “office of the <i>nārum</i> ”	172
5.2.1.1. ARM 1 78 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	172
5.2.1.2. FM 9 24 [M.5160] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	175
5.2.2. Texts with <i>nārūtum</i> as “music”	176
5.2.2.1. ARM 1 64 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	176
5.2.2.2. ARM 5 73 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	178
5.2.2.3. FM 9 13 [M.6851] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	179
5.2.2.4. FM 9 26 [M.14611] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	182
5.2.2.5. FM 9 27 [M.13050] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	184
5.2.2.6. FM 9 30 [M.7321] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	186
5.2.2.7. FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	187
5.2.2.8. FM 9 55 [A.905] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	189

5.2.2.9.	FM 9 62 [M.7281] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00).....	190
5.3.	Texts from the reign of Zimrī-Līm (1775–1761 BCE).....	191
5.3.1.	Texts with <i>nārūtum</i> as “office of the <i>nārum</i> ”.....	191
5.3.2.	Texts with <i>nārūtum</i> as “music”.....	192
5.4.	About the expression <i>enūt nārūtīm</i>	193
5.5.	Conclusions.....	196
6.	THE FIRST MILLENNIUM	198
6.1.	General Introduction.....	198
6.2.	The Neo-Assyrian Period.....	199
6.2.1.	Reflections about a “musical instrument” in a lexical text.....	199
6.2.2.	The term šer3 nam-nar during the Neo-Assyrian Period.....	202
6.2.3.	Conclusions.....	205
6.3.	The Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid Periods.....	206
6.3.1.	Introduction.....	206
6.3.2.	<i>nārūtu</i> in other Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid legal texts.....	208
6.3.2.1.	<i>nārūtu</i> as “profession of the <i>nāru</i> ” <i>lato sensu</i>	208
6.3.2.2.	Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid specializations of <i>nārūtu</i>	211
6.3.3.	Conclusions.....	214
6.4.	The Seleucid Period.....	214
6.4.1.	Introduction.....	214
6.4.2.	EZEN nam-lul instead of EZEN nam-nar ?.....	215
6.4.2.1.	Exposition of the hypothesis.....	215
6.4.2.2.	Discussion.....	216
6.4.2.3.	Conclusions.....	218
6.4.3.	šer3 nam-nar or kešda nam-nar ?.....	219
6.4.3.1.	Previous discussions.....	219

6.4.3.2.	Evidence for the reading kešda nam-nar	219
6.4.4.	How should we define kešda nam-nar ?.....	221
6.4.4.1.	Introduction	221
6.4.4.2.	Seleucid evidence for nam-nar and <i>nārūtu</i>	222
6.4.4.2.1.	A Seleucid prebend of the <i>nāru</i> ?.....	222
6.4.4.2.2.	About a “musical festival”.....	223
6.4.4.2.3.	The text <i>corpus</i> of the <i>nāru</i>	225
6.4.4.3.	A new definition for kešda nam-nar	228
6.5.	General Conclusions of the Chapter	229
7.	CONCLUSIONS	231
7.1.	Introduction.....	231
7.2.	Problems for any type of conclusion	231
7.3.	nam-nar and <i>nārūtu(m)</i> as “music”	233
7.4.	About other meanings for nam-nar and <i>nārūtu(m)</i>	236
7.5.	Final statement.....	237
8.	INDICES	238
8.1.	Terminological index	238
8.1.1.	Common People	238
8.1.2.	Deities and other mythological characters	240
8.1.3.	Rulers.....	241
8.1.4.	Toponyms	241
8.1.5.	Terms in Ancient languages	243
8.1.5.1.	Sumerian.....	243
8.1.5.2.	Akkadian and Sumerograms in Akkadian texts	254
8.1.5.3.	Other Ancient Languages.....	258

8.1.5.3.1. Aramaic	258
8.1.5.3.2. Biblical Hebrew	258
8.1.5.3.3. Chinese	258
8.1.5.3.4. Eblaite.....	258
8.1.5.3.5. Egyptian.....	259
8.1.5.3.6. Elamite.....	259
8.1.5.3.7. Greek	259
8.1.5.3.8. Hittite.....	259
8.1.5.3.9. Hurrian.....	259
8.1.5.3.10. Latin.....	260
8.1.5.3.11. Phoenician	260
8.1.5.3.12. Proto-Semitic	260
8.1.5.3.13. Sanskrit	260
8.1.5.3.14. Ugaritic	260
8.1.6. Mesopotamian Cuneiform Signs	260
8.2. Edited and Commented Texts.....	263
8.3. Cited Texts.....	266
8.3.1. Mesopotamian Texts	266
8.3.1.1. Uruk Period	266
8.3.1.2. Early Dynastic IIIa	266
8.3.1.3. Early Dynastic IIIb	267
8.3.1.4. Ebla.....	267
8.3.1.5. Old Akkadian	268
8.3.1.6. 2 nd Dynasty of Lagaš.....	271
8.3.1.7. Ur III Period	273
8.3.1.8. Old Assyrian.....	284
8.3.1.9. Old Babylonian southern Mesopotamian texts	284

8.3.1.10.	Old Babylonian northern Mesopotamia	307
8.3.1.11.	Middle Assyrian	310
8.3.1.12.	Middle Babylonian	311
8.3.1.13.	Neo-Assyrian.....	312
8.3.1.14.	Neo-Babylonian	321
8.3.1.15.	Achaemenid.....	321
8.3.1.16.	Seleucid	322
8.3.2.	Hittite texts	325
8.3.3.	Elamite texts	325
8.3.4.	Ugaritic texts	325
8.3.5.	Classical Antiquity	325
8.3.6.	Other Texts	326
9.	BIBLIOGRAPHY	327
10.	ABSTRACTS AND CONCLUSIONS IN OTHER LANGUAGES.....	398
10.1.	Resumen en Castellano	398
10.2.	Zusammenfassung auf Deutsch.....	408

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This text is the result of about four years of PhD studies and research. In these years, we have received the support of many institutions and people. In consequence, we would like to express to them our most sincere gratitude.

First, sincere thanks to the Spanish Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities. Certainly, said institution has funded all our activities between the 31/10/2015 and 29/10/2019 with the scholarship FPU14/00927. During that time, we have collaborated with the Department of History and Sciences of Music of the University of Granada (UGR). Moreover, this Ministry has funded our stays in Würzburg (01/09/2017–01/12/2017) and Leiden (09/07/2018–20/12/2018) with the concession of some supplementary economic helps addressed for grant holders of FPU scholarships.

As our first personal appreciation, thanks to Prof. Antonio Martín Moreno. He was our energetic, insightful and, above all, patient PhD advisor in these years and, in several senses, a *magister vitae*. He made possible our incorporation to the Department of Musicology of this University despite our background in Ancient History (from our B.A. and M.A.) but not in Musicology (although an oboe player). In addition, he has been very kind giving permission to us to do all our travels abroad for research and conferences. That has been very important in our particular case because of the current lack of an actual chair of Assyriology at our University. Finally, he has also been a shining example of how to confront the many difficulties of the world of Academia.

Because of their relevance in the first years of our PhD trajectory, thanks to Dr. Félix García Morá (Ancient History, UGR) and Dr. Francisco J. Giménez Rodríguez (Musicology, UGR). We are in debt to them for their advice in these years. We are especially indebted to the early guidance of Dr. Félix García Morá. He was supervisor of our B.A. and M.A. thesis, and gave to us a good introduction to ancient Near Eastern history and some tips on Middle Egyptian—sometimes remembered in this study.

Many thanks also to all the people belonging to the Department of Musicology of our University during our PhD trajectory for their respect and interest in our work. Needless to say, that is mutual. We would like to thank especially the people in charge of the courses where we have collaborated. They have been very flexible and patient with our teaching which was far from brilliant, as they have no doubt seen. They were Dr. Victor Neuman Kovensky, Dr. Consuelo Isabel Pérez Colodrero, Dr. Manuela Cortés García,

Dr. Cecilia Nocilli (many thanks also for our emails in Italian!), Dr. Miguel Ángel Berlanga Fernández and, last but not least, Prof. Artur Schmitt. Sincere thanks for your humanity, for making us feel like a partner and not a mere subordinate, and for our emails in German. Thanks also to Dr. Joaquín López González and Dr. Victoriano J. Pérez Mancilla for their support in the administrative tasks regarding the Graduate School and teaching. In addition, thanks to my colleagues, PhD candidates from this Department, M^a Victoria Arjona González, Torcuato Tejada Tauste, Fátima Martín Ruiz, Elsa Calero Carramolino, Álvaro Flores Coleto and Juan Carlos Galiano Díaz. Everything has been easier with you all. Looking forward to seeing the end of your PhD trajectories!

Other PhD candidates from our *alma mater* have also been very relevant in these years, above all for their personal support and help with the bureaucracy. They are Teresa López Martínez (Painting Department), Laura Martín Ramos (Medieval History), (now Dr.) José Ortiz Córdoba (Ancient History), Ángel Segovia Ganivet and José Carlos Maroto Blanco (Contemporary History), and, especially, three colleagues from the Department of Prehistory and Archaeology: David Laguna Palma, Juan Francisco Bermúdez Calle and our great friend Alexis Maldonado Ruiz.

Regarding our “Assyriological appreciations”, the first of them goes to the people who helped us in our first steps in this discipline and translations of Akkadian texts when our knowledge of that language was weaker than it is now. They are Prof. Enrique Jiménez (whose outstanding trajectory has run in parallel with our PhD life), Prof. Brigitte Lion, Dr. Sam Mirelman and, above all, Dr. Josué Justel Vicente. So importantly, among other things, he introduced us the *Archibab* database, gave some recommendations for our first stay abroad, and helped us to access to the online bibliographical database managed by (now Dr.) Adam Grant Anderson. That last fact has infinitely facilitated our access to the main Assyriological bibliography, normally located in libraries very far from our main living place.

By the summer of the academic year 2015–2016, we already started to contact Richard Dumbrill and Theo J. H. Krispijn, two scholars who have always helped us a lot about some technical aspects of Mesopotamian music. Moreover, they have kindly read and discussed with us some parts of this study with dedication despite their busy agendas.

At the beginning of the academic year 2016–2017 we started to take online courses from the CEPOAT (Study Centre of the Near East and Late Antiquity, *Centro de Estudios del Próximo Oriente y la Antigüedad Tardía* in its Spanish translation). They were by Dr. Josué Justel Vicente (Akkadian) and Dr. Daniel Justel Vicente (Sumerian), and then, Dr.

María Érica Couto Ferreira (Sumerian) and Dr. Bárbara Eugenia Solans Gracia (Akkadian). Many thanks to all of them for their teaching, which created a firm basis in our knowledge of those languages for facing later stages of our learning.

During that academic course 2016–2017 we also began working with a very relevant person in these years: Prof. Pascal Attinger. With his characteristic geniality, kindness, frankness, and rapidity for answering any email on any day of the week, he pointed us to some texts published by Dr. Anne Goddeeris studied in this PhD dissertation and to some aspects of the Sumerian prefix **nam-** in our first “electronic dialogue”. Furthermore, since that time, he has always given us many pieces of advice about bibliography and different aspects of the Sumerian linguistics so well mastered by him. Many thanks for all of that.

Among many other people, we had the pleasure to meet at that time (now Dr.) Sara Arroyo Cuadra, who was finishing her PhD dissertation on the Babylonian *kudurrū*. Since our first emails, she has given us many useful pieces of advice for surviving in the world of Academia. Many thanks for that and for our talks about Mesopotamian musical iconography. It was also very instructing for us to attend the defence of her PhD dissertation on April 2018. Many thanks all of that.

In May of the academic course 2016–2017, we participated in a conference in New York about archaeomusicology organized by Prof. Zdravko Blažeković where we met some people, such as Dr. Stef Conner, Dr. Heidi Köpp-Junk, and Prof. Bo Lawergren. They taught us that, even if our musical research was mainly theoretical, we should never stop playing any musical instrument if we wished to perform good research in our field. In addition to that, we spent some very useful days in the libraries of the ISAW and Met. Museum. As later in Würzburg, their scans helped us to obtain excellent digital material for continuing our research in Spain. Many thanks everybody for that.

As stated above, from 01/09/2017–01/12/2017, we resided as a PhD student in the *Lehrstuhl für Altorientalistik* of the *Universität Würzburg* under the responsibility of PD Dahlia Shehata. As a consequence of our meetings in those months, full of books and discoveries, she became very relevant for our approach to some texts discussed in this study. Furthermore, she has been an excellent mentor for our later trajectory and teacher in some courses taken in that institution. There, we also took other courses in Sumerian, Akkadian language, and texts. Our teachers were by Prof. Daniel Schwemer (whose miraculous teaching aptitude allowed us to follow him perfectly in spite of our very rudimentary knowledge of German, which was improved there thanks to a *Deutsch*

Intensivkurs of the *Universität Würzburg*), the infinitely kind PD Claus Ambos, and Dr. Greta van Buylaere. She made our learning of Akkadian easier. Sincere thanks.

We give thanks also to other members of that institution at that time (as Dr. Carlo Corti and Dr. Mikko Luukko) and the staff of the many university libraries of Würzburg. They helped us considerably to satisfy our main bibliographical problems. In addition to that, in a very short trip to Heidelberg, PD Betina Faist made possible our access to other books available on the famous Assyriological library of the *Seminar für Sprachen und Kulturen des Vorderen Orients* of the *Universität Heidelberg*. Many thanks for that.

During that stay in Würzburg, several relevant things for our later trajectory happened. First, we met finally Prof. Nele Ziegler in Jena (during the *DOT 33* conference), whose contributions about Mesopotamian music were the first thing we read in that domain. Later, as a part of the French-Spanish exposition *Musiques! Échos de l'Antiquité*, she invited to us to do a Spanish translation of *Šulgi B*, 154–174 and to act as a native speaker for the linguistic revision of the ANE contributions of the Spanish version of the catalogue of that exposition, and she invited us to attend the Spanish venues of that exposition in Barcelona and Madrid.

As a consequence, we definitely obtained a good start for a serious study of that excerpt from *Šulgi B*, of course analysed in depth in this study. In addition, we met people such as, among others, Dr. Agnès García Ventura, whose research on Phoenician music has been always very inspirational for us, and she has always given us jewels of advice in several senses. Madrid was the place for a nice conversation with Dr. Manuel Molina Martos, whose project BDTNS (*Base de Datos de Textos Neo-Sumerios*) has been very useful for us. In fact, in order to systematize the Ur III texts about a music which we might use in our dissertation, he let us to prepare some bibliographical revisions for several entries of that database. In this sense, we made explicit the research of some people like Dr. Sam Mirelman and, above all, Prof. Regine Pruzsinszky, who had helped us with some bibliographical aspects before. Many thanks everybody for that.

Additionally, we finally met the said Prof. Regine Pruzsinszky in Freiburg am Briesgau during our stay in Würzburg. Our meeting in her University was very inspirational for us as an occasion for reflecting about the study of Sumerian language in its different Sumerological schools and the figure of the **nar/nāru(m)**. She gave us an exemplar (including an autograph of hers) of the book edited by her and Dr. Dahlia Shehata published in WOO 8. That fact helped us to benefit much more from the rich contents of that book for our research.

Then, and following a recommendation from Dr. María Érica Couto Ferreira, we followed up on the Sumerian and Akkadian courses offered on an online platform of the *DULA (Diplôme d'Université de Langues Anciennes)* by the *Université de Strasbourg*. These courses were taught by Dr. Anne-Caroline Rendu Loisel, whose research on Sumero-Akkadian soundscapes was very interesting for us as a part of the larger world of the Mesopotamian music. We could have never found a better teacher. Certainly, she has been an excellent and very supportive teacher in all the possible academic aspects. Not only for the acquisition of that two-year degree, but also for many other aspects of our PhD trajectory: From discussion of texts, passing for the moment when she wrote for us some letters of recommendation. She also helped us in our most stressful and saddest moments of those years. Sincerely, many thanks for everything.

The last thing that happened in those months in Würzburg was the start of our application for a research and study stay at the *Universiteit Leiden* from the 09/07/2018–20/12/2018 as a visiting scholar. Our supervisor there was Dr. Abraham H. Jagersma, whom we had already contacted in January 2017. Our stay in that Paradise, Leiden, started with the attendance at courses of the 13th Edition of the renowned Leiden Summer School of Languages and Linguistics: “Sumerian” (with Dr. Abraham H. Jagersma, including a later assignment for extra ETCS Credits), “Introduction to Ugaritic” (with Prof. Agustinus Gianto), “Introduction to Classical Mandaic” (with Prof. Holger Gzella and Paul Noorlander) and “Dutch for beginners” (with the enthusiastic Petra Couvée). From those courses, and the other activities of that Summer School, we obtained some interests in Comparative Linguistics which we have tried to reflect in this study. Many thanks.

Then, we had time for exploring in depth the facilities of the library of the NINO (*Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten*), and we tried to write a bit of this dissertation with some feedback from Dr. Abraham H. Jagersma. After the summer, we attended some courses of that institution as guest student: “Royal Inscriptions from the Assyrian to the Persian Empire” (with Dr. Melanie M. Groß, whom we thank also for our conversations in German), “Werkcollege Akkadisch 1: Oudbabylonische brieven” and “Advanced Cuneiform Epigraphy” (with Dr. Jan Gerrit Dercksen) as well as “Advanced Sumerian” with Dr. Abraham H. Jagersma.

Thanks for these courses, especially the last two ones. In the first one, we had our first contact with real clay tablets from the *Böhl Collectie* written in Sumerian, Akkadian, and Elamite (many thanks for this invitation for initiating ourselves in that language). This was very useful for later stages of our study. In the second course, we edited in score and

commented on the first 141 lines of *Lugalbanda and the Anzud Bird*. That was definitely a high point for us. There, we definitely learned how to prepare scores for (Sumerian) literary texts. In fact, all the scores prepared for this PhD dissertation have followed on that. Moreover, we got familiar with reading photos from CDLI. As a part of that course, we discussed our first drafts of *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188 with Dr. Jagersma. He was an excellent teacher (one of the best we have known) and taught us how to go much further. That is not only for Sumerian grammar and literary texts (where his knowledge is out of question), but also for the academic world in general. Infinite thanks for that.

Many thanks also to other Leiden Assyriological colleagues, as Prof. Caroline Waerzeggers, PD Jeanette Fincke, Dr. Lidewij van de Peut, Dr. Jonathan Valk, Julia Giessler, Maarja Seire, Ivo dos Santos Martins, Akiko Tsujita and Stephen Moore. We could not forget to our classmates. Among others, Jasper Cremers, Martijn Kokken, Jet Vellinga, Jolieke van't Hoff, Lucrezia Menicatti, Alba de Ridder, and Lisa van Oudheusden. All of them made those months so nice and productive for us concerning Assyriology and life in general. We need to give thanks also to our friends of the *Leids Harmonie Orkest*. They let us to play as 1st Oboe with them during those months and the final concert. However, above all, they reminded us of the universality of music. Finally, thanks to my landlady, Welmoet Wels, and her family, for all their help and support, even for the Academia, since Welmoet is also a PhD Candidate at the *Universiteit Groningen*.

We would like also to give thanks to people like Emiliano Li Castro, Placido Scardina, and Marco Sciascia for the organization of the two meetings (May 2018, June 2019) of the Seminar “Euterpe” in Tarquinia (Italy). There, in addition to improving our Italian, we could materialize our (mainly theoretical) research and learn how to play the *aulos* (in our case, a replica of the “Silver Pipes” from Ur) with Barnaby Brown and Callum Armstrong, and the lyre with Prof. John Curtis Franklin. His lessons on the Mesopotamian tuning cycle and the culture of the lyre in the ancient Near East and Greece were definitely very useful for us. Of course, thanks to all the other students from these courses for teaching us so many things about ancient and modern musical practices.

Then, we would like to give thanks to the British Museum and the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology for allowing us to collate some tablets in 01–02/08/2019 and 19–23/08/2019 respectively. In London, we could return to the fantastic library of the SOAS. We already were there in December 2016 for the ICONEA conference (where we met Richard Dumbrell and Theo J. H. Krispijn) and, as in that occasion, our stay was very productive thanks to its facilities. In Philadelphia, we

benefited also from conversations with Prof. Steve Tinney, Prof. Grant Frame, Dr. Philip Jones, and other colleagues from said institution.

Finally, we would like to give thanks to these Assyriologists. In these years, they have helped us with bibliography, answered our questions, or just were interested in our work: Prof. Daniel Foxvog, Prof. Andrew R. George, Prof. John Hayes, Prof. Wouter Henkelman, Prof. John Huehnergard, Prof. Manfred Krebernik, Prof. Piotr Michalowski, Prof. Susanne Paulus, Prof. Walther Sallaberger, Prof. Mirjo Salvini, Prof. Gebhard Selz, Prof. Piotr Steinkeller, Prof. Michael P. Streck, Prof. Niek C. Veldhuis, Prof. Annette Zgoll, PD Anna Löhnert, Dr. Barbara A. Böck, Dr. Armando Bramanti, Dr. Manuel Ceccarelli, Dr. Lluís G. Feliu Mateu, Dr. Szilvia Jáka-Sövegjártó, Dr. Anne-Isabelle Langlois, Dr. Enrico Marcato, Dr. Jana Matuszak, Dr. Jeremiah L. Peterson, Dr. Gabriella Spada, Dr. Jonathan Taylor, Dr. Luděk Vacín, Dr. Klaus Wagensohn, Dr. Gioele Zisa, Dr. Elyze Zomer, Carlos Langa Morales, Erika Marsal Palomo and Iñaki Marro Sánchez.

Of course, many thanks also to Dr. Stephanie Lynn Budin. Her background on Ancient Near Eastern, Classical and Gender Studies and Music besides her experience as editor have contributed to improve notably the English and writing style of this text.

Needless to say, all the scientific and writing mistakes of this text are solely ours.

Concerning other appreciations, thanks to our many music friends from the Music Conservatories of Granada. They have taught us a lot about music, and they have been very patient with our busy schedule charged with conferences, stays, and the writing of this PhD dissertation. That especially applies to the last months before the submission of the Dissertation for its evaluation. Special thanks to our colleagues of the winds orchestras from Priego de Córdoba and Huétor Vega, as well as the “Ave María” of Granada, three ensembles where we have had the pleasure of making good music with excellent people as 1st Oboe. Certainly, they have been very supportive of our circumstances (travels, etc.) We missed a lot when we could not play with them. Thanks to everybody for all of that.

Our final *gratia*, but not the least, is for our parents and our sister besides, of course, the rest of our family, including our grandparents, some of them unfortunately deceased in these years. Thanks for all your love, support, and understanding for our work with “cookies” with “scratches” made by kids. We are certainly in debt to you for all of that, but no effort on our part will be enough to compensate you.

Granada, October 2019

ABBREVIATIONS AND WRITING CONVENTIONS

1. Index of abbreviations

1.1. Bibliographical abbreviations

As is usual in Assyriology, some publications referred in this study will be cited with an abbreviation in a footnote. For such abbreviations, we follow the list of CDLI (http://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/abbreviations_for_assyriology; [Last search on 12/10/2019])¹. That list seemed to us very updated and complete, especially for electronic publications and Sumerological collections. Moreover, it was also easier to search there our abbreviations than in AHW, CAD or RIA. We have also these other abbreviations (normally volumes of collections referred to on CDLI) and exceptions:

AbB 9	= Stol, 1981
AbB 14	= Veenhof, 2005
aBZL	= Mittermayer, 2006
Achemenet	Briant, P. (1999 -), <i>Achemenet Project</i> , [Online database] < http://www.achemenet.com/fr/ > [Last search on 12/10/2019].
AIHA	<i>The Ancient Inscriptions in Himrin Area</i>
AIHA 4	= Rašīd, 1981
AnOr 7	= Schneider, 1932
Archibab	<i>Archibab. Archives Babyloniennes</i> (XX ^e -XVII ^e siècles av. J.-C.), [Online database] < http://www.archibab.fr/ > [Last search the 12/10/2019]. Editions from this site will be cited with the catalogue numbers used in that database (a T + a number with four digits)
ARET 5	= Edzard, 1984
ARET 9	= Milano, 1990

¹ Obviously, in a study focused on Mesopotamian music like this one, we cannot follow the abbreviation “Musik” of CDLI for the Henrike Hartmann’s PhD Dissertation (= Hartmann, 1969) since there are many other works of this study with this “Musik” in the title (for instance, Volk, 1994).

ARM 1	= Dossin, 1950
ARM 5	= Dossin, 1951
ARM 10	= Dossin, 1978
ARM 13	= Dossin, <i>et alii</i> , 1964
ARM 18	= Rouault, 1977
ARM 21	= Durand, 1983
ARM 22/1	= Kupper, 1983
ARM 23	= Bardet, <i>et alii</i> , 1984
ARM 24	= Talon, 1985
ARM 25	= Limet, 1986
ARM 32	= Arkhipov, 2012
Atiqot 4	= Levy and Artzi, 1965
AUCT 1	= Sigrist, 1984
AUCT 3	= Sigrist, Gavin, Stein and Menard
BDTNS	<i>Base de Datos de Textos Neo-Sumerios</i> , [Online database] < http://bdtns.filol.csic.es/ > [Last search on 12/10/2019]. Editions from this site will be cited with the catalogue numbers used in that database (BDTNS + a number with six digits)
BIN 3	= Keiser, 1971
BIN 5	= Hackman, 1937
BIN 9	= Crawford, 1954
BIN 10	= van de Mieroop, 1987
BLMS	<i>Bilinguals of Late Mesopotamian Scholarship</i> , [Online database] < http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/blms/corpus > [Last search on 12/10/2019]. In order to access the editions, just write the abbreviation or the museum number of the manuscript.
BPOA 2	= Ozaki and Sigrist, 2006
BPOA 6	= Sigrist and Ozaki, 2009a
BPOA 7	= Sigrist and Ozaki, 2009b
BPOA 9	= Peterson, 2011
BPOA 10	= Paoletti, 2012

- bo. e. Bottom edge (for textual editions)
- CAL *The Comprehensive Aramaic Lexicon*, [Online database]
<<http://CAL.huc.edu>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- CAMS/GKAB *Corpus of Ancient Mesopotamian Scholarship: Geography of Knowledge Corpus*, [Online database]
<<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/cams/gkab/corpus/>>
[Last search the 12/10/2019]. In order to access a concrete edition, write the abbreviation or catalogue number of the text following this edition.
- CCP *Cuneiform Commentaries Project*, [Online database]
<<https://ccp.yale.edu/>> [Last search the 12/10/2019]. Editions from this database will be mentioned with their CCP numbers.
- CT 4 = Pinches, 1898
- CT 11 = Thompson, 1900
- CT 12 = Thompson, 1901
- CT 14 = Thompson, 1902
- CT 15 = King, 1902a
- CT 17 = Thompson, 1903
- CT 18 = Thompson, 1904a
- CT 19 = Thompson, 1904b
- CT 28 = Handcock, 1910
- CT 36 = Gadd, 1921
- CT 45 = Pinches, 1964
- CT 54 = Dietrich, 1979
- CT 58 = Alster and Geller, 1990
- CUSAS 11 = Visicato and Westenholz, 2010
- CUSAS 12 = Civil, 2010
- CUSAS 13 = Maiocchi, 2009
- CUSAS 19 = Maiocchi and Visicato, 2012
- CUSAS 20 = Pomponio and Visicato, 2015
- CUSAS 35 = Bartash, 2016
- DCCLT *Diachronic Corpus of Cuneiform Lexical Texts*,
[Online database] <<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/dcclt/pager>>

[Last search on 12/10/2019]. Composite editions from this database will be cited with a catalogue number of the type Q + six digits. For non-composite editions, write the abbreviation or the catalogue number of the text following an edition of this database.

- DGS = Jagersma, 2010
- ELS = Attinger, 1993
- eSAD *Supplement to the Akkadian Dictionaries*, [Online database] <<http://altorient.gko.uni-leipzig.de/etymd.html>>
[Last search the 12/10/2019]. For checking references, look for the term in question by its first letter.
- ETCSL *Electronic Text Corpus of Sumerian Literature*, [Online database] <<http://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019]. Editions will be cited using the catalogue numbers of that database.
- FM *Florilegium Marianum* (collection)
- FM 3 = Durand and Guichard, 1997
- FM 9 = Ziegler, 2007
- FM 11 = Chambon, 2009
- FM 16 = Reculeau, 2018
- Gestirn-* = Weidner, 1967
Darstellungen
- HAO *Hilprecht Archive Online*, [Online database] <<http://altorient.gko.uni-leipzig.de/etymd.html>>
[Last search the 12/10/2019].
- JANER *Journal of Ancient Near Eastern Religion*
- LaBaSi *Late Babylonian Signs*, [Online database] <<https://labasi.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- le. e. Left edge (for textual editions)
- NaBuCCo Abraham, K., Jursa, M. and Gordin, Sh. (2013), *The Neo-Babylonian Cuneiform Corpus (NaBuCCo)*, KU Leuven, [Online database] <<https://nabucco.arts.kuleuven.be/>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
Editions from that database will be cited with a catalogue number composed of four digits.

MDP 14	= Scheil, 1913
MVN 3	= Owen, 1975
MVN 5	= Sollberger, 1978
MVN 6	= Pettinato, 1977
MVN 7	= Pettinato and Picchioni, 1978
MVN 8	= Calvot, Pettinato, Picchioni and Reshid, 1979
MVN 10	= Grégoire, 1981
MVN 12	= Sigrist, Owen and Young, 1984
MVN 15	= Owen, 1991
MVN 20	= D'Agostino, 1997
MVN 21	= Koslova, 2000a
Nisaba 6	= al-Rawi and D'agostino, 2005
Nisaba 11	= al-Rawi and Verderame, 2006
Nisaba 15/2	= Owen, 2013
Nisaba 23	= al-Rawi and Verderame, 2009
Nisaba 24	= al-Rawi, D'Agostino and Taylor, 2009
Nisaba 26	= al-Rawi, Gorello and Notizia, 2013
Nisaba 30	= Owen, 2016.
o.	Obverse (for textual editions)
OECT 4	= van der Meer, 1938
OIP 11	= Chiera, 1929
OrSP 18	= Schneider, 1925
OrSP 47–49	= Schneider, 1930
PBS 1/1	= Myhrman, 1911
PBS 5	= Poebel, 1914
PBS 8/1	= Chiera, 1914
PBS 8/2	= Chiera, 1922a
PBS 12/1	= Langdon, 1917
PDT 2	= Yildiz and Gomi, 1988
PIHANS 117	= Eidem, 2011
Princeton 2	= Sigrist, 2005
Perseus	<i>Perseus Digital Library</i> , [Online database] < http://www.perseus.tufts.edu/hopper/ >

- [Last search the 04/09/2019].
- r. Reverse (for textual editions)
- RINAP *The Royal Inscriptions of the Neo-Assyrian Period*, [Online database]
 <<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/rinap/corpus/>>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019]. Editions from that database will be cited with its catalogue numbers (Q + six digits)
- SAA 3 = Livingstone, 1989
- SAA 7 = Nissinen, 1998
- SAA 10 = Parpola, 1993
- SAA 20 = Parpola, 2017
- SAAo *State Archives of Assyria Online*, [Online database]
 <<http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/saao/corpus>>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019]. In order to access to the editions from this database, write the original SAA number in the search tool.
- Sant'Agostino *Sant'Agostino / Agustinus Hipponensis*, [Online database],
 <<https://www.augustinus.it/index2.htm>>
 [Last search 04/09/2019].
- SANTAG 6 = Koslova, 2000a
- TCL 5 = Genouillac, 1922
- TCL 6 = Thureau-Dangin, 1922
- TCL 11 = Thureau-Dangin, 1926
- TCL 14 = Thureau-Dangin, 1928
- TLA *Thesaurus Linguae Aegyptiae*, [Online database],
 <<http://aew.bbaw.de/tla/index.html>> [Last search 12/10/2019].
- TMH 5 = Pohl, 1935
- TMH 10 = Goddeeris, 2016
- TH NF 4 = Kramer, 1967c
- TUT = Reisner, 1901
- UET 3 = Legrain, 1947
- UET 5 = Figulla and Martin, 1953
- UET 6/1 = Gadd and Kramer, 1963
- UET 6/2 = Gadd and Kramer, 1966
- UET 6/3 = Shaffer and Ludwig, 2006

UET 7	= Gurney, 1973
UET 9	= Darlene, 1976
VAS 10	= Zimmern, 1913
VS 26	= Veenhof, 1992
Wb	= Erman and Grapow, 1924–1961
YOS 5	= Grice, 1919
YOS 6	= Dougherty, 1923
YOS 10	= Goetze, 1947b
YOS 15	= Goetze, 2009
YOS 18	= Snell and Lager, 1991

In printed books, an abbreviation + number refers a text in the book mentioned with that abbreviation. Thus, FM 9 13 is text 13 in Ziegler 2007. If the citation refers to a p. (= page) or pl. (=plate), that page or plate in the cited work it meant.

1.2. Grammatical abbreviations

Finally, this study uses some grammatical abbreviations (both for Sumerian and Akkadian) following those of DGS, p. 17. However, there are some exceptions. They follow on the new version of Jagersma’s grammar, an unpublished and shortened text currently used for teaching purposes by his author and updated annually. These different abbreviations are from that grammar:

1SG.POSS	1 st singular possessive (Sumerian and Akkadian)
3SG.POSS	3 rd (human) singular possessive (Sumerian and Akkadian)
3NH.POSS	3 rd non-human possessive (Sumerian; nouns)
3NH.IO	3 rd non-human indirect object (Sumerian; verbal chains)
3NH.O	3 rd non-human direct object (Sumerian; verbal chains)
PFV	Perfective Verbal Form (Sumerian; verbal stems)

2. About terms in ancient languages

Following some Assyriological conventions, these are the different types of letters we are going to use for our different terms in the ancient languages used in this study:

- The few Elamite terms mentioned in this study will be written in normal letters. For instance, šu-ku-ri, a term of uncertain meaning.
- Akkadian terms, and most of the rest of the foreign terms used in this study, will be written in *italics*. For instance, *ilu(m)* (Akkadian) for “deity”. Concerning mimation in Akkadian terms, when we deal with texts before the end of the Old Babylonian Period, we shall always write the final *m*. For later periods, we shall always delete it. When we talk about a term without paying attention to a concrete period, said word will be written with an “(m)” in order to indicate the optional presence of that letter.
- Sumerian terms will be written in **bold letters**, for instance, **diġir** for “deity”².
- Sumerograms³ (here only for Akkadian texts) will be written in **BOLD SMALL CAPS**⁴. For instance, **DIDIR**, which must be read as *ilu(m)* in an Akkadian text, *siuna-* or *siunis-* (**siuniya* etymologically) in a Hittite text⁵, or *eni-* in a Hurrian one⁶. All these terms mean “deity” as the original Sumerian **diġir**.
- Finally, we use CAPITAL LETTERS for names of signs. For instance, the sign AN, which can be read logographically (for instance, **diġir**), but also phonetically (for instance, **an** as in the Sumerian **mu-na-an-du₃**, “he built it for him/her”).

² It is not relevant to use the conventions described in DGS, p. 12 because, as the author told us, they are used by nobody beyond DGS.

³ We understand the Sumerogram (also the Akkadogram) to be something between the sign (which has logographic and phonetic readings) and a concrete word (a Sumerogram never gives a phoneme). In this sense, we find it convenient to make this distinction which is sometimes forgotten. See, for instance, Black, 1991 for a confusion between Sumerograms and signs (go to our section 2.4 for demonstration).

⁴ We avoid the NORMAL SMALL CAPS as a matter of coherence with our conventions for the Sumerian.

⁵ Tischler, 2001: 153.

⁶ GLH, p. 80; Fournet, 2013: 32.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Approach to the topic of this study

The clay tablet RS 15.30 + 15.49 + 17.387 (Ugarit, modern Ra's Šamra in Syria; 15th century BCE¹) contains the world's oldest known (and complete²) musical piece: the fragment H.6 from the group of texts known as “Hurrian Songs”³, a fragment usually called the “Hurrian Hymn of Ugarit”. The content of that tablet (defined in its colophon as a “song”, *zamāru* in Akkadian) is divided in two parts. On the one hand, a prayer of an infertile woman to the moon goddess Nikkal written in Hurrian⁴. On the other hand, there are some numbers with terms (for instance, *kablite*) designating string combinations or intervals with origin in the Sumero-Akkadian tradition⁵ from southern Mesopotamia.

These technical musical terms (in addition to the *nīd qabli* describing the mode of this song⁶) are still difficult to understand for researchers. In fact, many monodic⁷ and polyphonic⁸ reconstructions for that piece have been proposed in the past. However, they are in any case a good example for knowing how rich the Sumero-Akkadian musical terminology could be. Certainly, we have many terms in these two languages for

¹ According to Kilmer, 2014: 92. However, Krispijn, 2002: 473 proposes the chronology \pm 1200 BCE.

² The usual agreement among Assyriologists/researchers on Mesopotamian music is that we have a complete melody here composed of an accompaniment and a melody. This melody would probably repeat the higher note of the dichord (see Kilmer, 1974: 80; Krispijn, 2002: 479 or Dumbrill, 2019: 65 for modern reconstructions of this song). However, Hagel, 2005: 290 and 2018: 109 thinks that those dichords would reflect just an accompaniment, not being necessary to write down the melody, learned by heart by the singer. In any case, neither option is perfect, as the dichords and text are notated separately in the tablet.

³ See Dumbril, 2005: 111–175 for the complete group of Hurrian songs from Ugarit.

⁴ See Krispijn, 2002: 474-475 for a grammatical analysis and translation of its content. That is based on Ilse Wegner's Hurrian grammar published in 2000. Perhaps it might be revised with Wegner, 2007.

⁵ Certainly, the intervals of that tablet were already known by the Old Babylonian “Tuning Instructions” UET 7 74 and UET 6/3 899 (see Krispijn, 2002: 472 and Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009 for reference).

⁶ Crocker, 1997: 195 and Kilmer, 2000: 114 said that it designated the Dorian Mode. However, Hagel, 2005: 298–311 gave some arguments for considering it the equivalent of the Lydian mode. Shehata, 2017b: 45 shared them. Nevertheless, Kilmer, 2014: 95 still maintained its identification with the Dorian mode.

⁷ Wulstan, 1971: 380-381; Duchesne-Guillemain, 1975: 166 (also 1980: 22, 1984: 31); Vitale, 1979-1980: 61–62 (also 1982: 261–262); Dumbrill, 2005: 130 (last update in Dumbrill, 2019: 65).

⁸ Kilmer, 1974: 80; Černý, 1988: 62 (also Černý, 2004: 30); West, 1994: 177; Krispijn, 2002: 479.

instruments and their parts⁹, musicians¹⁰, compositions (with their divisions)¹¹ in addition to performance techniques, and related topics¹². In this way, those musical terms (and the texts containing them) are a very important source for understanding the relationships of Mesopotamian people with their music. However, was there any term for “Music” *per se* in Sumerian and/or Akkadian? Was there a term gathering all these aspects as in our own word for “Music”?

From a Western perspective, the absence of such a word in any culture may be surprising. Certainly, our Indo-European languages have specific words for “Music,” itself coming from the Latin *musica*. That term would come in turn from the Greek μουσική τέχνη (literally “the Muses’ art”), a term which seems not to have been influenced by non-Indo-European languages¹³. However, outside this language family, the presence of a term for “Music” is not so common around the world¹⁴. It is relevant, for instance, that the languages of many African countries have only adopted the term for “Music” from the languages of the European countries which colonized them in the past. Instead, the native languages of these countries usually just refer to some concrete musical practices. This is the case of *kuimba* (“to sing”) and *kuridza* (“to play an instrument”) in Shona, a Bantu language from Zimbabwe¹⁵. The same happens in the modern Near East, where, for instance, the Arabic term *al-mūsīqā* seems to be a copy of the Greek μουσική (even with the equivalences $\bar{u} = \text{ou}$ and $\bar{a} = \eta$) coming from the Middle Age¹⁶.

In this sense, let us have a look in our next section at the various answers proffered to this question in the past — the existence (or not) of a word for “Music” in Mesopotamia.

⁹ Krispijn, 2010b: 131–148 (3rd and 2nd Millennia); Gabbay, 2014a: 84–154 (1st Millennium).

¹⁰ Sassmannshausen, 2001: 66, 100–101 (Middle Babylonian Period); Jakob, 2003: 518–522 (Middle Assyrian Period); FM 9, p. 13–53 (Old Babylonian Mari); Shehata, 2009: 13–106 (Old Babylonian southern Mesopotamia); Gabbay, 2014a: 63–84 (1st Millennium, with focus on the **gala**/*kalû(m)* lamentation priest). In addition, Pruzsinszky, 2007, 2010a, 2010b, 2013 for the Ur III Period and Tonietti, 1988, 1989, 1997a and 1997b, 1998, 2010, 2018 for the Early Dynastic Period especially for Ebla.

¹¹ Shehata, 2009: 223–336 (Old Babylonian Period), and Gabbay, 2014a: 1–15 (1st Millennium).

¹² *Lato sensu*, Mirelman, 2008: 103–107. For concrete periods, Shehata, 2009: 351–360; Mirelman and Sallaberger, 2010 and Shehata, 2018b: 68–81 (Old Babylonian Period); Koubková, 2016; Mirelman, 2010a; Gabbay and Mirelman, 2011; Rendu Loisel, 2011: 292–332 Mirelman, 2018b (1st Millennium).

¹³ Beekes, 2010: 972.

¹⁴ Zemp, 1978: 37, but, in page 63, there is an approach between the ‘Are’are term ‘*au* and “music”.

¹⁵ D’Amico and Kaye, 2004: 53–54.

¹⁶ Al-Faruqi, 1981: 209; Sultan, 1988: 388.

1.2. Previous Research

1.2.1. About a Word for “Music” in Mesopotamia

1.2.1.1. Introduction

The topic of our previously expressed question is not at all trivial for two reasons. First, to find a positive answer for that question is the first and main step to starting to reflect upon the concept of music in ancient Mesopotamia. Certainly, we cannot talk about a “Mesopotamian concept of music” if we do not even have such a word in Sumerian or Akkadian. This topic is still practically without studies for Mesopotamia¹⁷, unlike in the study of music in ancient Egypt¹⁸, India¹⁹, China²⁰ or Greece²¹.

Second, this topic has obtained a new interest in light of some Assyriological works²² and research projects²³ showing how, before the Greeks, Mesopotamian people already had a philosophical mode of thought. That is, they had a discourse based on universal principles in contrast to a more particularistic, mythical way of approaching reality.

1.2.1.2. Main Positions for this Question

1.2.1.2.1. Anne Draffkorn Kilmer

After the previous considerations, we start now analysing each of the different positions about the question of this study, presenting them according to the chronology

¹⁷ Music is absent in a recent study about Aesthetics in ancient Mesopotamia (Selz, 2018). As the author of that study said to us, contributions of this type are a *desideratum* at the moment.

¹⁸ Barahona, 1997, 2000, 2002 and 2005. We reflected a bit on this aspect in Sánchez Muñoz, 2017.

¹⁹ Rowell, 1981 and, above all, the excellent monograph Rowell, 1992.

²⁰ Hidemi, 1987; Cook, 1995; Park, 2013.

²¹ Among others, see Lippman, 1964; Mathiesen, 1984; García López, Redondo Reyes, and Pérez Cartagena, 2012: 199-268; Rocconi, 2012.

²² Gabbay, 2016; Van de Mierop, 2017.

²³ Like the ERC-2018-STG-funded project “Repetition, parallelism and creativity: an inquiry into the construction of meaning in ancient Mesopotamian literature and erudition”, a project conducted by Nicla de Zorzi. See the space of that author on the web of the *Universität Wien* for more details.

of publication. The first of those reflections came from Anne Draffkorn Kilmer²⁴. She said in 1993 that there “is no single word in Sumerian or Akkadian that means ‘music’ exclusively or as distinct from ‘song’, ‘jubilation’ or ‘revelry’”²⁵. Moreover, she made reference to some Sumerian and Akkadian words close to the concept of “music”, among them, the terms **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*²⁶, defined as “musicianship”²⁷. That translation tries perhaps to respect the nuances of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*, to be considered later. However, those ideas were presented without arguments for their defence and, above all, they are an heir of the previous (comprehensive but outdated) definitions of those terms.

1.2.1.2.2. Konrad Volk

We are going to deal now with an interesting contribution by Konrad Volk²⁸ usually forgotten among the main works on Mesopotamian music²⁹. According to the German author, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* are technical terms based on **nar/nāru(m)**, a term for designating a musician as we shall see later. Therefore, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* are translated there as “Musikertum”³⁰. In any case, for that author, these terms designated all the aspects of music: musicians, instruments, vocal and instrumental music, even the musical teaching and performance. Unfortunately, he did not refer any text as an example.

Despite that, according to Volk, there is no specific term for “Music” in Sumerian or Akkadian since we lack a term describing explicitly³¹ the organization of the sounds like

²⁴ These considerations were repeated in Kilmer, 1995: 2606. However, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* are paradoxically defined there as ““musicianship,” “music””, and not only as “musicianship”.

²⁵ Kilmer, 1990-1993: 468. Similar considerations are available on Kilmer and Mirelman, 2001.

²⁶ Kilmer, 1990-1993: 468, and later Volk, 2006: 5; Volk, 2000: 516; Michalowski, 2010b: 118; Ziegler, 2012: 30 n. 9 have considered both terms as equivalent, talking about **nam-nar/nārūtu(m)**. However, as Schramm, 2008: 10 n. 30 said, there is no text where such equivalence is explicitly referenced. In this sense, although they are too similar to consider as two different words, we shall never talk about them as **nam-nar/nārūtu(m)**, but always as **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*.

²⁷ For other translations as “musicianship”, see Collon and Kilmer, 1980: 22; CDA, p. 242; Kilmer and Mirelman, 2001; ePSD (and ePSD2); Parpola, *et al.* 2007: 74 and Foxvog, 2016: 45.

²⁸ Volk, 2006: 4-6.

²⁹ As far as we know, only referred in Ziegler, 2011: 305–306, 309.

³⁰ But not in this contribution (where there is no translation), but in Volk, 2000: 516.

³¹ Volk, 2006: 5 recognises that we can infer that sense of sound combination in some allusions to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. Nevertheless, according to him, that has to come mainly from our own deductions.

the Greek μουσική. As a justification, he says that Mesopotamia seems to have never developed an abstract thinking like the Greeks. Therefore, Mesopotamia could never develop abstract and universal concepts like that of “Music”. In fact, he says that the basis of Pythagoras’ theorem are in Mesopotamia, and Pythagoras learnt there its principles. However, the Greeks would develop the abstract form of that theorem we know today by themselves³². However, we have already seen how current research has stated that Mesopotamia actually had a philosophical-abstract thought like the Greeks³³. In addition, we have two main remarks for the Volk’s argumentation³⁴.

First, the recognition and use of different sounds with an artistic purpose might have belonged to **nam-nar** (and, why not, to the Akkadian *nārūtu(m)*) according to three lines of *Šulgi B*, a text to analyse in depth later. Certainly, as a part of his devotion to **nam-nar**, Šulgi says first³⁵ that he designed rules (**ḡeš ḡur**) for the ^{ḡeš}**šu-kar₂** lute concerning its **zi-zi** (literally “rising”, in this context possibly “ascendant intervals”) and **šu₂-šu₂** (literally “sinking down”, probably “descendant intervals”)³⁶. In the second line³⁷, the king claims to know the “good tuning” (**kam-ma sa₆-ga**) of the **za₃-mi₂** and **gu-uš** instruments. That recalls, by the way, the “Tuning Instructions” of the tablet UET 7 74 [U. 7/80] noted by Konrad Volk in the same study³⁸. Finally, Šulgi says that he could designate (**pad₃**), raise (**gid₂-i**), lower (**tu-lu**) and establish (**gen₆-na**) the musical intervals (**ad**, literally “voices”) of a **ḡeš-gu₃-di** lute³⁹.

Then and finally, we do not understand why Volk here mentions the term μουσική from Claudius Ptolemy’s *Harmonics*⁴⁰. Certainly, that text is a technical treatise from the

³² Volk, 2006: 4-5.

³³ As an example of the previously noted publications, see Van de Mierop, 2017: 186–187.

³⁴ In addition, we should point to a contradiction of Konrad Volk contradicts himself. Certainly, he translates **nam-nar** as “Musik” on page 23 n. 55. However, that term is then translated as “musikalische Ausföhrung” on the page 33 n. 100 of the same contribution.

³⁵ *Šulgi B*, 160 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

³⁶ See Krispijn, 1990: 5–6 and Krispijn, 2002: 472 for identification.

³⁷ *Šulgi B*, 161 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

³⁸ Volk, 2006: 38.

³⁹ *Šulgi B*, 171 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02). See Krispijn, 1990: 14-15 and Krispijn, 2002: 472 for identification of **ad pad₃**, **gid₂-i**, **tu-lu** and **gen₆-na**.

⁴⁰ The quoted excerpt in that publication is “die Fähigkeit, die zwischen hohen und tiefen Tönen bestehenden Unterschiede zu erkennen”. However, he did not cite it properly, and we could not find it having looked for it in the most updated edition of that text we had (Redondo Reyes, 2002).

2nd century CE. That is, it was created after the date of the last cuneiform text (ca. 79/80 CE)⁴¹. Instead of that, Volk might have chosen another of the many texts where μουσική appears⁴², such as Pindar’s *First Olympian Ode* (l. 15). This text is dated to 476 BCE as Volk mentions in his study⁴³. In this sense, it is still contemporary with the last stages of cuneiform culture. If we look at its content, we shall see how μουσική is used there to designate the use of a Dorian φόρμιγξ lyre. This aspect of μουσική is indeed closer to the references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* from that time. In any case, if we can make an allusion to μουσική independently of its chronology as Konrad Volk did, we would like to mention an excerpt where it is said that Pythagoras learned music (μουσική) with the Chaldean magicians⁴⁴. In fact, this text might suggest (paying attention to its chronology and purposes) that Mesopotamian people had actually a word for “Music” like the Greeks.

1.2.1.2.3. Dahlia Shehata

Dahlia Shehata makes her reflections about the presence, or not, of a term for “Music” in Sumerian or Akkadian in the introduction⁴⁵ of her PhD dissertation⁴⁶. There, she comments on an excerpt of the Sumerian literary text currently known as *The Father and his rude Son*⁴⁷. In this way, she was the first author in using, at least, one concrete textual excerpt with **nam-nar** (as in this case) or *nārūtu(m)*. However, due to its introductory character, Shehata’s analyses are sometimes highly imprecise.

⁴¹ See Hunger and De Jong, 2014 for evidence.

⁴² See the word frequency statistics for μουσική at Perseus for evidence.

⁴³ Before that date, the extent of the adjective μουσική had experienced some changes. Certainly, the Muses are already mentioned in the Hesiod’s *Theogony* by the 8th century BCE (see Clay, 1988 for an example of the role of the Muses in *Theogony*). However, Tragedy (one of the arts related to the Muses) appears in Greece by the 472 BCE (Winnington-Ingram, 1985: 258). Comedy and History would appear later in that century (Handley, 1985a: 362; Handley, 1985b: 426). In addition, the arts of the Muses might be originally non-musical by nature since they appear to pertain to the Muses’ mother, Mnemosyne, Titan associated with the Memory (Grimal, 2008: 363). Many thanks to Stephanie Lynn Budin for this remark.

⁴⁴ Iamblichus’ *Pythagoras’ Life*, 4, 19 (Deubner, 1937: 13).

⁴⁵ Shehata, 2009: 1–2.

⁴⁶ Shehata’s Dissertation was originally defended in 2004. However, her (revised) study was finally published in 2009. Therefore, we are dealing with her contribution at this moment, and not before.

⁴⁷ See our Section 4.2.2 for our edition of this excerpt and comments.

So, Dahlia Shehata begins by saying that **nam-nar** (translated as “‘Handwerkskunst’ des Musizierens”) is found in other ancient Near Eastern texts⁴⁸. However, she does not cite any text at the moment of doing that statement⁴⁹. Then, there is an allusion to the several translations of **nam-nar** in the past, something correct in our opinion. However, again, there are no references to publications or exact translations of **nam-nar**. The author says that the term **nar** is relevant in the definition of **nam-nar** (something correct again). Nevertheless, she gives three different definitions for **nar** (“Sänger”, “Instrumentalist” and “Musiker”), and she says that all of them will be equally considered in her work. Finally, she says that, in *The Father and his rude Son* (where **nam-nar** is opposed to **nam-dub-sar**, “writing” or “art of the scribe”), the translation of **nam-nar** as “Music”⁵⁰ might be correct without the risk of an anachronism. That is a very interesting idea although it is presented, again, without references. Certainly, it would have been very interesting to know in which period she thinks that we could find a first reference to “Music” in a modern sense.

In any case, although she seems to be open to the idea of the existence of a word for “Music” in Sumerian and/or Akkadian, she uses different translations for **nam-nar** such

⁴⁸ The author talks about “Literatur”. However, we do not know if she is talking about “literary texts” or simply “texts”. This last option is more probable according to the content of her work (see following footnote for comments). For different positions about the concept of “Literature” in ancient Mesopotamia, see Jiménez, 2013a: 9–11.

⁴⁹ Shehata, 2009 comments the following texts with **nam-nar**: *The Father and his rude Son*, 107–112 (p. 1–2); *Šulgi E*, 155 (p. 24 n. 98); *Proverbs* 3.150 (variant N_{U-JJ}; p. 35 n. 164); *Enki and Ninmah*, b 26–29 (p. 36–37); Geller, 2003: 111 [MS 2951] (p. 112–113); Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534], r. iii 1’–19’ (p. 113–114, 152); ARN 4 [Ist. Ni 9201] (Būr-Sîn 00-12-10) (p. 173); *Šulgi B*, 157 (p. 252), 278 (p. 254); *Proto-luz*, 590 (p. 262); *Death of Nannā*, 19 (p. 265); ARN 35 [Ist. Ni 1922] (Rīm-Sîn I 37-10-00) (p. 384, 394-395). In addition, she makes reference to term *nārūtu(m)* mentioned in Szlechter TJA 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna, 23-10-02 (?)) (p. 38, n. 181). In this sense, we might suppose that she was making reference to all these texts. However, that list is not exhaustive. Therefore, we do not know how large her concept is of “altorientalischen Literatur” (page 1) in this context.

⁵⁰ For other general translations of **nam-nar** as “Music”, see Kilmer, 1995: 468; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 340; Edzard, 2003: 24 and Foxvog, 2016: 45. Dumbrill, 2005: 437; Parpola, *et al.* 2007: 74; Pruzsinszky, 2010: 31 and Pozzer, da Silva and Cerqueira, 2012: 47 (also as “musicalidade”) do the same with the Akkadian *nārūtu(m)*.

as⁵¹ “*nar-Kunst*”⁵², “‘Handwerkskunst’ des Musizierens”, “Gesangskunst”⁵³, “Musikkunst”⁵⁴, “Musik”⁵⁵ and “‘Musik’”⁵⁶ (that is, as a provisional definition). Therefore, she might not be so convinced of this definition of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. In any case, we should note the excessive influence of some previous translations (with their different conceptions concerning **nam-nar**) for the Shehata’s interpretation of some textual excerpts presented in her monograph⁵⁷.

1.2.1.2.4. Piotr Michalowski

The next example comes from two nearly identical contributions from 2010 by Piotr Michalowski⁵⁸. According to this author, there is no word in Sumerian or Akkadian glossed as “Music”, since **nam-nar** is only referred to the “practical knowledge of playing, singing, and performing”. Therefore, it would not refer “the abstract notion of ‘music’”⁵⁹ “or singing, as has sometimes been suggested”⁶⁰. Unfortunately, he did not mention any publication as an example of those former suggestions.

Maybe he has a point in distancing himself from the modern Western concept of music. Certainly, many cultures around the world do not have a word for “Music” as we

⁵¹ In addition, **nam-nar** as “nam-nar-Pfründe” in administrative texts (Shehata, 2009: 173, 384, 394).

⁵² Shehata, 2009: 262, 268 (here as “nar-Musikkunst”). Pay attention also to the “Kaufvertrag über ein Amt (nam-nar) (Zeuge)” (p. 395).

⁵³ Shehata, 2009: 1.

⁵⁴ Shehata, 2009: 112, 252 (here as ‘Musikkunst’, that is, with a provisional character).

⁵⁵ Shehata, 2009: 1–2, 112, 254 n. 1472.

⁵⁶ Shehata, 2009: 36.

⁵⁷ That is more evident in literary texts, since Dahlia Shehata follows the ETCSL editions (Shehata, 2009: 11). Certainly, for *Šulgi B*, 157, ETCSL 2.4.2.02 translates **nam-nar** as “art of music”, and Shehata, 2009: 252 “‘Musikkunst’” (compare with Castellino, 1972: 4, “musical training”; Krispijn, 1990: 1, “Musik” or Ludwig, 1990: 185, “Gesangskunst”). In the same way, in *Šulgi B*, 279 ETCSL 2.4.2.02 has “the singers’ repertoire”, and Shehata, 2009: 254 “‘Gesangsrepertoire’” (compare with Castellino, 1972: 59 “to the art of music” and Ludwig, 1990: 51, “der Gesangskunst”). It might be also the case of *Enki and Ninmah*, b 28 as “musical arts” (ETCSL 1.1.2) and “‘Musik’” (Shehata, 2009: 36). Pay attention to the fact that three Shehata’s translations have ‘ ’ indicating, perhaps, a provisional character.

⁵⁸ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 n. 11–205 n. 13; Michalowski, 2010b: 118.

⁵⁹ Michalowski, 2010b: 118.

⁶⁰ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 n. 13.

have seen in the first part of this Introduction⁶¹. However, we find terms for “music” in other languages of the Western World, where, not everybody speaks an Indo-European language like English. This is the case of the Hungarian (an Uralic language) *zene*⁶² or the Czech (a West Slavic language) *hudba*⁶³. We also have a term for “music” in other world languages, like the Japanese *ongaku* (音楽 in *kanji*)⁶⁴ or the Tamil *isai*⁶⁵.

Concerning more “Assyriological” arguments, Michalowski has tried to justify his position saying that, in the Old Babylonian Sumerian legal texts, **nam-nar** seems to refer simply to “the profession of the **nar**”⁶⁶. In addition, he translated the term **nam-nar** in *Šulgi B*, 157 and Geller, 2003: 109–111 [MS 2951] with a meaning fitting with this position⁶⁷. However, beyond some minor contradictions⁶⁸, it is notable that he quoted *Gudea Cylinder B*15.20 without translation when, of course, he knows how to translate that text⁶⁹. Certainly, in that text, as we shall see later⁷⁰, **nam-nar** referred to the action of some instruments, but not their musicians. Therefore, it cannot refer to something related to musical knowledge as Michalowski thought. Maybe he was conscious about that, and he did not translate that except in order to avoid contradicting himself.

In this sense, despite attempts at using more textual evidence than previously in order to justify the non-abstract meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*, Michalowski still has many contradictions in his discourse.

⁶¹ Mirelman, 2010b: 115–116 for additional comments.

⁶² Weissmann, 1964: 50.

⁶³ Kettnerová, Lopatková and Bejček, 2012: 441–442.

⁶⁴ Johnson, 1999: 293.

⁶⁵ Terada, 2008: 203.

⁶⁶ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 n. 11 makes reference to ARN 4 [Ist. Ni 9201] (Būr-Sîn 00-12-10), ARN 35 [Ist. Ni 1922] (Rīm-Sîn I 37-10-00), ARN 58 [Ist. Ni 2182] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00) and Kraus, 1951: 200-201 [Ist. Ni 2181] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00). There is a reference to Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534] in page 205 n. 13 of that study. He said that, at that time, many model contracts were still unpublished. However, the new works publishing this type of texts (Spada, 2018; George and Spada, 2019) have brought forth no new examples with **nam-nar** (thanks to Gabriella Spada for her communications).

⁶⁷ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 and 206.

⁶⁸ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 translates the first reference to **nam-nar** in Geller, 2003: 109-111 [MS 2951] (o. 3) as “music”. Only the second (and reconstructed) one is translated as “*the skill of playing*”, where the italics may indicate an unsure translation.

⁶⁹ Michalowski, 2010a: 206 n. 17

⁷⁰ See our section 2.2 (and especially 2.2.3) for comments. Michalowski, 2010a: 206 n. 17 already says the musical terms of that excerpt designated drums without making reference to their musicians.

1.2.1.2.5. Sam Mirelman

We are going to deal now with a short archaeomusicological and ethnomusicological contribution by Sam Mirelman⁷¹ which deserves our attention due to its interesting take on the concept of the music in ancient cultures⁷². In this study, the American composer and Assyriologist says that there was no Akkadian (Sumerian in this case is not considered) word embracing all aspects of musical practice in Mesopotamia. Far from that two words—*nārūtu(m)* and *kalūtu(m)*—only referred to the activity of two common types of musicians in Mesopotamia: the *nāru(m)* and the *kalū(m)*⁷³. In any case, according to Mirelman, such absence of a word for “Music” does not imply *a priori* the absence of a concept which, through different words (like *nārūtu(m)* and *kalūtu(m)*), could certainly designate all aspects of the musical universe.

The author offers a very interesting group of ideas which, in any case and in our opinion, should be nuanced in two aspects. On the one hand, we should remember the beginning of the *Enūma Eliš*. In that text, the time before the existence of the heavens and the earth is not referred as the time when they exist (perhaps with *bašū*, “to exist”). However, the text says that they had not yet received a name (through the use of the stative forms of *nabû* and *zakāru*, “to call”)⁷⁴. In this sense, for the Mesopotamian people, something could not exist if it did not have a name. We may say something similar in our Western culture. In fact, according to Plato (as a more or less contemporary example of the *Enūma Eliš*), the name is the main way of representing a concrete reality⁷⁵.

⁷¹ Mirelman, 2010b (especially page 117).

⁷² Mirelman, 2011: 300.

⁷³ Some textual sources to exemplify that idea would have been very interesting in this study. However, they may be skipped here due to the non-philological orientation of said study. In this attempted comparison of terms for musical professions, we miss a reference to *zammārūtu* defined in SAAo as “music”. However, according to its unique reference (SAA 20 51 [Ass 13956cf], r. ii 11’–14’ (SAAo)), this term seems to be actually referring to the activity of the *zammāru*. This figure had to be a performer of popular music, and not a mere singer (see CAD Z, p. 40 and FM 9, p. 18–19 for the debate). Certainly, the chief *zammāru* has a *sammû* instrument according to the Middle Assyrian Coronation Ritual text, KAR 135 + 137 + 216 + 217 [VAT 9583 + VAT 9936 +? VAT 10113 (+) VAT 09978], r. iii 10–11 (Müller, 1937: 14).

⁷⁴ *Enūma Eliš*, I 1–2 (Lambert, 2013: 50).

⁷⁵ Plato, *Cratylus*, 439^a; see also Luce, 1969: 225 and Rodríguez Adrados, 1989: 416.

On the other hand, *kalûtu(m)* usually describes the profession and the textual *corpus* of the *kalû(m)*⁷⁶, but almost never his activity⁷⁷, which is not necessarily a musical one. Certainly, the *kalû(m)* is mainly a priest who, like the *āšipu(m)*⁷⁸, used occasionally some percussion instruments for the cult⁷⁹. However, the *kalû(m)* was not a musician like the *nāru(m)* who played many musical instruments. By the way, there is no equivalent with *kalûtu(m)* for the expression *enût nārûti(m)*⁸⁰ using the term *nārûtu(m)*.

Therefore, *nārûtu(m)* and *kalûtu(m)* can be compared as offices or text *corpora*⁸¹, but not as artistic musical activities.

1.2.1.2.6. Nele Ziegler

The last precursor⁸² to be considered here comes from Nele Ziegler⁸³. She reflected on this topic when she explained how, in Mesopotamia, music was contrasted to chaotic noise. This idea was mentioned there without any explicit ancient source demonstrating

⁷⁶ For the text *corpus* of the *kalû(m)* priest, see Gabbay, 2014c: 124–140.

⁷⁷ Ebeling, 1931: 16 (r. ii 11); Maul *Ershahunga*, p. 252–253, **er₂ ša₃ ħun-ġa₂** n. 49 [K. 9608], o. 2 (BLMS) (both in fragmentary contexts) and perhaps **Uru am₃-ma-ir-ra-bi**, XIX, 47 (Volk, 1989: 83).

⁷⁸ See our section 6.4.3.2 for reference. According to Gabbay, 2014c: 116, by the 1st millennium (that is, the best known period of the Mesopotamian history for Sam Mirelman), the *kalû* was less connected to the *nāru* musician than to the *āšipu* sorcerer. That was only possible keeping in mind this main function of the *kalû* as priest. See also Shehata, 2008: 124 and Shehata, 2013: 69 about the **gala**.

⁷⁹ Certainly, the *kalû(m)* is usually connected with the *lilisu(m)* kettledrum or the *ħalħallatu(m)* cymbals among others (see Gabbay, 2014a: 118–151 for reference). Rašid, 1984: 122–123 says that those people playing the horizontal harp and having a tall fish-like hat in the relief BM 124948 were *kalû* priests. However, as Gabbay, 2014a: 75 n. 115 says, those hats were also worn by other priests. Certainly, the music of those parades is described in the royal inscriptions as *nigûtu(m)*, “(joyful) music” (see *Aššurbānīpal 3*, vi 46–47, RINAP 5 Q003702; *Aššurbānīpal 4*, vi 48–49, RINAP 5 Q003703; *Aššurbānīpal 6*, vii 53, RINAP 5 Q003705 and *Aššurbānīpal 7*, vi 11”–12”, RINAP 5 Q003704 for reference). That type of music does not fit with the type of music performed by the *kalû(m)* priests. In any case, even if those individuals were *kalû*, their use of the *sammû* instruments might be *ad hoc* for that moment (BM 124948 describes a procession to Ištar’s temple).

⁸⁰ See our sections 5.4 and 6.2.1 for evidence and argumentation.

⁸¹ See our sections 2.4 and 6.4.4.2 (specially the comments about our text 70) for reference.

⁸² As far as we know, other researchers on this topic, such as Uri Gabbay, Regine Pruzsinszky or Richard Dumbrill, have not dealt with this topic.

⁸³ Ziegler, 2012: 30 n. 9.

that such a notion already existed in antiquity⁸⁴. For the French author, there is no word in Sumerian or Akkadian which could be translated as “Music”. That statement stands in contradiction to other publications of hers about Mesopotamian music, since they do have the word “Music” in their titles⁸⁵. Perhaps she did this statement in order to follow the previous research. However, we find more problems in her reflection.

Certainly, she said, on the one hand, that **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* referred to an “art of singing”⁸⁶. However, she never talked about “singers” in that work, only about “musicians”. Moreover, she talks about the “chef de musique” for the *nargallu(m)* when, according to her statement, we should have “chef du chant”⁸⁷. In addition, she had previously defined the *nārum* as an instrumentalist⁸⁸, so we would expect a wider definition of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. On the other hand, according to her, music as sound phenomenon was expressed by the Sumerian **mu7-mu7**⁸⁹ (from which would come

⁸⁴ The sound of musical instruments could be very annoying at times. For instance, in *The Cursing of Agade*, 260 (ETCSL 2.1.5), the city sleeps while the **tige**₂ drums were still playing. In the same way, the sound production of the **a2-la2** drum is usually defined in Old Babylonian times (that is, the period of specialization of Nele Ziegler) with the expression **gu3 nun dug4** (“to produce a powerful sound”) (*Uruk Lament*, H 16, ETCSL 2.2.5; *Iddin-Dagān A*, 79, Attinger, 2014a: 20). In our opinion, that is far from an image of music in Mesopotamia as something “sweet” or “relaxing”. 1st-millennium texts also suggest that instruments could sometimes be noisy. See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 27, 84, 97, 295, 300 for evidence. For music as part of the “urban noises” of Mesopotamian cities, see also Grandpierre, 1997: 62–64.

⁸⁵ See Ziegler, 2005, 2006, FM 9 and Ziegler, 2011 for reference. We do not understand why Ziegler, 2013: 48–50 is entitled “La musique: un art savant et respecté”.

⁸⁶ This type of translation has been popular, but always in translations of concrete texts. Therefore, we shall not repeat them here. They will be commented on in depth later. The sole generic translation we know beyond this one is Shehata, 2009: 1, already commented on in this introduction.

⁸⁷ See Ziegler, 2012: 30–42 for reference.

⁸⁸ FM 9, p. 17–18.

⁸⁹ She transliterates this term as “MU₇-MU₇”. We might agree *a priori* with this type of transliteration for **mu7-mu7**, which is commonly used by the Akkadologists for Sumerograms and Sumerian terms in general (even in monolingual Sumerian texts). However, **nam-nar** is written there as “nam.nar”, an old transliteration system still used, for instance, by Theo J. H. Krispijn (see Krispijn, 1990: 2 for an example). In this sense, we would understand “MU₇-MU₇” as a repeated sign. However, the sign name for **mu7** is KA×LI. See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 350–363 for comments about **mu7-mu7**. Anne-Caroline Rendu Loisel cites in pages 360–361 of that study Nele Ziegler’s reflections on the *bīt mummi* or *mummum*, the conservatory of music of Mari. In this sense, we do not understand why Ziegler did not avail herself of Rendu Loisel’s work (where, for instance, *hubūru(m)* is well-explained).

*mummu(m)*⁹⁰) and the Akkadian *hubûru(m)*. However, *hubûru(m)* actually describes the continuous noise of an enormous group of people, sometimes as a complaint and without musical connotations⁹¹. That is quite different from Nele Ziegler’s definition of that term.

1.2.1.3. Conclusions

Previous research has mostly agreed that there is no word for “Music” in Sumerian or Akkadian. Nevertheless, none of the said studies has taken into consideration the analysis of all the texts known at their respective publication times with **nam-nar** or *nārûtu(m)*, the single Sumero-Akkadian terms referenced in all these previous reflections.

1.2.2. Comprehensive Definitions of **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)*

1.2.2.1. Presentations and Specific Remarks

1.2.2.1.1. AHw II, p. 789 and CAD 1, p. 382

We have said that none of the previous reflections about the existence (or not) of a word in Sumerian or Akkadian for “Music” had used all the evidence existing at their time of writing to prove their arguments. Those texts and references are usually contained in comprehensive definitions, but, what are those definitions in this case?

The earliest of these definitions (appeared in 1972) is the entry for *nārûtu(m)* in the *Akkadisches Handwörterbuch* (AHw)⁹². The Akkadian term was defined there as “Musiker(innen)beruf”⁹³. The texts used in that definition were 1) the letters from Mari ARM 1 64 and 78 (both from the Šamšī-Addu’s reign without precise date)⁹⁴, 2) the teaching contract Szlechter TJA, p. 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna, 23-10-02 (?))⁹⁵, 3)

⁹⁰ See Heidel, 1948 for an overview about this word.

⁹¹ See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 166–168 for comments.

⁹² AHw II, p. 749.

⁹³ We find a similar definition for **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)* in MEA, p. 330 (“office de chanteur”); Rašīd, 1984: 19 (“Kunst der Sänger und Musiker”); CDA, p. 242 (“profession of musician”); Sallaberger, 2006: 474 (“Amt/Kunst des Sängers”) and DCCLT Glossary (“profession of musician”).

⁹⁴ See our Texts 42 and 44 for editions and comments.

⁹⁵ See our Text 28 for edition and comments.

the 1st -millennium lexical excerpt **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu*, B, II [= **Ur₅-ra** = *hubullu(m)* VII B]⁹⁶, and 4) the Achaemenid contracts BE 8/1 98 [CBS 3579] (Cambyses 14+-01-00) (about musical teaching) and *Dar.* 463 [BM 77393] (Darius (x)+3-1-18) (about the sale of a temple prebend)⁹⁷. However, we miss from that definition the texts VS 6 169 [VAT 1180] (Darius I 00-00-00)⁹⁸ (first translated in 1937⁹⁹) and ARM 5 73 (Šamši-Addu 00-00-00)¹⁰⁰, already edited by 1952.

AHw’s definition of *nārūtu(m)* was followed some years later (in 1980) by the entry for that same term in the *Chicago Assyrian Dictionary* (CAD)¹⁰¹. In that other main dictionary for the Akkadian language, *nārūtu(m)* is defined as “musician’s craft”¹⁰², a more definition than the one of AHw. However, CAD used the same number of texts than AHw. In any case, the *corpus* of texts with *nārūtu(m)* has been augmented in the recent years with the publication of new texts from Old Babylonian Mari¹⁰³ and some Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid texts¹⁰⁴. Moreover, we have texts from other periods. This is the case of the tablets IM 85455 and 85456 (Ur III Period)¹⁰⁵, or the Late Seleucid text BM 28825 published in 2005¹⁰⁶. In this way, both definitions are already outdated.

1.2.2.1.2. Theo J. H. Krispijn’s Definition of **nam-nar**

The two definitions considered above concern just *nārūtu(m)* without any reference to the Sumerian **nam-nar**. For a definition of this term, we need to wait until 1990. At that time, Theo J. H. Krispijn, as a part of his study of the musical terms in *Šulgi B*, 154–

⁹⁶ See our Text 58 for edition and comments.

⁹⁷ See our Texts 60 and 65 for edition and comments.

⁹⁸ See our Text 61 for edition and comments.

⁹⁹ NRV, p. 520.

¹⁰⁰ See our Text 44 for edition and comments.

¹⁰¹ CAD N1, p. 382.

¹⁰² We find a similar definition in Huehnergard, 2011: 552 (“musician’s craft”). This definition has been more common for **nam-nar**. See ETCSL Glossary; Tanos, 2007: 257 and Foxvog, 2016: 45 for reference. In addition, keep in mind Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 340 (“activity of the musician”).

¹⁰³ See our Chapter 5 for editions and comments.

¹⁰⁴ See our section 6.3 for editions and comments.

¹⁰⁵ Both published in al-Rawi, 1992: 185. See our Texts 7 and 8 for edition and comments.

¹⁰⁶ Frame and George, 2005: 270-277. See our Text 70 for edition and comments.

174¹⁰⁷, prepared the most complete definition of this term to date. In that contribution, he defined **nam-nar** in two different ways. The first definition was “hymnische Musik”, that is, a concrete type of music, a definition only shared by him until today. The second one was “Tätigkeit als Musiker”, which is closer to the “Musiker(innen)beruf” of AHW. Those definitions try to confront **nam-gala**, defined there as “elegische Musik, Tätigkeit als Klagesänger”. That procedure is apparently logical but not without mistakes¹⁰⁸.

In any case, following with his definition, Krispijn said that **nam-nar** belonged to the list of divine powers called “**me**”¹⁰⁹. Furthermore, he highlighted the connections of **nam-nar** with ceremonies (in contrast to lamentations). That would come from the participation of the **nar** in such events as singer and instrumentalist. In this sense, Krispijn cited excerpts about instruments with allusions to **nam-nar**¹¹⁰ and the **nar**¹¹¹ and excerpts about the **s/šer3-nam-nar** (literally “**nam-nar s/šer3** song¹¹²) besides other songs¹¹³.

This description of **nam-nar** is quite good. However, among the many texts omitted in that description and known at that time¹¹⁴, we miss some texts as *Enki and Ninmah* b

¹⁰⁷ Krispijn, 1990.

¹⁰⁸ Certainly, as Shehata, 2013: 69 states, the **gala/kalû(m)** is a priest who, on some occasions, could perform lamentations with music. That fact is especially clear when we see people accessing to the profession as **gala** priest (**nam-gala**) in the Ur III administrative texts. See our section 2.4 for comments.

¹⁰⁹ Citing *Inanna and Enki*, I v 33 and II v 51. See our section 4.5.3 for edition and comments.

¹¹⁰ With reference to *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20, *Šulgi B*, 162, *Šulgi E*, 155, 162–163 and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 367. See our Texts 4, 26, 32, 35 and 39 for our editions of those excerpts.

¹¹¹ With reference to *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.14 (Römer, 2010: 34); *Šulgi A*, 78 (Delnero, 2006: 1900–1901). In Krispijn, 1990: 2 is the line 81 since he used another (unknown) edition. Other excerpts referred in Krispijn, 1990: 2 are *Šulgi B*, 167 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02) and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 375 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

¹¹² For the Old Babylonian Period, *Proto-aa*, 757:1 (DCCLT Q000056) and *Proto-Ea*, 757 (DCCLT Q000055) write out the Sumerian reading of the sign EZEN meaning *zamārum* (“song”) with the signs SI (= **si** or **se**; not the sign IGI = **ši** or ŠE = **še**) and IR (= **ir** or **er**). Therefore, we should read **ser3** (**sir3** means “to bind”). However, by the Middle Babylonian Period, *Syllabary B*, II 348 (DCCLT Q0001455) has already **še-er** = EZEN = ‘*za*’-[*ma*]-‘*ru*’¹. That fact is confirmed in Neo-Assyrian times in CT 11, pl. 20 [K. 7671], r. ii’ 2 (DCCLT). Keep in mind that the Neo-Babylonian MSL 17, p. 6 [OIM A1595], o. i 2 EZEN^{si-ir-da} (DCCLT) seems to be actually referred to **šir3-da** (“to bind”), and not to our term for song.

¹¹³ With references to *Proto-Lu2*, 590–591; *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373–374 and *Examination Text A*, 24. See our Texts 9, 40 and 59 for edition and comments.

¹¹⁴ Other Old Babylonian texts omitted are *Death of Nannā*, 19 (edited by the first time in Kramer, 1960: 52–63; it is relevant for **ser3 nam-nar**) and several legal texts published in the 50s: ARN 4 [Ist. Ni 9201] (Būr-Sîn 00-12-10), ARN 35 [Ist. Ni 1922] (Rīm-Sîn I 37-10-00), ARN 58 [Ist. Ni 2182] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00) and Kraus, 1951: 200-201 [Ist. Ni 2181] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00). See our Texts 15–18 for editions

26–29¹¹⁵, *The Father and his rude Son*, 107–112¹¹⁶, or *Enkihegal and Enkitalu*, 94–99, 110–114¹¹⁷. Certainly, **nam-nar** is mentioned in those texts in more abstract contexts. In any case, Krispijn’s definition is now outdated due to the publication of new texts like the hymns *Ur-Namma A*¹¹⁸ and *Šulgi CC*¹¹⁹. We can refer also some Neo-Sumerian texts¹²⁰ and Old Babylonian model contracts¹²¹ and real¹²² administrative texts.

1.2.2.1.3. Review of Some Recent Contributions

Already in the 21st century, there is still no project gathering all the references to **nam-nar** and/or *nārūtu(m)*. Concerning **nam-nar**, ePSD gathered some lexical excerpts and the references originally contained in ETCSL, a *corpus* lacking of some literary texts like *The Father and his rude Son* and *Enkihegal and Enkitalu*.

The new version of this dictionary, ePSD2, has incorporated the text Nisaba 11 33 [BM 104768] (Šulgi 36-11-00) and some¹²³ texts recently edited by Jeremiah L. Peterson as a part of his edition of the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts from Ur¹²⁴. However,

and comments. These texts would justify his definition as “Tätigkeit als Musiker”. It also would have been interesting a comment on Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534], since that text had already been noted at that time by Wilcke, 1987: 104 and Waetzoldt, 1989: 33. Moreover, we would have expected a comment on the Seleucid text CT 17, pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 18–19 (already edited by Hunger, 1968: 123) due to the allusion, in Krispijn’s definition, to the *Gudea Cylinders* (from the 3rd Millennium BCE), and *Examination Text A* (whose manuscripts are from the 1st millennium; Sjöberg, 1974: 137).

¹¹⁵ This text was previously known (see Ceccarelli, 2016: 8–16 for historiography), but our reference to **nam-nar** comes with the Benito’s edition (Benito, 1969: 27). See our Text 27 for edition and comments.

¹¹⁶ Edited by the first time in Sjöberg, 1973. See our section 4.2.2 for editions and comments.

¹¹⁷ A transliteration of the text N_{I-A1} = TMH NF 3 42 [HS 1606] + TMH NF 4 86 [HS 1606a], o. ii 10-15 and 26–29 was already available on Sjöberg, 1976: 169.

¹¹⁸ This text had already been edited in Kramer, 1967b: 116. However, it was necessary to wait for Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133 to have a full transliteration with **nam-nar**. For the reading Ur-Namma instead of Ur-Nammû, see Sallaberger, 2014–2015: 423 (thanks to Theo J. H. Krispijn for this remark).

¹¹⁹ Our text 37. *Šulgi CC*, UET 6/3 522 [U. 7774], edited by Peterson, 2019c: 698.

¹²⁰ Mainly our Text 5 (= Nisaba 11 33 [BM 104768] (Šulgi 36-11-00)). However, thanks to Sallaberger, 1993: 68, the **nar-ta** of TRU 41 [ICP 41] (Šulgi 41-00-00), r. 5 (our Text 6) as <**nam**>-**nar-ta** made sense.

¹²¹ Our Text 12. Geller, 2003: 109–111 [MS 2951].

¹²² Our Texts 19a, 19b, 20a, 20b and 21, published by Anne Goddeeris in 2016.

¹²³ Especially the reference to **ser₃ nam-nar** in *Šulgi CC* edited in Peterson, 2019c: 698–700.

¹²⁴ Peterson, 2019a, 2019b and 2019c.

some Old Babylonian (*The Father and his rude Son*) or Seleucid texts (our Text 67 = CT 17, pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 18’–19’) are still missing. We shall probably see those texts in later updates of this Sumerological project.

Concerning *nārūtu(m)*, the French project *Archibab* has gathered all those texts from Mari in addition to practically all the Sumerian model contracts with **nam-nar**¹²⁵. The German project eSAD is the single current attempt of an actual update of our Akkadian comprehensive dictionaries. However, as far as we know, there is nothing in its database about *nārūtu(m)* by the moment.

1.2.2.2. General Remarks

1.2.2.2.1. Short Introduction

We appreciate the previous contributions concerning comprehensive dictionaries. However, in our opinion, any attempt in the creation of a new comprehensive definition for **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* will be condemned to failure if, like in the past, we do not pay attention to some basic aspects of our texts.

Certainly, Theo J. H. Krispijn seemed not to have had problems in using the *Gudea Cylinders* and *Examination Text A* for explaining the term **nam-nar** of *Šulgi B*. That is, he considers correct to mix a 3rd- and 1st-millennium text for commenting on an Old Babylonian text without, at least, a reflection on this matter. Moreover, the definitions of *nārūtu(m)* in AHW and CAD mix sources from different periods (Old Babylonian and Neo-Babylonian), regions (Mari and southern Mesopotamia) and typologies (letters and administrative texts). The reason is that they are focusing just on apparent parallels.

This practice might be justified by a supposed lack of texts. However, we have already seen how many texts have been forgotten in those studies. We could also understand that procedure due to the mainly philological orientation of those works and the background of their authors. However, from our perspective, chronological and geographical aspects are perfectly complementary to the linguistic ones in a good and complete philological

¹²⁵ Except Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534].

exercise¹²⁶. Finally, this practice is scientifically problematic in several aspects as we are going to explain right now.

1.2.2.2.2. About Chronological Variations in the Musical Lexicon

Despite the constant reference to tradition for any innovation in Mesopotamian culture¹²⁷, it is obvious that musical terms in Sumerian and Akkadian had to change their meaning or connotations in part or *in toto* at some point in the long history of Mesopotamia. That has happened in other cultures of the world. We might refer the case of the well-known Chinese *èrhú* (二胡) fiddle. Certainly, *èrhú* is a derivation of *húqin* (胡琴 literally “barbaric *qin*”). By the Tang Dynasty (618–907 CE), *húqin* designated a musical instrument to be plucked or strummed as a lute or zither. However, by the 11th century CE, *húqin* already designates a type of fiddle. The *èrhú* would be one of those fiddles and it would have two strings as it is indicated by the Chinese *èr*, (二) “two”¹²⁸.

Chronological considerations about the Mesopotamian musical lexicon are still not too common¹²⁹. However, they have already offered some good ideas for understanding some musical terms. This is the case of **balan**/*balaggu(m)*, a term whose identification has always been quite controversial¹³⁰. Certainly, according to Uri Gabbay¹³¹, this term seems to refer to a stringed instrument in the 3rd millennium BCE, but to a type of drum by the 2nd millennium BCE onward, something which makes sense as we shall see later¹³².

1.2.2.2.3. Geographical Changes in Sumero-Akkadian Music terms?

We do not know of any publication reflecting in depth on this aspect¹³³. However, we cannot dismiss the role of geography in the configuration of the meaning of a concrete

¹²⁶ See Delnero, 2006: 35–63; DGS, p. 7 and Borkowski, 2018 for several examples of the importance of geography (with some references to archaeology) for Sumerian literature and grammar.

¹²⁷ The different contributions edited in Archi, 2011 are an example of this idea.

¹²⁸ Stock, 1993: 90 and 97. Thanks to Rubén García Benito for his help with the Chinese terms.

¹²⁹ Kilmer, 2000 seems to deal with this topic, but there is actually no reflection about that.

¹³⁰ See Gabbay, 2014a: 93–94 for a summary of these disputations.

¹³¹ Gabbay, 2007: 57–65; Gabbay, 2014a: 93–102; Gabbay, 2014b; Gabbay, 2017: 46.

¹³² See our sections 2.2.2.3 and 4.4.2.3.3 for reference.

¹³³ The unique consideration of this type is, perhaps, Michalowski, 2010a: 229 n. 67.

musical term. Certainly, lexical lists mention instruments coming originally from regions like Mari, Dilmun¹³⁴ or Elam¹³⁵. In addition, we cannot forget those instruments whose name is derived from the name of a foreign region (being used, perhaps, by traveling musicians¹³⁶). This is the case of the **mi-ri2-tum**/*marītu(m)* (from Mari), the **sa₃-bi2-tum**/*sabītu(m)* or *šebītu(m)* (from the land of Sabum), the **ur-za-ba-bi2-tum**/*urzababītum* (from the city of Ur-Zababa)¹³⁷ or the *para(h)šītu(m)* (from Marḥaši, near to Elam)¹³⁸. There are other examples, such as the **ur-gu-la** instrument (also “lion”)¹³⁹.

¹³⁴ *ED Practical Vocabulary A*, 207–208 (DCCLT Q000293) mentions a **balaj** from Dilmun (**balaj dilmun**) and another one from Mari (**balaj ma-ri2^{ki}**).

¹³⁵ There is a ^{neš}**tigidla elam-ma** (“^{neš}**tigidla** of Elam”) according to the Old Babylonian text **Urs-ra**, I 616 (DCCLT Q000039) and the Neo-Assyrian text MSL 6, p. 81 [K. 2028], r. i’ 2’ (DCCLT; collated the 01/08/2019). However, we have more allusions to the ^{neš}**tigidla kaskal-la** (“^{neš}**tigidla** instrument of the way”, perhaps an instrument used by itinerant musicians from different regions). For reference, see **Urs-ra**, I 614 (DCCLT Q000039), CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214], b iv 11 (DCCLT) for the Old Babylonian Period, and Emar 6/1, p. 285 [Msk 74114d], r. 7 (DCCLT) and Emar 6/2, p. 508–515 + 730 [Msk 74209a + 7526], r. ii 24 (DCCLT) for the Middle Babylonian Period.

¹³⁶ For this topic, see FM 9, p. 27–31; Michalowski, 2010b, and Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 105–107.

¹³⁷ See respectively our Sections 2.2.2.3, 5.2.2.1 and 6.2.1 for their texts and identification.

¹³⁸ For the identification of Marḥaši, see Steinkeller, 1982: 246–255 and Steinkeller, 2006: 261–266. For the instrument, see Steinkeller, 2006: 266–271; FM 9, p. 49 and Michalowski, 2010a: 229 n. 67.

¹³⁹ This instrument is accompanied by the determinative for wooden objects ^{neš} in our Old Babylonian sources (*Šulgi B*, 166 = ETCSL 2.4.2.02, and **Urs-ra**, I 606 = DCCLT Q000039). The same happens in the Neo-Assyrian (MSL 6, p. 81 [K. 2028], r. i’ 27’ = DCCLT; collated the 01/08/2019) and Neo-Babylonian texts (MSL SS 1, p. 24 [Ashm. 1924-1883], o. 6’–7’ = DCCLT). That suggests its identity as a stringed instrument. In any case, we should keep in mind that a lion is playing a drum in an 8th–7th-century Neo-Elamite cylinder-seal (Lawergren, 2018: fig. 3.8.5[a]), and a female drummer together with a lion on *kudurru* Sb 25 (see Collon, 2013: 27 for comments). The Middle Babylonian lexical texts Emar 6/1, p. 240 [Msk 7498f], r. ii 18; Emar 6/1, p. 285 [Msk 74114d], r. 3 and Emar 6/2, p. 508–515 + 730 [Msk 74209a + 7526], r. ii 20 suggest, in addition, its foreign origin concerning southern Mesopotamia. The reason is that it is mentioned together with a [’]**dim3-ma’ mar-ḥa-a-ši/para(h)šu**, that is, an instrument from Marḥaši, perhaps the previously noted *para(h)šītu(m)* (Steinkeller, 2006: 266–267). We would identify **ur-gu-la**, therefore, with a northern Syrian lyre. Certainly, we have a lion playing a lyre in a 9th–8th-century relief from Tell Halaf (North-East Syria) (see Lawergren, 2018: fig. 3.8.5[b] for reference). Furthermore, a lyre player is next to a lion in the Neo-Assyrian relief BM 118916 (see Collon, 2010: 59 for comments). The origin of that connection would be much older, since we have another lion with a lyre in the *Turin Papyrus* (Egyptian 19th Dynasty, 1295–1186 BCE; see Hickman, 1961: 32–33 for reference). That scene might have a foreign origin. In fact, that lion is playing with other animal musicians with foreign instruments in Egypt, like the lute or the double pipes (see Manniche, 1988: 194–195 for comments). Egyptian language is also

Certainly, geographic distance can perform changes in the meaning of some musical terms. This is the case of the Arabic *al-būq*, which designates a horn (therefore, a brass instrument) while the Spanish *alboka* (originated from the previous term by the time of al-Andalus) designates a double clarinet (therefore, a single-reed instrument) using two hollowed horns, one covering the space for the reeds and another one acting as the bell of the instrument¹⁴⁰. Thus, a common musical term changes its meaning in two separated points of the same region. In our opinion, a similar phenomenon might be detected in the case of the term **za3-mi2/sammû(m)**. Certainly, while in southern Mesopotamia this seems to designate an angular harp¹⁴¹, we cannot avoid identifying this term with the horizontal harp¹⁴² in (Neo-)Assyrian¹⁴³ texts due to the similarities between the iconography and our lexical texts¹⁴⁴, royal inscriptions¹⁴⁵ and other texts¹⁴⁶.

interesting for this connection. Certainly, the sign E23 depicting a lion is used in some spellings of the Egyptian term *knr* (“lyre”, a Semitic loanword, Meeks, 1997: 53). This sign might act as determinative, since E23 is used for the letter “l” in Egyptian, a letter which does not fit in that transliteration *knr*.

¹⁴⁰ Fagoaga, 1975: 45–47.

¹⁴¹ See our Section 4.2.1.1 for argumentation.

¹⁴² We are, in this sense, against Cheng, 2012: 75.

¹⁴³ As far as we know, there is no Old Assyrian sources for this term, and our Middle Assyrian sources are quite fragmentary. See the Middle Assyrian Coronation Ritual text KAR 135 + 137 + 216 + 217 [VAT 9583 + 9936 +? 10113 (+) 9978], r. iii 10–11 (Müller, 1937: 14), and the text of *Tukultī-Ninurta’s epic* Lambert, 1957–1958: 44–47 [BM 98730], r. 32 (original publication) for reference.

¹⁴⁴ In the Neo-Assyrian text **Mur-gu4** = *imrû* = *ballu*, B, I 47 (DCCLT), a **za3-mi2** instrument correctly tuned (**si sa2**) is equated with *išartu(m)*. This term designates one of the Mesopotamian scales, which had 9 strings/notes (Krispijn, 2017: 226). Compare that with iconographical examples like the Neo-Assyrian relief BM 124533, where we find two horizontal harps with 9 strings (Lawergren and Gurney, 1987: 51).

¹⁴⁵ Compare *Aššarḥaddon 1*, iii 36–38 (RINAP 4 Q003230), *Aššarḥaddon 2*, i 50–56 (RINAP 4 Q003231) and *Aššarḥaddon 3* [BM 91029], ii 7’–10’ (RINAP 4 Q003232) with the relief BM 124920. In that relief, as in the cited excerpts, we have two musicians with horizontal harps in front of soldiers holding the heads of some enemies. The *nāru* musicians of these inscriptions are certainly playing that instrument, as we can infer from the expression *nārū ina sammê* of *Aššurbānīpal Assyrian Tablet 2* [K. 2694 + 3050], o. iii 3’–4’ (RINAP 5 Q003772) and Ebeling, 1948: 416–422 [VAT 13832], 19–22 (Ebeling, 1948: 417).

¹⁴⁶ In SAA 3 39 = KAR 307 [VAT 8917], o. 3 (SAAo) and *Aladimmû G*, CT 28, pl. 37 [K. 2166 + Rm 935 + 1879-7-8,89], o. 19 (Böck, 2000: 284), the shape of the **za3-mi2/sammû** is compared to human hands. Compare that with the depictions of Neo-Assyrian horizontal harps, which have a hand at the top of their sound-boxes. Especially interesting is the relief BM 124948 + BM ANE Or. Dr. VI 45 (now lost). We might identify the bracelet of the hands of the harps of said relief with the expression **SUḪUŠ kappišu** (“the foundation of his hands”) of *Aladimmû G*. For the hands of the horizontal harps, Cheng, 2012: 78–80.

1.2.2.2.4. Musical Terms vs. Textual Typologies

Finally, it is important to pay attention to the different textual typologies of our texts containing **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*. Certainly, the scribal training required for writing them could differ, especially when we compare administrative and literary texts (which required a longer training). In any case, we already have some contributions about musicians and songs in different types of texts¹⁴⁷.

1.2.3. General Conclusions

We definitely need to keep in mind all our references to **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* in order to talk about the existence (or not) of a word for “Music” in Sumerian or Akkadian. Nevertheless, those references cannot be studied without paying attention to some basic aspects of their texts, like their chronology, geography, and textual typology.

1.3. Hypothesis to be proved

1.3.1. Exposition of the hypothesis

Only a little evidence for **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* has been used in the past for answering to the question of the existence (or not) of a word in Sumerian and Akkadian for “Music”. Therefore, we believe that a study of all our texts containing these two terms might reveal that “Music” was actually their (main) meaning. In this sense, there would actually be a word for “Music” in Mesopotamia. We do not rule out other meanings for them, like office or text *corpus* of the **nar/nāru(m)**. However, they are secondary and, above all, they can be explained according to the chronology/typology of their texts.

¹⁴⁷ See Shehata, 2009, *passim* (texts about each type of musician or composition are usually gathered according to their typology) and Gadotti, 2010.

1.3.2. About the definition of “Music” used in this study

We are going to defend the actual existence of a word for “music” in Sumerian and Akkadian. However, what are we going to understand as “music” in this study? The necessity of having a clear idea about “music” and making it explicit in a scientific contribution has already been expressed for ancient Near Eastern Studies¹⁴⁸. The idea itself of “music” has been much debated around the world, and, in fact, not too many people (if anyone) are confident about its definition despite dealing with music every day. Perhaps it comes from the difficulty of disconnecting the “object” (music) from the “subject” (the individual) and its context (emotions)¹⁴⁹. In our opinion¹⁵⁰, we cannot define “music” just as the combination of sounds with a certain purpose (we shall reflect shortly about this matter later)¹⁵¹. Far from that, as Jean Molino suggested¹⁵², we need to include in our definition the social and personal circumstances around that sound combination and its production. We can neither forget its agents and instruments.

That idea is in the basis of the word from which the term “Music” comes: the Greek term μουσική. Certainly, that word simply referred to something “of the Muses”. That could be the use of a musical instrument. In fact, the Muse Euterpe is associated with the αὐλός. However, μουσική could also designate something along the lines of History, domain of Klio¹⁵³. The same happens with the Latin *musica*. Its definition by Augustine of Hippo (*musica est scientia bene modulandi*)¹⁵⁴ implies the measure of musical sounds, but also their movement and use in singing and dance¹⁵⁵. Maybe that movement of the sounds is not related at all to society. In any case, we cannot forget that music is the oldest form of social communication for humans, even earlier than spoken language¹⁵⁶.

¹⁴⁸ Certainly, Mirelman, 2011: 300 already requires that definition concerning Schulz, 2004, where the Hittite *zinar* was understood (as we shall comment on later) as an interjection for “Music!”

¹⁴⁹ See Nettle, 1983: 26–35 for some reflections.

¹⁵⁰ What follows is mainly a personal reflection. In any case, of course, we refer to some studies.

¹⁵¹ For instance, Clifton, 1983: 10.

¹⁵² Molino, 1975: 37 said that music should be perceived as a total social fact.

¹⁵³ Grimal, 2008: 367–368.

¹⁵⁴ Augustine of Hippo, *De Musica* I, 1, 2 (Sant’Agostino).

¹⁵⁵ See Correa Pabón, 2009: 30–49 for an analysis of this expression.

¹⁵⁶ See Altenmüller, 2004, Levitin, 2006: 242–261; Sacks, 2007: xi–xii for comments.

In fact, we tend to think that nobody is thinking (just) in sounds combinations when (s)he says “I like music!”¹⁵⁷. Certainly, many people become interested in music by playing an instrument or singing. That is not so common with the elaboration of random sound calculations without contact with any “material” reality. After all, if music were a numerical science like in the *Quadrivium*¹⁵⁸, why not just talk about “Soundology”? In this sense, for “Music” we understand here something as the combination of sounds with a communicative purpose. However, we include also in that definition the required instruments, agents, and personal and social circumstances of that sound combination.

1.3.3. Justification *A Priori* of our hypothesis

1.3.3.1. About terms for “Music” in Ancient Cultures

Our hypothesis might be doomed to failure if we do not keep in mind that there is no word for “Music” in some languages contemporary with Sumerian and Akkadian. Among them, Hurrian¹⁵⁹, Hittite¹⁶⁰, Eblaite¹⁶¹, Ugaritic¹⁶² and other Semitic languages¹⁶³.

¹⁵⁷ Compare this statement with our Texts 33 and 39.

¹⁵⁸ About the role of music in the *Quadrivium* in Late Antiquity, see Heilmann, 2007.

¹⁵⁹ See Richter, 2012, *passim* for different Hurrian musical terms.

¹⁶⁰ The Hittite *zinar* seems to be an interjection meaning “Music!”, but it might just refer to the music of the *zinar* lyre (see Schuol, 2004, *passim*). In our opinion, *zinar* is not a (Proto-)Hattic term as is usually said (Krispijn, 1990: 12; Schuol, 2004: 97; Krispijn, 2010b: 148; Tischler, 2016a: IV, 741). However, it might come from the Semitic $\sqrt{\text{KNR}}$. Certainly, in MEE 4 2 + 3 + 61 [TM.75.G.15301], r. ii 4’ (DCCLT), we have *gi-na-ru₁₂-um*. The sign GI might have been confused with ZI in very early times for rendering **zinarum* > *zinar*. This also happens in southern Mesopotamia, another “peripheral zone,” concerning Ebla. There, two Old Akkadian texts (both collated 22/08/2019; see Bauer, 1992: notice 51 for comments) have **lu₂ ʾza-ʾra-lu₂** (OSP 2 136 [N 278] (00-00-00), r. 5, CDLI P216290) and **lu₂ za-na-ʾru₁₂(EN)ʾ** (OSP 2 133 [N 433 + 581] (00-00-00), r. 12, CDLI P216287). That is, they have two early spellings of **za-na-ru**. The spelling **za-na-ru₁₂** recalls the Eblaite *gi-na-ru₁₂-um*: *gi-na-ru₁₂-um* > ***zi-na-ru₁₂** > **za-na-ru₁₂** > **za-na-ru-um** > **za-na-ru**. That is confirmed by the Old Babylonian lexical text CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214], b vi 21 (DCCLT). In that text we find ^{ne^s}**za-na-ru-um** with a classical *-um* Akkadian ending.

¹⁶¹ We have only Eblaite texts about the **NAR** (see Tonietti, 2018: 14-22 for a recent overview) like Mesopotamia at that time (see section 2.1 for comments).

¹⁶² Here we have the verbal stem *dmr* meaning “to sing” (Olmo de Lete and Sanmartín, 2003: 287).

¹⁶³ The Hebrew *zimrah* means “music”, but also “singing” (Klein, 1987: 200). The same happens with other words from the same root (Holladay, 1988: 404; Clines, 2009: 201) and the Aramaic *zmār(ā)* (CAL).

However, any statement on this matter is provisional since musical terminology in some of these languages is still unknown or uncertain because of our knowledge of said languages. This is the case of Urartian¹⁶⁴ or Elamite¹⁶⁵. Moreover, for us, ancient Egypt represents a contradiction. Certainly, Egyptian terms usually translated as “Music” never have the determinative Y1V for abstract nouns¹⁶⁶. In addition, they seem to concern just the “music” of some instrument (like *ihy*)¹⁶⁷ or a musical action (like *hst*¹⁶⁸ or *hn*¹⁶⁹). However, some Greek sources use the word μουσική for Egypt and its music¹⁷⁰.

Additionally, Greece (and, by extension, Rome) was not the unique ancient culture having a word for “Music”. Certainly, the Ancient Chinese *yuè* (樂) “Music” is already mentioned in the *Book of Odes* (*Shijing*, 詩經) compiling poems from the 11th to 7th centuries BCE¹⁷¹. For its part, the Sanskrit *saṅgīta* is mentioned for the first time in the *Saṅgīta ratnākara* (“Ocean of Music”) of Śārṅgadeva. That text is from the 13th century CE. However, some aspects of that book and the term *saṅgīta* make reference to the oldest texts of the Indian culture, as the *Ṛgveda* (composed in the 2nd millennium BCE)¹⁷².

¹⁶⁴ Previous musical research (Belli, 2007; Seidl, 2009) has been focused just on iconography and, according to Mirjo Salvini (personal communication), author of the main Urartian lexicon (Salvini, 2018), there is unfortunately no Urartian musical term (at the moment?)

¹⁶⁵ The *Elamisches Wörterbuch* (Hinz and Koch, 1987) contains several “musical terms”. Some of them have been already dismissed like ka₄-si-ik-ki ba-ak-ki-ra (“Posaunenbläser” on Hinz and Koch, 1987: 451, “lancer” in Henkelman, 2002 and Velázquez Muñoz, 2013: 19 n. 18). Other terms are contained in uncertain texts. This is the case of šu-ku-ri (“vielleicht Sänger(?)” in Hinz and Koch, 1987: 1995), term contained in Böhl, 1933: 30 [LB 1003], o. 5 and the unpublished LB 1004, lo. e. 1 (collated in November 2018).

¹⁶⁶ Gardiner, 1927: 533.

¹⁶⁷ It might refer only to sistrum music when it is used with the determinative A239 (a person playing a sistrum) (Wb I, p. 122). Only known in the Ptolemaic-Roman Period (see TLA for reference).

¹⁶⁸ Probably referred just to “singing” since it usually appears with the determinative D41 (Wb III, p. 165). The arm depicted in that determinative is a human arm in horizontal position like that of some ancient Egyptian singers (Manniche, 1991: 94). Known from the New Kingdom onward. See TLA for reference.

¹⁶⁹ Probably referred just to the dance (with musical accompaniment) due to the use of the determinative A32A (a dancing person) (Wb III, p. 286). Only known in the Ptolemaic Period (see TLA for reference).

¹⁷⁰ Plato, *Laws*, II, 656e; Diodorus Siculus, *Bibliotheca historica*, I 18, 4 and 81, 7 and Plutarch, *Isis and Osiris*, 13 A-B.

¹⁷¹ Journeau, 2008: 495. The poem with our allusion is the 141 in the order of Waley, 1960.

¹⁷² Rowell, 1992: 5–16 (overview); *Saṅgīta Ratnākara*, I, v, 21c–24b (Shringy, 1978: I, 10) (edition).

Finally, we should have a look for a second at the composition of the terms **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. On the one hand, they have a particle (a prefix, **nam-**, in Sumerian¹⁷³, a suffix, *-ūtu(m)* in Akkadian¹⁷⁴) which give these terms an abstract connotation. On the other hand, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* do not refer to a musical action like the Hebrew *zīmrah*, the Aramaic *zmār(ā)*, the Ugaritic *dmr*, or the Egyptian terms *ḥst* and *ḥn*. They neither refer to a musical instrument as the Hittite *zinar*¹⁷⁵ or the Egyptian *iḥy*. Far from that, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* are built from, **nar/nāru(m)**, a term which designated a musician. That is, they were referred to someone able to use his/her voice for making music as a singer, but also to use other instruments, what we call an instrumentalist.

None of these things is perceived in the other Hittite, Egyptian or Semitic terms which we have mentioned. In this sense, the scope of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* is much larger and, therefore, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* have more potential for being a term for “Music”.

1.3.3.2. About the condition of the **nar/nāru(m)**

A larger reflection on this topic as a consequence of an exhaustive study of the **nar/nāru(m)** in Mesopotamia is definitely out of the scope of this study for two reasons.

¹⁷³ Concerning the debate if this **nam-** is equal to the noun **nam** (“destiny”, “condition” or “state”), we are of the opinion of DGS, p. 118 that there is no reason for considering them two independent realities. At the most, following that contribution, **nam-** should be described as a lexical morpheme (Krecher, 1987: 71). Certainly, both **nam(-)** forms concern abstract entities (things which happen/are going to happen to someone/something). Furthermore, nouns with **nam-** can be translated as “condition of...” DGS, p. 118 does not cite Tanos, 2007, which defends the derivational condition of **nam-**. However, its example of **nam-a-ni** is not precise, and we have a **nam-bi** in *Enki and Ninmah*, b 28 (see our Text 27 for edition and comments). This is a more explicit comment against Tanos, 2007 than those of Attinger, 2009: 132 (we agree with them in any case). Tanos, 2007 should have also kept in consideration the existence of the expressions **nam-bi-še₃** (“because of that”) or the construction **nam** + Sentence + **a** [NMLZ] + **ak** [GEN] + **še** [TRM] (“at the occasion of...”) (Foxvog, 2016b: 22, 50, 101, 103). Thanks to Daniel Foxvog, Bram Jagersma and Pascal Attinger for their bibliographical and grammatical orientations.

¹⁷⁴ On the contrary to **nam-**, this suffix is just a noun formative without an independent meaning. It is also found in other Semitic languages like Mandaic, but also Egyptian, a Hamito-Semitic language. Abstract words can be constructed through nominal constructions (GAG, p. 70–73), which is not so common in Sumerian (DGS, p. 281). See Barth, 1894: 411–413; Steiner, 1972; Correll, 1990; Hecker, 1990: 301–309; Farber, 1991; GAG, p. 86–87 for reference. Thanks to Josué Justel, John Huehnergard, Manfred Krebernik and Holger Gzella for their bibliographical comments and remarks (or reminders!) on this topic.

¹⁷⁵ There is also another Hittite word, *išhamai-*, for “singing” (Tischler, 2001: 63; Tischler, 2016: 130).

On the one hand, we deal here mainly with the concept of “music” in Mesopotamia, not with musicians in that culture. This topic will be treated by Regine Pruzsinszky in depth a future study¹⁷⁶. On the other hand, the number of textual allusions to that **nar/nāru(m)** in some periods of Mesopotamian history is very high, and the study of said period(s) might occupy a large monograph by itself¹⁷⁷. In any case, here are some compulsory reflections on this topic. They will be also useful for justifying our hypothesis.

First, the **nar/nāru(m)** is a musician¹⁷⁸, and not an instrumentalist¹⁷⁹, a singer¹⁸⁰, or a “singer/musician”¹⁸¹ as in previous discussions¹⁸². We can infer that from an excerpt of the Old Babylonian lexical list *Proto-lu2* about the specializations of this figure¹⁸³. Certainly, there we find specializations where the **nar** acts mainly as a singer¹⁸⁴ or as an instrumentalist¹⁸⁵. However, the **nar/nāru(m)** is defined in other specialities just by the gender¹⁸⁶, age¹⁸⁷, position¹⁸⁸ or the context where (s)he used to perform music¹⁸⁹. In this sense, Mesopotamian people seem to have not put exclusive attention on the instruments

¹⁷⁶ See Pruzsinszky, *forthcoming* for reference.

¹⁷⁷ Certainly, only by the Ur III Period, BDTNS [Last search on 14/10/2019] has 823 mentions of **nar**. Only one of these allusions to the **nar** is a sure reference to **nam-nar** (= our Text 5).

¹⁷⁸ Among others, like AHW II, p. 748; CAD N1, p. 376; Collon and Kilmer, 1980–1983: 469; Charpin, 1986: 250; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 341; Archi, 2003–2005: 205; Kilmer, 2003–2005: 371; ETCSL Glossary; ePSD; Gadotti, 2010: 73 (neither this nor any of the following lists aims to be exhaustive).

¹⁷⁹ Like FM 9, p. 17–18.

¹⁸⁰ Sjöberg, 1976: 170 n. 39; Krispijn, 1990: 2; Sigrist, 1992: 216–217; Kienast, 1994: 170; Visicato, 1995: 108; Volk, 1995: 210; Zgoll, 1997: 441; Sallaberger, 2006: 481; D’Agostino, 2012: 92–94.

¹⁸¹ Gelb, 1976: 50; Pruzsinszky, 2010a: 96.

¹⁸² For a reflection about this debate including the iconography, Oberhuber, 1991.

¹⁸³ *Proto-lu2*, 641–650 (DCCLT Q000047). Following citations will refer to this text and edition. See Shehata, 2009: 16–17; Shehata, 2018b: 65 for previous comments on this text.

¹⁸⁴ **nar gu3 silim-ma** (“**nar** of the healthy voice”; line 648); **nar inim/gu3 bala-bala** (“**nar** of the responsorial chants”; line 648a); **nar gu3 dug3-ga** (“**nar** of the good voice”; line 648b); **nar gu3 nu-dug3-ga** (“**nar** of the unpleasant voice”; line 648c) and **nar ze2-za** (“croaking(?) **nar**”).

¹⁸⁵ **nar balaḡ** (“**nar** of the **balaḡ** instrument”; line 642), **nar sa** (“**nar** of the chordophones”; line 644).

¹⁸⁶ **munus-nar balaḡ** (“female **nar** of the **balaḡ** instrument”; 643b).

¹⁸⁷ **nar ḡal-la-tuš-a** (“apprentice **nar**”; line 649). Shehata, 2009: 16 adds **nar tur** (“young **nar**”).

¹⁸⁸ **nar gal** (“chief musician”; 642); **nar pad3-da** (“designated **nar**”, perhaps engaged for a sporadic performance; line 649b); **nar keše2-da** (“attached **nar**”, perhaps a **nar** with a permanent position; line 650).

¹⁸⁹ **nar igi suḡur-la2** (“**nar** before the **suḡur-la2**”; line 646); **nar igi lugal** (“**nar** before the king”; line 647); **nar eš3-a** (“**nar** of the shrine”; 649a). Through Shehata, 2009: 16 / Shehata, 2018b: 65, as a variant called 648e, **nar a2-na2** (“**nar** of the **a2-na2** bedroom”).

used by the **nar**, but also to other aspects. Therefore, a definition of that figure as “musician” fits better in this context without denying his/her vocal/instrumental abilities.

Some people¹⁹⁰ have defined the **nar/nāru(m)** as “singer” due to these specialities where **lu₂** (“person”) is accompanied by a musical instrument: **lu₂ a₂-la₂**¹⁹¹ (“player of the **a₂-la₂**”)¹⁹², **lu₂ bur₂-balaḡ** (“player of the **bur₂-balaḡ** instrument”)¹⁹³, **lu₂ balaḡ(-di)** (“player of the **balaḡ-di**” or “reciter of **balaḡ** laments”)¹⁹⁴, ***lu₂ za-na-ru**¹⁹⁵ (“player of the **za-na-ru** lyre/drum¹⁹⁶”), **lu₂ gi-di-da** (“player of the **gi-di** pipes”)¹⁹⁷, **lu₂ ḡṣtigidla**¹⁹⁸ (“player of the ḡṣtigidla”), **lu₂ gi-gid₂-da** (“player of the **gi-gid₂** pipes”)¹⁹⁹ and **lu₂ al-**

¹⁹⁰ Among others, Shehata, 2009: 261; Pruzsinszky, 2013: 31; Pruzsinszky, 2016: 27–28.

¹⁹¹ IAS 54 + 56 [IM 70293+], o. v 17 (DCCLT); *ED Lu₂ E*, 101 (DCCLT Q000006); ARET 9 107 [TM75.G.576], o. i 3 (CDLI P240694); UET 3 1265 [U. 4611] (00-00-00), o. i 4 (BDTNS 011570); UET 9 821 (Ibbī-Suen 06-05-00), o. 3 (BDTNS 019577); UET 9 830 (Ibbī-Suen 06-11-00), r. 4 (BDTNS 19586); MSL 12, 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 247 (DCCLT); MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830], r. i 32 (DCCLT).

¹⁹² See our sections 2.2.2.2 and 4.4.3.2.3.3 for identification.

¹⁹³ SF 47 [VAT 12619], 58_(23) (DCCLT); IAS 54 + 56 [IM 70293+], o. v 19 (DCCLT); *ED Lu₂ E*, 104 (DCCLT Q000006).

¹⁹⁴ MSL 12, 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 250-253 (DCCLT); MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830], r. i 31 and 35 (DCCLT); **An** = *Anum*, I 362 (DCCLT Q000264); CT 19, pl. 23 [Rm. 344], r. i 38’ (DCCLT).

¹⁹⁵ OSP 2 133 [N 433 + 581] (00-00-00), r. 12 (**lu₂ za-na-ru₁₂**) (CDLI P216287); OSP 2 136 [N 278] (00-00-00), r. 5 (**lu₂ za-ra-lu₂**) (CDLI P216290) (collated the 22/08/2019).

¹⁹⁶ For the identification as a lyre, see our previous considerations about *zinar* and **za-na-ru(-um)**. However, this identification does not fit with our Old Babylonian references to **za-na-ru**. Certainly, that instrument is equated to the *mazzû(m)* (a sistrum, see Gabbay, 2010: 26) and *alû(m)* in CUSAS 12 7.1.A [MS 4135], o. i 6’–8’ (DCCLT). In addition, its sound is described as **gu₃ nun** (“powerful voice”) in *Temple Hymns*, 183 (ETCSL 4.80.1). This sound does not fit with a stringed instrument, but does with percussion.

¹⁹⁷ SF 47 [VAT 12619], 60_9 (DCCLT); IAS 54 + 56 [IM 70293+], o. v 18 (DCCLT); *ED Lu₂ E*, 102 (DCCLT Q000006); MVN 6 300 [Ist. L 7309] (xx-00-00), o. ii 16 (BDTNS 020465); SNAT 533 [BM 106111] (00-00-00), r. 4 (BDTNS 033997); MVN 10 96 [AO 10391] (Šulgi 42-11-00), o. ii 20 (BDTNS 23197); TCL 5 6038 [AO 6038] (Amar-Suena 07-00-00), r. iv 11 (BDTNS 006189); CDLI P235573 [USC 6763 = L.63] (Šu-Suen 03-00-00), r. 12 (CDLI P235573); UET 3 1070 [U. 4841] (Ibbī-Suen 08-09-00), o. 2 (BDTNS 11375); MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 242, 244 (DCCLT); MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830], r. i 27 (DCCLT); *Proverbs* 2.54 (ETCSL 6.1.02).

¹⁹⁸ (All Ur III) UET 3 15 [U. 4864 (Iraq Museum envelope) + U. 7002 (British Museum tablet)] (Šulgi 47-00-00), o. 8 (BDTNS 10320); PDT 2 1120 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 04-02-02), o. 7 (BDTNS 31251); UDT 97 [NBC 97] (Amar-Suena 04-09-19), r. 21 (BDTNS 005482).

¹⁹⁹ BPOA 6 1190 [NBC 618] (Šulgi 45-00-00), r. 1 (BDTNS 75208); MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 243 (DCCLT); MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830], r. i 28 (DCCLT); *Proverbs* 2.54 (ETCSL 6.1.02).

nar-su-ra²⁰⁰ (“player of the **al-nar-sur** friction drum”)²⁰¹. However, the **nar** sometimes played the **a₂-la₂**²⁰² and the **balaj**²⁰³. Furthermore, we have specialities of the type **lu₂** + a type of song for referring some types of singers: **lu₂ ser₃(-ra)** (literally, “person of the **ser₃** song”)²⁰⁴ and **lu₂ i-lu (di)** (“person of the **i-lu** song”)²⁰⁵.

The opposition **nar** vs. **lu₂ gi-di(-da)** was exposed in the Old Babylonian proverb 2.54. In proverbs like that, we find references to the **nar**’s throat (**meli₂**)²⁰⁶ or mastering of the **en₃-du** songs²⁰⁷. We might identify, therefore, the **nar** with a singer. Moreover, some of its sounds are suitable for a singer. This is the case of the sounds **u₈¹-u_x(PA)-a** and **a-la-la**)²⁰⁸. However, other sounds of the **nar** might also refer to instruments, like the sound **za-pa-aṅ₂**²⁰⁹. That term designated the cries of the people, but also the noise of some animals²¹⁰. In this sense, the **nar** need not always have been a singer in these texts.

Another proverb referred to the use of the **ad ša₄** technique by the **nar**²¹¹. This technique is also found with some terms identifiable as musical instruments²¹². Moreover, **ad ša₄** is defined in Old Babylonian times²¹³ onward²¹⁴ as a term related to lamentations

²⁰⁰ MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 248 (DCCLT).

²⁰¹ Veldhuis, 1997–1998: 119–120; Shehata, 2006; Michalowski, 2010a: 225–228 for identification.

²⁰² *Gudea Statue L* [E3/1.01.07], a 41’ (CDLI P431893).

²⁰³ TMH 10 25 [HS 2205] (Šamšu-ilūna 12-07-03), r. 4 (Archibab T23363). In addition, see Gelb, 1976: 57; Tonietti, 2010: 83 and Tonietti, 2018: 19 for reference.

²⁰⁴ SF 47 [VAT 12619], 57_(22) (DCCLT); IAS 60 [IM 70171], o. vi 2’ (DCCLT); *ED Lu₂ E*, 107 (DCCLT Q000006); MEE 3 8 + 9 + unpublished fragment [TM.75.G.11651+], o. vi 2 (DCCLT); *Nippur Lament*, 117 (ETCSL 2.2.4); **Im-ma-al gu₃-de₂-de₂**, c+201 (Bowen, 2017: 184 n. 341).

²⁰⁵ MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 245–246 (DCCLT) and MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830], r. i 33–34 (OB; DCCLT). Pay attention also to the **balaj di lu₂ i-lu ba-ab-be₂-a** (“The reciter of **balaj** lamentations who recites an **i-lu** song”) of *Nippur Lament*, 109 (ETCSL 2.2.4).

²⁰⁶ *Proverbs* 2.43 (ETCSL 6.1.02). For this reading instead of the traditional **ṅili₃**, Attinger, 2019d: 130 n. 173 (with bibliography). *Proto-Ea*, 327 has **mi-li** for KA×LI, which suggests **mili₂** or **meli₂**.

²⁰⁷ *Proverbs* 2.39; UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88], o. 3–4 (Peterson, 2019b: 573); UET 6/2 290 [U. 17207,55], o. 1 (Peterson, 2019b: 582).

²⁰⁸ *Proverbs* 3.87 (ETCSL 6.1.03).

²⁰⁹ *Proverbs* 2.41 and 2.57 (ETCSL 6.1.02).

²¹⁰ See our Section 4.2.1.1 for additional explanations.

²¹¹ *Proverbs* 2.39 (ETCSL 6.1.02); UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88], o. 3–4 (Peterson, 2019b: 573).

²¹² *Šulgi B*, 171 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02; **ṅeš-gu₃-di** lute) and perhaps *Temple Hymns*, 183 (ETCSL 4.80.1; **za-na-ru** instrument).

²¹³ *Inanna G*, 61 (ETCSL 4.07.7) and *Dumu_{zi} and Inanna H*, 17 (Attinger, 2019b: 2)

²¹⁴ See Cooper, 1987: 89, 96–97 and Rendu Loisel, 2011: 204–206 for comments.

to be equated with *nasāḥu(m)*. Therefore, unlike some authors²¹⁵, the **nar/nāru(m)** was not only a ceremonial musician, but (s)he could also perform music suitable for lamentations²¹⁶. Beyond other pieces of evidence²¹⁷, that fact fits with the specialization **nar balaj** (“**nar** of the **balaj** instrument”). As we shall comment on later²¹⁸, that term should not always be read as **tige₂**. In addition, remember our considerations about the **gala/kalû(m)** as a priest and not musician. All of that is very relevant for a justification *a priori* of our hypothesis. In fact, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* would *a priori* both pertain to music, whether for festivals or lamentations. That happens also with the ideal musician. Certainly, a true musician is able to make good music in many musical styles.

Concerning the 1st-millennium evidence, Neo-Assyrian²¹⁹ and Seleucid texts²²⁰ describe the performances of the *nāru* with the verb *zamāru* (“to sing”). That might help to identify this figure as a singer. However, the *nāru* usually plays some instruments in his/her performances²²¹. In addition, we know instrumental specialities of that figure²²²

²¹⁵ Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“(Hymnen)Sänger”); Volk, 1994: 183, 185 n. 48 and 51, 187; Volk, 2006: 7 n. 14, 22 (“Festmusiker” in both publications).

²¹⁶ For additional comments on this topic, see Löhnert, 2008: 426-428, 420.

²¹⁷ As a part of his devotion to music (**nam-nar**), King Šulgi expresses his practice of several types of lamentations (*Šulgi B*, 173–174; ETCSL 2.4.2.02). The same might happen in *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373, where we find the expression **ser₃ še₁₁(LUL)-da**. See our section 4.4.4.2 for comments.

²¹⁸ See our section 3.2.2.2 for comments.

²¹⁹ SAA 3 37 = CT 15, pl. 43–44 [K. 3476], o. 21’; SAA 20 7 = KAR 215 [VAT ---] + PKT 16 [VAT 10464], o. ii 51’, r. iii 2; SAA 20 16 [K. 3455 + 5660 + 9937 + 17525 + 17648 + 18029 + 18117 + 18309 + 18440], o. i 12’, r. iv 13, 23; SAA 20 17 = PKT 19 [VAT 13597 + 13999] + OrSP 23, p. 115 [VAT 13830], r. 8, 11; SAA 20 18 [K. 9923], o. 14–15; SAA 20 19 = KAR [VAT 10112], o. ii 6–9, r. i 13’, r. ii 1’, 16’, 28’; SAA 20 20 = CA, pl. 6 [Ist. A 127], o. i 22; SAA 20 21 = PKT 12–13 [VAT 13717], r. 1, 7; SAA 20 31 = BBR pl. 56 [K. 8380], o. 6’, 15’–17’, 22’, r. 2, 8; SAA 20 32 = KAR 141 [VAT 13003], o. 20, r. 1, 3; SAA 20 52 = CA, pl. 1–2 [BM 121206], r. i 31’–32’; SAA 20 53 = PKT 14–15 [VAT 13596], o. i 16’, r. vi 1’. All these texts have been cited according to their editions in SAAo and they have a historic-geographical precedent in *Middle Assyrian Coronation Ritual text*, KAR 135 + 137 + 216 + 217 [VAT 9583 + VAT 9936 +? VAT 10113 (+) VAT 09978], r. iii 2 (Müller, 1937: 14).

²²⁰ TCL 6 41 [AO 6460], r. 31 (Linssen, 2005: 247).

²²¹ *Aššurbānīpal Assyrian Tablet 2* [K. 2694 + 3050], o. iii 3’–4’ (RINAP 5 Q003772); Ebeling, 1948: 416–422 [VAT 13832], 19–22 (Ebeling, 1948: 417); SAA 3 4 = *Nanaya Hymn of Sargon II*, ABRT 1, pl. 54–55 [K 3600 + DT 75], o. i 7’–9’ (SAAo). In addition, but more indirectly, *Maqlû VII* 155 (Abusch, 2015: 188). All these texts are from the Neo-Assyrian Period.

²²² **Lu₂ Short 1**, 205 (DCCLT) about the **nar balaj** (“**nar** of the **balaj** drum”).

and some instruments put to his/her disposal²²³. In this sense, we shall still identify the **nar/nāru(m)** with a musician also by the 1st millennium.

1.4. Objectives of this study

In line with the aspects discussed in the previous section, the main objective of this study will be to demonstrate our hypothesis—to prove the existence of a word for “music” in Mesopotamia— through analysis of all the texts with **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* currently known.

As a consequence of this main objective, a secondary objective of this study will be the compilation of all references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* in the *corpus* of Sumerian and Akkadian texts. Said task is a bit complicated since, every year, many new cuneiform texts are published or (re)edited. That affects, of course, our total number of references to **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*²²⁴. In this sense, why is it necessary? In Assyriology, when we try to define a concrete Sumerian or Akkadian term, we normally look at its different appearances in the lexical lists and series, the paradigms of Mesopotamian “science”. In those texts, each natural/cultural entity known in Sumerian and/or Akkadian was ordered in different groups. As a consequence, all the terms with a similar meaning were ordered in those lists together creating, for instance, lists of wooden objects²²⁵. Once we have established the relationships of our word with other words from those lists, maybe we have already a plausible idea about the sense of our term to be confirmed with other texts.

However, this procedure (which we can find in some studies about Mesopotamian music)²²⁶, has its limitations for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. Certainly, we have 70 allusions to both terms from the Old Akkadian Period until the Late Seleucid Period. However, we have just one Old Babylonian reference to **nam-nar** (perhaps as a generic abstract noun, perhaps as term for an office) and one to *nārūtu(m)* coming from the Neo-Assyrian Period

²²³ YOS 6 62 [YBC 7388] (Nabonidus 06-12-06), r. 7 (CAD S, p. 119).

²²⁴ Since the start of the origins of this study, by October 2015, the texts 19–21 (in 2016 by Anne Goddeeris; see our section 3.3.3 for comments) and *Šulgi CC* (our Texts 37 and 41, in 2019, by Jeremiah Peterson, see our section 4.4.3.5 and 4.5 for comments) have been published. In addition, Manuel Ceccarelli published a new edition of *Enki and Ninmah* (= Text 27) in 2016 (see our section 4.2.2 for comments).

²²⁵ Civil, 1995: 2305–2306.

²²⁶ In addition to Krispijn, 1990 and 2010, Shehata, 2009: 9–10, 15–18, 55–58, 228, 240, 262–264 or Rendu Loisel, 2011: 1–15, 29–54, 73–86, 122–158.

(perhaps about an instrument)²²⁷. Furthermore, we have two references to **s/šer₃ nam-nar** (literally “**nam-nar s/šer₃** song) from the Old Babylonian and Neo-Assyrian periods²²⁸. Therefore, most of our allusions to **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* remain unexplained from an exclusively lexical perspective, and we must also study other texts.

1.5. Methodology

1.5.1. General Definition

Since this work deals with Sumerian and Akkadian musical terms, its methodology will be mainly philological, and most concretely lexicographical. In any case, three disciplines are interconnected in this study:

- The main discipline, the Assyriology, encompasses the holistic study of the cultures sharing the (different varieties of) cuneiform script in the ancient Near East, especially from a philological perspective²²⁹.
- In second place is Musicology, since we deal with musical terms. Some comments coming from Organology and the History of Music will be necessary in certain points of this study. One of these occasions will be the moment of identifying a term related for an instrument related to **nam-nar** or *nārūtum* in a textual excerpt.
- Finally, our interest in the time and space comes from History and Historical Method²³⁰. We might also establish connections with Microhistory. This trend is focused on the history of small units of the past²³¹, such as an individual, concrete fact or a two terms as in this case. Concerning Archaeology, an independent discipline but in close connection with History, it will be not particularly relevant here since this study is mainly philological. However, some comments about ancient, preserved musical instruments and their iconography will sometimes be necessary in our

²²⁷ See our Texts 10 and 58 for reference and interpretation.

²²⁸ See our texts 9 and 59 for reference.

²²⁹ Römer, 1999: 139-141; Charpin, 2014: 6, 10-11.

²³⁰ Garraghan, 1946: 168.

²³¹ Szijártó and Magnússon, 2013: 147.

identifications of some specific musical terms in close connection to **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*.

We offer, in this way, a multidisciplinary study whose methodology will be based on two main aspects: 1) the edition of each one of our excerpts with **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*, and 2) the commentary on these excerpts.

1.5.2. About the Textual Editions

1.5.2.1. Main texts of this study

All the texts presented in this study have already been published and edited to some extent²³². We have also dealt with some unpublished texts. However, since they did not contain **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*, they have not been finally edited here²³³. Certainly, we have been edited only texts containing (possible) references to **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* here as an attempt to give them their necessary relevance.

In any case, all the texts in this study are presented in the newest editions possible made by ourselves. For that, we have checked the available copies and photos of each of cuneiform tablets studied here, making minor²³⁴ or major corrections (indicated in footnotes) on our most accurate²³⁵ available transliterations. In addition to those reference editions, other editions have also been checked, and their variations concerning different

²³² Except, perhaps, the editions of *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, which come from the generosity of Manuel Ceccarelli, who is editing the entire text for his *Habilitationschrift* (= Ceccarelli, *forthcoming*). In any case, we have tried to revise his edition (in its state as of 26/06/2019) with the ways to be explained right now. See our section 4.2.1 for editions and comments.

²³³ In addition to tablet LB 1004, see the beginning of our last chapter for the results of our study of some unpublished Middle Babylonian tablets referring to the *nāru* musicians.

²³⁴ For “minor corrections”, we shall understand those concerning the degree of readability of a concrete cuneiform sign, corrections which depend to some degree upon the one who is reading the manuscript. For instance, putting a **gal** as ‘gal’ since, according to what we have seen in the copy, photo or real manuscript (when we could collate it), the sign is damaged at a certain point. Generally, they are not specifically indicated in our editions, but the differences can be checked by having a look at our reference edition, normally indicated in the same footnote where these details are given.

²³⁵ We have not always followed the most recent edition for a text. That is the case of *Inanna and Enki*, where the edition of Farber-Flügel, 1973 was to our mind much more reliable than the one of ETCSL.

aspects of the epigraphy or the textual criticism are included with footnotes in our editions. Likewise, with translations of these texts. Certainly, all the textual excerpts edited in this study have been translated by ourselves starting from the original texts and languages, but we have had to pay attention also to their previous translations.

Moreover, we have had the opportunity to collate some tablets of this study in their original museums. In any case, the personal collation of all the tablets edited for the present study is something certainly complicated for reasons beyond the large dispersal of these tablets around the world. Certainly, some tablets could not be found in their supposed locations²³⁶. Others tablets have been too recently collated for making a recollation with a real impact in the current research²³⁷. Concerning the tablets in collections of the modern Near East, their location is usually unknown to us and probably dangerous. That is the case of the tablets from Mari studied here, which are now in Syria²³⁸.

In any event, when these collations have been made, we have indicated the day of the collation in our edition. These collations have been especially relevant in texts with a unique tablet, like several administrative²³⁹ and literary texts²⁴⁰. Certainly, those excerpts can be definitely considered as new editions presented for this study.

²³⁶ That is the case of our Text 67. CT 17 pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 18'–19'. Certainly, Enrique Jiménez could not find this tablet in 2013 (Jiménez, 2013b: 153, and personal communication). We could neither do it in 01/08/2019. The same seems to have happened with tablet N_{LE} = Castellino, 1972: fig. 3 [N 1741] containing *Šulgi B*. However, it was fortunately found (again) by Philip Jones during our collation visit to the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology (19–23/08/2019).

²³⁷ This is the case of Geller, 2003: 109–111 [MS 2951] (Text 12), recently published in George and Spada, 2019: 116–117 profiting from the collations by Konrad Volk in June 2018. In any case, our edition tries to discuss these collations as a part of the many previous editions of this text. Texts 19–21 of this study are another example because of their edition and publication in 2016 by Anne Goddeeris as Manfred Krebernik wisely advised us. We attempted to collate other texts from the *Hilprecht Sammlung* without success, as was also the case for several tablets from the *Musée du Louvre*.

²³⁸ See our Chapter 4 for their edition and study.

²³⁹ Like in Nisaba 11 33 [BM 104768] (*Šulgi* 36-11-00), r. i 3–10 (Text 5), BE 8/1 98 [CBS 3579] (Cambyses 14+-01-00) (Text 61); MacGinnis, 2002: 234, text n. 12 [BM 64026] (Cyrus 07-10-06) (Text 62); MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 83, text n. 3 [BM 70463] (00-00-00) (Text 64); Wunsch, 2003: 106, text n. 33 [BM 30515] (Nabonidus, 10-11-15) (Text 65) and *Dar.* 463 [BM 77393] (Darius (x)+3-1-18) (Text 66).

²⁴⁰ Except for *Inanna and Enki*, where the different manuscripts have different parts of this text. Other examples are *Šulgi CC* (at the moment only preserved in the manuscript UET 6/3 522 [U. 7774]) and Koch, 2004: 106–108 [BM 55466 + 55486 + 55627] (Text 69). See their editions for more details. We advise to proceed in the same way for the cases to be examined in the following footnotes.

We have some texts preserved in several manuscripts, as most of our lexical and literary texts. For those cases, we have prepared score editions transliterating the content of the different “witnesses” of these texts, inspecting the available copies and/or photos of said tablets and collating them we could. In this way, many excerpts are presented here for the first time in a score edition. Certainly, some of these texts had only been edited in the past as composite lines with an overview of their different variants²⁴¹. In other cases, composite lines were accompanied just by a list of manuscripts and²⁴² a short indication of the lines contained in each text²⁴³. Finally, for *Death of Nannā*, 19, the different variants of the text have been edited separately. Our task, in this case, was to gather them for our score²⁴⁴. In any case, the final result is, unfortunately, not very relevant²⁴⁵.

In the case of pre-existing score editions²⁴⁶, our task has mainly consisted of the consultation and discussion of these previous materials, as well as the attempt to improve said editions. On the one hand, we have tried to see if newly identified manuscripts of these texts according to CDLI— those not used in previous editions— contain the excerpts we are using. This was the case for our editions of *Inanna and Enki*, *Ur-Namma A*, and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*. On the other hand, we have provided a composite line (something common to all our score editions) for those score editions without it²⁴⁷. The reason is that we tend to think that composite lines are useful in order to summarize what we have in the totality of the manuscripts for a single line.

²⁴¹ That is the case of the *Šulgi B*, 154–157, 162, 277–279 (where we have used Casstellino, 1972 in addition to Krispijn, 1990: 21 for *Šulgi B*, 162) and *The Father and his rude Son* (Sjöberg, 1972).

²⁴² Except for *Šulgi E*. A list of manuscripts for *Šulgi E*, 155 (= Text 32) could be inferred from the score edition (revised and corrected in some points here) of *Šulgi E*, 162–163 (= Text 26) edited by BPOA 9, p. 166. In any case, we had to identify the lines contained in each manuscript for *Šulgi E* in order to prepare our edition of *Šulgi E*, 155.

²⁴³ This has been the case of **Niḫ₂-ga**, 73–75 (Text 11), never tried to prepare completely in DCCLT according to a personal communication of Niek Veldhuis). Other texts are **Mur-gu₄** = *imrū* = *ballu*, B, II 169 (Text 58), *Examination Text A*, 24 (Text 59) or *Nabnītu*, Tablet IVa 329 (Text 60).

²⁴⁴ Kramer, 1960: 52 and Sjöberg, 1983: 318.

²⁴⁵ See our Text 38 for reference.

²⁴⁶ *Proto-Lu₂*, 590–591 (Text 9; edited by DCCLT); *Proto-izi*, II 227–231 (Text 10; previously prepared by DCCLT and Crisostomo, 2019: 296); *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, 94–99, 110–113 (in Ceccarelli, *forthcoming*); *Enki and Ninmaḡ*, b 26–29 (Text 27; previously edited by Ceccarelli, 2016: 110–112); *Ur-Namma A*, 188 (Text 31; previously edited by Flücker-Hawker, 1999: 133); *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 367, A 373–374 (Texts 39 and 40; already edited by Ludwig, 1990: 167).

²⁴⁷ Basically, the texts edited by Manuel Ceccarelli: *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu* and *Enki and Ninmaḡ*.

Another important task in our editions has been the renovation of the *sigla* of the manuscripts used for these editions. Our purpose with that was to adapt them to new Assyriological conventions. Certainly, these new *sigla* are relevant for our study where we pay attention to the chronology, provenance, and textual typology of our texts. Certainly, these new *sigla* make explicit, at least, the provenance and tablet type of each of the manuscripts for a concrete text²⁴⁸. Those criteria have been used then in order to arrange the different manuscripts in our editions.

As final considerations for this section, here are some additional conventions for our textual editions normally used in Assyriology, but indicated here as a reminder:

?	<i>ka</i> [?]	Possibly the sign we have transliterated, but uncertain.
!	<i>ka</i> [!]	Sign incorrectly written.
x	<i>ka-x</i>	Unidentified sign, most probably because it is damaged.
⌈ ⌋	⌈ <i>ka</i> ⌋	Sign damaged but still mostly readable.
*	<i>ka</i> ^{*249}	Collated sign. We used that also for “collations” through copies and photos when it is clear.
!?	<i>ka</i> ^{!?}	Sign needing a collation
[]	<i>k[a]</i>	Sign partially destroyed. It was restored here keeping in mind its shape in the copy, photo, or the original tablet.
	<i>[ka]</i>	Destroyed sign completely restored, normally taking into account the grammar of the text and/or the context.
[x]	<i>ka-[x ...]</i>	Missing section where we know how many signs we could originally have.
[...]	<i>ka-[...]</i>	Missing section with an unknown number of missing signs.
{x}	<i>ka-{KA}-lu-u</i>	Redundant sign.
< >	<i>ka-<lu>-u</i>	Sign omitted/forgotten by the scribe. This sign is, however, necessary in the understanding of a word in a text.

²⁴⁸ See Delnero, 2006: 1857–1863 for an example.

²⁴⁹ This * should not be confused with the * put before some words in order to indicate that they are only theoretical or even non-existent in any currently extant text.

1.5.2.2. Secondary texts

Other relevant texts used for examining our excerpts with **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* will be just mentioned in the footnotes. At the most, we shall offer a short transliteration and translation in that footnote. We shall make reference to these secondary texts through a reference to the concrete excerpt and an indication of the edition we have followed for consulting that text. Maybe we might make changes in that edition, but that would require a different study. For instance, when we say “*Šulgi B*, 167 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02)”, we will mean that the excerpt to which we are making reference is the line 167 of the hymn *Šulgi B*, and the edition we have used for consulting that text is the one in ETCSL.

1.5.3. About the Commentary of these Edited Texts

After its edition, we offer a commentary for each of our texts containing **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)*. There, we shall try to discuss the strongest and weakest points of the different definitions previously given for those terms. Our purpose will be to justify why “Music” is, in most cases, the most suitable meaning for **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* in our texts.

Our discussions will usually pay attention to several aspects of the grammar and linguistics of the Sumerian and Akkadian languages with some musicological comments. However, the most important part of our discussions will rely on a longer/shorter description of other terms from those texts. That will usually imply to discuss the previous definitions of those terms in our texts.

The study of these terms mentioned together with **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* in a given text will normally be performed through the consultation of other similar texts concerning their chronology, provenance, and textual typology. For instance, in our comment on **nam-nar** in *Gudea Cylinders*, we shall try to use mainly other excerpts from that text. Then, we will use excerpts from other royal inscriptions and administrative texts of the same period (2nd Dynasty of Lagaš). Finally, references to earlier and later periods will be tried to be justified and contextualized as much as possible in our discussions.

1.6. Expected Results of this study

We expect, above all, to prove successfully our hypothesis that the main meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* was “Music”, although some secondary meanings also existed. Therefore, we hope to demonstrate there was a word indeed for “Music” in ancient Mesopotamia, something with its implications for future studies dealing with the most intellectual dimensions of music in that culture. Other secondary results are also foreseen. The most important of them is the hope to solve some debates about the identification of some Sumero-Akkadian musical terms to be studied here for their connections with **nam-nar** and/or *nārūtu(m)*.

The results to expect may be *a priori* simple. However, we need to deal with great difficulties in order to exceed them. Some of them are the long chronology to be covered here (from the Old Akkadian Period to the Late Seleucid Period) or the different involved textual typologies: lexical, legal and administrative and literary texts, these with different typologies (commentaries, royal praise hymns, or wisdom texts). Certainly, each of the periods and textual typologies is usually the sole expertise of many Assyriologists more competent than ourselves, and, despite their brilliant skills, they usually must devote themselves many years to master adequately their knowledge of that typology/period.

In this sense, we have a big responsibility. However, we are partially relieved since some studies crossing chronologies and typologies, have already been conducted in other fields of Assyriology. This has been the case for the study of Mesopotamian demons²⁵⁰ and hybrid creatures²⁵¹. However, they are increasingly becoming common also in the research on Mesopotamian music²⁵². Therefore, as it is, at least, possible to present an acceptable study of this kind, we shall do our best here.

²⁵⁰ Heeßel, 2002.

²⁵¹ Shehata, 2018a. We know just the abstract of that *Habilitationschrift* available on the website of the Lehrstuhl für Altorientalistik of the Universität Würzburg. In any case, while we wait for the publication of that study, see Shehata, 2017c for the main lines of that research.

²⁵² Pruzsinszky, *forthcoming*. A similar thing might happen with Mirelman, 2018b. We know from that study just an abstract amably sent to us by his author (many thanks for that). In any case, the large scope of that research can be traced from previous publications of that author as Mirelman, 2010 and Mirelman and Sallaberger, 2010. We also recommend having a look at Mirelman, 2018a.

2. THE THIRD MILLENNIUM

2.1. The Old Akkadian Period

We have references to the **nar** and abstract nouns with the prefix **nam-** from as early as the Early Dynastic IIIa²⁵³. In this sense, it is probable that the term **nam-nar** was already in use at that time. However, we do not actually have such early references to **nam-nar** *per se*. Even if we had them, they would be probably of uncertain meaning. In fact, this is indeed the case for our earliest (possible) references to **nam-nar** coming from the Old Akkadian Period, 2340–2200 BCE. One of these references to **nam-nar** is contained in this text from Dirsu:

Text 1. CT 50, pl. 168 [BM 86313] (00-00-00)²⁵⁴

- | | |
|------|--|
| o. 5 | 1 maš ₂ ur- ^d ištaran |
| o. 6 | dumu ṛx'-KA-ki |
| o. 7 | 1 udu niga ṛlugal'-nam(-)nar |
| o. 8 | 1 maš ₂ ṛur ₂ -a ṛ-ḫi |
| o. 9 | dumu AN.ṛBI [?] .IR [?] ²⁵⁵ |
| o. 5 | One kid (for) Ur-Ištaran, |
| o. 6 | son of [...]-ki. |
| o. 7 | One barley-fed sheep (for) Lugal-namnar |
| o. 8 | One kid (for) Uraḫi, |
| o. 9 | son of [...] |

Certainly, our problems with this Text 1 begin with whether we read **lugal-nam nar** (that is, a **nar** called Lugal-nam with no reference to **nam-nar**)²⁵⁶ or **lugal-nam-nar**. Following that second option, we would have in this text a personal name (Lugal-

²⁵³ According to CDLI, there are around 56 references to the **nar** in Early Dynastic IIIa texts, like the administrative text CUSAS 11 18 [CUNES 50-03-188], o. 2 (CDLI P329273). Concerning the abstract nouns, ePSD2 offers four terms already documented by this period: **nam-gu₂** (“oppression”), **nam-lu₂** (“condition as human being”), **nam-maḫ** (“majesty”) and **nam-tur** (“smallness”).

²⁵⁴ Edition dependent upon CDLI P213074 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy and photo of this manuscript available on that site.

²⁵⁵ CDLI P213074 has “dingir-bi-ir”. The shape of the last two signs is uncertain as, according to our inspection of the photo of this tablet, the central parts of the signs are erased.

²⁵⁶ CDLI P213074 (“lugal-nam nar”).

namnar)²⁵⁷ meaning something like “master (of) **nam-nar**”²⁵⁸. Therefore, we would have here a reference to **nam-nar**. This option seems likely to us. Certainly, Lugal-nam is documented as personal name in several Old Akkadian texts²⁵⁹. However, most²⁶⁰ of these texts come from Adab while our Text 1 comes from Dirsu. Furthermore, that Lugal-nam might be identified in one of these texts from Adab as scribe (**dub-sar**)²⁶¹. In addition, we know other names of the type **lugal** + **nam** + noun in the Old Akkadian texts: Lugal-namdag²⁶² and Lugal-namme²⁶³ from Dirsu, Lugal-nammes²⁶⁴ and Lugal-namdu²⁶⁵ from Adab²⁶⁶, Lugal-namgusu from Umma²⁶⁷, besides Lugal-namzitar(a)²⁶⁸, Lugal-nammuru’e²⁶⁹ and Lugal-namtare²⁷⁰, three people from Nippur.

This **lugal-nam(-)nar** might be connected with the **lugal nam-nar-ra** of the Old Babylonian literary text *Šulgi E*, 162 to be commented on later. Regarding the 3rd-

²⁵⁷ **lugal-nam-nar** lacks a preceding *Personenkeil*, which could indicate that it a professional and not a personal name. However, none of the other, more certain, personal names in this text have such a marker either.

²⁵⁸ For “master of music” without any auxiliary brackets, we should have **lugal-nam-nar-ra**.

²⁵⁹ Adab 658 [OIM A658] (00-00-00), o. 11 (CDLI P217476); CUSAS 13 2 [CUNES 47-12-177] (00-00-00), r. 8 and 11 (CDLI P328973); CUSAS 19 97 [CUNES 48-10-76] (00-00-00), o. 4’, 7’, r. 1, 5 (CDLI P323078); CUSAS 20 136 [CUNES 48-7-97] (00-00-00), o. 4 (CDLI P322791); CUSAS 20 164 [CUNES 48-06-173] (00-00-00), o. 2 (CDLI P329177); CUSAS 20 339 [CUNES 47-11-47] (00-00-00), o. 3 (CDLI P328933); CUSAS 35 360 [MS 4206] (Naram-Sîn 01-00-00³), o. ii 18 (CDLI P253281); STTI 1 20 [Ist. L 1176] (00-00-00), o. 5 (CDLI P217065); TCBI 1 212 [BdI 1,180] (00-00-00), r. 1 (CDLI P382464); TCBI 1 231 [BdI 1,86] (00-00-00), r. 2 (CDLI P382483).

²⁶⁰ Except ITT 2 4409 [Ist. L 4409] (00-00-00), r. 2 (CDLI P214231), coming from Dirsu.

²⁶¹ Farber and Walter, 2003: 66 n. 1 [Anonymous 499911] (00-00-00), r. 8 (CDLI P499911). Keep in mind, in any case, the uncertain provenance of this text.

²⁶² ITT 1 1100 [Ist. L 1100] (00-00-00), o. 7 (CDLI P213570).

²⁶³ RTC 96 [AO 31324] (00-00-00), o. 10’ (CDLI P216875).

²⁶⁴ Adab 1209 [OIM A1209] (00-00-00), o. ii 10 (CDLI P217636).

²⁶⁵ CUSAS 20 168 [CUNES 48-10-115] (00-00-00), r. 1 (CDLI P323117).

²⁶⁶ There is also a reference to one Lugal-namzitar(a) in a text from Adab, CUSAS 20 164 [CUNES 48-6-173] (00-00-00), o. 7 (CDLI P329177). That personal name is normally seen in texts of Nippur.

²⁶⁷ CDLI P390448 [Kress 150] (03-00-00?), o. i 2.

²⁶⁸ OSP 2 120 [CBS 6225] (00-00-00), o. 5 (CDLI P216274); OSP 2 134 [N 526] (00-00-00), o. 5 (CDLI P216288); OSP 2 136 [N 278] (00-00-00), o. 3 (CDLI P216290); OSP 2 149 [CBS 6223 + N 611] (00-00-00), o. 2 (CDLI P216303); OSP 2 154 [N 275] (00-00-00), o. 8 (CDLI P216308).

²⁶⁹ OSP 1 24 [N 281] (00-00-00), o. iii 2 (CDLI P216091).

²⁷⁰ OSP 2 100 [UM 29-15-202] (Šar-kali-šarrī 02-00-00), r. i 15 (CDLI P216254).

millennium, a personal name of the type **lugal-nam-nar** during the Old Akkadian Period would also be congruent with another Old Akkadian text from Adab (modern Bismaya). In this text, which deals with some grain deliveries, we might have the name **sipa-nam(-)nar**. This personal name might be translated as something like “shepherd (**sipa**) (of the **nam-nar**)”. Here is the text:

Text 2. Adab 652 [OIM A652] (00-00-00)²⁷¹

o. 6 **š**u-ni²⁷²in₂ 10 la₂ 1 še gur
o. 7 **e**₂ ḡiri₃-ne₂^{ki} [...]
o. 8 **s**ipa²⁷³-nam(-)nar
o. 9 **mu**-k[u_x(DU)]²⁷⁴

o.⁹ Delivery: o.⁶ a total of 10 straps (?) and one **gur** of barley o.⁷ (from) the house of Dirine [...] o.⁸ (for) Sipa-nam(-)nar.

As in the previously noted Text 1, we know several people called Sipa-nam by the Old Akkadian period²⁷⁵ acting as scribe (**dub-sar**)²⁷⁶, overseer (**ugula**)²⁷⁷, or royal secretary (**sukkal lugal**)²⁷⁸. Moreover, we have a term called **sipa nam-dumu** translated by Daniel Foxvog as “shepherd for all the (royal) children”²⁷⁹. That term is documented

²⁷¹ Edition dependent upon CDLI with corrections derived from our inspection of the original copy (Adab, p. 398) and the photos of the manuscript available on CDLI P217475.

²⁷² CDLI P217475 has “szunigin” (= **šunigin** = ŠU.GAN₂tenû) while the original edition (Adab, p. 292–293) has “šunigin” (= **šunigin₂**). According to our consultation of the copy and photo of this text, the original edition is closer to what we find in the text. In any case, the situation is a bit confusing since both signs are a bit “merged”. In fact, the sign LAGAB (= **ni₂gin₂**) of this text has here several unusual straight wedges, perhaps because of its contact with the previous sign ŠU. In this sense, we would consider this sign LAGAB as an incorrectly written sign.

²⁷³ CDLI P217475 has “sipa” (without any indication of damages) while the original edition (Adab, p. 292–293) has “sipa”. Despite the lack of correspondence between the edition and the copy of this tablet, we agree with the original edition after having checked the photo available on CDLI.

²⁷⁴ CDLI P217475 has “kux(DU)” without any damage on the sign. However, as we can see in the different copies and photos of this text, the tablet is broken by the end of this line.

²⁷⁵ In addition to the texts to be listed in the following footnotes, see CDLI P270837 [Anonymous 270837] (00-00-00), o. ii 3 (text from Umma); Westenholz, 1974: 78, text 4 [NMC 10071] (00-00-00), r. 2 (CDLI P214873) a text of uncertain provenance.

²⁷⁶ MDP 14 19 [Sb 1819] (00-00-00), r. 9 (CDLI P215583; text from Susa).

²⁷⁷ TMH 5 186 + 202 [HS 936 + 952 + 994 + 1000] (00-00-00), r. i 22 (CDLI P020600; from Nippur).

²⁷⁸ USP 26 [NMS A.1927.421] (00-00-00), r. 6 (CDLI P217383; text from Umma).

²⁷⁹ Foxvog, 2014: 7.

in three Early Dynastic IIIb texts²⁸⁰. That is, it is documented in the immediately previous period to our Text 2. In this sense, we would defend a transliteration of the type **sipa-nam-nar** in Text 2 instead of **sipa-nam nar** (that is, a **nar** called Sipa-nam).

Lugal-namnar and Sipa-namnar are just two personal names contained in a couple of administrative texts. Therefore, we cannot discuss much about their exact reference to **nam-nar** as “Music” or any other musical aspect. In any case, they are still of interest in order to think about the evolution of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* during the Mesopotamian history to be described in the next chapters of this study. Certainly, we have another **lugal-nam-nar(-ra)** by the Old Babylonian Period (*Šulgi E*, 162). However, that will not be the case of **sipa-nam-nar**, a term which will disappear from Mesopotamian records in the 3rd millennium as other musical terms only known in the earliest stages of Mesopotamian history. Among them, we have **bur2-balaṅ**, GI×TAK₄ and DEŠ×TAK₄²⁸¹.

2.2. The 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš

2.2.1. Introduction

By the 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš (2200–2112 BCE), another administrative text might contain a possible allusion to **nam-nar**:

Text 3. MVN 6 309 [Ist. L 7319] (00-00-00)²⁸²

o. i 12	[...]- ki-aṅ2
o. i 13	+1.0.4 1/2 1/4 gana2
o. i 14	[...]- nam(-)nar
o. i 15	[...] gana2
o. i 12	[...] measured
o. i 13	340,5 and ¼ gana2 of land
o. i 14	[...]-namnar(?)
o. i 15	[...] field

²⁸⁰ All of them come from the 4th year of Urukagina’s reign and probably from Dirsu (the provenance in the last of these text is, nevertheless, uncertain). These texts are DP 588 [AO 13796], o. i 6 (CDLI P221238); DP 590 [AO 13798], o. i 5 (CDLI P221240) and TSA 7 [MRAH O.653], r. i 3 (CDLI P221368).

²⁸¹ See *ED Lu2 E*, 103–105 (DCCLT Q000006) and *ED Practical Vocabulary A*, 210–212 (DCCLT Q000293) for reference.

²⁸² Edition dependent upon BDTNS 020474. We could not find any copy/photo of this manuscript.

However, as we can see, the context is highly fragmentary, and we cannot decide, for instance, if we are dealing with a person whose profession was **nar** or someone with a name including **nam-nar** as (possibly) in the previously studied Old Akkadian texts.

Therefore, in this section, we shall focus our attention on the other (and much surer) reference to **nam-nar** from this period. That reference is contained in the *Gudea Cylinders*. This is a literary text narrating the building of the E-ninnu temple by Gudea, ruler of Lagaš, for the god Ninḡirsu, the Enlil’s son²⁸³. More concretely, our excerpt belongs to a section referring to the gifts given to Ninḡirsu after his arrival in Lagaš once the temple had been finished and ready for its occupation²⁸⁴. Here is the excerpt:

Text 4. *Gudea Cylinders*²⁸⁵

B15.20 **se-em-da a2-la2 balaḡ²⁸⁶ nam-nar šu du7-a**
 B15.21 **balaḡ ki aḡ²⁸⁷-ne2 ušum-gal²⁸⁸-kalam-ma**
 B15.22 **saḡ-ba ḡen-na-da**

B15.20 With the **se-em**, the **a2-la2** (and) the **balaḡ** in perfect “music”,
 B15.21 with his **balaḡ**, Ušum-gal-kalam-ma,
 B15.22 which goes at its head (= of the procession).

In line with what we expressed in the introduction, **nam-nar** has been translated here in different ways: office of the singer²⁸⁹ or musician²⁹⁰, art of singing²⁹¹, concert²⁹², a type

²⁸³ For this overview, Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 198–200 (with previous bibliography). We thank Abraham H. Jagersma, who read an earlier version of these lines and gave us several suggestions which we have tried to follow here.

²⁸⁴ *Gudea Cylinders*, B14.25–B15.16 (Römer, 2010: 36). See Suter, 2000: 81 for comments.

²⁸⁵ Edition dependent upon Römer, 2010: 37 with consultations of the copies of this manuscript on Thureau-Dangin, 1925: pl. 45 and Price, 1927: 77–78.

²⁸⁶ Sign a bit erased at the beginning in Thureau-Dangin, 1925: pl. 45, but not in Price, 1927: 77–78.

²⁸⁷ Römer, 2010: 37 has “áḡa” in order, perhaps, to make explicit the full 3SG.POSS {**ane**}. However, we should have, at the most, **ága** (= **aga2**) and not Römer’s “áḡa” (= **aḡa2**). Moreover, the omission of “a” in the writing of that possessive was common in Gudea’s time (DGS, p. 217).

²⁸⁸ Averbeck, 1987: 702; Edzard, 1997: 97; ETCSL 2.1.7; CDLI P431882 and Elli, 2015: 444 have **ušumgal**(GAL.BUR₂). However, we have actually BUR₂-GAL (= **ušum-gal**) as in Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 136; Thureau-Dangin, 1925: 192; Wilson, 1996: 174, and Römer, 2010: 37. This confusion comes from the fact that **ušumgal**(GAL.BUR₂) is documented in other excerpts from *Gudea Cylinders*, like A6.24.

²⁸⁹ Heimpel, 2015: 606 (“art of the singer”).

²⁹⁰ Krispijn, 1998: 50 (“het muzikant zijn”); Römer, 2010: 76 (“Musikertum”).

²⁹¹ Averbeck, 1987: 702, Jacobsen 1987: 438 and Wilson, 1996: 174 (“the singing”).

²⁹² Krispijn, 1990: 2 “hymnische(r) Musik”.

of music²⁹³, or just as music²⁹⁴ in broad sense. In order to elucidate the meaning of **nam-nar** in this context, we propose an approach to the other musical terms mentioned in this excerpt whose identification has also been quite controversial in the previous research.

2.2.2. Lexicographical analysis of some terminology pertaining to this excerpt

2.2.2.1. **se-em-(da)**

Also known during the Ur III Period²⁹⁵ and the Old Babylonian versions of some hymns for Šulgi²⁹⁶, **se-em** is an archaic spelling of the instrument used for laments and known by the Old Babylonian Period as **šem₃**(AB₂×ŠAG₄)²⁹⁷ or **šem₅**(AB₂×GAN₂)²⁹⁸. These terms are now read for that Old Babylonian Period²⁹⁹ as **sem_{3/5}**, perhaps because the spelling **šem_{3/5}** can be documented only from Middle Babylonian times³⁰⁰ onwards³⁰¹.

²⁹³ Edzard, 1997: 97; ETCSL 2.1.7 and CDLI P431882 (“concert”); Elli, 2015: 444 (“sintonia”).

²⁹⁴ Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 137 (“Musik”); Price, 1927: 52, (“music”); Krispijn, 1998: 50 (“muziek”); Suter, 2000: 398 (“music”); Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205 (“arte de la Música”; we don’t support it anymore).

²⁹⁵ MVN 7 235 [Ist. L. 7836] (00-00-00), r. 2 (BDTNS 021307); Fish and Lambert, 1963: 96 18 [BM 105348] (00-00-00), r. 12, 15, 17, 20 (BDTNS 014272); AAICAB 1/2, pl. 105 [Ashm. 1937-68] (Šulgi 48-04-00), o. 2 (BDTNS 158518); Mirelman, 2010c: 33 [U. 18857] (Šu-Suen 01-06-00), o. 1 (BDTNS 071143); Nisaba 15/2 342 [Adra 15] (Šu-Suen 05-12-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 192924); Nisaba 15/2 462 [Anonymous 388020] (Šu-Suen 08-00-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 173308).

²⁹⁶ *Šulgi D*, 366 (ETCSL 2.4.2.04; see also Shulgi3Hymns, p. 68) and *Šulgi E*, 101 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

²⁹⁷ Lexical texts: **Ugu-ḡu₁₀**, 147 (DCCLT Q002268) and Veldhuis, 2017: 363–373 1 [BM 85983], r. ii 30 (CDLI P247857). Literary texts: *Enki and the World Order*, 447 (ETCSL 1.1.3); *Inanna and Enki*, II, iv 48 (Farber-Flüge, 1973: 52); *Cursing of Agade*, 201 (ETCSL 2.1.5); *Ur Lament*, 356 (ETCSL 2.2.2); *Eridu Lament*, A 61 (ETCSL 2.2.6); *Winter and Summer*, 236 (ETCSL 5.5.3) and CDLI P355702 [Haddad 2], KXXIV.16 (ePSD2).

²⁹⁸ Lexical texts: CDLI P247861 [IB 1612b], r i 7 (CDLI P247861); **Urs-ra**, II 565 (DCCLT Q000040); OIP 11 201 [CBS 6398 + 6522 + 6997], o. ii 5. Literary texts: *Iddin-Dagān A*, 70 (Attinger, 2014: 20); *Šulgi A*, 50 (Delnero, 2006: 1887); *Nippur Lament*, 38 (ETCSL 2.2.4); *Martu’s Marriage*, 60 (ETCSL 1.7.1); *Temple Hymns*, 107 (ETCSL 4.80.1); CT 36, pl. 41–42 [BM 96940], o. 19 (ePSD2).

²⁹⁹ Ceccarelli, 2012: 95; Delnero, 2015: 89, 93–94; Attinger, 2019d: 163.

³⁰⁰ Emar 6/1, p. 376 [Msk 74148k], r. i’ 13’: [**šem**]₅^{š_i-im}.^{[MIN<(zabar)]>} [...] (DCCLT with corrections derived from our consultation of the copy of the tablet).

³⁰¹ CT 11, pl. 14–18 [K. 110], iv 58: **še-em** AB₂×ŠA₃ ḫal-ḫal-la-tu (DCCLT with inspection of the copy). The Seleucid tablet SpTU 3 111 [W 23289], o. iii 9 (manuscript for **Urs-ra**, XII, Segment 1, 114)

Therefore, we prefer to read as **se-em(-da)** instead of the traditional **si-im(-da)**³⁰². Two aspects of this term are controversial. First, whether **se-em** (attested several times in Gudea's time³⁰³) and **se-em-da** (only documented in our Text 4 during the 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš) represent the same (musical) concept. Some people translated **se-em-da** as a single word³⁰⁴. However, ^(urudu)**se-em-da** (a loanword from the Akkadian *šimtum*, “mark”³⁰⁵) designates in Ur III times a type of brand mark for any kind of object³⁰⁶, and we do not believe that the meaning of that term could change so much in a century.

Theo J. H. Krispijn considered **se-em-da** as the complete orthography of the term normally written **se-em**³⁰⁷. That might make sense keeping in mind that our Text 4 already has a COM at the end of the sentence (**ḡen-na-da** = **ḡen** [PFV] + **a** [NMLZ] + **da** [COM]) and, therefore, another COM on **se-em** within the same sentence might be redundant. However, the first COM is referred to a nominalized sentence belonging to a much larger sentence of the text involving several lines, while the second COM would concern to an internal part of that nominalized sentence. In this sense, we believe that **se-em-da** would be a mere **se-em** with a COM {**da**}.

Our second difficult aspect of the **se-em** is its identity. Most previous translations³⁰⁸ agree that the **se-em** pertains to percussion, which makes sense due to the mentions of the **se-em** with other terms for percussion³⁰⁹. However, these translations disagree on its exact identification: a generic term for a percussion instrument³¹⁰, a group of cymbals³¹¹, a

has ṣem^{ṣe-em-zabar} ḡal-ḡal-[la-tu₂] (DCCLT Q000087 with corrections from our inspection of the copy of the manuscript available on CDLI P274484).

³⁰² Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 108, 136; Witzel, 1922: 95; Thureau-Dangin, 1925: 158, 192; Averbeck, 1987: 652, 702; Wilson, 1996: 84, 174; Edzard, 1997: 80, 97; ETCSL 2.1.7; Römer, 2010: 21, 37; CDLI P431882; Elli, 2015: 214, 444. In addition, Krispijn, 1998: 62 and Krispijn, 2010b: 147.

³⁰³ *Gudea Cylinders*, A18.18, A28.18 (Römer, 2010: 21, 27); Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 86 [AO 3367] (00-00-00), o. i 3, ii 7 (BDTNS 158703), and 88 [AO 3368] (00-00-00), o. i 1, iii 1, r. ii 1 (BDTNS 158704).

³⁰⁴ Falkenstein, 1949: 67 (“simda- (und)...”); Wilson, 1996: 174 (“the *simda*”).

³⁰⁵ Sallaberger, 2011: 346.

³⁰⁶ Foxvog, 1995: 1–7; Maaijer, 2001: 300–304.

³⁰⁷ Krispijn, 2010b: 147.

³⁰⁸ Except Thureau-Dangin 1907: 137, which left the term untranslated (“um.....”).

³⁰⁹ *Gudea Cylinders*, A18.18 (with the **a-dab₆** and **a₂-la₂** drums) and *Gudea Cylinders*, A28.18 (with the **a₂-la₂**) (Römer, 2010: 21, 27).

³¹⁰ Krispijn, 1998: 62 (“een trommelinstrument”); Maaijer, 2001: 305 (“percussion instrument”); (Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205 (“instrumento de percusión - s i - i m”).

³¹¹ Jacobsen 1987: 439 (“cymbals”).

tambourine³¹², a drum³¹³ or a kettledrum³¹⁴. Following the more specialized research³¹⁵, we should identify the **se-em** with a group of cymbals. That makes sense taking in account that, in a text of Gudea's times, there is a mention of a 15 pairs of this instrument³¹⁶. Such a number of instruments fits quite well with the **se-em** as a group of little cymbals (the unique instrument used in pairs, like zills). Certainly, it would be easier to produce than other and larger percussion instruments made of metal.

2.2.2.2. **a2-la2**

The identification of this term seems to have been a bit difficult for the translators of the *Gudea Cylinders*, since we find many translations of **a2-la2** just as “musical instrument”³¹⁷. Jacobsen identified it as a sort of lyre³¹⁸. This identification was followed by Anne D. Kilmer³¹⁹, who offered a general identification for the **a2-la2** as a wooden lyre with a drumable skinned surface. Her identification was based on the writings of **a2-la2** with the determinatives for wooden (^{neš}) and skinned objects (^{kuš}). This argumentation, however, does not make sense for Gudea's and earlier times, where the **a2-la2** almost never³²⁰ appears with those determinatives. Far from that, the **a2-la2** seems to be a percussion instrument due to its appearance together with other similar instruments³²¹.

³¹² Suter, 2000: 398 (“tambourines”).

³¹³ Averbeck, 1987: 702 (“sim-drum”); ETCSL 2.1.7. (“the sim drums”; followed by Kutzer, 2017: 86); Elli, 2015: 444 (“tamburi-‘sim’”) and Heimpel, 2015: 606 (“(the drums) sim”).

³¹⁴ Edzard, 1997: 97 (“kettledrums(?)”); followed by Mirelman, 2014: 158 and CDLI P431882); Römer, 2010: 76 (“si-im - Pauken(?)”). In the same way, Sallaberger, 2006: 581 (“Pauke”).

³¹⁵ See Gabbay, 2010: 24-25 and Mirelman, 2010c: 41 for details.

³¹⁶ Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 88 [AO 3368] (00-00-00), r. ii 5 (BDTNS 158704).

³¹⁷ Falkenstein, 1949: 67 (“ala-Instrument”), Wilson, 1996: 174 (“ala instrument”); Edzard, 1997: 97 (“ala instruments”; followed by Mirelman, 2014: 158 and CDLI P431882); Krispijn, 1998: 2 (“een muziekinstrument”); Heimpel, 2015: 606 (“ala”); Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205 (“a₂ - l a₂”). With our translation, we wanted to show the original term in the translation in order to avoid confusion for the reader. We were already familiar at that time with the common identifications of the **a2-la2**.

³¹⁸ Jacobsen 1987: 438 (“alu-lyres”) in reference. Perhaps, to the Akkadian *alû(m)*.

³¹⁹ Kilmer, 1993–1995: 465 and Kilmer, 2003–2005: 369.

³²⁰ Except the text from Ebla MEE 4 76 [TM.75.G.1445], r. iii 15 (DCCLT), where **a2-la2** appears with ^{neš}. However, this text is too far in time and distance for being considered here more in depth.

³²¹ *Gudea Cylinders*, A18.18 (with the **a-dab₆** drum and **se-em** cymbals), *Gudea Cylinders*, A28.18 (with the **se-em**) (Römer, 2010: 21, 27).

Moreover, that instrument is compared with a storm (**u₄**), and the production of its sound is described with the expression **šeg₁₂ ge₄**³²², an archaic³²³ variant for **šeg₁₁ ge₄** (“to roar”)³²⁴.

As a percussion instrument, the **a₂-la₂** has mainly been identified with cymbals³²⁵ and a type of drum³²⁶. Sam Mirelman identified it with the giant drum³²⁷. That seems plausible in light of the etymology of **a₂-la₂** as “hanged (**la₂**) arm (**a₂**)”, an attitude which we can see in the players of the giant drum depicted in the Ur III iconography³²⁸. However, according to a Gudea’s royal inscription³²⁹, a **nar** of the **a₂-la₂** instrument (**nar a₂-la₂**) “sits in front” (**igi-še₃ ba-gub**) of a temple gate. That is, a single musician seems to be able to play an **a₂-la₂** without the help of someone maintaining the instrument vertically³³⁰. Certainly, otherwise, we would expect a plural sentence like **nar a₂-la₂-ne-ka igi-še₃ ba-gub-be-eš₂**. Consequently, and concerning Gudea’s times, the **a₂-la₂** might be just a type of drum played up high with the arm raised. In this sense, it might not be a giant drum, a type of instrument documented a century later in the iconography. In any case, we have scarce pieces of evidence for the **a₂-la₂** and musical iconography³³¹ in Gudea’s times. Therefore, we should maintain the accepted identification of the **a₂-la₂** as a giant drum also for Gudea’s times as a matter of prudence³³².

³²² *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20 (see our Text 4 for edition). Moreover, remember *Gudea Cylinders*, A28.18 (Römer, 2010: 27), where the sounds of the **a₂-la₂**, together with those of the **se-em** and the **šudu₃** prayers, fill the E-ninnu’s courtyard (**kisal**).

³²³ According to ePSD2, this variant is attested for the first time in the Early Dynastic IIIb, and it is the unique form of /šeg/ during Gudea’s times.

³²⁴ See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 10, 285 for comments.

³²⁵ Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 137 (“die Cymbeln”), Price, 1927: 52 (“the cymbals”).

³²⁶ Averbeck, 1987: 702 (“ala-drum”); Suter, 2000: 398 (“tympaña”); ETC SL 2.1.7 (“ala drums”); Römer, 2010: 76 “á - l á (Pauken/Trommel)”; Elli, 2015: 444 (“tamburi-‘ala’”).

³²⁷ Mirelman, 2014: 149.

³²⁸ See Rašíd, 1984: 68–73 for reference.

³²⁹ *Gudea Statue L* [E3/1.1.7.StL], a 41’ (CDLI P431893).

³³⁰ Keep in mind also the text from the Early Dynastic IIIa IAS 54 + 56 [IM 70293 +], o. v 17 (**lu₂ x²a₂-la₂**). Nevertheless, we should be careful with the distance between both texts.

³³¹ See Rašíd, 1984: 66–67 for reference.

³³² For instance, Attinger, 2019d: 5 (“un très gros tambour à doublemembrane de forme cylindrique”).

2.2.2.3. **balan**

Defined in different ways simultaneously³³³, or just as a “musical instrument” in general³³⁴, the identification of **balan** has always been highly controversial. Thus, in the *Gudea Cylinders*, it has been defined as a drum³³⁵, but also as a stringed instrument³³⁶ (whether a lyre³³⁷, whether a harp³³⁸). In fact, Kilmer said that **balan** (like the **a2-la2**) “seems to represent both stringed instruments and percussion instruments”. She identified the **balan** with a lyre in order to justify the use of the determinative ^{neš} with this term. In addition, she said that its sound-box acted as a drummable surface in order to justify the use of the determinative ^{kuš} also used with **balan**³³⁹. However, she is not right since the single determinative used with **balan** in the 3rd-millennium texts was ^{neš}. That fact would suggest the condition of the **balan** as chordophone³⁴⁰. Moreover, we should remember its description as **neš-gu3-di** (“wooden speaking voice”) in the *Gudea Cylinders*³⁴¹.

In this sense, like Uri Gabbay³⁴², we think that **balan** would designate a bull lyre by the 3rd millennium BCE and a drum by the 2nd and 1st millennia³⁴³. We think that Gabbay was right for the 3rd millennium in some aspects. First, the early (pictographic) forms of

³³³ ePSD2 (“an instrument, a large drum or harp”); Attinger, 2019d: 19 (“harpe”; un tambour”).

³³⁴ Stauder, 1970: 214 (“Musikinstrument”); Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205. For **balan** as a general term for “musical instrument”, see Hartmann, 1967: 57; Civil, 2008: 99-100 (although MUŠ *gi-na-ri-im* might be the arm of a lyre!); Michalowski, 2010a: 221 n. 45 (in reference to the unpublished Michalowski, 2006 and generalizing on what is said on Cooper, 2006: 41–42 n. 6); Shehata, 2014: 123 and Shehata, 2017: 78 (about **balan** as a divine concept; she did not actually refute Uri Gabbay’s proposal to present below).

³³⁵ Suter, 2000: 398 (“drums”); ETCSL 2.1.7 (“balaĝ drum”); Römer, 2010: 76 (“b a l a ĝ - Pauken(?) (Trommel?)”); Elli, 2015: 444 (“i tamburi-‘ala’ e ‘balag’”).

³³⁶ PSD B, 75; Krispijn, 1990: 2, 6–7; Krispijn, 1998: 9.

³³⁷ Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 137; Price, 1927: 52; Averbek, 1987: 702; Heimpel, 2015: 606.

³³⁸ Jacobsen, 1987: 438; Wilson, 1996: 174; Edzard, 1997: 97.

³³⁹ Kilmer, 1980–1983a: 573; Kilmer, 1993–1995: 465. See also Kilmer, 2003–2005: 369.

³⁴⁰ For the Old Akkadian Period, see STTI 1 182 [Ist. L 9336] (00-00-00), r. 5 (CDLI P217215). For the Ur III Period, BDTNS has 41 mentions of ^{neš}**balan**.

³⁴¹ *Gudea Cylinders*, A6.25 and A7.25 (Römer, 2010: 13–14). Old Babylonian texts describe some features of this term which allow to us to identify **neš-gu3-di** with a lute. However, none of these features are present in *Gudea Cylinders*. In this way, although lutes were already popular in Mesopotamia (Krispijn, 2011: 117), we would maintain the condition of **neš-gu3-di** as “musical instrument” by Gudea’s times.

³⁴² With precedents in Cohen, 1974: 31.

³⁴³ Mainly, Gabbay, 2014b: 132, 134, 139-141. See also Gabbay, 2007: 57–65 and Gabbay, 2017: 46.

the sign BALAD suggest the shape of a lyre³⁴⁴ (but also a harp)³⁴⁵. Secondly, **balan** might be an onomatopoeia for the strumming of a chordophone³⁴⁶.

However, Gabbay's argumentation is not always perfect. An example is when he establishes a connection between the GU₄.BALAD mentioned in **An** = *Anum* (deity list from the Middle Babylonian Period onwards and the **balan** of the 3rd millennium³⁴⁷. Certainly, he contradicts himself because he says that **balan** designates a type of drum by the 2nd millennium onward. However, he connects the GU₄.BALAD mentioned in the Middle Babylonian text **An** = *Anum* (therefore, from 2nd millennium) with the bull lyres.

There are some recent supporters of the identity of the **balan** as a lyre in the 2nd millennium³⁴⁸. However, connections between bulls and drums from the 2nd millennium onward makes sense with the **kuš-gu₄-gal** (a drum used in exorcistic contexts)³⁴⁹ and the *lilisu* kettledrum. In fact, a kettledrum qualified as ^dLILIZ and a bull are depicted together in an Achaemenid tablet³⁵⁰. Furthermore, the *lilisu* membrane should be made with the skin of an entirely black bull according to a Seleucid ritual text³⁵¹. And so, GU₄.BALAD in **An** = *Anum* is already transliterated as ^{gud}gud₁₀ (“hero”)³⁵² and not **gu₄-balan**.

³⁴⁴ Gabbay, 2014b: 130 (signs), 133 (explanation).

³⁴⁵ As we can see in Gabbay, 2014b: 130, BALAD signs depicting a lyre come from the Early Dynastic IIIa–b (ca. 2700–2340 BCE). However, BALAD signs depicting a harp are from the Uruk IV and III Periods (3350–3200, 3200–3000 BCE). An example from Uruk IV is ATU 5 89 [VAT 15061], ii 3 (CDLI P001443). In this sense, keeping in mind the distance of almost a millennium between these periods and their texts, we want to think that **balan** designated first a harp and later a lyre. It is possible that the harp were called **bur₂-balan**, term only known in the Early Dynastic IIIa–b (see CDLI for evidence). It is true that we do not have texts from Uruk of the Early Dynastic IIIa–b with the sign BALAD, so we cannot know if it was just an Urukian particularity. In any case, it makes sense with our iconography, since harps are documented earlier than lyres in Mesopotamia (see Spycket, 1972: 158 and Rašid, 1984: 52–59 for evidence).

³⁴⁶ Gabbay, 2014b: 134 n. 7 (with references to Volk, 1994: 171 n. 22 and Selz, 1997: 195 n. 153). The name of the West African *bolon* harp might be also an onomatopoeia of its sound.

³⁴⁷ Gabbay, 2014b: 139 in reference to **An** = *anum*, I 264, 267–268, 270, 272–273, II 311, 313, III, 157–158, 260–262, 264. In addition to the original edition on Litke, 1998, these excerpts are available on DCCLT Q000264 (Tablet I), Q003221 (Tablet II), and Q003222 (Tablet III).

³⁴⁸ Shehata, 2017a. In page 70 she offers the translation of **balan** as “Leier”.

³⁴⁹ See our chapter about the 1st Millennium evidence for more comments.

³⁵⁰ TCL 6 47 [MRAH O.175], reverse (Livingstone, 1986: 194; see CDLI P363719 for an image).

³⁵¹ TCL 6 44 [AO 6479], i 1–6 (Linssen, 2004: 252).

³⁵² In addition to DCCLT Q000264 (Tablet I), Q003221 (Tablet II), and Q003222 (Tablet III), see Michalowski, 2010a: 221–222.

In any case, the identification of the **balan** with the bull lyre is still possible in our opinion keeping in mind that, unlike **balan**, other terms for chordophones are not well-documented before Gudea's times³⁵³. We have a similar issue in 3rd-millennium iconography: Bull lyres are much better known than harps or lutes at that time³⁵⁴.

Despite this argumentation, some people might still believe that the **balan** might also be a drum in the 3rd millennium, perhaps for two reasons. On the one hand, the expression **gu₄ gu₃ nun di** ("bull speaking loudly") is once used with the term **balan**³⁵⁵. That expression implies the production of a loud sound hardly easy to imagine in the case of a lyre. However, as in the Old Babylonian Period³⁵⁶, this expression does not refer to the **balan**, but to a "rear" (**a-ga**) of the **balan**. This rear should be a *cella* of the E-ninnu where the **balan** instrument could be worshipped by the people with prayers and/or musical instruments³⁵⁷ as a beloved object (**ki an₂**) of Ninġirsu (the E-ninnu's tutelary deity)³⁵⁸ or as a (minor) deity itself³⁵⁹. In this sense, the sonorous environment of that rear/*cella* could be perfectly loud and, therefore, comparable to the sound of a roaring bull.

³⁵³ Texts about **al-ġar**: CUSAS 20 194 [CUNES 50-1-10] (00-00-00), o. 5–6, r. 4 (CDLI P324633) (Old Akkadian). We are not sure if this text actually referred to a musical instrument. However, if it did, it should be a stringed instrument because of the reference to "excellent strings" (**sa dirig**) for one **al-ġar**. Texts about **balan-di**: SF 70 [VAT 12617], o. i 8 (CDLI P010663) (Early Dynastic IIIa); *ED Lu₂ E*, 98 (DCCLT Q000006) (Early Dynastic IIIb). Texts about **mi-ri₂-tum**: *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.11 (Römer, 2010: 33). Texts about the **za-na-ru**: OSP 2 133 [N 433 + 581] (00-00-00), r. 12 (CDLI P216287) and OSP 2 136 [N 278] (00-00-00), r. 5 (CDLI P216290) (Old Akkadian; collated the 22/08/2019; see Bauer, 1992: notice 51 for comments).

³⁵⁴ Rašid, 1984: 28–41, 44–45, 50–51, 64–67 (lyres), against 42–43, 52–59 (harps), 62–63 (lutes).

³⁵⁵ *Gudea Cylinders*, A28.17 (Römer, 2010: 27). Gabbay, 2014b: 142 n. 37 connected this excerpt with the Seleucid Emesal prayer SBH 86 [VAT 2190], o. 18–19. Nevertheless, we should be very careful with this comparison between such two very distant texts.

³⁵⁶ *Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta*, 265 (Mittermayer, 2009: 188). The expression from the *Gudea Cylinders* was not discussed in ELS, p. 531 and Mittermayer, 2009: 254.

³⁵⁷ As we have previously noted, in *Gudea Cylinders*, A28.18 (Römer, 2010: 27), the **šudu₃** prayers, and the sounds of the **se-em** cymbals and the **a₂-la₂** giant drum fill the E-ninnu's courtyard.

³⁵⁸ In addition to our Text 4, *Gudea Cylinders*, A6.24–25 and A7.24–25 (Römer, 2010: 13–14).

³⁵⁹ This might be the reason for which a **balan** instrument receives a goat (**maš₂**) as an allotment in the text RTC 247 [AO 3432] (00-00-00), o. i 10' (BDTNS 158708). Thanks to Abraham H. Jagersma for his encouragement to think on this matter more in depth. For divinized musical instruments in Mesopotamia, see Franklin, 2013.

On the other hand, some **balaj** instruments in the *Gudea Cylinders* are called with names as **ušumgal kalam-ma**³⁶⁰ (“great dragon of the land”³⁶¹) or **lugal igi huš-am₃** (“the reddish eyed-king”³⁶²). From a modern perspective, that suggests an identification of this term with a drum. Nevertheless, the sole reference to **ušum-gal** in the *Gudea Cylinders* is about a creature sleeping in the steppe³⁶³. That has nothing in common with the usual modern image of a furious and roaring dragon whose voice might remind one of a drum.

In any case, it is important to state that bull lyres are usually displayed in the 3rd-millennium iconography with several percussion instruments³⁶⁴. Moreover, the **balaj** is mentioned with some percussion instruments as we have already said. In fact, in our opinion and beyond the cultic reasons given by Gabbay³⁶⁵, if the term **balaj** started to designate a percussion by the early 2nd millennium BCE, it was because of the close connection of the **balaj** with these percussion instruments. Their interactions increased by the end of the 3rd millennium BCE. Certainly, the instrument known in Gudea’s times as **ti-ge₄**³⁶⁶ will be written by Ibbī-Suen’s reign as **tige₂**, that is, with a logogram using the signs LUL (= **nar**) and BALAD (= **balaj**)³⁶⁷. This logogram would suggest that this instrument was something like the **balaj** (still a lyre?) of the **nar**. It was probably a necessary distinction since the **gala** used to produce laments (**er₂**) from the **balaj**³⁶⁸.

³⁶⁰ *Gudea Cylinders*, A6.24, A7.24, B18.22 (Römer, 2010: 13, 14, 38). In addition, MVN 7 458 [Ist. L 8065] (*Gudea* 02-00-00), r. 1 (BDTNS 021527); Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 82 [AO 3324] (*Gudea* 02-00-00), o. 7’ (BDTNS 180423) and Çiğ, 1976: 87 text 7 [Ist. L 40470] (*Gudea* 03-00-00), r. 4’ (BDTNS 018361). A later mention of the **balaj ušumgal kalam-ma** is found the Ur III administrative document Amherst 17 [Amherst ---] (Šulgi 25-00-00), o. ii 18 (BDTNS 001551).

³⁶¹ Kilmer, 1993–1995: 464 translates that name as “Foremost of the Land”. However, she said that the name of this instrument might come from a “‘serpentine’ shape or decoration of a balaĝ’s ‘neck’?” For a similar translation, see also Krispijn, 1998: 78 (“koninklijk fabeldier”).

³⁶² *Gudea Cylinders*, B11.1 (Römer, 2010: 34).

³⁶³ *Gudea Cylinders*, B4.20–21 (Römer, 2010: 30).

³⁶⁴ Rašid, 1984: 40–41, 65 (with sistrum; see also Collon, 2010: 49), 50–51 (with clappers).

³⁶⁵ Gabbay, 2014b: 139–143.

³⁶⁶ *Gudea Cylinders*, B18.22 (Römer, 2010: 38).

³⁶⁷ BIN 3 262 [NBC 2176] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-01), o. 3 (BDTNS 016270); MVN 12 547 [FLP 2527] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-02), o. 3 (BDTNS 027963); Princeton 2 435 [PTS 1357] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 061452) and RTC 399 [AO 2444] (Ibbī-Suen 03-00-00), r. i 24 (BDTNS 000839). We agree with Pruzsinszky, 2010: 36 that the NAR.BALAD from Gomi, 1980: 33 text 92 [BM 17810] (Amar-Suena 06-02-00), o. 1 (BDTNS 022721) should be read actually as **nar balaj** because of the context.

³⁶⁸ *Gudea Statue B* [E3/1.1.7.StB], iv 3 (CDLI P232275).

However, that relationship would not be casual: the *Gudea Cylinders* already has a **nar** called **ušum(-)gal kalam-ma**³⁶⁹ like the **balan** lyre. However, that **nar** seems to not play the said instrument, but other instruments like the **al-ḡar** and the **mi-ri₂-tum**³⁷⁰.

2.2.2.4. šu du₇-a

This is not a musical term *stricto sensu*, but its correct understanding is very important to our elucidation of **nam-nar** in this excerpt. There are several translations for this expression in our Text 4³⁷¹: 1) “to complete/finish something”³⁷², 2) “to make perfect”³⁷³, and 3) “to be perfect”³⁷⁴. The first two translations might find a justification in some excerpts from the *Gudea Cylinders*. There, **šu du₇-a** makes reference to the condition of

³⁶⁹ *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.14 (Römer, 2010: 33).

³⁷⁰ *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.11 (Römer, 2010: 33). Concerning the **mi-ri₂-tum**, we agree with Krispijn, 1990: 8 in its identification as a lyre from Mari. However, we cannot share its rationale, based on the comparison with **za₍₃₎-mi-ri₂-tum**. However, this term actually designates a type of sword (BPOA 10, p. 160). That makes sense with the references to **za₍₃₎-mi-ri₂-tum** with the determinatives ^{zabar} (bronze) and ^{ḡeš} (see BDTNS for evidence). Concerning our argumentation, Old Babylonian texts usually show the **mi-ri₂-tum** with the determinative ^{ḡeš}. Among them, we would focus our attention on *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 63 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 64) and *Šulgi B*, 163 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02). In those excerpts, this instrument (like in *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.11) is connected with a “house of silence” (**e₂ si-ga**). On the other hand, according to *ED Practical Vocabulary A*, 208 (DCCLT Q000293), there is a **balan** from Mari (**balan ma-ri₂^{ki}**). The change to **mi-ri₂-tum** might have consisted of a harmonic vocalization and the addition of the typical suffix from Akkadian origin *-itum* for geographic origins. Here is our proposal for the origin of **mi-ri₂-tum**: **balan ma-ri₂^{ki} > balan mi-ri₂ > mi-ri₂-tum**. In any case, we should be careful, since we do not know relationships between Mari and southern Mesopotamia at this time justifying such hypothetical borrowings. We miss some comments about this matter in Marcetteau, 2010, mainly focused on archaeological sources.

³⁷¹ We cannot comment here in depth on Heimpel, 2015: 606, since it ignored this expression in its translation (“with the balang of the art of the singer, his beloved balang Great Dragon of the Homeland, having walked at the head of (the drums) sim (and) ala”).

³⁷² Thureau Dangin 1907: 137 (“welche Musik vollführt”); Price, 1927: 52 (“that round out the music”); Wilson, 1996: 174 (“might complete the singing”).

³⁷³ Averbeck, 1987: 702 (“which makes the singing perfect”); Jacobsen 1987: 438 (“making the singing perfect”); Suter, 2000: 398 (“perfecting the music”); Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205 (“ejerciendo perfectamente”). In addition, keep in mind Krispijn, 1998: 68 (“voltmaakt, geschikt zijn/maken (+dir)”).

³⁷⁴ Edzard, 1997: 97 (“might sound in perfect concert”; followed by Mirelman, 2014: 158 and CDLI P431882); ETCSL 2.1.7. (“will sound in perfect concert”); Römer, 2010: 76 (“in vollkommenem Musikertum”); Elli, 2015: 444 (“suonando in perfetta sintonia”).

the **išib** purification priest and the “cultic ordinances” (**me**)³⁷⁵. In addition, they might make sense with the COM {**da**} applied over the **se-em** cymbals in our excerpt. In this sense, the **balan** and the **a2-la2** were making perfect music with the **se-em**. However, in what sense is music “made perfect” or “completed” by these instruments? Are we talking about melodic aspects, rhythm, or harmony? Since the sense of this “perfection” is unclear in this context, we prefer to understand **šu du7-a** as “to be perfect”. This meaning for **šu du7-a** might have its parallels in other excerpts from the *Gudea Cylinders* about the sacrifice of perfect bulls and he-goats. However, they lack of the **šu** of **šu du7-a**³⁷⁶.

2.2.3. Discussion of the previous translations of **nam-nar** in this excerpt

Our Text 4 might describe a musical ensemble, in our opinion, heading a procession celebrating the Ninņirsu’s arrival in the E-ninnu temple. Perhaps, it would start in the interior of the E-ninnu and go around, at least, the circuit of its territories. The instruments participating in this ensemble would be the **se-em** cymbals, the **a2-la2** giant drum, and the **balan** lyre. These instruments could participate in festive events, but also had connections with the funerary world and lamentations as we have previously seen.

Keeping these ideas in mind, **nam-nar** should describe the action of these musical instruments, a perfect (**šu du7-a**) musical action not related exclusively to a ceremonial or funerary dimension³⁷⁷. In this sense, we should reject previous interpretations of **nam-nar** in this passage as literal ones taking this term as the office or condition of a musician or singer³⁷⁸. For identical reasons, we should proceed in the same way with the translations of **nam-nar** as a type of vocal art or singing³⁷⁹. It is true that those instruments should be played by musicians, and those musicians could sing at the same time that they were playing those instruments. However, we believe it is possible that those instruments would be rhythmically accompanying the movement of the people taking part into the religious procession described in our Text 4.

³⁷⁵ *Gudea Cylinders*, A2.15, A10.17–18, A20.13, B5.23, B16.4 (Römer, 2010: 10, 15, 22, 31).

³⁷⁶ *Gudea Cylinders*, A1.14, A18.7, B7.4–10, B18.19 (Römer, 2010: 9, 21, 31–32, 38).

³⁷⁷ We dismiss, therefore, the interpretations of Krispijn, 1990: 2 and Krispijn, 1998: 50 (see the introduction for reference).

³⁷⁸ Krispijn, 1998: 50; Römer, 2010: 76; Heimpel, 2015: 606 (see the introduction for full quotations).

³⁷⁹ Averbeck, 1987: 702, Jacobsen 1987: 438 and Wilson, 1996: 174 “the singing”.

Concerning the translations of **nam-nar** as “concert”³⁸⁰, they are incorrect in several aspects. First, if we talk about a “concert” as a public event where people attend to listen to music, we are dealing with a very modern concept³⁸¹. Furthermore, our text suggests instead the enactment of a religious procession. In this sense, people would see the **se-em**, **a2-la2** and **balan** instruments and listen to their music as in a concert, but they would also see other things like in any common procession. Additionally, and without dealing in depth with the polemic question of the existence of musical polyphony in the ancient Near East³⁸², the idea of a “concert” as an “assembly of sounds” has no sense in this passage. Certainly, we have an ensemble composed by two un-pitched percussions (the **se-em** and the **a2-la2**)³⁸³ and a single stringed instrument (the **balan**). It is true that this last instrument might have sounded several notes at the same time, but we would not expect the mention of the other instruments in order to talk of **nam-nar šu du7-a**.

In this way, the most suitable translation for **nam-nar** in this passage, in our opinion and according to our previous analysis and discussions, is “music”³⁸⁴.

³⁸⁰ Edzard, 1997: 97; ETCSL 2.1.7; Mirelman, 2014: 158; CDLI P431882 and Elli, 2015: 444 (see the introduction for full quotations).

³⁸¹ Ledent, 2009: 1 about the origins of concerts in Europe. FM 9, p. 19 has some reflections about this topic with focus on the city of Mari during the Old Babylonian Period.

³⁸² See Crocker, 2011 for a recent reflection on this aspect. Personally, we are open-minded to the possibility of the existence of polyphony in Mesopotamia. The reason is that we have the remains of an *aulos*-type instrument from that culture, the “Silver Ur Pipes”, dated around 2450 BCE (see Lawergren, 2000 for reference). That instrument is able to produce two independent sounds at the same time. In any case, as Dahlia Shehata wisely said to us, due to our so scarce evidence for Mesopotamian music theory, we can neither affirm nor deny the existence of polyphony in Mesopotamia at the time.

³⁸³ Perhaps one of these drums had snares and it could have a sort of “pitch” like some of the drums of a Japanese *taiko* drum ensemble. In any case, we would still deal with un-pitched percussion instruments (they produce a concrete note, so they do not have “pitch”), and we cannot confirm the existence of snares in the Mesopotamian drums. Many thanks to Stephanie Lynn Budin for the reference to the Japanese *taiko* instruments.

³⁸⁴ For previous translations, Thureau-Dangin, 1907: 137; Price, 1927: 52; Krispijn, 1990: 2; Krispijn, 1998: 50; Suter, 2000: 398; Sánchez Muñoz, 2016: 205 (see the introduction to this text for full quotations).

2.3. The Ur III Period

2.3.1. Music and Weaving in a text from Šulgi's reign

2.3.1.1. Introduction

We have many texts dealing with musicians³⁸⁵ and instruments³⁸⁶ during the Ur III Period (2111–2003 BCE). In addition, new abstract terms with the prefix **nam-** are known in the Ur III Period³⁸⁷. In this sense, the term **nam-nar** certainly had to be in use at the time. However, as far as we know, there are certain references to **nam-nar** only in one text from Umma (modern Tell al-Yoḥa, Iraq). This text is about the redistribution of barley, oil, lard, and wool rations for several workers from Umma³⁸⁸, an important provincial centre of the state created by the 3rd Dynasty of Ur³⁸⁹. Here is our excerpt:

Text 5. Nisaba 11 33 [BM 104768] (Šulgi 36-11-00)³⁹⁰

r. i 3. **P**nin-ezem
r. i 4. **P**geme₂-^{d2}’**dumu-zi-’da**’
r. i 5. **lu₂ šu nu-BAD/UŠ₂³⁹¹-a-me**

³⁸⁵ Michalowski, 2006, Pruzsinszky, 2007; Pruzsinszky, 2010a; Pruzsinszky, 2010b; Pruzsinszky, 2013; Pruzsinszky, 2015: 29–31; Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 97, 99–100, 107–111; Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 48–50.

³⁸⁶ Rašid, 1984: 66–73; Michalowski, 2010a: 222; Michalowski, 2010b: 120–123.

³⁸⁷ In fact, we have many terms of this type only documented in the Ur III Period according to ePSD2: **nam-agar₄-ni₂in₂** (“office as **agar₄-ni₂in₂** official”); **nam-lu₂azlag₂** (“function as **azlag₂** fuller”); **nam-e-ge₄-a** (“*status* as bride”); **nam-egir-er-in-na** (“*status* of the one behind other workers(?)”); **nam-enku** (“office of **enku** tax-collector”); **nam-gab₂-us₂** (“function as **gab₂-us₂** shepherd”); **nam-lu₂-gi-na-ab-tum** (“*status* as being guaranteed”); **nam-lu₂-la-ga** (“*status* of a cattle rustler”); **nam-lu₂-pi-lu-sa-da** (“ritualist’s art(?)”); **nam-mi₂-us₂-sa₂** (“*status* son-in-law”); **nam-ni₂ir-si** (“*status* as friend(?)”); **nam-u₄-da-tuš** (“office as **u₄-da-tuš** bear trainer”); **nam-uru₄(-a)** (“sowing”).

³⁸⁸ Nisaba 11, p. 1–2, 142.

³⁸⁹ Sallaberger, 2013: 227–230.

³⁹⁰ Edition dependent upon BDTNS 057430 with corrections derived from the inspection of the photo available on that database. We collated this manuscript in the British Museum on 01/08/2019. Thanks to Abraham H. Jagersma who read an earlier version of our analysis of this text, and helped us to prevent several significant mistakes about the sense of this text.

³⁹¹ According to our collation, this sign seems like the BAD on some parts of *Šulgi A*, manuscript S (= see aBZL 25 for context). Therefore, we agree with the original transliteration of this text. In any case, since BDTNS 057430 and CDLI 201735 are based on the presence of the similar sign UŠ₂, we include this sign

r. i 6. **nam-nar i3-in-^rge4**³⁹²
 r. i 7. **pa4-a-pa4-a**³⁹³
 r. i 8. **tab'-la-zu**
 r. i 9. **nam-nar-ta 'ib2`-/ta-^re3`**
 r. i 10. **uš-bar i3-in-ge4**

r. i 3. Nin-Ezem
 r. i 4. (and) Geme-Dumuzida,
 r. i 5. who were not [...],
 r. i 6. they returned (into) the music.
 r. i 7. Pāpā
 r. i 8. (and) Tablazu
 r. i 9. left the music
 r. i 10. (and) returned to the weaving

This text has been studied by several scholars³⁹⁴, the most important being Regine Pruzsinszky. She has commented on this text several times³⁹⁵ as a part of her research about the social *status* of musicians in Mesopotamian history. About this text, she has noted how several **nar munus** attached to the temple of the god Šara received barley allotments because they return or leave the weaving or **nam-nar**. Regine Pruzsinszky translated **nam-nar**³⁹⁶ as “singing”³⁹⁷ or “music”³⁹⁸ without any translation of the type

here. See *infra* for our discussion about the sense of this expression and the correct transliteration. For problems with the sign BAD in the 3rd millennium, see Steinkeller, 1981: 21–24.

³⁹² BDTNS 057430 reads “nam-nar-ni in-gi4” and “uš-bar-ni in-gi4”. However, Nisaba 11 33 (the *editio princeps*) has “nam-nar ì-in-gi4” and “uš-bar ì-in-gi4”. This difference is based on two different readings of the sign NI: **ni** and **i3**. Several editions agree with the original edition and have **i3-in-gi/e4** like Pruzsinszky, 2013: 42; CDLI P201735 and ePSD2. It is also the case of Lafont, 2016: 158. However, his translation seems like the one we might offer starting from BDTNS transliteration. We agree also with the original edition. Certainly, abstract nouns in Sumerian belong to the non-human gender. Therefore, they use the 3NH.POSS {**be**}, and not the 3SG.POSS {**ne**} for human nouns (DGS, p. 103). In the same way, the chain **i3-in** + verbal stem is explained by DGS, p. 25 as a usual complete writing of the VP {**i**}.

³⁹³ Previous editions have **pas(PAP.E)-pas**. However, that sign E is actually the sign A. That makes sense since there was no other mention to a person in Mesopotamia whose name was spelled **pas-pas**. About the female name **pa4-pa4**, see Foxvog, 2011: 85 n. 118, 92, 94, 96.

³⁹⁴ Lafont, 2016: 158; Gabbay, 2014a: 63 n. 2.

³⁹⁵ Pruzsinszky, 2007: 343 n. 43; Pruzsinszky, 2013: 34 n. 16, and 42; Pruzsinszky, 2015: 29; Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 108; Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50. All these references are indicated at the site of this text in BDTNS 057430.

³⁹⁶ She left this term untranslated in Pruzsinszky, 2007: 343 n. 43 (“nam-nar”).

³⁹⁷ Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50 (“from the singing/music to the weaving mill”).

³⁹⁸ Pruzsinszky, 2013: 42 (“the music”) and perhaps Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 108 (“ejercicio de la música”), although this expression is only indirectly referred to in our Text 5.

“office of the **nar**” as other authors have done³⁹⁹. In order to elucidate the meaning of **nam-nar** in this text, we propose a biographical outline of the four women of this text. We propose also an approach to the not yet considered chain **lu₂ šu nu-BAD/UŠ₂-a-me** (r. i 5)⁴⁰⁰ and the term **uš-bar** to which our term **nam-nar** is compared in this instance.

2.3.1.2. Biographical outline of the females mentioned in this text

2.3.1.2.1. Nin-Ezem (**Pnin-ezem**) (r. i 3)

Beyond some undated documents⁴⁰¹, Nin-Ezem is currently attested in the Ur III text *corpus* of Umma from the 32nd year of Šulgi’s reign until the first years of the reign of Ibbī-Suen (2028–2003 BCE). In our earliest records of her, she is mentioned together with other workers of the temple of Šara (the tutelary deity of Umma)⁴⁰² as a daughter (**dumu**) of Geme-Iškur (**geme₂-d³iškur**), probably a weaver (**geme₂-uš-bar**)⁴⁰³. Therefore, she had to be a weaver at some point⁴⁰⁴. However, she had to act as musician before the date of our Text 5, since she does not enter (**kur₉**), but “returns” (**ge₄**) to **nam-nar**. Moreover, she will be attested several times as **nar**⁴⁰⁵ from that point⁴⁰⁶. In fact, music

³⁹⁹ Gabbay, 2014a: 63 n. 2 (“nar service”); Lafont, 2016: 158 (“their function of musician”).

⁴⁰⁰ Pruzsinszky, 2013: 42 skipped this line in its edition of this excerpt.

⁴⁰¹ Nisaba 6 12 [BM 106051] (0000-00-00), o. v 6 (BDTNS 057977); YOS 15 118 [Private owner] (00-00-00), o. i 5 and r. ii 3 (BDTNS 187632).

⁴⁰² Nisaba 6 27 [BM 106043] (Šulgi 32-05-00), r. iv 12 (BDTNS 057970).

⁴⁰³ It is complicated to know her *status* by that exact date because her mention in TCNU 702 [MAT 702] (Šulgi 35-01-00), o. ii 3 (BDTNS 038521) is in a fragmentary context. Moreover, SAT 2 189 [YBC 11209] (Šulgi 38-00-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 048374) is about the return of a quantity of barley. However, in YOS 18 100 [CUL 9] (00-05³-00), o. 3 (BDTNS 034735), she works in the manufacture of a garment (**tug²bar-duls**). In the same way, she is a **geme₂-uš-bar** in Nisaba 15/2 1031 [Unknown] (00-00-00), o. ii’ 15’ (BDTNS 193292) and Nisaba 15/2 1032 [Unknown] (00-00-00), o. ii 24 (BDTNS 193293). That last *status* is confirmed by Nisaba 15/2 668 [Private owner] (Ibbī-Suen 01-00-00), o. ii 22 (BDTNS 193119).

⁴⁰⁴ Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50 said that Nin-Ezem was **nar munus** in Nisaba 6 27 [BM 106043] (Šulgi 32-05-00). However, **nar** are only mentioned in r. v 9–15.

⁴⁰⁵ Rochester 166 [Crozer 83] (Šulgi 44-00-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 034555); SNAT 377 [BM 106086] (Amar-Suena 07-00-00), r. i 2 (BDTNS 033841); STA 15 [PUL Ex. 833] (Ibbī-Suen 02-12-00), r. ii 15 (BDTNS 006149).

⁴⁰⁶ Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 108 says that musicians seem not to have received a specific training. However, since Nin-Ezem was **nar** for a long part of her life, she had to have received some training. In our opinion,

seems to have been her main job before her death⁴⁰⁷. In any case, she will also be attested as “personnel” (**ḡiri₃-se₃-ga**) of milling⁴⁰⁸ and as a weaver (**geme₂ uš-bar**)⁴⁰⁹ before that.

2.3.1.2.2. Geme-Dumuzida (**ḡeme₂-^ddumu-zi-da**) (r. i 4)

Beyond some undated texts⁴¹⁰, we have records from Umma about Geme-Dumuzida from the 25th year of Šulgi’s reign (2069 BCE) until the third year of the reign of Ibbī-Suen (2026 BCE). Before her “return to the music” of our Text 5, she seems to have performed several tasks, such as the transport of garments⁴¹¹ or work at the milling for Šara’s temple⁴¹². She had to act in any case as **nar** before the date of our Text 5, since, like Nin-Ezem, she “returns” (**ge₄**)— not “enters” (**kur₉**)— to **nam-nar**. However, we do not know when and how⁴¹³. After that “return” to **nam-nar**, she had to act as **nar** at a certain time. However, we currently know just one text mentioning her more or less explicitly as musician⁴¹⁴. In fact, it is difficult to know her professional life since some texts from Umma talk about a Geme-Dumuzida working as **lukur** priestess⁴¹⁵. However,

she could receive that training during the four years between the year of Nisaba 6 27 [BM 106043] (Šulgi 32-05-00), r. iv 12 (BDTNS 057970) and our Text 5 (dated to the 36th year of Šulgi’s reign).

⁴⁰⁷ Nebraska 49 [OPL 45] (00-00-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 015304). Keeping in mind the dates where Nin-Ezem is attested, we could date this tablet from the third year of Ibbī-Suen’s reign onward.

⁴⁰⁸ Nisaba 24 28 [BM 110122] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00), o. ii 37–o. iii 2 (BDTNS 069075); SAT 3 1708 [YBC 1166] (Šu-Suen 06-00-00), o. 3 (BDTNS 049891); STA 14 [PUL Ex. 835] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00), o. i 12, r. ii 4 (BDTNS 006148); STA 16 [PUL Ex. 665] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00), o. i 9, r. i 22 (BDTNS 006150); NYPL 120 [NYPLC 205] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00), o. i 9, r. i 23 (BDTNS 021779); Rochester 159 [Crozer 76] (Ibbī-Suen 03-04-00), o. i 17, r. ii 17–18: (BDTNS 034548); Nisaba 11 18 [BM 104752] (Ibbī-Suen 03²-03-00), o. i 14 (BDTNS 057414).

⁴⁰⁹ MVN 20 81 [Erm. 4040] (Ibbī-Suen 02-00-00), r. 1, 6–7 (BDTNS 044893).

⁴¹⁰ BIN 5 301 [NBC 1424] (00-00-00), r. 31 (BDTNS 009885); Nebraska 45 [OPL ---] (00-00-00), o. ii 34 (BDTNS 015300).

⁴¹¹ Ontario 2 488 [ROM 925.62.8] (Šulgi 25-00-00), o. 8 (BDTNS 060591).

⁴¹² Nisaba 6 27 [BM 106043] (Šulgi 32-05-00), o. vi 21, 32, o. viii 9, r. v 1 (BDTNS 057970) and Owen and Wasilewska, 2000: 15, text 57 [ASM 12054] (Šulgi 32-09-00), o. iv 14’, r. ii 12, r. iv 4 (professional occupation) (BDTNS 047746).

⁴¹³ See *supra* for our comment against the interpretation of Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50.

⁴¹⁴ YOS 15 115 [PM 19] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00), o. iii 31, o. iv 16 (BDTNS 187630).

⁴¹⁵ AAICAB 1/1, pl. 166 [Ashm. 1911-480] (Šulgi 42-00-00) o. ii 15, r. i 13, r. i 6, r. ii 14-15 (BDTNS 038668); AAICAB 1/2, pl. 166 [Ashm. 1975-293] (Amar-Suena 02-09-00), o. ii 14 and 17, r. ii 5 (BDTNS

other texts refer to Geme-Dumuzida working as a (forced) labourer (**geme₂**) attached to a brewery⁴¹⁶ or the mill⁴¹⁷.

Which of these two women was our **nar munus** Geme-Dumuzida? The **lukur gal** (the chief **lukur** priestess) of Umma was associated with the **balaj** lyre⁴¹⁸. However, while **lukur** priestesses used to live in a cloister, and they could not be slaves⁴¹⁹, female **nar** used to work in the weaving mill as a part-time work⁴²⁰. One example is the previously noted with Nin-Ezem. In this sense, we should connect the Geme-Dumuzida who entered “into the music” with the one who worked as forced labourer, and not with the **lukur** priestess despite the musical connections of that profession.

2.3.1.2.3. Pāpā (**pa₄-a-pa₄-a**) and Tablazu (**ptab-la-zu**) (r. i 7–8)

There is less information about the women of this document abandoning music to return as weavers than for the women previously addressed. Certainly, concerning Pāpā (**pa₄-a-pa₄-a**), our mentions of her are a bit uncertain⁴²¹.

158352); Nisaba 26 10 [BM 110149] (Amar-Suena 05-06-00), o. ii 9-10, 16, r. ii 11 (BDTNS 069099); Nisaba 23 24 [BM 110237] (Amar-Suena 05-06-00), o. ii 12, 18, r. ii 6 (BDTNS 069184); Nisaba 23 36 [BM 110272] (Amar-Suena 06²-00-00), o. ii 7, 14, r. ii 12 (BDTNS 069218); Mycenaean, p. 217 no. 7 [Ashm. 1924-668] (Šu-Suen 02-00-00), o. ii 20, r. i 16 and r. ii 7 (BDTNS 038739); NYPL 120 [NYPLC 205] (Ibbi-Suen 02-02-00), r. i 12 (BDTNS 021779). In addition, Nisaba 6 12 [BM 106051] (00-00-00) (BDTNS 057977) and AnOr 7 296 [MM 190] (00-00-00), o. ii 16 and r. ii 9 (BDTNS 008166).

⁴¹⁶ MVN 21 238 [Erm. 14487] (Amar-Suena 08-06-00), o. 4, 7 (BDTNS 046040).

⁴¹⁷ SET 274 [RC 929] (Amar-Suena 02-00-00), r. ii 5 (BDTNS 014195; see Englund, 1991: 273 n. 27, and 278 n. 37; Steinkeller, 2001: 37 n. 55; Englund, 2002: 2 for interpretation); Nisaba 24 28 [BM 110122] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00), o. ii 23–25 (BDTNS 069075). See BPOA 7 2401 [NBC 3641] (Amar-Suena 07-01-00), o. 1–2, 5–r. 2 (BDTNS 076756), and MVN 21 240 [Erm. 8087] (Šu-Suen 05-05-00), o. 4, r. 1–3 (BDTNS 046042) for other possible professional activities of Geme-Dumuzida as **geme₂**.

⁴¹⁸ UTI 4 2849 [Ist. Um 2849] (Šu-Suen 02-00-00), o. 6: 2 **kuš** ^{u₂}**hab₂** 1/3 **ma-na še-gin₃ balaj lukur-gal si-ga** (BDTNS 045587) “Two pieces of ^{u₂}**hab₂** leather and 1/3 minas of glue (for) the **balaj** lyre of the clear chief priestess **lukur**”. Dahlia Shehata (2009: 99 n. 526) applied the adjective **gal** to the instrument. However, **gal** is placed after **lukur**, not **balaj**. She commented on this excerpt since the **balaj** and the **lukur** also seem to have been connected during the Old Babylonian Period.

⁴¹⁹ Stol, 2016: 584.

⁴²⁰ Pruzsinszky, 2013: 39.

⁴²¹ See Nisaba 26 80 [BM 110247] (Amar-Suena 05-00-00), o. i 4 (BDTNS 069194) and BPOA 1 1364 [BM 107713] (Ibbi-Suen 02-01-05), o. 6 (BDTNS 059071) for evidence.

About Tablazu, we have an undated document⁴²² perhaps dealing with a different person to our woman musician/weaver⁴²³. Apart from that, we have several texts from the last years of Šulgi’s reign and the beginnings of Šu-Suen’s reign (2037–2029 BCE). In our first attestation of Tablazu (dated before our Text 5), she was a **nar munus** of Šara’s temple⁴²⁴. After the date of our Text 5, she should have left the music, but she will receive rations in the next years as **nar munus**⁴²⁵.

2.3.1.3. Lexicographical approach to some complex expressions/terms

2.3.1.3.1. **lu₂ šu nu-BAD/UŠ₂-a-me**

In the *editio princeps* of this text, this expression was transliterated as “lú šu nu-BAD-a-me”⁴²⁶. However, some years later, Manuel Molina collated the tablet⁴²⁷ and saw in that manuscript the sign UŠ₂ and not BAD. In consequence, he transliterated this chain as **lu₂ šu nu-uš₂-a-me** for CDLI and **lu₂ šu nu-ug₇-a-me** for BDTNS⁴²⁸.

Both readings of UŠ₂ (**uš₂** and **ug₇**) are forms of the verb **uš₂**. According to Pascal Attinger⁴²⁹, **ug₇** would act as a plural base of that verb which always meant “to die”, and not “to kill”, during the Ur III Period. The form **uš₂** would be the singular base of said verb. Concerning our excerpt, we should keep in mind that this **lu₂ šu nu-BAD/UŠ₂-a-me** is referred to two people (Nin-Ezem and Geme-Dumuzida). That is confirmed by the

⁴²² Nisaba 6 12 [BM 106051] (00-00-00), o. iv 12 (BDTNS 057977).

⁴²³ AAICAB 1/4, pl. 262 [Bod. S 379] (Šu-Suen 02-04-12), r. 1–4 (BDTNS 166093) mentions a Tablazu having the condition of KA-**us₂-sa₂**, a profession sometimes associated with the secretary (**sukkal**) and the “court messengers/officials” (Johnson, 2006: 4). Bertrand Lafont, with the Manuel Molina’s advice, considered it to be a dialectal variant of the term **aga₃-us₂**. That term would refer to a similar profession as the French *gendarme* (Lafont, 2009: 10 n. 62). That is, it has nothing in common with a **nar**. Moreover, rations delivered to this Tablazu are more varied than those given to women like the Tablazu of our study.

⁴²⁴ TCNU 702 [MAT 702] (Šulgi 35-01-00), o. ii 23, r. ii 19-21 (BDTNS 038521).

⁴²⁵ Nisaba 26 80 [BM 110247] (Amar-Suena 05-00-00), o. i 1–2, o. ii 17, r. ii 1–2 (BDTNS 069194); YOS 15 115 [PM 19] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00), o. ii 10–15, 21 (BDTNS 187630).

⁴²⁶ Nisaba 11, p. 145.

⁴²⁷ Collation on 2010 (*editio princeps* is from 2006). See BDTNS 057430 for reference.

⁴²⁸ CDLI P201735 (originally “lu₂ szu nu-usz₂-a-me”) and BDTNS 057430 respectively.

⁴²⁹ Attinger, 2011. See also Bauer, 1970: 188–189; Steinkeller, 1979: 55 n. 4; Thomsen, 1984: 136; Krecher, 1985: 142–143, n. 25; ELS, p. 190; Volk, 1995: 208 n. 995; DGS, p. 315.

enclitic plural particle **-me(š)** of that expression. In consequence, we should dismiss the transliteration **lu₂ šu nu-uš₂-a-me** since it has a grammatical contradiction.

In any case, the presence of a verb meaning “to die” does not make sense. Certainly, the verbal base in this text is not **uš₂**, but ***šu uš₂**. That verbal form has never been taken into consideration in previous studies on Sumerian compound verbs implying a part of the human body as in this case (**šu** means “hand”)⁴³⁰. Certainly, **šu uš₂** is actually a later form⁴³¹ of the expression known in Old Babylonian times as **šu nam-uš₂** (literally, “the hand (of) the death”)⁴³². It is true that we have sentences of the type **šu** + name of an animal (a donkey, **anše**, or an ox, **gu₄**) + **ba-uš₂** (“it has been killed”) in several texts from the Ur III Period⁴³³. However, **šu** is not actually connected to **uš₂** in those contexts. Far from that, it seems to describe the killed animal as “old”⁴³⁴.

In this sense, we are forced to use the original transliteration **lu₂ šu nu-BAD-a-me**. In fact, in our collation of this tablet, we have seen that the controversial sign seems like the sign BAD from a line of text S of the hymn *Šulgi A*⁴³⁵. Nevertheless, how should we understand this expression? According to Abraham H. Jagersma⁴³⁶, we should read the sign BAD as **bad** or **ba₉** in order to obtain the verbal form **/šu ba.r/** (“to release”)⁴³⁷. But, what is its sense in our text? It is actually a bit difficult to be precise since, as we have seen, we do not know the exact profession of the two women referred to with this **lu₂ šu nu-BAD-a-me** (Nin-Ezem and Geme-Dumuzida) at the date of our Text 5. The same happens with the years before the facts of our Text 5. In any case, we suppose that this expression was saying that Nin-Ezem and Geme-Dumuzida were (still) not released from their provisional duties in another work to the one designed with **nam-nar**. Perhaps, we

⁴³⁰ Karahashi, 2000: 172.

⁴³¹ **Udug ħul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, IV 125 (Geller, 2016: 155).

⁴³² *Death of Nannā*, 66–67 (ETCSL 5.5.2).

⁴³³ About **šu anše**: AAICAB 1/1, pl. 20 [Ashm. 1911-160] (Šu-Suen 02-09-00), o. 1 (BDTNS 038590). About **šu gu₄**: SANTAG 6 178 [Erm. 18768] (Amar-Suena 07-07-00), o. 4: (BDTNS 047977); BPOA 2 2318 [BM 112068] (Šu-Suen 04-00-00), o. 1 (BDTNS 070921), BPOA 6 137 [YBC 13653] (Šu-Suen 02-10-00), o. 1 (BDTNS 166366).

⁴³⁴ Genouillac, 1924: 37; Oppenheim, 1948: 69, 150; Englund, 2003: 2; Stepień, 2006: 27.

⁴³⁵ *Šulgi A*, manuscript S (= see aBZL 25 for context).

⁴³⁶ Personal communication. Many thanks for this helpful remark which we shall try to expand and comment critically on here.

⁴³⁷ See DGS, p. 328 (4); 329 (10); 332 (27); 422 (31a-b); 427 (42); 440 (111a-b and 112); 484 (96–97); 560 (57a-b); 561 (60); 712 (199) for some Ur III texts containing this expression.

might have here an indirect reference to the work of Nin-Ezem in the weaving and to Geme-Dumuzida in the mill (**kinkin**) as we have previously noted.

2.3.1.3.2. **uš-bar**

Dietz Otto Edzard said that the etymology of **uš-bar** was relatively uncertain, and that **uš-bar** was not an abstract noun⁴³⁸. That fits with its lack of prefix **nam-**⁴³⁹ and/or its origins from a verbal form⁴⁴⁰. However, its connotations are relatively wide. Certainly, it designates a profession, but also it may refer to a type of garment (always with the determinative **tug²**) such as the **tug²(saḡ-)uš-bar**⁴⁴¹. It might have even acted as an “adjective”. In fact, the expression **e₂ uš-bar** (“house” + “weaving” without genitive = “textile mill”) is more frequently attested in Ur III texts than **e₂ uš-bar-ra** (perhaps “textile mill”, but mainly “house of the weaver”, with a GEN {**ak**} connecting **e₂** and **uš-bar**)⁴⁴². Therefore, we might understand **uš-bar** as an abstract noun *non de nomine sed de facto* dealing with the world of (physically hard⁴⁴³) weaving with all its steps⁴⁴⁴.

This matter is important for dealing with another debatable aspect of this term **uš-bar**: its exclusive reference (or not) to the feminine world. Certainly, although some people have translated this term as “weaver”⁴⁴⁵ (as in the previous translations of our Text 5)⁴⁴⁶,

⁴³⁸ Edzard, 1963: 34.

⁴³⁹ The term **nam-ušbar** (UR₂×NUN, not ***nam-uš(UŠ)-bar**(BAR)) means something like “status of father-in-law” (ePSD2 definition).

⁴⁴⁰ De-adjectival nouns could act as abstract nouns without prefix **nam-** (DGS, p. 281–283).

⁴⁴¹ See García Ventura, 2012a: 97 for descriptions of **tug²uš-bar** and **tug²saḡ-uš-bar**.

⁴⁴² See BDTNS and ePSD2 for evidence. In addition, see DGS, p. 118 for “the left-headed noun-noun compounds” in Sumerian like **e₂ uš-bar**.

⁴⁴³ García Ventura, 2012a: 234.

⁴⁴⁴ For the weaving process, Waetzoldt, 1972: 138–140; García Ventura, 2012a: 81–101.

⁴⁴⁵ Edzard, 1963: 33 (“Weber”); Cocquerillat, 1972–1975: 102 (“tisserand”); Hübner and Reizammer, 1985: 1147 (“Weber”); ePSD (“weaver”); DGS, p. 118 (“**geme₂ uš-bar** ‘weaver maid’ (< **geme₂** ‘slave woman’ and **uš-bar** ‘weaver’)); Foxvog, 2016a: 70 (“weaver”).

⁴⁴⁶ Pruzsinszky, 2007: 343 n. 43 and Pruzsinszky, 2015: 29 (“Tätigkeit in der Weberei”); Pruzsinszky, 2013: 42 (“the weaving (mill)”; Gabbay, 2014a: 63 n. 2 and Lafont, 2014: 108 (“weavers”); Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 108 (“industria textil”); Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50 (“the weaving mill”). It is interesting to note that *Weberei* in German (at least, according to our modest proficiency in this language) alludes to two different English words: “weaving” (= action of weaving) and “weaving mill” (= place where weaving takes place).

other people have translated it as “female weaver”⁴⁴⁷. However, this last translation does not keep in mind that Sumerian language does not make distinctions between masculine and feminine gender⁴⁴⁸. Moreover, there are references to **juruš uš-bar** (“male weaver/worker of the weaving”)⁴⁴⁹ in addition to **uš-bar** or **gemez/munus uš-bar**.

2.3.1.4. Sense of **nam-nar** in this excerpt

Translations of this term of the type “office of the **nar**”⁴⁵⁰ make sense in this context. Certainly, we deal with, at least, three women working at some point as musicians (we know little about Pāpā, so we cannot intuit her professional occupation). However, we have also noted before that **uš-bar** seems to designate the world of weaving *lato sensu*: the weaver, but also some garments, and even the space for the activity of weaving.

The terms **uš-bar** and **nam-nar** are equated in our text as the former and new offices of Pāpā and Tablazu. In this sense, like **uš-bar**, we should perceive **nam-nar** also as a larger reality not only pertaining to the office of musician. Therefore, we follow to Regine Pruzsinszky in her translations of this term as “singing”⁴⁵¹ and “music”⁴⁵².

Translation as “singing” might fit well in this context for two reasons. On the one hand, we are dealing with four women working not only in musical activities, but also in other hard labours such as weaving or milling. It is well-known around the world that the use of songs alleviates fatigue during the performance of hard and repetitive work, such as the aforementioned weaving and milling⁴⁵³. In this sense, since they probably sang during their work time, they would certainly have obtained a certain musical training (at least at an *amateur* level) as a consequence of that practice. Therefore, they could shift at

⁴⁴⁷ Waetzoldt, 1972: 42 n. 27, 92 n. 9 and 94 n. 50 (but not in page 14, where he translated **gemez-uš-bar** as “Weberin”), Maekawa, 1980: 81; Neumann, 2004: 24 and ETCSL Glossary (“female weaver” although also “weaver”); and Sallaberger, 2006: 694 (“Weberin”). In any case, Harmut Waetzoldt (1972: 92 n. 9 and 94 n. 50) expressed that this term could allude also to a collective of male and female weavers.

⁴⁴⁸ Kraus, 1990: 150; García Ventura, 2012a: 94, 105, 115–116, 262; García Ventura, 2012b: 26–27.

⁴⁴⁹ UET 3 1449 [U. 3600] (Ibbī-Suen 07-10-00), r. ii 16 (CDLI P137774).

⁴⁵⁰ Gabbay, 2014a: 63 n. 2 (“nar service”); Lafont, 2016: 158 (“their function of musician”).

⁴⁵¹ Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 50 (“from the singing/music to the weaving mill”).

⁴⁵² Pruzsinszky, 2013: 42; Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 108 (“ejercicio de la música”).

⁴⁵³ For different examples of connections between music and weaving around the world, see Dilley, 1992: 77; Willson Aedo, 1992: 18; Lamphere, 1992: 92; Reichard, 1997; Kelly, 1997: 14; Korczynski, Pickering and Robertson, 2013: 47; Andrés-Toledo, 2016.

some point to musical activities in the temple, performing those activities at an acceptable level. On the other hand, the god Šara is known in Old Babylonian times as a reciter ((**lu**₂) **du**₁₁-**ga**) of **en**₃-**du** songs⁴⁵⁴, and we have some information⁴⁵⁵ about the performance of **ser**₃ songs and **bal-bal-e** responsorial chants in his honour⁴⁵⁶.

However, we are not currently dealing with the Old Babylonian Period. In fact, we should not rule out the existence of possible changes in the elements used for Šara’s cult at that time concerning the Ur III Period. In fact, we have some Ur III references to instruments used in the cult of Šara in his temple at Umma, like the **a**₂-**la**₂ giant drum⁴⁵⁷, the **li-li-is**₂ kettledrum, and the **ub**₅ frame drum⁴⁵⁸. It seems improbable that a woman could have played the **a**₂-**la**₂ or the **li-li-is**₂ since, according to the iconography, they are normally played by men⁴⁵⁹. However, females could play the **ub**₅ frame drum since we have other women playing that instrument in the Ur III texts⁴⁶⁰. That agrees with our Ur III iconography⁴⁶¹. In fact, women also played the **ma-ri**₂-**tum** lyre⁴⁶² and the **neš-tigidla**(ŠAG₄.TAR)⁴⁶³. Moreover, we have a text from Umma dealing with a long list of **nar nita**₂ and **nar munus** from the “house of the **balan** lyre” (**nar e**₂-**balan-me**)⁴⁶⁴. Furthermore, we should say that, at least from our knowledge, terms referring to singing

⁴⁵⁴ *Inanna’s Descent*, 335 (Attinger, 2019c: 62).

⁴⁵⁵ There is also a hymn for the Šara’s temple of Umma in *Temple Hymns*, 303–314, ETCSL 4.80.1).

⁴⁵⁶ The hymn *Šara A* = Sjöberg, 1975: 322 [CBS 10222] is defined in its colophon (r. 6’) as [**bal**]-**bal-e** **neš-šara**₂-**’kam**’ (CDLI P265461 with minor corrections derived from our inspection of the manuscript photo available in that site). Before that, line r. 3’ has **ser**₃-**zu** (“your **ser**₃ song”) in reference to this deity.

⁴⁵⁷ CDLI P218067 [WAM 2000.47] (Amar-Suena 05-00-00), o. i 32 (BDTNS 158254). See Mirelman, 2014: 154-155 for reference.

⁴⁵⁸ BPOA 7 1559 [NBC 1516] (Amar-Suena 04-00-00), r. 4–5 (BDTNS 075735).

⁴⁵⁹ See Rašid, 1984: 68–73 for (Ur III) iconography of the **a**₂-**la**₂ and 78–79 for the **li-li-is**₂ (it is an Old Babylonian plaque since, unfortunately, we do not have earlier depictions of kettledrums).

⁴⁶⁰ TUT 159 [VAT 2330] (Amar-Suena 01-05-00), o. v 25 (BDTNS 000509) The musician is called **i**₃-**na-na**. We are not sure if this pertains to a woman, but people mentioned in next lines seem to be women, so it seems probable. Other texts about that are STA 4 [PUL Ex. 183] (Amar-Suena 01-05-00), r. i 19 (BDTNS 006138; as a personal name); Atiqot 4 7–9 [IMJ 90.24.61] (Amar-Suena 05-04-00), o. ii 9 (BDTNS 014617; as personal name).

⁴⁶¹ Spycket, 1972: 180–181; Rašid, 1984: 96–97; Dumbrill, 2005: 373–382.

⁴⁶² AUCT 1 942 [AUAM 73.724] (Amar-Suena 02-00-00), o. 8 (BDTNS 027384).

⁴⁶³ PDT 2 1120 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 04-02-00), o. 7 (BDTNS 031251). It is rather indirect evidence, since the text just mentions a **nar munus** together with several **lu**₂ **neš-tigidla** musicians.

⁴⁶⁴ YOS 15 119 [Missouri 8] (00-00-00), o. 13 (BDTNS 187633).

are not very common in the Ur III texts⁴⁶⁵. In this sense, we cannot make abundant comments about this topic.

The phenomenon of women instrumentalists acting as weavers might not come exclusively from the Ur III Period. Certainly, some texts from Mari talk about the selection of women from a group of weavers so as to instruct and appoint them to the “Subarean ensemble (*šitrum*)”⁴⁶⁶. In that musical ensemble, female musicians used to play the *šebītum* harp⁴⁶⁷, but perhaps, they also could sing⁴⁶⁸. Therefore, we would define **nam-nar** in our Text 5 as “music”. In our opinion, Nin-Ezem, Geme-Dumzida, Pāpā and Tablazu could not only sing but also play some instruments as musicians.

⁴⁶⁵ ePSD2 gives two results for **ser₃** in Ur III times: *Šu-Suen* 9 [E3/2.1.4.9], xii 12 (Frayne, 1997: 318; the text referred to a pure **ser₃** song, **ser₃ ku₃**) and UTI 5 3152 [Ist. Um 3152] (Amar-Suena 09-00-00), r. 3. BDTNS 050558 reads as **keš₂** instead of **ser₃**, which fits better in this context. Certainly, the **ma₂-la₂** mentioned at the beginning of that line is a freight boat and **keš₂-ra** (nominal form of **keše₂** “to bind”) would suggest something attached in that boat. About **en₃-du**, see BPOA 10 558 [YBC 13384] (00-00-00), o. 3’ (BDTNS 191980; commented by Pruzsinszky, 2013: 38) and Delaporte, 1911: 192 text 14 [NME H94673] (Amar-Suena 08-11-00), o. 3 (BDTNS 002145; noted by Pruzsinszky, 2007: 341 n. 39).

⁴⁶⁶ ARM 10 126 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 8–r. 5 (Archibab T8687) and ARM 10 125 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 4–r. 4 (Archibab T8688). Moreover, some *nārtu* musicians and weavers are mentioned in FM 9 31 [A.3683] (Šamšī-Addu, 00-00-00), o. 6–10 (Archibab T6590). See Pruzsinszky, 2007: 343 n. 43 for comments on these texts and other from Nuzi and the Ottoman harems.

⁴⁶⁷ See our chapter about texts from Mari for identification.

⁴⁶⁸ See FM 9, p. 13–14 for comments.

2.3.2. A reference to **nam-nar** in TRU 41 [ICP 41] (Šulgi 41-00-00), r. 5?

We would now like to turn our attention to another text also dated to Šulgi's reign. This text, however, comes from Puzriš-Dagān (modern Drehem). Unlike the Umma of our Text 5, the archives of Puzriš-Dagān contained texts from the main institutions of the entire kingdom, and not from a single province like Umma⁴⁶⁹. Here is our next text:

Text 6. TRU 41 [ICP 41] (Šulgi 41-08-00)⁴⁷⁰

- o. 1 *Par-bi-tum*⁴⁷¹
o. 2 **Pa-ti-ma-tum**
o. 3 **Pu₃-be₂**
o. 4 **Paš-da-ga**
o. 5 **Šul-gi-tu^{ri}-ri**
o. 6 *Ki-ni-ib-ši*
o. 7 **Ma-ma-šar-ra-at**
r. 1 **AN-na-a**
r. 2 **{1/2}ša-lim-nu^{ri}-ri šu bar-ra**⁴⁷³
r. 3 **na-na-ki-ga-ga**
r. 4 Anepigraphic space
r. 5 **<nam>-nar-ta-gur-ra**
r. 6 **eš₃-eš₃ u₄-sakar**⁴⁷⁴-ka
r. 7 *u-bar-um* **ugula-uš-bar i₃-dab₅**

^{r. 6} By the **eš₃-eš₃** festivals of the New Moon, ^{r. 7} Ubārum, supervisor of the weavers, has taken (for the weaving (?)) (the women) ^{o. 1} Arbītum, ^{o. 2} Atimatum, ^{o. 3} Ube, ^{o. 4} Ašdaga, ^{o. 5} Šulgi-tūrī, ^{o. 6} Kinibši, ^{o. 7} Mama-šarrat, ^{r. 1} Annā, ^{r. 2} Šalim-nūrī, released (for that occasion (?)) and ^{r. 4} Nana-kigaga (...) ^{r. 5} who had returned from music.

⁴⁶⁹ BPOA 10, p. 19-20; Tsouparopoulou, 2013: 150.

⁴⁷⁰ Edition dependent upon BDTNS 003318 with corrections derived from our inspection of the original publication copy and its photo available on CDLI P134805.

⁴⁷¹ For some names on this list, we follow Feliu and Millet Albà, 2017: 114 and 125 (*Par-bi-tum* = Arbītum), 115 and 126 (Kinibši), 115, 116 n. 36 and 127 (**P^ošul-gi-tu-ri** = Šulgi-tūrī). A general remark about the Akkadian nature of these names is contained in Pruzsinszky, 2010b: 37.

⁴⁷² We keep in mind the description (based on collation) of this sign in Lafont, 1985: 167. Pruzsinszky, 2010b: 39 mistakenly said “All the other singers are marked with a ‘1/2’ sign” (corrected then in Pruzsinszky, 2013: 39 n. 36). We consider this sign superfluous because it does not fit well in this context.

⁴⁷³ CDLI P134805 and BDTNS 003318 have “ša-lim-nu-ri-šu bar-ra”, but Šalim-nūrī (“Šalim is my light”) is an Akkadian name (Steinkeller, 2015: 41). Therefore, **šu bar-ra** is a form of **šu bar** (“to release”) as Pruzsinszky, 2007: 342–343; Pruzsinszky, 2010b: 39 and Pruzsinszky, 2013: 39 n. 36

⁴⁷⁴ Pruzsinszky, 2010b: 39 has “u₄ šakar-ka”. The correct concatenation is **u₄-sakar-ka** since **sakar** exists just as a reading of the sign SAR. If we had two independent words (**u₄** and ***sakar**), the expression would be ***u₄-sakar-ra-ka** (**u₄.d sakar** + **ak** [GEN] + **a** [LOC]), not **u₄-šakar** (/u₄.d.šakar.ak/).

This text deals with a group people who returned (**gur**) to weaving after a period (but not the **eš3-eš3** festivals⁴⁷⁵) devoted to something related to music⁴⁷⁶. Previous studies have dealt here with terms like “musical performance”⁴⁷⁷, “singing”⁴⁷⁸ or “music”⁴⁷⁹ as if this text contained **nam-nar**. However, this text has only **nar** (there is no **nam-**). In this sense, we would talk in this text *a priori* just about **nar**, and not **nam-nar**.

However, the presence of **nam-nar** in this text as <**nam**>-**nar** makes sense from an epigraphic perspective. Certainly, as we have explained in our edition, there are some mistakes in this text, like a superfluous sign ½ before *ša-lim-^cnu^l-ri*. In the same way, <**nam**>-**nar** fits here due to the marker {**ta**} of the ablative (“from”)/instrumental nature (“with”)⁴⁸⁰ accompanying **nar**. This marker fits with **nam-nar** as a non-human noun, and we have seen it in our Text 5 (**nam-nar-ta**, “from music”). However, it does not fit well with **nar** since we are not dealing with something coming from/through (= ablative sense of the ABL {**ta**}) a **nar** as if we had the term **ḡiri3** (literally “foot”, used as “via”) as in

⁴⁷⁵ Sallaberger, 1993: 68 (“zurückgekehrt vom Gesang bei *e*-Feier zum Neulichtag”) has a small grammatical explanation in page 41 n. 171 of the same publication. It makes sense since, otherwise, where were those musicians going to perform music (or whatever is <**nam**>-**nar** here)? However, in order to have this translation, we should have (<**nam**>)-**nar-ta** **eš3-eš3 u4-sakar-ka gur-ra**. That is, the locative chain should be inside the nominalized verbal form, not after the verb as in this case. To understand both lines together makes neither sense from an epigraphic perspective, since there is an anepigraphic space between them. This new vision of the text partially invalidates the comments of Regine Pruzsinszky (2007: 342; 2010: 37; 2013: 39 n. 36 and 43; 2019a: 109). She had followed Walther Sallaberger who himself seems to have blindly followed Léon Legrain’s interpretation (see TRU, p. 3, 31, 55, 133 for reference).

⁴⁷⁶ Arbītum is documented as **geme2 uš-bar** in PDT 1 525 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 05-12-00), o. i 6, 14 (BDTNS 013232). On its behalf, Kinibši has this office in Nisaba 15/2 668 [Private owner] (Ibbī-Suen 01-00-00), o. i 4 (with reference to o. ii 30) (BDTNS 193119). That contributes to a partial rejection of Pruzsinszky, 2013: 39 n. 36, 43. See Feliu and Millet Albà, 2017: 113 for further reference. Atimatum is a miller (**geme2 kinkin2**) according to AnOr 7 285 [MM 188] (00-00-00), o. iii’ 7’ and 24’ (BDTNS 009122). Šulgi-tūrī is fuller (**azlag7**) in Nisaba 15/2 668 [Private owner] (Ibbī-Suen 01-00-00), o. iii 38 and iv 23 (BDTNS 193119). Other names, as **pu3-bi**, **paš-da-ga**, **pa-na-na-a** and **pa-na-na-ki-ga-ga** are unknown beyond this excerpt. In the same way, the professional occupation of other people in this text is much less certain to us. For instance, **ma-ma-šar-ra-at** usually appears with the word **ir**, being, therefore, a name of a canal in those texts although not in ours. See Owen, 2019: 395–396 for reference about this last matter.

⁴⁷⁷ Pruzsinszky, 2013: 39 n. 36 (“musical performance”); Pruzsinszky, 2010a: 109-110 (“practicar música vocal o instrumental”).

⁴⁷⁸ TRU, p. 3 (“chanter”); Sallaberger, 1993: 68 (“Gesang”); Pruzsinszky, 2007: 342 (“Gesang”).

⁴⁷⁹ Pruzsinszky, 2010b: 39 (“music”).

⁴⁸⁰ DGS, p. 191–196.

other texts⁴⁸¹. Moreover, the instrumental value of the ABL {**ta**} is only applicable to non-human realities. If we had a concatenation of the type “with the musician(s)” indicating that the women of our text returned to some place with a musician, we should have **nar-da** (with COM {**da**}, which is applied to human nouns⁴⁸²).

As we can see, this text does not give many details about the people mentioned therein. In any case, we would like to be prudent in our interpretations. Furthermore, we might take into consideration our Text 5, which is from the same period and reign. In this sense, we would translate this <**nam**>-**nar** as “music”— the musical activity performed by these people. The proposed translation fits well in this context since we do not negate any possible use of instruments or singing by the people of this text.

2.4. The transition to the Old Babylonian Period

We want now to deal with two *quasi*-duplicate texts from the northern Mesopotamian city of Awal, which is situated in the current settlement of Tell al-Sulaima (close to al-Sa’adiya, east bank of the Diyala River)⁴⁸³. These texts are addressed to a person called Tulpipše (or Tulpibše). That name might be from a Hurrian origin if we consider the -še of his name as an abbreviation of the Hurrian *šenni* (*še-e-ni* in the writing), “brother”⁴⁸⁴.

These texts concern the sister of an individual called Ilī-šummid about whom we have no more information beyond. This woman, according to these texts, is removed from an office/occupation called *kala’ūtum*⁴⁸⁵. That *kala’ūtum* and *nārūtum* will be given by an

⁴⁸¹ See DGS, p. 151 for the grammatical analysis of one example.

⁴⁸² DGS, p. 200–202.

⁴⁸³ They are almost the two unique texts found in this city. The other one is AIHA 4, p. 40 [IM 92363] (00-00-00), a text about the allotment of one sheep for each person. See BDTNS 175506 for an edition, Rašīd, 1981: 40 for an Arabic translation, and Steinkeller, 1984: 86 and Hilgert, 2002: 20 for its chronology.

⁴⁸⁴ Bush, 1964: 43; Laroche, 1980: 225–226; Richter, 2012: 384; Fournet, 2013: 5, 31, 68.

⁴⁸⁵ This spelling of *kalātu(m)* is certainly singular concerning southern Mesopotamia. However, it recalls the spelling *girsega’um* for *gi/erseqû(m)* in Mari (Shehata, 2009: 55 n. 275; Peled, 2015: 760). It recalls also the term *kula’ūtum* contained in the Middle Hittite text *The Siege of Uršu*, CTH 7/ KBo 1, 11 [VAT 7679], r. 13, 17-18 (Peled, 2015: 754). In that Hittite text, *kula’ūtum* would designate the activity of the *kulu’um*, a variant for *kuleššar* and it might make reference to the passivity of some generals. In any case, we cannot forget its connections with homosexuality (Peled, 2010: 78; Peled, 2015: 754).

anonymous king to a person called Wirri. That name might be also from Hurrian origin since the Hurrian *weri* means “sword”⁴⁸⁶. Here is our first text:

Text 7. al-Rawi, 1992:185 [IM 85455/as-Sulaima 410] (00-00-00)⁴⁸⁷

o. 1 *a-na tul₂-pi₂-ip-še*
 o. 2 *qi₂-bi₂-ma*
 o. 3 *ši₂-bu-tum*⁴⁸⁸
 o. 4 *li-zi-zu*
 o. 5 **NIN**⁴⁸⁹ *i₃-li₂-šum-mi-i[d]*
 o. 6 *i-^rna GALA^r-u₂-tim*⁴⁹⁰
 o. 7 *na-as-ḥa-at*
 r. 1 *šar-ru-um*
 r. 2 *a-na ¹wi-ri*
 r. 3 *ka₃-la-u₂-tam₂*
 r. 4 *u₃ NAR*⁴⁹¹ *-^ru₂-tam₂^r*
 r. 5 *i-ta-di₃-^rin^r*
 r. 6 *a-na IRI*^{492ki} *-^rim^r*
 r. 7 *wu-di₃-šu*

o. 2 Say o. 1 to Tulpipše: o. 3–4 “may the witnesses be present! o. 5 Ili-šummid’s sister o. 7 has been removed o. 6 from the office of the *kala’um*. r. 1 The king r. 5 has given r. 3 the office of the *kala’um* lamenter r. 4 and the office of the *nārum* r. 2 to Wirri. r. 7 Say it r. 6 to the city!”

Here is the *quasi*-duplicate of this text⁴⁹³, much more damaged than the previous text and with a partially different ending. In this case, the author of the letter does not want to deal with the matter again and refuses to have it brought back to his attention.

⁴⁸⁶ Laroche, 1980: 296; Richter, 2012: 299-300; Arnaud, 2013: 86.

⁴⁸⁷ BDTNS 170851 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy and photo of this tablet.

⁴⁸⁸ CDLI P381746 has “si-bu-tum”. However, *sibūtu* is a type of festival and *sibātu(m)* means “tavern” (CAD S, p. 232–233). The sign SI may be read *ši₂* (MZL, p. 84). CDLI transliterates “š” as “sz”, so the “z” might have casually been forgotten. For his part, Black, 1991: 27 has “ši-bu-tum”, which is also incorrect according to what we have in the manuscript.

⁴⁸⁹ Black, 1991: 27 has “NIN”. However, we should have the sign TUG₂ (**nin** = SAL.TUG₂ = “lady”) instead of the KU of this document according to its copy and photo.

⁴⁹⁰ Al-Rawi, 1992: 184 puts Akkadian syllables after Sumerograms in superscripts. However, they are not glosses for being transliterated in that way. In the same way, thanks to that procedure, he mistakenly mixes determinatives with main syllables, like in r. 6, where he has “URU^{ki.im}”.

⁴⁹¹ Black, 1991: 27 seems to give the name of the signs. Otherwise, we would expect “GALA” instead of its “UŠ.KU”. However, it writes “NAR” when, with his procedure, we would expect “LUL”.

⁴⁹² We follow CDLI P381746. Al-Rawi, 1992: 184; Black, 1991: 27 and BDTNS 170851 have **uru**. However, URU is actually the name of the sign for **iri**, the usual form for saying “city” in Sumerian.

⁴⁹³ For an additional (short) reference to this text, see Maul, 2002: 255 n. 1.

Text 8. al-Rawi, 1992: 185 [IM 85456/as-Sulaima 411] (00-00-00)⁴⁹⁴

- o. 1 [a-na x]-^rx-[x]⁴⁹⁵
o. 2 [qi₂]-^rbi₂-^rma
o. 3 [NIN]⁹ i₃-li₂-šum-mi-^rid^r
o. 4 ^rna^r-as-ḥa-^rat^r
o. 5 <a-na>⁴⁹⁶ ^r1^r wi-ir-ri⁴⁹⁷
r. 1 NAR u₃ GALA-^rtum¹⁴⁹⁸
r. 2 ^rna^r-di₃-šum
r. 3 a-wa-tum
r. 4 ^rla^r i-tu₃-ra-am

o. 2 [S]ay o. 1. [to] [...] : o. 3. “[I]r-šummid’s [siste]r o. 4. has been removed. r. 1 The office of the *kala’um* and the office of the *nārum* r. 2 have been given to him, o. 5. to Wirri. r. 3 The matter (of this letter) r. 4 must not return to me!”

One of the most controversial aspects of these texts in the past has been their chronology. Certainly, Farouk al-Rawi, their publisher, debated between the Late Old Akkadian Period and the Early Old Babylonian Period, keeping in mind the information from the Iraq Museum about their archaeological context⁴⁹⁹. However, some authors have proposed a later Old Babylonian chronology⁵⁰⁰. On its behalf, Markus Hilgert said that they could belong to the Ur III Period or the Early Old Babylonian Period⁵⁰¹.

⁴⁹⁴ Edition dependent upon BDTNS 170852 with minor corrections derived from our inspection of the original copy and photo of this tablet.

⁴⁹⁵ Al-Rawi, 1992: 184 and BDTNS 170852 suppose just two missing signs, while CDLI P381747 proposes three. Everything is possible in light of the preservation state of that tablet. However, we think that CDLI is right since we have *a-na tul₂-pi₂-ip-še* (with the *še* written in the edge) in our Text 7, that is, three signs in addition to those for *a-na*. Text 8 is supposed to be a duplicate of Text 7, so it makes sense.

⁴⁹⁶ Al-Rawi, 1992: 184 does not have any preposition here, and he translates: “Wirri — the office of *nārum* and the office of *kala’um* are given to him”. Similarly, Peled, 2014: 287 n. 27 translates: “Wirri is given the nar- and *kalû*-ship.” However, keeping in mind the existence of the preposition *ana* in our Text 7, we might suppose its original presence also in this text, although it would be forgotten by the scribe.

⁴⁹⁷ CDLI P381747 forgets the *Personenkeil* over *wi-ir-ri*.

⁴⁹⁸ Al-Rawi, 1992: 184 and BDTNS 170852 have “tum” (Black, 1991: 27 “*tum”, where * = “over erasure”), but, according to the copy of the manuscript, the sign TUM might be incorrectly written. We would agree, therefore, with CDLI P381747, although we do not agree with its transliteration “_gala{tum#!}_” (= GALA^{tum!}). That is opposed to CDLI P381746 (“_gala_-u₂-tim” = GALA-*u₂-tim*).

⁴⁹⁹ Al-Rawi, 1992: 181. CDLI P381746 and P381747 situate them in the Old Akkadian Period (contrary to Peled, 2015: 760 n. 43), while Gabbay, 2014b: 63 n.2 maintains al-Rawi’s duality.

⁵⁰⁰ Black, 1991: 27; Shehata, 2009: 55 n. 275. Contrary to Peled, 2015: 760 n. 43, Black, 1991 never talks about “Early Old Babylonian Period”, just “Old Babylonian Period”.

⁵⁰¹ Hilgert, 2002: 45–46 (“Ur III-zeitlich oder früh-altbabylonisch”). Chronological proposal followed by Molina, 2008: 53 n. 116 and BDTNS (170851 and 170852).

In our opinion, these texts should have more Sumerograms in order to be considered as coming from the Old Akkadian Period⁵⁰². In the same way, their style clearly recalls a typical Old Babylonian letter. Nevertheless, in addition to Hilgert's arguments⁵⁰³, a (Late) Ur III chronology makes sense with our Ur III references to **nam-gala** (Sumerian equivalent of the *kala'utum* of our Texts 7 and 8). In fact, at that moment, many people acceded (**ku4**)⁵⁰⁴, went (**nen**)⁵⁰⁵ or performed (**ak**)⁵⁰⁶ that "office of the **gala**". Among them, there are Amorites⁵⁰⁷ and local⁵⁰⁸ cooks⁵⁰⁹, messengers⁵¹⁰, military⁵¹¹, and even the

⁵⁰² A clear example of that is the Old Akkadian hymn for Šamaš of IAS 326 + 342 [IM 70169 + 70297?], *passim*. Certainly, the majority of the text of this hymn-myth (the oldest Akkadian literary text in the history) is written with Sumerograms. In this sense, its Akkadian content must be mainly inferred through a comparison with the Eblaite text ARET 5 6 [TM.75.G.2421 + 75.G.5511]. See Krebernik, 1992 for editions and Krebernik, 1998: 320-321 for additional remarks.

⁵⁰³ Concerning our Text 7: 1) Imperative G 2SG.M of *qabûm* ("to speak") of line o. 2 (Hilgert, 2002: 122, 423), 2) Preterite G 3PL.M of *izuzzum* ("to stand") of line o. 4 (Hilgert, 2002: 495), 3) Stative G 3SG.F of *nasāhum* ("to remove") of line o. 7 (Hilgert, 2002: 312), 4) Perfect G 3SG.M of *nadānum* ("to give") of r. 5 (Hilgert, 2002: 306), and 5) Imperative D of *i/udûm* ("to know") (Hilgert, 2002: 483). Concerning our Text 8, Hilgert, 2002: 351 pays attention also to the Present G 3SG.M from *târum* ("to return") of line r. 4.

⁵⁰⁴ Three texts with **u4 nam-gala-še3 in-ku4-ra**: MVN 15 142 [Cornell 30] (Šulgi 00-00-00), r. 22–23 (BDTNS 034165); Nisaba 30 23 [Owen ---] (Šulgi 47-08-18), r. 2–3 (BDTNS 063986). See Oppenheim, 1948: 110; Wilcke, 1988: 26; Balke, 2006: 200; Michalowski, 2006: 51 and Hallo, 2008: 105 for comments.

⁵⁰⁵ Nisaba 15/2 97 [Anonymous] (Amar-Suena 08-04-17), o. 10–r. 1 (BDTNS 192786).

⁵⁰⁶ See Attinger, 2005: 238 and Michalowski, 2006: 51, 54 for general remarks about **nam-gala ... ak**. For a textual example, see Amorites 20 (pl. 9) [OIM A4218] (Šu-Suen 04-09-02), r. 6–8 (BDTNS 015042).

⁵⁰⁷ MVN 12 112 [FLP 592] (Šulgi 47-10-25), r. 13–14 (BDTNS 027529); MVN 8 122 [AO 19603] (Amar-Suena 01-08-20), o. 8–10 (BDTNS 022237); OrSP 47–49 21 [VAT 6966] (Amar-Suena 02-09-24), o. 1-2 (BDTNS 007078); SAT 2 724 [YBC 8255] (Amar-Suena 02-10-30), o. iii 15–19, iv 31–34, vi 15–16; r. i 22–23 (BDTNS 048907).

⁵⁰⁸ See also AUCT 3 42 [AUAM 73.851] (Šu-Suen 01-12-00), o. 1–3 (BDTNS 029813) and TCBI 2/2 50 [BI C 11] (Šu-Suen 07-04-00), r. 2 (BDTNS 169759), about Šarrum-bāni and Du-iliām.

⁵⁰⁹ UDT 97 [NBC 97] (Amar-Suena 04-09-19), o. 8–9 (BDTNS 005482); George, 1987: 35 text 317 [B1 44.317] (Amar-Suena 09-09-00), o. 10298132 (BDTNS 029056); PDT 1 464 [Ist. PD ---] (Šu-Suen 01-09-06), o. 1–2 (BDTNS 013171).

⁵¹⁰ CST 189 [JRL 189] (Šulgi 47-10-14), o. 10298133 (BDTNS 008420); CST 442 [JRL 442] (Šu-Suen 07-11-18), o. 10298132 (BDTNS 008673).

⁵¹¹ OrSP 18 5 17 [Schneider ---] (Šulgi 48-09-09), o. 16–17 (BDTNS 006481; about an **u3-kul**, see Freedman, 1977: 14; Michalowski, 2006: 53; Dahl, 2007: 154 for its possible military condition); Princeton 1 90 [PTS 540] (Amar-Suena 02-06-09), o. 6 (BDTNS 033023; about an **aga3-us2** soldier) and TRU 350

royal family⁵¹². These allusions are highly useful for understanding why a woman (like Ilī-šummid’s sister) performed that office normally destined to men⁵¹³. Certainly, some people have thought that *kala’utum* (and *nārūtum* by context) was just as a prebend⁵¹⁴, keeping in mind our current evidence about women performing that office⁵¹⁵.

However, we have already commented on the “flexibility” of **nam-gala**, an office which could be performed (for a short time) by very different people⁵¹⁶. In this sense, we tend to think that Ilī-šummid’s sister would not be a prebend holder of the *kala’utum*. In our opinion, she had to perform that office for a short time before being removed (*nashat*) then from it. We believe that expulsion could be caused simply because the period when that women had to perform that office ended, and it was perhaps necessary for the anonymous king of this text to announce the next holder of that office and *nārūtum*.

Therefore, we would agree with the chronological reckoning of our Texts 7 and 8 as the end of the Ur III Period, in transition to the (Early) Old Babylonian Period as Markus Hilgert proposed.

Concerning the meaning of *nārūtum* in those texts, we should keep in mind two things. On the one hand, *nārūtum* is something given to someone (*nadiššum*). On the other hand, it is equated to *kala’utum*, the office from which Ilī-šummid’s sister is removed. In this sense, we would agree with the previous translations of this term as “office of the

[ICP 350] (Šu-Suen 02-09-07), r. 1–2 (BDTNS 003627; about an archer, **lu₂-nešban**). According to Carlos Langa Morales (personal communication), this figure was a civilian who worked for the army.

⁵¹² In MVN 5 116 [Pinches 13] (Amar-Suena 07-03-09), o. 8–10 (BDTNS 020903), Šu-Šulgi, Amar-Suena’s son, performed the office of the **gala** receiving three fattened sheep and two fattened billy goats.

⁵¹³ Gabbay, 2008; Shehata, 2009: 82–93; Shehata, 2013: 81; Peled, 2016: 135–144.

⁵¹⁴ Peled, 2014: n. 27 (which talks about a prebend holder) has simplified a bit what is said in Black, 1991: 26 and too much concerning al-Rawi, 1992: 182 in order to justify its own hypothesis.

⁵¹⁵ The text AWEL 1 [Erm. 14001] (Urukagina 02-00-00), r. iii 3 (CDLI P221708) deals with a **gala** priest whose name is written as **nin-e₂-balaḡ-ni-du₁₀** and who could possibly be a female **gala** priest. For other comments about female **gala** priests in Early Mesopotamia, see al-Rawi, 1992: 182–183; Black, 1991: 26; AWEL, p. 252 n. 1208.

⁵¹⁶ “Laboral flexibility” was common in Ur III Mesopotamia, and even more for professions with a certain musical content. We cannot forget in this study the connections between **nar** musicians, snake charmers (**muš-laḡ_{4/5}**) and bear trainers (**u₄-da-tuš**). See D’Agostino, 2012: 92–95 and Pruzsinszky, 2013: 40 for reference.

*nāru*⁵¹⁷. In this sense, our Texts 7 and 8 would be a precedent for the Old Babylonian situation. There, as we shall comment and study in depth in the following chapters, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* sometimes designate the office of the **nar/nāru(m)**. That will normally happen when **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* are followed by the name of a deity. In those cases, therefore, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* would designate the office of a musician devoted to said deity.

2.5. Conclusions

Concerning the 3rd millennium, our evidence for **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* is quite obscure/fragmentary (as in our Texts 1–3) or too schematic. This is the case of our Text 5 and 6, which deal with the access or return of some people to some professions.

However, it is possible that **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* designated “music” in a large sense as in our Text 4. There **nam-nar** did not refer the activity of some people as in our Texts 5–6. Far from that, it referred the activity of some instruments, perhaps together with their musicians. It is not a reference to the sound of these instruments, but it is already quite close to that notion, something surprising considering the antiquity of this text.

The 3rd millennium is also, in any case, the time when other, secondary meanings of **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* come to the fore. This is the case in our Texts 7–8, where the different verbs used suggest that we are dealing with some (temple) offices. In any case, we should be careful with its provenance much farther north than the rest of the texts studied in this chapter, which come from southern Mesopotamia.

In this sense, despite all the problems given by this documentation, we might say that the original meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* was “music” in this period. That will be very important to keep in mind for our later and final conclusions of this study.

⁵¹⁷ Al-Rawi, 1992: 184 (“office of *nārum*”); Black, 1992: 27 (“office of *nārum*”); Hilgert, 2002: 483 n. 168 (“Amt des Musikers”); Shehata, 2009: 56–57 n. 282 (“nar- Amt”). Compare with Gabbay, 2014a: 63 n. 2 (“*nārūtu*”); Peled, 2015: 287 n. 27 (“nar- and *kalû*-ship”).

3. NAM-NAR IN THE TEXTS OF THE OLD BABYLONIAN ELEMENTARY SCRIBAL CURRICULUM AND ADMINISTRATION

3.1. General Introduction to the Old Babylonian Sumerian Texts

After the collapse of the state built by the rulers of Ur at the end of the 3rd millennium BCE, the Amorites established several kingdoms in central and southern Mesopotamia in the period currently known as Old Babylonian/Amorite (2002–1595 BCE).

In southern Mesopotamia, the Amorites maintained the former Sumerian culture as a way of legitimizing their control over that region like the successors of the rulers of Ur⁵¹⁸. However, the main language of that culture, Sumerian, was already dead as a native language⁵¹⁹. In this sense, scribes (whose mother tongue was Akkadian) had to copy and create many texts of all kinds for learning that language and, in this way, “rejuvenate” that Sumerian culture⁵²⁰. As a consequence, the presence of the music (as a part of said culture), and, in particular, the musical terms describing that musical world, experienced an enlargement in our texts regarding previous times⁵²¹. Among those musical terms, we need to include also our term **nam-nar**, whose textual allusions in this period will more abundant than ever as far as we know.

Those references to **nam-nar** will be studied in this and our next chapter following the Old Babylonian scribal *curriculum* of Nippur (paradigm of the Sumerian culture at that time⁵²²), where most part of our texts (or their tablets) come from. In that model, scribes used to copy fragments of lexical lists, model contracts and short literary texts⁵²³. Then, they dealt with the most complex texts, like real administrative texts or other longer literary texts as those of the “Decad”⁵²⁴. In this chapter we shall deal more specifically with texts from the scribal elementary *curriculum* and legal texts.

⁵¹⁸ Charpin, 1995: 812–813.

⁵¹⁹ See Woods, 2006: 91–92 as a synthesis of previous discussions about this topic.

⁵²⁰ Cohen, 1981: 1; BWL, p. 3; Michalowski, 2004: 21; DGS, p. 6.

⁵²¹ These observations must be cautiously considered since there is not still a comprehensive study of all our Old Babylonian musical terms. Musicians and songs were studied in Shehata, 2009, but a similar study on instruments is lacking. By the moment, see Krispijn, 2010b and Michalowski, 2010a and 2010b.

⁵²² *Nippur Neighborhoods*, p. 13–28; Stol, 1998–2000: 539; Shehata, 2009: 162–164, 172.

⁵²³ EEN, p. 18–45, 63; Robson, 2001: 47; Spada, 2018: 3.

⁵²⁴ Delnero, 2006: 25–26.

3.2. The Elementary Scribal *Curriculum*

3.2.1. Lexical texts

3.2.1.1. About a type of song

Our study will begin with this excerpt from the thematic and acrographic list about human occupations and kinship terms known as *Proto-lu2*. This is the “easiest” text in the elementary scribal *curriculum* from Nippur where we have a reference to **nam-nar**:

Text 9. *Proto-lu2*⁵²⁵

590. [s]er₃ ʾnamʾ-nar

N_{I-A} r. ii 28. [s]er₃ ʾnamʾ-nar

591. [se]r₃ nam-gala

N_{I-A} r. ii 29. [se]r₃ nam-ʾgalaʾ
N_{I-Sʹ} o. iiʹ 8ʹ. ser₃ ʾnam -galaʾ(ʾUŠʹ.KUʹ)⁵²⁶
N_{I-G4} o. i 6ʹ. [ser₃ n]am -gala

590. Musical (sung) text

591. Lament (sung) text

*Sigla*⁵²⁷

N_{I-A} MSL 12, p. 28 A [CBS 2241 + 9850 + 9851 + 11394 + N 4631 + 5222] (photo available on CDLI P227886; collated the 19/08/2019)

N_{I-Sʹ} MSL 12, p. 30 Sʹ [Ni 5169] (photo on CDLI P228396; collated the 20/08/2019)

N_{I-G4} Taylor, 2001: 210–211 [Anonymous 349945] (publication’s handwritten copy)

⁵²⁵ Score edition dependent upon the one of DCCLT with changes derived from our consultation of the manuscripts through the copies/photos indicated down in addition to some collations.

⁵²⁶ DCCLT has “šer₃-x- raʾ”, and considered it a variant of **ser₃ nam-nar (ser₃ nam-nar-ra)**. However, its unknown sign seems UŠ. The second sign is a bit confusing because the tablet seems to have been rewritten by the scribe at this point. In any case, it makes sense to understand a wrongly written sign KU in order to read **gala(UŠ.KU)** and, therefore **ser₃ nam-gala**. That makes sense since the next composite line of *Proto-lu2* contains **ser₃ nam-šub**. The same happens with manuscript N_{I-Sʹ}, o. iiʹ 9ʹ.

⁵²⁷ They follow MSL 12, p. 28–32 except G₄, an own *siglum* inspired in that sequence. They are preceded by an “I” (= Type I; see MSL 12, p. 27) indicating their typology and an N (= Nippur) indicating their provenance.

In this excerpt, we find a reference to **ser₃ nam-nar**, term which has been previously translated in four different ways: 1) as a “subscript” for Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts⁵²⁸, 2) as a “song (**ser₃**) of the **nam-nar** (term translated differently in each case)”⁵²⁹, 3) as a “**ser₃** song of the **nar**”⁵³⁰ and 4) as a “musical song”⁵³¹.

The first translation (“subscript”) seems to be made in analogy with other terms (like **ser₃ gid₂-da**, “long **ser₃** song”) mentioned in the colophons of some Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts⁵³². However, **ser₃ nam-nar** has never been found in the colophon of an Old Babylonian Sumerian literary text. The unique exception to that is a 1st millennium text never taken into consideration for that definition⁵³³.

The second translation (“song of the **nam-nar**”) tries to observe the meaning of **ser₃** (“song”) and **nam-nar**. However, that interpretation forgets the absence of a genitive marker in **ser₃ nam-nar**. Certainly, if we had a genitive, we would have **ser₃ nam-nar-ra** (**ser₃ nam.nar** + **ak** [GEN]), like in **ser₃ nam-erim₂-ma** (“song of the oath(?)”; **ser₃ nam.erim** + **ak** [GEN]), word mentioned shortly after **ser₃ nam-nar** in our lexical texts⁵³⁴. The third interpretation (“**ser₃** song of the **nar**”) has also this same problem. In addition, it translates actually from **ser₃ nar-ra**, and not from **ser₃ nam-nar** as if both terms were equal. That procedure is dangerous since Christiane Ludwig⁵³⁵ has already explained that we should not read **ser₃ LUL**⁵³⁶ as **ser₃ <nam>-nar**. However, we should read it as **ser₃ kad_x** or **ser₃ še₁₁**. We shall comment on this expression later⁵³⁷.

⁵²⁸ ePSD (“subscript”); ePSD2 (“a subscript”).

⁵²⁹ PBS 12/1, p. 11 (“song of the singer’s art”); Kramer, 1960: 58 (“hymn of song”); Hunger, 1968: 123 (“Lied des Sangerberufes”); Kilmer, 1971: 143 (“song of the musician’s craft”, same translation in Rubio, 2009: 67 and Lohnert, 2016: 55); Sjoberg, 1974: 142 (“namnar(?)-Gesang”); Schramm, 2008: 9 (“Lieder der ‘Sangeskunst’”); Peterson, 2019c: 698 (“song of musicianship”).

⁵³⁰ Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“Lied des Hymnsensangers”); Volk, 1994: 185 (“Kompositionen fur die Tatigkeit als Fest-/Hymnenmusiker”); Krispijn, 2017: 226 (“song of the hymn singer”); Skelton, 2017: 49 (“nar song”).

⁵³¹ Kramer, 1963: 207 (“musical hymns”); Geller, 1995–1996: 245 (“musical songs”); ETCSL 5.5.2. (“musical song”); Geller, 2011: 253 (“cultic song”), and Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46 (“musical song”).

⁵³² See Shehata, 2009: 262–284 for the most comprehensive study of those terms until today.

⁵³³ CT 17 pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 19’.

⁵³⁴ *Proto-lu₂*, 590 (**ser₃ nam-nar**) (our own edition) and 593 (**ser₃ nam-erim₂-ma**) (DCCLT).

⁵³⁵ Ludwig, 1990: 189–195.

⁵³⁶ In *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 369, A 373–374 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

⁵³⁷ For an alternative interpretation, see Klein, 1990: 76 n. 50.

Last interpretation (“musical song”) is a bit redundant since all songs are musical by nature (at least, as far as we know). In any case, it is grammatically right since **nam-nar** acts here as an adjective of **ser₃** like, for instance, **nam-lugal** (“kingship”) in the expression **aga nam-lugal**⁵³⁸ (“royal crown”)⁵³⁹. We should remember that **ser₃** also means “to sing” and “(sung) text”⁵⁴⁰ as the equivalent of *zamāru(m)*⁵⁴¹. In this sense, we might translate **ser₃ nam-nar** as “musical [**nam-nar**] composition (to be sung) [**ser₃**]”.

As we can see, **ser₃ nam-nar** is mentioned just before **ser₃ nam-gala**. That is very important for seeing **ser₃ nam-nar**, not as a lament song⁵⁴², but as a (mainly) festive one.

3.2.1.2. About a type of music

We deal now with an excerpt of *Proto-izi*, another thematic and acrographic list placed just after *Proto-lu₂* (with which shares some features) in the scribal *curriculum*⁵⁴³:

Text 10. *Proto-izi*⁵⁴⁴

II 227	nam-bur-šu-ma		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 21’	‘ nam ’- bur-šu-ma ’
	N _{P-1}	c. iv 51	nam -bur-šu-ma
II 228	nam-dub-sar		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 22’	[nam]- dub -sar
	N _{I-12*}	o. iv 10’	nam -dub -sar
	N _{II/2-62}	r. vi 6	‘ nam -dub-sar ’
	N _{P-1}	c. iv 52	nam -dub -sar
	U _{T₁} ⁵⁴⁵	r. 3’	nam -dub -sar ’

⁵³⁸ *Proto-izi*, II 397 (DCCLT).

⁵³⁹ Literally **aga** (“crown”) + **nam-lugal** (“kingship”).

⁵⁴⁰ Krispijn, 2010b: 147 proposed “composition” as the original meaning of this term.

⁵⁴¹ *Proto-aa*, 757:1 (DCCLT). For *zamāru(m)*, see CAD Z, p. 35.

⁵⁴² Shehata, 2009: 265.

⁵⁴³ Taylor, 2001: 213.

⁵⁴⁴ Score edition dependent upon the one of Crisostomo, 2019: 296 with changes derived from our inspection of the handwritten copies and photos of the manuscripts (some of them collated) indicated down.

⁵⁴⁵ Omitted in Crisostomo, 2019 because of its provenance from Ur (its edition tries to reconstruct just the lexical list used in Nippur). However, we have used it since it is present in the edition of this text on DCCLT Q000050 in addition to the transliteration of the manuscript on CDLI P347041.

II 229	nam-gala		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 23'	[nam]-'gala'
	N _{I-12*}	o. iv 8'	nam -gala
	N _{P-1}	c. iv 53	nam -gala
II 230	nam-nar		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 24'	[nam] -nar
	N _{I-12*}	o. iv 11'	nam -nar
	N _{II/2-62}	r. vi 7	[na]m -nar
	N _{P-1}	c. iv 54	nam -'nar'
II 230a	nam-nar-balaḡ		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 25'	nam-nar-balaḡ
II 231	nam-ab-ba		
	N _{I-11}	o. v 26'	nam -ab-ba
	N _{I-12*}	o. iv 12'	nam -ab-ba
	N _{II/2-62}	r. vi 4	'nam'-ab-ba
II 227	The profession of the bur-šu-ma		
II 228	The writing		
II 229	The profession of the gala		
II 230	The music		
II 230a	The profession of the nar of the balaḡ		
II 231	The old age		

*Sigla*⁵⁴⁶

N _{I-11}	MSL 13, p. 40 B [Ist. Ni 10262] (none copy/photo available)
N _{I-12*}	MSL 13, p. 40 C [IM 58795] (none copy/photo available)
N _{II/2-62}	MSL 13, p. 40 A [CBS 2145 + 2252 + 2273 + 2276 + UM 29-13-721 + 29-15-369 + 29-15-529] (photo available on CDLI P227870; collated the 19/08/2019)
N _{P-1}	TMH <i>forthcoming</i> [HS 1802] (none copy/photo available)
Ur ₁	UET 7 78 [U. ---] (publication copy)

In this text, **nam-nar** is placed together with some terms designating professions or conditions mentioned with **nam-nar** in advanced texts of the scribal *curriculum*⁵⁴⁷. Therefore, **nam-nar** might designate the profession of the **nar**⁵⁴⁸. However, it might also

⁵⁴⁶ They follow those of Crisostomo 2019: 200–226, except Ur_{U-1}, which is ours. Ur indicates its provenance, U its uncertain condition, and the number 1 is adapted from its *siglum* A in MSL 13, p. 35. We have also changed the order of the manuscript N_{II/2-62} in the score for coherence (Type II after Type I).

⁵⁴⁷ **nam-bur-šu-ma** (TMH 10 55 [HS 2396] (Rīm-Sîn I 35-10-00), o. 5; TMH 10 59a [HS 2081] (Rīm-Sîn I, 54-01-00), o. 2–3); **nam-dub-sar** (*The Father and his rude Son*, 109-110); **nam-gala** (*Proto-Lu*₂, 590–591); **nam-ab-ba** (*Inanna and Enki*, I v 33 and *Inanna and Enki*, II v 51–52). See our editions of the cited texts for reference.

⁵⁴⁸ Like according to DCCLT Q000050 (“office of the singer”).

refer music in general⁵⁴⁹. Certainly, not all the terms from that list beginning with **nam-** are professions. In fact, the single common thing to them is that their first sign is NAM⁵⁵⁰.

We would like, however, to reflect more about the term **nam-LUL.BALAD** mentioned just after **nam-nar**. That term has been transliterated as **nam-tige₂** because of the logographic composition of **tige₂** as LUL.BALAD⁵⁵¹, and it has been defined as a reference to the musician of the **tige₂**⁵⁵² instrument or a type of music⁵⁵³. This last definition remembers to us the previous definitions of **nam-nar** as a concrete type of music⁵⁵⁴. In addition, we might remember the Akkadian *nigûtu(m)* which, among its many definitions, has the meaning “(joyful) music”⁵⁵⁵. However, we have just a tablet with this **nam-LUL.BALAD** and our conclusions must be provisional. We should also keep in mind several things:

- We are in a section of *Proto-izi* mainly devoted to professions. In this sense, an interpretation of **nam-LUL.BALAD** as a concrete type of (instrumental) music does not fit in this context. In the same way, if **nam-LUL.BALAD** had been referred to that type of reality, we would have already found other similar terms like, for instance, ***nam-a-da-ab** (“music of the **a-da-ab** (?)”). However, these terms have not been found to date.

⁵⁴⁹ Crisostomo, 2019: 393 (“musical arts”).

⁵⁵⁰ *Proto-izi*, II 218 (**nam-mah**, “majesty”), II 219 (**nam-gal**, “greatness”), II 220 (**nam-kalag-ga**, “mightiness”), II 235 (**nam-sa₆-ga**, “goodness”) (Crisostomo, 2019: 296–297).

⁵⁵¹ MSL 13, p. 48 has “nam-tigi”. However, we should have **nam-BALAD.LUL** for that. For **nam-tige₂**, see DCCLT Q000050 and Crisostomo, 2019: 296.

⁵⁵² We read **tige₂** instead of the traditional reading **tigi₂** (for instance, Krispijn, 1990: 3) following aBZL 163, 195, 196 since *Proto-Ea*, 461 (DCCLT Q000055) contains GI₄-e. That makes sense with the original writing of /**tige**/ as **ti-ge₄** (*Gudea Cylinders*, B10.9, B18.22; Römer, 2010: 33, 38). That spelling might be etymologically understood as “to approach” (**ti** < **te**η₄) + “to return” (**ge**₄).

⁵⁵³ DCCLT Q000050 (“office of the tigi player”); ePSD2 (“a designation of music”). However, Crisostomo, 2019: 393 (“tigi arts”).

⁵⁵⁴ Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“hymnische Musik, Tätigkeit als Musiker”).

⁵⁵⁵ Concerning the Old Babylonian times, we know only the reference to that term in the Hymn to Nannā for Šamšu-ilūna, VAS 10 215 [VAT 598], r. 16. In that text we find the sentence *šanīš nigûtam tēriš* (“she requested joyful music again”). However, it is in fragmentary context. See CAD N2, p. 217-218 for other (non-Old Babylonian) texts with *nigûtu(m)*.

- An administrative text has **nam-nar-sa**⁵⁵⁶, term referred to the office of the **nar** specialized in the use of stringed instruments (**sa**), a speciality mentioned in the contemporary lexical evidence⁵⁵⁷.
- The non-human gender of **tige₂** is expressed by the references to that term as an object (**niq₂**)⁵⁵⁸ or with a 3NH.POSS {**bi**}⁵⁵⁹. Therefore, **tige₂** cannot designate the musician of the **tige₂** instrument, just the instrument. Otherwise, we would expect human-gender markers with **tige₂**. In this sense, LUL.BALAD may be read as **tige₂**, but also as **nar balaq**. That makes sense since musicians of the **balaq** instrument are known before⁵⁶⁰ our spellings of /**tige**/ as **ti-ge₄**⁵⁶¹. Furthermore, **nar balaq** is documented in some administrative texts⁵⁶².

Therefore, we would read **nam-LUL.BALAD** as **nam-nar-balaq**, whose meaning would be “office of the **nar** of the **balaq**” unlike the previous interpretations. That makes sense since **nar balaq** is known as specialization of the **nar** in the Old Babylonian lexical texts⁵⁶³. Moreover, the **balaq** is played sometimes in praise contexts⁵⁶⁴. Therefore, a **nar** (and not only the **gala**) might have sounded the said instrument too.

3.2.1.3. About *nārūtum* and *narūtum*

We shall comment here an excerpt of **Niq₂-ga**. This list is placed in the elementary scribal *curriculum* of Nippur after the *Proto-izi* and *Proto-ka₂-gal*, a list not commented on here since there is no reference to **nam-nar** in that text⁵⁶⁵. Here is our excerpt:

⁵⁵⁶ TMH 10 55 [HS 2396] (Rīm-Sîn I 35-10-00), o. 4 (see *infra* for our edition of this text).

⁵⁵⁷ *Proto-lu₂*, 644 (DCCLT Q000047).

⁵⁵⁸ *Keš Temple Hymn*, 116a (Delnero, 2006: 2230) and *Nanna N*, 23, 26 (ETCSL 4.13.14).

⁵⁵⁹ *Enki and the World Order*, 448 (ETCSL 1.1.3).

⁵⁶⁰ See Tonietti, 2010: 83 and Tonietti, 2018: 19 for Early Dynastic Ebla texts, and Gelb, 1976: 57 for an overview of the Ur III Period.

⁵⁶¹ *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.9, B18.22 (Römer, 2010: 33, 38).

⁵⁶² TMH 10 25 [HS 2205] (Šamšu-ilūna 12-07-03), r. 4 (Archibab T23363).

⁵⁶³ *Proto-lu₂*, 643–643b (DCCLT Q000047).

⁵⁶⁴ *Šulgi N*, 45 (ETCSL 2.4.2.14).

⁵⁶⁵ EEN, p. 63; Robson, 2001: 47.

Text 11. **Niḡ2-ga** (monolingual version)⁵⁶⁶

73	niḡ2-^{ri-ṣa-ʿaʿ-[tum]}-me-ḡar			
	N _{I-Q}	o. iii 2'	niḡ2-^{ri-ṣa-ʿaʿ-[tum]}-[]
	N _{II/2-A}	r. iii 11'	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-me-[
	N _{II/2-B}	r. iii 6'	niḡ2	-ḡme-ḡar
	N _{II/2?-U}	o. 4	niḡ2	-ḡme^ʿ-ḡar
	N _{II/2-Y}	r. i 8'	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-me-[
	N _{II/2-Z}	r. i 5	niḡ2	-ḡme^ʿ-[
	N _{II/2-B1}	r. i 5	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-me-ḡar^ʿ
74	niḡ2-^{qu3-ʿla-ʿ-[tum]}-me-ḡar			
	N _{I-Q}	o. iii 3'	niḡ2^{qu3-ʿla-ʿ-[tum]}-[]
	N _{II/2-A}	r. iii 12'	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-me-[
	N _{II/2-B}	r. iii 7'	[]-me-ḡar
	N _{II/2-Y}	r. i 9'	niḡ2	-me-[
	N _{II/2-B1}	r. i 6	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-me-ḡar^ʿ
75	ḡniḡ2^ʿ-na-ru-[tum^ʿ]-ḡSAR^ʿ-SA[R] ⁵⁶⁸			
	N _{I-Q}	o. iii 4'	ḡniḡ2^ʿ-na-ru-[tum^ʿ]-[]
	N _{II/2-A}	r. iii 13'	ḡniḡ2^ʿ	-SAR-[
	N _{II/2-B}	Omits ⁵⁶⁹		
	N _{II/2-Y}	r. i 10'	[ni]ḡ2	-ḡSAR^ʿ-[
	N _{II/2-A1}	r. i 7'	ḡniḡ2	-SA^ʿ[R]-ḡSA[R^ʿ]
	N _{II/2-B1}	r. i 7'	ḡniḡ2	-SAR^ʿ-[

- 73 Jubilation
 74 Silence
 75 A type of malt

*Sigla*⁵⁷⁰

N _{I-Q}	MSL 13, p. 93 Q [CBS 13937 + N 6347 + 6562] (photo on CDLI P227752; collated the 22/08/2019)
N _{II/2-A}	MSL 13, p. 92 A [CBS 6560] (copy on SLT 14; photo on CDLI P229633; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2-B}	MSL 13, p. 92 B [CBS 4805] (copy on SLT 30; photo on CDLI P227955; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2?-U}	MSL 13, p. 93 U [N 4847] (photo on CDLI P229640; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2-Y}	MSL 13, p. 93 Y [CBS 6461] (copy on SLT 21; photo on CDLI P229644; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2-Z}	MSL 13, p. 93 Z [N 5072] (photo on CDLI P220645; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2-A1}	MSL 13, p. 93 A ₁ [CBS 6471] (copy on SLT 25; photo on CDLI P229646; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{II/2-B1}	MSL 13, p. 93 B ₁ [IM 58574] (photo on SP, pl. 27)

⁵⁶⁶ Own score edition starting from the consultation of the copies and photos of the manuscripts (some collated) indicated down. Sincerely thanks to Niek Veldhuis for his help with the manuscript N_{I-Q}.

⁵⁶⁷ SLT 21 see a sign ḌAR, but the traces at that point have nothing in common with that sign ḌAR.

⁵⁶⁸ See our comments *infra* for this reading instead of **mu₂** of MSL 13, p. 98 and DCCLT Q000052.

⁵⁶⁹ Line r. iii 8' seems to be line 71 = **[niḡ2-ḡal2]-la₂**.

⁵⁷⁰ They follow those of MSL 13, p. 92–93 (paying attention also to the typology of each tablet, indicated on brackets in that publication), but we put before an N (= Nippur) for their provenance.

In the last line of this text, we find a reference to an Akkadian term probably written as *na-ru-tum* which is here the equivalent of a Sumerian term normally transliterated as **niḡ2-mu2-mu2**⁵⁷¹. If we think in that *na-ru-tum* as the musical term *nārūtum*, we might think that the musical terms **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* studied here are not equivalent. That fact *a priori* might make sense since we have the Sumerogram **NAM.NAR** in an Akkadian Seleucid text⁵⁷², but there is no bilingual text with both term. We can only imagine that equivalence because of their similar connotations⁵⁷³. In addition, another **niḡ2-mu2-mu2** has the Akkadian gloss *ik-ri-b[u]* (= *ikrību*, “prayer”, “blessing”, “votive gift”)⁵⁷⁴, that is, another element related, in a certain way, with the cult, perhaps like *nārūtum*.

Nevertheless, in the previously reproduced excerpt of the monolingual **Niḡ2-ga**, the Akkadian glosses seem to have a similar meaning to the Sumerian terms. Certainly, **niḡ2-me-ḡar** may be equated with *qūlatum* (“silence”) since **me ḡar** means “to make silence” in Sumerian⁵⁷⁵. However, it may be equated to *rīšātum* (“rejoice”) since **niḡ2-me-ḡar** is sometimes mentioned in context of rejoice in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literature⁵⁷⁶. However, **niḡ2-mu2-mu2** does not make sense with the musical term *nārūtum* according to its literal meaning (“growing thing”). Therefore, that *na-ru-tum* might be actually a reference to the Akkadian *narūtum*⁵⁷⁷ (or **narratu*)⁵⁷⁸. This term would designate a type of malt in some Old Assyrian letters from Kaniš⁵⁷⁹. That would make sense with the existence of the term **niḡ2-SAR** (**mu2** is a reading of SAR), a term which might designate

⁵⁷¹ MSL 13, p. 98 and DCCLT Q000052.

⁵⁷² Koch, 2004: 106–108 [BM 55466 + 55486 + 55627], r. 26 (see our chapter about 1st Millennium evidence for an edition and comments).

⁵⁷³ This fact was already suggested by Schramm, 2008: 10 n. 30.

⁵⁷⁴ **Niḡ2-ga** = *makkūru* (bilingual version), 61 (MSL 13, p. 116).

⁵⁷⁵ Jaques, 2006: 205–217; ePSD2; Attinger, 2019d: 83.

⁵⁷⁶ Among them, *Inanna and Bilulu*, 145 (ETCSL 1.4.4) and *Instructions of Šuruppak*, 264 (CDLI P478969). See Jaques, 2006: 205–207 for other references.

⁵⁷⁷ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 n. 11–205 n. 13; Michalowski, 2010b: 118 transcribes wrongly our musical term as *narūtu*, rendering a similar word to this another one. On its behalf, Michel, 2016: 176 n. 13 offers the same transcription (*narūtum*) for this another term *narūtum*.

⁵⁷⁸ Suggestion of CAD N1, p. 382.

⁵⁷⁹ TCL 14 47 [AO 8717], o. 7 (CDLI P357537; see Michel, 2001: 478–479; Larsen, 2002: 76–77 and Michel, 2016: 174 n. 28 for comments) and VS 26 75 [VAT 13516], r. 7' (CDLI P358227).

a type of plant in some Ur III administrative texts⁵⁸⁰. Therefore, we would read the Sumerian term of **Niḡ₂-ga**, 75 not as **niḡ₂-mu₂-mu₂**, but as **niḡ₂-SAR-SAR**⁵⁸¹. About its connections with the Akkadian *ikrību*, we tend to think that **niḡ₂-SAR-SAR** = *narātu* might be understood as a product offered as “votive gift”⁵⁸². However, we do not have a clear opinion on this matter and, in any case, our textual evidence for this topic is scarce.

3.2.2. Model contracts

3.2.2.1. A text about musical teaching

We are now going to deal with the domain of model contracts⁵⁸³. Those texts were non-functional since they lacked real dates and a list of witnesses, two important elements for the legal validity of real administrative texts in Mesopotamia. Nevertheless, they were still relevant as an introduction for the scribes into real legal and administrative practice⁵⁸⁴. We shall first comment here on a text from the *Schøyen Collection* about the instruction of a young student in the use of several types of instruments and songs⁵⁸⁵.

⁵⁸⁰ We follow the interpretation of Neumann, 2004: 22 for the **niḡ₂-SAR** in the text Snell, 1982: pl. 4 3 [CUL 2] (Amar-Suena 04-00-00), r. i 9 (BDTNS 024109). Snell, 1989: 202 read “nīg-kéš” and translated as “bound (reed)”. However, signs SAR and EZEN are not quite so identical at the time (to the contrary of Neo-Assyrian and later times). In this sense, we cannot have that confusion for Ur III times. See BDTNS for other references to **niḡ₂-SAR** from the 3rd Dynasty of Ur.

⁵⁸¹ Concerning **Niḡ₂-ga**, 145, MSL 13, p. 100 reads “nīg-SAR”, but DCCLT reads “niḡ₂-sakar”. The last reading makes more sense in light of the following lines of that text, where **niḡ₂-sakar buru₃-buru₃** designates a tool (**niḡ₂-sakar**) for perforating something (**buru₃-buru₃**). In this sense, there is no apparent contradiction with our hypothesis about **niḡ₂-SAR-SAR** as a type of plant.

⁵⁸² See CAD I-J, p. 64–65 (entry 2’) for different types of votive gifts called *ikribu*.

⁵⁸³ EEN, p. 63–64; Robson, 2001: 47.

⁵⁸⁴ Spada, 2018: 3.

⁵⁸⁵ The following edition and comments have benefited from Gabriella Spada’s help. She has shared with us her edition of this text at a time when the book containing it was not yet available for purchase. In addition, she indicated to us that Michalowski, 2013 and Démare-Lafont, 2017 (two texts she could not use for her edition) also commented on this text. Thanks for all that.

Text 12. Geller, 2003: 109–111 [MS 2951]⁵⁸⁶

- o. 1 **m**ḥe_[2]-**du**₇⁵⁸⁷-**eridu**^{ki}-**ga**
o. 2 **ṛdumu**^ṛ **IM**^ṛ-**la-ma-si**₂⁵⁸⁸
o. 3 **nam-nar zu-zu-de**₃
o. 4 **ki** **DIDIR**^ṛ-**ši-ri** **ba-tuš**
o. 5 **u**₄-**ba**⁵⁸⁹ <**nam**?> -**nar** ^ṛ**ṛ****tigidla**_x^ṛ (ṚSAG₄ .MIN₃ .<DI/TAR>)⁵⁹⁰
o. 6 **asila**₃(EZEN×A)⁵⁹¹ **tige**_x(**LUL**^ṛ .**TIN.LIŠ**^ṛ)⁵⁹² **a-ṛ da**^ṛ-**ba**
o. 7 **ṛa**^ṛ-**ra**₂ **ṛ7**-**kam zu-zu-de**₃
o. 8 **5 giṇ**₄ **ku**₃-**babbar**
o. 9 **a**₂ **DIDIR**-**ši-ri**
o. 10 **md**^ṛ**IM**^ṛ-**la-ma-si**₂
o. 11 **ṛin**^ṛ-**na**-**ṛan**^ṛ-**šum**₂
r. 1 **u**₄⁵⁹³ (anepigraphic space)
r. 2 [**m**i]₃⁵⁹⁴-**li**₂-**ip-pa-al-sa**₃-**am**
r. 3 **ṛdumu**^ṛ⁵⁹⁵ **um-mi-a**

o. 1 Ḥedu-Eriduga⁵⁹⁶, o. 2 son of Adad-lamassi⁵⁹⁷, o. 4 sat with Il-širi⁵⁹⁸ o. 3 in order to learn music. o. 5–7 In those days, in order to learn the music of the ^ṛ**tigidla**_x lute (and) (how to produce) the **asila**₃ rejoicing cries of the **tige**_x and **a-da-ab** songs seven times (without fatiguing the voice too much), o. 9 Il-širi^ṛ o. 11 gave o. 8 five silver shekels o. 10 to Adad-lamassi. r. 1 Day (...) r. 2 Ilī-ippalsam⁵⁹⁹, r. 3 master's apprentice.

⁵⁸⁶ Our own edition from checking the photos of this tablet on CDLI P252010.

⁵⁸⁷ Konrad Volk (= George and Spada, 2019: 116) has [d]u₇ perhaps since U (U.GUD = du₇) is missing. However, the manuscript is slightly erased there. In this way, we prefer to follow Michalowski, 2010a: 204.

⁵⁸⁸ Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 mistakenly transcribed **si** and not **si**₂ as in the rest of the editions (Geller, 2003: 109; Shehata, 2009: 112; Michalowski, 2010a: 204; George and Spada, 2019: 116).

⁵⁸⁹ Geller, 2003: 109 mistakenly reads **ud-a**, and it was followed by Shehata, 2009: 113 and Démare-Lafont, 2017: 50. We agree, however, with Michalowski, 2010a: 204 and George and Spada, 2019: 116.

⁵⁹⁰ The transliteration of George and Spada, 2019: 116–117 as MIN₃ is also probably right.

⁵⁹¹ Geller, 2003: 109; Michalowski, 2010a: 204 and Démare-Lafont, 2017: 50 have **asila**(EZEN×LAL₂), but Shehata, 2009: 113 and George and Spada, 2019: 116 have **asila**(**I**)₃(EZEN×A). We see two vertical signs inside EZEN. That fact supports the last reading **asila**(**I**)₃ (= EZEN×A).

⁵⁹² This sign differs concerning BULUD (Geller, 2003: 109; Shehata, 2009: 205). We would follow Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“NAR.BULUĜ^ṛ”) or George and Spada, 2019: 116 (“NAR.TIN.LIŠ^ṛ”). If we accept this last interpretation, we should take into consideration that the sign LIŠ is incorrectly written.

⁵⁹³ Omitted in Michalowski, 2010a: 204 and George and Spada, 2019: 117, it is almost on the edge.

⁵⁹⁴ Piotr Michalowski (2010: 204 and 2013: 17) reads ku/i₆, while all other editions read i₃. To our mind, the sign is too broken for any supposition, but we would follow the most popular transliteration (i₃).

⁵⁹⁵ We follow George and Spada, 2019: 117, which makes sense with Michalowski, 2013: 17.

⁵⁹⁶ Geller, 2003: 109 (“Hebe-Eridu”) forgot the genitive of this name.

⁵⁹⁷ Only Shehata, 2009: 112 and George and Spada, 2019: 117 remembered this -ṛ 1SG.POSS.

⁵⁹⁸ We follow Geller, 2003: 109; Shehata, 2009: 112 and Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50. For Ilī-širi (Michalowski, 2010a: 204; Michalowski, 2013: 17; George and Spada, 2019: 117), we would expect **diṇir**-**ši-ri**, and not **diṇir**-**ši-ri**. Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“Ilu-širi”) tries to keep this aspect in mind.

⁵⁹⁹ Michalowski, 2013: 17 George and Spada, 2019: 117. However, Geller, 2013: 111 has sign NI. We cannot verify, but Ilī-ippalsanni and Ilī-ippalsam both mean something like “My god looks at me”.

We find a first reference to **nam-nar** in the third line of this text which has been normally understood as “Music”⁶⁰⁰. This translation fits well in this context, where Ḫedu-Eriduga is going to learn with Il-širī how to master two main things:

- The **tigex** and **a-da-ab**: They have sometimes been understood as two instruments⁶⁰¹. However, following other authors⁶⁰², we prefer to identify them as songs in this case since both terms are in a genitive chain together with **asila3**⁶⁰³. This said term cannot designate another instrument, but a vocal technique. Certainly, it is logographically written as EZEN×A. That suggests a connection with the **ser3** song, a term also written with that sign EZEN. Moreover, **asila3** is usually documented in Old Babylonian royal inscriptions and literary texts as a sort of cry for joy⁶⁰⁴. In our opinion, the **a-ra2 7-kam** accompanying that **asila3** should be understood as “seven times”⁶⁰⁵ and not “to the seventh degree” as Piotr Michalowski and others have sometimes understood⁶⁰⁶. Certainly, **a-ra2** means “times”⁶⁰⁷, not “degree”. Furthermore, we should have **a-ra2 7-kam-ma-še3** (that is, a sequence with a TERM {še}) for Michalowski’s interpretation. The idea of learning how to produce many times a sort of shout without

⁶⁰⁰ Geller, 2003: 109 (“music”); Shehata, 2009: 112 (“die Musikkunst”); Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“music”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“music”); Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“l’art de la musique”); Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 93 (“el arte de la música”); George and Spada, 2019: 117 (“the musician’s craft”).

⁶⁰¹ Geller, 2003: 109 (“*tigi* instrument and the *adab* instrument”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“the *tigi* and the *adab*”); George and Spada, 2019: 117 (“*tigi*, and *adab* instruments”).

⁶⁰² Shehata, 2009: 112 (“den Jubel(gesang) von Tigi und Adab”). We miss, however, an additional explanation of this term beyond Shehata, 2009: 112 n. 606 in the same monograph.

⁶⁰³ Forgotten in Geller, 2003: 109 (“the *asila*, *tigi* instrument”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“the *asila*, the *tigi*”) and George and Spada, 2019: 117 (“*asila*, *tigi*, and *adab* instruments”). Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“the skill of playing the *tigidla*, *asila*, *tigi*, and *adab* instruments/songs”) and Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“la musique de la lyre-*tigidla*, de l’instrument-*asila*, les chants (accompagnés de) l’instrument-*tigi*, des (chants)-*adab*”) supposed a long genitive <nam>.nar ... a.da.b + ak [GEN] + ø [ABS]. However, since ^{ne}tigidla_x already ends in “a”, we might suppose two genitives: <nam>.nar ^{ne}tigidla + a(k) [GEN] + ø [ABS] and **asila3.l tigex a.da.b + a(k) [GEN] + ø [ABS]**.

⁶⁰⁴ See Jaques, 2006: 35–38 for textual evidence and an etymological origin.

⁶⁰⁵ Geller, 2003: 109 (“seven times”); Shehata, 2009: 112 (“sieben Male”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“seven times”); Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“sept fois”).

⁶⁰⁶ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“to the seventh degree”; followed by George and Spada, 2019: 117).

⁶⁰⁷ ePSD (“times (with numbers)”; Attinger, 2019d: 4 (“fois”).

damaging the voice makes sense to us. Certainly, doing that action without previous training might be harmful for a long-term musical career.

- The 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 : Nele Ziegler identified this term with a type of lyre⁶⁰⁸. However, its logographic writing ($\text{ŠAG}_4.\text{MIN}_3.<\text{DI/TAR}>$) suggests to us that we have a sound-box ($\text{ŠAG}_4 = \text{šaga}$, “interior”) traversed ($\text{TAR} = \text{tar}$, “to cut”)⁶⁰⁹ by two strings (MIN_3 , a writing variation of $\text{MIN} = \text{min}$, “two”). Certainly, Egyptian lutes (which came from Mesopotamia) had only two strings⁶¹⁰. This identification of the 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 seems to be confirmed by the three lexical specializations of that term: 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 sa eš (“three-stringed 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 ”)⁶¹¹, 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 elam-ma (“ 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 of Elam”)⁶¹² and 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 kaskal-la (“ 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 of the way”)⁶¹³. Furthermore, another literary text might suggest a neck (𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠 kul , “shaft”) like the one of a lute for a 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠(DI.TAR) ⁶¹⁴.

This last term, 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 , is mentioned here together with a **nar** normally understood as $<\text{nam}>-\text{nar}$ in previous editions⁶¹⁵ and translations⁶¹⁶ of this text. While $<\text{nam}>-\text{nar}$ may be explained as one of the mistakes of the young scribe authoring this text, the supposition of a reference to **nar** implies a search for several non-existent words in this text⁶¹⁷. There have been several previous translations for this $<\text{nam}>-\text{nar}$:

⁶⁰⁸ Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“la lyre-*tigidla*”). Other editions left it unidentified (Geller, 2003: 109; Shehata, 2009: 112; Michalowski, 2010a: 204; Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50; George and Spada, 2019: 117).

⁶⁰⁹ Civil, 1987b; Krispijn, 2010b: 148.

⁶¹⁰ Turnbull, 1972: 63; Manniche, 1988: 194; von Lieven, 2008: 155; Eichmann, 2011: 25; Emerit, 2013: 3; Köpp-Junk, 2018: 95.

⁶¹¹ In light of our previous considerations, this instrument would have an extra, third string. Therefore, it would make sense to have a recognized identification for that variety of 𐎧𐎥𐎴𐎠𐎠 .

⁶¹² This speciality makes sense with the lute players depicted in several Old and Middle Elamite clay plaques. See Krispijn, 2011: 116–117 and Caubet, 2016: 37–40 for reference. In addition, see Ziegler, 1996: 479–480 [M. 8426+9046], o. 6’ (original publication) for a *tikkittalû* female player together with another one of the *paraḥšitum* instrument, which comes from Marḥaši, an Iranian region.

⁶¹³ See Krispijn, 2011: 116 for the itinerant lute players of the Old Babylonian clay plaques

⁶¹⁴ *Proverbs* 5.124 (Michalowski, 2010a: 224).

⁶¹⁵ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“ $<\text{nam}^?>-\text{nar}$ ”).

⁶¹⁶ Geller, 2003: 109 (“singing”); Shehata, 2009: 112 (“die Musik”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“singing”); Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“la musique”).

⁶¹⁷ Like George and Spada, 2019: 117 (“teach (his son to be) a musician (playing)”).

- Something like “(profession) of the **nar**”⁶¹⁸. This translation does not recognize that, in Old Babylonian times, the ^{neš}**tigidla** seems to not be played by the **nar**⁶¹⁹. On the one hand, a **ke-ze₂-er** uses a ^{neš}**tigidla**(DI.TAR) in a literary text⁶²⁰. On the other hand, a letter from Mari has *ša munus ti-in-ki₂-ta-al-lim* (“of the woman of the *tikkittallû* instrument”) after a reference to a group of *nārtu* musicians⁶²¹. If that letter mentioned a *nārtu* musician of the *tikkittallû* instrument, we would expect just *ša ti-in-ki₂-ta-al-lim*. The *nārtu* musicians of this text are certainly referred as “these (= *an-ne₂-tim*) musicians”. Therefore, we believe that the **nar** would not usually play such an instrument, and a reference to its profession would not be logical in this context.
- “Skill of playing”⁶²². This translation requires the term **e-ne-di** (“play”) sometimes used with instruments⁶²³, or the verb **du₁₂** (“to play (an instrument)”)⁶²⁴.
- “Singing”⁶²⁵. This translation is also not suitable in this context, since <**nam**>-**nar** refers to an instrument (the ^{neš}**tigidla_x**), and not a group of songs.

In this sense, we would agree with those having translated <**nam**>-**nar** as “music”⁶²⁶. Such a translation would imply that **nam-nar** could have a similar meaning to our “music” as an organized group of sounds with a certain artistic aim. That translation seems to be probable in light of the text *Šulgi B*, 157 to be considered below.

⁶¹⁸ Geller, 2003: 109 (“singing”); Démare-Lafont, 2016–2017: 50 (“singing”).

⁶¹⁹ This situation would come from the 3rd Dynasty of Ur, where the player of this instrument was simply known as **lu₂** ^{neš}**tigidla**. For reference, see UET 3 15 [U. 4864 (IM envelope) + U. 7002 (BM tablet)] (*Šulgi* 47-00-00), o. 8 (BDTNS 010320); PDT 2 1120 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 04-02-02), o. 7 (BDTNS 031251); UDT 97 [NBC 97] (Amar-Suena 04-09-19), r. 21 (BDTNS 005482).

⁶²⁰ *The Slave and the Scoundrel*, 24 (Shehata, 2007: 523). See Shehata, 2009: 103 for additional comments on this excerpt.

⁶²¹ Ziegler, 1996: 479–480 [M.8426+9046], o. 5’–6’ (Archibab T4845).

⁶²² Shehata, 2009: 112 (“die Musik”); Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“la musique”).

⁶²³ *Cursing of Agade*, 35 (ETCSL 2.1.5).

⁶²⁴ ePSD; Attinger, 2019d: 44.

⁶²⁵ Michalowski, 2010a: 204 (“the skill of playing”).

⁶²⁶ George and Spada, 2019: 117 (“a musician”).

3.2.2.2. A text about the construction of an instrument?

We are now going to deal with an excerpt of a very badly preserved, 12-columned tablet from Isin with different model legal texts⁶²⁷. Among these texts, we have a marriage contract with a parity divorce clause with waivers, custody clauses, and oath formula⁶²⁸. We have also an apprenticeship contract about the profession of the cook (**nam-muḥaldim**)⁶²⁹ and this following contract involving the term **nam-nar**⁶³⁰:

Text 13. Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534]⁶³¹

r. iii 1' [...]

r. iii 2' [...]

r. iii 3' [...] 'x'

r. iii 4' [...] 'x'-ra

r. iii 5' 'x' [... -b]al

r. iii 6' **tukum-b[e₂(x)] 'x'**

r. iii 7' ^mr e₂'-a-re-'š_u₂'-š_u

r. iii 8' 'x'-DEŠ-lu₂-kam šeš šu dus-a-ne₂

r. iii 9' **gu₂-ne₂ ba-ra-an-šub**

r. iii 10' **a₂[?] kalag-<ga>⁶³² nam-nar-r[a]**

r. iii 11' **nu-mu-na-an-du₃[?]**

r. iii 12' **2/3 giṇ₄ ku₃-babbar**

r. iii 13' **KA la-ba-KA[?].NI[?]- 'x'**

r. iii 14' **šu-ta(?) ba-ab-'x x'**

r. iii 15' **nam-nar-ra in-ne-d[a-x]**

r. iii 16' **ku₃ šu ba-ab-te-ṇa₂**

r. iii 17' ^mgub-ba-ne₂-dug₃ ad-da-ne₂

r. iii 18' **kišib-ba-ne₂ in-na-an-taka₄**

r. iii 19' **mu lugal-bi in-pad₃**

r. iii 1'-5' [...] r. iii 6' i[f ...] r. iii 7' Ea-rēš_uš_u r. iii 9' neglected r. iii 8' [...] his captive brother, r. iii 10-11' he did not made the strong arm (?) o[f] the music for him. r. iii 13' [...] r. iii 16' accepted r. iii 12' 2/3 of a silver shekel r. iii 14' from the hand of [...] r. iii 15' for the music [...]. r. iii 17' Gubbane-dug, his father, r. iii 18' left behind his seal (and) r. iii 19' swore that by the king.

⁶²⁷ See Wilcke, 1987: 104–105 for contents and their distribution in the tablet.

⁶²⁸ Stol, 2016: 213.

⁶²⁹ Waetzoldt, 1989: 33; Volk, 2011: 279.

⁶³⁰ See Wilcke, 1987: 104; Waetzoldt, 1989: 33; Volk, 1994: 185 n. 50; Volk, 2006: 22 n. 52; Shehata, 2009: 113–114, 152 and Michalowski, 2010a: 205 n. 13 for previous comments, but no translation. We have tried to be as literal as possible in our translation of this text.

⁶³¹ Edition dependent upon Wilcke, 1987: 104–105 and Shehata, 2009: 114 n. 613. Unfortunately, there is no copy/photo of this manuscript available for consultation.

⁶³² Wilcke, 1987: 105 has “DA.KALAG” (followed by Shehata, 2009: 114 n. 613). As far as we know, there is no Sumerian word with DA and KAL(AG). However, keeping in mind the similarities between A₂ and DA, we might have **a₂ kalag**, a possible musical element as we describe *infra*. We would expect **a₂ kalag-ga** (like in *Winter and Summer*, 165, 261; ETCSL 5.3.3), but this might be a scribal mistake.

The term **nam-nar** has normally been understood in this excerpt as a learned profession⁶³³. However, it has also been suggested that it is a (temple) prebend⁶³⁴. Both interpretations are problematic in our opinion. On the one hand, unlike the apprenticeship contract about the profession of the cook (**nam-muḥaldim**) mentioned in the same text, we do not find any reference to the verb **zu** (“to learn”) in this case⁶³⁵. On the other hand, it is true that **nam-nar du₃** might be understood as “to perform the profession of the **nar**”. Certainly, **du₃** is lexically equated with *epēšum* (“to do/perform”)⁶³⁶. This term is sometimes used with *nārūtum* for making reference to the performance of an office⁶³⁷. Nevertheless, in those cases we normally have **ak**⁶³⁸ (also equated with *epēšum*)⁶³⁹.

In addition to these considerations, we should keep in mind that we have **nam-nar-ra**, that is, **nam-nar** and a case marker. In r. iii 15’ that case marker seems to be a locative according to the context (**in-ne-d[a-x]** seems to be a verbal form). However, in r. iii 10’ **nam-nar** seems to have a GEN {**ak**} since it is placed after what we have read as **a₂**[?] **kalag**. The complete chain (**a₂**[?] **kalag**-<**ga**> **nam-nar-r[a]**, literally “strong arm of the music”) might designate a musical element, perhaps the neck of a lute. In fact, the neck of the ^{neš}**su-kar₂** lute is called **a₂** (literally “arm”)⁶⁴⁰. In addition, **du₃**, the verb modifying that chain, also means “to build” or “to erect”⁶⁴¹. In this context, it might refer to the construction of the neck of a lute. Certainly, the Akkadian *epēšum* is used sometimes for the construction of musical instruments⁶⁴².

⁶³³ Wilcke, 1987: 104 (“Lehrvertrag über Gesangskunst”); Waetzoldt, 1989: 33 (“die Ausbildung zum Koch oder Sänger”); Volk, 1994: 185 referred to this text as one of our Old Babylonian contracts regulating the training of a young musician with a master; Volk, 2006: 22 n. 52 (“einem altbabylonischen Lehrvertrag, der die Ausbildung eines Jungmusikers regelt”); Shehata, 2009: 113 (“Lehrvertrag über Musik”); Volk, 2011: 279 (“Eine Ausbildung zum Koch/Bäcker bzw. Hymnoden”).

⁶³⁴ Michalowski, 2010a: 205 (“office or prebend rather than musical apprenticeship”).

⁶³⁵ Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534], r. ii’ 9.

⁶³⁶ *Karpeles 1*, CUSAS 12 13 [PAS 27], r. i 25 (DCCLT).

⁶³⁷ ARM 1 78 (Šamši-Addu 00-00-00), r. 4–5; FM 9 27 [M.13050] (Šamši-Addu 00-00-00), r. 2–4 (see *infra* for our editions of these texts).

⁶³⁸ Attinger, 2005: 209.

⁶³⁹ **Lu₂-azlag₂** B–C, Segment 2, 167 (DCCLT Q000302).

⁶⁴⁰ *Šulgi B*, 159 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

⁶⁴¹ ePSD; Attinger, 2019d: 34.

⁶⁴² For instance, FM 9 11 [ARM 13 20] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), r. 1–4 (Archibab T6571).

Therefore, we would translate **nam-nar** here as “music” according to our hypothesis about **a2’ kalag-<ga>**. In any case, everything should be seen as hypothetical in light of the preservation of this text and our sources for accessing its content.

3.2.3. Elementary literary texts

We arrive finally at the last step in the elementary curriculum: the proverbs. These texts were an introduction to the Sumerian literary texts to be studied in depth in the second (and elective) part of the scribal curriculum⁶⁴³. In any case, they were useful for their moral lessons⁶⁴⁴. There is a reference to **nam-nar** in one of these proverbs:

Text 14. *Proverbs* 3.150⁶⁴⁵

1	eridu^{ki} ħe2-ġal2-la du3-a-ba^{ug^u} uġu4-bi				
	N _{I-H} r. vii 8’	eridu^{ki}	ħe2-ġal2-’la’	du3 -a -ba	ug^u uġu4 -bi /
	N _{I-X} o. iv 23–24	’eridu^{ki}	ħe2’-ġal2 -la	[du3]-a -ba /	’ug^u’ uġu4-’bi’
	N _{U-JJ} o. 3’	’eridu^{[k]i}	ħe2 -ġal2 -la	du3 -a	’ug^u’ uġu4 -bi
2	e2 nar <gal>-la-ka igi-la2-bi ba-tuš				
	N _{I-H} r. vii 9’	e2	nar <gal>-’la-kam’	igi-’tums’-la2’	al -’tuš’
	N _{I-X} o. iv 24–25	’e2	nar’ -ra-ka /	’igi’ -la2 -bi’	’ba’ -tuš’
	N _{U-JJ} o. 4’	e2’	na[m]-nar -ra-ka	’igi -la2’-bi	ba’-[tu]š’
1	In its (city of) Eridu, built in abundance, the monkey				
2	is seated with an eager look inside the house of the chief musician.				

*Sigla*⁶⁴⁶

N _{I-H}	Alster, 1997: pl. 22 [Ni 3172] ⁶⁴⁷ + ISET 2 100–101 + 103 + 120 [Ist. Ni 4444f. + 4457 + 9644] (publication copy).
N _{I-X}	Alster, 1997: pl. 31 [IM 58434] (publication photo)
N _{U-JJ}	ISET 1 168 [Ist. Ni 9493] (publication copy)

⁶⁴³ EEN, p. 63–64; Veldhuis, 2000: 383–386.

⁶⁴⁴ Pearce, 1996: 2271; Veldhuis, 2000: 385.

⁶⁴⁵ Our own edition in “real score” keeping in mind the variants of Alster, 1997: 106. We have corrected Alster’s transliterations through the inspection of the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

⁶⁴⁶ They follow Alster, 1997: 76–78, but we put an N (= Nippur) for their provenance and, since they belong to Nippur, we put also an I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain). This procedure is more common in lexical texts, but it tries to follow Paul Delnero’s procedure for literary texts, and we shall use it in all our following literary texts. See Delnero, 2006: 1857–2473 for examples, and Delnero, 2010: 54 for argumentation.

⁶⁴⁷ Not collated since our excerpt is actually contained in the join ISET 2 101 [Ist. Ni 4457].

In this text, we have a mention of the expression **e2 nam-nar-ra** (literally “house of music”). This expression, which will appear in *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188 (a text to be commented on in the next chapter) is a variant in the second line of this text together with **e2 nar-ra** (“house of the nar”) and **e2 nar <gal>-la** (“house of the chief musician”). *A priori*, **e2 nam-nar-ra** might be understood as a reference to the house of a musician⁶⁴⁸. However, we have two reasons for dismissing that identification.

On the one hand, in addition to other writing mistakes, signs E₂ (= **e2**) and NUN (= **eridu**) are identical in manuscript N_{U-JJ}. That makes sense keeping in mind that this text might have been copied by a young scribe who, perhaps, still had some problems with Sumerian. In this case, such mistake invite us to read ***nun na[m]-nar-ra** instead of **e2' na[m]-nar-ra**. On the other hand, the scene described in this text is similar to the one from “*Monkey*” to his mother⁶⁴⁹. In that text, the student Ugubi (^{ug}**ugu4-bi** = “monkey”) complains about his miserable life in Eridu, where he lives and learns music with the chief musician (**nar gal**) of said city⁶⁵⁰.

Therefore, for *Proverbs* 3.150, 2, we should select **e2 nar gal-la** or **e2 nar-ra** for a composite line of that text. The variant **e2 nar-ra** has usually been preferred⁶⁵¹. Certainly, from a grammatical perspective, manuscript N_{I-X} is the best written variant of the three of this text. However, in this case, we prefer to sacrifice the grammar and to place an **e2 nar <gal>-la** in order to reinforce the noted parallels of this text with “*Monkey*” to his mother. In addition, as we shall comment on later, the **nar gal** could act as a music teacher or musical organizer, but never as a performer.

3.3. Legal Texts

3.3.1. Introduction

The following pages will be a study of the presence of the term **nam-nar** in some legal texts from the Isin and Larsa Dynasties. We shall normally be constrained here to

⁶⁴⁸ Taylor, 2005: 29 translated **nam-nar** as “singers” (therefore, **e2 nam-nar-ra** as “house of the singers”). However, we would have expected in the text something like **e2 nar-e-ne-ka**.

⁶⁴⁹ “*Monkey*” to his mother, 6 (Kleinerman, 2011: 158 and 278).

⁶⁵⁰ Ziegler, 2013: 55; Pruzsinszky, 2016: 26–27.

⁶⁵¹ Alster, 1997: 106; ETCSL 6.1.03 and Shehata, 2009: 35.

translate **nam-nar** as “office of the **nar**”. The reason is that **nam-nar** is usually mentioned with the name of the deity whom that musician served with music.

3.3.2. About musicians and anointed priests

We shall study some texts from the first conflict between Dudu-Kalla and Lugal-gabari-nutuku and their families due to the (supposed) irregularities in the distribution of the temple prebends of their father, the **nar** Lu-Ninurta I⁶⁵². These prebends, or positions, concerned the office of the **nar**, but also the **gudu₄** priest⁶⁵³ as in this case:

Text 15. ARN 4 [Ist. Ni 9201] (Būr-Sîn 00-12-10)⁶⁵⁴

- o. ii 1” ^rd¹ n[in[?]-...]
o. ii 2” ^rd¹ ni[n[?]...]
o. ii 3” ^din[anna[?] ...]
o. ii 4” ḫa-la-ba d[u-du-kal-la]
o. ii 5” ibila-n[e-ne]
o. ii 6” šu ba-an-[ti-eš]
o. ii 7” 1 nam-[nar]⁶⁵⁵
o. ii 8” ^dnin-nibru^[ki]
o. ii 9” u₃ e₂ ^dina[nna]
o. ii 10” gudu₄ keše₂⁶⁵⁶-d[a ^dnin-urta]
o. ii 11” ^dnin-ni[bru^{ki(?)}]
o. ii 12” šu-ri-^ra[?]-[be₂]
o. ii 13” ^dnin-^rx[?] [...]
o. ii 14” ^d[...]

o. ii 1–3” [...] o. ii 5” The he[irs] o. ii 6” have [accepted] o. ii 4” the inheritance share of Dudu-Kalla: o. ii 12” the half [of] o. ii 7” the condition of **nar** o. ii 8” of Ninnibru, o. ii 9” and the temple of Inanna, o. ii 10” (in addition to) the (condition of the) “attached” **gudu₄** anointed priest of Ninurta o. ii 11” and Ninni[bru]. o. ii 13–14” [...]

The process reflected in this document has some supplementary texts where the offices of the **nar** and **gudu₄** anointed priest are also mentioned. Here is one of those

⁶⁵² See Kraus, 1951: 187–208 and Shehata, 2009: 162–164, 172 for references and descriptions of the complete legal/administrative process.

⁶⁵³ For the functions of this priest, see Renger, 1969: 162; Hutter, 1996: 88.

⁶⁵⁴ Edition dependent on Archibab “Renger Corpus Berlin” with modifications derived from the inspection of the handwritten copy from the original publication.

⁶⁵⁵ Reconstruction as [nar] is possible in this context due to the condition of Lu-Ninurta I as **nar**.

⁶⁵⁶ Renger, 1969: 162 read “gudu₄ šir-da”. However, sign EZEN/ŠER₃/KEŠDA (according to aBZL 152a-c, there are three subtypes of a similar sign in Old Babylonian times; what we see in the handwritten copy is more similar to KEŠDA) has normally been read as **keše₂**. See Kraus, 1951: 205; Shehata, 2009: 17–18, 57 n. 287, 173; Archibab “Renger Corpus Berlin”, p. 11 for discussion.

supplementary texts. In this case, the **gudu₄** priest appears in the last inheritance share of the three mentioned here:

Text 16. ARN 58 [Ist. Ni 2182] (Bür-Sîn 00-00-00)⁶⁵⁷

- o. 1 [nam-nar] ^d[en-ki *u*₃ ^dasal-lu₂-*hi* igi-3-*η*al₂-bi-*še*₃]
o. 2 [x x] ^rd⁶⁵⁸ ^rx x x ^r659
o. 3 [nam]-nar[?] ^dlugal-ban₃-^rda mu-am₃ [itu]d.[6]
o. 4 ^rd^ri-*šum* ^rša x x x^r
o. 5 ^rd^rnin-si₄-an-^rna^r ba-la-a
o. 6 [^d]nin-maš-ku₃-ga
o. 7 [^d]gu₂-^ra₂-nun[?]-ge₄-a
o. 8 [^d]^ršul'-pa-e₃-^ra^r-dar-a igi-3-*η*al₂-bi-*še*₃^r
o. 9 *ha*-la-ba-1-am₃
o. 10 [nam]-^rnar^r ^den-ki ^r*u*₃ ^dasal-lu₂-*hi* igi-3-*η*al₂-bi-*še*₃
o. 11 ^rnam[?]-^rnar ^dlugal'-ban₃-da ^rmu¹-am₃ itud-6
o. 12 ^dlugal'-tilla
o. 13 ^dgibil
o. 14 ^dšul-pa-e₃-a *ša*^(?) <e₂>-sa₂-dug₄
o. 15 [x x l]u ak UM BI TUM
o. 16 ^dšul'-pa-e₃-dar-a igi-3-*η*al₂-bi-[*še*₃]
o. 17 ^rd^rigi-šag₅-šag₅
lo. e ^r*ha*-la-ba-2-am₃
r. 1 ^rnam'-nar ^den-ki ^r*u*₃ ^dasal-lu₂-*hi* igi-3-*η*al₂-bi-*še*₃
r. 2 [x] **gudu₄**(?) ta du₇ SAĤAR-ra
r. 3 [^d]li-si₄
r. 4 [^d]mar-tu a-KU GAN₂-nun-ti
r. 5 [^d]nin-PA
r. 6 [^d]i-šum *ša* ^dnin-urta-ba-ni
r. 7 [^d]gu-la
r. 8 [^d]ir²-da
r. 9 [^dšul-p]a-e₃-^rdar-a^r i[gi]-3²-[*η*al₂-bi-*še*₃]
r. 10 [*ha*-l]a-b[a] ^r3^r-[am₃]

o.⁹ First inheritance share is o.¹ [the condition of **nar** of Enki and Asallu_{hi} in one third], o.² [...] o.³ [the condition of] **nar** of Lugalbanda this year (for) [six mont]hs, o.⁴ (the condition of **nar** of) Išum of [...], o.⁵ of Ninsi'anna in the libation, o.⁶ of Ninmaškuga, o.⁷ of Guanungia, o.⁸ (and) one third of (the condition of **nar** of) Šulpa'eadara.

lo. e. Second inheritance share is o.¹⁰ [the condition of] **nar** of Enki and Asallu_{hi} in one third, o.¹¹ the condition of **nar** of Lugalbanda this year for six months, o.¹² (the condition of **nar** of) Lugal-tilla, o.¹³ Gibil, o.¹⁴ Šulpae'a of the Esadug, o.¹⁵ [...] o.¹⁶ Šulpa'eadara [in] one third o.¹⁷ (and) Igišagšag.

r.¹⁰ Third [inheritance share is] r.¹ the condition of **nar** of Enki and Asallu_{hi} in one third, r.² [...] the **gudu₄** priest [...], r.³ Lisi(n), r.⁴ Martu [...], r.⁵ NinPA, r.⁶ Išum of Ninurta-Bāni, r.⁷ Gula, r.⁸ Irda r.⁹ (and) Šulpa'eadara [in one third].

⁶⁵⁷ Edition dependent upon Archibab "Renger Corpus Berlin" with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy of the original publication.

⁶⁵⁸ Johannes Renger proposes a "dingir" (archibab.fr "Renger Corpus Berlin", ARN 58).

⁶⁵⁹ Kraus, 1951: 199 has "[i]g i 3 g[á l . b i . š è]". However, the tablet is not so well-preserved in this section, and we do not understand why writing in two lines what could be written in a single one.

This supplementary document for the administrative process we are commenting on does not contain any reference to the **gudu4** priest. However, perhaps that profession was mentioned as a part of the original context of the text in light of our previous comments:

Text 17. Kraus, 1951: 200–201 [Ist. Ni 2181] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00)⁶⁶⁰

- o. 1' [... **k**jug-g[a⁽²⁾]
- o. 2' [...]-e3-a DAR-a
- o. 3' [... **ḥ**a-la-ba-1-a[m3]
- o. 4' **n**[am-n]a[r] d^r en^r-ki u₃ d^aasal-l[u₂-ḥi ...]
- o. 5' **nam-nar** d^lugal-ban3-da **igi-3-ḡ**[al2 ...]
- o. 6' ^rzag ta^r EŠ dⁿnin-e2-dar-a
- o. 7' [...] **igi-3-ḡ**al2-bi-še3
- o. 8' ^dḥi^r-si4
- o. 9' dⁿnin-PA
- o. 10' d^rigi^r-šags-^ršags^r

o. 1' [... Nink]ugg[a], o. 2' [... Šulpa]'eadara, o. 3' [...] i[s] one [in]heritance share.

o. 4' The co[ndition of **n**a[r] of Enki and Asal-l[uḥi...], o. 5' one third of the condition of **nar** of Lugal-banda, o. 6' from the side [...] Ninedara, o. 7' one third of [...] o. 8' Lisi, o. 9' NinPA o. 10' (and) Igišagšag. [...] is one inheritance share].

The previously discussed texts concern the inheritance of several temple prebends. In this sense, connections between **nar** and **gudu4** priests might just have an economic origin as two rentable incomes. However, Lu-Ninurta I was a **nar**⁶⁶¹ and, therefore, very probably had to perform music for the deities as indicated in our Texts 15–17. As a consequence of that, we suppose that he also sometimes had to act as a **gudu4** priest or, at least, to participate in some rituals performed by this type of priest. We suppose the same concerning his sons (also musicians)⁶⁶².

However, how that was possible? What things were in common in the professions of the **nar** and **gudu4** priest? In order to answer that question, we should keep in mind that **gudu4** priests performed bloodless rituals like offerings to the dead⁶⁶³ or lustrations⁶⁶⁴. In

⁶⁶⁰ Edition dependent upon Kraus, 1951: 200–201 with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy of Kraus, 1951: 185.

⁶⁶¹ Shehata, 2009: 169–170 n. 955, 172–173.

⁶⁶² Shehata, 2009: 170 n. 955, 174. Because of that we prefer the translation of **nam-nar** in these texts by Kraus, 1951: 205 (“die Sängerstelle”) instead of Sommerfeld, 1972: 13 (“Sängerpfründen”) or Shehata, 2009: 173 (“(die) nar-Pfründen”). In our opinion, the idea of “position” reflects better the duties of this people in addition to the prebendary benefices, beneficiaries whose existence we are not negating for this case.

⁶⁶³ Renger, 1969: 162; Hutter, 1996: 88.

⁶⁶⁴ *Enlil A*, 58 (Attinger, 2015: 21); *Grain and Sheep*, 110–112 (Mittermayer, 2019: 200).

this sense, in order to remain pure for those rituals, they used to smear their bodies with oil⁶⁶⁵. Certainly, the performance of some musical activities in those rituals might have been common because some instruments⁶⁶⁶, songs⁶⁶⁷, even intervals⁶⁶⁸ (and possibly musicians⁶⁶⁹) were also considered to be “pure” in Old Babylonian texts.

Therefore, musical agents could share the same purity as that required for the **gudu₄** priests. In this sense, **nar** and **gudu₄** priests could take part in the same rituals and, as a consequence, their prebends could be easily inherited/assumed by the same person despite the differences between both professions.

3.3.3. Some comments about several recently published texts

3.3.3.1. Introduction

The publication in 2016 of the Old Babylonian legal texts from Nippur conserved in the *Hilprecht Sammlung* has provided several new legal texts about prebends from Nippur with the term **nam-nar**⁶⁷⁰. Their information is certainly relevant for the understanding of **nam-nar** (again referred to the office of the **nar**, and not “music” *lato sensu*⁶⁷¹) in this type of texts. Nevertheless, because of their still recent publication, they have not yet been fully analysed regarding their musical information⁶⁷². In consequence, we shall consider them in the following pages.

⁶⁶⁵ Renger, 1969: 161; Steinkeller, 2017: 86–87.

⁶⁶⁶ *Enki's journey to Nippur*, 66 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 95) (^{ne}**al-ḡar** instrument); *Iddin-Dagān A*, 35–43 (Attinger, 2014a: 18) (^{ne}**al-ḡar**, **ub₇**, **li-li-is₃** and **balan_ḡ** instruments); *Inanna and Enki*, II vi 24 (Farber-Flüge, 1973: 60) (about the **tige₂** drum); *Šulgi C*, B 90 (ETCSL 2.4.2.03) (about the **balan_ḡ** drum).

⁶⁶⁷ We think especially about the **ser₃ ku₃** (“the pure **ser₃** song”). See Shehata, 2009: 266–268 for a description and reference to many Old Babylonian sources for this type of song.

⁶⁶⁸ UET 7 74 [U. 7/80], o. 4–7 (Krispijn, 2002: 472).

⁶⁶⁹ ARM 10 126 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), lo. e. 1–r. 1 (Archibab T8687) talks about a group of 30 weavers destined for the Subarean ensemble (*šitrum*) who could have no defects on their bodies. Nevertheless, this “purity” obviously referred to their physical beauty. See Ziegler, 2015: 203 for comments.

⁶⁷⁰ TMH 10, p. 3–4.

⁶⁷¹ TMH 10, p. 495 (“office of the musician”).

⁶⁷² Some of them have been considered to be part of the purchase activities of their main protagonist, Ur-Pabilsaḡ (van Wyk, 2018: 18). However, there is no specific reference to music in those studies.

3.3.3.2. Musicians and **bur-šu-ma** officials

The following text concerns the activities of Ur-Pabilsaḡ, the youngest son of the **nar** Ubārum⁶⁷³. When his father died, Ur-Pabilsaḡ will buy a field and temple offices in Nippur with the purpose of rivaling his brothers⁶⁷⁴. Our Text 18 is an example of those purchases involving the office of the **nar**. This Text 18 dates before the texts 19a and b published by Anne Godderis and to be commented here in a moment. Here is said text:

Text 18. ARN 35 [Ist. Ni 1922] (Rīm-Sîn I 37-10-00)⁶⁷⁵

- o. 1 **nam-nar** ^dlugal-^rab`-{**ta**}-**a**⁶⁷⁶
o. 2 *u*₃ ^dmar-tu **niḡ**₂ *ša-am-na-am a-ku-ul*⁶⁷⁷
o. 3 **nam-nar** ḡir₃-ne₂-i₃-sa₃ **dumu** ^dsuen-iš-me-ni
o. 4 **ki** ḡir₃-ne₂-i₃-sa₃ **dumu** ^dsuen-iš-me-ni
o. 5 ^mur-^dpa-bil₂-saḡ-ke₄ **dumu** *u-bar-ru-um*
o. 6 **in-ši-in-sa**₁₀
o. 7 **šam**₂-til-la-bi-še₃
o. 8 **2/3** gin₂ ku₃-babbar
o. 9 **in-na-an-la**₂
o. 10 **u**₄-kur₂-še₃ ḡir₃-ne₂-i₃-sa₃
o. 11 **u**₃ ibila-a-^rne₂ a-na-me`-a-bi
r. 1 **inim** nu-um-ḡa₂-ḡa₂-a
r. 2 **mu** ^rlugal`-bi in-pad₃

^{o. 5} Ur-Pabilsaḡ, son of Ubārum, ^{o. 6} has bought ^{o. 4} (that) from Dirne-Isa, son of Sîn-išmēni: ^{o. 1} the condition of **nar** of Lugal-a'abba ^{o. 2} and Martu, property of [...], ^{o. 3} the condition of **nar** belonging to Dirne-Isa, son of Sîn-išmēni. ^{o. 9} He (= Ur-Pabilsaḡ) has paid to him (= Dirne-Isa) ^{o. 8} 2/3 shekels of silver ^{o. 7} in total, and ^{r. 2} he (= Dirne-Isa) has sworn by the king's name that, ^{o. 10} in the future, Dirne-Isa, ^{o. 11} or his heirs, ^{r. 1} will not make a claim ^{o. 11} about all that.

⁶⁷³ Renger, 1969: 185.

⁶⁷⁴ Stone and Owen, 1991: 11, 14–15, 18; TMH 10, p. 361, 365.

⁶⁷⁵ Edition dependent upon Archibab “Renger Corpus Berlin” with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy in the original publication.

⁶⁷⁶ We follow Richter, 1999: 115. Shehata, 2009: 170 has Lugal-abta, a wholly unattested deity. We recommend the consultation of Richter, 1999 for all the divine names appearing in these legal texts, divine names whose nature and identification are unfortunately a bit far from the aim of this study.

⁶⁷⁷ Our reading of the line combines the readings from Kraus, 1951: 143 and Archibab “Renger Corpus Berlin”. We agree with Renger that the first sign of this line should be read **niḡ**₂ (“thing”, “property”) since it describes that these temple conditions belong to someone. However, the Akkadian *ša* is incompatible with **niḡ**₂ because it has the same function as relative pronouns. In the same way, we prefer the reading of the rest of the signs by Fritz Kraus, especially the sign GU₄×KUR (= **am**). Certainly, the interior of the sign we can read on ARN 35 has three *Winkelhaken*. These three *Winkelhaken* may be a sign KUR. In any case, the meaning of this line still remains unclear to us.

Here is one of the texts published by Anne Goddeeris involving the term **nam-nar**:

Text 19a. TMH 10 58a [HS 2072]
(Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00)⁶⁷⁸

o. 1 ʿnam-nar^dlugal-ʿir⁹-ra
niq₂ ud-da-da
o. 2 <nam-nar>^diškur
niq₂ ḥa-bi-il-ʿki⁷-nu-um
o. 3 ʿu₃ bur-šu-ma tur₃-ra-na
o. 4 ʿa-na me-a-bi
o. 5 ki ku₃-^dnin-gal dumu ib-ni-ia
o. 6 ^mur-^dpa-bil₂-saḡ-ḡa₂
dumu u-bar-ru-um
o. 7 in-ši-in-ʿsa₁₀
o. 8 šam₂ til-la-bi-ʿše₃⁷
o. 9 ʿ1/3⁷ giḡ₄ 15 še ku₃-babbar
r. 1 in-na-an-la₂
r. 2 u₄ kur₂-še₃ ku₃-^dnin-gal
r. 3 ʿu₃ ibila-a-ne₂ a-na-me-a-bi
r. 4 nam-nar inim nu-um-ḡa₂-ḡa₂-a
r. 5 ʿmu⁷ lugal-bi in-pad₃

Text 19b. TMH 10 58b [HS 2116]
(Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00)⁶⁷⁹

o. 1 nam-nar^dlugal-ir⁹-ra
o. 2 niq₂ ud-da-da
o. 3 nam-nar^diškur⁷
o. 4 niq₂ ḥa-bi-il-ki⁷-nu-um
o. 5 u₃ bur-šu-ma tur₃-ra-na
o. 6 a-na me-a-bi
o. 7 ki ʿku₃-^dnin-gal dumu ib-ni-ia
o. 8 ^mur-^dpa-bil₂-saḡ-ḡa₂⁷
dumu u-bar-ru-um
o. 9 in-ʿši-in-sa₁₀
o. 10 šam₂ til-la-bi-ʿše₃
o. 11 1/3 giḡ₄ 15 še ku₃-babbar⁷
r. 1 in-na-an-la₂
r. 2 u₄ ku[r₂-š]e₃ ku₃-^dnin-gal
r. 3 u₃ ibil[a]-ʿa-na-me-a-bi
r. 4 nam-nar ini[m] nu-um-ḡa₂-ḡa₂-a
r. 5 mu lugal-bi in-pad₃⁷

o. 6 / o. 8⁶⁸⁰ Ur-Pabilsaḡ, son of Ubārum, o. 7 / o. 9 has bought o. 4 / o. 6 all these things o. 5 / o. 7 from Ku-Ningal, son of Ibnīya: o. 1 / o. 1-2 the condition of the **nar** of Lugal-Irra belonging to Udada, and o. 2 / o. 3-4 the condition of the **nar** of Iškur belonging to Ḥabil-Kinum o. 3 / o. 5 in addition to the condition of the **bur-šu-ma** of his courtyard.

r. 1 / r. 1 He (= Ur-Pabilsaḡ) has paid to him (= Ku-Ningal) o. 9 / o. 11 1/3 shekel of silver and 15 shekels of barley o. 8 / o. 10 in total. r. 5 / r. 5 He (= Ku-Ningal) has sworn by the king's name that, r. 2 / r. 2 in the future, Ku-Ningal, r. 3-4 / r. 3-4 or his heir, will not make a claim (about) the office of the **nar**.

For uncertain reasons⁶⁸¹, this text is a *quasi*-duplicate of the following (together with its envelope) also published by Anne Goddeeris:

⁶⁷⁸ Edition dependent upon TMH 10, p. 143 with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy (TMH 10, pl. 75), the image on the CD attached to that publication, and the photo/3D model available on HAO.

⁶⁷⁹ Edition dependent upon TMH 10, p. 143 with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy (TMH 10, pl. 75) and the image on the CD attached to that publication (no image available on HAO).

⁶⁸⁰ Numbering respectively from TMH 10 58a [HS 2072] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00) and TMH 10 58b [HS 2116] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00).

⁶⁸¹ TMH 10, p. 144.

Text 20a. TMH 10 59a [HS 2081]
(Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00)⁶⁸²

o. 1 **nam-nar** ^dlugal-^rir⁹-[r]a
ni^q2 ^mud-da-^da^r
o. 2 **nam-nar** ^diškur ni^q2 ^mḥa-bi-il-ki-nu-um
o. 3 ^u3 **nam-bur-**^rš^u^r-**ma** tur³-^rra^r-**na**
o. 4 **a-na me-a-bi**
o. 5 **ki** ^rku³-^dnin-gal **dumu** *ib-ni-ia*
o. 6 ^u3 *na-ra-am-tum*
dumu-munus ^dutu-u²-**a**
o. 7 ^mur-^dpa-bil²-sa^q-**ḡa²**
^rdumu^r *u-bar-ru-um*
o. 8 **in-ši-in-s**[a¹⁰]
o. 9 **šam² til-la-bi-še³**
r. 1 **2/3** gi^q4 **ku³-babbar**
r. 2 **in-ne-en-**^rla²^r
r. 3 **u⁴ kur²-še³ ku³-^dnin-gal**
r. 4 ^m1 *na-ra-am-tum*
^ru³ **ibila^r-ne-ne**
r. 5 **inim nu-^rum^r-^rḡa²-^rḡa²-ne-a**
r. 6 **mu** lugal-^rbe²^r **in-pad³-^rde³^r**

Text 20b. TMH 10 59b [HS 2350 (case)⁶⁸³]
(Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00)⁶⁸⁴

[...]
[...]
[...]
o. 1' **[a-na-me-a-b]e²**
o. 2' **[ki ku³-^dnin-ga]l** [**dumu** *ib-ni-ia*]
o. 3' [^u3 *na-ra-am-tum*]
dumu-munus ^dutu-u²-**a**]⁶⁸⁵
o. 4' [^mur-^dpa-bil²-s]a^q-**ḡa²**
[**dumu** *u-bar-ru-um*]
o. 5' [**in-ši-i]n-sa¹⁰**
o. 6' [**šam² til]-la-bi-še³**
r. 1'' **2/3** gi^q4^r [...]
r. 2'' **in-ne-^ren^r-[la²**
r. 3'' **u⁴ kur²-še³ ku³-^dn[in-gal]**
r. 4'' ^m1 *na-ra-am-t[um]*
r. 5'' ^ru³ **ibila-ne-ne a-na-me-a-bi**
r. 6'' **inim nu-um-^rḡa²-^rḡa²-^rne^r-a**
r. 7'' **mu** lugal-**bi in-^rpad³-^rde³**

o. 7 / o. 4' ⁶⁸⁶ Ur-Pabilsaḡ, son of Ubārum, ^{o. 8 / o. 5'} has bought ^{o. 4 / o. 1'} all these things ^{o. 5 / o. 2'} from Ku-Ningal, son of Ibnīya ^{o. 6.} and Naramtum, daughter of Utu'ua: ^{o. 1} the condition of **nar** of Lugal-Irra, (condition) belonging to Udada, and ^{o. 2} the condition of **nar** of Iškur, (condition) belonging to Ḥabil-Kinum ^{o. 3} in addition to the condition of the **bur-š^u-ma** of his courtyard.

r. 2 / r. 1'' He (= Ur-Pabilsaḡ) has paid to him (= Ku-Ningal) ^{r. 1 / r. 1''} 1/3 silver shekel and 15 barley shekels ^{o. 9 / o. 6''} in total. ^{r. 6 / r. 7''} He (= Ku-Ningal) has sworn by the king's name that, ^{r. 3 / r. 3''} in the future, Ku-Ningal, ^{r. 4 / r. 4''-5''} Naramtum or (their) heirs ^{r. 5 / r. 6''} will not make a claim about it.

According to what we have observed about Texts 15–17, connections between the office of the **nar** and the **bur-š^u-ma** were unknown until this moment in our textual documentation. As in Texts 15–17, the mention of both offices might have economic in origin, referring to two sources of income for Ur-Pabilsaḡ. However, he was son of a **nar** (Ubārum) and his brothers were also musicians⁶⁸⁷. In this sense, we suspect that Ur-

⁶⁸² Edition dependent upon TMH 10, p. 144–145 with corrections derived from the consultation of the handwritten copy (TMH 10, p. 76), the image on the CD attached to the publication, and the photo/3D model available on HAO.

⁶⁸³ Joint to HS 2350 + 2351 + 2368 + Ist. Ni 9309 (See TMH 10, p. 144 for details).

⁶⁸⁴ Edition dependent upon ARN, p. 110 (o. 1'–6', without copy for verifying the transliteration) and TMH 10, p. 144–145 with corrections derived from the consultation of the handwritten copy (TMH 10, p. 76), the image on the CD attached to the publication, and the photo/3D model available on HAO.

⁶⁸⁵ Restitution from Archibab T23435. This line appears in TMH 10, p. 144 without content.

⁶⁸⁶ Numbering respectively from TMH 10 59a [HS 2081] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00) and TMH 10 59b [HS 2350 (case)] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00).

⁶⁸⁷ Shehata, 2009: 107, 170 n. 955.

Pabilsaṅ had to act as a musician at some point because of a family tradition. However, his exact occupation (as musician or as another worker) is unknown at the moment⁶⁸⁸.

He might also have acted as **bur-šu-ma** according to two logics. First, **bur-šu-ma** concerns the elderly in general (not only women as some people say⁶⁸⁹). We can see that much better with *puršumum* (masculine) / *puršumtum* (feminine). Then, Ur-Pabilsaṅ would already be advanced in age when he purchased that office. It is true that we do not know the exact date of the death of his father Ubārum⁶⁹⁰. However, our Text 18 was situated in the 37th year of Rīm-Sîn I's reign, while our Texts 19–20 are dated to the 54th year of the reign of that same king. In this sense, after 17 years, Ur-Pabilsaṅ might have been a mature or elderly person. However, can we talk about a specific professional connection between the **nar** and **bur-šu-ma** officials in order to explain Ur-Pabilsaṅ's purchases? We should keep in mind that, because of his/her old age, the **bur-šu-ma** was a respected person⁶⁹¹ and is thought to have had a high social *status*⁶⁹². As a consequence, (s)he performed several tasks in palaces⁶⁹³ and temples⁶⁹⁴ like the **nar**⁶⁹⁵.

Therefore, Ur-Pabilsaṅ's purchases would make sense according to his origins (as son and brother of musicians) and his (possible mature/old) age. It makes also sense with the

⁶⁸⁸ FM 9, p. 15; Shehata, 2009: 175.

⁶⁸⁹ Bauer, 1998: 437 (“alte Frau”); Krebernik, 1998: 265 (““Greis(in)” auch Titel oder Berufsbezeichnung”); Heimpel, 1998–2000: 155 (“old woman”); ePSD (“dowager, matriarch, matron; an official; senior; old”); Foxvog, 2016a: 12 (“old woman, matron, matriarch”); Attinger, 2019d: 18 (“matrone, matriarche”); ePSD2 (“an official; dowager, matriarch, matron; old; senior”). Pay attention also to Wilcke, 1998: 24 (“alderman” for **nam-bur-šu-ma**, while “old woman office” for **nam-um-ma**).

⁶⁹⁰ See Stone and Owen, 1991: 12 for details.

⁶⁹¹ In Goetze, 1957: 106 [CUA 57] (00-00-00), 16–19 (original publication), Ipatum, a *kalûm* priest, is called *puršum bītim* (= *pu-ur-šu-um bi-tim*), “the old person of the house”.

⁶⁹² In *Gilgameš and the Netherworld*, Ur₆ rev. 6–7, 12–13 (Gadotti, 2014: 79, 103), the **bur-šum₂-ma** are with the foremost (**saṅ-tuku**) of Uruk. In the same way, in *Ḫendursaga A*, 207 (Attinger and Krebernik, 2005: 46), the “pauper” people (**uku₂**) is set in opposition to the respected one (**bur-šu-ma**).

⁶⁹³ In *Iddin-Dagān A*, 99–100 (Attinger, 2014a: 21), the matriarchs **bur-šu-ma** are the queen's assistants who provide copious food and drinks for banquets.

⁶⁹⁴ In *Lugalbanda in the mountain cave*, 251–253, the **bur-šu-ma** and **ab-ba** old people praise the god Utu. In addition, we should remember all those documents where **nam-bur-šu-ma** is a temple prebend sold together with the offices of the **gudu₄** priest (**nam-gudu₄**), brewer (**nam-lu₂-bappir**), overseer (**nam-ugula**) or courtyard sweeper (**nam-kisal-luḫ**). See ePSD2 for a long list of those documents.

⁶⁹⁵ For the palatial sphere, see our section about royal praise poetry in the next chapter in order to reflect (always with focus on **nam-nar**) on this aspect.

character of the two purchased professions. As two professions closely connected with the palace and the temple, a person acting as **bur-šu-ma** might have a basic knowledge of the activities of the **nar** and vice versa. However, we do not have much evidence about **bur-šu-ma/puršumu(m)** explicitly regarding music⁶⁹⁶.

3.3.3.3. About the term **nam-nar-sa**

Finally, we are going to look at a text from the archive of the descendants of Damiq-ilišu, an individual about whom we do not have many documents. The reason for this is that his father Lugal-ḥeḡal (elder brother of Ur-Pabilsaḡ about whom we have written above), had a long life. In consequence, Lugal-ḥeḡal blocked his son's access to the family estate for a long time⁶⁹⁷:

Text. 21. TMH 10 55 [HS 2396] (Rīm-Sîn I 35-10-00)⁶⁹⁸

- o. 1 **ḏmar-ṛtu** ṣa ṛpuzur⁴ ḏmar-tu
o. 2 **ḏnin-ṛsi4-an-na** ṣa ṛku-bi^ṛia
o. 3 **ḏnin-si4-an-na** ṣa ka-ṛri^ṛ-ru-um
o. 4 **nam-nar-ṛsa**
o. 5 **u₃ nam-bur-šu-ma tur₃-ṛra^ṛ-na**
o. 6 **ki tab-ni-ištar₃ lukur ḏnin-urta dumu-munus ur-ḏba-ṛba⁶**
o. 7 ^mda-mi-iq-i₃-li₂-šu-ke⁴
o. 8 **in-ši-in-ṛsa¹⁰**
o. 9 **šam₂ til-la-bi-še₃**
o. 10 **1 giṇ₄ ku₃-ṛbabbar**
o. 11 **ṛin^ṛ-na-an-ṛla^ṛ**

^{o. 7} Damiq-ilišu ^{o. 8} has bought ^{o. 6} from Tabni-Ištar, **lukur** priestess of Ninurta, daughter of Ur-Baba ^{o. 4} the office of the **nar** of the stringed instruments ^{o. 5} and the office of **bur-šu-ma** of the courtyard of ^{o. 1} the god Martu, (condition) belonging to Puzur-Martu, (the one of) ^{o. 2} the goddess Ninsianna, (condition) belonging to Kubīya, (and the one of) ^{o. 3} the goddess Ninsi'anna, (condition) belonging to Karirum. ^{o. 11} He has paid (to her = Tabni-Ištar) ^{o. 10} one shekel of silver ^{o. 9} in total.

This text concerns the purchase of two temple offices of several deities (or their statues)⁶⁹⁹: the **bur-šu-ma (nam-bur-šu-ma)** and a sub-type of **nam-nar** called the **nam-**

⁶⁹⁶ In the Neo-Assyrian text SAA 10 226 = ABL 1 2 [K. 183], o. 16–18, the *puršumū* dance while the young people sing. However, that is all our information on this matter.

⁶⁹⁷ See Shehata, 2009: 45 and 170; TMH 10, p. 361, 366 for reference and additional details.

⁶⁹⁸ Edition dependent upon THM 10, p. 138 with corrections derived from our inspection of the handwritten copy (TMH 10, pl. 72), the image on the CD attached to the publication, and the photo/3D model available on HAO.

⁶⁹⁹ We follow the suggestion of TMH 10, p. 139.

nar-sa. This term has been controversial in previous research⁷⁰⁰. Certainly, this is the first time that we know of this sub-type of **nam-nar**, but its presence in this text can be explained in several aspects.

On the one hand, the **nar sa** (“**nar** of stringed instruments”) is mentioned in the Old Babylonian lexical texts close to the **nar balag**⁷⁰¹. At this moment, we should recall the existence of the term **nam-nar-balag** for the office of the **nar balag** as we commented on concerning our Text 9, an excerpt from the lexical list *Proto-izi*.

On the other hand, the **nar sa** (also groups composed of several individuals of this specialization⁷⁰²) is attested in the Old Babylonian administrative texts receiving beer and bread rations⁷⁰³. Sometimes, that musician also received fields⁷⁰⁴. Moreover, a legal text makes mention of a musician of this type, a **nar sa**, devoted to the god Enki⁷⁰⁵. Therefore, we have a similar situation to that of our Text 21, where **nam-nar-sa** (“office of the **nar** of the stringed instruments”) would pertain to some deities.

3.4. Conclusions

The understanding of some texts of this chapter is difficult due to their ambiguous context (as in our Text 10). In other cases, we have some problems with the epigraphy.

⁷⁰⁰ TMH 10, p. 138 simply translated as “office of musician”. However, we should have **nam-nar** for that. The author herself (personal communication) recognized that the sense of some references to **nam-nar** in this documentation was a bit obscure to her.

⁷⁰¹ *Proto-lu2*, 643–644 (**nar balag** and **nar sa**) (DCCLT Q000047).

⁷⁰² YOS 5 163 [YBC 5418] (Warad-Sîn 10-10-00), r. 2 (Archibab T22379) mentions a **nar sa** together with a **nar gal** chief musician and a **gala maḥ** chief lamenter (in lines r. 1 and r. 3 respectively). However, we cannot agree with Shehata, 2009: 45 (who considered the **nar sa** to be a high-ranking musician). Certainly, we find mentions of several **nar** of the stringed instruments (**nar-sa-me(š)**) in CT 45, pl. 84 [BM 78284] (00-00-00), r. 15–16 (Archibab T4883); TCL 11 146 [AO 8430] (Ḫammu-rāpi 33-09-06), r. 3–4 (Archibab T20388) and CT 4, pl. 8 [BM 78210] (Šamšu-ditāna 07-12-20), r. 13 (Archibab T4882). In this sense, the **nar sa** had to be a relatively common musical profession. The similar ration to the **nar sa**, **nar gal** and **gala maḥ** might come just from their participation as musicians in the cult of Nanna.

⁷⁰³ Beer (**kaš**): Sigrist, 1977: 169–183 [CBS 8550 + 14217] (Ḫammu-rāpi 35-00-00), r. viii 19 (Archibab T22070). Bread (**ninda**): CT 4, pl. 8 [BM 78210] (Šamšu-ditāna 07-12-20), r. 13 (Archibab T4882) and YOS 5 163 [YBC 5418] (Warad-Sîn 10-10-00), r. 2 (Archibab T22379). Beer and bread: Lerberghe, 1986: text 4 [CBS 50] (Abī-ešuh 28-03-25), o. 7 (Archibab T4681).

⁷⁰⁴ TCL 11 146 [AO 8430] (Ḫammu-rāpi 33-09-06), r. 3–4 (Archibab T20388).

⁷⁰⁵ UET 5 191 [U.31352] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00), r. 22–23 (Archibab T6256).

This is the case of the bad preservation state of our Text 13 or the scribal mistakes of our Text 14. In addition, some texts of this chapter (as our Text 11) are not definitely related to **nam-nar** or *nārūtū(m)*. In any case, we can perceive two tendencies.

First, in our texts of the elementary scribal curriculum, **nam-nar** means “music”. This term, **nam-nar**, makes reference to some parts or types of songs as in our Text 9, with **ser₃ nam-nar**. In our Text 13, **a₂ kalag nam-nar-ra** is perhaps referred to the neck of a lute. However, we find also references to music as sound. This is the case of our Text 12, with the music/sound of the ^{neš}**tigidla_x** lute. In that text, in addition, **nam-nar** also referred to the **asila₃** cry of joy of the **tige_x** and **a-da-ab** songs.

Second, in our administrative texts, **nam-nar** designates the office of the **nar** since it appears in genitive constructions with divine names. However, there is no verb related to the musical performance (for instance, **ak**) for translating those expressions as “music of the deity” We know also from these texts that **nam-nar** could be specialized concerning the instrument used by the **nar**, and not only the god worshipped by that musician. This phenomenon might be suggested also in the lexical texts of this time if we remember the **nam-nar-balaḡ** of our Text 10. In any case, it is relevant to note that this meaning of **nam-nar** appears in real administrative texts. Moreover, as far as we know, it always concerns the purchase/inheritance of temple prebends. Certainly, our model contracts (Texts 12 and 13) are also, in theory, legal texts, but they refer to other situations, and **nam-nar** has a different meaning in those texts, not the one of “office of the **nar**” or similar.

In this sense, by the beginning of the 2nd millennium BCE, we see the transformation of **nam-nar** into a term with two meanings. This change was already announced in the end of the 3rd millennium BCE with our Texts 7 and 8. In any case, as we shall see in the next chapter about literary texts, “music” *sensu lato* will still be the main meaning for **nam-nar** at this time.

4. NAM-NAR IN THE OLD BABYLONIAN SUMERIAN LITERARY TEXTS

4.1. Introduction to this Chapter

Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts represent, without doubt, the most complex group of texts to be analysed in this study. In fact, they were mastered by just a few of those scribes wishing to work in the temples and the palace after have completed the stage of elementary scribal stage discussed in the previous chapter.

This complexity comes, among other reasons, from our impossibility to know some basic aspects of these texts like their exact creation date⁷⁰⁶, their provenance⁷⁰⁷, and of course their authors. As such, we are still far from being able to understand them completely since we cannot situate them in an exact historical and socio-cultural context. This lack of context is highly regrettable since we cannot know how much of their content actually comes from the 3rd millennium. That is especially important in the case of our royal praise hymns for the Neo-Sumerian kings Ur-Namma and Šulgi⁷⁰⁸. In the same way, this lack of context prevents us from knowing how much of the content of these texts is real as opposed to simple rhetorical exercises in order to impress their audience⁷⁰⁹.

Keeping in mind these considerations, we shall study the excerpts with **nam-nar** coming from these Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts in four steps. First, we shall study those excerpts coming from the debates which, in this case, concern the (musical) education. Second, we shall focus our attention on two mythical episodes. On the one hand, the contest between Enki and Ninmah shortly after the creation of the human beings at the dawn of history. On the other hand, we shall talk about the visit of the goddess Inanna to Enki once the latter had ordered the world. Third, we shall analyse several (very complex) excerpts from the laudatory hymns of the kings, mediators between the gods and humans according to Mesopotamian ideology. Finally, we shall comment on a text only very recently edited and of uncertain typology.

⁷⁰⁶ See Delnero, 2006: 2 and DGS, p. 6 for two different positions on this topic.

⁷⁰⁷ Most of our manuscripts for these texts come from Nippur, but also from other Mesopotamian cities. In this sense, we cannot know their place of creation. See Delnero, 2006: 35–63 for comments.

⁷⁰⁸ The same happens with *Enki and Ninmah* as we can see in Ceccarelli, 2016: 35–38.

⁷⁰⁹ See Steinkeller, 2017: 174 for the audience of Sumerian literary texts, and Mittermayer, 2019: 30–34 for the idea of “rhetoric” in Old Babylonian literary texts, with focus on the debates.

4.2. Debates

4.2.1. Music at school according to two excerpts of *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*

4.2.1.1. *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, 94–99

4.2.1.1.1. Introduction

The first text to be studied here is known as *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, but also *Dialogue 2* or *Edubba’ a 5*⁷¹⁰. The majority of its content is currently being edited for the first time by Manuel Ceccarelli⁷¹¹. In any case, according to the excerpts already published⁷¹², we know that the central part of this text contains a dialogue between two students, Enkiheḡal and Enkita(lu). In that dialogue, they compare their musical abilities⁷¹³. As part of that “musical” disputation, we have two excerpts with **nam-nar**. Here is the first of them:

Text 22. *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*⁷¹⁴

94		ḡe[š]r za ₃ ² -mi ₂ ^{1?} 715	an-da-ḡal ₂	nam-nar	nu-un-zu ⁷¹⁶
	N _{I-A1}	o. ii 10’	ḡe[š]r za ₃ ² -mi ₂ ^{1?} an-da-ḡal ₂	nam-nar	nu-un-zu
	N _{U-AA}	r. i’ 3’	[] an-da -ḡal ₂	nam-nar	nu-u[n-]
	N _{U-LL}	o. 2’	[]-ḡar’	nu	-ḡu’
	U _{NA}	r. iii 1	Deliberately omitted in this score ⁷¹⁷		

⁷¹⁰ For this last (and less common) name of this text, see ELS, p. 33 and Volk, 2011–2013: 221.

⁷¹¹ See Ceccarelli, 2018: 133 n. 2 and Mittermayer, 2019: 5–6 n. 37 for reference.

⁷¹² In addition to the excerpts to be noted here, see Ceccarelli, 2018, *passim*.

⁷¹³ Civil, 1992: 303; Michalowski, 2010a: 201; Volk, 2011–2013: 220; Ceccarelli, 2018: 136–137.

⁷¹⁴ Edition dependent upon that of Ceccarelli, *forthcoming* (we thank this author for sharing it with us) with changes derived from our inspection of the copies/photos indicated below and some collations.

⁷¹⁵ Ceccarelli, *forthcoming* does not have anything here. Our transliteration (similar to Sjöberg, 1976: 169 and Michalowski, 2010a: 201) keeps in mind the content of the handwritten copy of the manuscript (there is no available photo on HAO). In any case, the presence of the **za₃-mi₂** instrument makes sense here, just as we shall comment *infra*.

⁷¹⁶ Michalowski, 2010a: 201 n. 3 says “There are no significant variants in these lines, but l. 99 is a problem”. However, he does not specify why.

⁷¹⁷ This tablet of the Crozer Collection of the Oriental Institute of Chicago (Gordon, 1960: 140–141 n. 148, 143 n. 175) is still unpublished. In this sense, and because of the Oriental Institute publication rights, Manuel Ceccarelli could not share with us any material on that tablet beyond its line numbering, reflected here as a guide. About this tablet, see ELS, p. 33; Ceccarelli, 2018: 142 and Matuszak, 2018: 265.

95	a-ga-aš ge₄ge₄-me-a-aš-e-ne	
N _{I-AA}	o. ii 11'	ʿaʰ-[g]a-aš ge ₄ -me-a-aš -ʿeʰ-ne
N _{U-D2}	r. 1'	[g]e ₄ ? []
N _{U-AA}	r. i' 4'	a -ga ge ₄ ge ₄ -me-a-aš -e-[]
N _{U-LL}	o. 3'	[]-ʿeʰ-ne
U _{NA}	o. iii 2	Deliberately omitted in this score
96	ad ša₄ za-pa-aḡ₂ nu-sa₆ ⁷¹⁸	
N _{I-AA}	o. ii 12'	ʿad ʰša ₄ za -pa -ʿaḡ ₂ ʰ nu-sa ₆
N _{U-D2}	r. 2'	ʿad ʰša ₄ ?ʰ []
N _{U-AA}	r. i' 5'	ad ʰša ₄ ʰ za -pa -aḡ ₂ nu-s[a ₆]]
N _{III-GG}	o. 1'	[] ʰša ₄ ?ʰ za-[] -ʿaḡ ₂ ?ʰ []
N _{U-LL}	o. 4'	[] -sa] ₆
U _{NA}	omits	Deliberately omitted in this score
97	eme-gi₇-še₃ al-dugud eme-ne₂ si nu-ub-sa₂	
N _{I-AA}	o. ii 13'	eme -ʿgi ₇ -še ₃ al -dugud eme*ʰ-bi si nu-ub-sa ₂
N _{U-D2}	r. 3'	eme -ʿgi ₇ -še ₃ al -du[gud]]
N _{U-AA}	r. i' 6'	[e]me -ʰx x alʰ-dugud eme -ne ₂ []
N _{III-GG}	o. 2'	[em]eʰʰ-gi ₇ -še ₃ ʰalʰ-dugud e[me-]
U _{NA}	o. iii 3	Deliberately omitted in this score
98	en₃-du nu-mu-un-da-DI ⁷¹⁹ ka ⁷²⁰ ḡal ₂ nu-un-da ₁₃ -da ₁₃	
N _{I-AA}	o. ii 14'	en ₃ -du nu -un-da-ʰDI kaʰ ḡal ₂ ʰ nu-un -taka ₄
N _{U-D2}	r. 4'	en ₃ -du nu -un-ʰdaʰ-[]
N _{U-Q}	o. 1'	[]-mu-da ₁₃ -da ₁₃]
N _{U-AA}	r. i' 7'	en ₃ -ʰdu nu-mu-un -DIʰ ka ḡal ₂ []
N _{III-GG}	o. 3'	en ₃ -du nu -un-da-ʰDI xʰ []
U _{NA}	o. iii 4	Deliberately omitted in this score
99	u₃ ze₄-e lu₂ til₃-le-me-en	
N _{I-AA}	o. ii 15'	ʰu ₃ ze ₄ -ʰeʰ lu ₂ til -me -en
N _{U-D2}	r. 5'	u ₃ ze ₄ -e l[u ₂]
N _{U-Q}	o. 2'	[]-me-ʰenʰ
N _{U-AA}	r. i' 8'	u ₃ ze ₄ -ʰeʰ lu ₂ til ₃ -l[e-x-x] (erasure)
N _{III-GG}	o. 4'	u ₃ ze ₄ -e ʰlu ₂ til ₃ ʰ-l[e-x-x]
U _{NA}	o. iii 5	Deliberately omitted in this score

⁷¹⁸ See Löhnert, 2009: 335 n. 927 for a reference to this line.

⁷¹⁹ Sjöberg, 1976: 169 and Michalowski, 2010a: 201 have “di”. However, **di** is a NFIN verbal form, and it cannot have verbal prefixes. Gragg, 1973: 58 has “sá”, but the sense of his translation is strange (“You are not equal (to the task of) singing”). Moreover, we would expect the verb **du₇** (“to fit”, “to be suitable”) for that sentence as in *Enkiḡeḡal and Enkitalu*, 110 (see *infra* for our edition). In this sense, we prefer to maintain the Ceccarelli’s DI.

⁷²⁰ Gragg, 1973: 58 transliterates “[ka]”, but we do not know to which variant the author is making reference. That study is supposed to have followed a forthcoming edition (at that time) by Miguel Civil which, unfortunately, never came to fruition because of the death of said author.

94 (Even if) a **za₃-mi₂** was at his disposal (literally, “with him”), he did not learn music.
 95 He is the most awkward among (his) colleagues:
 96 unable to make well the **ad ša₄** (or) the **za-pa-aṅ₂** sound,
 97 (and too) heavy for Sumerian language, he cannot correctly move his tongue.
 98 He cannot recite an **en₃-du** song, (and) he (even) does not open the mouth.
 99 However, you are an accomplished person!

*Sigla*⁷²¹

N_{I-A1} TMH NF 3 42 [HS 1606] + TMH NF 4 86 [HS 1606a]
 (publication copy and notes of Wilcke, *Kollationen*, p. 40)
 N_{III-GG} N 1049 + 3370 (photo on CDLI P276195; collated the 21/08/2019)
 N_{U-D2} ISET 2 108 [Ist. Ni 4114 + 4139] (publication copy)
 N_{U-Q} ISET 1 146 [Ist. Ni 4352] (publication copy) + ISET 3 167 [Ist. Ni 13154]
 N_{U-AA} 3N-T 406 (none copy/photo available ; Ceccarelli’s original transliteration)
 N_{U-LL} CBS 10397 (photo on CDLI P265614; collated the 21/08/2019)
 U_{NA} OIM A24192 (none copy/photo available)

4.2.1.1.2. Terms only referred to singing?

In this excerpt, **nam-nar** (in line 94) has usually⁷²² been translated as “art of singing”⁷²³. This translation makes sense with the following lines of this excerpt. Here we find references to the use of the Sumerian language (**eme-gi₇**) with a specific mention to the tongue (**eme**) (line 96), but also the recitation of the **en₃-du** (epic) songs⁷²⁴ and the opening of the mouth (**ka ṅal₂ taka₄**) (line 97). However, we have some doubts about the (exclusive) connection with singing in the case of **ad ša₄** and **za-pa-aṅ₂** (line 95).

Concerning **ad ša₄**⁷²⁵, it seems to be a *tremolo* mainly connected with the **en₃-du** (epic) songs⁷²⁶ and the **i-lu** ceremonial/lament songs⁷²⁷. However, we should not forget its etymology as **ša₄** (an auxiliary verb) + **ad** “(soft) sound” (in opposition to the **šeg₁₁**

⁷²¹ They follow Ceccarelli, *forthcoming*, but we have put in the middle an I (= Type I), III (= Type III) or U (= Uncertain) according to their typology when they come from Nippur. This classification might change once Manuel Ceccarelli publishes his edition of this text.

⁷²² Except Michalowski, 2010a: 201 (“the craft of music making”).

⁷²³ Sjöberg, 1976: 169 (“art of singing”); Ceccarelli, 2018: 136 n. 24 (“Sängerkunst”).

⁷²⁴ Volk, 2006: 23 n. 55 talks directly of “Hymnus” for this text. It makes sense mainly because of *Gilgameš and the Bull of An*, A 1–6 (ETCSL 1.8.1.2), where **en₃-du** describes the text to be narrated.

⁷²⁵ For the use of this technique by the **nar**, see *Proverbs* 2.39 (ETCSL 6.1.02); UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88], o. 3–4 (Peterson, 2019b: 573).

⁷²⁶ *Proto-Lu₂*, 600–603 (**en₃-du** songs), 604–605 (**ad ša₄**) and 606 (**sa-gid₂-da**, term designating division of stanzas) (DCCLT Q000047) and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, C 8 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

⁷²⁷ Shehata, 2009: 234 for this double nature. For texts, *Inanna G*, 61 (ETCSL 4.07.7) and *Dumuzi and Inanna H*, 17 (Attinger, 2019a: 2), where **ad ša₄** is equated with *nasāsu(m)* (“to lament”). That anticipates the post-Old Babylonian situation quite well delineated in Rendu Loisel, 2011: 204–206.

“loud sound”)⁷²⁸. Certainly, the **ad** is type of sound also produced by some instruments⁷²⁹. A similar thing happens with the **ad ša₄** technique⁷³⁰.

For its part, **za-pa-aṇ₂** designates a type of powerful cry/sound produced by human beings, but also by animals or some objects such as weapons⁷³¹ or the “Mighty Copper” (**urudu-niṇ₂-kalag-ga**), a sort of copper bell used to terrify demons⁷³². This expression also referred to the **nar** in some proverbs as we saw in the introduction of our study⁷³³. However, as we also said there, **za-pa-aṇ₂** might refer in that context not only to the voice of the musician like in other proverbs⁷³⁴, but also to what (s)he could do with some instruments. Certainly, **za-pa-aṇ₂** appears after **akkil** (“clamour”, “uproar”) and before **ṇeš-gu₃-di** (a type of lute as we shall comment on later) in the lexical list *Proto-lu₂*⁷³⁵.

4.2.1.1.3. Identification of the **za₃-mi₂/sammû(m)**

The condition of **nam-nar** in *Enkiheṇal and Enkitalu*, 94–99 as “music” (as a larger category than just “singing”) makes sense when keeping in mind that **nam-nar** is mentioned in line 94 together with a musical instrument: the ^{ṇeš}**za₃-mi₂**⁷³⁶. Beyond its

⁷²⁸ Krispijn, 1990: 15; Rendu Loisel, 2011: 205 n. 862.

⁷²⁹ *Šulgi B*, 171 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02; **ṇeš-gu₃-di** lute) and perhaps *Temple Hymns*, 183 (ETCSL 4.80.1; **za-na-ru** instrument).

⁷³⁰ *Enki's Journey to Nippur*, 64–65 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94).

⁷³¹ See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 306–309 for comments and texts.

⁷³² **Udug ḥul / Utukkū Lemnūtu**, VII 15–20, 47–48, 87–88 (Geller, 2015: 253–254, 261, 268). This edition includes the Old Babylonian forerunners we wish to refer to in this particular case. For a specific edition of those forerunners, see Geller, 1985: 56–80. For more comments about this musical instrument, the **urudu-niṇ₂-kalag-ga**, see our chapter about the 1st-millennium evidence.

⁷³³ *Proverbs* 2.41 and 2.57 (Attinger, 2018: 8).

⁷³⁴ *Proverbs* 2.39 (Attinger, 2018: 9); UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88], o. 4–6 (Peterson, 2019b: 573), and UET 6/2 290 [U. 17207.55], o. 1 (Peterson, 2019b: 582).

⁷³⁵ *Proto-lu₂*, 638–640 (DCCTL Q000047). CUSAS 12, 7.1 B [MS 4158], r. i 11'–15' (DCCLT) mentions this term before **za-na-ru**, an instrument whose voice is loud (**gu₃ nun**) according to *Temple Hymns*, 183 (ETCSL 4.80.1). In any case, be careful, since that excerpt, *Temple Hymns*, 183 says then that the sound of the **za-na-ru** is making good (**sa₆-sa₆**) the sounds (**ad**) of a calf (**amar**).

⁷³⁶ The reading **za₃-mim** (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94; Attinger, 2014: 25; Attinger, 2019d: 214) is based on *Proto-Ea*, 423 (DCCLT Q000055) where one of the readings of the sign SAL is spelled ME-**im** (= **mi₃-im** = **mim**). This might agree with the Neo-Assyrian text Meek, 1920: 119 [K. 945], o. 3 (edition dependent upon DCCLT), where we find **za-ME-in** (= **za-mi₃-in**). In any case, we have the variant **za₃-me'** (or **za₃-**

definition as a stringed instrument, its exact identification has been controversial⁷³⁷. We would propose its identification with an angular harp because an Old Babylonian lexical text mentions a ^{neš}ḫeštug za3-mi2 (“ear of the za3-mi2”)⁷³⁸. Certainly, this term should be considered similar to ab2 za3-mi2 (literally, “cow of the za3-mi2”) due to their common Akkadian equivalent *ḥasīs sammîm*⁷³⁹.

This ab2 za3-mi2 cannot be understood as a reference to the cow-shaped sound-box of a bull-lyre as has been previously suggested⁷⁴⁰. Certainly, those lyres were common in Early Dynastic times (when za3-mi2 did not exist yet⁷⁴¹) but had almost disappeared in the Near East by the 2nd millennium BCE, just when we find references to za3-mi2⁷⁴². In addition, Early Dynastic zoomorphic lyres depicted bulls and calves, but never cows⁷⁴³. A similar thing happens in literary texts, since ab2 ḫi nun (“Cow, noble charm”)⁷⁴⁴ is the

mi3¹) for the za3-mi2/mim as an instrument in *Šulgi B*, 161, manuscript N_{U-q} = Castellino, 1972: pl. 17 [3N-T300], o. ii 6. Moreover, several administrative documents from the Išbī-Erra’s reign contain ^{neš}za3-mi as in BIN 9 185 [NBC 8416] (Išbī-Erra 22-12-00/23-01-00), r. 1 (CDLI P236195; see CDLI for other texts). This writing is similar to the ^{neš}za-mi of Fish, 1958: 84–87 [BM 106055] (Šulgi 45-01-00), r. i 12’ (BDTNS 012371). Therefore, we would maintain ^{neš}za3-mi2 instead of ^{neš}za3-mim.

⁷³⁷ Identifications with (zoomorphic) lyres: Krispijn, 1990: 7; Kilmer, 2000: 116; Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009: 45; Krispijn, 2010b: 148; Mirelman and Kilmer, 2013. Volk, 2006: 34 n. 100 talks, concerning *Enkiḫeyal and Enkitalu*, about “Leier”. Harps *lato sensu*: Lawergren and Gurney, 1987: 49-51; Dumbrell, 2014: 28 and Gabbay, 2014: 134. Horizontal harp/lute: Michalowski, 2010a: 229. Dahlia Shehata (2002: 490; 2009: 350; 2017: 45) usually defines this terms as “harp/lyre”.

⁷³⁸ CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214], b iv 7 (DCCLT).

⁷³⁹ The expression ^{neš}ḫeštug za3-mi2 is known only in the monolingual lexical text mentioned in the previous note, being *ḥasīs sammîm* a literal translation. For ab2 za3-mi2 as *ḥasīs sammîm*, see the Middle Babylonian texts Emar 6/1, p. 240 [Msk 7498f], r. ii 17; Emar 6/1, p. 285 [Msk 74114d], r. 1, and Emar 6/2, p. 508–515 + 730 [Msk 74209a + 7526], r. ii 1 (editions dependent upon DCCLT).

⁷⁴⁰ Krispijn, 1990: 25; Kilmer, 2000: 116; Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009: 50.

⁷⁴¹ The za3-me of the Early Dynastic times is just referred to a doxology. Our earliest reference to the za3-mi2 (in this case ^{neš}za-mi) as instrument is contained in the Ur III administrative text Fish, 1958: 84–87 [BM 106055] (Šulgi 45-01-00), r. i 12’ (BDTNS 012371). See Michalowski, 2010a: 219 for comments.

⁷⁴² The latest depictions of zoomorphic lyres come from two stamp seals from Failaka, ancient Dilmun, by 2100–2000 BCE. We have also a copper head of a bull found in the level IIA of the Barbar temple in Bahrain (2000 BCE) (Kutzer, 2017: 200–201). From that moment, we start to have giant lyres without zoomorphic features in the Ancient Near East. See Shehata, 2017: 70–73 for a recent overview on this topic.

⁷⁴³ Lawergren, 2010: 86-88.

⁷⁴⁴ *Našše A*, 40 (Attinger, 2019e: 84).

name of a **tige**₍₂₎⁷⁴⁵ term to be identified with a drum⁷⁴⁶, not with a lyre⁷⁴⁷. However, **ab**₂ **za3-mi2**/*apsamikku(m)* might be an alternative writing for **ab** **za3-mi2**/*apsamikku(m)* (“window of the **za3-mi2**”). This term describes in the Old Babylonian mathematical texts a concave square⁷⁴⁸. That fact is very relevant since the interior of that concave square is similar to the X-hole of the angular harps in the Old Babylonian iconography⁷⁴⁹.

Anne Draffkorn Kilmer seems to connect **ab**₍₂₎ **za3-mi2**/*apsamikku(m)* with the “nose (*appu*) of the *sammû* instrument” (**ap sammûm*)⁷⁵⁰ since the nose of the head of these bull-lyres usually have the shape of a concave square. However, that detail is obviously irrelevant in the configuration of that instrument⁷⁵¹, and not all the noses of the bull heads of bull-lyres are exactly like a concave square⁷⁵². Furthermore, the Sumerian equivalent for *appu(m)* is **giri**₁₇⁷⁵³. This **giri**₁₇ related to the physical aspect of a human being since it is written with the sign KA whose pictographic form describes a human head⁷⁵⁴. Returning to *appu(m)* this term is documented only from Old Akkadian times and later⁷⁵⁵, that is, after the main period of development of bull-lyres in Mesopotamia. If it were not enough, later depictions of bull-lyres are not so explicit in this type of detail⁷⁵⁶.

Our identification of the **za3-mi2** with an angular harp makes sense in the context of our Old Babylonian administrative texts⁷⁵⁷. In those texts the **za3-mi2** appears as made of

⁷⁴⁵ As Uri Gabbay, 2014a: 110 commented.

⁷⁴⁶ See our Section 4.4.3.2.3 for identification.

⁷⁴⁷ As in Kilmer, 1980–1983b: 574 or Kilmer and Mirelman, 2013.

⁷⁴⁸ See Robson, 1999: 51; Friberg, 2007: 214 and Robson, 2007 for texts and philological and mathematical comments and rejection of **ab**₂ **za3-mi2** as “cow of the lyre” on Kilmer, 1980–1983b: 574.

⁷⁴⁹ See Rašīd, 1984: 80–85 for evidence. Unlike the Elamite horizontal harp from the Neo-Assyrian relief BM 124802 (Rašīd, 1984: 136–137, fig. 151), Old Babylonian horizontal harps do not have holes in their sound-box. See Rašīd, 1984: 86–89 for evidence.

⁷⁵⁰ Kilmer, 1980–1983b: 572, without any reference to a concrete excerpt with that expression.

⁷⁵¹ Certainly, we should remember the “boat-lyre” UM 30-12-253, whose sound-box does not have the shape of a bull or calf, but a boat with a stag on its top (Rašīd, 1984: 36–37; de Schauensee, 2002: 17).

⁷⁵² See Dumbrill, 2010: 67-80 for heads of bull-lyres.

⁷⁵³ CAD A2, p. 184; ePSD; Attinger, 2019d: 67.

⁷⁵⁴ MEA 15; Couto Ferreira, 2009: 150-153.

⁷⁵⁵ CAD A2, p. 184.

⁷⁵⁶ See Rašīd, 1984: 36–37; Michalowski, 2010a: 230–231, and Kutzer, 2017: 200–201 for bull-lyres after the Early Dynastic Period.

⁷⁵⁷ In addition to the texts commented on in Michalowski, 2010a: 224, see BIN 9 185 [NBC 8416] (Išbī-Erra 22-12-00/23-01-00), o. 5–r. 1 (CDLI P236195); BIN 10 104 [NBC 10075] (Išbī-Erra 13-02-00),

wood covered with a goat-skin surface like the Egyptian angular harps⁷⁵⁸. One of those texts talks about three **za3-mi2** instruments for the house of the **nar munus**⁷⁵⁹. In this sense, the **za3-mi2** could be played by women in addition to men⁷⁶⁰, just as is the case of angular harps in the Old Babylonian iconography, which are played by both sexes⁷⁶¹.

Another of those administrative texts talks about a ^ues**za3-mi2** covered with a silver layer⁷⁶². That may recall the “Silver Bull Lyre” BM 121199 dated in the Early Dynastic Period⁷⁶³. However, metal layers for wooden instruments were not unique to bull-lyres, a type of instrument no longer extant in Mesopotamia by Old Babylonian times as we have already stated. On the one hand, a letter from Mari referred to the elaboration of a wooden instrument (a lute (?)) with gold (^ues*i-nu-ut* KU3.SI22)⁷⁶⁴. On the other hand, a metal layer over the sound-box of an angular harp makes sense with the Old Babylonian depictions of players of those harps. Certainly, they usually wear opulent clothes typical of the royal sphere. In this sense, they might play an instrument with a metal layer like the **za3-mi2**⁷⁶⁵.

Another letter from Mari has been used to prove the identification of the **za3-mi2/sammû(m)** as a lyre because of the reference to the *kirrum* (“collar-bone”) of a supposed *sammûm* instrument⁷⁶⁶ which has been identified with the crossbar of a lyre⁷⁶⁷. However, what was transliterated at the time of this identification as *sa-mi-im* (and normalized as *sammîm*), now it is just written *x-mi-im*. That is closer to the actual content of the clay tablet in its current state of preservation⁷⁶⁸. In any case, a spelling of *sammîm*

o. 1–8 (CDLI P236648), Fish, 1955: 115, text 1 [Wahbi 1] (Išbī-Erra 13-02-00/13-10-00), o. 4–7 (CDLI P500660) and the lexical text CDLI P231749 [YBC 2127], d i 16 (DCCLT).

⁷⁵⁸ Emerit, 2017: 132.

⁷⁵⁹ BIN 10 104 [NBC 10075] (Išbī-Erra 13-02-00), r. 4 (CDLI P236648).

⁷⁶⁰ For instance, BIN 9 352 [NBC 5684] (Išbī-Erra 13-08-00), o. 5 (CDLI P236362), where we find an **e2 nar** (“house of the **nar**”).

⁷⁶¹ Michalowski, 2010a: 224 said that “men are restricted to lutes, certain types of horizontal harp, and various pipes”, but men also played the angular harp (Rašīd, 1984: 80–85, figs. 62, 63–64, 66–68).

⁷⁶² PBS 8/2 194 [CBS 345], o. i 20 (CAD S, p. 119).

⁷⁶³ Dumbrill, 2010: 28, 31–39.

⁷⁶⁴ FM 9 43 [A.1185] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 5–lo. e. 1 (Archibab T6601). This instrument is made on gold in FM 9 12 [ARM 10 137] (Zimrī-Līm 13-00-00), r. 4 (Archibab T6206). See also FM 9, p. 49.

⁷⁶⁵ Thomas, 2017: 304.

⁷⁶⁶ ARM 32, p. 421–422 (= earlier ARM 25 752) [M.10449] (00-07-10), lo. e. 1 (Archibab T12035).

⁷⁶⁷ Kilmer, 2000: 116, which simplified the considerations of Durand, 1989. Kilmer’s contribution is followed by Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009: 45.

⁷⁶⁸ See photos of the tablet in Archibab T12035 through Archipix for reference.

(genitive of *sammûm*) as *sa-mi-im* is generally unusual for *sammû(m)*⁷⁶⁹. That term is spelled as *sa₃-am-mi-im* in our only other reference to this instrument in Mari⁷⁷⁰. That is, it is written with ZA (= *sa₃*), and not SA (= *sa*), and two “m”, not a single one. Moreover, the spelling *sa-mi-im* is normally used with people (^P*sa-mi-im*)⁷⁷¹ or places (^{URU}*sa-mi-im*^{KI})⁷⁷². In this sense, that text cannot be used for an identification of **za₃-mi₂/sammû(m)**.

Finally, although it does not concern *stricto sensu* Old Babylonian times, we would consider the use of the sentence [ᵐᵉᶠTE].ᵐUNUG[?].KU = MIN<(il-x-[x])> ša₂ *sa-am-me-e* of a Neo-Babylonian lexical list in the identification of **za₃-mi₂/sammû(m)**⁷⁷³. Previous research has seen here the “cheek (**unu₂/usukku(m)**) of the **za₃-mi₂/sammû(m)**” understood as the cheek of the bull of the sound-box of the zoomorphic lyre⁷⁷⁴.

However, the expression [ᵐᵉᶠTE].ᵐUNUG[?].KU might refer to a different instrument. Certainly, in the Sumerian column, this [ᵐᵉᶠTE].ᵐUNUG[?].KU is followed by two allusions to the ᵐᵉᶠḥar-ḥar, another instrument⁷⁷⁵. Then, *usukku(m)* (= **unu₂(TE.UNUG)-ku** = *usukku*) may also make reference to the side of an object⁷⁷⁶. Furthermore, **unu₂** referred to the cheek (always the human one)⁷⁷⁷, but also it referred to a type of ornament⁷⁷⁸. That last remark is very interesting, since *sammû* instruments in Neo-Babylonian administrative texts appear decorated with “rings” (*qullu*)⁷⁷⁹ and “mountings”

⁷⁶⁹ See CAD S, p. 118–119 for references, especially for later periods.

⁷⁷⁰ FM 9 62 [M.7281], r. 8”. See our chapter about texts from Mari for our edition.

⁷⁷¹ See AbB 14 137 [AO 6907] (00-00-00), o. 1 (Archibab T13275); ARM 13 142 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 17 (Archibab T8923); ARM 21 106 (Zimrī-Līm 03-08-25), r. 5 (Archibab T14484); Charpin, 1984: 69 [TH 82.67] (Tab-šilli-Aššur eponym 196-09-11), o. 5 (Archibab T19671), and FM 11 180 [M.10447] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 2 (Archibab T8128) for evidence.

⁷⁷² See ARM 1 103 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 21 (Archibab T4521) and PIHANS 117 80 [L. 87-627] (00-00-00), r. 2 (Archibab T14472) for evidence.

⁷⁷³ CT 14, pl. 47 [BM 42339], o. 4 (DCCLT). According to our inspection of the copy of this manuscript, we prefer this transliteration to the one of MSL 6, p. 121 (“[giš.TE+U]NU.KU”).

⁷⁷⁴ Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009: 50.

⁷⁷⁵ CT 14, pl. 47 [BM 42339], o. 5–6 (DCCLT). See Krispijn, 1990: 11–12 and Krispijn, 2010b: 146.

⁷⁷⁶ CAD U-W, p. 283.

⁷⁷⁷ Couto Ferreira, 2009: 206–208.

⁷⁷⁸ Attinger, 2019d: 208.

⁷⁷⁹ GCCI 2 24 [GCBC 389] (Nabopolassar 17-08-27[?]), 1 (CAD S, p. 119). Here these rings are in gold, but they could be made in other materials, such as silver (CAD Q, p. 298).

(*mandītu*)⁷⁸⁰. The *sammû* had to be an angular harp at that time. Certainly, a Late Achaemenid text (by 400 BCE) defines **AB₂.ZA₃.MI₂** as the opening of that instrument⁷⁸¹. That makes sense with the holes in the sound-box of Seleucid angular harps⁷⁸², but not with cows, just as **ab₂ za₃-mi₂** had been previously defined⁷⁸³.

4.2.1.1.4. The musical role of the **za₃-mi₂**/*sammû*(*m*) and conclusions

Although it is normally played with other instruments without any reference to singing⁷⁸⁴, the ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**za₃-mi₂** angular harp seems to accompany the song performed by a group of **nar**⁷⁸⁵. In this sense, we might understand its connection with **nam-nar** in *Enkiheṅal and Enkitalu*, 94 because of its condition as a suitable instrument for musical accompaniment. However, we should remember that the ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**za₃-mi₂** was the instrument used for the Old Babylonian Tuning Texts UET 7 74 [U. 7/80] and UET 6/3 388⁷⁸⁶. Moreover, its “good tuning” (**kam-ma sa₆-ga**) is also known through other contemporary texts⁷⁸⁷. Perhaps the ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**za₃-mi₂** was an “easy” instrument for learning some important aspects in musical practice, like tuning sense. Maybe for that reason this ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**za₃-mi₂** seems to be described in *Enkiheṅal and Enkitalu*, 94 as a basic instrument for musical learning.

⁷⁸⁰ CAD M1, p. 209. See YOS 6 192 [YBC 7536] (Nabonidus 15-09-07), r. 1 (CAD S, p. 119) for an example involving a *sammû* instrument.

⁷⁸¹ SpTU 1 72 [W 22307/12], r. 10–11: ^{r. 10} [...] **AB₂.ZA₃.MI₂** *ḥa-si-si: aš₂-š_u₂* U ^{r. 11} *ap-ta ša₂ sa-am-mu-u₂* [...] (CCP 3.6.3.E; no photo available to with the copy checked for this edition), “^{r. 10} [...] (The expression) **AB₂.ZA₃.MI₂** (means) “ear” ^{r. 11} (since the sign) U (referred to) the opening of the *sammû* [...]”.

⁷⁸² See Rašīd, 1984: 150–151 for reference.

⁷⁸³ Kilmer, 1980–1983: 575; Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009: 50 and Krispijn, 2010b: 148. Those works tried to make a connection between **ab₂ za₃-mi₂** and the Ugaritic *r²imt* (defined as “cow” by comparison with the Akkadian *rīmtu*) (Koitabashi, 1999: 374; Mirelman and Kilmer, 2013). However, *r²imt* means “beloved” in Ugaritic (Olmo de Lete and Sanmartín, 2015: 713). Furthermore, it actually describes the *knr* lyre of the previous line (*Baal’s Myth*, CAT 1.101, 17–18; Smith and Wayne, 2009: 216).

⁷⁸⁴ *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 62 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94).

⁷⁸⁵ *Iddin-Dagān A*, 206–207 (Attinger, 2014: 25). Concerning Old Babylonian iconography, that idea makes sense with clay plaque IM 11135 (Rašīd, 1984: 82–83, fig. 65). In said plaque, an open-mouthed woman plays an angular harp, perhaps singing in accompaniment to that instrument.

⁷⁸⁶ See Mirelman and Krispijn, 2009; Michalowski, 2010a: 208–209; Kilmer, 2014: 92–94, and Dumbrell, 2019: 31–46 for the most recent comments about these texts.

⁷⁸⁷ *Šulgi B*, 161 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

Therefore, we would define **nam-nar** in this excerpt *Enkihejal and Enkitalu*, 94 as “music”⁷⁸⁸ and not “art of singing”⁷⁸⁹. Certainly, the connections of the **za₃-mi₂** with **nam-nar** might have nothing in common related to singing and other musical terms of this excerpt might refer not only to singing, but also instrumental music (as **za-pa-aṅ₂**).

4.2.1.2. *Enkihejal and Enkitalu*, 110–113: music and morality

Here is the next excerpt of *Enkihejal and Enkitalu* to be commented on this study:

Text 23. *Enkihejal and Enkitalu*⁷⁹⁰

110 **nam-nar-e nu-ub-du₇ kiṅ₂-ge₄-a-aš la-ba-ab-du₇**

N _{I-A1}	o. ii 26'	nam -nar-e nu -ub-du₇ kiṅ₂-ge₄ -a -aš la -'ba' -ab -d[u₇]
N _{I-N}	o. ii' 3'	nam'-nar nu-'ub'-[]
N _{I-BB}	r. ii 7'	nam -nar nu -ub-du kiṅ₂ -ge₄ -a-'aš la' -ba -'ab' -du₇?
N _{III-GG}	r. 5	[]-'e²' nu -ub-du / [-g]e₄ -a -aš la -ba -ab -'du₇'
N _{U-D1-3}	r. 16'+5'+4'	'nam'-[] nu -ub-du₇ kiṅ₂ -g[e₄]-a -aš la -ba -ab -du
N _{U-FF}	o. ii' 7	'nam'-nar-e nu -ub-du 'kiṅ₂'-[] / 'la -ba' -ab -d[u₇]
N _{U-HH}	4'	[] -b]a -'ab' -du₇
U _{NA}	o. iii 16	Deliberately omitted in this score

111 **e₂ lu₂-še₃ u₃-un-DU lu₂ nu-mu-un-da-sa₂-e**

N _{I-A1}	o. ii 27'	'e₂' lu₂ -'še₃' u₃ -un-DU 'lu₂' nu -mu -e -'da-sa₂'
N _{I-N}	r. ii' 4'	'e₂' lu₂ -še₃ u[₃-]
N _{I-BB}	r. ii 8'	e₂ 'lu₂ -še₃' u₃ -DU lu₂ nu -mu-'un'-da-sa₂-e'
N _{III-GG}	r. 6	[] 'x' [I]u₂ 'nu²-mu²-un²']
N _{U-D1-3}	omits	
N _{U-FF}	o. ii' 8'	'e₂ lu₂ -'še₃ 'u₃ -DU' lu₂ 'nu'-[]
U _{rw}	r. 1'	[] [I]u₂-'še₃' []
U _{NA}	o. iii 17	Deliberately omitted in this score

112 **a₂-ne₂ ṅal₂ u₃-bi₂-in-taka₄ ser₃ gid₂-da nu-ub-be₂**

N _{I-A1}	o. ii 28'	'a₂' -ne₂ ṅal₂ u₃-<bi₂>-'in' -taka₄ ser₃ gid₂ -da nu -ud -b[e₂]
N _{I-N}	r. ii' 5'	a₂ -ne₂ ṅal₂ []
N _{I-BB}	r. ii 9'	'a₂' -ne₂ 'ṅal₂' in² -taka₄ ser₃ gid₂ -'da' nu -'ub'-be₂
N _{III-GG}	r. 7	'a₂² -ne₂ ṅal₂' u₃ -'bi₂'-[] / 'ser₃ gid₂' -da []
N _{U-D1-3}	r. 17'+6'+5'	'a₂² -[n]e₂ ṅal₂ u₃ -bi₂ -i[n]-taka₄ ser₃ gid₂ -da nu -ub -be₂
N _{U-FF}	o. ii' 9'	a₂ -ne₂ ṅal₂ u₃ -bi₂ -'in'-[] / ser₃ <gid₂>-da 'nu'-da-'x'
U _{rw}	r. 2'	'x' -ne₂ ṅal₂ u[₃-]
U _{NA}	o. iii 18	Deliberately omitted in this score

⁷⁸⁸ Therefore, we would agree with Volk, 2006: 33 n. 100 (“musikalische Ausführung”) and Michalowski, 2010a: 201 (“craft of music making”). However, we understand **nam-nar** in this context in a more abstract way than Piotr Michalowski did for the previously commented reasons.

⁷⁸⁹ Sjöberg, 1976: 169 (“art of singing”); Ceccarelli, 2018: 136 n. 24 (“Sängerkunst”).

⁷⁹⁰ See the previous excerpt for all the details of this edition (including the omission of U_{NA}).

113 **igi dumu um-mi-a-ke4-še3 u3-ba-tuš / tige2 a-da-ab nu-ub-be2**⁷⁹¹

N _{I-A1}	o. ii' 29'	'igi' dumu um-mi -a-'ke4'-še3 u3-ba-tuš / 'tige2' a-da-ab nu-ub-'be2'
N _{I-N}	r. ii' 6'	igi dumu um-m [i]
N _{I-BB}	r. ii' 10'	igi 'dumu' um-'mi'-a -ke4-'še3' u3-ba'-tuš / 'tige2' a-da-ab nu-ub'-be2
N _{III-GG}	r. 8	'igi dumu um'-[-š]e3' 'u3'-[]
N _{U-D1-3}	omits	
N _{U-FF}	o. ii' 10'	'igi' dumu um-'mi' -a -še3 u3-'ba'-[] / 'tige2' a-da-ab nu-u[b-]
U _{rw}	r. 3'	igi dumu 'um'-mi-'a-x' []
U _{NA}	o. iii' 19	Deliberately omitted in this score

- 110 He is not fit for music, he is not fit for (its) content(s)⁷⁹².
 111 (When) he goes to the house of (another) person, he is not respectful to him.
 112 After he has “opened” his arm, he does not recite a long **ser3** song.
 113 After he has sat before the master, he does not recite any **tige2** or **a-da-ab** hymn.

*Sigla*⁷⁹³

N _{I-A1}	TMH NF 3 42 [HS 1606] + TMH NF 4 86 [HS 1606a] (publication copy and notes of Wilcke, <i>Kollationen</i> , p. 40)
N _{U-D1}	ISET 2 108 [Ist. Ni 4114 + 4139] (publication copy)
N _{U-D2}	ISET 2 97 [Ist. Ni 4056] (publication copy)
N _{U-D3}	ISET 2 108 [Ist. Ni 4241] (publication copy)
N _{I-N}	ISET 1 148 [Ist. Ni 4384] (publication copy)
N _{I-BB}	UM 55-21-307 (photo available on CDLI P257246; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{U-FF}	N 4104 + 4115 (photo available on CDLI P278992; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{III-GG}	N 1049 + 3370 (photo on CDLI P276195; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{U-HH}	CBS 15004 (photo available on CDLI P269583; collated the 21/08/2019)
U _{rw}	UET 6/3 634 (photo available on CDLI P346671)
U _{NA}	OIM A24192 (none copy/photo available)

In this text, someone is considered “not fit” (**nu-ub-du7**) for **nam-nar** (line 94) with some explanations mixing tips about the recitation of songs (the **ser3 gid2-da**⁷⁹⁴ or the **tige2** and **a-da-ab** hymns) and good behaviour: to be respectful with a host (line 111)⁷⁹⁵,

⁷⁹¹ 1) ***um-mi-a-ke4-ne-še3** (Sjöberg, 1976: 169; Shehata, 2009: 257 and Attinger, 2019: 20 n. 147) vs. **um-mi-a-ke4-še3**: There is actually no sign NE here. 2) **um-mi-a-ke4-še3** is confirmed by manuscript N_{BB}. Volk, 2006: 23 n. 55 has “igi-(dumu-)um-mi-a-ke4-e-ne”. However, there is no variant of this text where **dumu** is optional. 3) **tige** (Sjöberg, 1976: 169; Ceccarelli, *forthcoming*) vs. **tige2** (Attinger, 2019: 20 n. 147): we find LUL.BALAD (= **tige2**) and not BALAD.LUL (= **tige**).

⁷⁹² Sjöberg, 1976: 169 “task”. However, that meaning is too free concerning the meaning of **kiŋ2-ge4-a** as “messenger”, and, as extension, “message” (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 331; Attinger, 2019d: 63).

⁷⁹³ They follow Ceccarelli, *forthcoming*.

⁷⁹⁴ Volk, 2006: 23 n. 55 talks about **ser3 gid2-da** just as “Liedtypus”. That contrasts with the precise reference of that publication to the **tige2** and **a-da-ab** of this text as songs/hymns.

⁷⁹⁵ That is the way in which we understand line 111th: the student goes to the house of someone who has invited him. However, because is very arrogant, he will not be polite to that person. In any case, we should keep in mind that the verb **sa2** literally means “to be equal”.

to greet other people (line 112)⁷⁹⁶, or to sit before his masters with the intention of learning (line 113). Åke Sjöberg translated **nam-nar** as “art of singing”⁷⁹⁷. That translation makes sense with the perception of musicians as learned people⁷⁹⁸, but also with (the apparent sense of) *Proverbs* 2.54, 2–3⁷⁹⁹, where “singers” seem to be more valuable than (wind) instrumentalists. There, the “defiled” (**pe-el-la₂**) **nar** (traditionally seen here as a “singer”⁸⁰⁰) becomes a musician of the **gi-di** pipes (**lu₂ gi-di-da**)⁸⁰¹, while the **pe-el-la₂ gala** (sometimes understood as a singer of laments⁸⁰²) becomes a player of the **gi-gid₂**⁸⁰³ pipes (**lu₂ gi-gid₂-da**)⁸⁰⁴. That interpretation of *Proverbs* 2.54, 2–3, however, does not keep in mind the rest of the proverb. There, two professions without any hierarchical

⁷⁹⁶ Volk, 2006: 23 n. 55 is referred to **a₂-ne₂ ŋal₂ taka₄** as “in Haltung (Armzeichen?) zu gehen”. On its behalf, Shehata, 2009: 278 defined it as a musical performance indication. However, she forgot the reference to a similar expression in *Gilgameš and the Netherworld*, 264 (Gadotti, 2014: 226). In that excerpt, like someone who does a formal gesture before an important activity (Attinger, 2019a: 20 n. 147), the scribe “opens his arm” before entering into the palace. Our interpretation as “greeting” comes from *Šulgi B*, 350 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02), where it is followed **ki silim-eš₂ di-ŋa₂** (“of my place of saying “health!””).

⁷⁹⁷ Sjöberg, 1976: 169 (“He is not fit for the art of singing, not fit for that task”).

⁷⁹⁸ See FM 9, p. 16–18 for the difference between the *aštalûm/aštalîtum* and *nāru/nārtu* musicians.

⁷⁹⁹ Edition dependent upon Attinger, 2018: 10.

⁸⁰⁰ Alster, 1997: 55 (“singer”); ETCSL 6.1.02 (“singer”); Attinger, 2018: 10 (“chanteur”).

⁸⁰¹ Attinger, 2018: 10 has “lu₂ ge-di-da-kam”. The reading of GI as **ge** as is based in the composite version of *Proto-Ea*, 460 (DCCLT). However, each variant of this text has a different thing: MSL 14, p. 18 B₄ [UM 55-21-347], r. iv 37 = ‘GI’-e (collated the 22/08/2019); MSL 14, p. 29 L_e [HS 1756], o. 5 = ‘GI’-i and MSL 14, p. 19 B_g [CBS 15221], o. 10 = ‘GI’-[x’] (collated the 23/08/2019). Therefore, we prefer to maintain by the moment the traditional **gi-di** as a matter of prudence

⁸⁰² Attinger, 2018: 10 (“chantre”).

⁸⁰³ Attinger, 2018: 10 has “lu₂ ge-SU₃-(-a)-kam”. In addition to our previous comments about the sign GI, we cannot share his “ge-SU₃” since manuscript AA of this text (= Kramer, 1952: 12 fig. 2 [Ist. Ni 5376], o. 13 = checked through its photo on CDLI P229706) has **lu₂-gi-‘gid₂’-a-kam** (Alster, 1997: 55 forgot the sign GI “lu₂-‘gid’-a-kam”), where the third sign seems like the BU (= **gid₂**) of *Šulgi R*, 50, manuscript B (= aBZL 265), not SUD (= **su₃**). We find **lu₂-gi-gid₂-‘kam’** in the text CC (= SP, pl. 46 [UM 55-21-439], o. 3 = collated the 22/08/2019). Sign BU seems in that text and chain like the one of *Šulgi X*, 120 (see Attinger, 2019f: 10 for edition), manuscript C (see aBZL 265 for reference). Therefore, we would write here **gi-gid₂**.

⁸⁰⁴ The expression **lu₂-gi-gid₂-‘kam’** is apparently used in Manuscript CC of *Proverbs*, 2.54 with the **nar**, while the **gala** is connected there with **lu₂-gi-di-‘da’** (we say apparently since **nar** and **gala** do not appear actually in the tablet because it is broken at that part as we saw in our collation of the tablet the 22/08/2019). The opposition **nar** vs. **lu₂ gi-di-da** is ensured by UET 6/2 267 [U. 17207,21], o. 7–8 (Peterson, 2019b: 572), and Alster, 2005: 396–403 [Cornell University Lib05], 7 (Alster, 2005: 397). Moreover, see the reference to **nar** and **gi-di** in **Lugal u₄ me-lam₂-bi nir-ŋal**, 617 (ETCSL 1.6.2).

distinction confront each other. We can see that in its first line, where the scribe (**dub-sar**) is opposed to the “person of incantations” (**lu₂ mu₇-mu₇**). Certainly, the scribe was familiar with the refined Sumerian dialect of high literature. In contrast, the incantations of the **lu₂ mu₇-mu₇** must have seemed as though they were composed in a barbaric language, not Sumerian (although exorcists were not at all illiterate!⁸⁰⁵) In our opinion, *Proverbs* 2.54 deals with professionals who are doing the opposite of their usual jobs due to their lack of talent, something fitting with the usual irony of Sumerian proverbs⁸⁰⁶.

That makes sense with the opposition **nar** vs. **lu₂ gi-di-da** and **gala** vs. **lu₂ gi-gid₂-da**. In fact, the **nar** performed mainly (but not exclusively) in festivals⁸⁰⁷, but the **gi-di** pipes were mainly used for lamentations⁸⁰⁸. In the same way, the **gala** was mainly occupied with the lamentations⁸⁰⁹. However, the **gi-gid₂** pipes were used in ceremonial events⁸¹⁰. In this sense, **nar** and **gala** might be respectively understood as “musician” and “lamentation priest” without any exclusive connection to singing. Certainly, if *Proverbs* 2.54 wished to establish an opposition between singers and instrumentalists, why not use the term **lu₂ i-lu** (“singer”, literally “person of the **i-lu** song”)⁸¹¹ instead of **nar**? Why not mention other instruments whose musicians were designated by the term **lu₂**⁸¹²?

In light of these considerations, and those of our previous comments on *Enkihegal and Enkitalu*, 94–99, we would translate the term **nam-nar** from *Enkihegal and Enkitalu*, 110 also as “music” (like Konrad Volk)⁸¹³ and not “art of singing” as Åke Sjöberg did.

⁸⁰⁵ For this interpretation, Rendu Loisel, 2018: 94–95. In addition, see Pedersén, 1986: 41–76.

⁸⁰⁶ Shehata, 2013: 78–79.

⁸⁰⁷ Shehata, 2009: 29–31.

⁸⁰⁸ See *Proto-ka₂-gal*, 374 and PBS 5 149 [CBS 10466], o. 10 (DCCLT) for lexical evidence on the laments of the **gi-di (er₂ gi-di(-da))**. In addition, see CT 15, pl. 18 [BM 15821], r. 14 (Cohen, 1981: 91); CT 36, pl. 41–42 [BM 96940], o. 21 (Cohen, 1981: 104) and *The Raging Sea*, a+38 (Cohen, 1988: 386).

⁸⁰⁹ Shehata, 2013: 69.

⁸¹⁰ See *Inanna’s Descent*, 353 (Attinger, 2019c: 66) and *Cursing of Agade*, 36 (ETCSL 2.1.5) for evidence. In addition, *Ur-Namma A*, 187 (see *infra* for our edition) and *Šulgi E*, 38 and 56 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05) for this term as a praise hymn (see Shehata, 2009: 259–260).

⁸¹¹ MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 245–256 (DCCLT)

⁸¹² MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 247–252 (DCCLT) mentions four specialities of this type: **lu₂ ku^sa₂-la₂**, **lu₂ al-ḡar-su-ra** (“player of the **al-ḡar-sur**”), **lu₂ balāḡ** and **lu₂ balāḡ(-)di-da** (“player of the **balāḡ-di** instrument” or “reciter of **balāḡ** laments”).

⁸¹³ Volk, 2006: 55 n. 23 translates the entire line 110 as “Für die Musik ist er ohne jedes Talent, (aber auch) für jede (sonstige) Arbeit untauglich”.

4.2.2. *The Father and his rude Son*, 107–112

In this composition, a father talks to his son, receiving back curt replies from the latter. In the excerpt to be studied here, the father wishes for his son a future as a scribe⁸¹⁴, while the son wants to become a musician⁸¹⁵. Here is the first part of that discussion:

Text 24. *The Father and his rude Son*⁸¹⁶

107		nam-lu₂-ulu₃ gašam-ta ma-da al-tuš-a					
N _{I-K}	r. i 11	ˈnamː-lu ₂ -ulu ₃	gašam	-ta ma -da	al -tuš-a		
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 13	nam-ˈlu ₂ -x-ba ²	gašam	-ta ˈmaː-[]
N _{I-GG}	r. i 3	nam-lu ₂ -ˈulu ₃	g[ašam ² -]
N _{I-II}	o. 1-2	[-u]18 ² -luː	gašam-[]/ [-d]a	ab-tuš	
N _{III-Z}	r. 8	nam -lu ₂ -ˈulu ₃	gašam _x (NUN.ME)-ta	ma -da		ab-tuš-a	
N _{III-AA}	r. 4	ˈnam-lu ₂ -ulu ₃	gašamː	-ta ˈmaː-d[a]
N _{III-DD}	o. 15	nam-ˈlu ₂ -[]	gašam	-ta m[a-]
N _{III-EE}	o. 10	ˈnam-lu ₂ -u18-lu	ˈgašamː	-ta ma-da		ˈalː-tuš-ˈaː	
N _{III-EE1}	o. 6ː	[]-ta ma-da		ˈtuš -a ¹	
N _{III-FF}	o. 3-4	ˈnam-lu ₂ -[]	ˈgašamː	-ta / ˈma-da a		abː-tuš-a	
N _{III-HH}	o. 1	[]-tuš-[]	
Ur ₂	r. i 17ː	[gaša]m	-ta ma-da ¹		ab-tu[š-a]	
Ur ₄	o. 13	n[am]-lu ₂ -lu _x (URU)	ˈgašamː-[ˈma-daː		tuš -ˈaː	
108		^den-ki-ke₄ niḡ₂-nam mu-sa₄-a-ba					
N _{I-K}	r. i 12	^d en	-ki -ke ₄	niḡ ₂ -a-na	mu -sa ₄	-ba	
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 14	^d enː	-ki-ˈke ₄	n[iḡ ₂]-ˈa-naː []
N _{I-GG}	r. i 4	^d en	-ki-ˈke ₄	niḡ ₂ ː []
N _{I-II}	o. 3	[]-ˈke ₄		mu-ˈsa ₄ -[]
N _{I-JJ}	o. 1ː	[-ˈnam	mu -sa ₄ ː -a-[]
N _{III-Z}	r. 9	^d en	-ki -ke ₄	niḡ ₂ -nam	mu -sa ₄ -a -ˈbaː		
N _{III-AA}	r. 5	^d en	-ki -ke ₄	niḡ ₂ -nam	ˈmu -sa ₄ ː -a-a ² -ˈbaː		
N _{III-DD}	o. 16	[ˈmuː-s[a ₄ -]
N _{III-EE}	o. 11	^d enː- ^{LIL} -ki -ke ₄	ˈniḡ ₂ -nam	muː -sa ₄ -a			
N _{III-EE1}	o. 7ː	[ˈmu -sa ₄ -ˈa -ba ²		
N _{III-FF}	o. 5	^d en	-ˈki -ke ₄	niḡ ₂ -ˈnam ²	muː-sa ₄ -a -ba		
N _{III-HH}	o. 2	[-k]e ₄	niḡ ₂ -nam	mu -s[a ₄ -]
Ur ₂	r. i 18ː	[n[iḡ ₂ ː] -nam	mu -ˈše ₂₁ ː -a -x		
Ur ₄	o. 14	[]-ˈke ₄ ː	[ni]ḡ ₂ -ˈnamː	še ₂₁ -a -ˈbaː		

⁸¹⁴ Römer, 1999: 201.

⁸¹⁵ Wilcke, 2002: 22; Volk, 2011: 277–278. Alster, 1975: 81 misunderstood of the term **ḡeš-gid₂-da** (“lance”, “length”, by context “trajectory”). In addition, he does not keep in mind that musicians might have had some problems for reading some texts written by scribes (*Šulgi E*, 249–251; ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

⁸¹⁶ Own score edition following the variants of Sjöberg, 1973: 146–147 (composite line on page 112), and the inspection of the copies/photos indicated below. Line 109 has been divided here in two since several manuscripts divided that line into two/three parts, and it was easier for us to arrange the edition in this way.

109a **kiḡ₂-ge₄-a ki nam-dub-sar-ra-gen₇ al-ge₁₇-ga**

N _{I-K}	r. i 13	kiḡ ₂ -ge ₄ -a	nam -dub -sa[r]	-gen ₇	al	-ge ₁₇ -ga x	
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 15	kiḡ ₂ -ge ₄ -a	ki n[am-]
N _{I-GG}	r. i 5	ḡkiḡ ₂ -ge ₄ -a	[]
N _{I-II}	o. 4	[]-ḡa	nam -dub -ḡsar		al]-[
N _{I-JJ}	o. 2'	[]-ge ₄ -a	ḡki	nam ² -dub -sar-ḡra	al	-[ge ₁₇]-ḡga
N _{III-Z}	r. 10	kiḡ ₂	nam -dub -sar -ra	-gen ₇	al	-ḡge ₁₇ -ḡga	
N _{III-AA}	r. 6	kiḡ ₂ -ge ₄ ² -ḡa	ḡki	nam -dub -ḡsar -ra	-gen ₇	al	-ge ₁₇ -ḡga
N _{III-EE}	o. 12	kiḡ ₂ -ḡge ₄ -a	ki	nam -ḡdub -sar -ra		al	-ḡge ₁₇]
N _{III-EE1}	o. 8'	[]-gen ₇		al	-ḡge ₁₇
N _{III-FF}	o. 6-7	ḡkiḡ ₂ -ge ₄ -a	ki	ḡnam -ḡdub -ḡsar -ra	-še ₃ /	ḡal	-ḡge ₁₇ -ḡga
N _{III-HH}	o. 3	[]-ge ₄ -a	ki	nam -ḡdub -ḡsar	[]
Ur ₂	r. i 19'	[sa]r ² -gen ₇		ḡal ²	-ḡge ₁₇
Ur ₄	o. 15	kiḡ ₂ -ḡgi -ḡa	nam -ḡdub -sar -r[a-g]en ₇		al	-ḡge ₁₇ -ḡga []	-ḡše ₂₁ /
	o. 16	a-ḡna ² -[...]-e-NE	ḡx [x]	nam-dub-ḡsar	[...]		

109b **ga-na mu-ni-in-pad₃-da**

N _{I-K}	r. i 13	ḡga -na	mu -ni	-ḡpad ₃ -da
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 15	[]
N _{I-GG}	r. i 5	[]
N _{I-II}	o. 4	KI	mu -ni -in-	[
N _{I-JJ}	o. 3'	ḡga -na	mu -ni-[i]n-pad ₃ -ḡda	
N _{III-Z}	r. 10	ga -<na>	mu -ni -in -ḡpad ₃ -de ₃	
N _{III-AA}	r. 6	ga -ḡna	mu -ni-	ḡpad ₃ -da ¹
N _{III-EE}	o. 12	ḡga -na	mu -ni	-[
N _{III-EE1}	o. 8'	ga -na	mu -ni	-ḡpad ₃ ² -da
N _{III-FF}	o. 8	ga -ḡna	mu-	[-ḡpad ₃ -da
N _{III-HH}	o. 3	ga-<na	mu>	-ni -x-[
Ur ₂	r. i 19'	ga -na	ḡmu -n[i-]
Ur ₄	o. 17	ḡga -na ²	mu -ḡni ²	ḡe ₂ -x-[

110 **mu-še₃ la-ba-sa₄ tukum-bi nam-nar-nu**

N _{I-K}	r. i 14	mu-ḡše ₃	la -ba	-sa ₄	tukum -bi	nam -nar -nu
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 16	mu -še ₃	la -[]/	tukum -b[i]
N _{I-II}	o. 5	mu -še ₃	la-[]-ḡsa ₄	tukum -b[i]
N _{I-JJ}	o. 4'-5'	[m]u-še ₃	la -ba-{ḡHU}	⁸¹⁷ -ḡsa ₄ /	ḡtukum -bi	nam -nar -nu
N _{III-Z}	r. 11	mu -še ₃	la -ba	-sa ₄	tukum ¹ -bi	nam -ḡnar -ḡnu ₁₀
N _{III-AA}	r. 7-8	ḡmu -še ₃	la -ba	-ḡsa ₄ /	tukum -bi	nam -[n]ar -ḡnu
N _{III-EE}	o. 13	ḡmu -še ₃	la -ba	-sa ₄ /	ḡtukum -bi	nam-ḡnar -nu
N _{III-EE1}	o. 9'	[]-ḡba	-sa ₄ /	[n]ar -ḡnu
N _{III-FF}	o. 9-10	mu-ḡše ₃	la ² -ḡba	-sa ₄ /	ḡtukum -bi	nam -nar -ḡnu
N _{III-HH}	o. 4	[]	tukum -bi	nam-[
Ur ₂	r. i 20'	[]	tu[kum]-bi	nam -ḡnar []
Ur ₄	o. 18	ḡmu-še ₂₁ -a	la -ḡba-še ₂₁		tu[kum]

(Father:) “¹⁰⁷ Among the people living in the country with (their) craftsmen, ¹⁰⁸ when Enki gave a name to all the things, ¹¹⁰ he did not designate ^{109a} contents which are so painful like those of the place of the scribal art!

^{109b} Come on! (Can) you name something (like that)?”

¹¹⁰ (Son:) “Except (those of) music!”

⁸¹⁷ The scribe probably tried to write here the sign ḡHU of the logogram sa₄(ḡHU.NA₂). However, perceiving that it might be confusing, he tried to erase that sign and rewrote it a bit closer to NA₂. Obviously, we say “he tried” because that sign is still readable in the tablet.

N _{I-K}	FTS, p. 62 [2 N-T 376] (publication copy)
N _{I-BB}	Wilcke, 1973: 35–37 [HS 1478 + 1538 + 1602] (publication copy)
N _{I-GG}	Sjöberg, 1973: 166 [N 3218] (publication copy; collated the 20/08/2019)
N _{I-II}	SEM 60 [CBS 13950] (publication copy; photo on CDLI P268950; collated the 20/08/2019)
N _{I-JJ}	SEM 61 [CBS 13964] (photo on CDLI P268962; collated the 20/08/2019).
N _{III-Z}	Kaneva, 1966: 70–73 [Hermitage 15234] (publication copy and photograph)
N _{III-AA}	Sjöberg, 1973: 158 [N 1063] (publication photo; collated the 20/08/2019)
N _{III-DD}	SEM 62 [CBS 13297] ⁸¹⁹ (publication copy; photo on CDLI P268378; collated the 22/08/2019)
N _{III-EE}	TMH NF 3 39 [HS 1459] (publication copy; photo/3D model on HAO)
N _{III-EE1}	Sjöberg, 1973: 166 [3 N-T 927,518] (publication copy) ⁸²⁰
N _{III-FF}	Sjöberg, 1973: 159 [UM 29-15-195] (publication photo; collated the 20/08/2019)
N _{III-HH}	Sjöberg, 1973: 167 [3 N-T 919,462] (publication copy) ⁸²¹
Ur ₂	UET 6/2 161 + 164 + 619 [U. ---] (photo on CDLI P346246; collated the 02/08/2019)
Ur ₄	UET 6/2 162 [U. ---] (photo on CDLI P346247; collated the 02/08/2019)

In this excerpt, the father tries to highlight the “aspects” (**ki₂-ge₄-a**)⁸²² of the writing (literally, “the place of the writing”, **ki nam-dub-sar-ra**)⁸²³ among the crafts (**gašam**) of the humanity (**nam-lu₂-ulu₃**)⁸²⁴. For that, he uses the expression **ge₁₇** referring to

⁸¹⁸ They follow Sjoberg, 1973: 107–109, but manuscripts from Nippur have an initial N (= Nippur) and an I (= Type I) or III (= Type III) according to their textual typology.

⁸¹⁹ Sjoberg, 1973: 108 confused the manuscripts and assigned SEM 62 to CBS 7099. Certainly, this tablet is a manuscript for the text *Two Scribes* (ETCSL 5.04.01) as we can see on CDLI P262138.

⁸²⁰ This tablet was not available for its collation on 19–23/08/2019 in the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology since it had already been returned to Iraq at that time.

⁸²¹ This tablet was not available for its collation on 19–23/08/2019 in the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology since it had already been returned to Iraq at that time.

⁸²² Previous translations: Sjoberg, 1973: 117 (“Beruf”, *idem* in Shehata, 2009: 1); Farber-Flüge, 1973: 110 (“Arbeit”); Römer, 1990: 85 (“Aufgabe”); Wilcke, 2002: 22 (“Handwerken”); Ziegler, 2013: 48 (“specialization”); Ceccarelli, 2018: 141 n. 64 (“Beruf”); Peterson, 2019b: 463 (“assigned task(?)”). See our thoughts on the meaning of this word in the previously studied text.

⁸²³ Sjoberg, 1973: 117 (“Schreiberhandwerk”, *idem* in Shehata, 2009: 1); Farber-Flüge, 1973: 110 (“Schreibkunst”); Römer, 1990: 85 (“Schreibkunst”), Wilcke, 2002: 22 (“Schreibkunst”) and Ziegler, 2013: 48 (“art du scribe”) forget the presence of **ki**, but not Peterson, 2019b: 463 (“place of(?) scribal art”).

⁸²⁴ Sjoberg, 1973: 117 (“Unter den sachkundigen Meistern“, *idem* in Shehata, 2009: 1); Römer, 1990: 85 (“Unter den Menschen, (*die*) jeweils Weisheit (*besitzen*)”); Civil, 1994: 73 (“the people who live at the artisans”); Wilcke, 2002: 22 (“Unter der Menschheit, die nach Handwerken”); Ziegler, 2013: 48 (“Parmi les spécialistes”); Ceccarelli, 2018: 141 n. 64 (“Für die Menschen, die unter Fachmännern im Lande wohnen”); Peterson, 2019b: 463 (“From the (ranks of) skilled humanity”). Our translation of lines 107–108 is based on this grammatical analysis: **nam.lulu** \emptyset [ABS] **gašam** + **ta** [ABL] **ma.da** + **a** [LOC] **a(l)** [VP] + **tuš** [PFV] + **a** [NMLZ] + **a** [distributive LOC = DGS, p. 257] **en.ki.k/g** + **e** [ERG] **ni₂.nam** + \emptyset [ABS] \emptyset [VP] + **mu** [VNT] (+ **n** [3SG.A]) + **sa₄** [PFV] + \emptyset [3NH.O] + **a** [NMLZ] + **be** [3NH.POSS] + **a** [LOC].

something able to sicken the one who practices it⁸²⁵. The father tries to show in this way that the scribal office is something so difficult that only a few people are able to master it completely. The son replies that **nam-nar** is also very complex. This term, **nam-nar**, has usually been translated here as “art of singing”⁸²⁶, something making sense with the comparison between the scribe’s hand and the **nar**’s throat (**meli**)⁸²⁷. However, our text compares here two professions *sensu lato*. Therefore, a meaning as “music”⁸²⁸ (as a larger entity than just “singing”) might fit better. The son argues his reply in these lines:

Text 25. *The Father and his rude Son*⁸²⁹

111 **peš₁₀ a-ab-ba-gen₇ peš₁₀ ‘peš₁₀-e’ bad-bad-ra₂**

N _{I-K}	r. i 15	pe[š ₁₀] a -ab -ba -gen ₇	peš ₁₀ -e	bad -bad -ra ₂
N _{III-Z}	r. 12	peš ₁₀ a -ab -ba -gen ₇	peš ₁₀ peš ₁₀ -bi	šag ₄ -nar -ka
N _{III-AA}	r. 8	peš ₁₀ a-‘ab -ba’-gen ₇	peš ₁₀ ‘peš ₁₀ -e’	
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 17	peš ₁₀ a -ab -ba -g[en ₇]
N _{III-EE}	o. 14	peš ₁₀ a -ab -ba -gen _x	peš ₁₀ -‘peš ₁₀ -e’	ba -bad -ra ₂
N _{III-EE1}	o. 10’	[pe]š ₁₀ ’	‘ba’ -bad -ra ₂
N _{III-FF}	o. 11	‘peš ₁₀ a -ab -ba -gen ₇ ’	[pe]š ₁₀ pe[š ₁₀ x	‘ba’ -bad -ra ₂
N _{III-HH}	o. 5	peš ₁₀ ‘a’-ab -ba -ka’ x []
N _{I-II}	o. 6	peš ₁₀ a-‘ab -ba -gen ₇ ’ x	‘pe[š ₁₀ -]
N _{I-JJ}	o. 6’	[pe]š ₁₀ ‘a’-ab -ba -gen ₇ ’ ²	‘peš ₁₀ peš ₁₀ ’ -a	ba -‘bad’ -ra ₂
Ur ₂	r. i 21’	[]	ba]d-‘bad -ra ₂ ’
Ur ₄	o. 19	peš ₁₀ a -ab -ba -gen ₇	‘peš ₁₀ ’ pe[š ₁₀]-‘še ₃ ’ []

112 **šag₄ nam-nar-ra ur₅-gen₇ al-su₃-ud**

N _{I-K}	r. i 16	šag ₄ nam -nar-ra’ ²	ur ₅ -gen ₇	al -su ₃ -ud
N _{III-Z}	r. 13	nam-dub-sar	ur ₅ -gen ₇	al -su ₃ -ud
N _{III-AA}	r. 9	[šag ₄ n]am-nar-ra-ka	‘ur ₅ ’-gen ₇	‘al’ ² -s[u ₃ -u]d
N _{I-BB}	r. iii 18	‘šag ₄ nam -na’[r]
N _{III-EE}	o. 15	[š]ag ₄ nam -nar-ra	ur ₅ ’-gen ₇	al -su ₃ -ud
N _{III-FF}	o. 12	‘šag ₄ nam’-nar’-ra-ka’	ur ₅ -gen ₇	al -‘su ₃ -ud’ ²
N _{III-HH}	o. 6	šag ₄ nam -‘nar’-[]
N _{I-II}	o. 7	šag ₄ nam -‘nar’-ra	ur ₅ -gen ₇	‘al’-[
N _{I-JJ}	o. 8’	[] nam -‘nar’-ra	ur ₅ -gen ₇	al -‘su ₃ ’ -ud
Ur ₂	r. i 22’	[]	‘al’ ² -[] x
Ur ₄	o. 20	šag ₄ nam-nar-ra-‘ke ₄ ’ []	x []

111 Like a shore of the ocean is very remote to the (other) shores,

112 so the (deep) sense of music (is) remote (to us)!

⁸²⁵ Attinger, 2019d: 65 for **ge₁₇**(-g) and related entries.

⁸²⁶ Sjöberg, 1973: 117 (“Gesangkunst”, *idem* in Shehata, 2009: 1); Farber-Flüge, 1973: 110 (“Gesangkunst”); Thomsen, 1984: 84 (“art of singing”); Zamudio, 2017: 81 (“arte de cantar”); Wilcke, 2002: 22 (“Sängertum”); Ceccarelli, 2018: 141 n. 64 (“Sängertum”).

⁸²⁷ *Proverbs* 2.43 (ETCSL 6.1.02).

⁸²⁸ Falkenstein, 1950: 150 n. 4 (“Musikantentum”); Römer, 1990: 85 (“Musikkunst”); Ziegler, 2013: 48 (“art de la musique”); Peterson, 2019b: 463 (“art of the musician”).

⁸²⁹ See *supra* all the details of this edition (also the *sigla*).

This excerpt has the **šag4 nam-nar-ra** (literally, “heart (šag4) of music”⁸³⁰), expression defined in the past as “knowledge⁸³¹ / secrets”⁸³² / sense⁸³³ / content(s)⁸³⁴ of music”⁸³⁵. We should keep in mind that only “sense” and “content” are accepted meanings for **šag4**⁸³⁶. Rest of these translations have their own words in Sumerian⁸³⁷. Furthermore, we need to analyse the term **su3-ud** explaining **šag4 nam-nar-ra** in our excerpt. We have four **al-su3-ud** in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts. The term **su3-ud** describes how distant are the richness⁸³⁸ or the roads to be crossed⁸³⁹ for a common person. However, it also describes how long life may be for the righteous person⁸⁴⁰.

The expression **al-su3-ud** might thus refer in our excerpt to something remote, which does not fit with **šag4 nam-nar-ra** as “aspect(s) of music”. Certainly, aspects of an entity can be “extensive” (**daṅal**), but not “remote” (**su3-ud**). In this sense, we should define **šag4 nam-nar-ra** as “(deep) sense of music”. That fits well with the sense of this expression in the excerpt *Šulgi B*, 162 to be discussed later. As we shall see again, **šag4 nam-nar-ra** is mentioned in *Šulgi B*, 162 in an enumeration of musical terms mainly referring to instruments, not to songs. Certainly, **šag4 nam-nar-ra** as “(deep) sense of singing”⁸⁴¹ is not suitable since a **nar** used to become a good musician when he has already mastered just one song (**en3-du**)⁸⁴². Therefore, in our opinion, there was not too much to explore concerning singing to have a “(deep) sense of singing”. However, music

⁸³⁰ Translated in this way in Sjöberg, 1973: 117 (“das ‘Herz’ der Gesangkunst”); Römer, 1990: 85 (“‘Herz’ der Musikkunst”) and perhaps Ziegler, 2013: 48 (“coeur (savoir?) de la musique!”).

⁸³¹ Wilcke, 2002: 22 (“vom Wesen des Sängertums” *idem* in Pruzsinszky, 2007: 331 and 2010: 97). Volk, 2011: 278 (“Wesen des Musikertums”).

⁸³² Shehata, 2009: 1 (“die ‘Geheimnisse’ der Musik/Gesangkunst”).

⁸³³ Farber-Flüge, 1973: 110 (“Sinn der Musik”).

⁸³⁴ Peterson, 2019b: 463 (“the content of the art of the musician”).

⁸³⁵ Alster, 1975: 83 translates the complete line as “so difficult is to learn the art of the singers”.

⁸³⁶ Attinger, 2019d: 176 (“contenu (d’un message)” and “sens (profond)”).

⁸³⁷ See ePSD for **niq2-umun** and **niq2-zu** (“knowledge”), **umun2** (“knowledge”, also “workshop” as we shall discuss below) in addition to **LIL2** (“secret knowledge”).

⁸³⁸ *Proverbs* 1.15 (Attinger, 2018: 3).

⁸³⁹ *Aba-taḥ-lugalḥa to his brothers*, 3 and 11 (ETCSL 3.3.06).

⁸⁴⁰ UET 6/2 258 [U. 17207,27] (Peterson, 2019b: 568.).

⁸⁴¹ As in Sjöberg, 1973: 117; Alster, 1975: 83; Wilcke, 2002: 22; Pruzsinszky, 2007: 331; Shehata, 2009: 1 and Pruzsinszky, 2010: 97 (see our previous notes for translations).

⁸⁴² *Proverbs* 2.39 (Attinger, 2018: 9).

might certainly have that “(deep) sense” as discipline/practice (perhaps a reflection of the type “what is the authentic purpose of music in our lives?”). Certainly, its contents were already very specialized by Old Babylonian times as we shall see, *inter alia*, in our section on Sumerian royal praise poetry.

In light of these considerations, we believe that the son tries to convince his father in this excerpt that difficulties of the writing concern just the body and its weakness, difficulties which can be solved with an additional training. However, problems of music concern the mind, something not so easy to train or to solve.

4.3. Mythological Narrations

4.3.1. Introduction: about a master of the music (**lugal nam-nar-ra**)

As an introduction to this section, we shall consider an excerpt dealing with the gods Enki and Deštinanna. It does not come from a mythological text but from a royal praise hymn. In any case, maybe this excerpt is useful for contextualizing what follows:

Text 26. *Šulgi E*⁸⁴³

162 **lugal nam-nar-ra** ^den-ki [...]

N _{I-I}	r. i' 7'	[na]m-nar -ra	^d en- ^r ki'	[...]
N _{U-J}	13'	[-na]r-^rra	^d suen'	[...]
X _{I-B}	r. i 14'	lugal	nam -nar -ra	^d e[n-	...]

163 ^dlamma ^rnam¹-nar-ra ^dḡeštin-an-[na⁸⁴⁴ ...]

N _{I-I}	r. i' 8'	[na]m -nar -ra	^d ḡeštin-[- ...]
N _{U-J}	14'	[-n]ar-^rra	diḡir-^rbe² ⁸⁴⁵ ^d ḡeš[tin- ...]
X _{I-B}	r. i 15'	^d lamma	^r nam ¹ -nar -ra	^d [...]

162 The master of music, Enki, [...]

163 The protective deity of music, Deštinan[na, ...]

⁸⁴³ Our own score edition keeping in mind that of BPOA, p. 166. However, we made some changes in that edition as a consequence of having consulted the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

⁸⁴⁴ ETCSL 2.4.2.05 has “^dḡeštin-an-/na\”, but there is no evidence of the last sign NA in the manuscripts according to our inspection.

⁸⁴⁵ Connections with the Kassite text PBS 1/1 11 [CBS 11341], r. 10 (CKST) are especially evident here due to the presence in that text of a **lamma-bi** (“their protective goddess”). See Westenholz, 2005: 362–363 for a previous comment and thanks to Luděk Vacín for the reference to this text and publication.

*Sigla*⁸⁴⁶

N_{I-I} Ni 3281 + BPOA 9 140 [Ni 3450] + Ni 3487 + 3497
(copy of BPOA 9 140; photo on CDLI P467839; collated the 20/08/2019)
N_{U-J} ISET 1 117 [Ist. Ni 9619] (publication copy)
X_{I-B} TCL 15 14 [AO 5380] (publication copy and photo on CDLI P345358)

The first line of this text has usually been understood as a reference to the moon god Nanna/Suen as “master” (**lugal**) of music⁸⁴⁷ starting from the variant N_{U-J}. However, the manuscript N_{I-I} suggested that Enki might be actually that master of music⁸⁴⁸. We are faced with two different conceptions about the supreme musical figure in Mesopotamia since manuscript N_{U-J} seems to have actually ^dEN.ʽZUʽ (= ^dʽsuenʽ)⁸⁴⁹ and not ^den-kiʽ. Moreover, Nanna/Suen was also praised with songs⁸⁵⁰ and instrumental music⁸⁵¹.

In any case, some legal texts⁸⁵² and the excerpt of *The Father and his rude Son* previously commented on here invite us to privilege the variant ^den-kiʽ for this excerpt of *Šulgi E*. Certainly, the fourth string of the instrument described in our Mesopotamian

⁸⁴⁶ They follow Klein, 2005: 149, but we have put an N (= Nippur) or X (= Uncertain) for their provenance. Manuscripts from Nippur have I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain) for their typology. For other *sigla* of Klein’s forthcoming edition of *Šulgi E*, see Klein and Sefati, 2013 and Klein, 2014: 174 n. 35.

⁸⁴⁷ Krispijn, 1990: 2 translates “Der Gott Sîn ist Herr der Musiker und der Musik, und Ĝestinanna ihre Schutzgöttin”. However, he confuses here **lugal nar-e-ne-ka** (“master of musicians”) with **lugal nam-nar-ra** (“master of music”). For his translation, we should have **u₃ nam-nar-ra**. The sentence **nam-nar-ra dlamma-bi** is neither explained well in that translation. We would follow Ludwig, 1990: 207 (“Der Herr der Gesangeskunst, Sîn...”) since the translation of **lugal** in ETCSL 2.4.2.05 translation (“King of the singer’s art, Suen”) does not fit correctly here. Certainly, we are dealing with a hymn for King Šulgi, and, therefore we should just have a king. That is, the god Suen cannot be another king.

⁸⁴⁸ BPOA 9, p. 166.

⁸⁴⁹ BPOA 9, p. 166 read “^dEn-ʽkiʽ?” However, the second sign is far from being KI (even incorrect) in our opinion, at the most ZU or BA (we have chosen the first one in light of the context).

⁸⁵⁰ **tige** (*Ibbī-Suen A*, 38 (ETCSL 2.4.5.1), *Nanna I*, 42 (ETCSL 4.13.09) and **a-da-ab** hymns (*Ibbī-Suen C*, 71; ETCSL 2.4.5.3); **bal-bal-e** responsorial chants (*Nanna A*, 6; ETCSL 4.13.01); **šer₃ nam-šub** sung texts (*Nanna K*, 28; ETCSL 4.13.11); **u₃-lu-lu-ma-ma** (*Ibbī-Suen D*, 16; ETCSL 2.4.5.4) and **i-lu** songs (*Nanna A*, 34–36; ETCSL 4.13.01).

⁸⁵¹ *Šulgi A*, 49–51 (Delnero, 2006: 1886–1888 with Vacín, 2011: 273, music of the **šems** cymbals, the **a₂-la₂** giant drum and the **tige₂**); *Temple Hymns*, 107 (ETCSL 4.80.1; music of the **a-da-ab** in the **nešbun** banquets of the Nanna’s temple in Ur, and music of the **šems** and the ^{ku₅}**a₂-la₂** play in its **unu₂** dining hall).

⁸⁵² See our Texts 16–17 for reference.

music theory texts is called in Akkadian *a ba-nu-u₂* or ^d*e₂-a DU₃* = “Ea the creator”⁸⁵³. In the following pages, we shall consider two excerpts from mythological narrations where **nam-nar** and the god Enki are related.

4.3.2. Music as destiny: **nam-nar** in *Enki and Ninmah*, b 26–29

At the dawn of the universe, the gods will demand for a solution that allows them to survive without working. At that moment, Enki, god of wisdom, together with the “Mother Goddesses” like Ninmah, decides to create human beings who will work for the gods henceforth. That fact was then celebrated at an after-party where Enki and Ninmah will get deeply drunk. At that moment, Ninmah threatens to curse humanity. Enki answers her that he will reverse all her evil actions. Because of this, Ninmah challenges Enki to decree a good destiny for seven disabled beings created by her⁸⁵⁴. In these pages, we shall focus our attention on the second of the said disabled beings of Ninmah:

Text 27. *Enki and Ninmah*⁸⁵⁵

b 26	ge₄-bi ḡeš-nu₁₁ ge₄-ge₄ lu₂ u₆-e am₃-ma-ni-in-dim₂
	OB-N _{I-A} o. ii 2 ḡe₄-bi [am₃-ma-ni-in-dim₂ ⁸⁵⁶]
	OB-X _{I-C} o. ii 26' ge₄-bi ḡeš-^rnu₁₁ ⁸⁵⁷ ge₄-g[e₄] lu₂ u₆'-e am₃-^rma' -ni-in-dim₂
b 27	^d en-ki ^{-ke₄} ḡeš-^rnu₁₁ ge₄-ge₄ lu₂ u₆-e i[gi du₈-a-ne₂-ta]
	OB-N _{I-A} o. ii 3' ^d en-ki ⁻⁸⁵⁸ [igi du₈-a-ne₂-ta ⁸⁵⁹]
	OB-X _{I-C} o. ii 27' ^d en-ki-ke₄ ḡeš-^rnu₁₁ ge₄-ge₄ lu₂ u₆'-e i[gi du₈-a-ne₂-ta ⁸⁶⁰]

⁸⁵³ Krispijn, 2002: 469; Shehata, 2002: 488. The connections of Enki with the instrumental music help to dismiss the translation of **nam-nar** as “singing” defended on Ludwig, 1990: 207 and ETCSL 2.4.2.05.

⁸⁵⁴ For the most recent overview of this narration, see Ceccarelli, 2016: 2–3.

⁸⁵⁵ Score edition dependent upon that of Ceccarelli, 2016: 110–112 with corrections derived from our consultation of the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated below (some of them collated).

⁸⁵⁶ Restitution ensured by OB-X_{I-C} o. ii 23' (Ceccarelli, 2016: 110).

⁸⁵⁷ Ceccarelli, 2016: 110 forgot a sign DEŠ between BI (= **bi**) and NU₁₁/ŠIR (= **nu₁₁**) reading **ḡešnu**(NU₁₁/ŠIR). However, we should read **ḡeš-nu₁₁** for keeping in mind that sign DEŠ. In this sense, we should follow the previous editions of this text (for instance, ETCSL 1.1.2 or, better, Lambert, 2013: 338).

⁸⁵⁸ Lambert, 2013: pl. 58 has here the beginning of an additional sign. However, our collation of the manuscript allows us to say that there is actually no sign in that part of said manuscript.

⁸⁵⁹ Restitution ensured by OB-N_{I-A} o. ii 15' (Ceccarelli, 2016: 114).

⁸⁶⁰ Restitution ensured by OB-X_{I-C} o. ii 24' (Ceccarelli, 2016: 110).

- b 28 **na[m]-bi i-ni-in`-tar` nam`-nar` mi`-ni-`in-ba`**
 OB-N_{I.A} o. ii 4' **na[m]-`bi` []-`in`-[]**
 OB-X_{I.C} o. ii 28' **na[m]-bi i-`ni-in`-tar` nam`-nar` mi`-ni-`in-ba`**
- b 29 **[nar]⁸⁶¹-`gal zag gu`-la⁸⁶² `igi lugal-la`-ke₄ `am₃`-[m]a-ni-i[n-gub]⁸⁶³**
 OB-N_{I.A} Omits
 OB-X_{I.C} o. ii 29' **[nar]-`gal zag gu`-la `igi lugal-la`-ke₄ `am₃`-[m]a-ni-i[n-gub]**
- b 26 Second, she (= Ninmah) created a “damaged-sighted man”, a “man to admire”.
 b 27 [After] Enki [sa]w the “man with the damaged sight”, the “man to admire”,
 b 28 he decreed his destiny: He allotted (to him to) music (and)
 b 29 he [established] (him as) Chief [Musician] in a pre-eminent position before the king.

*Sigla*⁸⁶⁴

- OB-N_{I.A} Ceccarelli, 2016: pl. 1–10 [CBS 2168 + 2202 + 11327 + 12738 + 13368 + N 1889]
 (publication photo; RTI model on CDLI P259234; collated the 19/08/2019)
 OB-X_{I.C} Ceccarelli, 2016: pl. 11–12, 14–15 [AO 7036]
 (copy on Lambert, 2013: pl. 60; publication photo; photo on Thomas, 2017)

The term **nam-nar** describes here the destiny (**nam**) of an individual who, according to the expressions **neš-nu₁₁ ge₄ ge₄** (“a damaged-sighted person”)⁸⁶⁵ and **lu₂ u₆-e** (“man

⁸⁶¹ This is the most popular (Sauren, 1993: 198; Casey, 1998: 207; Shehata, 2009: 37; Gadotti, 2010: 52; Ceccarelli, 2016: 46, 113) and logical restitution here. However, there have been other restitutions: 1) [en] (Benito, 1969: 27, 39), 2) [balan] (perhaps Wilcke, 2007: 32) and 3) [e₂] (Rodin, 2014: 287, 340).

⁸⁶² This has usually been transliterated as **ušumgal-la** (Benito, 1969: 27; ETCSL 1.1.2; Shehata, 2009: 37). However, we agree with Ceccarelli, 2016: pl. 13, but, we should be careful, since the ZAG of OB-X_{I.C}, r. i 4' has a central vertical wedge not present in OB-X_{I.C}, o. ii 29'. In any case, OB-X_{I.C}, r. i 4' is damaged at that part, and both shapes are still similar to ZAG. In our opinion, Henri de Genouillac (author of the copy of this tablet in TCL 16 71) confused the beginning and the end of ZAG respectively with another GAL and the beginning of BUR₂ (**ušumgal** = GAL.BUR₂). The term **ušumgal kalam-ma** is mentioned in *Šulgi T*, 10 (ETCSL 2.4.2.20), but it comes from Gudea's times as we saw in our first chapter.

⁸⁶³ Restitution ensured by OB-X_{I.C} o. ii 25' (Ceccarelli, 2016: 110).

⁸⁶⁴ They follow Ceccarelli, 2016: 89–91, but we put OB (= Old Babylonian) for the chronology of the tablets of this text. Certainly, there are also some Neo-Assyrian tablets for *Enki and Ninmah*. See Ceccarelli, 2016: 90 for reference. In addition, we put an I (= Type I) for their tablet typology when the tablets come from Nippur, and N (= Nippur) or X (= Uncertain) for their provenance.

⁸⁶⁵ We agree with Ceccarelli, 2016: 47–48 as a consensus between the main positions for this expression. On the one hand, those understanding it as “blind person” (Renger, 1969: 184, n. 839; Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 191; Ziegler, 2006b: 39; Lambert, 2013: 339; Ziegler, 2017: 32). On the other hand, those translating as “someone who turned back the light” (ETCSL 1.1.2: 61–64; Shehata, 2009: 36; Gadotti, 2010: 53; Westenholz, 2013: 265; Rodin, 2014: 287). In addition, see Couto Ferreira, 2009: 145, 240, **Lugal u₄ me-lam₂-bi nir-ḡal**, 514 (ETCSL 1.6.2) and *Dumuzi-Inanna T*, 22 (ETCSL 4.08.20) for comments about the ^{na4}**neš-nu₁₁-gal/ašnugallu(m)**, a brilliant object able to project light like the human eye.

to admire”)⁸⁶⁶, seems to be blind. In this way, the content of this excerpt recalls those Old Babylonian texts about blind musicians⁸⁶⁷, like this one (of uncertain provenance). In this text, the blind female, Šinunutum, is going to learn music (*nārūtum*)⁸⁶⁸:

Text 28. TJA, p. 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna, 23-10-02 (?))⁸⁶⁹

- o. 1 *iš-tu* ITI AB. ʾE₃. ʾA U₄. 18.KAM⁸⁷⁰
 o. 3 ^{pf}*ši-nu-nu-tum* IGI.NU.<DAL₂>⁸⁷¹
 o. 4 ʾa-na ʾna-ru-tim a-ḥa-zi-im
 o. 5 ʾa-na ʾma-aḥ-ri-ia
 o. 6 ub-lu-ʾni ʾi-š

o. 1. From the 18th day of the month Ṭebētum, o. 2-6. he brought to me Šinunutum, a blind female, for learning music (with me).

In order to elucidate the meaning of **nam-nar** in *Enki and Ninmaḥ*, we should have a look at the term **nar gal**. This term, placed at the last line of our excerpt, designates the exact condition of the blind individual of Ninmaḥ once Enki has decided his musical destiny (**nam**). According to the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts, the **nar gal** could be 1) the teacher of some inexpert musicians⁸⁷², 2) a sort of professional colleague of the **um-mi-a** (“scholars”) in charge of the hymns for the king⁸⁷³, or 3) a supervisor of

⁸⁶⁶ See Ceccarelli, 2016: 48 for the most plausible interpretation of this expression.

⁸⁶⁷ See FM 9, p. 21–22 for those texts, all of them coming from Mari.

⁸⁶⁸ Previous translations of *nārūtum* in this excerpt: CAD A1, p. 177b (“the art of singing”); TJA, p. 151 (“le chant”); CAD N1, p. 382 (“the art of the musician”); Gelb, 1976: 59 (“singing”); Shehata, 2009: 38 (“nar-Kunst”); Démare-Lafont, 2011: 14 (“musique”); Cohen and Kedar, 2011: 240 (“the musician’s craft”); Stol, 2012: 550 and 2016: 362 (“music”); Ziegler, 2017: 38 (“la musique”); Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 98 (“música”). We prefer the translations as “music” since we do not have sufficient information about Šinunutum to know her concrete musical specialization as singer (in reference to the translations of CAD A1, p. 177b and TJA, p. 151) or another type of musician.

⁸⁶⁹ Edition dependent upon TJA, p. 151 and CDLI P315346. We have corrected their transliterations inspecting the handwritten copy and photo of this manuscript on CDLI P3153456.

⁸⁷⁰ TJA, p. 151 and CDLI P315346 have considered U₄.18.KAM as an independent line. However, as TJA, p. 151 showed it, this sequence actually does not start at the beginning of the supposed line 2.

⁸⁷¹ Restitution following Fincke, 2000: 61, which helps to dismiss TJA, p. 151 n. 1.

⁸⁷² “*Monkey*” to his mother, 6 (Kleinerman, 2011: 158 and 278), and *Proverbs* 3.150.

⁸⁷³ *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 333, C 6–7 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

music⁸⁷⁴. In fact, the **nar gal** appears just once⁸⁷⁵ in those texts using an instrument (the **a2 tarah**, “ibex horn”) which probably was used just as a signal instrument, and not as a true melodic instrument like the other instruments mentioned in that excerpt⁸⁷⁶.

Therefore, the **nar gal** should not be considered in our excerpt a performer as it has usually been understood⁸⁷⁷. Far from that, and even if he had to be an excellent musician in an earlier point in his career⁸⁷⁸, the **nar gal** should be seen as a musical organizer. According to the Old Babylonian administrative texts from southern Mesopotamia, his competences could *a priori* pertain to all kind of musicians⁸⁷⁹. However, they differed concerning those in northern Mesopotamia, and especially the kingdom of Mari. Certainly, in that kingdom, a single *nargallum* used to be the in charge of all the musical activities of the state in addition to other, occasional non-musical activities⁸⁸⁰. In Southern Mesopotamia, the musical competences of the **nar gal** became more limited in the most important cities from a cultic perspective. Certainly, we have several references to two **nar gal** at the same time in Nippur. Each of them might be in charge of the musical activities of some temples as in other southern Mesopotamian cities at that time⁸⁸¹.

The said condition of the **nar gal** as a specialization of the **nar** makes sense also in light of our Old Babylonian lexical evidence, where this figure is just one of the different

⁸⁷⁴ Šulgi E, 155. See the beginning of the next section of this study for our edition and comments.

⁸⁷⁵ Unlike Shehata, 2009: 24, **nar gal-zu** of *Uruk Lament*, H 27 (ETCSL 2.2.5) is not a variant of **nar gal** since **gal-zu** (“skilful”) is an adjective of **nar**, as in *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 338 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01) with **nar gal-an-zu-ne** (**gal-zu** is an alternative spelling of **gal-an-zu**).

⁸⁷⁶ *Našše A*, 41–44 (Attinger, 2019e: 84–85). See Kümmel, 1972–1975: 469 for comments.

⁸⁷⁷ Sauren, 1993: 198 n. 3 (“king’s singer”); Kikawada, 1994: 171 (“singer”); Casey, 1998: 207 (“singer”); Stol, 2000: 109 (“singer”); FM 9, p. 22 (“grand musicien”); Espak, 2010: 197 (“a musician in the king’s court”); Westenholz, 2010: 202 (“singer and musician”); Ziegler, 2011: 294 (“musician”); Zgoll, 2012: 48 (“Sänger”); Rodin, 2014: 290 (“musician of the king”); Westenholz, 2013: 265 (“a court rather than a sacerdotal musician”); Ceccarelli, 2016: 55 (“großer Sänger”); Ziegler, 2017: 32 (“musicien”).

⁸⁷⁸ FM 9, p. 9 talked about the *nargallum* in Mari texts. However, that idea still makes sense since, in many Spanish *amateur* wind orchestras, the conductor is usually the most veteran musician of that group.

⁸⁷⁹ In AbB 9 193 [NBC 5309] (Ḫammu-rāpi 31+), r. 1 (Archibab T767), the *nargallum* Šu-Amurru is responsible for a group of *huppûm* acrobatic dancers.

⁸⁸⁰ See the different works by Nele Ziegler (2006a: 347–348; 2006b: 36–37; 2007: 7–12; 2011: 90; 2012: 35–41; 2013: 50–62) for an overview of the *nargallum* in that kingdom.

⁸⁸¹ Shehata, 2009: 22 besides Mayer, 2005: pl. 35–36 [IB 211] (Rīm-Sîn I 38-11-00), r. 4–5 (Archibab T19565) (not commented on by Shehata, 2009: 22) and TMH 10 8 [HS 2077] (Šamšu-ilūna 15-02-01), o. 8–9 (Archibab T23260).

specialities of the **nar**⁸⁸². Therefore, we would follow to those who have understood **nar gal** in *Enki and Ninmah* as a “chief musician”⁸⁸³.

In this sense, **nam-nar** cannot designate the profession of the **nar**⁸⁸⁴ since we are dealing with a different type of musical figure. In the same way, we should dismiss the translations of **nam-nar** as “art of song”⁸⁸⁵ or “art of singing”⁸⁸⁶ (in addition to “musicianship”⁸⁸⁷). The reason is the **nar gal** was a musical organizer, not a performer, and, at the most, he should be understood as an instrumentalist, and not as singer.

We arrive finally to the translations of **nam-nar** in *Enki and Ninmah* as “art of music”⁸⁸⁸ and “music”⁸⁸⁹. Both translations are very similar. However, if we consider “art” as “technique” (as in “the art of war”), we shall transform our **nar gal** in a specialist when his profession as “musical administrator” was certainly generalist within the field of music. On the other hand, if we consider “art” as “artistic manifestation”, we shall forget that the **nar gal** should also deal with the non-artistic parts of the music (for instance, the good maintenance of the musical instruments). In this sense, we would support the interpretations of **nam-nar** as “music”, whose generic character is in line with the profession of the **nar gal**.

⁸⁸² *Proto-lu2*, 642 (DCCLT Q000047).

⁸⁸³ Kramer and Maier, 1989: 34 (“[chief] musician”); Klein, 1997: 518 (“chief-[musician]”) and perhaps Shehata, 2009: 36 (“großen/Ober-[Musiker]”).

⁸⁸⁴ Renger, 1969: 184, n. 839 (“Amt des nar”).

⁸⁸⁵ Kramer and Maier, 1989, 34 (“art of song”).

⁸⁸⁶ Benito, 1969: 39, 65 (“art of singing”); Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 191 (“art du chant”); Saporetti, 1993: 121 (“arte del canto”); Wilcke, 2007: 32 (“Sangeskunst”); Lambert, 2013: 339 (“art of singing”); Ceccarelli, 2016: 46, 111, 113 (“Sangeskunst”).

⁸⁸⁷ Gadotti, 2010: 53 (“musicianship”).

⁸⁸⁸ Jacobsen, 1987: 159 (“musical arts”; same translation in ETCSL 1.1.2; Walls, 2007: 17; Westensholz, 2013: 265 and Rodin, 2014: 287, 340); Klein, 1997: 518 (“musical art”; same translation on Schipper, 2006: 64) and Ziegler, 2006b: 39 and Ziegler, 2017: 32 (“art de la musique”).

⁸⁸⁹ Römer, 1993: 394, n. 64a (“Musik”); Fincke, 2000: 63 (“Musik”); Shehata, 2009: 36 (“Musik”).

4.3.3. About *Inanna and Enki* I v 33–34 and II v 47–52

4.3.3.1. Introduction

The goddess of love and war and the lady of Uruk, Inanna, was disappointed with the cultic/ordinances (**ḡarza**) received from Enki during the Ordering of the World. In this sense, she decided to go to Enki’s city, Eridu, in order to speak with him and to obtain additional powers. Once she arrived in that city, Enki decided to prepare a welcoming feast for her where he got (again) very drunk. As a consequence, he unconsciously gave to Inanna many of his “divine powers” (**me**)⁸⁹⁰, among which we find a reference to **nam-nar**, and the goddess decided to carry these to Uruk. When she was arriving in her city, Enki, recovered from his drunkenness, asked his assistant, Isimud, where his divine powers were. We find our first allusion to **nam-nar** in one of those questions:

Text 29. *Inanna and Enki*, PBS 1/1 1 [CBS 13571 + 13602 + 13617 + 13623 + 13629]⁸⁹¹

I v 33 [...] ‘**ku**₃’ DAR² AN **nu-ge**₁₇ **an-na ḡeš-gu**₃-‘**di**⁸⁹² **nam**²-**nar**² **nam**²-**ab-ba me**²-‘**a**⁸⁹³
I v 34 [**lugal-ḡu**₁₀] ‘**dumu**²’-[**ne**₂-**er ba-an-na-šum**₂]

I v 33 (Enki:) “Where are the pure [...], the [...], the heaven’s **nu-ge**₁₇, the **ḡeš-gu**₃-**di**, the music and the old age?”

I v 34 (Isimud:) “[My lord, they were given to his] daughter!”⁸⁹⁴

⁸⁹⁰ About the “**me**” and their relationships with Inanna, see Cavigneaux, 1978 and Glassner, 1992.

⁸⁹¹ Edition dependent upon Farber-Flüge, 1973: 28 with consultation of the photo and RTI model of the tablet available on CDLI P268601. This tablet was collated on 19/08/2019. BPOA 9 16 [N 4838] has Tablet I, iii 2 and 10 and iv 32–41, and BPOA 9 17 [N 5730] has several lines from the end of the myth whose position in the whole text is still unclear.

⁸⁹² In this case, everybody seems to agree in the transliteration as **ḡeš-gu**₃-**di** and not ^h**gu**₃-**di**: Farber-Flüge, 1973: 29 (“ḡiš-gù-di”); Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“ḡiš.gù.di”); Glassner, 1992: 65 (“ḡiš.gu₃.di”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“ḡiš-gù-di”); ETCSL 1.3.1. (“ḡiš-gu₃-di”); Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 (“ḡiš-gu₃-di”) (Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233, and Farber, 1998: 522 give just a translation of this term). We shall return to this matter for our commentary on *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188, where there is more controversy about it.

⁸⁹³ Last lines of this column are bad preserved in general, and signs are very compressed in the writing just as we could see in our collation of the tablet. In this sense, the transliteration is not entirely sure.

⁸⁹⁴ Farber-Flüge, 1973: 29; Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233; ETCSL 1.3.1 have seen a transitive sentence. However, we should have **mu-un-na-šum**₂, not **ba-an-na-šum**₂ since the MM {**ba**} usually gives a passive sense to the verb (DGS, p. 386, 402, 468, 488). In this way, **lugal-ḡu**₁₀ might be analysed as a vocative. See DGS, p. 160, 300–301 for vocatives with the 1SG.POSS {**ḡu**}.

Enki's attempts to recover those powers were unsuccessful, and Uruk praised her mistress for having brought them, now individually enumerated in the text:

Text 30. *Inanna and Enki*, Farber-Flügel, 1973: pl. 1 [CBS 15283]⁸⁹⁵

II v 47	nigin3-ṛar [ku]g [b]a'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 48	ṛx' AN [...] [b]a'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 49	ṛnu'-ge ₁₇ a[n-n]a [b]a'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 50	ṛeš-gu3-di [b]a'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 51	nam-nar ṛba'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 52	nam-ab-ba ṛba'-<e-de ₆ >
II v 47	<You have brought> the [pur]e nigin3-ṛar
II v 48	<You have brought> the [...]
II v 49	<You have brought> the nu-ge₁₇ [o]f the hea[ven]
II v 50	<You have brought> the ṛeš-gu3-di lute
II v 51	<You have brought> music
II v 52	<You have brought> old age

Concerning these excerpts and their previous translations, **nam-nar** has been defined here as 1) “profession of the **nar**”⁸⁹⁶ or similar⁸⁹⁷, 2) “art of the song/singing⁸⁹⁸”, and 3) “music”⁸⁹⁹. In order to elucidate its exact meaning, we propose a lexicographical study of some terms mentioned together with **nam-nar** in these excerpts.

4.3.3.2. Lexicographical approach to the terms of this excerpt

4.3.3.2.1. **ṛeš-gu3-di**

This term has sometimes been translated as “musical instrument” *lato sensu*⁹⁰⁰ in this excerpt. From that, and keeping in mind the non-human gender of **ṛeš-gu3-di**⁹⁰¹, this term

⁸⁹⁵ Edition dependent upon Farber-Flügel, 1973: 56 with consultation of the photo and RTI model on CDLI P269824. This tablet was collated on 19/08/2019.

⁸⁹⁶ Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 (“l’office de musicien”).

⁸⁹⁷ Hartmann, 1960: 151 (“nar-Amt”); Waetzoldt, 1975: 383 (“Sänger” as “ein ‘künstlerischer’ Beruf”); Krispijn, 1990: 2; (“(Hymnen)Sänger”); Glassner, 1992: 65 (“l’office du chantre”).

⁸⁹⁸ Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233 (“l’Art du chant”); Farber, 1997: 522 (“the art of singing”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“Sängeramt/Sangeskunst”); ETCESL 1.3.1. (“the art of song”).

⁸⁹⁹ Farber-Flügel, 1973: 29 (“die Musik”).

⁹⁰⁰ Farber-Flügel, 1973: 29 (“das lauttönende Instrument”); Glassner, 1992: 65 (“l’instrument sonore”).

⁹⁰¹ *Šulgi B*, 168 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

has also been understood here as “musical instruments”⁹⁰², even as “orchestra”⁹⁰³. However, this interpretation of **neš-gu3-di** is anachronistic. On the one hand, it is based on an excerpt from an earlier text, the *Gudea* Cylinders. In that text, **neš-gu3-d** is an epithet describing the Ninjirsu’s beloved **balan** lyre Ušumgal-kamma⁹⁰⁴, and not an independent instrument. On the other hand, according to other Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts, the **neš-gu3-di** is an object having strings (**sa**)⁹⁰⁵ and frets (**si-EZEN**)⁹⁰⁶, and it is also played with a “fingering technique” (**aga šu-si**). Such features⁹⁰⁷ fit suitably with the description of a lute, just as the term **neš-gu3-di** has occasionally been translated⁹⁰⁸. In fact, the term **neš** (“wood”) and the etymological construction of **neš-gu3-di**, recalls the Arabic term *al-’ūd* (literally “wood”) used for designating the lute in Arabic⁹⁰⁹.

The terms **neš-gu3-di** and **nam-nar** are closely connected in Old Babylonian literary texts. On the one hand, the **neš-gu3-di** is the unique instrument connected to the **e2 nam-nar-ra** of *Ur-Namma A*, 188 to be studied below. It was also one of the instruments mastered by Šulgi and Išmē-Dagān in their devotion to the music (**nam-nar**)⁹¹⁰. On the other hand, the **nar** plays the **neš-gu3-di** on several events⁹¹¹. Some authors argued that the origin of this connection might be the condition of the **neš-gu3-di** as an instrument enabling the musicians to sing while playing a melody or accompaniment with said **neš-gu3-di**⁹¹². However, it is evident that this instrument would not be the only⁹¹³ one allowing

⁹⁰² ETCSL 1.3.1. (“loud musical instruments”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“Holz(-Blas?)-Instrument”)

⁹⁰³ Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233 (“l’Orchestre sonore”; same translation in Slobodzianek, 2012: 40).

⁹⁰⁴ *Gudea Cylinders*, A6.25 (Römer, 2010: 13).

⁹⁰⁵ *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 370 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01.)

⁹⁰⁶ *Summer and Winter*, 235 (ETCSL 2.2.5).

⁹⁰⁷ Forgotten in Gabbay, 2014: 117, who focused on the lexical evidence and defined this term just as an instrument in order to explain what we have in *Gudea Cylinders*, A6.25 (Römer, 2010: 13). However, we tend to think into a chronological evolution of the meaning of the term **neš-gu3-di** towards its identification with a lute in Old Babylonian times. That makes sense with the increasingly bigger popularity of lutes in Mesopotamia by the Early 2nd Millennium BCE (Krispijn, 2011: 117).

⁹⁰⁸ Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“Laute(nspieler)”; Farber, 1997: 522 (“the resounding lute”).

⁹⁰⁹ Kilmer 1980–1983a, 512.

⁹¹⁰ *Šulgi B*, 167–168 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02) and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 370 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

⁹¹¹ *Iddin-Dagān A*, 204–207 (Attinger, 2014a: 25); *Šulgi B*, 159–160 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

⁹¹² Personal communication of Dahlia Shehata.

⁹¹³ This fact might be suggested by *Iddin-Dagān*, 204: **neš-gu3-di ulu3-ta eme nar-ra** (Attinger, 2014a: 25) “with the **neš-gu3-di**, which places the tongues against the south wind(?)”. However, its sense is still unclear for us. See Attinger, 2014a: 58 for comments about this excerpt.

the musician to do that⁹¹⁴. In our opinion, and keeping in mind the information from our Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts, we tend to think that the **neš-gu₃-di** might be a very common musical instrument because it would be an easy instrument for learning some basic musical aspects, like the designation (**pad₃**), raising (**gid₂-i**), lowering (**tu-lu**) and maintaining (**gen₆-na**) of the musical intervals (**ad**, literally “voices”)⁹¹⁵.

4.3.3.2.2. **nam-ab-ba**

This term was mentioned after **nam-nar** in our lexical Text 10. Many people have understood **nam-ab-ba**⁹¹⁶ in this context as something like “the profession of the **ab-ba**”⁹¹⁷. However, that term seems to refer only to old age as a human vital phase⁹¹⁸ in other Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts⁹¹⁹, and nothing related to a profession.

Music and old age had to be related in ancient Mesopotamia. Certainly, **nam-nar** and **nam-bur-šu-ma** were mentioned together in our Texts 18–20, and the **nar gal** might be defined as a chief musician because of his/her experience as a “mature (**gal**)”⁹²⁰ musician”. It is true that young people could already be accomplished musicians, and a person could become a good musician if (s)he were able to perform a single **en₃-du** song well⁹²¹.

In any case, as Farber-Flüge said⁹²², relationships between music and old age should come from the fact that old age would probably be the unique moment where a person

⁹¹⁴ For instance, in *Šulgi A*, 78 (Delnero, 2006: 1900–1901), a group of **nar** used seven **tigez** drums for accompanying themselves during the performance of a **ser₃** song.

⁹¹⁵ *Šulgi B*, 171 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

⁹¹⁶ For a description starting from **Ugu-ḡu₁₀**, 284 (DCCLT Q002268), see Couto Ferreira, 2009: 358.

⁹¹⁷ Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233 (“l’Office d’Ancien”); Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“(Kult)ältester”); Glassner, 1992: 65 (“l’office d’abba”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“Amt/Funktion des Ältesten”).

⁹¹⁸ We agree, in this sense, with Farber-Flüge, 1973: 29 (“das Alter” although it is actually a translation from **ab-ba**, not from **nam-ab-ba**); Farber, 1997: 522 (“the (wise) state of old age”); ETCSL 1.3.1. (“venerable old age”) and Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 (“l’ancienneté”). This last translation is, in our opinion, the best possible, since Farber, 1997: 522 and ETCSL 1.3.1 suppose a “venerable” condition which we can infer from other allusions to this term (see previous note) but it is not explicitly indicated in the text.

⁹¹⁹ *Enlil A*, 34 (Attinger, 2015: 13); *Death of Nawirtum*, 59 (ETCSL 5.5.3); *Heron and Turtle*, 17 (Peterson, 2007: 297); UET 6/2 371 [U. 17207,76], o. 5 (Peterson, 2019b: 622).

⁹²⁰ For this meaning of **gal**, see ePSD (“(to be) retired, former; (to be) mature (of male animals)”).

⁹²¹ *Proverbs* 2.39; UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88], o. 6 and UET 6/2 290 [U. 17207,55], o. 1 (Peterson, 2019b: 573, 582).

⁹²² Farber-Flüge, 1973: 110.

could actually be a good musician, always according to the Mesopotamian mentality. That would be due to the long time for mastering all the difficulties of music described, for instance, in *The Father and his rude Son*, a text previously studied in this chapter.

4.3.3.3. Conclusions

The term **neš-gu3-di** helps us to dismiss the previous translations of **nam-nar** in this context as “art of song/singing”. Certainly, if **nam-nar** referred to something pertaining to singing, we would have expected the mention of a term from that domain, and not a musical instrument such as the **neš-gu3-di**. Additionally, **nam-ab-ba** is not at all referred to a profession, but to a phase of the human life. In this sense, we cannot translate **nam-nar** (mentioned just before that term) as another profession.

The terms **niġin3-ġar ku3**⁹²³ and **nu-ge17 an-na**⁹²⁴ of this text have not been studied here. However, they are irrelevant for an identification of **nam-nar** beyond, perhaps, the mention of **niġin3-ġar ku3** in *Temple Hymns*⁹²⁵, or the relationships of the *qadištum* (Akkadian equivalent of **nu-ge17**) with the **gala(-mah)** in the Old Babylonian texts⁹²⁶.

In this sense, we would translate **nam-nar** as “music” in *Inanna and Enki* despite the mention of other instruments (the **tige2**, **li-li-is3**, **ub3**, **me-ze2** and ^{kuš}**a2-la2** drums) in a separate part of the enumeration of the divine realities brought to Uruk by Inanna⁹²⁷. Certainly, their mention in that place might suggest that **nam-nar** is actually just a concrete part of music, and those instruments represent another part of that music. However, **tige2** is connected with **nam-nar** in other contemporary texts⁹²⁸, and the section where those instruments are mentioned is highly damaged. In this sense, we cannot know

⁹²³ Farber-Flügel, 1973: 29 (“Das reine [niġin-gar]”); Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233 (“saint Nigingar”); Glassner, 1992: 64 (“le saint niġin.gar”); Farber, 1997: 523 (“holy NIGINĜAR shrine”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“Heilige Cella”); ETCSL 1.3.1. (“holy niġin-ġar shrine”); Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 (“pur ningingar”).

⁹²⁴ Farber-Flügel, 1973: 29 (“die Himmelshierodule”); Bottéro and Kramer, 1989: 233 (“la Hiérodoliceleste (?)”); Glassner, 1992: 64 (“la femme du rang nugig.anna”); Farber, 1997: 523 (“the hierodule of heaven”); Selz, 2003: 252 (“Himmlische Hierodule”); ETCSL 1.3.1. (“mistress of heaven”); Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 (“la souveraine du ciel”). For “mistress of heaven” and similar translations, Slobodzianek, 2012: 40 n. 136 starting from Cavigneaux and al-Rawi, 1995: 193–194; Zgoll, 1997: 194.

⁹²⁵ *Temple Hymns*, 206, 316, 513 respectively (ETCSL 1.4.1).

⁹²⁶ See Shehata, 2009: 108, 186, 188 n. 1082, 200–201 for reference.

⁹²⁷ *Inanna and Enki*, II vi 24 (Farber-Flügel, 1973: 60).

⁹²⁸ *Šulgi B*, 157 (see *infra* for our own score edition of this text).

their actual context in the list of divine powers of Inanna and, therefore, the reason for which they are separated from **nam-nar**.

4.4. Royal Praise Poetry

4.4.1. Introduction

We proceed now to have a look at our references to **nam-nar** in the Old Babylonian royal praise poetry. These texts usually contain many musical allusions. Certainly, music itself was the mechanism for making “alive” and rendering “eternal” the praises addressed to the Mesopotamian kings⁹²⁹. In addition, some of these kings were very involved in said musical practice as we shall see in some textual excerpts to be studied here⁹³⁰. As a result, we find a very complex musical terminology in the royal praise hymns, and the term **nam-nar** will take part in the said complexity as we shall see.

4.4.2. About a musical room in *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188

4.4.2.1. Introduction

In this section⁹³¹, we are going to deal with an excerpt of hymn *Ur-Namma A*, a text which “is unique within the corpus of literary Sumerian compositions, insofar as it honours a king posthumously and tells of his actual death”⁹³². Certainly, it is a singular combination of two different subgenres: royal praise poetry and city laments. This is the excerpt:

⁹²⁹ *Šulgi E*, 249–259 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

⁹³⁰ In addition, *Šulgi B*, 196 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02); *Šulgi C*, B 75–82 (ETCSL 2.4.2.03) and *Šulgi E*, 51 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

⁹³¹ An earlier version of these lines will appear in Sánchez Muñoz, *forthcoming* – a. This version uses some later remarks of Theo J. H. Krispijn and our collations of the manuscripts of this text at the University of Pennsylvania Museum (thanks to Theo J. H. Krispijn and Philip Jones for making it possible).

⁹³² Flückiger-Hawker 1999, 16.

187 **tige₂ a-[d]a-ab gi-gid₂¹ za-am-za-am- η u₁₀ [e]_{r2}-ra mu-da-an-ku₄**⁹³⁴

N _{I-A}	r. v 21	tige₂ a-[d]a-ab gi-gid₂ ¹⁹³⁵	za-am-za-am-ηu₁₀ / er₂ ⁹³⁶	ra mu-da-¹an¹-ku₄
N _{U-E}	o. 24 ¹	[]
Sb ₃	r. 4 ¹	[] a¹-da-¹ab¹ gi-gid₂²	za₃-za₃-mi₂	er₂ ba-¹ni-x¹-[]

188 **η eš-gu₃-di e₂ na[m]-¹nar¹-ra-ka zag e₂- η ar₈-e¹ i¹-ni-in-us₂**

N _{I-A}	r. v 22	ηeš-gu₃-di ⁹³⁷	e₂ na[m]-¹nar¹-ra-ka	zag e₂-ηar₈-e¹ i¹ -ni-in-us₂
N _{U-E}	o. 25 ¹	[] ¹ x ¹ []
Sb ₃	r. 5 ¹	[-d i e ₂	¹ x x(-)[k]a ² ⁹³⁸ zag e₂-ηar₈ ¹ba²-ni² -us₂

187 My **tige₂, a-da-ab, gi-gid₂**, and **za-am-za-am** changed into **er₂** laments with me.188 (About) the **η eš-gu₃-di**, someone was inactive in the (palace) music room.*Sigla*⁹³⁹N_{I-A} *Kollationen*, p. 66–67 [HS 1428 + 1450 + 1528 + 1548 + 1549 + 1560 + 1570 + 1581] (publication copy) + PBS 12/1 24 [CBS 4560] (photo on CDLI P260874; collated the 20/08/2019)N_{U-E} *Kollationen*, p. 68–69 [HS 1440 + 1529] (publication copy)Sb₃ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: pl. 11–13 [Sb 12358 + 12362] (photo on CDLI P357266)

⁹³³ Score edition dependent upon that of Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133 with changes derived from our inspection of the copies/photos of the manuscripts of this text indicated below.

⁹³⁴ Composite lines follow here the Nippur manuscripts (N_{I-A} and N_{U-E}) due to the uncertain readings and peculiarities of manuscript Sb₃ (from Susa), like the unusual spelling **za₃-za₃-mi₂** for /*zamzam*/.

⁹³⁵ The sign is more similar to SUD (= **su₃**). However, we would consider it a *Sonderform* of BU (= **gid₂**) (aBZL 265). Certainly, the preservation of SUD and BU is not the same in manuscript A, and Sb₃ might contain BU and not SUD according to Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133 n. 131.

⁹³⁶ Kramer, 1967b: 116; Ludwig, 1990: 53; Kramer, 1991: 208 have **a-nir**, but N_{I-A} has ¹A¹.IGI = **er₂**.

⁹³⁷ Some editions have ¹eš-gu₃-di (Kramer, 1967b: 120; Alster, 1974: 104; Krispijn, 1990: 13; Kramer, 1991: 209; Krispijn, 2008: 177). However, other editions have **η eš-gu₃-di** (Ludwig, 1990: 53; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133; ETCSL 2.4.1.1; CDLI P469688). Old Babylonian Emesal lamentations have **mu-gu₃-di** with the typical substitution of the Standard **η eš** by the Emesal **mu** (Schretter, 1990: 223–225; Gabbay, 2014a: 116). For two examples, see CT 36, pl. 41–42 [BM 96940], o. 22 (Cohen, 1981: 104), and **Er₂ na-mu-ma-al**, 12 (Bowen, 2017: 188). In addition, spellings without **η eš** are not Old Babylonian: **gu-di** (Rudik, 2013: 481–482 [HS 1556], o. 2–4; Ur III Period); **gu₃-de₂-gu₃-de₂** (LKA 66 [VAT 10843], r. 4a, Neo-Assyrian; BLMS); **gu₃-di** (Veldhuis, 1996: 233 [UM 29-15-134], r. ii 1¹, Neo-Babylonian; DCCLT).

⁹³⁸ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133 has “NE²” However, as Theo J. H. Krispijn suggested to us, we might also have the right side of KA. That would make sense with text N_{I-A}. In any case, a chain **e₂ nar-e-ne**(NE) (“to the house of the musicians”) might also make sense with the singularities of manuscript Sb₃.

⁹³⁹ They follow Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 98–99, but we have put an N (= Nippur) for the manuscripts coming from Nippur. After, that, I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain) precise the tablet typology. Concerning Sánchez Muñoz, *forthcoming* - a, we returned to Flückiger-Hawker’s text “A” as a matter of coherence with other texts of this study as *Proverbs* 3.150 (see *supra* for our edition).

In the second line of this text, we find **e₂ nam-nar-ra** a nominal chain almost never explored in previous studies about Mesopotamian musical spaces⁹⁴⁰. This expression has been understood in previous editions of *Ur-Namma A* as a house for the singing⁹⁴¹, the music⁹⁴² or the musicians⁹⁴³ besides to a “conservatory of music”⁹⁴⁴.

However, we can arrive to a better explanation of that expression in *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188 with a deeper study of the entire excerpt where it is contained.

4.4.2.2. Lexicographical analysis of this excerpt

4.4.2.2.1. **tige₂, a-da-ab, gi-gid₂, and za-am-za-am**

The nature of those terms in this text has been controversial in the past: beyond some generic translations⁹⁴⁵, they have been understood as songs⁹⁴⁶, but also as instruments⁹⁴⁷. This last identification might be supported by an excerpt from *Cursing of Agade*⁹⁴⁸ (text closely related to *Ur-Namma A*)⁹⁴⁹. There, **tige₂, gi-gid₂, and za-am-za-am** may designate instruments due to the reference to the ^{9e5}**al-ḡar-sur₉** instrument in the previous line⁹⁵⁰.

However, **tige₂** is already used in *Ur-Namma B* for designating that text as a praise hymn for Ur-Namma and the god Enlil⁹⁵¹. In addition, other musical terms in Ur-Namma hymns are referred to songs⁹⁵², like the **er₂**, a type of lament similar to the **a-nir** and **i-**

⁹⁴⁰ For (very short) previous references to **e₂ nam-nar-ra**, see Sallaberger, 2006: 139 and Shehata, 2009: 35. In addition, see Shehata, 2009: 158–161 for the houses of the musicians, and FM 9, p. 77–79; Michalowski, 2010a: 199–207 and Ziegler, 2013: 51–52 for the learning spaces of those musicians.

⁹⁴¹ Ludwig, 1990: 53; CDLI P469688.

⁹⁴² Krispijn, 1990: 13; Kramer, 1991: 209; ETCSL 2.4.1.1; Krispijn, 2008: 177.

⁹⁴³ Alster, 1974: 104.

⁹⁴⁴ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133, 312.

⁹⁴⁵ Kramer, 1967b: 120; Kramer, 1991: 209.

⁹⁴⁶ Ludwig, 1990: 53; ETCSL 2.4.1.1; Shehata, 2009: 258; CDLI P469688.

⁹⁴⁷ Krispijn, 1990: 4; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133; Krispijn, 2008: 177.

⁹⁴⁸ *Cursing of Agade*, 36 (ETCSL 2.1.5).

⁹⁴⁹ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 94.

⁹⁵⁰ For its identification as a percussion, see Shehata, 2006 and Michalowski, 2010a: 225–228.

⁹⁵¹ *Ur-Namma B*, 72 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 199).

⁹⁵² **bal-bal-e** (“responsorial chant”) (*Ur-Namma G*, 28; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 134); **balan-di** (“reciter of **balan** lamentations”) (*Ur-Namma A*, 194; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 284); **ser₃ nam-šub** (“incantation text (to be sung)(?)”) (*Ur-Namma E-F*, 52; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 294).

lu⁹⁵³. Therefore, **tige₂**, **a-da-ab**, **gi-gid₂**, and **za-am-za-am** would designate in *Ur-Namma A* four types of praise hymns⁹⁵⁴ transformed into four types of laments⁹⁵⁵. On the one hand, this change has parallels in other texts⁹⁵⁶, and it is more logical than a substitution of four instruments for a group of laments. On the other hand, those hymns might have been accompanied by their homonym instruments: the **tige₂**, **a-da-ab**, and **za-am-za-am** percussions⁹⁵⁷, and the **gi-gid₂** pipes⁹⁵⁸.

Certainly, to identify those terms as instruments would imply to propose a non-existent word in *Ur-Namma A*, 187 for describing their sound⁹⁵⁹, or to suppose that the **er₂** laments were also accompanied by instruments. The instrumental accompaniment of those **er₂** laments seems plausible according to some lexical⁹⁶⁰ and literary⁹⁶¹ texts. However, it is partially opposed to *Ur-Namma A*, 188, and we cannot always ensure the connections between *Ur-Namma*, 187 and the said texts⁹⁶². In any case, it is clear that we deal in this line with a scenario related to the royal sphere.

4.4.2.2.2. **neš-gu₃-di and zag e₂-ḡars-e us₂**

The condition of the **neš-gu₃-di** lute⁹⁶³ is expressed in this text by the expression **zag e₂-ḡars-e us₂**, a verbal chain usually understood here as a reference to putting the **neš-**

⁹⁵³ See Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 301–361 for reference to these terms.

⁹⁵⁴ These songs are “(epic) songs” (**en₃-du**) in *Šulgi E*, 53–58 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

⁹⁵⁵ Since it is a non-human noun, **er₂** may also designate a single lament (Kramer, 1967b: 120; Krispijn, 2008: 177), but it makes sense to translate **er₂** as “laments” due to the mention of four types of praise hymns.

⁹⁵⁶ A **tige₂** hymn becomes an **a-nir** lament in *Ur Lament*, 360 (Samet, 2014: 74).

⁹⁵⁷ Shehata, 2009: 258–259.

⁹⁵⁸ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133 and Krispijn, 2008: 177 translate it as “flute” starting from the **gi-su₃** (“empty/hollow reed”) previously dismissed. See Shehata, 2009: 260 for the identification of **gi-gid₂**.

⁹⁵⁹ Krispijn, 2008: 177 “(The music of) my bass-lyre, the *adab*-drum, flute and *zamzam*-instrument”.

⁹⁶⁰ *Proto-ka₂-gal*, 370–374 (DCCLT Q000048), where we find four types of laments: **er₂ balan-ḡa₂** (“lament of the **balan** drum”), **er₂ ub₃-a** (“lament of the **ub₃** frame drum”), **er₂ s/šem₃-ma** (“lament of the **šem₃** cymbals”), and **er₂ gi-di** (“lament of the **gi-di** pipes”).

⁹⁶¹ The **balan** instrument is played for the king in *Šulgi N*, 45 (ETCSL 2.4.2.14).

⁹⁶² The **za-am-za-am** of *Proto-ka₂-gal*, 371 might have been transformed into the **er₂ ub₃-a** lament since **za-am-za-am** and **ub₃** are equated to the *lilisu* in Langdon, 1931: 128 [K. 4547], r. ii 9–10 (DCCLT). However, that text is Neo-Assyrian, so, we should be careful with the said connection.

⁹⁶³ Some authors have defined **neš-gu₃-di** as a concrete instrument (Kramer, 1967b: 120; Alster, 1974: 104; Krispijn, 1990: 13; Kramer, 1991: 209; Krispijn, 2008: 177). However, other people have translated

gu₃-di lute beside a wall (of the **e₂ nam-nar-ra**, we guess) for not using it any more⁹⁶⁴. This interpretation might be based on an analysis of **zag e₂-ḡar₈-e** as an archaic spelling of **zag e₂-ḡar₈-ra-ke₄** (**za₃.g e₂.j.ḡar₈ + ak [GEN] + e [DIR]**) in order to build a nominal chain in the directive case meaning “to/for the right side of the wall”, while **ḡeš-gu₃-di** would have an ABS. However, on the one hand, we do not have too many archaisms in Ur-Namma hymns⁹⁶⁵. On the other hand, the expression **zag e₂-ḡar₈-e us₂** is known in other Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts⁹⁶⁶. In those texts, **zag e₂-ḡar₈-e us₂** means literally “to approach (**us₂**) the right side (of the body) (**zag**, in ABS) to the wall (**e₂-ḡar₈**, with the DIR {**e**})”⁹⁶⁷. Therefore, **ḡeš-gu₃-di** would not be the unique ABS here⁹⁶⁸, and the idea of storing the **ḡeš-gu₃-di** lute would not make sense in this context.

Taking into consideration that **zag e₂-ḡar₈-e us₂** makes allusion to the inactivity of something/someone⁹⁶⁹, *Ur-Namma A*, 188 would indicate that the **ḡeš-gu₃-di** lute would be inactive. That fact makes sense with the death of the king. In fact, the **ḡeš-gu₃-di** lute is documented in praise contexts⁹⁷⁰, not in lamentations.

that term just as “(musical) instrument(s)” in general (Ludwig, 1990: 53; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133; ETCSL 2.4.1.1; CDLI P469688; Attinger, 2019d: 211). See the argumentation for our position in the commentary of the term **ḡeš-gu₃-di** in our edition of *Inanna and Enki*, I v 33 and II v 50.

⁹⁶⁴ Kramer, 1967b: 120; Ludwig, 1990: 53; Kramer, 1991: 209; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133; ETCSL 2.4.1.1. For a contrary position, see Krispijn, 1990: 13 and Krispijn, 2008: 177.

⁹⁶⁵ For archaisms in Ur-Namma hymns, see Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 22–23, 68, 143–144.

⁹⁶⁶ *Instructions of Šuruppak*, 156 (Alster, 2005: 84) and *Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta*, 373–374 (Mittermayer, 2009: 136).

⁹⁶⁷ See Alster, 1974: 104 for this grammatical analysis. Theo J. H. Krispijn (personal communication) placed the DIR {**e**} in **zag**. Nevertheless, he was unable to explain the grammatical function of **e₂-ḡar₈**.

⁹⁶⁸ The term **ḡeš-gu₃-di** cannot be in locative case since we should have **ḡeš-gu₃-di e₂ nam-nar-ra-ka-ka** (= **ḡeš.gu₃.di.d e₂.j nam.nar + ak [GEN] + ak [GEN] + a [LOC]**) or **ḡeš-gu₃-di-da e₂ nam-nar-ra** (inspired on *Iddin-Dagān A*, 204; see Attinger 2014, 25 for edition and 39, n. 154 for comments. Not can it be the transitive subject taking into consideration by the {**n**} infix in the verbal chain (**i-ni-in-us₂ = i [VP] + ni [LOC] + n [3SG.A] + us₂ [PFV] + ø [3NH.O]**) (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 178). Certainly, its non-human gender is indicated in other texts. For instance, in *Šulgi B*, 168 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02), we have **ḡeš-gu₃-di ḡeš la-ba-ra-ab-tuku-a** (= **ḡeš.gu₃.di.d (+ e [DIR]) ḡeš + ø [ABS] nu [NEG] + ba [MM] ra [ABL] + b [3SG.A] + tuku [PFV] + ø [3NH.O] + a [NMLZ] + ø [ABS]** = “a **ḡeš-gu₃-di** lute which had never been listened to”). Therefore, it cannot be an agent (with ERG {**e**}, used only with human nouns).

⁹⁶⁹ Römer, 1990: 59.

⁹⁷⁰ *Iddin-Dagān A*, 204–207 (Attinger, 2014a: 25); *Summer and Winter*, 235–236 (ETCSL 2.2.5).

4.4.2.2.3. e₂ and e₂-gal

Finally, we should have a look at **e₂** (“house”, “temple”, “room”), the term connected to **nam-nar** in **e₂ nam-nar-ra**. Beyond some secondary meanings⁹⁷¹, **e₂** seems to be highly connected in Ur-Namma hymns with the palace (**e₂-gal**). In that space Ur-Namma rules⁹⁷², makes offerings (**neš tag**)⁹⁷³ or sleeps (**nu₂**)⁹⁷⁴ as in his house. In fact, **e₂** is a variation of **e₂-gal** in an excerpt of *Ur-Namma A*⁹⁷⁵. In this sense, we should privilege these palatial connotations of **e₂** in our analysis of *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188, albeit mentions of **e₂** as “temple” are also common in *Ur-Namma A*⁹⁷⁶. To see the **e₂ nam-nar-ra** as a palace room makes sense with other expressions referred in that text to possible palace rooms⁹⁷⁷: **e₂ sumur-ra** (“furious room”) and **e₂ zu₂-ra-ah-a** (“tooth-gnashing room”)⁹⁷⁸.

4.4.2.3. Towards a new definition of e₂ nam-nar-ra

The terms previously studied are all connected in some way to the palatial sphere, and the identification of **e₂ nam-nar-ra** as a palace room seems highly probable in light of the connotations of the term **e₂** in *Ur-Namma A*. In this sense, the translation of **e₂ nam-nar-ra** as “house of music”⁹⁷⁹ is not suitable since it supposes an independent building when we do not have evidence for one in this case.

The translation “house of singing”⁹⁸⁰, in addition to that, does not keep in mind that the text refers to songs (the **tige₂**, **a-da-ab**, **gi-gid₂**, and **za-am-za-am** hymns), but also some instruments (the **neš-gu₃-di** lute). Therefore, the translation “singing” here is less

⁹⁷¹ *Ur-Namma A*, 88 mentions the **e₂-mar-ru₁₀**, “arrow quiver” (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 117).

⁹⁷² *Ur-Namma A*, 224 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 140).

⁹⁷³ *Ur-Namma A*, 91, 96, 101, 105, 109, 113, 119, 128 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 117–128).

⁹⁷⁴ *Ur-Namma A*, 42, 48 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 108, 112).

⁹⁷⁵ *Ur-Namma A*, 149–150 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 127).

⁹⁷⁶ *Ur-Namma A*, 199, 201–202, 212 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 135–136, 138). Surprisingly, we find in *Ur-Namma A* no reference to the Ekišnuḡal, a widely mentioned temple in other hymns for King Ur-Namma. See Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 312–313 and 368 for reference.

⁹⁷⁷ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 166.

⁹⁷⁸ *Ur-Namma A*, 40–41 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 108).

⁹⁷⁹ Krispijn, 1990: 13; Kramer, 1991: 209; ETCSL 2.4.1.1; Krispijn, 2008: 177.

⁹⁸⁰ Ludwig, 1990: 53; CDLI P469688.

suitable than “music” for **nam-nar**. The similar translation “in the house of the singers”⁹⁸¹ has two problems in our opinion. On the one hand, it referred just to the **nar** (translated there as “singers”) when, for instance, the **gi-gid₂** pipes has their own player (the **lu₂-gi-gid₂-da**, literally “person (of) the **gi-gid₂**”)⁹⁸², therefore, we are dealing with more types of musicians besides the **nar** in this text. On the other hand, it is not grammatically well-written since we should have here **e₂ nar-e-ne-ka**, not **e₂ nam-nar-ra-ka**.

In this sense, we would translate **e₂ nam-nar-ra** as “(palace) music room” for making explicit the condition of **e₂** in this text and the presence of the instruments, musicians and songs involved in our excerpt. However, what would be its function? Flückiger-Hawker translated **e₂ nam-nar-ra** as “conservatory of music”⁹⁸³. Moreover, we can deduce from her translation a secondary function of said room as a storehouse for instruments⁹⁸⁴. In fact, she established a parallel between our excerpt and *Enki and the World Order*⁹⁸⁵.

On the one hand, it is possible that the **e₂ nam-nar-ra** acted as a storehouse for musical instruments. However, the expression **e₂-ba ge₄** (literally “to return to their house”) from that excerpt of *Enki and the World Order* mentioned by Esther Flückiger-Hawker is actually a literary way to say “to make inactive/silent”⁹⁸⁶ something (in this case, the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** drums). On the other hand, most of the music teaching in Mesopotamia had to happen in the private sphere⁹⁸⁷. Moreover, **e₂/ki umun₂** (“workshop”) might have already referred to a sort of conservatory, a space where students could receive a musical education⁹⁸⁸. In any case, even if this were a palatial school of music, it should have been also devoted to musical performances at some point, as in the case of the *bīt tegêtim* (“house of the *tigû* female players”) of Mari⁹⁸⁹.

⁹⁸¹ Alster, 1974: 104.

⁹⁸² *Proverbs* 2.54, 3 (Attinger, 2018: 10).

⁹⁸³ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133.

⁹⁸⁴ Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 178–179.

⁹⁸⁵ *Enki and the World Order*, 448 (ETCSL 1.1.3).

⁹⁸⁶ Attinger, 2019d: 63, with references to *Ur Lament*, 4, 483–485 (ETCSL 2.2.3). Civil, 2011: 255 n. 49 mentions also *Enki and the World Order*, 50 (ETCSL 1.1.3) besides the unclear *Ur-Namma C*, 89 (Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 216). Furthermore, said publication cites the possible case of *Copper and Silver*, A 33 due to a chain of the type **ama ge₄**. However, we have not found that excerpt in the main current edition of *Copper and Silver* (ETCSL 5.3.6).

⁹⁸⁷ FM 9, p. 16; Shehata, 2009: 112–114.

⁹⁸⁸ Michalowski, 2010a: 201–202 for **e₂/ki umun₂**, and FM 9, p. 78 for the Akkadian *bīt mummim*.

⁹⁸⁹ See FM 9, p. 79; Shehata, 2009: 114 for more about this building.

If it is not a palatial music school nor a storehouse for musical instruments, could the **e2 nam-nar-ra** be, perhaps, a space for musical performances like our concert halls? It is complicated to talk about such spaces in Mesopotamia. Certainly, our textual⁹⁹⁰ and archaeological⁹⁹¹ evidence usually shows music only as a sort of accessory for other non-musical events in the daily life of Mesopotamia. However, *Ur-Namma A*, 188 says that someone was inactive with the **ḡeš-gu3-di** lute in the **e2 nam-nar-ra**. In this sense, the said space had to be musically active at some point for the use of that **ḡeš-gu3-di** or other instruments, like those accompanying the **tige2**, **a-da-ab**, **gi-gid2** and **za-am-za-am** hymns from *Ur-Namma A*, 187. Therefore, the **e2 nam-nar-ra** could be the home for some musical performances in the palace⁹⁹².

That condition of the **e2 nam-nar-ra** might be supported with our references to the **e2 tige2** (“room of the **tige2** drum”). Certainly, the praises for the king (perhaps accompanied by the **tige2** drum) should never stop in that **e2 tige2**⁹⁹³. Other excerpts suggest, in addition, the performance of pure **ser3** songs (**ser3 ku3**) by the **a-u3-a** singer in that place⁹⁹⁴. Nevertheless, we believe that the **e2 nam-nar-ra** would involve more instruments and songs than the **e2 tige2**. In addition, the content of its performances would be more related to the palace, not to the temple as in the case of the **e2 tige2**.

Therefore, according to our scarce evidence, the **e2 nam-nar-ra** would designate a space destined as the locus of some musical performances in palatial daily life. In this sense, its best translation, in our opinion, would be “(palace) music room”.

⁹⁹⁰ For instance, the **a-da-ab** drum plays during a **ḡešbun** banquet, while the **šems** cymbals and the **kuš-a2-la2** drum play in the **unu2** dining hall (*Temple Hymns*, 107; ETCSL 4.80.1).

⁹⁹¹ For instance, the Old Babylonian clay plaque BM 91906 (Rašīd, 1984: fig. 60) shows a kettledrum played during a wrestling match.

⁹⁹² Theo J. H. Krispijn (personal communication) speculated that musicians might change the tuning of their instruments in this space. That might make sense since we have three tunable instruments here: the **gi-gid2**, the **ḡeš-gu3-di**, and perhaps the **tige2** (see *infra* for comments). In any case, we would not consider that as the unique function of the **e2 nam-nar-ra**.

⁹⁹³ *Šulgi E*, 255–257 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05; to be completed with Zólyomi, 2003: 98).

⁹⁹⁴ *Sumer and Ur Lament*, 436–437. We follow the edition of *Kollationen*, p. 60 since it makes more sense than Michalowski, 1989: 180 according to the content of our manuscripts for that text. We shall prove in Sánchez Muñoz, *forthcoming* - a, where we shall present a new edition of that text.

4.4.3. Šulgi and **nam-nar**

4.4.3.1. Introduction: a king devoted to music

The Neo-Sumerian king defines himself as the “supervisor (**nu-banda₃**) of music (**nam-nar**)”⁹⁹⁵ in the following excerpt of the hymn *Šulgi E*:

Text 32. *Šulgi E*⁹⁹⁶

155 **šul-gi-me nar gal nu-banda₃ nam-n[ar-ra ...] / nar ki-nu₂ x [...]**

N _{I-I}	r. i 1'	[šul] ⁹⁹⁷ -[]
N _{U-J}	r. 5–6'	[] x nu-banda₃ nam-n[ar-ra ... / na]r ki -n[uz]
X _B	r. i 7'	š[ul -g]i-me nar gal nu-banda₃ nam'-[] / 'x' nar 'ki'²-nu₂ x

155 I am Šulgi, the chief musician⁹⁹⁸, the supervisor [of] mus[ic ...]
The **nar** [of] the **ki-nu₂** bedroom [...]

*Sigla*⁹⁹⁹

N _{I-I}	Ni 3281 + BPOA 9 140 [Ni 3450] + Ni 3487 + 3497 (copy of BPOA 9 140; photo on CDLI P467839; collated the 19/08/2019)
N _{U-J}	ISCT 1 117 [Ist. Ni 9619] (publication copy)
X _B	TCL 15 14 [AO 5380] (publication copy and photo on CDLI P345358)

In our opinion, there is nothing strange in that statement. Certainly, the same king says in another hymn that he gave (**šum₂**) his entirety (**gu₂**, literally “neck”) to music, that is, he devoted himself to that art. This is the said excerpt:

⁹⁹⁵ Previous translations: Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“Leiter der Musiker”) and ETCSL 2.4.2.05 (“superintendent of the art of music”). We prefer ETCSL translation since Krispijn’s translation would imply in the text **nu-banda₃ nar-e-ne-ka** (“supervisor of the musicians”).

⁹⁹⁶ Our own score edition based on the consultation of the copies/photos of the tablets (some of them collated) indicated below.

⁹⁹⁷ Just two straight wedges according to our collation.

⁹⁹⁸ Krispijn, 1990: 2 (“Großmusiker”); ETCSL 2.4.2.05 (“great musician”); Shehata, 2009: 24 (“großen Musiker”). However, **nu-banda₃ nam-nar-ra** might be an epithet of **nar gal** as chief musician.

⁹⁹⁹ They follow Klein, 2005: 149, but we have put an N (= Nippur) or X (= Uncertain) according to the provenance of the manuscripts. Manuscripts from Nippur have an additional I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain) according to their tablet typology.

154 **šul-gi lugal urim^{ki}-ma-me-en**

N _{I-A}	o. iii 46'	šul -gi []	-ma-[]
N _{I-E}	r. ii 5	^d šul ^ˊ -gi	lugal urim ^{ki}	-ma - ^ˊ me ^ˊ -en	
N _{I-t}	o. 13	^ˊ šul ^ˊ -g[i]-m[e]- ^ˊ en	lugal ^ˊ urim ^{ki}	- ^ˊ me ^ˊ -en	
N _{III-L}	r. 16	šul -gi ¹⁰⁰¹	lugal ur[im ^{ki}]	
N _{U-aa}	r. 5	[urim ^{ki}]	-ma-[]
U _{RM}	o. 32	^d šul -gi ^ˊ	lugal ^ˊ urim ^{ki}	-ma -me -en	
X _{II}	r. ii 6	šul -gi	lugal urim ^{ki}	-ma -me -en	

155 **u₃ nam-nar-ra gu₂-ḡu₁₀ ḡa-ba¹⁰⁰²-šum₂¹⁰⁰³**

N _{I-A}	o. iii 47'	u ₃ nam -nar -ra	gu ₂ - ^ˊ ḡu ₁₀ ^ˊ []		
N _{I-E}	r. ii 6	^ˊ u ₃ ^ˊ []-nar -e	gu ₂ -ḡu ₁₀ ḡa -ba	- ^ˊ šum ₂ ^ˊ	
N _{I-t}	o. 14	[]	nam- ^ˊ nar ^ˊ -ra	gu ₂ -ḡu ₁₀ ^ˊ ḡa ^ˊ -ba	- ^ˊ šum ₂ ^ˊ
N _{III-L}	r. 17	u ₃ nam -nar -ra []			
N _{U-aa}	r. 6	[]	gu ₂ -ḡu ₁₀ ḡ[a-]	
N _{U-kk}	r. 1'	[]	- ^ˊ šum ₂ ^ˊ		
U _{RM}	r. 1	^ˊ u ₃ ^ˊ nam -nar -a	^ˊ gu ₂ ^ˊ -ḡu ₁₀ ḡa -ba ¹⁰⁰⁴	-šum ₂		
X _{II}	r. ii 7	u ₃ nam- ^ˊ nar ^ˊ -e	gu ₂ - ^ˊ ḡu ₁₀ ^ˊ ḡa - ^ˊ ba ^ˊ	-šum ₂		

156 **niḡ₂-na-me-ḡa₂ la-ba-da-gi₁₆-e**

N _{I-A}	o. iii 48'	[]- ^ˊ na -me ^ˊ -bi []- ^ˊ an ¹⁰⁰⁵ -[]
N _{I-E}	r. ii 7	[]- ^ˊ me ^ˊ -ba	^ˊ la ^ˊ -ba-da-an	- ^ˊ gi ₁₆ -en ^ˊ
N _{I-t}	o. 15	[]-na -me -ḡa ₂ la- ^ˊ ba	-da ^ˊ	- ^ˊ gi ₁₆ - ^ˊ e ^ˊ
N _{III-L}	r. 18	niḡ ₂ -na -me -ḡa ₂ l[a ^ˊ -]		
N _{U-aa}	r. 7	[]-x-da	- ^ˊ gi ₁₆ ^ˊ -[]
N _{U-kk}	r. 2'	[]- ^ˊ x ^ˊ	-en	
U _{RM}	r. 2	niḡ ₂ -na -me -bi	la -ba-an-da	- ^ˊ gi ₁₆ ^ˊ -e	
X _{II}	r. ii 8	niḡ ₂ - ^ˊ na-me ^ˊ -ba	^ˊ la -ba-da-an ^ˊ	-ḡa -e	

¹⁰⁰⁰ Our own score edition following the variants given in Castellino, 1976: 46, and Peterson, 2919a: 212–213 and having consulted the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

¹⁰⁰¹ According to Castellino, 1972: 46, only manuscripts N_{I-A} and N_{I-t} did not have a ^d before **šulgi**. However, according to our inspection of its handwritten copy, manuscript N_{III-L} also lacks that sign.

¹⁰⁰² Krispijn, 1990: 1 has “**ḡa.ma.sum**” in the composite line. However, that variant is contained only in manuscript U_{RM}, and we need a prefix for explaining the **nam-nar-a** of that sentence. It is true that **ḡa-ma-šum₂** might be explained as **ḡa** [MOD] + **mu** [VNT] + **ba** [3NH.IO] + ? [1SG.A] + **šum₂** [PFV] + **ø** [3NH.O]. However, for that we would expect something like **ḡa-am-ma-šum₂** as a parallel with the **ḡe₂-em-ma-ab-šum₂-mu** of *Gilgameš and the Bull of An*, D 28 (ETCSL 1.8.1.2).

¹⁰⁰³ Jaques, 2006: 14 calls attention to the connection between this excerpt and *Išmē-Dagān Z*, Text D (= Ludwig, 1990: 22) TRS 27 [AO 5392], o. 11 (Cavigneaux, 1996: 40).

¹⁰⁰⁴ Castellino, 1972: 46 read “ma”, but it might be also **ba**. The sign MA of the previous line is a bit different.

¹⁰⁰⁵ Castellino, 1972: 46 saw “-da-an-” just in manuscript N_{I-E}. However, manuscript N_{I-A} also suggests the sign AN according to CDLI photo. The copy also seems to contain a part of the sign DA.

154 I am Šulgi, the king of Ur,
 155 and I have devoted myself to music¹⁰⁰⁶.
 156 For me, nothing was difficult about it.

*Sigla*¹⁰⁰⁷

N_{I-A} STVC 52 [CBS 7076] + CBS 8029 + Castellino, 1972: 27 [CBS 13992] + N 2804 + 2805 + 2806 + 2807 + 2808 + 2809 + 2810 + 2811 + 2812 + 2813 + 2814 + 2815 + 2816 (photo on CDLI P262125)¹⁰⁰⁸
 N_{I-E} Castellino, 1972: fig. 3 [N 1741] (photo on CDLI P259086; collated the 21/08/2019)
 N_{I-t} Castellino, 1972: pl. 19 [OIM A30219] (photo on CDLI P356651)
 N_{III-L} SLTN 73 [Ist. Ni 4028] (copy on CDLI P345204)
 N_{U-aa} ISET 2 60 [Ist. Ni 4211] (reference on CDLI P343707)
 N_{U-kk} ISET 2 93 [Ist. Ni 4078] (reference on CDLI P343752)
 U_{RM} UET 6/1 81 [U. 16848] (photo on CDLI P346166; collated the 01/08/2019)
 X_{II} Volk, *forthcoming* [MS 3343] (photo on CDLI P252284)

As a consequence of that devotion to music, musical terminology in Šulgi hymns is especially complex, including the term **nam-nar** as we shall see here.

4.4.3.2. *Šulgi B*, 157: **nam-nar** as musical sound

4.4.3.2.1. Introduction

The hymn *Šulgi B* is one of the most important texts for the study of Old Babylonian musical practice due to the long enumeration of musical terms in its lines 154–174. They were studied in depth by Theo J. H. Krispijn some decades ago¹⁰⁰⁹. However, his new reflections¹⁰¹⁰ and those coming from other authors¹⁰¹¹ show how far we still are from a

¹⁰⁰⁶ Castellino, 1972: 47 (“music”); Edzard, 1976: 172 (“der Musik”); Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“die Musik”); Jaques, 2006: 14 n. 38 (“l’art musical”); ETCSL 2.4.2.02 (“the art of music”); Charpin, 2006: 59 (“la musique”); Woods, 2008: 281 (“music”); Civil, 2013: 39 (“music”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“musique”); Peterson, 2019a: 213 (“the art of the musician”).

¹⁰⁰⁷ They follow Castellino, 1972: 27–29, but we have put an N (= Nippur), Ur (= Ur) or X (= Uncertain) according to the provenance of the manuscripts they are designing. Manuscripts from Nippur have an I (= Type I), III (= Type III) or U (= Uncertain) according to their tablet typology.

¹⁰⁰⁸ This tablet was not available for collation during 19–23/08/2019 since it belonged to the material displayed in the galleries of the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology.

¹⁰⁰⁹ Krispijn, 1990.

¹⁰¹⁰ Krispijn, 2008: 176–178; Krispijn, 2010b: 144–148, and Krispijn, 2011.

¹⁰¹¹ Shehata, 2009: 238–239 (about **za3-mi2** in *Šulgi B*, 161), 251–257 (about **tige**₂ and **a-da-ab** in *Šulgi B*, 157), 301 (about **gi-di** in *Šulgi B*, 172); Michalowski, 2010a: 123 n. 10 (about **ur-za-ba-bi2-tum**

definitive understanding of these terms. Therefore, new studies are necessary in order to arrive at a proper definition of them. In this section, we focus our attention on line 157:

Text 34. *Šulgi B*¹⁰¹²

157 **tige₂**¹⁰¹³ **a-da-ab** nam-nar šu du₇-a buru₃ daḡal-bi mu-zu

N _{I-E}	r. ii 8–9	[] BALAD ^{*1014}	a-da ¹ -ab	[n]am-nar ¹ šu du ₇ -a ¹ / buru ₃ daḡal-bi mu ¹ -zu ¹
N _{I-G}	r. 1	tige₂ ^{2,1}	[] mu ¹ -zu ¹
N _{I-t}	o. 16	[] LUL ¹]-nar šu du ₇ -a []
N _{III-L}	r. 19	tige₂	a-da- []
N _{U-q}	o. ii 2	tige₂	a-da- []
N _{U-aa}	r. 8	[] nam -nar šu d[u ₇]
N _{U-kk}	r. 3'	[daḡ]al-bi mu ¹ -zu ¹]
U _{RM}	r. 3	tige₂	a-da -ab nam -nar šu du ₇ -a buru ₃ daḡal-bi mu ^{1,1015} -zu ¹	
X _{II}	r. ii 9	tige₂ ^{2,1}	a-da -ab n[am] šu du ₇ -a buru ₃ daḡal-bi mu-un -zu ¹	

157 I know the depth and width of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** drums, (instruments of) perfect music.

*Sigla*¹⁰¹⁶

N _{I-E}	Castellino, 1972: fig. 3 [N 1741] (photo on CDLI P259086; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{I-G}	Castellino, 1972: fig. 5 [UM 29-16-408 + 29-16-214G] (photo on CDLI P256906; collated the 19/08/2019)
N _{I-t}	Castellino, 1972: pl. 19 [A 30219] (photo on CDLI P356651)
N _{III-L}	SLTN 73 [Ist. Ni 4028] (copy on CDLI P345204)
N _{U-q}	Castellino, 1972: pl. 17 [3N-T300 = OIM A30203] (publication photo)
N _{U-aa}	ISET 2 60 [Ist. Ni 4211] (publication copy)
N _{U-kk}	ISET 2 93 [Ist. Ni 4078] (publication copy)
U _{RM}	UET 6/1 81 [U. 16848] (photo on CDLI P346166; collated the 01/08/2019)
X _{II}	Volk, <i>forthcoming</i> [MS 3343] (photo on CDLI P252284)

in *Šulgi B*, 165); Michalowski, 2010b: 218–225, 228–229 (about **za₃-mi₂**); Shehata, 2014: 106–109 (about **tige₂**).

¹⁰¹² Our own score edition taking in account the variants given by Castellino, 1972: 47 and Peterson, 2019a: 213, but mainly coming from our consultation of the copies/photos of the tablet indicated below.

¹⁰¹³ Most of the editions have **tige**(BALAD.LUL) (Castellino, 1972: 46; Krispijn, 1990: 1; ETCSL 2.4.2.02; Shehata, 2009: 252; Michalowski, 2010a: 206). This option is only suggested by the manuscript N_{I-t}. The rest of the manuscripts seem to have the **tige₂**(LUL.BALAD) of Ludwig, 1990: 185.

¹⁰¹⁴ It is not a canonical shape of BALAD, nor does it seem to be another sign. In fact, it would be strange to have here a term for a different instrument than the **tige₂**. Certainly, **a-da-ab** never appears immediately mentioned with any other instrument (see ePSD2 for evidence). In any case, we would maintain BALAD since the shape of this sign is similar to the wrongly written sign BALAD of UET 6/1 140 [U. 16881], r. 19, an Old Babylonian manuscript of **Uru am₃-ma-ir-ra-bi** (Peterson, 2019c: 405).

¹⁰¹⁵ Castellino, 1972: 47 read “gál” and Peterson, 2019a: 213 “mu-ḡ”. In our collation, we found two crossed wedges and a *Winkelhaken*. It might be an incorrect MU; IG (= **gal₂**) does not make sense here.

¹⁰¹⁶ They follow Castellino, 1972: 27–29, but we have put an N (= Nippur), Ur (= Ur) or X (= Uncertain) according to the provenance of the manuscripts they are designing. Manuscripts from Nippur have an I (= Type I), III (= Type III) or U (= Uncertain) according to their tablet typology.

In this excerpt, the term **nam-nar** (translated in different ways in the past¹⁰¹⁷) is connected to two musical terms: **tige₂** and **a-da-ab**. Since the first edition of this text¹⁰¹⁸, those words haven't normally been identified, with two praise¹⁰¹⁹ (vocal) compositions¹⁰²⁰, music or songs¹⁰²¹. Other excerpts of the hymns for Šulgi¹⁰²² make mention of them as (vocal) compositions. Nevertheless, the nature of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** as hymns is not so evident, at least in these two cases:

- In *Šulgi C*¹⁰²³, the king claims to know the **ad ša₄** technique of the **tige₂**, **a-da-ab**, and **ma-al-ga-tum**. These terms have been traditionally defined as hymns¹⁰²⁴ starting from the idea that **ad ša₄** was a singing technique¹⁰²⁵. However, we have already seen that several instruments were able to produce the same **ad ša₄** technique¹⁰²⁶. Certainly, **ad** referred to a “soft sound” by opposition to the **šeg₁₁** (“loud sound”)¹⁰²⁷. Therefore, **tige₂**, **a-da-ab**, and **ma-al-ga-tum** might designate here a group of instruments.

¹⁰¹⁷ Castellino, 1972: 47 (“musical training”); Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“Musik”); Ludwig, 1990: 185 (“Gesangeskunst”); ETCSL 2.4.2.02 (“art of music”); Charpin, 2006: 56 (“musique”); Shehata, 2009: 252 (“Musikkunst”); Michalowski, 2010a: 206 (“the practice of music”); Wolfe, 2015: 228 (“music”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“musique”); Peterson, 2019a: 213 (“the musician’s craft(?)”).

¹⁰¹⁸ Castellino, 1972: 47 (“the tigi and adab compositions”).

¹⁰¹⁹ See Shehata, 2009: 251–257 for the most complete current study of those compositions.

¹⁰²⁰ Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“Tigi- und Adab-Kompositionen”); Ludwig, 1990: 185 (“t i g i und a - d a - a b”); Michalowski, 2010a: 206 (“the tigi and adab instruments/songs”) (he states in n. 18 their meaning as songs); Wolfe, 2015: 97 (“the tigi and adab (compositions)”).

¹⁰²¹ Shehata, 2009: 252 (“Tigi - und Adab-Lieder”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“(les chants accompagnés) de l’instrument-tigi et les chants-adab”); Peterson, 2019a: 213 (“tigi and adab songs (or instruments?)”).

¹⁰²² In *Šulgi B*, 272 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02) and 278 (see our edition *infra*) they are **en₃-du** (“(epic) songs”) and **ser₃ gid₂-da** (“long **ser₃** song”). *Šulgi E*, 14–22 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05) describes their content, and they are again classified in its line 53 as **en₃-du**. *Šulgi G* (ETCSL 2.4.2.07) is an **a-da-ab** hymn to Enlil for Šulgi according to its colophon (line 70), and the text Peterson, 2015a: 46–47 [N 2821a] is an **a-da-ab** hymn of Nergal for King Šulgi.

¹⁰²³ *Šulgi C*, B 76 (ETCSL 2.4.2.03).

¹⁰²⁴ ETCSL 2.4.2.03 (“I can perform *tigi*, *adab* and great *malgatum* compositions”); Shehata, 2009: 257 (“Tigi, Adab und die groß(artig)en Malgatum-Lieder, ihre ad-ša₄-Technik kenne ich”); Wolfe, 2015: 231 (“I know the sound of the tigi and adab in great (matters of) advice”).

¹⁰²⁵ Shehata, 2009: 231–232, 296.

¹⁰²⁶ *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 63–67 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94).

¹⁰²⁷ Krispijn, 1990: 15; Rendu Loisel, 2011: 205 n. 862.

- In another text, *Šulgi E*, 34¹⁰²⁸, the king claims to know the place (**ki**) of the **zi-zi** (possible equivalent of our *crescendi* here, literally “rising”) and the **šu2-šu2** (literally “sinking down”, possible equivalent of our *diminuendi* in this particular context) of a **tige2** and a **za-am-za-am**. Dahlia Shehata identified them with hymns due to a supposed connection of **zi-zi** and **šu2-šu2** with singing¹⁰²⁹. However, they also referred to the ^{neš}**šu-kar2** lute¹⁰³⁰. Moreover, when **šu2-šu2** referred to a hymn, it is usually accompanied by **ḡa2-ḡa2** (literally “placing”) not **zi-zi**¹⁰³¹. In this sense, **tige2** and **za-am-za-am** might be two instruments¹⁰³².

The exact identity of **tige2** and **a-da-ab** is relevant for the correct understanding of our term **nam-nar** in this excerpt. Since **tige2** and **a-da-ab** did not always refer to songs in the *corpus* of hymns for *Šulgi* as we have already noted, we would propose their identification in *Šulgi B*, 157 as two instruments. That new identification fits better with the musical terms mentioned in *Šulgi B*, 158–174, where we normally find instruments with their playing techniques, but not compositions. In addition, that identification is also very relevant for the definition of **nam-nar** as “music”.

In order to arrive at the aforementioned new identification of **tige2** and **a-da-ab** in this excerpt, we propose an analysis of some of the other terms mentioned in *Šulgi B*, 157: **buru3**, **daḡal** and the expression **šu du7-a**.

¹⁰²⁸ *Šulgi E*, 34 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

¹⁰²⁹ Shehata, 2009: 256 and 352. Theo J. H. Krispijn (personal communication) defined **tige2** and **za-am-za-am** as “compositions, although originally referring to musical instruments”. For that definition, he started from a supposed connection of the term **ki** of *Šulgi E*, 34 with **ki-ru-gu2**. This term, which is well-known in the Sumerian hymns, would mean originally “place where one (re)tunes (the instrument)” according to Krispijn. However, that definition does not fit with **ru** (form derived from **ri** “to impose”) and **gu2** (“pulse” (?)), and there are other rubrics with **ki** (Shehata, 2009: 348–351).

¹⁰³⁰ *Šulgi B*, 160 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

¹⁰³¹ Shehata, 2009: 352–354.

¹⁰³² ETCSL 2.4.2.05 (“about how I know exactly at what point to raise and lower the *tigi* and *zamzam* instruments”); Foxvog, 2016b: 135 (“About how I always knew the places for the raising and lowering of the *tigi* and *zamzam* instruments”). Ludwig, 1990: 37 was impartial (“daß ich weiß, und welcher Stelle (die Stimmung) von *t i g i* und *z a - a m - z a - a m* zu erhöhen und zu erniedrigen war”).

4.4.3.2.2. Approach to some terms in this excerpt

4.4.3.2.2.1. **buru₃**

Theo J. H. Krispijn¹⁰³³ said that “**buru₃.daġal**” was mathematical and arithmetic nature, and it was referred to the measuring of land surfaces in other Sumerian literary texts¹⁰³⁴. However, he forgot that **buru₃** and **daġal** are better documented as independent terms, and, above all, they have a more extensive meaning beyond the mathematical.

Concerning **buru₃** (“(to be) deep”, “to perforate”)¹⁰³⁵, it is not documented in other hymns for Šulgi. However, there are many allusions to this term in other contemporary literary texts. As a verb, **buru₃** describes an action mostly applied to physical realities¹⁰³⁶: the entry of a thief into a house for stealing¹⁰³⁷, the holes of several materials¹⁰³⁸, or the action of plant roots growing into the ground¹⁰³⁹. As a noun, it designates the hiding places of enemies or deep sites¹⁰⁴⁰ like the Engur. In that place, Enki slept far from the protests of the deities against the obligation of working for survival¹⁰⁴¹.

In light of this information, **buru₃** might refer in our excerpt to the depth of an object, something which fits better with **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** as musical instruments. The **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** hymns have a “depth” since they have a certain quantity of lines of text. However, this “extension” is already expressed in Sumerian by the expression **mu šid-bi** (“total of lines”, literally, “its counting (**šid**) of lines (**mu**) (gives a total of)...”)

¹⁰³³ Krispijn, 1990: 4.

¹⁰³⁴ *Utu Incantation*, 19–20 (Castellino, 1969: 9); *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 360 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

¹⁰³⁵ In *Šulgi B*, 157: Castellino, 1972: 47 (“depth”); Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“Tiefe”); Ludwig, 1990: 185 (“Tiefe”); Geller, 2003: 109 (“depth”); Charpin, 2006: 59 (“profondeur”); Shehata, 2009: 252 (“Tiefe”); Michalowski, 2010a: 206 (“depth”); Wolfe 2015: 46 (“depth”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“profondeur”).

¹⁰³⁶ In *Asalluḫi A*, 16–17 (ETCSL 4.01.1) and *Nuska A*, D 1 (ETCSL 4.01.1), they are referred to the penetration of the mind of a person.

¹⁰³⁷ *Diatribes C*, 12 (ETCSL 5.4.12); *Instructions of Šuruppak*, 29, 214 (ETCSL 5.6.1); *Proverbs* 13.8 (ETCSL 6.1.13).

¹⁰³⁸ Wood (*Flood Story*, D 7; ETCSL 1.7.4); earth (*Hoe and Plough*, 52; Mittermayer, 2019: 307.).

¹⁰³⁹ *Heron and Turtle*, 17 (Peterson, 2007: 297).

¹⁰⁴⁰ *Gilgameš and Aga*, 7, 13, 22 (ETCSL 1.8.1.1); *Inanna and Ebiḫ*, 86 (ETCSL 1.3.2); *Ibbī-Suen B*, A 29 (ETCSL 2.4.5.2); *Šu-Suen to Šarrum-bāni*, 17 (Michalowski, 2011: 409).

¹⁰⁴¹ *Enki and Ninmah*, a 13–14 (Ceccarelli, 2016: 98).

4.4.3.2.2.2. **daṅal**

Unlike **buru₃**, **daṅal** (“(to be) broad/wide/large”)¹⁰⁴² is indeed documented several times in the *corpus* of hymns for Šulgi. In those texts, **daṅal** is used once as an expression for the enemies dispersed by the king¹⁰⁴³. However, it usually describes the width of the human ears (in reference to the wisdom)¹⁰⁴⁴ and other objects¹⁰⁴⁵. In this sense, **daṅal** might refer in *Šulgi B*, 157 to the breadth of two objects. That fits better with **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** as instruments. Certainly, if we had to think of the “breadth” of two hymns, we can evoke their “metrical structure”, a still very little studied aspect of Sumerian poems¹⁰⁴⁶.

4.4.3.2.2.3. **šu du₇-a**

The presence of the expression **šu du₇-a** (“(to be) perfect”)¹⁰⁴⁷ together with **nam-nar** in *Šulgi B*, 157 recalls to us the excerpt of the *Gudea Cylinders* (as one of the many parallels between Gudea’s and Šulgi’s texts¹⁰⁴⁸) noted in our Chapter 1. There, that expression described the musical action of a stringed instrument (the **balan**) and two percussion instruments (the **se-em** cymbals and the **a₂-la₂** giant drum). As we shall see later, **balan** and **tige₂** are etymologically connected. Therefore, despite the long chronological distance between the *Gudea Cylinders* and *Šulgi B*, this excerpt is useful for our identification of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** in *Šulgi B*, 157 as two musical instruments.

¹⁰⁴² In *Šulgi B*, 157: Castellino, 1972: 47 (“width”); Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“Breite”); Ludwig, 1990: 185 (“Weite”); Geller, 2003: 109 (“breadth”); Charpin, 2006: 59 (“largeur”); Shehata, 2009: 252 (“Weite”); Michalowski, 2010a: 206 (“breadth”); Wolfe 2015: 46 (“breadth”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“largeur”).

¹⁰⁴³ *Šulgi D*, 217, 333 (ETCSL 2.4.2.04).

¹⁰⁴⁴ *Šulgi B*, 18–19 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02), *Šulgi C*, A 115, B 95 (ETCSL 2.4.2.03), *Šulgi D*, 15, 37, 62 (ETCSL 2.4.2.04), *Šulgi R*, 5 (ETCSL 2.4.2.18), and *Šulgi T*, 14, 22 (ETCSL 2.4.2.20).

¹⁰⁴⁵ Tree branches (*Šulgi D*, 224, 396, ETCSL 2.4.2.04; *Šulgi T*, 2, ETCSL 2.4.2.20); tiaras (*Šulgi D*, 295, ETCSL 2.4.2.04; *Šulgi X*, 156, Attinger, 2019f: 13); boats (*Šulgi R*, 52, ETCSL 2.4.2.18), temples (*Šulgi G*, 21, ETCSL 2.4.2.07), and the sunbeams (*Šulgi A*, 47, Delnero, 1886 with Vacín, 2011: 272).

¹⁰⁴⁶ See Izre’el, 2001: 70 n. 20 for a *status quaestionis* on that topic.

¹⁰⁴⁷ Previous translations in *Šulgi B*, 157: Castellino, 1972: 47 (“the consummate”); Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“vollkommene”); Ludwig, 1990: 185 (“in Vollendung”); ETCSL 2.4.2.02 (“the perfection”); Geller, 2003: 109 (“to perfection”); Charpin, 2006: 59 (“perfection”); Shehata, 2009: 252 (“vollendete”); Michalowski, 2010a: 206 (“which are perfect”); Wolfe, 2015: 97 (“perfect”); Ziegler, 2017: 39 (“perfection”).

¹⁰⁴⁸ Klein, 1989: 292–294. We have not found this parallel in said publication.

4.4.3.2.2.4. Conclusions

The use of the terms **buru₃** and **daḡal** in *Šulgi B*, 157 is essential for the identification of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** as two instruments. Certainly, these two terms mainly referred to physical things, and not abstract concepts like the lines or the metrical structure of two hymns. The expression **šu du₇-a** here is also highly relevant due to the parallel with the aforementioned *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20–22 where it referred to some instruments and contained that same expression. We believe, therefore, that **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** were referred in *Šulgi B*, 157 to two instruments, and not two compositions.

4.4.3.2.3. **tige₂** as musical instrument in *Šulgi B*, 157

4.4.3.2.3.1. Introduction

What type of instruments exactly would the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** be? They have sometimes been identified with melodic instruments¹⁰⁴⁹. That implies their *quasi*-automatic identification with stringed instruments. Certainly, we have not found pitched percussions (like xylophones) in Mesopotamia yet, and the **gi-di** (an aerophone, also a melodic instrument) is later mentioned in *Šulgi B*¹⁰⁵⁰. Therefore, why aerophones should appear again in *Šulgi B*, 157? However, that identification sets out some problems, so we shall propose an alternative identification for both **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** in this excerpt.

4.4.3.2.3.2. A supposed connection between **tige₂** and **tigidla**

Krispijn has identified the term **tige₂** with several stringed instruments¹⁰⁵¹ starting from the supposed etymological connection between ^ḡ**tigidla** and **tige₂** given by an Akkadian Old Babylonian omen about the gallbladder (*martum*)¹⁰⁵². Certainly, that text has the expression *ti-gi-dal-li*¹⁰⁵³, which Krispijn analysed as ***tige₂-dal** (“crossbar (**dal**)

¹⁰⁴⁹ ETCSL 2.4.2.02; Charpin, 2006: 59.

¹⁰⁵⁰ *Šulgi B*, 172 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

¹⁰⁵¹ Krispijn, 1990: 3 (a big lyre; followed by Ziegler, 1999: 94 n. 583); Krispijn, 2010b: 147 (a harp).

¹⁰⁵² YOS 10 59 [Smith College 12], r. 6 (9th omen) (Goetze, 1947a: 255).

¹⁰⁵³ Goetze, 1947a: 255; Lieberman, 1977: 504, word 670.

of the **tige**(2)). We would have here, therefore, a reference to the upper part of a lyre, the crossbar¹⁰⁵⁴. However, the writing **ti-gi** for /**tige**/ is mostly absent in Old Babylonian texts, and it should be understood as a variant¹⁰⁵⁵ of **ti-ge**₄, an old-fashioned spelling of /**tige**/ at that time¹⁰⁵⁶. In the same way, for *tigû(m)*, we would expect the reduplication of the second vowel (*ti-i-gu-um*). Therefore, we should not have just *ti-gi* as in this case¹⁰⁵⁷.

Moreover, *ti-gi-dal-li* may be read as *ti-ki₂-tal-li*, a form of *tikittallû(m)* (the Akkadian version of **tigidla**)¹⁰⁵⁸. As we have already discussed, this instrument seems to be a lute¹⁰⁵⁹ which, among others, had the speciality ^{neš}**tigidla kaskal-la** (“^{neš}**tigidla** of the way”)¹⁰⁶⁰. That makes sense in this context since *ti-ki₂-tal-li* is part of a chain with *apim*¹⁰⁶¹, a form of *apum* (“marsh”¹⁰⁶²), having *tikittallû apim* (“*tikittallû* instrument of the marsh”). In addition, lutes’ sound-boxes usually have the shape of a pear, just like the gallbladder. In this sense, we believe that the text YOS 10 59 [Smith College 12], r. 6 (9th omen) was comparing the shape of the gallbladder to the *tikittallû* lute. Therefore, there would be no reference here to the **tige**(2), to the contrary of Krispijn’s suggestion.

In any case, even if we understood **tigidla** (< ***tige**(2)-dal) as “crossbar of the **tige**(2) instrument”, there is no obligation of seeing here a reference to a lyre. Certainly, crossbars are also present on some drums like the Irish *bodhrán*¹⁰⁶³.

4.4.3.2.3.3. **balan** during the Old Babylonian Period

Krispijn also identified **tige**(2) with a stringed instrument based on the notion that the **balan** (contained in the *Diri tige*₂ = LUL.BALAD) was another chordophone. This term

¹⁰⁵⁴ Krispijn, 1990: 3; Krispijn, 2010b: 148.

¹⁰⁵⁵ *Nanna N*, 23, 26–27 (ETCSL 4.13.14).

¹⁰⁵⁶ See *Gudea Cylinders*, B10.9, B18.22 (Römer, 2010: 33, 38) for evidence.

¹⁰⁵⁷ Like *ti-ig-gu-um* in OECT 4 153 [Ashm. 1923-400], c 2–4 (DCCLT).

¹⁰⁵⁸ CAD T, p. 397.

¹⁰⁵⁹ We agree in this sense with Krispijn, 2010b: 148 and Krispijn, 2011: 117.

¹⁰⁶⁰ That makes sense with the naked and itinerant lute players depicted in the Old Babylonian clay plaques. See Krispijn, 2011: 116 for reference.

¹⁰⁶¹ Goetze, 1947a: 205 reads *aga'im* (from *agûm*, “tiara”) since the second sign is broken, and it might be GA. However, the reading of that sign as BI is more recent (Zorzi, 2011: 270, n. 94). Therefore, *apim* might be an improved reading, and we should follow it.

¹⁰⁶² CAD A2, p. 199.

¹⁰⁶³ Woods, 2015: 57.

has recently been identified as a giant lyre¹⁰⁶⁴. However, as we have already seen, according to Uri Gabbay¹⁰⁶⁵, **balan** actually seems to designate a percussion instrument by the early 2nd millennium BCE (the period of our *Šulgi B*) and later times. We can check that statement with the information given by the contemporary Sumerian literary texts.

In those texts, the sound production of the **balan** is described with the verbs **sag3** (“to beat”) and **šu dar**¹⁰⁶⁶. This expression might refer to a playing technique of an instrument using the edge of the hands¹⁰⁶⁷. Both verbs suggest the condition of **balan** as a percussion.

In addition, **balan** appears in those literary texts with the determinatives **neš** (for wooden objects)¹⁰⁶⁸ and **kuš** (for leather objects)¹⁰⁶⁹ in line with the lexical evidence¹⁰⁷⁰. There, and together with **a2-la2** (identified with a giant drum¹⁰⁷¹), the **balan** appears as a wooden¹⁰⁷² and leather object¹⁰⁷³. We have already seen how Kilmer thought that they referred to chordophones whose sound-box (partially covered in leather) would act as a sort of “percussive surface”¹⁰⁷⁴. This idea makes sense with the modern acoustic guitar sound-boxes, drummed with the hand in some modern styles. It is also interesting the case of the Japanese *shamisen*: A wooden sound-box covered in cat-skin it is strummed with a *bachi* (a plectrum) that thwacks the cat-skin to create a percussive effect¹⁰⁷⁵.

However, sounds produced from those surfaces are not very loud while the sound of the **a2-la2** is described in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts with the expressions

¹⁰⁶⁴ Shehata, 2017a: 73–74.

¹⁰⁶⁵ Gabbay, 2007: 57–63; Gabbay, 2014: 132, 134, 139–141; Gabbay, 2017: 46.

¹⁰⁶⁶ *Šulgi N*, 45 (ETCSL 2.4.2.14) and *Iddin-Dagān A*, 41 (Attinger, 2014a: 18) respectively. Literally, **šu dar** means “to split (**dar**) with the hand (**šu**)”.

¹⁰⁶⁷ Attinger, 2019d: 28.

¹⁰⁶⁸ *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 62 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94, 98); *Man and his god*, 4 (ETCSL 5.2.4).

¹⁰⁶⁹ *Old Babylonian Catalogue possibly from Sippar*, A 8 (edition dependent upon ETCSL 0.2.07).

¹⁰⁷⁰ But not in the administrative one, where we find only **kuš**: BIN 9 213 [NBC 7594] (00-10-03), o. 1 (CDLI P236223), and BIN 9 312 [NBC 7172] (00-00-00), o. 8 (CDLI P236322). Moreover, UET 3 282 [U. 6708] (00-00-00), o. 15 mentions a **balan** made of bronze (**zabar**) (CDLI P136599).

¹⁰⁷¹ See our Section 2.2.2.2 for identification in the 3rd millennium.

¹⁰⁷² EEN, p. 303 Ni II-075 [UM 29-16-294], r. i 6’–7’ (DCCLT); SLT 175 [CBS 8164], o. i 1’–2’ (DCCLT).

¹⁰⁷³ MSL 7, p. 211 V₁₆ [N 5056 + UM 29-16-391], o. ii 18–19 (DCCLT); MSL 7, p. 211 V₂₄ [3N-T649], c i’ 2’–4’ (DCCLT).

¹⁰⁷⁴ Kilmer, 1993–1995: 465.

¹⁰⁷⁵ Many thanks to Stephanie Lynn Budin for this interesting reference.

gu₃ nun dug₄ (“to produce a powerful sound”)¹⁰⁷⁶ and **šeg₁₁ ge₄** (“to roar”)¹⁰⁷⁷, two expressions making sense with the sound of a percussion, not a stringed, instrument. In the same way, Anne D. Kilmer’s argument forgets that **balan** and **a2-la2** are connected with the term **ḡešgur₂** (“circle”, “circumference”¹⁰⁷⁸) in Old Babylonian lexical texts¹⁰⁷⁹. Certainly, a rounded shape fits well with the Old Babylonian depictions of drums¹⁰⁸⁰, but not with those of chordophones except, perhaps, those depicting lutes¹⁰⁸¹. Therefore, **balan** and **a2-la2** might actually designate two types of drums with a leather membrane, perhaps fastened to their wooden frame with cords of animal gut or sinew.

4.4.3.2.3.4. **tige₂**: the **balan** instrument of the **nar**

If **balan** designated a type of drum and is contained in the logographic composition of **tige₂**, we should suppose that **tige₂** would designate a similar type of instrument. Certainly, the **tige₂** is mentioned together with other percussion instruments like the **sems** cymbals, the **a2-la2** giant drum¹⁰⁸², and the **balan** drum¹⁰⁸³. Both instruments, **tige₂** and **balan**, had a pure condition (**ku₃**)¹⁰⁸⁴, and texts talk about seven **tige₂** and seven **balan**¹⁰⁸⁵. Therefore, their single difference might be in their players and performance contexts¹⁰⁸⁶.

¹⁰⁷⁶ *Uruk Lament*, H 16 (ETCSL 2.2.5); *Iddin-Dagān A*, 79 (Attinger, 2014a: 20).

¹⁰⁷⁷ *Keš Temple Hymn*, 115a (Delnero, 2006: 2229-2230); *Hoe and Plough*, 28 (Mittermayer, 2019: 302). See Rendu Loisel, 2011: 10, 285 for comments.

¹⁰⁷⁸ Sallaberger, 2006: 265.

¹⁰⁷⁹ MSL SS 1, p. 96 [Ashm. 1923-402], a ii 37’–38’ (DCCLT); CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214], c iv 28–31 (DCCLT).

¹⁰⁸⁰ See Rāšid, 1984: 74–75 (fig. 58), 76–77 (fig. 59), 96–97 (figs. 91–96; to be completed with Dumbrill, 2005: 373–382). We would pay attention to fig. 59 (VA 7224) due to its connections with Dumuzi and Inanna (connections also established with the **balan**; see Shehata, 2014: 118 for comments).

¹⁰⁸¹ See Rāšid, 1984: 80–91 (harps and lyres), 92–93 (lutes).

¹⁰⁸² *Inanna and Enki*, II iv 47-48 (Farber-Flüge, 1973: 52); *Sumer and Ur Lament*, 436 (ETCSL 2.2.3); *Uruk Lament*, H 16–17 (ETCSL 2.2.5; with an **ub₃**, a **za-am-za-am**, and an **a2-la2** giant drum); *Šulgi A*, 50–51 (Delnero, 2006: 1887–1888 with Vacín, 2011: 273); *Iddin-Dagān*, 79 (Attinger, 2014a: 20).

¹⁰⁸³ *Našše A*, 41 (ETCSL 4.14.1 vs. Attinger, 2019e: 84, which has **sur₉** without indication of variants).

¹⁰⁸⁴ *Inanna and Enki*, II iv 48 (Farber-Flüge, 1973: 52) for **tige₂**; *Sumer and Ur Lament*, 441 (ETCSL 2.2.3), *Šulgi C*, B 90 (ETCSL 2.4.2.03), *Iddin-Dagān A*, 41 (Attinger, 2014a: 18) for **balan**.

¹⁰⁸⁵ *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 122 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 106) and *Šulgi A*, 78 (Delnero, 2006: 1900–1901) for **tige₂**; *Cursing of Agade*, 200 (ETCSL 2.1.5) for **balan**.

¹⁰⁸⁶ For considerations, see Gabbay, 2007: 61–62; Gabbay, 2014: 101–102 and Gabbay, 2017: 46.

Certainly, while the **balan** would be played for lamentations by the **gala** priest¹⁰⁸⁷, the **nar** would use the **tige₂** mainly for situations of general rejoicing¹⁰⁸⁸, food offerings¹⁰⁸⁹, royal praise¹⁰⁹⁰, or religious festivals¹⁰⁹¹.

An interesting example of this opposition between the **tige₂** and the lamentations might be an excerpt of the Old Babylonian tablet YBC 9862 belonging to the **er₂ sem₃-ma** lament **A uru₂-ḡu₁₀ im-me** (““Oh, my city!” She says”)¹⁰⁹². In that text, the goddess Inanna seems to say that the groups of **gala (nam-gala)**¹⁰⁹³ and **bur^{ur2}** priests (**nam-bur-ra**) disappear for her (**mu-ra-re₆(DU)**, literally “march for you”) before the sounds of her **tige₂** (**tige₂-ḡa₂**, literally “before my **tige₂** instrument”).

From this perspective, the expression **si sa₂** (“to arrange”; “to tune”) —sometimes mentioned with **tige₂**— might be understood as a reference to adjusting the leather membrane of the **tige₂**, and not to tuning it as a lyre¹⁰⁹⁴. That makes sense since, unlike the modern percussion instruments (whose membranes are usually made in synthetic

¹⁰⁸⁷ See *Cursing of Agade*, 198–200 (ETCSL 2.1.5) for its use by the chief lamenter (**gala mah**), and see *Ur Lament*, 86 (Samet, 2014: 58), *Inanna B*, 33 (Delnero, 2006: 2045), and *Dumuzi and Inanna F*, 37 (ETCSL 4.08.06) for its use in lamentation contexts (normally in connection with **er₂** “tears”).

¹⁰⁸⁸ *Cursing of Agade*, 36 (ETCSL 2.1.5).

¹⁰⁸⁹ *Inanna and Enki*, II iv 48 (Farber-Flügel, 1973: 52); *Šulgi A*, 51 (Delnero, 2006: 1888 with Vacín, 2011: 273); *Nanna N*, 23 (ETCSL 4.13.14).

¹⁰⁹⁰ *Šulgi A*, 78 (Delnero, 2006: 1900–1901).

¹⁰⁹¹ *Ur Lament*, 356 (ETCSL 2.2.2).

¹⁰⁹² **A uru₂-ḡu₁₀ im-me**, Cohen, 1988: 647–649 [YBC 9862], 43 (Cohen, 1988: 648). We have not found any copy/photo of this manuscript to check the transliteration. For that reason we have put **tige₂**.

¹⁰⁹³ Here is one of the few references to **nam-gala** we know of for the Old Babylonian Period beyond the lexical texts already commented on in our section 3.2.2 and the administrative texts where this term referred to the office of the **gala** priest (see Shehata, 2009: 175, 382–383, 385, 389–390, 394 for texts and comments). The other references to **nam-gala** we know for this period come from VS 2 29 [VAT 1339], o. 6–7: ^{o. 6} [**ga**]-**ša-an-e nam-ga[la]-e`eden-na`** ^{o. 7} [**e-a**]**n-na-e nam-ga[la-e eden-na`**] (Cohen, 1988: 556 with corrections derived from our inspections of the original handwritten copy of the manuscript), “^{o. 6} (what has) the lady (brought) for the office of the **ga[la]** priest? ^{o. 7} (what has the lady brought) for the [E-a]nna and the office of the **ga[la]** priest?” Cohen, 1988: 556 also transliterates **nam-gala** in line 11 of the same text. However, it is actually **nam-ur-`saḡ** according to the copy of that text, which makes sense with the previous line. Maybe **nam-gala** means here “lamentation music”, but the context is uncertain. In this sense, there is no clear reference to a “lamentation music” with the term **nam-gala** by the Old Babylonian Period, an important fact in order to define **nam-nar** as “music” *lato sensu*.

¹⁰⁹⁴ *Šulgi A*, 51 (Delnero, 2006: 1888 with Vacín, 2011: 273); *Nanna N*, 23, 26–27 (ETCSL 4.13.14). None of those references is in Wilcke, 2005. For these contradictions of **tige₂**, Michalowski, 2017: 223.

materials) the leather membranes of ancient percussions used to become loosened because of humidity and the repetitive use of said instruments¹⁰⁹⁵.

4.4.3.2.4. **a-da-ab** as musical instrument in *Šulgi B*, 157

The identification of the **a-da-ab** as a melodic instrument in *Šulgi B*, 157 has been made exclusively by derivation from the identification of **tige₂**. The **a-da-ab** is mentioned with the **sem₅** cymbals and the **a₂-la₂** in an excerpt from *Temple Hymns*¹⁰⁹⁶. In the same way, the **a-da-ab** is mentioned with the **tige₂** drum¹⁰⁹⁷ in another text where both instruments were made silent¹⁰⁹⁸. We suppose, in this sense, a certain similarity or complementarity between both instruments for their size or elaboration materials, but we cannot be more precise about that relationship, at least, for the Old Babylonian Period¹⁰⁹⁹.

4.4.3.2.5. Conclusions

In *Šulgi B*, 157, the king boasts about his knowledge of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab**, two types of percussion instruments, and not hymns as they have been traditionally defined. This new identification gives a new sense of the rest of the terms mentioned in that line.

Concerning **buru₃** and **da_{ḡal}**, they would make allusion to the depth and breadth of both instruments. The depth (**buru₃**) would affect to the “profundity” of the timbre of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** drums. On its behalf, the breadth (**da_{ḡal}**) would be important for the pitch of both instruments together with the tension of their percussive membranes.

In our opinion, the king would have learned both aspects by an active use of those instruments. Certainly, the verb of this sentence, **zu** (“to know”), referred to a cognitive process based on the use of the sight (**igi**) and ears (**ḡeštug₂**)¹¹⁰⁰. That fact also makes

¹⁰⁹⁵ Raman, 1922: 475.

¹⁰⁹⁶ *Temple Hymns*, 107 (ETCSL 4.80.1).

¹⁰⁹⁷ Krispijn, 1990: 4; Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 133; Krispijn, 2008: 177, have identified **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** in *Ur-Namma A*, 187 with two instruments, but we have previously dismissed that identification.

¹⁰⁹⁸ *Enki and the World Order*, 448 (ETCSL 1.1.3). TMH NF 4 1 [HS 1475 + 1476 + 1502], r. vi 18 has **tige₂** and not **tige**(BALAD.LUL) as in Benito, 1969: 113; Vanstiphout, 1999: 37 and ETCSL 1.1.3.

¹⁰⁹⁹ In the Neo-Assyrian document CT 14, pl. 8 [K. 4330], o. i 26’–27’ (DCCLT), they are two copper (**urudu**) objects, supposing, therefore, a difference concerning their size or shape.

¹¹⁰⁰ Wolfe, 2015: 205–206.

sense in the modern musical practice, where musicians learn the (ideal) measures of their instruments by the regular use and experimentation with said instruments.

If the king spent a long time playing those instruments, maybe he liked them. That might be due to their sound. In fact, in our opinion, **nam-nar šu du7-a** in *Šulgi B*, 157 would mean “perfect music” as “perfect sound”. Therefore, **nam-nar** might mean here the same as our current term “music”: a combination of sounds with (artistic) purposes. This idea makes sense with the place of the **tige2** and **a-da-ab** at the beginning of the list of instruments mastered by the king, and with the description of the **tige2** as a something (**niq2**) sweet (**duq3**)¹¹⁰¹ which is able to gladden the heart (**šag4 hu2-la**)¹¹⁰².

4.4.3.3. *Šulgi B*, 162: about Šulgi’s musical limits

We now are going to deal with another reference to **nam-nar** in the section of hymn *Šulgi B* about king’s musical abilities whose line 157 we have just analysed:

Text 35. *Šulgi B*¹¹⁰³

162 ^{ueš}sa-eš5 u3 šag4 nam-nar-ra-ka šag4 du-bu-ul-la mi-ni-zu

N _{I-B}	o. iv 4–5	^{ueš} sa ^ˊ -eš ^ˊ u3 ^ˊ []	/	šag4 du-bu-ul ¹¹⁰⁴ []
N _{I-E+d}	r. ii 14	^{ueš} sa2-eš	x [-k]a [?]	šag4 d[u-]-zu [?]
N _{I-G}	r. ii 6	^{ueš} sa -eš	u3	šag4 nam-nar-ra -ka ^ˊ	šag4 du-gu -la	ˊ mi ^ˊ -ni-zu
N _{U-q}	o. ii 7	sa -eš5	u3	šag4 nam-nar-ra-ˊka	šag4 ^ˊ du-[]
N _{I-t}	r. 2–3	^{ueš} X ¹¹⁰⁵ []	šag4 nam-nar-ra -ka / []	du-bu -la mi-ni-zu
N _{U-aa}	r. 13	[]	u3	šag4 nam-nar-ra -k[a]
N _{U-kk}	r. 8	[]		du-bu-ul-la ¹¹⁰⁶	mi-ni-zu
U _{TM}	r. 8	^{ueš} sa -eš	u3	šag4 nam-nar-ra -ka	šag4 du -g[u-]
X _{II}	Omits					

¹¹⁰¹ *Inanna and Enki*, II iv 48 (Farber-Flügel, 1973: 52); *Cursing of Agade*, 260 (ETCSL 2.1.5); *Nippur Lament*, 83 (ETCSL 2.2.4); *Uruk Lament*, H 17 (ETCSL 2.2.5); *Šulgi A*, 51 (Delnero, 2006: 1888 with Vacín, 2011: 273); *Nanna N*, 23, 26 (ETCSL 4.13.14).

¹¹⁰² *Winter and Summer*, 237 (ETCSL 5.5.3).

¹¹⁰³ Our own score edition taking into consideration the edition in composite line with notes about the variants of Castellino, 1972: 47 and Gerd Haayer’s score (through Krispijn, 1990: 21). We have corrected their transliterations inspecting the copies/photos of the tablets (some of them collated) indicated below.

¹¹⁰⁴ Castellino, 1972: 47 has “BU.UL^(l)”, while Gerd Haayer (= Krispijn, 1990: 21, *siglum B*) has “bu-ul”. We agree with Castellino because the sign lacks a straight wedge, and it seems rather a TI.

¹¹⁰⁵ It might be AL, but that sign does not make sense in this context.

¹¹⁰⁶ Gerd Haayer (= Krispijn, 1990: 21, *siglum Ah*) has “du.bu.ul.šē?”, but his EŠ₂ (= še3) seems LA¹. We consider it as incorrect due to the unusual length of its straight wedges, which “trample” the sign MI.

162 I know how to “stir” the interior of the ^{ueš}sa-ešs three-stringed instrument and the (deep) sense of the music.

*Sigla*¹¹⁰⁷

N _{I-B}	Castellino, 1972: pl. 1–6 [CBS 2345 + 2354 + 7071] (photo on CDLI P259350; collated the 19/08/2019)
N _{I-E+d}	Castellino, 1972: figs. 3 and 15 [N 1492 + 1741] (photo on CDLI P259086; collated the 21/08/2019)
N _{I-G}	Castellino, 1972: fig. 5 [UM 29-16-408 + 29-16-410 + 29-16-214G + 29-16-411 + 29-16-414A] (photo on CDLI P256906; collated the 19/08/2019)
N _{U-q}	Castellino, 1972: pl. 17–18 [3N-T300 = OIM A30203] (publication photo)
N _{I-t}	Castellino, 1972: pl. 19 [OIM A30219] (photo on CDLI P356651)
N _{U-aa}	ISET 2 60 [Ist. Ni 4211] (publication copy)
N _{U-kk}	ISET 2 93 [Ist. Ni 4078] (publication copy)
Ur _M	UET 6/1 81 [U. 16848] (photo on CDLI P346166; collated the 01/08/2019)
X _{II}	Volk, <i>forthcoming</i> [MS 3343] (photo on CDLI P252284)

Giorgio Castellino translated **šag4 nam-nar-ra** literally as “the essence (heart) of the musical craft”¹¹⁰⁸. However, Theo J. H. Krispijn supposed (without too many arguments) that **šag4 nam-nar-ra** described a musical instrument (maybe the ^{ueš}sa-ešs). Starting from that, he translated that term as “music sound-box”¹¹⁰⁹. This translation has been followed in the later research¹¹¹⁰. However, we miss in Krispijn’s identification of this **šag4 nam-nar-ra** a comparison with the allusion to the same expression in *Father and his rude Son*, 112. In fact, that text had already been published at the time of Krispijn’s proposal¹¹¹¹. As we have already said, in *The Father and his rude Son*, 112, **šag4 nam-nar-ra** did not describe a musical instrument. However, that term described a much more abstract reality; the “(deep) sense (**šag4**¹¹¹²) of music (**nam-nar**)”.

In our opinion, the entire excerpt *Šulgi B*, 162 might be on the limits of *Šulgi*’s musical capacities. On the one hand, the text talks about an “easy” musical ability: the playing of the three-stringed instrument ^{ueš}sa-ešs. Certainly, since it has just three strings, that instrument would have little musical possibilities and, therefore, it would be easy to play it. On the other hand, we have the *Šulgi*’s knowledge (**zu**, “to know”) of how to master

¹¹⁰⁷ They follow Castellino, 1972: 27–29, but we have put before an N (= Nippur), Ur (= Ur) or X (= Uncertain) according to the provenance of the manuscripts they are designing. Manuscripts from Nippur have an I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain) according to their tablet typology.

¹¹⁰⁸ Castellino, 1972: 47.

¹¹⁰⁹ Krispijn, 1990: 1 (“dem Schallkasten der Musik”), 8.

¹¹¹⁰ ETCSL 2.4.2.02; Charpin, 2006: 59; Wolfe, 2015: 53; Ziegler, 2017: 39–40; Peterson, 2019a: 213.

¹¹¹¹ This text cited by Castellino, 1972: 164 and Sjöberg, 1973: 128 (cited in Krispijn, 1990: 21!).

¹¹¹² See Attinger, 2019d: 176 (“sens (profond)”).

(literally “stir”, **du-bu-ul**) a very complex and abstract musical reality, the “(deep) sense of the music” (**šag4 nam-nar-ra**).

4.4.3.4. *Šulgi B*, 277–279: study of **šu nam-nar-ra**

We move now to a different section of the same hymn *Šulgi B*. In that section, the king boasts about his interest in the ancient knowledge of the humanity. As an example, he shows how, under his reign, the “ancient” **tige2** and **za-am-za-am** songs have returned to musical practice¹¹¹³. Here is an excerpt of that section:

Text 36. *Šulgi B*¹¹¹⁴

277 **ser3 gid2-da-bi e2 dug3-ga-ŋa2 pa ʿe3 ʰa-ba-ʿniʿ-in-ak**¹¹¹⁵

N _{I-B}	r. ii 1ʹ	ʿs[er3-gid2]-da ʿe2 dug3-ʿgaʿ-na / ʿe3 ʰaʿ-ba -niʿ-inʿ-ak
N _{U-y}	6	[]-da -bi e2 []
U _{r-w}	r. 9	ʿser3ʿ-gid2ʿ-daʿ-biʿ2 e2 dug3-gaʿ-ŋa2ʿ paʿ-ʿe3ʿ []
X _T	o. 15	ser3 -gid2 -daʿ-bi [e]2 dug3-ʿgaʿ -ŋa2 pa UD.[-b]a-ni -ak

278 **niŋ2 šu-ta ba-ra-šub-bu-da-ʿbi**^{ʿlu-u2 ar-mi}

N _{I-B}	r. ii 2ʹ	ʿniŋ2 šu -ta ba -raʿ -šub-ba-ʿbiʿ
N _{U-y}	7	[]-ta ba -ʿraʿ-[]
U _{r-w}	r. 11	ʿniŋ2ʿʹ []-ʿtaʿʹ [b]a -ra -ʿšubʿ-[] ¹¹¹⁶
X _T	o. 16	niŋ2 šu -ʿtaʿ š[i]-ʿra -šub -bu -daʿ-X-[] ^{ʿlu-u2 ar-mi}

279 **ʿšu nam-nar-ra-ʿke4 ʰe2-bi2-la2-ʿla2**^{ʿlu-u2 u3 x-x}

N _{I-B}	r. ii 3ʹ	ʿšu namʿ -nar -ʿraʿ-ʿkam ʰe2-bi2-la2-ʿla2ʿ
N _{I-R}	o. ii 1	ʿšu namʿ-[]
N _{U-y}	8	[]-nar -r[a-]
X _T	o. 17	ʿšu nam -nar-ʿra -ke4ʿ ʰe2-bi2 -la2 -ʿla2 ^{ʿlu-u2 u3 x-x}

¹¹¹³ This is clearly royal propaganda. Certainly, **tige2** and **za-am-za-am** hymns were already known in a text about Šulgi’s predecessor: *Ur-Namma A*, 187 (see above for our own edition). Moreover, in Ur III times, the chain LUL.BALAD = **tige2** is document only after Šulgi’s reign and it is not referred to a hyn (see BDTNS for evidence).

¹¹¹⁴ Our own score edition taking into consideration the composite line and variants in Castellino, 1972: 58 and Ludwig, 1990: 48, corrected with our consultation of the photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

¹¹¹⁵ Probably this excerpt has been studied by Anna Glenn in her recently finished and (successfully) defended PhD Dissertation (Glenn, 2019) about the role of the **ser3 gid2-da** songs in the cult in the Old Babylonian Period. In this sense, we could not access its content yet, we know just the Dissertation’s title. In any case and by the moment, see Glenn, 2018 and Glenn and Peterson, 2018 for a sample of her work.

¹¹¹⁶ Peterson, 2019a: 216 has a more fragmentary transliteration. However, the standard shape of some signs of this line does not differ too much from what we can read in the erased parts of that manuscript.

277 I caused to appear those long **ser**3 songs in my good house
 278 (and), in order to avoid their oblivion¹¹¹⁷, (Akkadian gloss) or be covered (?)¹¹¹⁸
 279 they were bound (again) to musical practice. (Akkadian gloss) may [...]

*Sigla*¹¹¹⁹

N_{I-B} Castellino, 1972: pl. 1–6 [CBS 2345 + 2354 + 7071]
 (photo on CDLI P259350; collated the 19/08/2019)
 N_{I-R} Castellino, 1972: fig. 14 [UM 29-16-451 + N 3312A]
 (photo on CDLI P256948; collated the 20/08/2019)
 N_{U-y} Castellino, 1972: fig. 15(y) [3N-T 902,068] (photo on CDLI P356140)¹¹²⁰
 Ur_w UET 6/1 82 [U. 16847] (photo on CDLI P346167; collation the 01/08/2019)
 X_T TCL 16 50 [AO 6712] (photo on CDLI P345394)

The last line of this text has **šu nam-nar-ra**, an expression understood in many ways in the past: 1) **šu** and **nam-nar** as separated words¹¹²¹, 2) as a normal allusion to **nam-nar**¹¹²², 3) as an allusion to the **nar**¹¹²³, and 4) as a musical repertoire¹¹²⁴. The first of these interpretations is the most correct because it keeps in mind the presence of **šu** (“hand”) and **nam-nar**. Nevertheless, both terms are separated in their translation when we actually have a genitive marker connecting them (**šu nam.nar + ak** [GEN] + **e** [DIR]). Therefore, **nam-nar** is not an inserted noun between **šu** and the verb of the sentence, (**la**2, “to hang”, “to suspend”) as Giorgio Castellino thought¹¹²⁵. Other translations forget **šu** and, therefore, the GEN {**ak**} connecting **šu** and **nam-nar**¹¹²⁶. Moreover, we have these specific remarks for some of those translations:

- The third option also forgets the prefix **nam-**. For that option, we would have expected something like **šu nar-e-ne-ke**4 (“to the musicians’ hand”) or **nar-e-ne-ra** (“for the musicians”, with the DAT {**ra**}). There is one manuscript (N_{U-y}) without **nam-**.

¹¹¹⁷ Literally “their fall from the hand”. See Lämmerhirt, 2010: 95 n. 620 for comments.

¹¹¹⁸ Our translations of the glosses should be considered as provisional due to their fragmentary context.

¹¹¹⁹ They follow Castellino, 1972: 27–29, but we have put before an N (= Nippur), Ur (= Ur) or X (= Uncertain) according to the provenance of the manuscripts they are designing. Manuscripts from Nippur have an I (= Type I) or U (= Uncertain) according to their tablet typology.

¹¹²⁰ This tablet was not available for its collation during 19–23/08/2019 in the University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology since it had been already returned to Iraq.

¹¹²¹ Castellino, 1972: 59 (“his hand to the art of music”).

¹¹²² Ludwig, 1990: 51 (“der Gesangeskunst”); Pitts, 2015: 63 n. 248 (“to musicianship”).

¹¹²³ Jáka-Sövegjártó, 2019: 48 (“to the musicians”).

¹¹²⁴ ETCSL 2.4.2.02 (“to the singers’ repertoire”); Shehata, 2009: 254 (“dem ‘Gesangsrepertoire’”).

¹¹²⁵ Castellino, 1972: 213–214. Shehata, 2009: 254 n. 1472 summarizes some of Castellino’s points.

¹¹²⁶ For Ludwig, 1990: 51 (“der Gesangeskunst”), we would expect in the text **nam-nar-re**.

However, that line in said manuscript is broken at its beginning. Therefore, it might have originally contained **nam-** too.

- The fourth translation forgets that **šu** refers to “writing” like “calligraphy”¹¹²⁷. Moreover, if we are right in understanding “repertoire” as “group of songs”, we must say that Sumerian abstract nouns referred to groups concern mainly numbers. This is the case of **nam-ia**, (“group of five”)¹¹²⁸, or **nam-ḡeš2** (“group of 60”, **ḡeš2** “60”)¹¹²⁹. In fact, **nam-nar** as “text *corpus*” is only mentioned in 1st-millennium texts¹¹³⁰.

Therefore, how should we understand **šu nam-nar-ra**? In order to propose a new definition for **šu nam-nar-ra**, we should study other expressions with **šu** (“hand”) and a Sumerian abstract noun¹¹³¹. Two examples are **šu nam-sa6-ga** (literally, “the hand of the goodness”)¹¹³² and **šu nam-uš2** (literally, “the hand (of) the death”)¹¹³³. In those cases, **šu** might allude to the “action” of the goodness and the death, an action metaphorically made by a hand (**šu**)¹¹³⁴. Therefore, we would translate **šu nam-nar-ra-ke4** as “to the action of music”¹¹³⁵. That expression might refer to the musical practice to which the “ancient” **tige2** and **za-am-za-am** hymns are supposed to have returned thanks to Šulgi.

4.4.3.5. Šulgi CC and the term **ser3 nam-nar**

The hymn *Šulgi CC*, recently edited for the first time, is one of our last new sources for the study of the term **nam-nar** in the Old Babylonian period because of this excerpt:

¹¹²⁷ Attinger, 2019d: 183 about *Edubba’ a A*, 41 (CDLI P464238).

¹¹²⁸ The word **ia** would be variant of **ia2** (“five”).

¹¹²⁹ For a larger list, see ePSD and ePSD2.

¹¹³⁰ See our chapter about the 1st millennium for details.

¹¹³¹ For a complete catalogue of those expressions, see Cavigneaux and al-Rawi, 2000: 40–42.

¹¹³² *Edubba’ a C*, 48 (ETCSL 5.1.3). Attinger, 2019d: 66 translated **šu nam-sa6-ga** as “une main bienfaisante”. However, we would have used just **šu sa6-ga** (“good hand”) for that.

¹¹³³ *Death of Nannā*, 66–67 (ETCSL 5.5.2).

¹¹³⁴ For instance, *Edubba’ a C*, 48: **a-šag4-za šu nam-sa6-ga ḡe2-bi2-ge4** (ETCSL 5.1.3) “I have returned the prosperity (literally, “the action/hand of the goodness”) in your fields”.

¹¹³⁵ In this sense, we might agree with Cavigneaux and al-Rawi, 2003: 42 (“qu’il l’intègre dans son art musical (‘qu’il attache à la main de musicalité’)”). Nevertheless, they suppose a non-existent possessive and do not take into account that the sentence is referred to several songs, and not to a single chant.

Text 37. *Šulgi CC*, UET 6/3 522 [U. 7774]¹¹³⁶

- o. i 1 **ur-^dlamma-ra^dlamma¹ki-gal-la-ta** [...]
 o. i 2 **ulutim¹sago¹alan¹z[ag]-še³nar AN¹gišgal²** [...]
 o. i 3 **nar¹saḡ keše²i³-ḡal²ser³nam-nar¹PI²PI GA¹MI KAK²M[I ...]**
 o. i 4 **kiḡ²maḡ kiḡ²galam eme¹SUH²dara³-ban³-da¹zag GALAM²x [...]**
- o. i 1 For Ur-Lamma, a protective deity from a pedestal [...]
 o. i 2 Good signs towards a statue on the ri[ght side], ... stand(?)... a station [...]
 o. i 3 The “very careful” **nar** was present, a sung musical composition [...]
 o. i 4 A majestic work, an artfully made work, (created by) the sophisticated language of Darabanda, the right side made artfully [...]

This excerpt helps us to revisit the character of the **ser₃ nam-nar** composition. The exact nature of this term is difficult to describe since we do not have texts having the rubric **ser₃ nam-nar** as, for instance, we have in the case of **ser₃ nam-gala**¹¹³⁷. In order to describe the nature of **ser₃ nam-nar**, let us have a look at another text:

Text 38. *Death of Nannā*¹¹³⁸

19 **dumu¹er₂in-pad₃saḡar-ta ma-ra-da-šub ser₃na[m]-nar¹mu-un-na-ab-e**

N_{I-A} o. i 19 **dumu¹er₂in-pad₃saḡar-ta**
ma-ra-da-šub ser₃na[m]-nar¹mu-un-na-ab -e
 N_{III-B} r. 1–2 []-an-ta²¹¹³⁹ /
 [] ma-ab¹¹⁴⁰-e¹

19 The son wept, fell down into the dust, and recited a “musical, sung text” for him.

*Sigla*¹¹⁴¹

N_{I-A} Kramer, 1960: pl. [G.1.2.b.1725] (publication photo)

N_{III-B} Sjöberg, 1983: 317 [CBS 14063 + N 4205]
 (photo available on CDLI P269079; collated the 20/08/2019)

¹¹³⁶ Edition dependent upon Peterson, 2019c: 698 with corrections derived from our inspection of the original copy and photo (on CDLI P346560) of this tablet. We collated it on 01/08/2019.

¹¹³⁷ See *Ibbi-Suen B*, C 13 (ETCSL 2.4.5.2), *Lipit-Ištar E*, 31 (ETCSL 2.5.5.5) and *Nanna L*, 53 (ETCSL 4.13.12) for reference and Shehata, 2009: 268 for description.

¹¹³⁸ Our own score edition starting from Kramer, 1960: 52 and Sjöberg, 1983: 318. We have corrected their transliterations consulting the photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

¹¹³⁹ According to the manuscript photo and our collation, there is here a sign TA due to a vertical wedge on the top, and not ŠAR₂ as in Sjöberg, 1983: 318.

¹¹⁴⁰ Copy shows an erased TAB after this sign. However, according to the manuscript photo and our collation, there is actually no such sign in the original clay tablet.

¹¹⁴¹ They follow Sjöberg, 1983: 315, but we have put before an N (= Nippur) insofar both tablets come from Nippur. Their typology is indicated with I (= Type I) and III (= Type III).

Dahlia Shehata, author of the longest description of **ser₃ nam-nar** to date, defined it as “die Bezeichnung einer melodiös ausgestalteten Vortragsweise für Klagegesänge”¹¹⁴² in light of this excerpt where **ser₃ nam-nar** seems to appear in a context of lamentation. However, Anne Löhnert¹¹⁴³ talked about that **ser₃ nam-nar** as a song connected with the **nar** as opposed to the **gala**. At that time, Löhnert’s opinion made sense vis-à-vis our Text 9 *Proto-Lu₂*, 590–591. In that Text 9, as we saw, there was a “lament (sung) text” (**ser₃ nam-gala**) together with **ser₃ nam-nar**. We would expect this **ser₃ nam-gala** in our Text 38 if Lu-diŋira were actually performing a lamentation for his father Nannā.

The new reference to **ser₃ nam-nar** in a praise context contained in the hymn *Šulgi CC*¹¹⁴⁴ confirms this impression of the ceremonial character of the song called **ser₃ nam-nar**. Furthermore, it invites us to rethink in the sense of **ser₃ nam-nar** in *Death of Nannā*, 19. In our opinion, the **ser₃ nam-nar** would also act as a ceremonial song in said text. That song would be a way of remembering and immortalizing the deeds of Nannā’s father (Lu-diŋira), once Nannā has wept (**er₂ pad₃**) at his death¹¹⁴⁵. This interpretation makes sense in light of *Šulgi E*, where different types of hymns performed by the **nar** praised several specific abilities of King Šulgi¹¹⁴⁶.

In this sense, thanks to *Šulgi CC*, o. i 3, we can change the previous identification of **ser₃ nam-nar** established by Dahlia Shehata, and we can identify this term now as a musical composition to be sung with a mainly ceremonial nature *lato sensu*.

4.4.4. Išmē-Dagān and **nam-nar**

4.4.4.1. *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, 367: devotion to the music

Ur-Namma and Šulgi were not the sole rulers interested in the music according to the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts. Certainly, in line with the rich musical life of

¹¹⁴² Shehata, 2009: 265.

¹¹⁴³ Löhnert, 2016: 55.

¹¹⁴⁴ The reference to a certain *Šulgi Cc* hymn (STVC 59) in Flückiger-Hawker, 1999: 53 is actually a reference to the manuscript F of the *Šulgi C* hymn (see Castellino, 1972: 247). See Sallaberger, 2011–2013: 278 for the reference to UET 6/3 522 [U. 7774] as *Šulgi CC*.

¹¹⁴⁵ We give thanks to Anne Löhnert for her feedback on this interpretation.

¹¹⁴⁶ *Šulgi E*, 16–38 (ETCSL 2.4.2.05).

their cities at that time¹¹⁴⁷, some rulers of the Isin and Larsa Dynasties of the early second millennium BCE were also interested in music. This is the case, for instance¹¹⁴⁸, of Išmē-Dagān of Isin (1889–1871 BCE)¹¹⁴⁹. We can see that in this excerpt¹¹⁵⁰:

Text 39. *Išmē-Dagān A + V*¹¹⁵¹

A 367 [n]am-[n]ar-ra ʾa₂ʾ-ḡu₁₀ ba-e-šum₂-ma

N _{III-A}	o. 10	[na]m-nar -ʾra	a ₂ ʾ-ḡ[u ₁₀ ba]-ʾeʾ-šum ₂ -ma
N _{III-B}	o. 5ʾ	[-n]ar -a	ʾa ₂ ʾ-ḡu ₁₀ ba -e -šum ₂ -ma
Ur _C	r. iiiʾ 4ʾ–6ʾ	[-na]r -e ²¹¹⁵² / ʾa ₂ ʾ-ḡu ₁₀ / [-šu]m ₂ -ʾmaʾ	

A 367 That I have devoted myself to music.

*Sigla*¹¹⁵³

N_{III-A} Ludwig, 1990: pl. 4–5 [3N-T 386 = A 30230] (publication photo)

N_{III-B} Ludwig, 1990: pl. 6–7 [3N-T 727 + 3N-T 925,506 = IM 58657]
(copy in OPBF 4 18; publication photo and CDLI P356556)¹¹⁵⁴

Ur_C UET 6/3 529 [BM – PJ] (publication copy; photos on Ludwig, 1990: pl. 8 and CDLI P346567; collated the 01/08/2019)

¹¹⁴⁷ For their musical life during this period, see Shehata, 2009: 126–147 (Larsa), 149–162 (Isin).

¹¹⁴⁸ We might remember also Išbī-Erra (ca. 1953–1921 BCE). Certainly, in the lexical text CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214], b iv 14 (DCCLT) we possibly find a reference to the **balan** of that king (^{ueš}balanʾʾ [...] ^diš-biʾ-[ir₃-ra]; DCCLT with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of CDLI P273880). Moreover, in the text Civil, 1987a: 14–15 [IM 58336] (Išbī-Erra 00-00-00), o. 7 (original publication; see also Frayne, 1990: 6–7), Išbī-Erra offers a majestic (^{maḥ}) **balan** to Enlil. In the same way, we can recall some instructions for the accompaniment of a hymn for Lipit-Ištar (ca. 1870–1860 BCE). See Kilmer and Civil, 1986; Kilmer and Tinney, 1996 and 1997; Kilmer and Peterson, 2009; Colburn, 2009; Michalowski, 2010a: 208 for editions and comments. Finally, see Shehata, 2019 for music under other Amorite kings.

¹¹⁴⁹ We have chosen the middle chronology given in Edzard, 1976–1980: 194.

¹¹⁵⁰ We follow the ETCSL edition of this text because Marie-Christine Ludwig also used that edition in Ludwig and Metcalf, 2017: 12 n. 14, 14 n. 15. We should remember that Marie-Christine Ludwig was the author of the *editio princeps* the (originally separated) hymns *Išmē-Dagān A* and *Išmē-Dagān V*.

¹¹⁵¹ Score edition dependent upon Ludwig, 1990: 167 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated down. CDLI P277029 [N 1915 + N 6268] contains lines A 37–50 of *Išmē-Dagān A + V* according to our collation of the tablet the 22/08/2019. Therefore, we cannot update Ludwig’s edition with new manuscripts as we would like to.

¹¹⁵² Ludwig, 1990: 167, Peterson, 2019c: 711 and CDLI P346567 have the sign RA, but it seems more like E (= e) since it has two superposed vertical wedges, not one like in the sign RA. That makes sense as a writing mistake since abstract nouns are non-human, and we must use the DIR {e}, not the DAT {ra}.

¹¹⁵³ They follow those of Ludwig, 1990: 163, but we have put an N (= Nippur) or Ur (= Ur) for the provenance of their manuscripts. Tablets from Nippur have also an III (= Type III) indicating their typology.

¹¹⁵⁴ This tablet was not available for its collation since it had been already returned to Iraq.

In this excerpt, the king expressed his devotion to music, literally saying that he has given (**šum₂**) his strength (**a₂**)¹¹⁵⁵ to music (**nam-nar**)¹¹⁵⁶. This expression has a parallel with the previously studied excerpt *Šulgi B*, 155¹¹⁵⁷. There, the king claims to have given, not his “arm” or “strength” (**a₂**), but his “neck” or “entirety” (**gu₂**) to music. Both expressions (**a₂ šum₂** and **gu₂ šum₂**) may be translated as “to devote oneself to”. However, **gu₂ šum₂** may be also translated as “to pay attention”¹¹⁵⁸. Therefore, Išme-Dagān might have focused less attention to music than Šulgi.

That makes sense with the musical contents of *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, 367–377 and *Šulgi B*, 154–174. While Išmē-Dagān only masters some songs and instruments, Šulgi claims to have mastered more complex concepts, like the tuning of some instruments¹¹⁵⁹ or the “(deep) sense of music” (= **ša₄ nam-nar-ra**). Furthermore, he was able to adjust the frets (**si-EZEN**) of the ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**šu-kar₂** lute without damaging its neck (**a₂**, literally “arm”)¹¹⁶⁰.

4.4.4.2. *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373–374: the difficulties of music

Even if Išmē-Dagān might have not had paid as much attention as Šulgi to his musical activities, the king from Isin thus speaks to us in this excerpt:

¹¹⁵⁵ ePSD (“to give power (to somebody)”); Attinger, 2019d: 188 (“octroyer la puissance”). We prefer to translate **a₂** as “strength” for the reasons to be discussed below.

¹¹⁵⁶ Ludwig, 1990: 173 (“der [Ge]sangeskunst”) and ETCSL 2.5.4.01 (“the art of singing”) ignore the instruments of *Išmē-Dagān A + V*: **ᵐᵉᵗ-ᵍu₃-ḏi** (A 370), ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**al-ᵍar-sur₉**, ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**sa-eš**, **sa-bi₂-tum** (A 371), ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**ḥar-ḥar** and **za-na-ru** (A 372). There is a player of the ^{ᵐᵉᵗ}**al-ᵍar-sur₉** instrument (**lu₂ al-ᵍar-su-ra**) in MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496], 248 (DCCLT). Therefore, we can follow neither to Klein, 1990: 76 (“the art of the musician”) nor Peterson, 2019c: 711 (“the art of the musician”). Both translations are focused on the **nar** when we actually find here references to different musicians, instruments and songs. We would instead follow Ziegler, 2013: 49 (“la musique”).

¹¹⁵⁷ This parallel was briefly suggested, but not commented on, in Klein, 1990: 76 n. 48.

¹¹⁵⁸ Civil, 2013: 39, with several examples.

¹¹⁵⁹ *Šulgi B*, 161, 171 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

¹¹⁶⁰ *Šulgi B*, 158–159 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

A 373 **nam-nar-a ki bal-bal-[l]a-bi**

N _{III-A}	o. 16	nam -nar-a ki bal-ba[l-la¹¹⁶²-b]i
N _{III-B}	o. 11 ⁷	[]-nar-a ki bal-bal -a -bi
Ur _C	r. iii ⁷ ? ⁷	[]

A 374 **šag₄ ser₃ še₁₁(LUL)-da ki dul-dul-la-bi zag im-mi-^rus₂-sa^r**¹¹⁶³

N _{III-A}	o. 17	šag₄ ser₃ še₁₁ -[d]a k[i dul]-dul-l[a -bi z]ag ^rim^r-mi-^rus₂-sa^r
N _{III-B}	o. 12 ⁷	[š]ag ₄ ser ₃ še ₁₁ -d[a k]i dul -dul-la -bi zag im -til- ^r la ^r
Ur _C	r. iii ⁷ ? ⁷	[]

¹⁷ That I have devoted myself to ¹⁶ the troublemaking parts of music (and) ¹⁷ to the most difficult aspects of the soothing of the heart (with) the **ser₃** songs.

*Sigla*¹¹⁶⁴

N _{III-A}	Ludwig, 1990: pl. 4–5 [3N-T 386 = A 30230] (publication photo)
N _{III-B}	Ludwig, 1990: pl. 6–7 [3N-T 727 + 3N-T 925,506 = IM 58657] (copy in OPBF 4 18; publication photo and CDLI P356556) ¹¹⁶⁵
Ur _C	UET 6/3 529 [BM – PJ] (publication copy; photos on Ludwig, 1990: pl. 8 and CDLI P346567; collated the 01/08/2019)

In this excerpt, we find the term **nam-nar** in an inverse genitive chain together with the expression **ki bal-bal**¹¹⁶⁶. The sense of **ki bal-bal** in this text is obscure since the usual meaning of **ki-bal** (“rebel land”) does not fit well in this context¹¹⁶⁷. However, it should designate something complicated¹¹⁶⁸ concerning music¹¹⁶⁹. Certainly, the expression **ki**

¹¹⁶¹ Score edition dependent upon the one in Ludwig, 1990: 167 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copies/photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

¹¹⁶² Ludwig, 1990: 167 has “bal-bal-[a-b]i”. However, the *lacuna* in the tablet is quite large, and we might have LA instead of the sign A. That might make sense with the following line of that manuscript.

¹¹⁶³ We adopt the variant ^rim^r-mi-^rus₂-sa^r for our composite line since it contains a 3NH.OO in reference to **ki bal-bal-[l]a-bi** and **ki-dul-dul-la-bi**, directive of **us₂** (“to follow”) (Attinger, 2019d: 211).

¹¹⁶⁴ They follow those of Ludwig, 1990: 163, but we have put an N (= Nippur) or Ur (= Ur) for the provenance of their manuscripts. Tablets from Nippur have also an III (= Type III) indicating their typology.

¹¹⁶⁵ This tablet was not available for collation on 19–23/08/2019 in the University of Pennsylvania’s Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology since it had been already returned to Iraq.

¹¹⁶⁶ Krispijn, 1990: 2 saw a LOC {a} in **nam-nar-a** and **šer₃ še₁₁(LUL)-da**. However, the 3NH.POSS {be} of **ki bal-bal-la-bi** and **dul-dul-la-bi** would remain unexplained in that way.

¹¹⁶⁷ Attinger, 2019d: 109 in addition to ePSD and ePSD2.

¹¹⁶⁸ We agree with Ludwig, 1990: 173 (“den widerspenstigen Stellen”) and Ziegler, 2013: 49 (“des passages difficiles”), but we do not understand the ETCSL 2.5.4.01 translation (“the developed aspects”).

¹¹⁶⁹ Except Krispijn, 1990: 2 (who translates **nam-nar** as “den (hymnischen) Musik”) **nam-nar** is referred to the singing in other translations: Ludwig, 1990: 173 (“der Gesangeskunst”), ETCSL 2.5.4.01

dul-dul-la (literally, “covered (**dul**) places”) of the following line of this text means “difficult aspects” in other texts¹¹⁷⁰. The use of **bal** (“to turn against”) would imply a reference to a confusing reality. That fact recalls to *Šulgi B*, 156, where anything (**niḡ2-na-me**) about music was “difficult to understand” (**gi16**) for *Šulgi*¹¹⁷¹.

Šulgi B, 162 and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373–374 both referred to the difficulties of music. However, while *Šulgi B*, 162 mentions an instrument with **šag4 nam-nar-ra**, *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373–374 makes reference to “the soothing (**še11**) of the heart (**šag4**) (by) the **ser3** songs”¹¹⁷² with **nam-nar-a ki bal-bal-la-bi**. In our opinion, we might have here a reference to the performance of lamentations. Certainly, **šag4 še11** (literally “to make cold the heart”) may describe the action of soothing the heart of a deity, the usual action in the performance of lamentations in Mesopotamia¹¹⁷³. Therefore, *Išmē-Dagān*, as *Šulgi*¹¹⁷⁴ and as a part of his musical expertise, would master some laments in addition to some instruments (like the **neš-gu3-di**) and praise songs (as the **za3-mi2** hymns)¹¹⁷⁵.

4.5. A last (and uncertain) literary text

We present here a final reference to **nam-nar** contained into a fragment belonging to a probable multi-column tablet from Ur¹¹⁷⁶. The nature of its content as a literary text is uncertain as it has some aspects more suitable to an administrative text¹¹⁷⁷, such as the

(“art of singing”), Ziegler, 2013: 49 (“l’art du chant”). However, we find many instruments (in addition to songs) in *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 368–372 (ETCSL 2.5.4.01). We prefer, therefore, to translate as “music” in this sense in order to keep in mind those instruments in our translation.

¹¹⁷⁰ *Eduḫba’a A*, 62 (CDLI P464238). See Attinger, 2019d: 46 for interpretation.

¹¹⁷¹ Ludwig, 1990: 199–200 for comments about **ki bal-bal** and connections with *Šulgi B*, 156.

¹¹⁷² In this occasion, **šag4** (“heart”, “interior”, “content”) is part of a chain together with **še11(LUL)**, not an independent word. Otherwise, we would find **šag4 ser3 še11(LUL)-da-ka** in our text. Ludwig, 1990: 189–195 suggested the reading **kad_x** and **še11**. In her opinion, the reading of LUL **ka_s** might be connected with the verb **kad4** (“to tie”). However, we would expect rather ***kad4-ser3** to have something like the **kešda nam-nar**. This term, **kešda nam-nar**, will be discussed later in our chapter on 1st-millennium evidence.

¹¹⁷³ Gabbay, 2007: 95–96.

¹¹⁷⁴ *Šulgi B*, 173–174 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

¹¹⁷⁵ *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 368 and A 371 respectively (ETCSL 2.5.4.01).

¹¹⁷⁶ UET 6/3, p. 21.

¹¹⁷⁷ For that reason, Jeremiah Peterson did not include this text among the texts edited in Peterson, 2019a-c. In any case this author might include this text in a future update of those editions. This text has

reference to two individuals attested in the Old Babylonian administrative texts: Šešmakal (only known in texts from Nippur as far as we know)¹¹⁷⁸ and Ku-Enlila, known in texts from Nippur¹¹⁷⁹ and Ur¹¹⁸⁰ (something very relevant in this context).

In any case, nobody could join the content of this text to another more complete text (literary or not) by the moment¹¹⁸¹. This text has been only recently edited by ePSD2 with an almost complete lemmatization of its content although with no translation. Due to the various novelties of this text, we present here an edition of the entire content of this recently edited Old Babylonian cuneiform tablet:

Text 41. UET 6/3 721 [U. ---]¹¹⁸²

- o. 1' [...] x² x²'
 - o. 2' [...] x RI-gen⁷ ka-na ba-e-si
 - o. 3' [...] u₃ nu]-um-ši-ku-ku-'ne'
 - o. 4' [...] x-'am₃' du₁₄¹¹⁸³ i₃-ak nu-'be²'
 - o. 5' [...] -bⁱ'-še₃ diri mu'-un-ḡa₂-ḡa₂
 - o. 6' [...] -ta 'ur₅'-ra-'gen⁷ uzu ga-'na'-[...] nam-'ab²'-ba d^ha[-ia₃' ...]
 - o. 7' [...] D]U nu-un-na-kal KAR₂ g[a- ...]
 - o. 8' [...] 'PA[?] x RU[?]'-ra pad₃-da[?] [...]
 - o. 9' [...] 'x' gur₃²-ru 'x' [...]
 - o. 10' [...] 'x' [...]
- Unknown number of missing lines

also been identified as a literary text in ePSD2 in the edition of Niek Veldhuis and Stephen Tinney. Thanks to Jeremiah Peterson and Niek Veldhuis for their personal communications.

¹¹⁷⁸ PBS 8/1 27 [CBS 13947] (00-00-00), o. 3 (Goddeeris, 2018: 107) and PBS 8/1 92 [CBS 10888] (00-00-00), r. 2 (our own consultation the photo of the tablet on CDLI P266081; see *Nippur Neighborhoods*, p. 239 and 280 for reference).

¹¹⁷⁹ TMH 10 13a [HS 2352 + Ist. Ni 9207 + N unnumbered] ([...]-[...] - [...]), ii 14" (TMH 10, p. 59); TMH 10 26 [HS 2390] (Sumu-el 22-10-00), r. 6 (Archibab T23364).

¹¹⁸⁰ UET 5 170 [U. 7795a + U. 7786d] (Sumu-El 07-10-00), r. 6' (Archibab T12141).

¹¹⁸¹ The verbal chain **ga-ni-ib-zu** (r. 3') is only known currently in *Enkiḡeḡal and Enkitalu*, 227 (Ceccarelli, 2018: 144), where we have **ga-ni-ib-zu-zu** (that is, the same verbal chain although with the verbal stem in the imperfective form). However, this manuscript is not among those to be used in the forthcoming edition of that text by Manuel Ceccarelli. In any case, there are no additional common elements between both texts.

¹¹⁸² Edition depending upon <http://oracc.museum.upenn.edu/epsd2/literary/P346758> [Last consultation 11/10/2019] with some corrections derived from our own inspection of the hand copy and photo of the manuscript, both available on CDLI P346758.

¹¹⁸³ We see just three *Winkelhaken* from the supposed sign NE for writing the **du₁₄**(LU₂×NE, "combat") transliterated by ePSD2. Actually, it seems as if we had **am'**(GU₄'×KUR) and not **du₁₄**. In any case, **am** ("wild bull", a non-human noun) does not make much sense with the 3SG.POSS {**ne**} of this sentence.

- r. 1' [...] ^rna[r² ...]
 r. 2' [...] ^rx KIḌ₂ ^rḥa-^rba²¹¹⁸⁴ [...]
 r. 3' [...]-a-ne₂ ^ršu ga-ba-ab-[T² ...] [e₂/ki umun₂¹¹⁸⁵]-^ra¹¹⁸⁶ nam-nar ga-ni'-ib-zu IM- [...]
 r. 4' [...] ^ršeš a-na lu₂ in-na-an-^ršum₂ [...]
 r. 5' [...] ^rsir₃'-sir₃-ra-ni in-duḥ x U[Š²¹¹⁸⁷ ...]
 r. 6' [...] ^rgu₄' eden'-e ba-^rni'-in-^rge₄²¹¹⁸⁸ u₄-1- [...]¹¹⁸⁹
 r. 7' [...] ^rimin²'-am₃ mu-un-^rḥa-za' [...]
 r. 8' [... D]U DU ^ršeš-ma-kal
 r. 9' [...] ^rku₃-^den-lil₂-la₂
 r. 10' [...] ^rmar'-tu
 r. 11' [...D]U-^rde₃' [...]

Unknown number of missing lines

- o. 1' [...]
 o. 2' [...] filled in his mouth like [...]
 o. 3' [...] they do [not sl]eep
 o. 4' He does not say: “[...] he foughted [...]!”
 o. 5' He places the radiance towards i[ts ...]
 o. 6' I want the flesh thus from [...]! [...] the Old Age, Ḥa[ya ...]
 o. 7' he provided for him [...]
 o. 8' [...] designated for [...]
 o. 9' [...] the bearer [...]
 o. 10' [...]

Unknown number of missing lines

- r. 1' [...] the musician [...]
 r. 2' May the [...]
 r. 3' I want to approach [...] to his [...], I want to learn music in [the conservatory]! [...]
 r. 4' [...] What did the brother give (to that) man? [...]¹¹⁹⁰
 r. 5' [...] He released (him from) his “bindings” [...]
 r. 6' He returned the bull to the stepe, one day [...]
 r. 7' He holds seven [...]
 r. 8' Šeš-makal [...]
 r. 9' [...] Ku-Enlila [...]
 r. 10' [...] Martu [...]
 r. 11' [...]

Unknown number of missing lines

As we can see, our term **nam-nar** appears in the line r. 3' of this text. In that part of the text, someone seems to wish to study music (**nam-nar**) in a place, probably the **e₂/ki umun₂** conservatory restored for our edition. These words (“I want to study music in the

¹¹⁸⁴ While the manuscript photo seems to have BA, the copy has IGI.

¹¹⁸⁵ Our own restitution inspired in *Proto-lu₂*, 59 (DCCLT Q000047) and making sense with the role of the **e₂/ki umun₂** in the musical education (see Michalowski, 2010a: 201–202 for reference).

¹¹⁸⁶ Omitted in ePSD2, but perceptible in the copy and photo of the manuscript. It makes sense with the LOC infix {**ni**} of the verbal chain.

¹¹⁸⁷ However, on the copy, this sign seems to be NI.

¹¹⁸⁸ The sign is a bit erased and it might be IG. However, GI₄ makes grammatically more sense.

¹¹⁸⁹ ePSD2 has “^rx' ba-an-šum₂’” after the break, but the tablet is definitely broken after that part.

¹¹⁹⁰ Very hypothetical translation. We should have actually something like [...] **šeš-e a-na lu₂-ra in-na-an-šum₂** [...].

conservatory!”) would be suitable for the son of the composition *The Father and his rude Son* which we have previously commented on in this study. However, that son never said such words. In addition, our Text 41 is broken on the right and the left sides. Therefore, the context of that sentence is currently highly obscure. Certainly, only a small portion of its content may actually be related to anything musical, for instance, the possible reference to the musicians (**nar**) in line r. 1’¹¹⁹¹.

In this sense, only with additional research (search of joins, edition of unpublished fragments, etc.) might we arrive at a better understanding of this text and, more specifically, its reference to **nam-nar**.

4.6. Conclusions about **nam-nar** in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts

We currently lack of all the basic data pertaining to our Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts, such as their chronology or original provenance. Therefore, we are still far from a definitive understanding of our allusions to **nam-nar** in this type of texts. In any case, if we continue the trend of recent years, where new references to **nam-nar** have been published, it is probable that our understanding of **nam-nar** in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts will experience some changes in the future.

These changes will be ensured, at least, by two aspects suggested in this study. First, the finalization and publication of the *forthcoming* edition of the full text of *Enkiheṅal and Enkitalu* by Manuel Ceccarelli. That *editio princeps* will definitely be an interesting source for further discussions and, probably, new and fresh approaches to the many musical terms contained in that text, some of them analysed in this study. Second, we have stressed the necessity of looking for some joins for the current tablet of our Text 41 and/or to find tablets with a similar content. Certainly, we need to improve what we currently know regarding this fragmentary text.

There is a recent example of what new publications and/or editions of specific tablets can do for our understanding of **nam-nar** in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts. We are talking about our Text 37, an excerpt from the hymn *Šulgi CC* edited in 2019 by Jeremiah L. Peterson. Certainly, that text has helped us to propose a new interpretation

¹¹⁹¹ In r. 5’, **sir3-sir3** might be read as **ser3-ser3** in order to refer something related to the **ser3** songs, but it does not fit with **duh**, probably the most suitable reading for the sign GAB in this context.

for the term **ser₃ nam-nar**, traditionally seen as a literary designation for the performance of lamentations in light of our Text 38, an excerpt of the *Death of Nannā*.

We pay attention now to what we have currently about **nam-nar** in the Sumerian literary texts from the Old Babylonian Period. In practically all our current references to **nam-nar** in that type of texts, a translation as “Music” is correct. That normally happens because there is an equal representation of elements of the instrumental and vocal music in close connection to **nam-nar**. Some of our Old Babylonian references to **nam-nar** are especially very interesting. This is the case of *Šulgi B*, 157. Certainly, in that text, **nam-nar** might designate the sounds of the (probably) favourite instruments of King Šulgi: the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** drums. This sense of **nam-nar** is also found in the Text 12, a model contract discussed in our previous chapter, and it is very relevant in our argument for the existence of a word for “Music” in Sumerian and/or Akkadian. Certainly, we are definitely dealing with a word with the same connotations as our modern term “Music”.

Other literary excerpts studied in this chapter are also very interesting. In them, **nam-nar** appears in situations where we would still use the word “music”:

- In *Enkihejal and Enkitalu*, 110 (= Text 23), someone is not suitable for **nam-nar** in the same way that, still today, we can say that someone is not fit for music in the sense of having little/no musical talent or inclination.
- In *The Father and his rude Son*, 107–112 (= Texts 24–25), the son wishes to become a musician. However, his father believes that the scribal profession would be more honourable (and, perhaps, economically profitable) for him.
- In *Enki and Ninmah*, b 26–29 (= Text 27), **nam-nar** is defined as the destiny or condition (**nam**) of a blind individual.
- In *Šulgi B*, 154 (= Text 32) and *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 367 (= Text 39), the kings claim to have devoted themselves to music as someone still may say that (s)he is devoted to music, probably as his/her (main) professional occupation.

This term **nam-nar** not only designates music *lato sensu* in our Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts, but also some more concrete musical aspects. Among them, we have the notion of “musical practice” (**šu nam-nar-ra**, *Šulgi B*, 279 = Text 36) or some

place for that musical practice (the **e₂ nam-nar-ra** of *Ur-Namma A*, 187–188 = Text 31). We have also a reference to the most difficult aspects of the music (**nam-nar-a ki bal-bal-la-bi**) in *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, A 373 (Text 40).

However, the most striking the reference to **nam-nar** we have from this Old Babylonian Period is the one to the “(deep) sense of Music” (**šag₄ nam-nar-ra**) in *The Father and his rude Son*, 112 (Text 24) and *Šulgi B*, 162 (Text 26). Certainly, that expression makes reference to a deeper reality than the mere ability for playing music suggested by Piotr Michalowski as the meaning for **nam-nar**.

All these facts are very relevant for the definition of **nam-nar** mainly as “music” and the defence of the existence of a word for “music” in ancient Mesopotamia. Someone might say that this meaning might be a mere literary variation of the meaning of **nam-nar** available in the contemporary legal texts. However, we must remember the existence of some connections between the literary texts studied here and our texts coming from the earliest stages of the scribal curriculum, which were studied in the previous chapter. This is the case of *Inanna and Enki*, I v 33–34 and II v 47–52 (= Texts 29–30), to be compared with *Proto-izi*, II 227–231 (= Text 10). Moreover, we might compare our texts *Šulgi CC*, o. i 3 and *Death of Nannā*, 19 (= Texts 37–38) with our Text 9 (= *Proto-lu₂*, 590–591).

In any case, for further reflections, we recommend proceeding with the next chapter. There, this dichotomy of Old Babylonian literary vs. legal texts containing **nam-nar** will be considered from another perspective.

5. *NĀRŪTUM* IN THE OLD BABYLONIAN TEXTS FROM MARI

5.1. Introduction

In the two previous chapters, we have seen that **nam-nar** meant “office of the **nar**” in the legal texts, while **nam-nar** as “Music” was mainly found in the Old Babylonian Sumerian literary texts. One might think that the real meaning of **nam-nar** was, in consequence, “office of the **nar**” because that was the meaning of **nam-nar** in the texts of the daily life of the real people from that time. On the contrary, “music” might be just a mere “distortion” of the original meaning of **nam-nar** with literary purposes.

However, we have also said that **nam-nar** as “music” is equally found in some texts of the elementary scribal curriculum. In addition, most of the literary texts discussed here were performed before an audience. As a consequence, that audience could also have been familiar with “music” as a meaning for **nam-nar**. Therefore, the main meaning of **nam-nar** by Old Babylonian times might still have been “music”. The meaning “office of the **nar**” would be, in this sense, a secondary meaning of that term in some legal texts.

This situation might be better illustrated in the case of the texts from Mari during the Old Babylonian Period. There, because of the rich musical life developed in this city at that time¹¹⁹², we find 16 references to *nārūtum*¹¹⁹³. That means that we are confronted by the largest group of allusions to this term in the early 2nd millennium BCE. Certainly, the closest thing we have from that period are two Old Assyrian texts from Kaniš¹¹⁹⁴ with *narūtum*, term actually designating a type of malt.

But, why should we go to Mari, a northern Mesopotamian city, in order to understand a problem located in southern Mesopotamia? The reason is that all the texts containing

¹¹⁹² In addition to the Nele Ziegler’s contributions (2005, 2006, FM 9, 2010, 2011, 2013, 2015), Soden, 1988; Marcetteau, 2008; Colonna d’Istria, 2011; Dumbrill, 2014; Franklin, 2015: 73–88; Shehata, 2017a.

¹¹⁹³ FM 9, p. 332 transcribes “*nârūtum*” instead of the Babylonian form *nārūtum*. This type of transcription of *nāru(m)* as *nāru(m)* or *nuāru(m)* is more common for later periods and northern regions (see Groß, 2014: 223–224 for Neo-Assyrian times). However, as FM 9, p. 332 shows, there is no spelling of *nârūtum* like **na-a’-ru-tum* (following what happens in Kassite Babylonia, see Sassmannshausen, 2001: 100 for reference) or *nu-a-ru-tum*. The same happens with *nārum* (FM 9, p. 332). In this sense, we prefer to maintain the usual transliterations *nārum* and *nārūtum* for the records from Old Babylonian Mari despite the northern location of that city and the hypothetical presence of some spelling regional variations.

¹¹⁹⁴ TCL 14 47 [AO 8717], o. 7 (CDLI P357537; see Michel, 2001: 478–479; Larsen, 2002: 76–77 and Michel, 2006: 174 n. 28 for comments) and VS 26 75 [VAT 13516], r. 7’ (CDLI P358227).

references to *nārūtum* in Mari belong to a single textual typology (letters), unlike southern Mesopotamia. Therefore, the suitability of a meaning for a reference *nārūtum* as an office or music does not depend upon the textual typology, but the context of said reference.

5.2. Texts from the reign of Šamšī-Addu (1795–1776 BCE)

5.2.1. Texts with *nārūtum* as “office of the *nārum*”

5.2.1.1. ARM 1 78 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

This first text recalls to us our Texts 7 and 8. There, the sister of an individual called Ilī-šummid was expelled from her position as *kala’um* in Awal, the said position (together with *nārūtum*) then being given to a person with the Hurrian name Wirri. In our text from Mari, a man with another Hurrian name, Kulpi-Atal¹¹⁹⁵, son of Ḫaṣrī-Āmîm (name of Western Semitic origin, “Āmûm is my ‘fold’”)¹¹⁹⁶ is removed by the king Yasmaḥ-Addu from his position as *nārum* of Āmûm (local form of the Netherworld god Nergal)¹¹⁹⁷ in the north Mesopotamian city of Ḫubšalum (also called Ḫubšil)¹¹⁹⁸. After that, he is deported to the city of Mari. In this letter, the Yasmaḥ-Addu’s father, Šamšī-Addu¹¹⁹⁹, will try to convince his son to attach that musician, not to a temple of Mari, but to Āmûm’s temple in the near-by city of Šubat-Ellil¹²⁰⁰.

¹¹⁹⁵ In addition to LAPO 16, p. 91 (with reference to NPN, p. 229), see GLH, p. 151; Fournet, 2013: 53 for the Hurrian term *kul-* (“to say” (?)), and Maidman, 2010: 23, 50, 73, 78, 241 for personal names. Pay special attention to Maidman, 2010: 50, where we find a Kulpen-dayyān not mentioned in LAPO 16, p. 91. We have transliterated Kulpi-Atal instead of Kulpi-Adal in order to reinforce this Hurrian origin.

¹¹⁹⁶ LAPO 16, p. 91 (which saw here a Western Semitic origin) translated this name as “Mon-secour-est-Āmûm”. This is a bit of a free translation of that name since *ḫasīru(m)* means in CAD Ḫ, p. 130 just “enclosure for sheep” or “enclosed area for delivery of dates”.

¹¹⁹⁷ About Nergal and Amûm in Mari and its cult places, see Durand, 1993a and 1993b.

¹¹⁹⁸ About this city, Ziegler and Langlois, 2017: 146.

¹¹⁹⁹ We prefer the transcription Šamšī-Addu instead of Samsi-Addu since *sa-am-si* can be read as *ša₁₀-am-ši₂*. For Addu instead of Adad, see Schwemer, 2000: 34–72 and 292. Moreover, we find the Proto-Semitic **šamš* (“sun”) in other North-Western Semitic languages like the Amorite: *šemeš* (Hebrew), *šmš* (Phoenician) (Krahmalkov, 2000: 472) or *špš* (Ugaritic; Olmo de Lete and Sanmartín, 2003: 836). From an Akkadian perspective, Šamšī-Addu explains better its meaning as “My Sun (Šamšī) is Addu”.

¹²⁰⁰ See FM 9, p. 65 for this interpretation of the content.

Text 42. ARM 1 78 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁰¹

- o. 1 [a-na i]a-as₂-ma-aḫ-^dIŠKUR^ʾ
o. 2 [qi]₂-bi₂-ma
o. 3 [u]m-ma ^dUTU-ši-^dIŠKUR a-bu-[k]a-a-ma
o. 4 [l]ku-ul-pi₂-a-tal
o. 5 [DU]MU ḫa-aṣ-ri-a-mi-im N[A]R^{*1202}
o. 6 ša ^dNERGAL¹²⁰³
o. 7 ša ḫu-ub-ša-lim-x^{?1204}-[ki]
o. 8 ʾa^ʾ-na na-si-ḫu-tim
o. 9 [a-n]a ma-ri^{ki}
o. 10 [t]a-ʾsu-uḫ^ʾ
r. 1¹²⁰⁵ i-na-an-na ʾLU₂ʾ ša-a-t[i]
r. 2 wa-aš-še-ra-aš-šu
r. 3 an-ni-ki-a-am
r. 4 NAR-tam¹²⁰⁶ ša ^dNERGAL
r. 5 li-pu-{ x x }¹²⁰⁷-uš

o. 2 [S]ay^{o. 1} [to Y]asmaḫ-Addu, o. 3 [t]hus (speaks) Šamšī-Addu, [y]our father: o. 10 [Y]ou expelled^{o. 4} Kulpi-Atal, o. 5 [s]on of Ḫašrī-Āmīm, n[ār]um^{o. 6} of Āmûm^{o. 8} in Ḫubšalum, o. 9 [t]o Mari^{o. 8} as deported!
r. 2 Release^{r. 1} right now thi[s] man¹²⁰⁸! r. 5 Let him perform^{r. 3} here^{r. 4} the *nārum*'s office of Āmûm!

In this text, *nārūtum* appears together with a precative form of the verb *epēšum* (“to perform”). That expression (*nārūtam epēšum*) can be translated as “to make/perform

¹²⁰¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T4497 with corrections derived from our inspection of the original copy of this tablet (available also on CDLI P254279). ARM 1 78 is actually the edition of the tablet copied in TCL 22, pl. 101 when it was still conserved at the Louvre Museum (it is now in Syria).

¹²⁰² CDLI P254279 has *i7* (“canal”). It is true that we do not have the most canonical written form of LUL (= NAR), but the CDLI transliteration does not make sense in this context.

¹²⁰³ Usual transliteration is NE₃.ER₁₁.GAL (like Archibab T4497). However, ePSD already gave the reading **nergal** for the combination of signs PIRID (= ne₃) AB_{gunû} (= er₁₁) GAL (= gal) and it is established in this way in aBZL 291a (here as KIŠ.UNUG.GAL; KIŠ is practically identical to PIRID in Old Babylonian cursive writing). Therefore, we prefer to use this more updated transliteration.

¹²⁰⁴ However, between ŠI (= lim) and the lacuna, there is another sign that we cannot connect with some other forms of this place name. CDLI P254279 reads ^{ki}, but we should have ^{ki} since that sign is not similar to the sign KI of line o. 9.

¹²⁰⁵ CDLI P254279 says “reverse / beginning broken”, but the copy shows perfectly that there is no erasure or broken section in the tablet for saying that.

¹²⁰⁶ CDLI P254279 has “_i7_”. The reading of the first sign in this way is based on what we have said about line o. 5. However, sign LUL is clear here, and that transliteration of CDLI P254279 omits the second sign of this line, UD (to be read here as *tam*).

¹²⁰⁷ CDLI P254279 omits these two superfluous signs clearly depicted in the copy of this tablet.

¹²⁰⁸ We follow ARM 1 78. LAPO 16 14 (followed by Archibab T4497) “rends-lui sa liberté” supposes a non-existent noun with a 3SG.POSS feminine and ignores the *awīlam šāti* as “this man”.

music”. However, in this case, because of the genitive chain *nārūtam ša Āmûm*, we should translate this expression as “to practice/perform the office of the *nārum* of Āmûm” as it has usually been translated in the past¹²⁰⁹. Certainly, for a sentence of the type “may he perform music for Āmûm!” we should find in the text something like *nārūtam ana Āmûm līpuš* (NAR-tam a-na ^dNE₃.ERI₁₁.GAL li-pu-uš), that is, with *ana* instead of *ša*.

The first edition of this text proposed the translation “service du chant”¹²¹⁰. Whether the cult of Nergal/Āmûm in Mari and related regions mainly required the use of songs or instruments is difficult to say. Certainly, we know several *gerseqqûm* eunuchs having acted as musicians for Nergal¹²¹¹. However, they are known just as ^{lu}2NAR DIRI₃.SAG₁₀.GA¹²¹² and their musical functions cannot be specified, for instance, by going to other texts where they are with other musicians¹²¹³. In any case, the use of instrumental music in addition to the singing for the Nergal/Āmûm’s cult might be possible. For that, we should keep in mind¹²¹⁴ that the *Nergal C* and *E* are defined in their colophons as **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** hymns¹²¹⁵. That is, they supposed for their performance the use of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** and the singing¹²¹⁶. In this sense, we would understand *nārūtum* in this text as a reference to the *nārum* as a musician in the broad sense, and not just as a singer.

¹²⁰⁹ CAD N1, p. 382 (“the duty of musician”); LAPO 16 14 (“l’office de musicien”; followed by Archibab T4497); FM 9, p. 65 (“fonction de musicien”). AHw II, p. 749 has this text among those used there for giving the definition of *nārūtu(m)* as “Musiker(innen)beruf”.

¹²¹⁰ ARM 1, p. 147. In addition, Læssøe, 2014: 56 (“his singing”).

¹²¹¹ FM 9 9 [M.7618+M.14609] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), r. 3, o. e. 1 (Archibab T6569), and FM 9 10 [A.93+A.94] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 5, lo. e. 1 (Archibab T6570). About FM 9 10 [A.93+A.94] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), lo. e. 1, Nele Ziegler (= FM 9, p. 66) talks about a “chanteur yamhadéen” when the text has ^{lu}2NAR DIRI₃.SAG₁₀.GA. Moreover, according to FM 9, p. 17–18, the **nar/nārum** was an instrumentalist.

¹²¹² This reading following the Attinger’s transliteration system fits with FM 9, p. 23 n. 116. There it was said that the Akkadian reading for the Sumerogram normally written as DIR₃.SIG₅.GA was *kirisakkum*.

¹²¹³ In FM 9 38 [A.78] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 5–r. 5 (Archibab T6596), one DIRI₃.SAG₁₀.GA accompanies several young *nārtum* musicians from Mišlan to Šuprum in a boat. In the same way, according to FM 3 2 [A.3165], r ii 17’ (FM 3, p. 54), the DIRI₃.SAG₁₀.GA are present in the Eštar rituals performed by the *kalûm* lamentation priests. Nevertheless, they were just as attendants in the said rituals.

¹²¹⁴ Obviously keeping in mind the geographical distances between Mari and southern Mesopotamia.

¹²¹⁵ *Nergal C*, 75 (Peterson, 2015a: 52) and *Nergal E* (ETCSL 4.15.5; only catalogued). In addition, *Šu-ilīšu A* is defined in its line 68 (ETCSL 2.5.2.1) as an **a-da-ab** hymn for Nergal. See Shehata, 2009: 253 n. 1404–1405 for reference. Pay attention to the fact that some variants of *Nergal C* defined this composition as **a-da-ab** hymn, and not as **tige₂** hymn. See Peterson, 2015a: 45 for reference.

¹²¹⁶ The use of **ser₃** songs in order to praise the name of Nergal appears in *Nergal C*, 57 (ETCSL 4.15.3).

5.2.1.2. FM 9 24 [M.5160] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

The following excerpt comes from a letter where, possibly, the *nargallum* Rîšīya¹²¹⁷ is explaining to his king Šamšī-Addu some aspects of musical instruction for a group of *aštalûm* musicians, *kalûm* priests and *nārum*:

Text 43. FM 9 24 [M.5160] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²¹⁸

- r. 7 [š]a-ni-^rtam^r a[š]-^ršum^r LU₂.TUR.MEŠ aš-t[a]-^rli^r-ia
r. 8 be-^rli₂ ke-em^r iš-^rpu^r-ra-am
r. 9 um-^rma^r-mi^r LU₂.TUR.MEŠ^r-ka
r. 10 [u₃] LU₂.TUR.MEŠ^r ša^r DIDIR^r-šu-i-bi-šu
r. 11 pu-uh-^rhi-^rra-ma LU₂.TUR.MEŠ aš-ta-li^r DUMU^r /^rka^r-[e]-e
r. 12 [li-li-ku]-^rnim^r lu²[NAR].MEŠ^r-ru-ni
r. 13 [ul-la-nu-um na-ru-tam] ^ri^r-^rha-zu

^r. 7-8 [A]nother thing: My lord wrote to me in the following terms [conce]rning my young ašt[a]lûm musicians: ^r. 9-13 “Gather your young people and the young ones of Ilišu-Ibišu! May the *aštalûm* young musicians and *kalûm* lamentation priests come to me! Our musicians will learn [music there]!”

The term *nārūtum* is hypothetical because of the relatively uncertain context, as NAR in [nārū]ni (= lu²[NAR].MEŠ^r-ru-ni) of the previous line is also hypothetical. In this sense, any interpretation of the exact content of this text is provisional. This *nārūtum* has normally been understood as “music”¹²¹⁹ or “art of music”¹²²⁰. Nevertheless, this term seems not concern anything general about music in this context. Far from that, it concerned something highly related to the musicians mentioned in the previous line of this text. Certainly, the *aštalûm* young musicians and the *kalûm* priests seem to not be affected by *nārūtum* in this case. In fact, they had already their instructions in this text (to be gathered and to come together in the presence of Rîšīya). Therefore, we tend to think that *nārūtum* should be understood in this case as “office of the *nārum*”. This term would make reference to the musical “subject” to be learned by those *nārum* in this text.

¹²¹⁷ For “Rîšīya” and not “Rišīya” (for instance, in Ziegler, 2011: 293) or “Rišīya” (for instance, in de Boer, 2014: 378), see Schneider, 1992: 157. There, this term is seen as an adaptation from the Hebrew *rôš* (“head”, “chief”). We would translate the name Rîšīya as “(He (= in reference to a deity)) (is) my chief”.

¹²¹⁸ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6582 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹²¹⁹ Ziegler, 2006a: 349 (“Musik”); Ziegler, 2010: 125 (“music”).

¹²²⁰ FM 9, p. 16 and 130 (“l’art de la musique”; followed by Archibab T6582).

5.2.2. Texts with *nārūtum* as “music”

5.2.2.1. ARM 1 64 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

The first text of this section (possibly dated to the early years of Šamšī-Addu’s reign)¹²²¹ deals with instructions to teach music to a group of women. These females had to be hosted in Ekallātum and Šubat-Ellil as part of the organization of the facilities of the new royal residence. However, they seem to have been ultimately hosted in Mari¹²²²:

Text 44. ARM 1 64 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²²³

- o. 1 *a-na ia-as₂-m[a-aḫ-^dISKUR]*
o. 2 *qi₂-bi₂-^rma^ˀ*
o. 3 *um-ma ^dUTU-ši-^dISKUR*
o. 4 *a-bu-ka-a-ma*
o. 5 *tup-pi₂ an-ne₂-em¹²²⁴ la-u₂-um*
o. 6 *ma-aḫ-ri-ka li-iš-me*
o. 7 **MUNUS.TUR.MEŠ** ^ria^ˀ-aḫ-du-ul-li-im
o. 8 *ša ad-di-na-kum*
o. 9 **MUNUS.TUR.MEŠ** ši-na ir-ta-be₂-e
o. 10 *[u]₃ ^rki-a^ˀ-[am] ^ri^ˀ-na sa-ga-ra-tim^{ki}*
o. 11 *[aš-šu-mi-ši-na i]q-bu-nim*
o. 12 *[um-ma-mi] ^rši^ˀ-na si₂-in-ni-ša*
o. 13 *[...]-^rx-ni^ˀ-iš-ma*
r. 1 *[...]-x*
r. 2 *[... u₃ i-na-a]n^{*1}-na*
r. 3 *[a-na e₂-kal₂-la-ti]m^{*ki}*
r. 4 *u₂-lu-ma a-[na šu-b]a-at-^dEN.LIL₂^{ki}*
r. 5 *šu-re-eš-š[^ri^ˀ-n]a-ti-^rma^ˀ*
r. 6 *i-na e₂-ka lu-u₂ wa-aš-[b]a[?]*
r. 7 *na-ru-tam li-ša-ḫi-zu-ši-n[a[?]-ti]*
r. 8 *[u]₃ a-na U₄-um t[a]-a[l-la-ka]m*

o. 1-4 Say to Yasm[aḫ-Addu], thus (speaks) Šamšī-Addu, your father: o. 5-6 May Lâ’ûm listen to this tablet of mine before your presence! o. 7-8 (Concerning) the young women whom I gave to Yaḫdun-Lîm, o. 9 these young women have (already) become adults, o. 10-12 [an]d [they (masc.) said to m]e in Sagaratim [about them] (fem.) in this [way]: “they are nubile!”

¹²²¹ See LAPO 16, p. 91–92 for this matter.

¹²²² See FM 9, p. 32, 42–43 for reasons.

¹²²³ Edition dependent upon Archibab T4484 with some corrections derived from our inspection of the original copy (available also on CDLI P254265).

¹²²⁴ CDLI P254265 has “t,up-pi an-ni-im”, but we see the sign BI (= pi₂), not PI (= pi). Moreover, its “an-ni-im” ignores the contraction in Mari of *anniam* by *annêm* (accusative singular of *annûm*, “this”).

o. 13-r. 2 [...and no]w r. 3-5 carry t[he]m [to Ekallātu]m or t[o Šub]at-Ellil and r. 6 may they li[v]e in your house r. 7 (and) may they teach th[em (fem.)] music! r. 8 [an]d, for the day yo[u will] c[ome to] me [...]

The term *nārūtum* has normally¹²²⁵ been translated here as “music”¹²²⁶ or something similar¹²²⁷. We tend to think that this makes sense in this context. Certainly, those women (possibly instructed by the *nargallum* Rīšīya¹²²⁸) could be destined to join one of the harem ensembles¹²²⁹ where they could play the *šebītum*¹²³⁰, the *tigû* drum¹²³¹ and/or to sing as *zammertum*¹²³² or other types of singers¹²³³. In this way, *nārūtum* as a reference

¹²²⁵ Except Oppenheim, 1952: 134 (“art of singing”); CAD N1, p. 382 (“the musician’s art”).

¹²²⁶ ARM 1, p. 127 (“la musique”).

¹²²⁷ LAPO 16, p. 91 (“l’art de la musique”; followed by FM 9, p. 42 and Archibab T4484). Stol, 2016: 360 talks about “music lessons”.

¹²²⁸ FM 9, p. 43 in light of FM 9 17 [A.2806] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 9’-20’ (Archibab T4274).

¹²²⁹ See FM 9, p. 13-14, 31-48 for reference about this aspect in general.

¹²³⁰ FM 9 38 [A.78] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), bo. e. 3 (Archibab T6596) and FM 9 41 [M. 14663] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), r. 1 (Archibab T6599). In the translations of these texts (see their editions on Archibab for reference), *šebītum* is defined as a lyre (see also FM 9, p. 330, where it is defined as “une petite lyre”). However, this term might be a variation of the *sa3-bi-tum/sabītum* (as it is defined in CAD S, p. 4 and Š2, p. 251) according to the Middle Babylonian lexical text Emar 6/2, p. 508-515 and 730 [Msk 7526 + 74209a], r. ii 6-7 (DCCLT). In light of this possibility, *sabītum/šebītum* should be considered an instrument coming from Sabum (probably the modern Baneh; see Liverani, 1992: 54 and Stol, 2006-2008: 480). Since that settlement has given no iconography with musical instruments as of yet, we cannot know what instruments were typical from there. In any case, we should pay attention to the text ARM 18 9 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 8 (Archibab T8799). In that text, a *sabītum/šebītum* should be returned to the king contained into a red leather bag(?) (KUŠ.HI.A *ša-ar-pu-tim*) together with some bows (*qaštum*). The most similar instrument to a bow is a harp. Therefore, we would identify the *sabītum/šebītum* with a small harp.

¹²³¹ The identification of the *tigûm* as a lyre in FM 9, p. 13 comes probably from Krispijn, 1990: 3-4, identification already dismissed in this study. In addition, concerning *Takil-ilissu 2* [E4.11.2.2], 52 (FM 9, p. 13 n. 37, originally in Frayne, 1990: 674), the idea of 200 lyre players is very difficult to imagine because of the amount of wood and strings required for that, even when the production of the strings was abundant in Mari (see FM 9 23 [A.4336] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), l. e. 7-8 (Archibab T6581) for reference). On the other hand, the term *hubûrum* (“noise”) in *Takil-ilissu 1* [E4.11.2], 54 fits better with 200 drummers.

¹²³² FM 9 17 [A.2806] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 18’ (Archibab T4274).

¹²³³ See FM 9, p. 14 n. 45 for reference. We should be careful with this argumentation. Certainly, at least from our knowledge, *šērum* (“song” in CAD Š2, p. 335 and not “to sing” as suggested in FM 9, p. 14 n. 45) is only attested in FM 3 2 [A.3165], r. i 12 (FM 3, p. 55). In addition, we have already discussed some evidence for reading *ser3* instead of *šir3/šer3* by the Old Babylonian Period. In any case, *šērum* might be considered a forerunner to the reading of *ser3* as *šir3/šer3* from Middle Babylonian times onward as we saw in the introduction of this PhD Dissertation.

to a general musical training (and not to a more focused training such as that of the *nārtum*) may be correct here.

5.2.2.2. ARM 5 73 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

Our next excerpt concerns Nanna-manšum¹²³⁴, a musician who was supposed to receive a house from the king. However, some people complained about that since this musician moved to Mari without the permission of the *nargallum*. “His” house was finally purchased by someone. In any case, Nanna-manšum still seems to have worked in Mari during the Zimrī-Līm’s reign. However, he would be paid for his (musical (?)) actions, but not for his status as a public servant as with other musicians¹²³⁵. Here is our excerpt:

Text 45. ARM 5 73 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²³⁶

r. 2' [... š]u-ub-ši
 r. 3' [m^dNA]NNA-^rMA.AN.ŠUM₂^{r.1237} er-se-^rem^r-ma
 r. 4' [aš-šum¹²³⁸ na]-^rru^r-tam dam-^rqi₂-iš^r aḥ-zu
 r. 5' [it]-ti be-li₂-ia uš-ta-^rme^r-er-šu-^rma^r
 r. 6' ^rbe^r-li₂ E₂-tam na-^rda-nam^r u₂-ša-^rhi^r-iz-ma
 r. 7' u₂-ul ^rid^r-di-nu-^ršu^r

^{r.2'} [... ma]ke it is [...]^{r.3'} [Na]nna-Manšum is well-trained, and ^{r.4'} [since] he has learned well [mu]sic,
^{r.5'} I made that he know my lord, and ^{r.6'} my lord ordered the concession of a house (for him), although
^{r.7'} they have (finally) not given it (to him).

¹²³⁴ The spelling “Nanna-mansum” starts from an outdated reading of SUM as **sum** for “to give”. We read nowadays that Sumerian verb as **šum₂**, a reading which has its justification in *Proto-Ea*, 275 (DCCLT Q000055). There, one of the readings of SUM is spelled **šu-um** (for **sum**, we should have **su/su₂-um**).

¹²³⁵ FM 9, p. 259; Ziegler, 2013: 57.

¹²³⁶ Edition dependent upon Archibab T8866 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy (= TCL 26 65–67) and the photo of that tablet available on Archibab T8866 through PSL-DIGIBARCHI.

¹²³⁷ ARM 5 78 has “[s]è”. However, as LAPO 17, p. 554 says, this personal name is based on a sentence “Nanna has given it to me”. This translation is, by the way, more correct than the “Le-Dieu-Lune-m’a-fait-un-present” of LAPO 17, p. 554. Certainly, there is no term in the sentence for “present”. The term **se₃** of ARM is a writing of **sa₂** (“to be equal”), but we should have another sentence for justifying its presence.

¹²³⁸ FM 9 259 n. 88 and Archibab T8866 have *u₃* because they have *ki-ma*^{md} in the previous line. However, concerning line r. 3', the scribe might have had problems writing four signs in that space of the tablet. Concerning r. 4', a coordinative conjunction *u* might be redundant with the enclitic conjunction *-ma* at the end of the previous line. It is important to state that *aššum* would act here as a particle introducing a subordinate sentence with *aḥzu* (Stative G of *aḥāzum* (here, “to learn”) + Subordinate Particle *-u*: **aḥiz* + *u* = *aḥzu*). Therefore, it is not as a preposition going with *nārūtam*. Otherwise, we would find *nārūtīm*.

The term *nārūtum* has been normally¹²³⁹ translated here as “musical arts”¹²⁴⁰, a variant of “music”. Perhaps that is the most suitable translation for *nārūtum* in this context. Certainly, the content of the tablet containing this term is not always certain as we have previously seen in our edition. Moreover, it is difficult to distinguish this Nanna-manšum from other people in Mari with that same name but working as scribes¹²⁴¹, merchants¹²⁴² or with the *šābum* workers¹²⁴³. Furthermore, the single (possible) alternative reference to Nanna-manšum as musician¹²⁴⁴ says only that he received a garment.

5.2.2.3. FM 9 13 [M.6851] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

In this letter, Šamšī-Addu tries to convince to his son Yasmaḥ-Addu that the *nārum* Rīšīya cannot be the new *nargallum* of Mari due to his apparent lack of (supposed) basic musical qualities. Instead of him, Šamšī-Addu suggests the appointment of Gumul-Dagān in that position together with the assistance of Ilšu-Ibbīšu:

Text 46. FM 9 13 [M.6851] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁴⁵

- o. 1 *a-na ia-as₂-ma-a[h^dIŠKUR]*
o. 2 *ʿqi₂ʿ-bi₂-ʿmaʿ*
o. 3 *[u]m-ʿmaʿ^dUTU-ši-^dIŠKUR*
o. 4 *[a-bu]-ka-a-ma*
o. 5 *[^l]ri-ši-ia NAR*
o. 6 *[ša]ʿbaʿ-ʿad-de-e ku-ul-la-ʿamʿ*
o. 7 *[l]a i-le-lu-ʿu₂ʿ*
o. 8 *a-na NAR.GAL-tim i-na ʿmaʿ-ri^{ki}*
o. 9 *ta-aš-ku-ʿunʿ-š_u-ma*
o. 10 *NAR-tum i-na ma-ri^{ki} uḫ-ta-li-iq*
o. 11 *ma-a gu-mu-ul-^dda-gan-ma*
o. 12 *a-na aḫ-ḫi-š_u LU₂ ma-ra-yi^{ki}*
o. 13 *a-na ʿNARʿ.GAL-tim š_u-ku-unʿ-š_u*
o. 14 *u₃ DIDIR-š_u-ʿibʿ-[bi-š_u]*
r. 1 *[ša] NAR.GAL-tam l[a i-le-u₂]*
r. 2 *ʿš_u-kuʿ-un-[š_u-um]*

¹²³⁹ ARM 5 73 (“le [ch]ant”).

¹²⁴⁰ LAPO 17, p. 553 (“art musical”, followed by FM 9, p. 259; Ziegler, 2013: 57; Archibab T8866).

¹²⁴¹ FM 16 41 [ARM 24 6 + M.6473 + M.12387] (Zimrī-Līm 00-07-10), o. i 28 (Archibab T19384).

¹²⁴² FM 3 8 [ARM 22/1 205] (Zimrī-Līm 05-00-00), o. iʿ 9ʿ-10ʿ (Archibab T11218).

¹²⁴³ FM 16 12 [A.309] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), r. 1–2 (Archibab T22384). This text has been recently published, therefore, it could not be used at the time of the publication of FM 9.

¹²⁴⁴ ARM 23 375 (Zimrī-Līm 13-01-10 = Zimrī-Līm 8), 15 (ARM 23, p. 297).

¹²⁴⁵ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6572 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo available on that site through Archipix.

^{o.2} Say ^{o.1} to Yasma[h-Addu], ^{o.3} [t]hus (speaks) Šamšī-Addu, ^{o.4} your [father]: ^{o.5} (I speak to you about) the *nārum* Rīšīya, ^{o.7} [who] can[n]ot ^{o.6} return the [...].^{o.9} You have installed him¹²⁴⁶ ^{o.8} in the position of *nargallum* in Mari, and ^{o.10} (in this way) the music has been destroyed in Mari!

^{o.11-13} What? Gumul-Dagān, install him into the position of *nargallum* for his Mariote brothers, ^{o.14-r.2} and (concerning) Ilšu-Ib[bīšu, who is] (actually) i[n]appropriate] (for) the condition of *nargallum*, place (him) [under his authority]!

The term *nārūtum* has been normally translated in this context as “music”¹²⁴⁷. That makes sense since we do not deal here with a normal *nārum*, but with the *nargallum*, the chief musician. In fact, this letter is the only text, as far as we know, containing the term *nargallūtum* (“office of *nargallum*”)¹²⁴⁸. That term is without equivalent by the moment (as far as we know) in Sumerian (where we would expect something like ***nam-nar-gal**). In addition, it should not be confused with the *nargallutu* (“female chief musician”) from Neo-Assyrian times¹²⁴⁹. Therefore, for Šamšī-Addu, music (*nārūtum*) had been destroyed (*uḫtalliq*) in Mari because of the appointment for the “*nargallum*-ship” of Rīšīya, defined

¹²⁴⁶ Our translation tries to justify the presence of the *taškunšuma* with its Accusative 3SGM -šū (“him” in our translation), which referred to a direct object previously stated in the sentence.

¹²⁴⁷ Durand, 1991: 36 (“la musique”); Ziegler, 2006a: 347 (“die Musik”); FM 9, p. 100 (“La musique”; followed by Ziegler, 2013: 50; Archibab T6572); Ziegler, 2011: 291 (“music”). Sasson, 2012: 533 translates that term as “music”. However, his translation of the entire line (“in the death of music at Mari”) omits the meaning of the 3SG.M of the Dt stem of *ḫalāqu(m) uḫtalliq* (“it has been destroyed”).

¹²⁴⁸ The *nārūtum* of this text might have been another reference to *nargallūtum* since its spelling (NAR-tum = *nārūtum*) might be understood as NAR.<GAL>-tum (*nargallūtum*). That might give more coherence to the text, which mainly referred to the *nargallum*. In any case, the spelling NAR-tum for *nārūtum* is already contained in our aforementioned Text 42 = ARM 1 78 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 4. In addition, the signs LUL (= NAR) and TUM (= tum) seem to be connected in the writing of our Text 46 through the prolongation of the straight wedges of the sign LUL. Therefore, we cannot suppose any empty space in the tablet for a hypothetical sign GAL (= GAL).

¹²⁴⁹ Only known with Sumerograms: SAA 7 24 [K. 1473 + 1944a + 10447], o. 20 (^{mmuus}NAR.GAL) and SAA 20 9 [Ist. A 125 + 181], r. iii 22' (^{mmuus}NAR3.GAL2). The usual transcription of this term is *nargallutu* (Teppo, 2007: 401–402, 411; Shehata, 2009: 22 n. 88; Pruzsinszky, 2010a: 101 n. 19; Çavuşoglu, Işik, and Göcke, 2014: 238; Groß, 2014: 223, 228, 231, 244; Joannès, 2016: 32; Álvarez Mon, 2017: 16; Pruzsinszky, 2018b: 95; Svärd, 2018: 118). However, we prefer to follow those having transcribed *nargallatu* (CDA, p. 242; Maul, 2000: 399; Stol, 2015: 702). Certainly, in ^{mmuus}NAR3.GAL2, the GAL2 can be read as GALA7, being the new reading ^{mmuus}NAR3.GALA7 closer to *nargallatu* than to *nargallutu*. We also avoid confusions with *nargallūtu(m)* in this way.

here as unable (*lā ilelû*)¹²⁵⁰ to hold (back) (*kullâm*) someone/something written in the text as *ba-ad-de-e*.

Jean-Marie Durand¹²⁵¹ connected *ba-ad-de-e* with *baddum* and proposed its definition as “*individu/isolé*” through a comparison with the Hebrew root $\sqrt{\text{BDD}}$. From that point, Nele Ziegler¹²⁵² defined that term as “solistes”. That identification makes sense with the plural form of this word. Otherwise, we would have *ba-ad-de-em*. However, Michael P. Streck has remarked¹²⁵³ that the repetition of the vowel “e” suggests the presence of a long vowel in this word which, therefore, should be normalized as *baddê*, and not *baddê* as in the case of a word of the type *baddum*. Therefore, we would have a root $\sqrt{\text{BD}^?}$ ¹²⁵⁴ (not $\sqrt{\text{BDD}}$) and a different meaning for this word. Streck defined *baddûm* as “a musical instrument(?)” only, since the context rather speaks in that case for an instrument.

We are dealing with a delicate matter, since the verb *kullum* modifying this *baddum* / *baddûm* may mean “to control” / “hold back” as Durand¹²⁵⁵ or Ziegler¹²⁵⁶ translated, a translation fitting with an identification of this term as “soloists”. However, that verb also means “to hold something physically” or “to handle” it¹²⁵⁷ as Michael P. Streck translated¹²⁵⁸, and it may fit, therefore, with *baddum/baddûm* as an instrument.

Dominique Charpin has tried to refute Streck’s identification saying that, in such a case, we would have a musical *hapax*, while we have many musical terms in the texts of Mari¹²⁵⁹. However, his reply is irrelevant since *baddûm* would not be the first musical *hapax* in Akkadian¹²⁶⁰. On the other hand, Streck’s identification makes sense with an

¹²⁵⁰ The normalization “*ile’û*” (eSAD B; Streck, 2018: 3) ignores LU (= *lu*) in the tablet. We would be before an R-Stem of *le’û(m)* (“to be able”) for Durand, 1993: 61 (see Groneberg, 1989: 29 for details).

¹²⁵¹ Durand, 1991: 36.

¹²⁵² FM 9, p. 100.

¹²⁵³ eSAD B; Streck, 2018: 3; Streck’s personal communication). See also Charpin, 2018: 207.

¹²⁵⁴ The Semitic root $\sqrt{\text{BD}^?}$ has the meaning “to start” in languages like Arabic (بَدَأَ, [*badaʿa*]) (Bar-Moshe, 2016: 137, 140). However, we are afraid that a similar meaning might not fit in this context.

¹²⁵⁵ Durand, 1991: 36 (“absolument incapable de diriger des *baddê*”).

¹²⁵⁶ FM 9, p. 100 (“[qui] est absolument incapable de tenir des « solistes »”).

¹²⁵⁷ CAD K, p. 508.

¹²⁵⁸ eSAD B and Streck, 2018: 3 (“[who] is not able to hold *b.s*”).

¹²⁵⁹ Charpin, 2018: 207.

¹²⁶⁰ Concerning Old Babylonian times, the term *zennum* was originally considered a *hapax* (Kilmer and Civil, 1986: 95). However, later it was identified with a term referring to tuning (Kilmer and Tinney, 1996:

important aspect. We know Rîšīya mainly as a chief musician. However, in this text he is still a mere *nārum* as we know from line o. 5. Therefore, he could not yet control under his authority any group of musicians like those “soloists” of Nele Ziegeler. However, he could, quite to the contrary, hold or use a musical instrument, or a group of musical instruments. This last option would fit with *baddê*, plural form of *baddûm*.

5.2.2.4. FM 9 26 [M.14611] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

The following excerpt for consideration here belongs to a letter where Rîšīya asks Šamšī-Addu, among others, about his musical labour in general and, more concretely, about some types of musicians:

Text 47. FM 9 26 [M.14611] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁶¹

- r. 1 [... a-na LU₂.MEŠ hu]-^rup^r-pi₂-ia [...[?]
r. 2 [u₃ a-na] iḫ-^rzi^r-{LUL[?]}-im
r. 3 [ša na-ru-ti]-^rim^r a-ḫi la na-de-^re^r-[k]u-u₂
r. 4 [i-na ka-ša]-^rdi^r-[š]u
r. 5 [mi-im]-^rma^r ša uš-ta-a[š-bi-t]u₂-^ru₂^r
r. 6 [be-li₂ im-ma]-^rar^r-ma^r i^r-ḫa-a[d-du]
r. 7 [u₃ ki-ma MUNUS.NAR].^rTUR.MEŠ^r i-na [ši-ip-ri-ši-n]a
r. 8 [er-se-e be]-li₂ i-^rde^r-[...-e]
r. 9 [U₄-um ḫup-p]a₂-am an-ne₂-em [a-na be-li₂-i]a
r. 10 u[š-t]a^r-[b]i-[lam]
r. 11 U₄-um^r e^r-se-^rsi^r-[im-ma]
r. 12 [ma]-za-za-am ra-^rbe₂-em^r a[š₂-ta-ka-an-ma]
r. 13 [i]t-ta-še₂ š[i-pi₂-ir-ši-na]
lo. e. 1 ka-ši₂-^rir^r b[e-li₂ lu-u₂ i-de]

r. 1-3 [I] am not careless [about my hu]ppûm acrobats [and about] the learning [of musi]c!^{r.4} (Certainly) [once he arri]ves,^{r.5-6} [my lord will see] [everyth]ing that I [provided] (for these two matters) and he will rej[oice].^{r.7-8} [In addition], he will know [if] the young [*nārtu*]m are well-trained in [the]ir [art].

r. 9-10 [The day] that I made this [tabl]et be sent [to m]y [lord],^{r.11-12} is (the same) day of the eššēšum festival. I [have provided] (for this festival) a big [ma]zzâzum ensemble (with these females),
r. 13-Lo. e. 1 (and) [they] have already gone out (to the place of this festival). May the *kāširum* official [of m]y [lord know (those things)]!

The first thing to keep in mind is the highly fragmentary preservation state of the whole tablet and of this excerpt in particular. As a consequence, our term *nārūtum* is

53–54). For later times, see *Maqlû*, VII 155 (Abusch, 2015: 188) for a reference to the *ni'u* instrument (of unknown identification; Meier, 1966: 79).

¹²⁶¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6584 with corrections coming from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

almost a restoration here and, therefore, any conclusion about this excerpt is hypothetical. Having said that, *nārūtum* (whose context recalls our Text 39¹²⁶²) has been translated as “musical teaching” (together with *iḥzum*, “learning”)¹²⁶³.

This translation makes sense in light of the comparison between that musical teaching and something¹²⁶⁴ about the *ḥuppûm*. Nevertheless, despite their subordination to the *nargallum* as any other musicians in Mari, these *ḥuppûm* were not musicians. Far from that, they were acrobatic dancers using some sort of knives¹²⁶⁵ as those usually recognized on the clay plaque AO 12443¹²⁶⁶. In this sense, their profession was not entirely musical, but it was also related to (theatrical) fighting¹²⁶⁷. Moreover, music and dance¹²⁶⁸ were not always so closely related in Mesopotamia (at least for Old Babylonian times¹²⁶⁹) as we might believe from our Western perspective. An example of that is the hymn *Šulgi B*. In that text, there is nothing about dance in the section devoted to music analysed in our previous chapter. Far from that, the term for “dance” (**gu4-ud** or **gud2**, which also means “to jump”) is mentioned in an excerpt dealing with the king’s strength¹²⁷⁰.

In this sense, *nārūtum* is not compared here with another (and, we suppose, subordinate) musical aspect. It is, however, compared but with a different reality, the one of the *ḥuppûm* acrobat dancers. In this sense, it is worthwhile to see *nārūtum* as a reference to the music in a broad sense, even if our excerpt mentions (in restoration) a *nārtum*.

¹²⁶² Certainly, while Išmē-Dagān gave (**šum2**) his arm (**a2**) to the music (**nam-nar**), Rišīya literally says that he is not “abandoned” (G Stative 1sgc from *nadû(m)*) concerning his “arm” (*aḥu(m)*).

¹²⁶³ FM 9, p. 134 (“l’enseignement [*de la musique*]”, followed by Archibab T6584).

¹²⁶⁴ Previous editions have restored only [... *a-na LU2.MEŠ [ḥu]-^rup³-pi2-ia ...?*] and we believe that they have a point in this sense. However, that restitution might have been always more complex in light of the expression *iḥzim nārūtum* of this excerpt.

¹²⁶⁵ FM 9, p. 261–263; Shehata, 2009: 49–51 and Ziegler, 2013: 63–65.

¹²⁶⁶ See FM 9, p. 263 for a photograph of the said plaque.

¹²⁶⁷ FM 9, p. 264. Music and wrestling are also connected in the Old Babylonian clay plaque BM 91906 (see Rašīd, 1984: 78 for illustration and comments). For acrobat dancers and wrestlers in the Old Babylonian Period, see also Feliu and Millet, 2008: 97.

¹²⁶⁸ For an overview of dance in Mesopotamia across the times, see Gabbay, 2003 and Ambos, 2012 (texts) and Collon, 2003 and Seidl, 2012 (iconography).

¹²⁶⁹ Certainly, by the 1st Millennium, several *riqdū* (“dances”, a term from Neo-Assyrian times and coming from *raqādu(m)*, “to dance”) (CAD R, p. 166, 367) are mentioned in the ritual texts (Gabbay, 2007: 122, 130 for evidence). That is, at that time, there was in Mesopotamia a specific term for “dance”. That contrast with the situation in the Old Babylonian Mesopotamia.

¹²⁷⁰ *Šulgi B*, 128 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

5.2.2.5. FM 9 27 [M.13050] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

In this letter, Rîšīya complains to King Šamšī-Addu about Muḥaddum, who accuses the *nargallum* of having taught immoral/incorrect things to his sons:

Text 48. FM 9 27 [M.13050] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁷¹

- o. 1 [a-na] ʿbe ʿli₂-ia
o. 2 [qi₂]-bi₂-ʿma ʿ
o. 3 ʿum-ma ʿri-ši-ia
o. 4 IR₃-ka-a-ma
o. 5 ʿmu-ḥa-ʿad ʿdu-um ma-ri-šu
o. 6 id-de₄-ʿem ʿma
o. 7 na-ru-ta-ʿam ʿu₂-ša-ḥi-iz
o. 8 ʿda ʿma-am i-na ʿpu ʿur-si-tim
o. 9 ʿak ʿšu₂-ur
o. 10 [u₃] ʿu₂-ra-ʿbi ʿšu-nu-ti
o. 11 [i]-ʿna-an-na ʿil-[i-ka]m-ma
o. 12 [DIDIR-lam l]a-ma-su₂ ʿib ʿbi
Lo. e. 1 [DIDIR-tam na-ši₂-r]a-su₂ ib-ʿbi ʿ
Lo. e. 2 [iṭ-ṭe₄-ḥ]e-em ʿi ʿna
Lo. e. 3 [ša-ma-al-l]i la-ma-ʿad ʿ
r. 1 ʿa ʿwa-ʿtim bi ʿša-tim ʿid ʿbu-ba-am
r. 2 um-ma a-ʿna-ku ʿma ʿit-ti ʿ
r. 3 ma-ʿri-ka še₂-eḥ ʿri-im
r. 4 na-ʿru ʿta-am e-ʿpu-uš₂ ʿ
r. 5 ʿum ʿma šu-ma it-ʿti ʿka-a-ʿma ʿ
r. 6 e-pu-uš₂ be-ʿli₂ ʿḥu-ša-ʿba ʿa[m]
r. 7 i-na pa-ni ma-ka-al-ʿtim ʿ
r. 8 ʿip ʿri-ik
r. 9 i-da-bu-ba-am an-ne₂-ʿtim ʿ

o. 2 [S]ay o. 1 [to] my lord, o. 3 thus (speaks) Rîšīya, o. 4 your servant. o. 5-6 Muḥaddum has abandoned to me his sons, and o. 7 I taught music to them: o. 9 “I organized o. 8 the blood in the veins” o. 10 [and] I made them grow! o. 11 [Ho]wever, he ca[me to] me, o. 12 he invoked his p[ersonal god], Lo. e. 1 he invoked his p[rotective goddess], Lo. e. 2-r. 1 [he approached] to me, (and) he accused me of having instilled bad things into [the apprentices]. r. 2-4 (I said to him) “I performed music with your son!” r. 5-8 (and) he (answered to me) “Make it with yourself! My lord has rejected a branch of *ḥuṣabu*[m] firewood in front of a *makaltum* wooden dish”. r. 9 He says it to me!

There are two references to *nārūtum* in this letter. In the first (o. 7), *nārūtum* referred to the content of the teaching provided by Rîšīya to Muḥaddum’s sons. This educational process is described in mythological terms with the expression *dāmam ina pursītīm akšur*

¹²⁷¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6585 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

(“I organized the blood in the veins”) of lines o. 8–9¹²⁷². The term *nārūtum* has been translated here as “art of music”¹²⁷³ or just “music”¹²⁷⁴, which makes sense keeping in mind that, although Rîšīya is known as *nārum* in our Text 13¹²⁷⁵, he had to act at the time of our Text 48 already as a *nargallum*, and not as *nārum*. In this sense, the musical contents that he could teach to Muḥaddum’s sons would be probably more generic than those of the profession of the *nārum*.

The musical teaching provided by Rîšīya had to be annoying to Muḥaddum for some reason¹²⁷⁶. In any case, Rîšīya had to offer a complete musical education to Muḥaddum’s sons including some musical performances¹²⁷⁷. It is in that context that we find our second allusion to *nārūtum* in our Text 48. The term *nārūtum* (modified here by the verb *epēšum*) has been translated as “music”¹²⁷⁸, something which makes sense with the expression *nigūta epēšu* (“to perform (joyful) music”) found in 1st-millennium texts applied to

¹²⁷² See Ziegler, 2005 (with additional comments in FM 9, p. 138 and Ziegler, 2013: 55) for a comparison with the *dāmī luḫsurma ešmēta lušabšīma* (“may I gather the blood and create a skeleton!”) from *Enūma Eliš*, VI, 5 (Lambert, 2013: 110). Unfortunately, this parallel has not been noted in the most recent editions of *Enūma Eliš* (for instance Tallon, 2005 or Lambert, 2013). We might be dealing with a different conception of musical teaching regarding our southern Mesopotamian texts. Keep in mind our Texts 33 (= *Šulgi B*, 154) or 39 (= *Išmē-Dagān A + V*, 367) besides “*Monkey*” to his mother, 6 (= Kleinerman, 2011: 158 and 278). In those texts, the student makes efforts in the musical learning without many references to his master (see also our Texts 12 and 28 for reference). The same happens in the myths. In addition to our Texts 24 and 27, see the text Kramer, 1981: 2–6 [BM 29616], o. 21–23 (Shehata, 2009: 67) and *Inanna’s Descent*, 223 (Attinger, 2019c: 45. In them, the creation of musical figures is not a big problem for the deities. We find the opposite in our Text 48. It is Rîšīya, the master, who makes the efforts.

¹²⁷³ Ziegler, 2005: 5 (“art de la musique”; followed by FM 9, p. 136; Démare-Lafont, 2011: 15 and Archibab T6585).

¹²⁷⁴ Ziegler, 2010: 124 (“music”).

¹²⁷⁵ FM 9 13 [M.6851] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 5. See our Text 45 for edition.

¹²⁷⁶ The reason is unclear because *bištu(m)* may describe something of bad quality, but also something morally evil (CAD B, p. 270–271). In addition, as far as we know, most of our references to this word come from Middle Assyrian/Babylonian Period onward. Therefore, we might have here one of our earliest references to *bištu(m)*. Both senses of this word are interesting here. However, we wanted to pay attention to the meaning “bad quality”, since the musical abilities of Rîšīya were already questioned in our Text 46. Muḥaddum might have questioned Rîšīya’s abilities in order to have his children returned to him. Certainly, once a child was abandoned, it was difficult to have him return to his parents (Ziegler, 2010: 124).

¹²⁷⁷ That makes sense with FM 9 51 [A.3115] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 2–5 (Archibab T6609), where the activity of the *mumum* conservatory is described as continuous.

¹²⁷⁸ FM 9, p. 136 (“la musique”; followed by Archibab T6585).

musicians¹²⁷⁹ and other people¹²⁸⁰. In this way, *nārūtum* might have acquired in the Mari texts a similar connotation to our word “music” as something “playable”.

5.2.2.6. FM 9 30 [M.7321] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

We find another reference to *nārūtam epēšum* as “to perform/make music” in this letter of an unknown author. Its central part deals with a musician whose name is lost due to the preservation state of the tablet:

Text 49. FM 9 30 [M.7321] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁸¹

o. 5 [... o] *u*₃ DUG *na-aš-pa-^rak* I₃ *s[i]-i[r-di-im]*
o. 6 [*a*]-*na ma-ši-im* *it^r-ta-na-^rad^r-di-i[n]*
o. 7 *u*₃ *na^r-ru-tam a-na* *la^r-i-im i-pe₂-^reš^r*
Lo. e. 1 *ma-^rti^r-ma* {HA} *ma-ḥa-ar* *be-li₂-ia^r*
Lo. e. 2 *i-na* {SIZKUR} *ni^r-qi₂-im* {x}
Lo. e. 3 *u*₂ *-ul iz-zⁱ1282-iz*
r. 1 *u*₃ *i-na^r-ia-^rd^r* UTU *lu²ra-pi₂-^rqa-yu^{ki}*
r. 2 *i-ip-pe₂-eš^r*

^{o.5} [...] and he gives regularly to Mašim ^{o.6} one pot with o[ll]i[ve] oil. ^{o.7} In addition, he performs music for Lâ’ûm, ^{Lo. e. 3} (but) he never stands ^{Lo. e. 1} before my lord ^{Lo. e. 2} during the (execution of the) prayers. ^{r. 1} Nevertheless, it is Inaya-Šamaš, from Rapiqûm, ^{r. 2} who does.

Line o. 7 of this text has been previously translated as “and he acts as musician in Lâ’ûm”¹²⁸³. However, for that translation, we should have *ina* (“in”, “into”, “from”, “with”) instead of *ana* (“to”, “for”, “in order to”)¹²⁸⁴. Moreover, we should find the place determinative ^{ki} after *la^r-i-im* in order to classify it as a place name. In fact, this supposed place name does not appear in the list of place names of the study where this text was published¹²⁸⁵. In addition, Lâ’ûm was the name of the king of Samānum and the land of

¹²⁷⁹ *Aššurbānīpal* 3, vi 46–47 (RINAP 5 Q003702); *Aššurbānīpal* 4, vi 48–49 (RINAP 5 Q003703), *Aššurbānīpal* 6, vii 53 (RINAP 5 Q003705); *Aššurbānīpal* 7, vi 11” –12” (RINAP 5 Q003706). Here, in these texts, the *nāru* musicians are performing joyful music when entering into Nineveh.

¹²⁸⁰ *Azzū’s Epic* (Standard Babylonian Version), III 29 (CAMS Q002771), and perhaps *Sēnnaḫērib* 37, r. 11’ (RINAP Q003511) and *Aššarḫaddon* 33, lo. e. 1 (RINAP Q003262).

¹²⁸¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6588 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹²⁸² On the contrary to Archibab T6588, we do not see a superfluous sign ZI here.

¹²⁸³ FM 9, p. 142 (“il sert de musicien à La’um”, followed by Archibab T6568).

¹²⁸⁴ CAD A2, p. 100 and CAD I-J, p. 141–142.

¹²⁸⁵ FM 9, p. 329. It neither appears in the database of HIGEOMES (see Archibab for access).

Uprabum according to the Yaḥdun-Līm's foundation inscription¹²⁸⁶. We should also keep in mind that other personal names in this text (as Inaya-Šamaš) do not have *Personenkeil*. Therefore, this identification of Lâ'ûm as the name of an individual (of course different from the one of the Yaḥdun-Līm's inscription¹²⁸⁷) might be suitable in this context.

Therefore, since Lâ'ûm is a personal name, *u nārūtam ana lâ'im īpeš* (‘*u₃ na[˘]-ru-tam a-na[˘] la[˘]-i-im i-pe₂-eš*’) should be translated as “and he makes music for Lâ'ûm”.

5.2.2.7. FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

The following excerpt for study is a letter addressed to King Šamšī-Addu and written by Ilišu-ibbīšu, a musical instructor under the authority of the *nargallum* Rîšīya. This musical instructor will go to Mari and ask Šamaš-magir (an official of Yasmaḥ-Addu (?)¹²⁸⁸) to hurry up with the construction of several musical instruments. This is the best preserved part of this letter, and we are going to analyse it now:

Text 50. FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁸⁹

- o. 1 ‘*a[˘]-na be-li₂-ia qi₂-bi₂-ma[˘]*
o. 2 ‘*um[˘]-ma DIDIR-šu-i-bi-šu IR₃-ka-a-[˘]ma[˘]*
o. 3 [*be-li₂*] ‘*ki[˘]-a-am u₂-wa-i-ra-an-ni*
o. 4 [*um-m*]a-‘*a-mi[˘] at-la-ak a-na ma-r[^ki*
o. 5 [*a-na š*]i-‘*pi₂-ir na-ru-tim[˘] u₃[˘] [si₂-id-di]*
o. 6 [*šu-ḥ*]u-zi-im a-aḥ-‘*ka la ta[˘]-n[a-ad-di]*
o. 7 [*i-na-a*]n-‘*na[˘] a-na ma-ri[˘] al[˘]-l[i-kam-ma]*
o. 8 [*aš-šum*] š*i-pi₂-ir[˘] [si₂-id-di]*
o. 9 [*a-na* ^d]UTU-ma-‘*gir[˘] aq-bi-[˘]ma[˘]*
o. 10 [*um-ma a*]-‘*na[˘]-ku-[˘]ma[˘] [si₂-id-di]*
o. 11 [*li-id-di-n*]u-nim-‘*ma[˘] u₃ š*i-pi₂-ir [i₂-id-di]**
o. 12 [*ki-ma*] š*a be-[˘]li₂ u₂-wa-i-la[˘]-an-[ni]*
o. 13 [*a-na*] pa-ni ‘*be[˘]-li₂-ia lu-u₂[˘] uš[˘]-t[a-aḥ-ba-at]*

¹²⁸⁶ Dossin, 1955: 4–11 [M. 2802], iii 4–5 (Matthews, 1977: 208). See Matthews, 1977: 208–210; Wossink, 2009: 128 and Burke, 2018: 94 for comments.

¹²⁸⁷ Certainly, that Lâ'ûm is one of the kings who decided to counteract the power of Yaḥdun-Līm at the beginning of his reign in Mari, which is before that of the Šamšī-Addu of our text.

¹²⁸⁸ Heimpel, 2003: 558. In any case, according to FM 9, p. 213, his exact professional career is still uncertain. Moreover, the new texts published after FM 9 (from southern Mesopotamia) do not furnish too much information about him. For these texts, see YOS 15 35 [University of Michigan 849–469] (Ḥammurāpi 31+-00-00), o. 5 (Archibab T6076) and YOS 15 44 [YBC 13339] (00-00-00), o. 10, r. 1 (own consultation of the copy of the tablet; see also Archibab T5602 and Veenhof, 2012 for comments).

¹²⁸⁹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6607 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

o. ¹ Say to my lord, o. ² thus (speaks) Ilšu-ibbīšu, your servant. o. ³ My [lord] has ordered of me the following: o. ⁴ “Go to Mar[i]! o. ⁵⁻⁶ [You] must not ne[gl]ect your effort [for] the [instr]uction of the [m]usic and (more concretely) [the *siddum* instruments]!

o. ⁷ I w[ent imme]diately to Mari (after that), [and] o. ⁹ I spoke [to] Šamaš-magir, o. ⁸ [about] the work of the *siddum* instruments. o. ¹⁰⁻¹² [Thus] I (spoke to him): “[May] they [give] me the *siddum* instruments]! Furthermore, [as] my lord ordered [me], o. ¹³ [I wish to start the work] with these *siddum* instruments [for] (the arrival) of my lord!”

In this excerpt, the term *nārūtum* has been understood as “art of music”¹²⁹⁰. This translation might be *a priori* strange because the musical terms (*nārūtum* and *siddum* perhaps designating a type of stringed instrument¹²⁹¹) seem to be compared here as is suggested by the use of *u₃* (“and”) placed between them. In this sense, *nārūtum* might refer the “office of the *nārum*”, while the use of the *siddum* (and their instrumentalists) would be another music specialization.

However, the text later deals more in depth with some concrete aspects of the *siddum* instruments. In this sense, it is possible that Ilšu-ibbīšu was saying that he was attentive to all the musical aspects (*nārūtum*) under his purview, but he was especially careful with the *siddum* instruments.

It is true that the letter seems to make reference later to several *nārum*¹²⁹², so *nārūtum* might designate the office of the *nārum*. Nevertheless, the context of that reference is highly fragmentary. In any case, that allusion seems to have been said by the king (in response to Ilšu-ibbīšu) and not by Ilšu-ibbīšu. Therefore, it is possible that the king was simply asking about that aspect (the *nārum* musicians) supervised by Ilšu-ibbīšu. In this sense, we would support the condition of *nārūtum* in this text as “music” in a broad sense, and not as “office of the *nārum*”. The use of the *siddum* instruments would be, in consequence, just a part of that “music”, and not a separate music specialization.

¹²⁹⁰ FM 9, p. 212 (“l’art de la musique”; followed by Archibab T6607).

¹²⁹¹ The identification of FM 9, p. 210 (followed by Dumbrill, 2014: 325) of the term *siddum* as a stringed instrument seems to make sense with our Standard Babylonian texts containing *sadādu* (“to make a raid”, “hold a thread (?)”). However, in our opinion, we should be careful with the chronological distance between these Standard Babylonian texts with *sadādu* and our Old Babylonian texts from Mari having this term *siddum*.

¹²⁹² FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamši-Addu 00-00-00), o. 18 (Archibab T6607).

5.2.2.8. FM 9 55 [A.905] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

This letter was written by Imgur-Šamaš, probably an instructor (*mušāḫizum*) whose main residence was in Šubat-Ellil, although he went occasionally to Mari for various activities. He had a certain familiarity with Yasmaḥ-Addu, the king to whom this letter is addressed. In our excerpt, Imgur-Šamaš had entrusted to the king two of his former students: Ilšu-Ibbīšu and Lipit-Ellil. Imgur-Šamaš was supposed, therefore, to have received some gifts from the king. However, that never happened:

Text 51. FM 9 55 [A.905] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹²⁹³

- o. 12 **P**DIDIR-š_u-ib-bi-š_u u₃ li-pi₂-it-^dEN.LIL₂⁷
o. 13 **LU**₂.TUR.MEŠ qa-ti-ia ša⁷na-ru-ta-am
o. 14 u₂-š⁷a⁷ḫi-zu-š_u-nu-ti ma-ḫa-ar be-li₂-ia
o. 15 uš-zi-is-su₂-nu-⁷ti⁷
o. 16 ma-ti-i-ma⁷ be-li₂⁷ [z]i-[ki]-⁷ir⁷ [š]u-⁷mi-ia⁷
o. 17 aš-šum **LU**₂.ME[Š ... šu-nu-t]i
o. 18 u₂-ul⁷ iḫ⁷-s[u₂-...-u]s
o. 19 u₂-⁷lu-ma⁷ be-l[i₂ da-ḫa-ti u₂-u]l i-ša-al

o. 12–15 I set before my lord to Ilšu-Ibbīšu and Lipit-Ellil, (two) young people to whom I taught music.

o. 16–18 (However) my lord has never considered the [r]e[p]utation of my [n]ame because of [thes]e (two) me[n],^{o. 19} or [my] lord is [n]ot worried [with my explanations].

The term *nārūtum* has been translated here as “art of music”¹²⁹⁴. We believe that a translation of this type is suitable in this context. Certainly, Lipit-Ellil, one of the students of Imgur-Šamaš mentioned in this letter, worked as a *nārum*¹²⁹⁵ using the *lē’um*¹²⁹⁶ instrument¹²⁹⁷. Ilšu-Ibbīšu, the other student of Imgur-Šamaš, is documented, among

¹²⁹³ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6613 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹²⁹⁴ FM 9, p. 226 (“l’art de la musique”; followed by Archibab T6613)

¹²⁹⁵ FM 9 36 [A.2521] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 10–16 (Archibab T6594) it is actually indirect evidence for his condition as *nārum*. The reason is that this musician and his family receive the house of another *nārum* called Akšaya.

¹²⁹⁶ FM 9 57 [ARM 1 63 + M.11322] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 5–8 (Archibab T4483).

¹²⁹⁷ The term *lē’um* has the meaning “board” in other contexts (see, for instance, Arkhipov, 2019: 136, where it describes a part of the throne for the god Dagān given by Zimrī-Līm). In light of this, *lē’um* has sometimes been defined as a type of percussion instrument (Krispijn, 2010a). It might be identified with the chalcophone, a type of percussion instrument depicted twice with their musicians in the Neo-Assyrian *pyxis* of Nimrūd N.973 (see Rašīd, 1984: 108–109 for image and comments). However, the *lē’um* was made of ebony or *elammakkum* wood (= a wood from Elam (?)), and covered with a layer of gold according to

other tasks, as musical instructor (*mušāḫizum*), instructor for the performance of the incantations and supervisor of the fabrication of musical instruments¹²⁹⁸. In this sense, Imgur-Šamaš had to teach general musical skills to his two students because of their different trajectories, and not a single discipline as the profession of the *nārum*. Therefore, we would translate *nārūtum* in this context as “music”.

5.2.2.9. FM 9 62 [M.7281] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

We are now going to deal with a very much damaged letter probably written by Rīšīya or Ilišu-Ibbīšu¹²⁹⁹. This letter is about Tir-Ea, a person first documented in the Mari texts as a musician of the *lē’um* instrument together with the previously mentioned Lipit-Ellil. Then he is known in those texts as *aštalûm* and *nārum*¹³⁰⁰. Here is the excerpt:

Text 52. FM 9 62 [M.7281] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹³⁰¹

- r. 6’ *na-ru-tam* ‘*ti-ir*’-[*e₂-a*]
r. 7’ *i-na li-’bi be-li₂’-i*[*a la e-pu-uš*]¹³⁰²
r. 8’ *ma-an-nu-’um an-nu-um* ‘*ša* ‘**AL**’,[**DAR.SUR₉**]¹³⁰³
r. 9’ ‘*u₃’ sa₃-am-’mi-im* ‘*i-na* ‘*qa-at*’ [*be-li₂-ia*]
r. 10’ ‘*i-ma* ‘*ḥa-’ru*’ ‘*a-na na-’ru-tim*’? [*u₂-ul re-di*]

r. 6’-7’ Tir-[Ea] [did not make] music according to the will of m[y] lord. r. 8’-10’ Who is the one who accepted from the hands [of my lord] an *alḡasurrûm* friction drum and a *sammîm* angular harp (but [is not suitable] for music)?

We have two references to *nārūtum* in this text. The first one has been translated as “music”¹³⁰⁴. That might make sense keeping in mind the fragmentary state of the part of

FM 9 43 [A.1185] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), lo. e. 2–le. e. 3 (Archibab T6601). In this sense, it might be perhaps a type of lyre or zither, an identification perhaps suggested in FM 9, p. 76.

¹²⁹⁸ FM 9, p. 206–207.

¹²⁹⁹ FM 9, p. 245. We can see there how the date is also hypothetical

¹³⁰⁰ FM 9, p. 241.

¹³⁰¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6619 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹³⁰² Our own restitution keeping in mind the following lines of this text.

¹³⁰³ This restoration makes sense, although we might have restored also just **AL.DAR**. Certainly, a ^{ueš}**al-ḡar** and a ^{ueš}**al-ḡar-sur₉**, both instruments, appear together with a ^{ueš}**za₃-mi₂** in the different variants of *Enki’s Journey to Nippur*, 62 (Ceccarelli, 2012: 94, and 98 for the variants).

¹³⁰⁴ FM 9, p. 244 (“la musique”; followed by Archibab T6619).

this text where *nārūtum* is mentioned. The second reference to *nārūtum* in our Text 52 is similar to *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, 94 (= Text 22). There, as we have previously discussed, someone was unable to learn (**zu**) music (**nam-nar**) despite having a **za3-mi2** angular harp with him. In our Text 52, Tir-Ea seems to not be fit (*ul redī*) for *nārūtum* despite having with him a *sammûm* (the same instrument as in our Text 22!) besides an *algasurrûm* instrument. If we could translate **nam-nar** in *Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu*, 94 as “music”, we believe that is also possible to translate *nārūtum* in our Text 52 as “music” and not *nārum*’s “office”¹³⁰⁵ or “path”¹³⁰⁶ as in previous studies. These texts might be dealing, therefore, with an expression that still makes sense in English: “to be good at music”, something useful for proving our hypothesis.

5.3. Texts from the reign of Zimrī-Līm (1775–1761 BCE)

5.3.1. Texts with *nārūtum* as “office of the *nārum*”

The sole excerpt belonging to this section comes from a letter written by a Ḫitte and addressed to a person probably called Iṣar-Līm¹³⁰⁷. The content of our excerpt seems to be described as “another matter” (*ṣanītam*). However, it is actually the only preserved part of this letter. Here is the excerpt in question:

Text 53. FM 9 5 [A.4377] (Zimrī-Līm¹³⁰⁸ 00-00-00)¹³⁰⁹

lo. e. 1 š[a-ni-tam na-ru-tam]
 r. 1 ^{munus}na-ra-ṭu-ṭk[a]
 r. 2 it-ti ^{munus}na-ra-ṭim ṭ
 r. 3 ša sa-mi-ia ṭi-ḥa-[za]
 r. 4 i-nu-ṭma ṭša-al-ma-nu-m[a]
 r. 5 u₃ ni-ṭin ṭna-ṭam ṭma-ru
 r. 6 i-na u₄-mi-šu ta-ṭam-ma ṭar-[ši-na-ti]

¹³⁰⁵ FM 9, p. 244 “(au métier de) musicien”; followed by Archibab T6619).

¹³⁰⁶ Michalowski, 2010a: 225 (“a musician’s path”).

¹³⁰⁷ See FM 9, p. 41–42 for reference.

¹³⁰⁸ For this transcription giving the meaning “The Tribe (*līm*) is my protection (*zimrī*)”, we follow Rubio, 2002: 239 n. 3. See eSAD Z for *zimru(m)* (from *zamāru(m)* III “to protect”) as “protection”. At the moment, *zimru* is defined just as “song” in AHw (III, p. 1528) and CAD (Z, p. 119). That last meaning does not fit here since the *zimru* songs are known only in Standard Babylonian and Neo-Babylonian dialects.

¹³⁰⁹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6565 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

Lo. e. 1-r. 3 A[nother matter:] yo[ur] *nārtum* are lear[nin]g music with the *nārtum* of Samīya. r. 4 When we are fine r. 5, and we see ourselves, r. 6 you will see [them] at that moment¹³¹⁰!

The term *nārūtum* (in restoration, so, any conclusion is considered hypothetical) has been translated here as “music”¹³¹¹. This meaning fits well in this context, especially keeping in mind other texts dealing with musical teaching, where we have normally translated *nārūtum* as “music”. In any case, a group of *nartum* is going to teach to another group of *nartum*. Therefore, a translation of *nārūtum* as “office of the *nārum*” might also fit well here, since that office would be probably the content of that instruction.

5.3.2. Texts with *nārūtum* as “music”

The sole excerpt to be studied in this section¹³¹² belongs to a letter where Rîšīya complains that his musical activities are being forgotten by Zimrī-Līm. Certainly, Zimrī-Līm seemed to have been not very interested in music, and was distrusting with his musicians, especially those having worked for the previous king, such as Rîšīya¹³¹³:

Tetx 54. FM 9 18 [A.903] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)¹³¹⁴

o. 1 [a-na be-li₂-i]a q_i₂-^rbi₂-ma^r
o. 2 [um-ma ri-ši-i]a IR₃-ka-a-^rma^r
o. 3 ^dd[a-gan] ^di-tur₂-^rme-er
o. 4 u₃ la-ma-as-sa₃-at ma-ri-^{ki} li-iš-^rš_u₂-ru-ka^r
o. 5 a-na mi-^rnim^r be-li₂ me-^rša^r-an-ni
o. 6 u₃ ši-^rit^r-r[i] ^ru₂-[ul i-de-ek-ke]
o. 7 [...] x x [...] x
r. 1 [...] E₂.GAL-^rlim^r
r. 2 a-[... x].MEŠ be-^rli₂ li^r-di-^rnam-ma^r
r. 3 na-ru-t[a]m-^rma li^r-^rhi-^rt_u^r
r. 4 u₃ mu-um-^rma^r-am^r li^r-id-ku-^ru₂^r
r. 5 i-ba-aš-ši-^ri^r mu-^rum^r-mu-um
r. 6 ^rša^r-de-^rke^r-e-^rem la^r i-š_u-^ru₂^r
r. 7 [a]-^rnu^r-um u₃ ^dEN.LIL₂ li-ra-mu-ka
r. 8. [ma-ma]-^ran^r-ma^r ^rša^r pa-qa-di-im
lo. e. 1 [be-li₂ li]-ip-q_i₂-da-^ran-ni^r

¹³¹⁰ Literally “day”.

¹³¹¹ FM 9, p. 41 (“[la musique]”; followed by Archibab T6565).

¹³¹² Other texts from the Zimrī-Līm’s reign where *nārūtum* means “music” will be commented on in the next section of this chapter.

¹³¹³ See FM 9, p. 114 for the rest of the argumentation. In any case, we have interesting things concerning music during this reign. See Lacambre and Millet, 2008 for reference.

¹³¹⁴ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6576 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

o.¹ Say [to m]y [lord], o.¹ [thus (speaks) Rîšīy]a, your servant. o.³⁻⁴ May Dagān, Itūr-Mēr, and the protective deities from Mari guard you! o.⁵ Why my lord forgets me o.⁶ and does not call my *šitrum* ensemble? o.^{7-r.1} [...] of the [pa]lace.

r.² May my lord give [...] to me, r.³ may they control the(ir) music[a]ll activity and r.⁴ employ (at least) a workshop (for providing them)! r.⁵ Is there a workshop r.⁶ with nobody calling him (for that task)? r.⁷ May [Ā]nûm and Ellil love you Lo. e. 1 (and) [may my lord] appoint for me r.⁸ [anybod]y who can be appointed!

The term *nārūtum* has been translated here as “music”¹³¹⁵ or “music(al service)”¹³¹⁶. That makes sense, but not as an independent or general “musical service”¹³¹⁷. For that, we would expect to find in the text something like *apāl nārūtum* (from *apālum* “service”). In our opinion, *nārūtum* might refer to the activity of the *šitrum* mentioned in the text. Certainly, if the activity of Rîšīya’s *šitrum* ensemble was perceived as positive, that music group might get more relevance in the musical life of the kingdom. As a last consequence, Rîšīya’s *šitrum* might obtain some (material) support from the different *mummmum* (term meaning probably here just “workshop”¹³¹⁸) of Mari.

5.4. About the expression *enût nārūtum*

We would like to dedicate some final lines to the study of the expression *enût nārūtum* found in two letters respectively dating from the reigns of Šamšī-Addu and Zimrī-Līm. However, before considering these letters, we would like to make two general remarks. First, *enût nārūtum* should be translated as “instrument of music (*nārūtum*)”, and not as “instrument of the *nārum*’s office”. Certainly, a variant of that expression (*enût nārī = e-nu-ut lu²NAR.MEŠ*¹³¹⁹), seems to concern several musicians. The translation “instrument of the *nārum*’s office” refers, however, to a single musician and his profession. Second,

¹³¹⁵ Ziegler, 2011: 295 (“music”).

¹³¹⁶ FM 9, p. 114 (“le (service de) la musique”; followed by Ziegler, 2013: 56 and Archibab T6576).

¹³¹⁷ FM 9, p. 114; Ziegler, 2013: 56; Archibab T6576). Similarly, Ziegler, 2011: 295 talks about the “music in Mari”. However, Mari is not explicitly mentioned in our excerpt.

¹³¹⁸ FM 9, p. 115 understood *mummmum* here as a reference to the artists in general, and not the physical building of the *mummmum* conservatory of the city. However, that meaning is far from the nature of *mummu(m)* as “workshop” (CAD M, p. 197; FM 9, p. 77) and, as a plausible extension per the context, “conservatory” or “musical workshop”. Our interpretation of that term is probably far from the usual for Mari texts (FM 9, p. 77–78). However, we believe that it makes sense here.

¹³¹⁹ FM 9 12 [ARM 10 137] (Zimrī-Līm 13-00-00), lo. e. 5 (Archibab T6206). The musical instrument designated by this term seems to be made with gold (KU3.SI22). See Ziegler, 2015: 202 for comments.

enût nārūtīm had to concern a specific musical instrument. Certainly, there is already an expression in Mari for designating “musical objects” in general: *ḥišeḥtum ša nārūtīm*. This expression is found in this excerpt of a letter written by Ellil-īpuš to King Zimrī-Līm. That letter deals with the services of the new provincial palace in Dūr-Yaḥdun-Līm, being music one of these palace services¹³²⁰:

Text 55. FM 9 3 [A.4202] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)¹³²¹

- o. 23 ^ˈu₃ ˈḥi-še-eḥ-ta-ˈam ša ˈna-ˈru-tim ˈ
o. 24 [m]i-im-ma ˈel-ˈt[e]-ˈqe₂ˈ (Anepigraphic space)

o. 23-24 On the other hand, I have taken all the necessary musical objects¹³²².

Having said that, we present now the first of our two excerpts with the expression *enût nārūtīm*. This excerpt is contained in a letter where Ilšu-Ibbišu, the musical instructor, writes to Šamšī-Addu about some *aštalûm* young musicians and the construction of several (stringed (?)) musical instruments. In addition, he requests to have with him the new musical instructor Sîn-aḥam-iddinam. Here is the excerpt in question:

Text 56. FM 9 48 [M.6900] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)¹³²³

- o. 8 ši-ˈip-ˈri i-la-ak ˈu₃ aš-ˈ-[t]a-li
o. 9 ša be-li₂ iq-bu ša-ab-ta-ku
o. 10 aš-šum ˈe-ˈnu-ut na-ˈru-ˈtim
o. 11 ^ˈu₃ ˈeš^ˈsi₂-id-di be-li₂ ˈda-ˈan-na-tim
o. 12 ˈa-ˈna u₂-šur-a-wa-ˈsu₂ˈ li-iš-pu-ˈur₂-ma ˈ
o. 13 u₃ ar-ḥi-iš li-ˈpu-ˈlu-ni-in-ni

o. 8-9 My work is going (well), and I have with me the *aštalûm* young musicians which my lord said! o.
10-12 May he send firm (orders) to Ušur-Awassu about the “instruments of music” and the *siddum*
stringed instruments, o. 13 and satisfy me immediately!

¹³²⁰ FM 9, p. 32

¹³²¹ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6563 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹³²² Literally “all (*mimma*) the necessary objects (*ḥišeḥtam*) of (*ša*) the music (*nārūtīm*)”. “For the music” (= FM 9, p. 35, followed by Archibab T6563), would require *ana* instead of *ša*.

¹³²³ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6606 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

In this excerpt, *enût nārūtīm* is probably in plural, and not singular, per the context¹³²⁴. In addition, it is mentioned together with the *siddum* stringed instruments. However, we do not have more information about this instrument beyond, perhaps, the reference to the *pitnum* strings requested by Išū-Ibbīšu several lines below in the same letter¹³²⁵. Our information is not more abundant in our second excerpt about the *enût nārūtīm*. There, this *enût nārūtīm* is “made to be equipped” (*ušašbit*, Š 3SG.M Preterite of *šabātu(m)*, in Š Stem “to equip”) as a part of a group of several instruments prepared for the king¹³²⁶:

Text 57. FM 9 44 [M.8181] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)¹³²⁷

- o. 1 *ʿa-na`be-li2-ʿia`*
o. 2 *ʿqi2`-bi2-ma*
o. 3 *[um]-ma`IR3-i3`-[li2-š]u IR3-ka-a-ma*
o. 4 *[aš-šum e]-nu-ut`na`-ru-[tim]`ša be-li2 u2`-w[a-e-ra-an-ni]*
o. 5 *[e-nu-ta]m`ša-a-ti`[u2-ša-aš-bi-i]t`*
o. 6 *[1 e]-nam`ša a-na`b[e-li2-i]a u2-[še-pi2-šu]*
o. 7 *ʿe-nam`ša-a-tu`ša-ab-ta-ku`i-na mu-um`-m[i-im]*
o. 8 *ʿu3`-ša-ak-`pa-la-šu`aš-šum`^{es}pa-ra-aḥ-ši-ti`NIN`. [IGI².ZI².BAR²]¹³²⁸*
o. 9 *[^{es}pa-`ra`-aḥ-ši-[ta]m`ša`-a-ti`qi2-`iš`-ti-^dnu-[nu]*
o. 10 *[u2]-ul`iṣ-ba-as-s[i2]*

o. 2 Say to o. 1 my lord, o. 3 [th]us (speaks) Warad-Ilišu, your servant. o. 4 [Concerning the in]strument of mus[ic] which my lord or[dered me], o. 5 I [equippe]d this instrument¹³²⁹. o. 6–10 I have taken [one ins]trument which I [built] for m[y] lor[d], (and) I will “curve” it in the *mumm[um]*. Concerning the *paraḥšitum* “Lady [of the righteous sight]”, Qišti-Nunu did not take this (said) *paraḥši[tu]m*.

In our opinion, this *enût nārūtīm* might be an Akkadian version of the **ḡeš-gu3-di** mentioned close to **nam-nar** in *Inanna and Enki*, I v 33 and II V 50–51 and *Ur-Namma* A, 188. It is true that **ḡeš-gu3-di** has already been compared to the Akkadian

¹³²⁴ We agree, therefore, with FM 9, p. 210 (“instruments de musique”; followed by Archibab T6606). Theo J. H. Krispijn (personal communication) translated this term as “tools of the musicians”.

¹³²⁵ FM 9 48 [M.6900] (Šamši-Addu 00-00-00), r. 2–4 (Archibab T6606).

¹³²⁶ Perhaps these instruments would be covered with a layer of gold. Certainly, in FM 9 12 [ARM 10 137] (Zimrī-Līm 13-00-00), lo. e. 5 (Archibab T6206), we have an “instrument of the *nāru* of gold” (*enût nārī ša ḡurāšim*) (*e-nu-ut* ^{lu2}NAR.MEŠ *ša* KU3.SI22). See also FM 9 43 [A.1185] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 5–9 (Archibab T6601), about a ^{es}*inūtum* of gold sent to the metalworkers (*kutīmū* = LU2.KU3.DIM2.MEŠ).

¹³²⁷ Edition dependent upon Archibab T6602 with corrections derived from our inspection of the photo of the manuscript available on that site through Archipix.

¹³²⁸ See FM 9, p. 192 for comments about the restitution. We miss a comment, even a short reference, to this text in Shehata, 2017: 73–74.

¹³²⁹ Concerning the commentary of lines o. 3–4 in FM 9, p. 192, personally, we would talk about just an *enût nārūtīm* due to *enūtam šāti* (singular form is marked by *enūtam*), and not about several instruments as in FM 9, p. 192 (“[ins]truments de musique”; followed by Archibab T6602).

*enum/inum*¹³³⁰. In addition, other instruments will sometimes be called *enût nārūtīm* too, like the *urzababītum* in Neo-Assyrian times¹³³¹. Nevertheless, those equivalences are only based on 1st-millennium sources¹³³². In this sense, we cannot apply them to the texts of Mari. Certainly, relationships between Sumerian and Akkadian musical terms might have changed at that time. Even the meaning itself of *enût nārūtīm* might have changed by that time as we shall discuss at the beginning of our next chapter.

In this sense, we find it plausible that *enût nārūtīm* was an Akkadian equivalent for the Sumerian **neš-gu3-di** by the Old Babylonian Period. Therefore, we might have here a type of lute. In any case, we do not rule out that the identification of *enût nārūtīm* could change in later periods of Mesopotamian history. Maybe that identification already changed by the 2nd half of the 2nd millennium BCE¹³³³.

5.5. Conclusions

As we said in the introduction to this chapter, our references to *nārūtum* in the texts from Mari are contained in texts belonging to a common single textual typology (letters). In this sense, the exact sense of *nārūtum* in our textual excerpts depends mainly upon the context where this term is mentioned. Other factors do not seem to be particularly relevant in the configuration of that meaning. We talk about, for instance, the reign during which the letters were written. Certainly, we have talked about the different attitudes towards the music shown by Šamšī-Addu and Zimrī-Līm in their respective reigns.

In our study of these references to *nārūtum*, we have found two different meanings in the texts from Mari: “office of the *nārum*” and “music”. However, those meanings have a different representation in our documentation. We have only three texts (42, 43 and 53) with *nārūtum* referring to the office of a (specific¹³³⁴) *nārum*. However, *nārūtum* designates music *lato sensu* in the rest of the texts of this chapter (10 in addition to the three excerpts about the *enût nārūtīm*).

¹³³⁰ Collon and Kilmer, 1980: 13–28; Krispijn, 1990: 13.

¹³³¹ See the commentary of the Text 57 in the next chapter for evidence and previous bibliography.

¹³³² **Erim-ḫuš**, III Segm. 2, 40 (DCCLT Q000205); **Mur-gu4** = *imrû* = *ballu*, B, II 117 (MSL 6, p. 125).

¹³³³ Certainly, Weidner, 1931–1932: pl. 7–8 [VAT 5744], o. ii 33 (CDLI P282337), is a Middle Assyrian manuscript for the aforementioned **Erim-ḫuš**, III Segment 2, 40 (DCCLT Q000205).

¹³³⁴ In reference to our Text 42, where this term referred to the office of a *nārum* specifically devoted to the cult of the god of the Netherworld Nergal/Āmûm.

This situation replicates what we had in southern Mesopotamia at that time, where **nam-nar** meant “office of the **nar**” in our legal texts (7 texts in total) and “music” in our literary texts (20) and the texts from the elementary scribal *curriculum* (6, although without, the **nam-nar-balaṅ** from *Proto-izi*, II 230 = Text 10).

Concerning the meaning as “music”, sometimes this sense is suitable simply due to a general reference to musical teaching (like, among others, our Text 47) or the musical activity in general, as in our Text 46. There, we find a reference to the “destruction” (with the Dt Stem of the verb *ḫalāqu(m)*) of that music. However, at other times this “music” probably referred to a possible musical performance. In any case, according to our knowledge, there is no example of *nārūtum* as the sound of a musical instrument beyond, perhaps, our references to *enūt nārūtīm*. They might be understood as “instrument for making music”. Nevertheless, that translation ignores the grammar of that expression. Certainly, we should have something like *enūtum ana nārūtīm epēšim* for that.

One example of the texts from Mari with *nārūtum* meaning “music” pertaining to a performance might be our Text 48. There, as we saw in the commentary, the expression *nārūtam epēšum* said by the *nargallum* Rîšīya could be related to the *nigūta epēšu* of later texts which was referred, on some occasions, to something done by the musicians¹³³⁵. We might also make a connection (always keeping in mind the chronological distances) with the reference to **nam-nar** in *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20–22 (= Text 4), where **nam-nar** designated the activity of some musical instruments.

In any case, we can still establish in “music” the main meaning for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* by the early 2nd millennium BCE with a secondary meaning as “profession of the **nar/nārum**”. This secondary meaning only happens when **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* are mentioned in a genitive chain together with a divine name (as in our Text 42). In addition, according to our Texts 43 and 54 from Mari, this meaning should also be considered when **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* are mainly making reference to a (group of) **nar/nārum** musician(s) without any reference to instruments and/or other musicians. With this situation in mind, we are ready to pass to the next and last chapter of this study.

¹³³⁵ Remember the excerpts *Aššurbānīpal* 3, vi 46–47 (RINAP 5 Q003702); *Aššurbānīpal* 4, vi 48–49 (RINAP 5 Q003703), *Aššurbānīpal* 6, vii 53 (RINAP 5 Q003705); *Aššurbānīpal* 7, vi 11”–12” (RINAP 5 Q003706).

6. THE FIRST MILLENNIUM

6.1. General Introduction

We proceed now to a study the references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* in the 1st millennium BCE because there is no reference to those terms in the Middle Babylonian and/or Assyrian texts. That is certainly a pity since we have several interesting texts for the musical life of those periods¹³³⁶. At the moment, we have only references to *nār(t)u* in both letters and personnel lists in Akkadian¹³³⁷. Some of them are as yet unpublished¹³³⁸, like the tablets CBS 7826¹³³⁹, CBS 8500¹³⁴⁰, UM 29-15-72¹³⁴¹ and UM 29-15-211¹³⁴². Unfortunately, their edition and in-depth analysis are out of the scope of this study whose sole aim is the study of the terms **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*.

¹³³⁶ See Westenholz, 2005: 357–373 for a lexicographical analysis of PBS 1/1 11 [CBS 11341], a text with many references to musicians and chants. Krispijn, 2002: 469–475 and Michalowski, 2010a: 208–217 offer recent and musically and philologically well-balanced commentary on music theory texts from that time and Shehata, 2009: 319, 329 makes comments about the song catalogue KAR 158 [VAT 10101].

¹³³⁷ See AHw II, p. 748–749 and CAD N1, p. 363–364, 378 for evidence. For comments on Middle Babylonian texts, see Sassmannshausen, 2001: 101–102, Tenney, 2011: 99 n. 41, 231; Sibbing Plantholt, 2014: 172 (thanks to Lynn-Salammō Zimmermann for this reference); Zimmermann, 2017 and Arroyo Cuadra, 2018: 158–161. See Jakob, 2003: 520–522 and Pruzsinszky, 2018a: 104–105 for the Middle Assyrian Period, and Pruzsinszky, 2007: 330 n. 3 for musicians in the texts from Nuzi.

¹³³⁸ The following comments come from our collation of these tablets on 22–23/08/2019, whose aim was just to check if they contained any possible reference to *nārūtu* (although they don't).

¹³³⁹ Photo available on CDLI P262831. See Sassmannshausen, 2001: 101 n. 1705 and Sibbing Plantholt, 2014: 172, n. 9 and 173 n. 17 for some comments. The reference to the *nāru* is on o. 2 (*a-na na-a'-r[e-e]*). The obverse of the letter is mostly broken, so the context of this reference is uncertain.

¹³⁴⁰ See CDLI P263307 for a photo, and CAD N1, p. 378; Mayer and van Soldt, 1991: 118; Sassmannshausen, 2001: 56 n. 839, 58 n. 890, 100 n. 1707, 102 n. 1743, 121 n. 2057, 154 n. 2609; Brinkman, 2004: 295 and Murai, 2018: 206 n. 579 for comments. Line o. i 24 has [...] 16.1.4 ^{lu2}*na-a'-ru-u2*, so, we are looking at ration list (and not a personnel list as Sassmannshausen said).

¹³⁴¹ See CDLI P255925 for a photo, and Brinkman, 1988: 20 n. 47; Sassmannshausen, 2001: 101 n. 1724, 133 n. 2287, 136 n. 2314, 151 n. 1547; Brinkman, 2004: 297 and Tenney, 2011: 252 for some comments. It is a list of workers where the *nāru* are mentioned in line r. 4 (*na-a'-ru-ru-u2*). However, we do not know the quantity of musicians mentioned in this text because the tablet is broken at that point.

¹³⁴² See CDLI P256042 for a photo and Sassmannshausen, 2001: 60, 82 n. 1337, 84, n. 1354 and 1365, 85 n. 1401, 98 n. 1669, 102 n. 1729 for comments on the whole tablet. Said tablet is a list of bread rations where the *nāru* are mentioned in r. ii 18.

Concerning the 1st millennium, this chapter will be divided into three sections based on chronological considerations: 1) the Neo-Assyrian Period, 2) the Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid Periods, and 3) the Seleucid Period. In any case, we should take into consideration that Assyria and Babylonia interacted very intensively throughout this period, and that fact is reflected in our texts. Certainly, the lexical texts to be studied here are composed by Neo-Assyrian and Neo-Babylonian manuscripts. In the same way, our Seleucid texts (from Babylonia) sometimes make allusion to the earlier Neo-Assyrian textual tradition. In this sense, we should avoid here too strict a separation of the different periods involved in this chapter.

6.2. The Neo-Assyrian Period

6.2.1. Reflections about a “musical instrument” in a lexical text

This section deals with an excerpt of the recension B of **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu*. This text is a three column commentary of the canonical version of the bilingual lexical text **Ur₅-ra** = *hubullu(m)* which, in the first column, contains a Sumerian word from an entry of the canonical version of **Ur₅-ra** = *hubullu(m)*. The second column contains an Akkadian equivalent of the Sumerian word. Finally, the third column contains a commentary of the Akkadian term of the second column of the type *šātu u šūt pī* (“explanatory word list and comments”) that is, a synonym and/or a short clarification¹³⁴³.

These early 1st-millennium commentaries had their origin in the necessity of preserving and understanding old Mesopotamian terms and traditions because, at that moment, the Akkadian language was experiencing a situation similar to what Sumerian experienced in the early 2nd millennium BCE. Certainly, by the 2nd millennium BCE, many typical words in Akkadian had already disappeared from the daily language by the early 1st millennium BCE. The reason is that Akkadian was being replaced by Aramaic as the main spoken language of the Mesopotamian people. Here is our excerpt:

¹³⁴³ Vedeler, 2002: 4–5; Frahm, 2011: 250; Veldhuis, 2014: 365.

Text 58. **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu*, B II [= **Urs-ra** = *hubullu(m)* VII B]¹³⁵⁰

169					ŠU	[e]- ^r nu*- tu ₂ * ^a ša ₂ na-ru-[ti]
	NA-Ni _{I-A1}	r. i' 20	[...]		[...]	[e]- ^r nu*- tu ₂ * ^a ša ₂ na-ru-[ti] ¹³⁵¹
	NA-Ni _{I-A7}	o. i' 4	[^d] ^r nin' -urta	ŠU	[...]
	NA-Ni _{I-C2} ¹³⁵²	r. i' 20'	ηēš	ur-za-ba-bi- ^r tu ₂ '	[...]	[...]
		r. i' 21'	ηēš	MIN ^d nin' - ^r urta'	[...]	[...]
	NB-X _{L2}	r. i' 10'	MIN ηēš	nin-<urta> ur-za-ba-bi -tu ₂	ŠU ^{*1353} - ^r tum ^{*1354}	[...]

169 ηēš**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂** ^dnin-urta (is equal to) *urzababūt Ninurta* (and it means) musical instrument.

*Sigla*¹³⁵⁵

NA-Ni _{I-A1}	Meissner, Suppl. 11 [K. 4341 + 4556] (photo on CDLI P365391; not available for its collation the 01–02/08/2019)
NA-Ni _{I-A7}	MSL 6, p. 139 [K. 16156] (photo on CDLI P401797; collated the 01/08/2019)
NA-Ni _{I-C2}	MSL 6, p. 81 [K. 2028] (photo on CDLI P238140; collated the 01/08/2019)
NB-X _{L2}	MSL 6, p. 108 [BM 34129] (collated the 01/08/2019)

¹³⁵⁰ Our own edition in score. We have revised the individual transliterations of the manuscripts of this score (all of them available on DCCLT) consulting the photos of those manuscripts, most part of them collated by us. Thanks to Niek Vieldhuis for making available on DCCLT by our request the transliterations of some of those manuscripts.

¹³⁵¹ MSL 6, p. 142 has “šá na-ru-ti” and DCCLT “[...]-^rx' ša₂ na-ru-ti”. According to the photo on CDLI P365391, final *ti* is practically absent. Where DCCLT places an unknown sign, we see a sign UD lacking the vertical wedge (always following CDLI’s photo, this manuscript was not available for its collation on 01/08/2019). Moreover, we still see what might be a sign NU with damage in its horizontal wedge. Our restored [e] is made according to the context.

¹³⁵² This manuscript actually belongs to **Urs-ra** = *hubullu* VII B, not to **Mur-gu₄**. However, we have used it here in order to complete our main text.

¹³⁵³ DCCLT has *ur*^l. According to our collation, it seems to be the sign ŠAG₄. Keeping in mind the context (see the following note), it might be an incorrect sign ŠU. In any case, we are not totally confident, since that sign is repeated several times in the previous lines.

¹³⁵⁴ Omitted in DCCLT, our collation has allowed us to see a shape similar to the sign TUM. It makes sense with the previous lines of that manuscript, where we have several ŠU-*tum* as abbreviations for lexical entries.

¹³⁵⁵ They follow MSL 5, p. 43 (A₁), 81 (C₂), 108 (L₂) and 139 (A₇). However, we have put before NA (Neo-Assyrian) or NB (= Neo-Babylonian) according to their chronology, Ni (= Nineveh) and X (= Uncertain) according to their provenance, and I (= Type I) for their typology paying attention to Civil, 1995: 2308.

This excerpt pertains to the ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂**, a musical instrument mastered by King Šulgi according to the Old Babylonian hymn *Šulgi B*¹³⁵⁶. This instrument has usually been connected with King Ur-Zababa of Kiš overthrown by Sargon of Akkad¹³⁵⁷. However, it should rather be connected with Ur-Zababa, a city known during the Ur III times¹³⁵⁸.

That would fit better with the earliest and latest mentions of that city during the Šulgi's reign¹³⁵⁹ and the Old Babylonian times¹³⁶⁰ respectively. In addition, it makes sense with the Akkadian names of certain “ethnic instruments” which have the suffix *-ītum* and are mentioned in some texts¹³⁶¹ with the ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂**. In fact, that name is actually an Akkadian loanword. Moreover, at least for the Neo-Assyrian period, we would identify the term ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂** with a lute, and not with a lyre as it is usual¹³⁶². It is true that it has the determinative ^{neš} for wooden objects, main construction material for all stringed instruments¹³⁶³. However, ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂** is preceded by the term ^{neš}**gu₂** (“wooden neck”) in a line of a manuscript of **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu*¹³⁶⁴. This term makes us think that it is a lute, since the lute is the only instrument having a sort of “neck”¹³⁶⁵.

In our opinion, in this excerpt, *enûtu ša nārûti*¹³⁶⁶ would describe ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂** just as a “musical instrument”, and not as an “instrument of the *nāru*'s profession” as Krispijn suggested¹³⁶⁷. Certainly, in the section of **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu* where our

¹³⁵⁶ *Šulgi B*, 165 (ETCSL 2.4.2.02).

¹³⁵⁷ Falkenstein and Matouš, 1922: 147; Kramer, 1967a: 374 n. 13; Stauder, 1970: 217; Spycket, 1972: 184; Krispijn, 1990: 11; Franklin, 2015: 35.

¹³⁵⁸ Michalowski, 2010b: 121 n. 10 and Krispijn's personal communication.

¹³⁵⁹ MVN 3 136 [FLP 157] (*Šulgi*, 33-04-00), o. 4 (BDTNS 018079).

¹³⁶⁰ MSL 11, p. 56–59 [IM 51143 + 51153], 131 and 196 (original publication).

¹³⁶¹ Although it is prior to our text, Emar 6/2, p. 508–515 + 730 [Msk 74209a + 7526], r. ii 6–9 is the best textual example for this matter. Certainly, we find a **sa₃-bi-tum/sabītum** (r. ii 6; “instrument from Sabum”, see the comments to our Text 44 for reference) and a **ma₂-ri₂-tum/mārītum** (“instrument from Mari (?)”) with an **ur₂-za-ba₄-ba₄** / *urzababītum*.

¹³⁶² AHw III, p. 1437, and then, Krispijn, 2010: 148; Gabbay, 2014b: 139 without (many) arguments.

¹³⁶³ Pay attention, in any case, to the use of the **a₂-la₂/alû** in the cult of Zababa, the deity referred in the name Ur-Zababa connected with ^{neš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂** (Mirelman, 2014: 159; Shehata, 2014: 110).

¹³⁶⁴ MSL 6, p. 81 [K. 2028], r. i' 19' (collated the 01/08/2019).

¹³⁶⁵ Thanks to Theo J. H. Krispijn for helping us to improve an earlier version of these reflections.

¹³⁶⁶ It is usual for Neo-Assyrian texts to have *nuāru* (see Groß, 2014: 223–224 for argumentation), but we would maintain here *nāru* (and, therefore, *nārūtu*) since we do not have *nu-a-ru-ti* here.

¹³⁶⁷ Krispijn, 1990: 11.

excerpt comes from¹³⁶⁸, musical terms are normally compared with similar concrete terms for other instruments¹³⁶⁹. That stands in contrast to our ^{ueš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂**.

The reason for that description might be that the compilers of **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu* did not know the exact nature of the ^{ueš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂**, and, they defined it just as “musical instrument”. That definition would be an orientation for other scribes about what had to be an already ancient instrument not in use any more by the Neo-Assyrian period. That makes sense with the previously described early origins of the musical term ^{ueš}**ur-za-ba-bi-tu₂**. In addition, if we had here an instrument of the *nāru*’s office (following Krispijn’s interpretation) we would expect to find said instrument in close association with the *nāru*. These *nāru* are abundantly mentioned in Neo-Assyrian texts¹³⁷⁰. However, from what we can tell, that connection *nāru* — *urzababîtu* never happens in those texts.

6.2.2. The term **šer₃ nam-nar** during the Neo-Assyrian Period

As we have previously noted, **ser₃ nam-nar** in Old Babylonian texts should be defined as a “musical (**nam-nar**) composition to be sung (**šer₃**)”, a type of song whose content would mainly be ceremonial and not related to laments. In Neo-Assyrian times, the presence of **šer₃ nam-nar** has been proposed for the excerpt of *Examination Text A* to be presented on next page. This text pertains to ancient (= Old Babylonian) school practices¹³⁷¹. However, none of its manuscripts actually comes from that period¹³⁷². Most of this text consists of questions of a teacher to his student in order to test his knowledge in several domains, including music¹³⁷³. Here is our excerpt:

¹³⁶⁸ **Mur-gu₄** = *imrû* = *ballu* B, II [= **Urs-ra** = *hubullu* VII B], 162–170 (MSL 6, p. 142). See Veldhuis, 1997–1998: 121; Shehata, 2006: 370 for additional comments.

¹³⁶⁹ For instance, manuscript NA-Ni_I-C₂, r. i’ 2’ has ^{ueš}**a-la₂** = *a-[lu-u₂]* (collated the 01/08/2019) (most of this side of the tablet is broken, so we cannot offer closer equivalences to our **ur-za-ba-bi₂-tum**). In the same way, manuscript NB-X_{L2}, r. i’ 12 has ^{ueš}**sa-eš_s** = *pit₂-’nu^{?’}* [x]-x-[x²] (collated the 01/08/2019).

¹³⁷⁰ For a recent and complete overview of the *nāru* in Neo-Assyrian times, see Groß, 2014: 223–244. Thanks to the author of that contribution for this useful and remarkable reference.

¹³⁷¹ Maybe for this reason Krispijn, 1990: 2 used this text in order to discuss the term **nam-nar** in *Šulgi B*, but he has also used this text for comments about the Neo-Assyrian Period (Krispijn, 2017: 226).

¹³⁷² For this reason, we discuss this text here, and not in our chapter on Old Babylonian literary texts.

¹³⁷³ Sjöberg, 1974: 137–138.

Text 59. Examination Text A¹³⁷⁴

24		[... šer₃ nam-gala ¹³⁷⁵ šer₃ nam-en-na šer₃ nam-u[ru-na ki-ru-g]u₂ šid gul-la 'i ₃ -zu'-u ₃ [... š]er ₃ -nam-gala-ke ₄ šer ₃ -na[m-en-na-k]e ₄ [šer ₃ -nam]-'u ₂ -ru'-na-ki per-si-š _u ₂ -nu pa-r[a-s]u [...] mi-iḥ-ra e-ni e-ni u ki-la ti-de-e
	NA-Ni _{III-F}	o. 1' [... -n]e-ki [šer ₃ -nam]-'u ₂ -ru'-na-ki [...]-'ki' /pe'-er-si-š _u ₂ -nu pa-ra-su [...] mi-iḥ-ra [...] u ki-la 'KI.MIN'
	NA-Ni _{U-H}	o. 2' [... šer₃ nam -en-na [...]-'x'-zid-da [...]-'zu'-u ₃ [...]-'x'-ne [...]-'x'
	NA-X _{III-E}	o. 3 [... šer₃ nam-gala šer₃ na]m-en-na šer₃ nam-u[ru-na ki-ru-g]u₂ šid gul-la 'i ₃ '-[...] [... š]er ₃ -nam-gala-ke ₄ šer ₃ -na[m-en-na-k]e ₄ [... šer ₃ -na]m-gi-na-ke ₄ per-si-š _u ₂ -un pa-r[a-s]u [...-r]a e-ni ki-li ti-de-e
	NB-Ba _{III-M}	o. 1' [...] 'x' [...]
	NB-Si _{U-R} ¹³⁷⁶	o. 13' [... -b]a-'lam' sa-am-sa-a[m-...] [...]-'x' sa-am-sa-[...]

- 24 (Sumerian) Do you know [... the lament text to be sung, the **šer₃** song of the lordship, the **šer₃** song of the exal[tedness, the **ki-ru-g]u₂**, how to restrain the count?
(Akkadian) Do you know [... the *šernamgalakku* song, the *šerna[mennakk]u* song, the [*šernam]urunakku* song, and how to “separate” their “divisions”, [...] the “answer” and how hold back the “change”?

*Sigla*¹³⁷⁷

NA-Ni _{III-F}	Gadd, 1957: 256 [K. 2459] (photo available on CDLI P357082)
NA-Ni _{U-H}	Sjöberg, 1974: 138 [K. 9345] (photo available on CDLI P357121)
NA-X _{III-E}	Gadd, 1957: 256 [DT 147] (photo available on CDLI P357076)
NB-Ba _{III-M}	van Dijk, 1987: pl. 24, text n. 64 [VAT 17071] (photo available on CDLI P347183)
NB-Si _{U-R}	CT 58, pl. 64 [BM 54981 + 69265 +?] (copy available on CDLI P274260)

¹³⁷⁴ Our own edition in score starting from the edition in composite line in Sjöberg, 1974: 142 and the transliterations of the individual manuscripts available on BLMS. We have revised those transliterations inspecting the manuscripts mentioned in the score through the copies/photos indicated below.

¹³⁷⁵ For other 1st-millennium references to **nam-gala**, see **Uru am₃-ma-ir-ra-bi**, XIX, 47–48 (Volk, 1989: 83). This excerpt refers to the things brought by Inanna for the office of the **gala** priest (**nam-am₂-gala-e**) as the Old Babylonian VS 2 29 [VAT 1339], o. 6–7 (Cohen, 1988: 556). In addition, see Maul *Ershahunga*, p. 252–253, **er₂ ša₃ ḥun-ḡa₂** n. 49 [K. 9608], o. 2 (BLMS). It is in fragmentary context, but, perhaps, **nam-gala** referred to a group of **gala**. Otherwise, we should find **nam-gala-e**, not **nam-gala-ra**.

¹³⁷⁶ CT 58, pl. 64 [BM 54981 + 69265 +?], o. 12' contains part of line 23 of this text and the following lines are damaged. See this variant as provisional.

¹³⁷⁷ They follow Sjöberg, 1974: 138 except manuscript R, whose *siglum* follow ELS, p. 36. However, we have put before all the *sigla* an NA/NB (Neo-Assyrian/Babylonian), Ba/Ni/Si/X (= Babylon/Nineveh/Sippar/Uncertain) and III/U (Type III/Uncertain) according to their chronology, provenance, and tablet typology respectively.

In the *editio princeps* of this Text 59, Åke Sjöberg proposed the term **šer₃ nam-nar** as a part of the restoration for the gap in the Sumerian line¹³⁷⁸. That restoration might have followed the Old Babylonian lexical text *Proto-Lu₂*, 590–599¹³⁷⁹. However, the songs of that text differ from those mentioned in our excerpt of *Examination A*, whether in its Sumerian or Akkadian versions. We can perhaps explain these differences due to the chronological distance between both texts. Therefore, even if that restoration might make sense, we should be careful with it¹³⁸⁰.

We have another (and more certain) reference to **šer₃ nam-nar** in this text¹³⁸¹:

Text 60. *Nabnītu*, IVa¹³⁸²

329 [š]er₃ [n]am-nar [ka-am-mu(?)]

Ni _{I-D}	r. i 38	[š]er ₃ []	[...]
Ka _{U-I}	r. i 17	[n]am-nar ¹³⁸³	[...]

329 [š]er₃ [n]am-nar (is the correct Sumerian word for the Akkadian) [kammu(?)]

*Sigla*¹³⁸⁴

Ni _{I-D}	Rawlinson, 1866: 7 [K. 197] (publication copy) + CT 12, pl. 34–35 [Sm. 294] (photo on CDLI P365268; object on display (G55/dc8) and, therefore, not available for collation)
Ka _{U-I}	Wiseman and Black, 1996: pl. 129 n. 217 [ND 2555] (publication copy; CDLI P274514 contains just the obverse).

The *editio princeps* of this text transliterated this line as “[S]AR-nam-LUL”¹³⁸⁵. However, the signs SAR and EZEN (= šer₃) are very similar in Neo-Assyrian script. The

¹³⁷⁸ Sjöberg, 1974: 142, translated **šer₃ nam-nar** as “namnar(?)–Gesang” (followed by Ceccarelli, 2018: 137 n. 33). Later, Volk, 1994: 185 has “Kompositionen für die Tätigkeit als Fest-/Hymnenmusiker”. Finally, Krispijn has translated this term as “Lied des Hymnsängers” (Krispijn, 1990: 2) and “song of the hymn singer” (Krispijn, 2017: 226).

¹³⁷⁹ DCCLT.

¹³⁸⁰ In this sense, we agree with Peterson, 2015b: 3, who did not do any restoration in the Sumerian *lacuna*. Shehata, 2009 did not make comments about **šer₃ nam-nar** in *Examination Text A*.

¹³⁸¹ Thanks to Enrique Jiménez for his comments about this text, which we have tried to follow here.

¹³⁸² Our own edition starting from the copies and photos of the manuscripts indicated below.

¹³⁸³ To the contrary to MSL 16, p. 90 and according to our inspection of its copy, this manuscript seems not contain a broken sign SAR or EZEN.

¹³⁸⁴ *Sigla* follow MSL 16, p. 90, but we have put before an N/K (= Nineveh/Kalḫu) and I/U (= Type I/Uncertain) according to, respectively, their provenance and tablet typology.

¹³⁸⁵ MSL 16, p. 90.

main difference between them is their beginning, which is the broken part of the sign from the tablets of this text. Therefore, the transliteration as EZEN (= **šer3**) might be possible in this context in our opinion. From that point, the reading of the sign LUL as **nar** is a personal proposition according to the context. In any case, it makes sense insofar as ***šer3 nam-lul** (“song of falseness (?)”) is documented nowhere. Moreover, **šer3 nam-nar** might fit with the mention of the term **niġin3** (“shrine”)¹³⁸⁶ in *Nabnītu*, IVa 332, that is, four lines after our line IVa 329. Certainly, a similar expression (**niġin3-ġar**) was already mentioned with **nam-nar** in Old Babylonian times¹³⁸⁷. In that excerpt, these two words referred to two elements related to cultic activities. Despite the chronological distance, this relationship should not be ruled out for our Neo-Assyrian case.

We cannot derive too much information about **šer3 nam-nar** in this case since the Akkadian column is broken. However, since *Nabnītu*, IVa 325–344 is based on Akkadian terms with the radicals K and M, Enrique Jiménez¹³⁸⁸ proposed two possible restorations for the Akkadian part: *kammu* (“literary composition”) or *kamû* (“external”). That author preferred the second term (we shall return to this matter later). However, we would rather follow the first one (*kammu*) as a short definition for **šer3 nam-nar**.

To conclude, if **šer3 nam-nar** experienced some changes between the Old Babylonian and the Neo-Assyrian Period, it is a matter that we cannot resolve at the moment due to the highly fragmentary preservation state of our texts.

6.2.3. Conclusions

Despite its possible interest, and in contrast to Mari in Old Babylonian times (as a “northern Mesopotamian” case studied here) we cannot say much for certain about **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* in Neo-Assyrian times. That happens because of the fragmentary preservation state of many of the texts studied here.

¹³⁸⁶ This meaning of **niġin3** as “shrine” (instead of the homonym word meaning “foetus”) is ensured by the Akkadian word *kummu* (“cella, private room”, CAD K, p. 533) and the following line of *Nabnītu* IVa, 333: **agrun** = MIN, where **agrun**(E₂.NUN = “noble room”) means also “cella” (ePSD).

¹³⁸⁷ *Inanna and Enki*, I v 33 and II, v 47–52 (see our Texts 29 and 30 for edition).

¹³⁸⁸ Personal communication.

6.3. The Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid Periods

6.3.1. Introduction

We base this section on a contract excerpt from Nippur. In this text, Ellil-šumu-ibni (probably a temple musician)¹³⁸⁹ will teach music for three years to Nabī-Ellil¹³⁹⁰, the son (or the slave¹³⁹¹) of an individual called Aplāya:

Text 61. BE 8/1 98 [CBS 3579] (Cambyses II 14+-01-00)¹³⁹²

- o. 1 ^map-la-a A-^rš_{u2} ša₂ ^{md}MAŠ.TIN-^ri² [a-na]
o. 2 ^{md}EN.LIL₂-MU-DU₃ A-š_{u2} ša₂ ^mMUR-^dr^rNIN.TIN^r. [UG₅.GA]¹³⁹³
o. 3 ki-a-am iq-bi um-ma ^mna-bi-^dEN.LIL₂ D[UMU-u₂-a]
o. 4 iḫ-z[i] ^{lu2}NAR-u₂-tu¹³⁹⁴ šu-ḫi-^rzi^r-su
o. 5 ^{md}EN.LIL₂-MU-DU₃ iḫ-^rzu^r ^[lu2]NAR-^ru₂-tu ša₂ z[i²-im²-ri²]¹³⁹⁵
o. 6 ša₂ ^rkal^r-la MU.AN.NA u₂-š_{a2}-aḫ-^rsu zi^r-[i]m-^rri^r
o. 7 u₂-š_{a2}-az-mur-š_{u2}¹³⁹⁶ ^rši-mit-tu₄ u₂-š_{a2}-as-sak-š_{u2} [(x x)]
o. 8 [i]š-ka-ri ḫar-ri ^ra-di^r muḫ-ḫi^r u₂-lu-u[₂-lu ul]
lo. e. 1 ^ru₂-š_{a2}-am-mar-š_{u2} a-d[i] ^r3^r MU.^rAN^r.N[A.MEŠ]
r. 1 ^riḫ^r-zu ^{lu2}NAR-u₂-t[u u₂]-^rš_{a2}-aḫ^r-[su il-ku ša₂]
r. 2 ina E₂.MEŠ^r DIDIR.MEŠ^r in^r-[d]u* ^ril^r-la^r-ku ša₂^r
r. 3 ^rMU.AN.NA^r 5 ^rGID₄ KU₃.BABBAR^r NID₂.^rBA^r-[š_{u2}]
r. 4 ^map-la-a a-na ^{md}EN.LIL₂-MU-DU₃ ^ri-qa-a-š_{u2}^r
r. 5 ^ra^r-di^r 3^r MU.AN.NA.MEŠ^r 15 GID₄ KU₃.BABBAR^r NID₂.^rBA^r-[š_{u2}]
r. 6 ^map^r-la-a a-na ^{md}50^r-MU-DU₃ ^rŠUM₂-i[n]

¹³⁸⁹ Petschow, 1980–1983: 570; Sandowicz, 2018: 50.

¹³⁹⁰ Stol, 2016: 361 n. 105 talks about a possible girl, but we do not know to whom he is making reference exactly in that publication.

¹³⁹¹ Petschow, 1980–1983: 570 offers the restoration **IR₃-i** (“my slave”) in addition to **DUMU-i** (“my son”). In our collation of the tablet, we saw the beginning of **TUR** (= **DUMU**). Therefore, the restoration as **IR₃** does not make sense. However, it might still make sense in light of the mentions of the “yoke team” (^rši-mit-tu₄, o. 7) and the work in the moats ([i]š-ka-ri ḫar*-ri, o. 8), two expressions fitting with a slave.

¹³⁹² Edition dependent upon Hackl, 2007–2010: 15–16 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy in BE 8/1 and our collation of the tablet the 20/08/2019. In that collation, we saw that the photo of this tablet available on CDLI P259952 was definitely made with a bad use of the lighting.

¹³⁹³ For this reading, instead of Hack, 2007–2010: 92, see the reference to Ellil-šumu-ibni in Sandowicz, 2018: 48–51, text n. 3 [BM 16996], r. 5. Read also the comments on Sandowicz, 2018: 50.

¹³⁹⁴ The sign seems to be **TU** (= *tu*), although the context would require **TI** (= *ti*) for the genitive chain *iḫzī nārūti*. Oppenheim, 1952: 134 has here a lacuna, although we do not understand why.

¹³⁹⁵ Oppenheim, 1952: 134 has “*iḫ-z[u] L[Ú.NAR]^{ú-tu} ... ú-šá-aḫ-zu*”. Nevertheless, that does not make sense with the following line (not cited in that publication).

¹³⁹⁶ CAD Z, p. 38 has “*ú-šá-az-mar_x(MUR)-šú*”. However, the conjugation of *zamāru(m)* as an *a/u* verb only happens in Old Babylonian times (CDA, p. 444).

o. 1–o. 4 Aplāya, son of Ninurta-uballiṭ spoke [to] Ellil-šumu-ibni, son of Kalbi-Nintin[uga] in this way: “Instruct Nabī-Ellil [my] s[on] (in) the precepts of the *nāru*’s profession!”

o. 5–o. 7 (And consequently) Ellil-šumu-ibni will teach him the profession of the *nāru* of the *z[imru]* songs of the entire year. He will teach (how) to sing (these) *zimru* s[on]gs to him (= Nabī-Ellil), and he will make him to abandon the yoke team [...]

o. 8–r. 4 (And) he (= Ellil-šumu-ibni) will make him (= Nabī-Ellil) avoid the assigned work in the moats until the beginning of the month *Ulū[lu]* (because) he (= Ellil-šumu-ibni) will instruct (him = Nabī-Ellil) (in) [the p]recepts of the *nāru*’s profess[sion] unti[l have passed] three yea[rs]. [The work] imposed (on him) in the temples of the gods will be done (in this way). Each year, Aplāya will give five silver shekels to Ellil-šumu-ibni (as) his fees.

r. 5–r. 6 Over the course of three years, Aplāya will give 15 silver shekels to Ellil-šumu-ibni (as) his fees.

According to lines o. 4 and r. 1 of this text, Nabī-Ellil will be trained in “the precepts of the profession of the *nāru* musician” (*iḫzī nārūti*). The object of his musical training seems to be described in more detail in line o. 5 with the expression *nārūtu ša zimrī*. That expression literally might mean “the profession of the *nāru* of the *zimru* songs”. However, Johannes Hackl proposed a long restoration in his translation in order to connect *nārūtu* and *zimrī* as two independent terms¹³⁹⁷. That is a consequence of the previous research. Certainly, the *nārūtu* had always been discussed without any reference to *zimrī*¹³⁹⁸.

Hackl’s interpretation makes sense in light of the other mentions of *nārūtu* in this text. However, it omits the presence, between *nārūtu* and *zimrī*, of *ša*. That particle implies the existence of a genitive chain where *zimrī* depends on *nārūtu*. Therefore, we suggest that, what we have here, is a specialization of *nārūtu* focused in the mastering of the *zimru* songs. The name of that profession would be abbreviated in lines o. 4 and r. 1 since the exact content and consequences of that musical training are already explained in detail in lines o. 5–r. 1. The mention of a concrete specialization of *nārūtu* here makes sense in light of other contemporary legal texts with *nārūtu*. In those texts we sometimes find specializations of that *nārūtu*. We are going to comment that right now.

¹³⁹⁷ Hackl, 2007–2010: 16 (“den Musikerberuf (einschliesslich der Kenntnis sämtlicher) Lieder des gesamten (kultischen) Jahres”).

¹³⁹⁸ Oppenheim, 1952: 134 (“the articling of a slave(?) to an artist who was to teach him the art of singing”); CAD J, p. 47 (“instruct PN in the art of the singer”); CAD A1, p. 180 (“instruct PN in the art of singing”); AHW II, p. 749 (“*iḫzi* ^{lū}*n.-ú-tu* lehre sie!”); CAD N1, p. 382 (“teach her the musician’s art”, this translation forgets the *iḫzu*); Petschow, 1980–1983: 570 (“Musiker/Sängerkunst”) and, perhaps, Stol, 2016: 360. This one talks about “musical education” as the topic of this contract. For additional comments although without any translation, see Kedar, 2014: 539–540.

6.3.2. *nārūtu* in other Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid legal texts

6.3.2.1. *nārūtu* as “profession of the *nāru*” *lato sensu*

First of all, we would like to consider this excerpt of a text from Sippar:

Text 62. MacGinnis, 2002: 234, text n. 12 [BM 64026] (Cyrus 07-10-06)¹³⁹⁹

- o. 1 ^rzi-it-ta-a ^fši-iš-ka-^rtu⁴ ^r¹⁴⁰⁰
o. 2 ^ral-ti ^me-te₃-ru ^{lu}2ENGAR ^{ša}2 ^dUTU
o. 3 ^{ša}2 ^fsu-ud-du-uš-^rtu⁴ ^{DUMU.MUNUS}-su ^fNAR-tu⁴
o. 4 ^mu₂-bar-^ria ^rina na-ru-tu⁴ tu-li-du²-ma
- o. 1 Zittāya (is) an oblate
o. 2 and the wife of Eteru, farmer of Šamaš,
o. 3 whose daughter, Sudduštu, the *nārtu*,
o. 4 gave birth to Ubaria during (her) status as *nāru*.

Martha Roth¹⁴⁰¹ has proposed that the *na-ru-tu₄* of this text (referring to the oblate¹⁴⁰² Sudduštu) would not have any connection with music. On the contrary, that term would be an abstract form of **nu'artu* (“non-virgin”), a term connected with *batultu* (“virgin” (?)) in the 1st-millennium legal texts. This matter has divided the research¹⁴⁰³. However, we cannot share Roth’s opinion mainly because of her weak arguments. Certainly, she said that there are texts where *nāru* and *nārtu* might not necessarily designate musicians, as in two Neo-Assyrian colophons. In her first example¹⁴⁰⁴, Roth understood the chain *na-ru* as a reference to the youthful state of the “apprentice (*šamallû* = ^{lu}2ŠAMAN₂.LA₂) *āšīpu*” just mentioned¹⁴⁰⁵. However¹⁴⁰⁶, it is a bit redundant to have a “young apprentice”

¹³⁹⁹ Edition dependent upon MacGinnis, 2002: 234 with (minimal) corrections derived from our collation of the manuscript on 01/08/2019 in the British Museum.

¹⁴⁰⁰ CAD Š3, p. 106 has “*ši-iš-ka-tum*”, but that is an out-dated spelling for Neo-Babylonian times.

¹⁴⁰¹ Roth, 1987: 741–746 and Roth, 1989: 6–7, later followed by van Driel, 1998: 192–193.

¹⁴⁰² She had this status since her mother, Zittāya, was an oblate, according to Bongenaar, 1997: 296.

¹⁴⁰³ Van Driel, 1998: 192 translated *nu'artu* just as “function”, but seems to follow Martha Roth since he did not talk about music. Joannès, 2013 also translates this *na-ru-tu* as “status as a single woman”. However, on the contrary, MacGinnis, 2002: 234 translated ^fNAR-tu₄ as “singer” and *na-ru-tu* as “status as singer” as later Stol, 2016: 409 (“position of a singer”). Jursa, 1995: 7 n. 33 said nothing about this matter.

¹⁴⁰⁴ TDP, pl. 48–49 [AO 6680], r. 33 (CAD N1, p. 379; this edition, to the contrary of Roth’s opinion, supports our interpretation).

¹⁴⁰⁵ Roth, 1987: 746.

¹⁴⁰⁶ See CAD N1, p. 379 for a similar opinion to ours.

because an apprentice should be already young. Furthermore, we might understand here a reference to the *nāru*. Therefore, we would have in this text a reference to a young *āšīpu* and *nāru*. That makes sense since the *nāru* and *āšīpu* are mentioned together in the 1st-millennium ritual texts as we shall see later. Furthermore, about Roth’s second example¹⁴⁰⁷, we have references to young (*šamallû*) *nāru* musicians already in the Old Babylonian records from Mari¹⁴⁰⁸.

In this sense, we would like to see in this text a reference to the “profession of the *nāru* musician”¹⁴⁰⁹ *lato sensu*, since Roth’s arguments are not strong enough in our opinion. The profession of the *nāru* is also present in this another text probably also coming from Sippar¹⁴¹⁰:

Text 63. VS 6 169 [VAT 1180] (Darius I 00-00-00)¹⁴¹¹

- o. 1 ᵀEN¹⁴¹² u₄-mu [...] ¹⁴¹³-u₂-tu ina itⁱDU₆
o. 2 U₄.9.KAM₂ ša₂ itⁱAPIN¹ lu²DIR₂.LA₂-u₂-tu
o. 3 SAD.DU ša₂ lu²NAR-tu⁷ U₄.8.KAM₂ ša₂ itⁱAPIN¹⁷
o. 4 HA.LA-šu₂ ša₂ lu²DIR₂.LA₂-u₂-tu ša₂-lam-mu E₂-ᵀti¹⁴¹⁴
o. 5 ša₂ a-<na> kal ᵀMU.AN⁷.NA ša₂ ina E₂-UL.MAŠ E₂ diš-ᵀta⁷-[ri]¹⁴¹⁵
o. 6 m¹⁴¹⁶ARAD-an-nu-ni-tu A-šu₂ m¹⁴¹⁶DUB.NUMUN A lu²SADA-A.GA.DE₃[?] a-na¹⁴¹⁶
o. 7 e-piš-an-nu-tu a-ᵀna^{md} ᵀAG-PAP A-šu₂ ša₂
o. 8 d¹⁴¹⁷MARDUK-15-SUR A lu²SADA-A.GA.DE₃[?] ma-ḫi[?]-ru[?]

¹⁴⁰⁷ SCT 110 [Unknown], 18 (see CAD N1, p. 379 for edition and reference, we could not access the original publication for further details).

¹⁴⁰⁸ FM 9, p. 15 and 85 as a commentary for the text FM 9 27 [M. 13050], lo. e. 3 (Archibab T6585).

¹⁴⁰⁹ Stol, 2016: 409 (“the position of a singer”) in addition to MacGinnis, 2002: 234.

¹⁴¹⁰ See McEwan, 1981a: 10–11 and Oelsner, 1980–1983: 12 for general comments about this text.

¹⁴¹¹ Our own edition starting from the original copy, the translation given in NRV, p. 520 and the partial transliterations on CAD E, p. 240 and CAD Š1, p. 203.

¹⁴¹² For the Sumerogram EN = *adi*; see Schramm, 2010: 43.

¹⁴¹³ NRV, p. 520 n. 1 suspected another lu²DIR₂.LA₂-u₂-tu. However, according to the copy of this tablet, what we have here is different from the lu²DIR₂.LA₂-u₂-tu of line o. 3.

¹⁴¹⁴ NRV, p. 520 read “*bîta-an-n[i](?)*”. However, the -an- of this edition seems rather a -ti according to our consultation of the copy of this document.

¹⁴¹⁵ This part of the manuscript is damaged. In any case, we believe we found a sign IŠ, which helps to read the next sign as TA). In addition, the E⁷ulmaš was the Ištar’s temple in Sippar (Frame, 1993: 22).

¹⁴¹⁶ For a partial transliteration of this line, see McEwan, 1981a: 14. However, he has “A-Gada (Sippar)” when the possible signs for that “Gada” are a bit different from what we have in the copy.

¹⁴¹⁷ The last sign seems to be KUR. We are not sure of our transliteration, but, following NRV, p. 520, we read ma-ḫi-ru as a form of *maḫāru* with an incorrectly written sign RU (= ru).

^{o. 1} During the days [...] from the month of Tašrītu ^{o. 2} (until) the 9th day of the month of Araḥsamnu, ^{o. 6-8} Arad-Anunnitu, son of Šāpik-zēri, son of Sangu-Akkad, has given(?) to Nabû-našir, son of Marduk-ētir, son of Sangu-Akkad, for the(ir) performance ^{o. 2-5} the prebend of the butcher, the first amount of the prebend of the *nāru* of the 8th day of Araḥsamnu, (and) his share of the prebend of the butcher for the greeting of the temple for the entire year, in the E’ulmaš, the house of Ištar.

In this text¹⁴¹⁸ about the *šalam bīti* (“greeting of the temple”) ceremony of the E’ulmaš of Sippar, we find a mention of a first amount (**SAD.DU** = *qaqqadu*) of the prebend of the *nāru* (*nārūtu*)¹⁴¹⁹. The presence of the *nāru* is highly relevant, because the musical life in 1st-millennium Sippar¹⁴²⁰ is mainly known for the activities of the **gala/kalû** priest, like the performance of **balāḡ** and **er2 šem3-ma** laments or the use of the *lilisu*¹⁴²¹. However, we do not have much information on the activities of the **nar/nāru**¹⁴²². In the same way, *nārūtu* is mentioned after a reference to the profession of the butcher (*tābiḫu*; **lu2DIR2.LA2-u2-tu** = *tābiḫūtu*), something to keep in mind for the next section of this chapter.

Finally, we should have a look at this other (very fragmentary) text from Sippar:

Text 64. MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 83, text n. 3 [BM 70463] (00-00-00)¹⁴²³

- o. 4’ [...] *u3 mi-šil U4. 15²⁷(+).KAM2* [...]
o. 5’ [...] **lu2NA**R¹⁴²⁴-*u2-tu DEŠ.ŠUB.BA ina E2. BABBAR.RA*’ [...]
o. 6’ [...] *pa-ni-šu2 a-na u4-mu ša-a-tu4* [...]
o. 7’ [...] ^{md}X-*u2*]-*bal-liḫ iš-me-ši-ma* [...]
o. 8’ [...] ‘x’ *a-na lu2DUMU-u2-tu*¹⁴²⁵ ‘*id-din-šu11*’¹⁴²⁶

¹⁴¹⁸ In addition to NRV, p. 520, see Bongenaar, 1997: 289; Streck, 2001: 85, Sallaberger and Huber Vulliet, 2003–2005: 634 and Linssen, 2004: 60–61 for previous comments.

¹⁴¹⁹ Bongenaar, 1997: 289 (“cultic singer’s prebend”); Sallaberger and Huber Vulliet, 2003–2005: 634 (“Pfründe des Sängers”); Still, 2019: 249 n. 24 (“the temple-enterer’s prebend (cultic singer)”).

¹⁴²⁰ For Old Babylonian Sippar’s musical life, Harris, 1975: 172–175, and Shehata, 2009: 177–209.

¹⁴²¹ See Maul, 1999: 311 and 2002: 256–257; Linssen, 2004: 30 and Gabbay, 2007: 88, 102, 132, 158.

¹⁴²² See Bongenaar, 1997: 289 for evidence.

¹⁴²³ Edition dependent upon MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 83 and Wunsch, 2003: 231–232 and some corrections from our inspection of the copy from the tablet (not available for its collation on 01/08/2019).

¹⁴²⁴ Wunsch, 2003–2004: 232 thinks that **LUNGA2** might fit better here than **NAR**. However, a comparison of the signs ŠIM (**LUNGA2** = ŠIM×A) and LUL (=NAR) in the texts available on LaBaSi allows us to say that what we have in the manuscript (according to MacGinnis’s copy) is closer to LUL.

¹⁴²⁵ MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 83 has LUL. However, as Wunsch, 2003: 232 says, it might be a misreading. Certainly, in Neo-Babylonian script, signs LUL and TUR are not equal, and *ana mārūti nadānu* (“to give in adoption”) is known in other Neo-Babylonian texts. See CAD M1, p. 320–321 for evidence.

¹⁴²⁶ We follow Wunsch, 2003: 232 (which has *su*) but keeping in mind that 1) we should actually have *id-di-iš-šu*, 2) there is only the MacGinnis’ copy of the tablet, and 3) we could not collate this tablet.

- o. 4' [...] and half of the 15th day [...]
o. 5' [...] the profession of the [*nār*]u (as) prebend in the Ebabbar [...]
o. 6' [...] before him for the future [...]
o. 7' [...-u]balliṭ listened to it (= the tablet?) and [...]
o. 8' [...] he gave him for adoption [...]

Here, *nārūtu* is again mentioned independently. However, the expression **DEŠ.ŠUB.BA ina E2.ʾBABBAR.RA** (“(as) prebend in the Ebabbar temple”) of line o. 5’ invites us to think in an indirect reference to a specialization of *nārūtu* as “the profession of the *nāru* of the Ebabbar temple”. That brings us to our next section of this chapter...

6.3.2.2. Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid specializations of *nārūtu*

As mentioned, *nārūtu* sometimes designated the profession of a *nāru* worshipping a specific deity in some Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid legal texts. That already happened in Old Babylonian times with **nam-nar**¹⁴²⁷ and *nārūtu*¹⁴²⁸. Here is one of these texts, which comes from the Egibi/Nūr-Sîn’s archive¹⁴²⁹:

Text 65. Wunsch, 2003: 106, text n. 33 [BM 30515] (Nabonidus, 10-11-15)¹⁴³⁰

- r. 2 ʿe-ʾlat 4-ʾu₂ ʾHA.ʾLA-ʾš_{u2} š_{a2} ʾit-ti ʾŠEŠ.MEŠ-š_{u2} pa-ʾni ʾ^{md}za-ba₄-ba₄-ʾBA-ʾš_{a2}
r. 3 DUMU-š_u ša-ḥar ku-ʾma ʾš_{a2} ip-qid-aš₂-ši-im-ma a-na il-ki š_{a2} ^{lu2}NAR-ʾu₂-tu ʾ
r. 4 š_{a2} ^dEN la ib-ṭi-il u ma-aš-ša-aš₂-ʾtu₄ ʾš_{a2} ^{md}MARDUK-ʾDU₃-NUMUN ʾAD-š_{u2} ʾu₂-ʾšur-ru¹

r. 2-r. 4 In addition to his ¼ share¹⁴³¹ which (Zababa-iqīša will inherit) together with his brothers, he (= Marduk-bān-zēri) entrusted¹⁴³² unto Zababa-iqīša, his youngest son, to be concerned about the *ilku* service (of the inherited lands¹⁴³³), (but also) not to abandon the office of the *nāru* of Bēl and to keep the duties of his father Marduk-bān-zēri.

In this document, Zababa-iqīša is going to become *nāru* of the god Bēl. Such specialization makes sense if we consider a Seleucid text¹⁴³⁴ about the rituals of the

¹⁴²⁷ See our Chapter 3 for evidence.

¹⁴²⁸ See our Text 42 for reference.

¹⁴²⁹ Kessler, 2008: 89 n. 43. This text is described on LaBaSi without any musical reference.

¹⁴³⁰ Edition dependent upon Wunsch, 2003: 106 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy available on that publication, in addition to the collation of the manuscript on 01/08/2019.

¹⁴³¹ For comments about this sentence and the Marduk-bān-zēri’s life, see Baker, 2002: 18 n. 72.

¹⁴³² This verb (*ušadgil*, Š Preterit of *dagālu(m)*, “entrust”) actually appears at the beginning of r. 5. That section of the text already deals with the consequences of neglecting the clauses of this document.

¹⁴³³ They are described in o. 1–r. 1 of this text, not presented here due to their length.

¹⁴³⁴ Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 89–90; Linssen, 2004: 11.

second New Year Festival (in the month of Kislīmu) for the Eşaṅil of Babylon. That text talks about a *nāru* devoted to the gods Bēl and Bēltīya¹⁴³⁵. Said *nāru* could be the same person who recited the *Enūma Eliš* for Bēl on the 4th day of that festival and “stay” (*ušābu*) while the ^{lu2}DUMU.NID2.LA.LA recited a ŠU.IL2.LA2 prayer for Bēl and Bēltīya¹⁴³⁶.

The other text to be discussed here comes from the Nappāḫu’s archive in Babylon:

Text 66. *Dar.* 463 [BM 77393] (Darius I (x)+3-1-18)¹⁴³⁷

- o. 1 [DEŠ]. ŠUB. BA ^{lu2r}NAR*¹⁴³⁸-u₂-tu¹ pa-ni^r d^riš-ḫa-ra^r [...]
o. 2 [1]-en^r SAD. DU GU₄ u₃ 1-en SAD. DU UDU. NITA ša₂ NU <il>-lu^r?-[u₂](?)¹⁴³⁹
o. 3 u ḫa^r-ab¹⁴⁴⁰-su-ru-uk-ka^r la il-lu-u₂ ša₂ U4.8. KAM₂^r
o. 4 ša₂ it^r BAR₂ ša₂¹⁴⁴¹ mKA₅.A DUMU^r-ša₂^r mŠUM₂-na-a DUMU ^{lu2}SIMUG^r
o. 5 ina qa-at^{md} MARDUK^r-re^r-man-ni DUMU-ša₂ mki^r-din-nu
o. 6 DUMU^r mdEN-e-ṭe₃-ru a-na^r KU₃.BABBAR^r a-na ŠAM₂^r TIL-[tim]
o. 7 im-ḫu^r-ru u KU₃.BABBAR ŠAM₂ DEŠ.ŠUB.BA šu-a-tim
o. 8 mdMARDUK^r-re^r-man-ni ina ŠU.2 mKA₅.A TI^r-u₂
o. 9 [a]_{r2}-ki¹⁴⁴² 2 GID₄ KU₃.BABBAR mKA₅.A ut-tir-ma
o. 10 [a]-na mdMARDUK^r-re-man-ni id-din mS[U. dMARDUK]
lo. e. 1 DUMU-ša₂^r mdNA₃-na-šir DUMU mdEN-e-ṭe₃-[ru]
r. 1 ina imDUB KI. LAM^r ša₂ DEŠ.ŠUB. BA šu-a-tim
r. 2 a-na ši-bu-u₂-tu ina lib₃-bi a-ši-ib¹

o. 1–o. 8 (Concerning) the [pre]bend of a *nāru* before the goddess Išḫara (including) the head of an ox and the head of a non-choic[e](?) male sheep in addition to a non-choice(?) cut of meat *ḫabsurukku* of the

¹⁴³⁵ Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 93–100 [BM 32206 + 32237 + 34723 (S+ 76-11-17, 1933+1964 + Sp II 213) (+) F 220], o. ii 2 (Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 93–100).

¹⁴³⁶ *Ibidem*, o. ii 15–16, o. iii 24–25. See, in addition, Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 90.

¹⁴³⁷ Edition dependent upon MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 84–85 with corrections from our inspection of the copy of the tablet and the remarks of Baker, 2004: 136. In addition, we collated this tablet on 01/08/2019.

¹⁴³⁸ Most of the previous editions of this text have ^{lu2}NAR-u₂-tu¹ or similar (San Nicolò, 1947: 295; AHW II, p. 749; CAD N1, p. 382; MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 84; Baker, 2004: 38; Pirngruber and Waerzeggers, 2011: 140 n. 79; Sciandra, 2011: 140; NaBuCCo 8261). However, (beyond Peiser, 1890: 136 = *paḫ-ḫir*(?)*-tu*, untranslated) Achemenet (Strassmaier, Darius 463) has ^{lu2}DIR₂¹.LA₂-u₂-tu. MacGinnis’s copy depicts here a different sign regarding lines o. 4, 8–9, where we find the name Šēlebi (= mKA₅.A). However, like Strassmaier, *Dar.* 463 and our collation, what we find in o. 1 is similar to o. 4, 8–9.

¹⁴³⁹ Achemenet reads *nu-ur*-[x]. However, *nūru* (“light”) does not make much sense in this context. In addition, the expression *lā illu* (“non-choice(?)”) appears again in the next line of this text.

¹⁴⁴⁰ On the contrary to MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 84, we believe that this sign is AB and not DU.

¹⁴⁴¹ MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 84 forgot this ša₂ (“which”) in his translation. As a consequence, he forgot that *imḫuru* (o. 7) has the final -u for subordinate clauses. This might be the reason why, according to Baker, 2004: 136, MacGinnis’ translation does not respect the grammar of the text.

¹⁴⁴² We agree with Baker, 2004: 136: the sign seems definitely a damaged sign UB = ar₂. Second sign is KI and not DI according to the number of straight wedges in the interior of that sign.

8th day of the month Nisānu which Šēlebi¹⁴⁴³, son of Iddināya, son of Nappāhu), bought by its comp[lete] price to Marduk-rēmanni, son of Kidinnu, son of Bēl-eṭēri, and (then) Marduk-rēmanni took from Šēlebi the silver, the purchase price of that prebend, o. 9-r. 2 Šēlebi returned [la]ter two silver shekels, and he gave them [t]o Marduk-rēmanni. Erība-[Marduk], so[n] of Nabû-nāšir, descendant of Bēl-eṭē[ri], was present as a witness in (the drawing up of) the purchase tablet of that prebend.

The reference to a *nāru* makes sense here, since musicians perform several activities in the *akītu* New Year Festival, event which was celebrated in the month of Nisānu mentioned in line o. 4 our text. Among these activities, we find musicians (*nāru*) in the main procession of that festival¹⁴⁴⁴ or in the ceremony for “awakening” the temple, a ceremony to be celebrated 7th day of that festival according to the Uruk calendar¹⁴⁴⁵. In addition, they perform some activities in the 8th day of the Nisānu month of our text, like accompanying the golden chariot of Anu to its temple¹⁴⁴⁶, and pouring libations¹⁴⁴⁷.

In this sense, we might have in our Text 66 a concrete specialization of *nārūtu*, in this case as *nārūtu pāni Išhara* (literally “the profession of the *nāru* before Išhara”). In our opinion, it would be a singular way¹⁴⁴⁸ to make reference to “the profession of the *nāru* of (the temple of)¹⁴⁴⁹ Išhara”¹⁴⁵⁰. Certainly, the formula *pāni Išhara*¹⁴⁵¹ recalls, in a certain way, to some Old Babylonian specializations of the **nar**: the **nar igi suḥur-la2** (“the **nar** in front of the **suḥur-la2**”) and the **nar igi lugal** (“the **nar** in front of the king”)¹⁴⁵².

¹⁴⁴³ Peiser, 1890: 137 has as “Šillibi”, and later editions Šellebi (San Niccolò, 1947: 295; MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 86; Achemenet; van Driel, 2002: 80 n. 53; Baker, 2004: 135). *ṁše-el-le-bi* is well-documented in Neo-Babylonian texts (Baker, 2004: 369–370). However, **KA5.A** is *šēlebu* (“fox”) in Akkadian (Schramm, 2010: 79). Furthermore, Šēlebī might explain the *ṁše-le-bi* of Baker, 2004, text no. 233 [BM 77544], o. 3.

¹⁴⁴⁴ KAR 132 [VAT 7849], o. i 18’, 22’, 26’, r. i 14 (Linssen, 2004: 201–202).

¹⁴⁴⁵ TCL 6 39 [AO 6459], o. 7, 12 (Linssen, 2004: 185).

¹⁴⁴⁶ TCL 6 39 [AO 6459], o. 3 (Linssen, 2004: 184).

¹⁴⁴⁷ TCL 6 39 [AO 6459], o. 35 (Linssen, 2004: 185).

¹⁴⁴⁸ It has sense keeping in mind that this is the newest administrative text with *nārūtu* we have.

¹⁴⁴⁹ Precision from John MacGinnis (personal communication), to whom we give thanks for that.

¹⁴⁵⁰ Perhaps like CAD N1, p. 382 (“the musician’s prebend in the service of Išhara”). In any case, other translations are also good, like San Nicolò, 1947: 295 (“das Einkommen(srecht) der Sängerschaft vor der Göttin Išhara”) or MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 86 (“The prebend of ... a singer before Išhara”). See also Baker, 2004: 135 (“the singer’s [pr]ebend before Išhara”); Pirngruber and Waerzeggers, 2011: 140 n. 79 (“singer’s prebend”); Sciandra, 2011: 140 (“the perquisite of the *nāru*”). See, in addition, Van Driel, 2002: 80.

¹⁴⁵¹ We found nothing about music in Išhara’s cult. For the cult to that goddess in Neo-Babylonian times, see Prechel. 1997: 147–162.

¹⁴⁵² *Proto-lu2*, 646–647 (DCCLT).

6.3.3. Conclusions

As we have seen, *nārūtu* sometimes referred to “the profession of the *nāru*” *lato sensu* in some Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid legal texts. However, in other texts, that term designates a concrete specialization of the *nāru* according to the deity worshipped by that musician. However, in the case of our Text 66, that speciality is mainly musical, the performance of the *zimru* songs. This last speciality is certainly singular and it might be explained as a later innovation in the specialities of the *nāru*. However, we have seen in our Chapter 3 how the office of the **nar** also had some specialities according to a particular musical instrument, such as the **balāḡ** or the stringed instruments (**sa**). Perhaps this *nārūtu ša zimrī* should be considered as a sort of continuation of said former specializations.

6.4. The Seleucid Period

6.4.1. Introduction

This section will be based on these lines of a tablet written in Babylon the 13th of April 183 BCE. Their content is about an incantation of the *Compendium* exorcistic series¹⁴⁵³:

Text 67. CT 17, pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+]¹⁴⁵⁴

iv 18' **en2 saḡ-gig an-edēn-na i3-du7-du7 im-gen7 mu-un-ri-ri**
iv 19' **im-dub 24-<kam>**¹⁴⁵⁵ EZEN nam-LUL eš2-gar3 udug ḫul-ṛ meš' nu al-til

iv 18' Incantation: “The (demon of the) headache battles in the steppe,
and it blows there like the wind”¹⁴⁵⁶ (= **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**, IV, Incantation 1)
iv 19' 24th Tablet [...] Series **Udug ḫul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu* (“Evil demons”) series. Not complete.

¹⁴⁵³ Jiménez, 2013b: 153.

¹⁴⁵⁴ Edition dependent upon Schramm, 2008: 9 with corrections derived from our inspection of his copy of the manuscript (p. 339). Manuscript was not available for collation on 01–02/08/2019.

¹⁴⁵⁵ In this way, we try to keep in mind the grammatical considerations of Schramm, 2008: 9.

¹⁴⁵⁶ We follow Oshima, 2015: 249 (“Headache thrusts in the field, like a wind it blows”). Certainly, Linton, 1972: 79 (“Head disease butted in the steppe, blowing like the wind”) kept in mind the equivalences **du7** (“to push”; ePSD) with *nakāpu* (“to butt”; CAD N1, p. 156) and **ri** (“to impose”, “to pour out”; ePSD) with *zāqu* (“to blow”; CAD Z, p. 64). However, we should have **du7-du7** and **ri-ri** without verbal prefixes for “butted” and “blowing”. Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46 (“the headache demon circles around in the steppe and blows like the wind”) was grammatically correct, but not in the meaning of **du7** and **ri**.

The reading of the sequence EZEN **nam-LUL** in line iv 19' has generated much controversy in two main aspects. On the one hand, the reading of **nam-LUL** as **nam-nar** (“music”) or **nam-lul** (“falseness”). On the other hand, the reading of EZEN as **šer3** (“song”) or **kešda** (“cycle”)¹⁴⁵⁷. In the following lines, we shall try to arrive at a clear conclusion about the reading and the exact interpretation of this nominal chain.

6.4.2. EZEN **nam-lul** instead of EZEN **nam-nar**?

6.4.2.1. Exposition of the hypothesis

We shall study here a yet unpublished interpretation of this excerpt by Enrique Jiménez, who has kindly shared it with us for this study¹⁴⁵⁸. This reflection merits our attention since this author has edited a previously ignored section from the tablet containing our chain¹⁴⁵⁹. According to him, we should not read the chain **nam-LUL** as **nam-nar** (“music”)¹⁴⁶⁰, but as **nam-lul** (literally “falseness”). That word would act here as a strange way to qualify the term under the sign EZEN as “external” or “additional”. Jiménez chose the word **šer3** as reading of EZEN in this particular case. To his mind, the entire line would make allusion to an apocryphal text from the **Udug hul / Utukkū Lemnūtu** incantation series.

In order to justify his hypothesis, Jiménez establishes a connection with *Nabnītu*, IVa 329 (excerpt previously studied in the Neo-Assyrian section of this chapter). In contrast to us, Jiménez reads [š]er3 **nam-lul** and proposes, as its equivalent, the word *kamû* (“external”). That word appears in a Late Babylonian colophon¹⁴⁶¹ and its meaning would be close to the term *aḥû* (“uncanonical”) used to designate some apocryphal tablets¹⁴⁶².

¹⁴⁵⁷ Schramm, 2008: 9–10 vs. Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46.

¹⁴⁵⁸ Personal communication of Enrique Jiménez, to whom we give thanks for his invaluable comments.

¹⁴⁵⁹ Jiménez, 2013b: 153–154.

¹⁴⁶⁰ As Geller, 1995–1996: 245, Schramm, 2008: 9–10 and Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46.

¹⁴⁶¹ George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413], o. 2–3, le. e. 19'–20' (George, 1992: 162).

¹⁴⁶² See Rochberg-Halton, 1987: 328–329 for comments.

6.4.2.2. Discussion

Enrique Jiménez's hypothesis tries to contextualize the text **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**, IV Incantation 1 of our Text 67 in the group of texts belonging to the **Udug hul / Utukkū Lemnūtu** series. In the same way, it fits with the particular style of the colophon of that tablet, which was edited by Jiménez¹⁴⁶³. However, we find several problems in his argumentation:

- The author seems to contradict himself in avoiding a musical connotation for that sequence but maintaining the reading of EZEN as **šer₃**. Certainly, **šer₃** is equated in Neo-Assyrian lexical texts (the most recent ones for that matter) just with *zamāru* (“song”)¹⁴⁶⁴ and *šarāḫu* (“to sing a lament”)¹⁴⁶⁵. Therefore, we should translate **šer₃ nam-lul** as an additional “song”, and not “tablet” as Jiménez was suggesting.
- Even if **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**, IV Incantation n. 1 were not a chant, it might be in any case recited by a musician as a part of his/her text *corpus*. Certainly, the witch (*kaššāptu*) recited a *šiptu* incantation “like the musicians (*nāru*)” in an anti-witchcraft text¹⁴⁶⁶.
- Far from sharing the unusual style of the colophon of its tablet, our excerpt is even more correct than the original text. Certainly, our excerpt corrects the original hypercorrect form ***an-na-eden-na**¹⁴⁶⁷ by **an-eden-na** (“in the steppe (**eden**)”) as a part of the collation of the original text described in the tablet¹⁴⁶⁸. In this sense, why should we expect here a strange word like ***šer₃ nam-lul**, which is nowhere attested?

¹⁴⁶³ Jiménez, 2013b: 153.

¹⁴⁶⁴ CT 12, pl. 40–41 [K. 39], o. i 1 (DCCLT); Bezold, 1887–1888: pl. 3 [K. 4603], o. i' 2' (DCCLT).

¹⁴⁶⁵ CT 12, pl. 40–41 [K. 39], o. i 14 and 17 (DCCLT).

¹⁴⁶⁶ Abusch and Schwemer, 2016: 110 [W 22316], 2' (original publication).

¹⁴⁶⁷ Falkenstein, 1952: 72; DGS, p. 118. The entire text of CT 17, pl. 19–20 [K. 3169 + 7848], o. 1 (where that *incipit* is contained) is: **en₂' saḡ-gig an-na-eden-na i₃-du₇-du₇ im-gen₇ mu-un-ri-ri** (our own transliteration from the cuneiform copy). It cannot be understood as a reference to something happening “in heaven” (**an-na**) and “in the steppe” (**eden-na**) because the Akkadian version of that text just says “in the steppe” (CT 17, pl. 19–20 [K. 3169 + 7848], o. 2: *mu-ru-uš qa-q-a-di ina še-e-ri it-tak-kip ki-ma ša-a-ri i-zaq-qa*). We might transliterate, therefore, **an-{NA}-eden-na** with NA as an unnecessary sign.

¹⁴⁶⁸ CT 17 pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 20' (Jiménez, 2013b: 153).

- The Sumerian **lul** is well-documented in the Seleucid texts contemporary to our Text 67. In these texts, **lul** is used for describing something false/unreal (normally a “false dream”, **lul-la ku-ku**)¹⁴⁶⁹. However, it is also used for qualifying as treacherous those **a-zu** diviners and **šim-mu₂** priests who worked with the “words” (**e-ne-eḡ₃-ḡa₂**) of other people instead of their own or those of the deities¹⁴⁷⁰. This sense of **lul** as something false is closer to the meaning of **nam-lul** documented in Old Babylonian literary texts. In those texts, **nam-lul** is used to describe the treacherous plans of the fox (**ka₅-a**), who wants to carry its city to the river¹⁴⁷¹ perhaps in order to destroy it. In this sense, to see **nam-lul** as a way to say something like “strange” might suppose a misunderstanding of the actual connotation of that word.
- We find several risks in Jiménez’s procedure, like to compare Neo-Assyrian text (canonical version of *Nabnītu*) with our Seleucid Text 67, or making a hypothesis from a *lacuna* (like the Akkadian column of *Nabnītu*, IVa 329 = our Text 60). However, the most relevant is that Jiménez does not keep in mind that *Nabnītu*, IVa 325–344 only repeats the same Akkadian word in consecutive lines. Moreover, the equivalence of **bar** = *kamû* (“external”) is already established in line 335 (our Text 60 is the line 329). It is true that line 331 has a *kamû* as the equivalent of **izi šu hu-uz**. However, this *kamû* is a late form of *kawû* (“to burn”), that is, an equivalent of the Sumerian **izi šu hu-uz** of *Nabnītu*, IVa 331. Therefore, we would support the presence in our Text 60 of *kammu* (“literary composition”) as the equivalent of [š]er₃ **nam-nar** as we have already noted in the Neo-Assyrian section of this chapter.
- If we restore *kamû* as the equivalent of [š]er₃ **nam-nar/lul**, we should remember that the context of that word in the text George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413] (o. 2–3, le. e. 19’–20’) discussed by Jiménez is still uncertain. Basically, we lack of evidence

¹⁴⁶⁹ SBH 13 [VAT 214], o. 7’; SBH 14 [VAT 248 + 396], r. 9’; SBH 21 [VAT 288 + 318 + 553 + 1828 + 1858], o. 10; SBH 22 [VAT 283 + 401], r. 8; SBH 25 [VAT 406 + 1782], o. 11; SBH 26 [VAT 298 + 1736 + 1748 + 1791 + 1825 + 2178], o. 20’. In SBH 44 [VAT 555], r. 21’–28’, we find the variant **lul-la-bi-se₃** [...] **al-nu₂** (“to lie down in the falseness (?)”, perhaps “to sleep badly”). All the aforementioned texts are cited according to their respective editions on BLMS.

¹⁴⁷⁰ SBH 1 [VAT 269 + 272 + 285 + 417 + 438 + 1774 + 1705], o. 54–57 (BLMS); SBH 2 [VAT 247 + 1815], o. 10’–12’ (BLMS), and SBH 5 [VAT 427], o. 6–7 (BLMS).

¹⁴⁷¹ UET 6/2 217 [U. 17207,92], *passim* (Peterson, 2019b: 553) and *Proverbs* 8.b33 (ETCSL 6.1.08).

showing *kamû* in similar contexts¹⁴⁷². Certainly, Uri Gabbay translated *malsûtu* in that text as “lesson”. However, the traditional meaning of *malsûtu* (“reading”¹⁴⁷³) fits better with the scene of that text, where something is “read by the mouth of a scholar”¹⁴⁷⁴. That change might imply a dismissal of Gabbay’s translation of *kamû* as “external interpretations”. In fact, we think that “attached (parts)”¹⁴⁷⁵ might be a better translation for *malsûtu* in this context. Moreover, the sentence with *kamû* appears twice in the same text: at the beginning (o. 2–3, the usually cited part of this text¹⁴⁷⁶) and the end of the tablet (le. e. 19’–20’, a damaged section)¹⁴⁷⁷. In this sense, we do not deal with a “colophon”, just with a “scribal mark”¹⁴⁷⁸. Therefore, it is not so suitable to compare this text with our Text 67. In fact, the tablet of our Text 67 finishes in the lines edited by Jiménez, not in the lines we are studying here.

6.4.2.3. Conclusions

To sum up, Enrique Jiménez’s hypothesis is interesting for the understanding of our text. Furthermore, it comes from his experience with Late Babylonian colophons¹⁴⁷⁹ and expertise in 1st-millennium Babylonian literature in general. However, in light of the previous reflections and problems in his argumentation, we would definitely read here **EZEN nam-nar**, and not **EZEN nam-lul** as that author proposed.

¹⁴⁷² Gabbay, 2014c: 14 n. 7.

¹⁴⁷³ AHw II, p. 619; CAD M1, p. 171. This translation was also adopted by George, 1992: 162. Gabbay, 2016: 21–22 bases his translation of *malsûtu* as “lesson” mainly on George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413], o. 2–3 and le. e. 19’–20’ because of the Stative of *šemû* (“to hear”) contained in that line. However, we can listen to a lesson, but we cannot read a “lesson” (just the text exposing that lesson). In addition, Gabbay’s translation “the lesson of their external interpretations(?)” does not make sense to us. Certainly, we would expect “the lesson about...” However, we would need a preposition like *aššu* (“concerning”) for that sentence. This preposition, unfortunately, is not contained in this text.

¹⁴⁷⁴ George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413], o. 2: *ana pi-i UM.ME.A ša’-mu-’u₂* (own transliteration).

¹⁴⁷⁵ For this meaning of *kamû*, CAD K, p. 130.

¹⁴⁷⁶ George, 1992: 162; Gabbay, 2016: 14.

¹⁴⁷⁷ George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413], le. e. 19’–20’: [*ša₂-me*]-’*e*’ *ša₂ ka-mu-ti-šu-nu Z[I-ni] MU.’ME’ [...]* x *’TIL’.LA ’DAR’- [...]* (own edition starting from the copy of George, 1992: pl. 29).

¹⁴⁷⁸ Gabbay, 2016: 14.

¹⁴⁷⁹ In addition to Jiménez, 2013b, see Jiménez, 2013a: 403–405 and Jiménez, 2016b.

6.4.3. šer₃ nam-nar or kešda nam-nar?

6.4.3.1. Previous discussions

According to Markham J. Geller, we should read EZEN as **kešda** (*riksu* in Akkadian), a term referring to the ‘binding’ of several items together. In his opinion, the “usual interpretation” of EZEN **nam-LUL** as **šer₃ nam-nar**¹⁴⁸⁰ is not suitable since “this term is rare and does not apply to any known corpus of texts, and bears no special relationship to Udug-hul incantations”¹⁴⁸¹.

However, Geller does not make comments on other references to **šer₃ nam-nar** in that statement, and his evidence seems to contradict him when he talks about the term *šerkugū*¹⁴⁸². Certainly, the Sumerian **ser₃ ku₃** is mentioned very close to **ser₃ nam-nar** in several manuscripts from the Old Babylonian lexical text *Proto-lu₂*¹⁴⁸³. Moreover, **šer₃ ku₃** is mentioned in the **Udug hul / Utukkū Lemnūtu** series¹⁴⁸⁴ to which the EZEN **nam-nar** of our Text 67 is supposedly connected.

In any case, we shall give some arguments here to read **kešda nam-nar** instead of **šer₃ nam-nar** in our Text 67 not previously kept in mind by Markham J. Geller.

6.4.3.2. Evidence for the reading **kešda nam-nar**

We noted in the Neo-Assyrian section of this chapter that evidence for **šer₃ nam-nar** at that time was highly fragmentary and hypothetical. Consequently, we could not say anything certain about the nature of **šer₃ nam-nar** in this or later periods, like the Seleucid one. Additionally, the reading **šer₃ nam-nar** does not fit with the musical world drawn in

¹⁴⁸⁰ This is a tendentious simplification of the previous research. Certainly, Hunger, 1968: 123 had “ŠÌR.NAM.NAR”, but Schramm, 2008: 9–10 accepted “ŠÌR-NAM-NAR” and “KEŠDA-NAM-NAR” as possible readings without choosing any of them. In addition, Geller, 1995–1996: 245 and Geller, 2011: 253 have transliterated “šir-nam-nar” (respectively translated as “musical songs” and “cultic song”).

¹⁴⁸¹ Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46.

¹⁴⁸² On which, paradoxically, he bases his reflections as he mentioned to us personally (thanks for his feedback for our interpretations of this text).

¹⁴⁸³ MSL 12, p. 28 A [CBS 2241 + 9850 + 9851 + 11394 + N 4631 + 5222], r. ii 26–28 (DCCLT) and MSL 12, p. 30 S’ [Ni 5169], o. ii’ 6’ (DCCLT).

¹⁴⁸⁴ Tablet VII, 131 (Geller, 2015: 279).

the textual *corpora* involved in our Text 67: *Compendium*, **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, and **Udug ḫul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*. Certainly, we find in these texts only¹⁴⁸⁵ allusions to the *šerkugū*¹⁴⁸⁶, the sole song to be mastered by the *āšipu*¹⁴⁸⁷. In fact, the *āšipu* seems to act rather as an instrumentalist since a Neo-Assyrian lexical text¹⁴⁸⁸ equates **nar balan** and *āšipu*. This is very relevant¹⁴⁸⁹, since *Compendium*, **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, and **Udug ḫul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu* usually mention two instruments played the *āšipu*¹⁴⁹⁰:

- The “Big Bull Skin” (**kuš-gu4-gal**), perhaps a sort of drum per the term **kuš** which might make reference to the skinned membrane of that instrument¹⁴⁹¹. However, its identity and features remain unclear because of the bad state of preservation of the excerpts referring to that **kuš-gu4-gal**¹⁴⁹². This instrument was also used against the headache demon of **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, IV Incantation 1¹⁴⁹³.
- The “Mighty Copper” (**urudu-niṅ2-kalag-ga**), a copper¹⁴⁹⁴ bell, perhaps similar to the bell VA 2517 from the *Vorderasiatisches Museum* of Berlin¹⁴⁹⁵. It was sometimes

¹⁴⁸⁵ Except **Udug ḫul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, I 7’ (Geller, 2015: 45), where Enki is the “lord of song” (**en šer3-ra**).

¹⁴⁸⁶ **Udug ḫul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, II 46 and VII 131 (Geller, 2015: 73 and 279).

¹⁴⁸⁷ *Exorcist’s Manual*, 28 (Geller, 2018: 300).

¹⁴⁸⁸ **Lu2** Short 1, 205 (DCCLT).

¹⁴⁸⁹ We might compare it with *Maqlû*, VII 155 (Abusch, 2015: 188), where the warlocks are playing, like the *nāru*, the *ni’u* instrument (by the moment, unidentified).

¹⁴⁹⁰ Linssen, 2004: 215–224 [DT 15 + DT 109 (+ BM 32485) + DT 114, MNB 1848], 338–342 (Linssen, 2004: 221), a *mašmaššu* plays a *nigkalagû* instrument. Moreover, the mention of **kuš-gu4-gal** in **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, A, Incantation 1, 20 (Linton, 1975: 143) is preceded by a mention of a **lu2 mu7-mu7** incantation priest (literally a “person of the **mu7-(mu7)** incantation”).

¹⁴⁹¹ For its identification, see Schramm, 2008: 192, 196; Mirelman, 2014: 151.

¹⁴⁹² *Compendium*, Incantation 1, 52–57, 78 (Schramm, 2008: 97), and Incantation 9, 24–26 (Schramm, 2008: 143); **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, A, Incantation 1, 20 and 36 (Linton, 1975: 143–144) and C, Incantation 3, 27–29 (Linton, 1975: 200).

¹⁴⁹³ *Compendium*, Incantation 9, 24–26 (Schramm, 2008: 58); **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, C, Incantation 3, 27–29 (Linton, 1975: 200).

¹⁴⁹⁴ *Compendium*, Incantation 2, 11’–12’ (Schramm, 2008: 101); **Saṇ-gig-ga-meš**, A, Incantation 2, 7 (Linton, 1975: 148).

¹⁴⁹⁵ Panayotov, 2013: 83–84. For previous identifications, Rendu Loisel, 2015: 216 n. 11.

beaten with a stick to increase its sound¹⁴⁹⁶. According to the aforementioned textual *corpora*, its nature fluctuates between the wild¹⁴⁹⁷ and the divine, in this case, as an object ritually purified by the gods¹⁴⁹⁸. Moreover, the “terrifying splendour” (**me-lam₂**) of its sound¹⁴⁹⁹ was able to frighten (**ḥu-luḥ**)¹⁵⁰⁰ demons. In this sense, it became an essential musical-ritual instrument for the *āšipu*¹⁵⁰¹.

6.4.4. How should we define **kešda nam-nar**?

6.4.4.1. Introduction

The reading **šer₃ nam-nar** for EZEN **nam-LUL** in our Text 67 does not fit with the elements previously considered. In this sense, we should adopt the reading **kešda nam-nar**, but, what is its exact meaning? Schramm defined this term as “Zyklus der Sangeskunst”¹⁵⁰² while Geller defined it as “*riksu* of chanting” and “corpus of liturgy (lit. ‘song’)”¹⁵⁰³. These definitions fit well with **kešda/riksu** as “cycle” and the *rikis zamārī* (“cycle of songs”) of a tablet¹⁵⁰⁴ belonging to the 1st-millennium version of **Uru am₃-ma-**

¹⁴⁹⁶ **Udug ḥul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, VII 47–48, and XVI 120’–121’, 147’–148’ (Geller, 2015: 261–262, 527, 529–530).

¹⁴⁹⁷ We follow Rendu Loisel, 2015: 219, who keeps in mind its provenance from the mountain: *Compendium*, Incantation 1, 79 (catch line) and Incantation 2, 1’ (Schramm, 2008: 98–100); **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**, A, Incantation 2, 1 (Linton, 1975: 148).

¹⁴⁹⁸ *Compendium*, Incantation 2, 1’–25’ (Schramm, 2008: 100–101). See comments on that matter in Schramm, 2008: 195 and Rendu Loisel, 2015: 220–221.

¹⁴⁹⁹ *Compendium*, Incantation 2, 34’–37’ and 10, 41 (Schramm, 2008: 102, 151); **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**, A, Incantation 2, 17 and D, Incantation 1, 47 (Linton, 1975: 150, 210); **Udug ḥul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, VII 18–20, 47–48 (Geller, 2015: 254, 261–262, 268).

¹⁵⁰⁰ **Udug ḥul** / *Utukkū Lemnūtu*, VII 15–17, IX 48’, and XVI 120’–122’ (Geller, 2015: 253, 310, 527, 530).

¹⁵⁰¹ *BID*, Hauptritual A, IIa 66–67 (Farber, 1977: 131) mentions two wind musical instruments in an exorcistic ritual, the *ebbubbu* and the *šinnatu*. However, nothing is said about the identity of the musician of those instruments, but nothing prevent us from identifying it with the *āšipu*. See CAD Š, p. 201 for the identification of *šinnatu* and see Rendu Loisel, 2011: 329 and 2016: 174 for comments about this ritual.

¹⁵⁰² Schramm, 2008: 10.

¹⁵⁰³ Geller, 2018: 51 n. 46.

¹⁵⁰⁴ Volk, 1989: 74 text H [K. 7598 + 19304 + Sm. 1294], o. 4’ (Volk, 1989: 82).

ir-ra-bi¹⁵⁰⁵. However, *rikis zamārī* is found in a fragmentary context, and connections with the ^{meš}BALAD *za-ma-ri* of the other variant for this line of **Uru am₃-ma-ir-ra-bi**¹⁵⁰⁶ cannot be ensured¹⁵⁰⁷ since ^{meš}BALAD suggests an instrument. Moreover, neither Schramm nor Geller say nothing about other Seleucid allusions to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu*¹⁵⁰⁸. We are going to study now these allusions for our identification of **kešda nam-nar**.

6.4.4.2. Seleucid evidence for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu*

6.4.4.2.1. A Seleucid prebend of the *nāru*?

There are three texts for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* from the Seleucid Period including this first excerpt coming from a text about the sale of some temple prebends in Uruk¹⁵⁰⁹. Here, Marc Linssen, following Gilbert McEwan¹⁵¹⁰, saw a “*nārūtu* (singers)-prebend”¹⁵¹¹:

Text 68. VS 15 19 [VAT 8552] (Seleucid Era 109-09-24)¹⁵¹²

- o. 1 ^mNU.TEŠ₂ DUMU [*ša*₂¹⁵¹³ ^m*ina-qi₂-bit-^d60* ...] ‘x’ [...]
o. 2 *ina hu-ud ŠAG₄-^{bi}-š_u²*¹⁵¹⁴ [10]-‘*u-u*’[?] [...] ‘x x x x DU[?].MEŠ’ *ša*₂ GU₄.MEŠ *ga*[*b-bi*]¹⁵¹⁵
o. 3 *ša*₂ ‘*ina*’^{e2}[EŠ₃.GAL^{e2}*re-eš u* ^{e2}]‘*a*’-*ki-tu₄*-MEŠ *a-na gi-nu-u₂*
o. 4 ‘*a-na*’ [...] ^d‘60’[?] *an*-[*tu₄*] ^d30 ^uTU ^uIŠKUR
o. 5 [...] ^d[*n*]*a-na-a* ^dGAŠAN.EDIN ^dGAŠAN *ša*₂ ^{e2}SAD
o. 6 [...] DI]DIR.MEŠ *E₂-š_u²-nu gab-bi e₁₁-u₂*
o. 7 [...] IT]I-‘*us*’-*su* [...] +5-‘KAM₂’ [...] -‘*a gab*’-*bi* *ša*₂ KI ^{lu2}NAR¹⁵¹⁶. ‘MEŠ’

¹⁵⁰⁵ It is a variant of the 38th line of the XIX tablet of this text in the Konrad Volk’s edition (1989: 82).

¹⁵⁰⁶ Volk, 1989: pl. Ia–III [BM 38593], r. iv 24.

¹⁵⁰⁷ For a different position, see Shehata, 2009: 96 n. 514; Klein and Sefati, 2013: 101 n. 114.

¹⁵⁰⁸ Schramm, 2008: 10 n. 30 had a look only to other Old Babylonian mentions of **nam-nar**.

¹⁵⁰⁹ Corò, 2005: 447.

¹⁵¹⁰ McEwan, 1981b: 89 (the exact excerpt was copied on Wright, 2007: 377).

¹⁵¹¹ Linssen, 2004: 72. Previously, Sallaberger and Huber Vulliet, 2003–2005: 634.

¹⁵¹² Edition dependent upon Corò, 2005: 415–416 with some corrections derived from our inspection of the copy of that manuscript (VS 15 19).

¹⁵¹³ According to VS 15 19, the sign DAR (= *ša*₂) is actually missing.

¹⁵¹⁴ Corò, 2005: 415 has “*lib-bi-šú*”, but the first sign seems actually to be ŠAG₄ and not LUL (= *lib/p*).

¹⁵¹⁵ Sign BI (= *bi*) is missing in VS 15 19.

¹⁵¹⁶ McEwan, 1981b: 89 (followed later by Corò, 2005: 416) read NAR without arguing against the LU₂.DEŠTIN.MEŠ (“wine makers(?)”) of Doty, 1977: 222. Having checked VS 15 19, we agree with McEwan, 1981b: 89: sign LUL would be similar to the one in our Text 67.

- o. 1 Labaši, son [of Ina-qibīt-Anu ...] [...]
- o. 2 (has sold) with satisfaction in his heart, 1/[10] [...] the legs(?)¹⁵¹⁷ of all the bulls
- o. 3 which are for the regular offerings inside the [Ešgal] temple, [the Rēš temple and] the Akītu temples
- o. 4 for [...] Anu, An[tu], Šin, Šamaš and Adad
- o. 5 [... N]anā, Bēlet-šēri, Bēlet-ša-rēš
- o. 6 [...] (and) all the [go]ds associated (with) their temples
- o. 7 [... m]onthly [...] 5+[...] days, everything which is with the *nāru*.

Linssen confused *nārū* (“musicians”) with *nārūtu* (“the office of the *nāru* musician”). However, that does not happen in his reference to *ittinnūtu* as “office of the building master” instead of an expected translation as “building masters”. Moreover, he simplified McEwan’s interpretation. Certainly, McEwan only said that $\text{ša}_2 \text{KI}^{\text{lu}_2} \text{NAR.MEŠ}^{\text{1518}}$ was an indirect argument for proving the existence of a (then non-existent by the moment) “prebend of the *nāru*” in the Seleucid period. In any case, if we remember the texts about temple prebends noted in previous chapters, none of them made reference to a single prebend belonging to several musicians as Linssen tries to defend here. Therefore, we would just see here a reference to a group of musicians, just as Paula Corò has¹⁵¹⁹.

6.4.4.2.2. About a “musical festival”

Our second document is an astral-mythological commentary dated to the time of the *Diadochenkämpfe* (Early Seleucid Period, late 4th century BCE):

Text 69. Koch, 2004: 106–108 [BM 55466 + 55486 + 55627]¹⁵²⁰

- r. 25 [... PA]N ^ra ^r-bu-bu kak-ka-šu₂ GAL-a^r aš₂ ^r-šu₂ ša₂ ^dnin ^r-urta a-še aš₂-šu₂ an-^rni-i^r [...]
- r. 26 [...] ^rx i^r-qab-bu-^ru^r KI¹⁵²¹ ^rIZIN^r ^rNAM^r.NAR ^rša₂ U₄.17.^rKAM^r ina ^rKID₂.SIG^r [...]
- r. 25 [...] the flood, its great weapons. Because of the exit of Ninurta, because of that [...]
- r. 26 [...] it will be said at the “musical festival” of the 17th day (of the month Ṭebētu) during the afternoon meal [...]

¹⁵¹⁷ Corò, 2005: 417 translated “teste dei buoi” from DU.MEŠ. Following Schramm, 2010: 35–36, we should find SAD.DU.MEŠ. However, previous sign to DU (= DU) does not seem to be SAD. Keeping in mind the equivalence DU = *išdu* (“lower extremities”; CAD I-J, p. 235), we might translate DU.MEŠ as “legs”.

¹⁵¹⁸ This expression is mentioned again in this document in r. 3 (Corò, 2005: 416).

¹⁵¹⁹ Corò, 2005: 417 “con i *nārū* (cantori)”.

¹⁵²⁰ Edition dependent upon Koch, 2004: 108 with corrections derived from our inspection of the copy on STC, pl. 72 and the photo on the British Museum website. The tablet was collated on 01/08/2019.

¹⁵²¹ For KI as *itti* (“at”), see CAD I-J, p. 302 and Schramm, 2010: 83. KI.IZIN (= *ki-ezem*, “festival place”, see ePSD2 for evidence) does not fit well here. Moreover, we would need a preposition before that.

It is the first time in Mesopotamian history that we find a Sumerogram involving **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. However, the mention together with **IZIN**¹⁵²² (“festival”), the late date of the text, and the absence of an explicit equivalent of **nam-nar** = *nārūtu(m)* in earlier times invites us for reading **NAM.NAR** as *nigūtu* (“(joyful) music”) instead of the expected *nārūtu*. Certainly, *nāru* and *nigūtu* were mentioned together in some Neo-Assyrian royal inscriptions¹⁵²³. Furthermore, *nigūtu* appears in a Seleucid microzodiacal text, that is, an astronomical text of the same typology as the one we are considering now¹⁵²⁴.

In any case, according to a Neo-/Late Babylonian commentary of **Saḡ-gig-ga-meš**¹⁵²⁵, *nigūtu* seems merely to designate actually just the spontaneous consequence (to sing joyfully, to make merry) of a more general mood (to be happy), nothing specifically musical as **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. Moreover, according to a Seleucid ritual text¹⁵²⁶, the *nāru* used to sing in the celebrations for the 17th day of the month Ṭebētu. In this sense, we would still consider this **NAM.NAR** as a reference to the Akkadian *nārūtu(m)*.

This last information is useful for situating this “musical (**NAM.NAR**) festival (**IZIN**)” in the month of Ṭebētu as Julia Krul proved with several astronomical arguments¹⁵²⁷. We would dismiss, therefore, the Johannes Koch’s proposal for the month of Kislīmu¹⁵²⁸. It is true that festivals for the month Kislīmu in the Esānil had many musical performances according to a Late Babylonian ritual text¹⁵²⁹. However, nothing about music is actually known for the ceremonies on the 17th day of the month mentioned in our Text 69.

¹⁵²² We believe that the reading of sign EZEN for the word “festival” at Seleucid times was **izin**. This is supported by the text Langdon, 1919: 73–84 [Bod. S 302], o. 14 (BLMS), where we find ⁱ-zi-in**ezem**. That reading might explain the Akkadian *isinnu*. The Akkadian version of this text has *ina i-sin-nu* (“in the festival”), therefore, ⁱ-zi/si2-in is not an Akkadian gloss in the Sumerian version of that bilingual text.

¹⁵²³ *Aššurbānīpal* 3, vi 46–47 (RINAP 5 Q003702); *Aššurbānīpal* 4, vi 48–49 (RINAP 5 Q003703), *Aššurbānīpal* 6, vii 53 (RINAP 5 Q003705); *Aššurbānīpal* 7, vi 11”–12” (RINAP 5 Q003706).

¹⁵²⁴ *Gestirn-Darstellungen*, p. 15–34 [VAT 7847 + AO 6468], o. C Aquarius (= o. 12) (Monroe, 2016: 169) and r. C Aquarius (= r. 13) (Monroe, 2016: 172).

¹⁵²⁵ CCP 4.1.7.C.a-**Saḡ-gig** VII C [BM 48727 + 48741], o. 7’ (CCP). See Jiménez, 2016a for comments.

¹⁵²⁶ TCL 6 41 [AO 6460], r. 31 (Linssen, 2004: 247).

¹⁵²⁷ Krul, 2018: 130–132, 134.

¹⁵²⁸ Koch, 2004: 110 and 2006: 129.

¹⁵²⁹ Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 93–100 [BM 32206 + 32237 + 34723 (S+ 76-11-17,1933+1964 + Sp II 213) (+) F 220]. See p. 90 of that work for a synthesis of that aspect.

6.4.4.2.3. The text *corpus* of the *nāru*

Finally, we have our third text, published in 2005¹⁵³⁰. It is Late Seleucid (end of 2nd–early 1st century BCE)¹⁵³¹ copy of a Neo-Assyrian literary letter about the reaction of the Babylonian scholars to the Aššurbānīpal’s request for texts for his library in Nineveh¹⁵³²:

Text 70. Frame and George, 2005: 270–277 [BM 28825]¹⁵³³

- o. 8 [x] x kil[?]-’-a kul-’ lat[’] lu²DUB. SAR[’]-tu₂ gab-bi ne₂-me-’ q_i²’ d_e²-a u d_asal-’ l’ [u₂-h_i...]
o. 9 [BE iz]-’ bu[’] URU ina ’SUKUD[’]-e DAR-’ in lu²MAŠ.MAŠ-tu₂ lu²GALA-tu₂ na^{1?}-ru-tu₂ u kul-lat lu²D[’][UB.SAR-tu₂ ma-la ba-š_u-u₂[?] ša]
o. 10 [ŠAG₄ NID₂.]’ GA dMARDUK dEN GAL[’]-u₂ EN-ia₂ 12 lu²UM.ME.A.MEŠ ’an-nu[’]-tu₂ md30-’SUR[’] [DUMU m... m... DUMU m...]
- o. 8 [...] the totality of the repertoire of the scribe, all the wisdom from Ea and Asall[uhi...],
o. 9 [...] (the series of) *Šumma iz]bu* (and) *Šumma ālu ina mēlē šakin*, the textual repertoires of the *āšipū*, the *kalū*, the *nāru* (and) the s[cribe as large as they are],
o. 10 (and) what is among the properties of Marduk, the great lord, my lord. These twelve scribes, Sîn-ētir [son of ..., ... son of ...]

Line o. 9 of this text¹⁵³⁴ makes allusion to the omen series *Šumma izbu* and *Šumma ālu ina mēlē šakin*. In addition, we have in said line o. 9 the terms *āšipūtu*¹⁵³⁵ and *kalūtu*¹⁵³⁶, whose meaning as “text *corpus* of...” is well-known in the 1st millennium. Therefore, we would define *nārūtu* as a text *corpus* of the *nāru*¹⁵³⁷. Its meaning would differ from our Text 69, where **NAM.NAR** meant “music” in general. Moreover, unlike some authors¹⁵³⁸, we cannot this *nārūtu* as “the profession of the *nāru*”. The reason is that said meaning does not fit with the allusions to *Šumma izbu* and *Šumma ālu* in this text.

¹⁵³⁰ That makes more surprising the absence of references to this text (or Koch, 2004: 106–108 [BM 55466 + 55486 + 55627], r. 25–26) in the comments of CT 17, pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 18’–19’.

¹⁵³¹ It might already be from the Parthian Period (247 BCE–224 CE) according to its features and the scribal family mentioned in the colophon (Frame and George, 2005: 266, 270, 277; Goldestein, 2010: 200).

¹⁵³² Frahm, 2005: 43, contrary to the original publication (Frame and George, 2005: 270), saw here a letter from that king to the scholars of Babylon. However, Frahm’s interpretation seems not to be accepted lately (Beaulieu, 2010: 2; Goldstein, 2010: 199–200; Zorzi, 2011: 19 indirectly).

¹⁵³³ Edition dependent upon Frame and George, 2005: 272–274. The copy was used for correcting this edition. The tablet was not available for its collation on 01/08/2019.

¹⁵³⁴ For other aspects of this text, Garrison, 2012: 40; Beaulieu, 2017: 553; Finn, 2017: 70.

¹⁵³⁵ See Pedersén, 1986: 41–76 for the library hC/D/E81 belonging to a Neo-Assyrian exorcist family.

¹⁵³⁶ For *kalūtu* as the text *corpus* of the *kalū* lamentation priest, see Gabbay, 2014c: 124–140.

¹⁵³⁷ Compare with Frame and George, 2005: 275 (“song corpus”, followed by Fincke, 2017: 385).

¹⁵³⁸ Wee, 2017: 238 (“the arts of the musician”).

The presence of *nārûtu* as textual *corpus*¹⁵³⁹ in this line instead of *bārûtu* (“text *corpus* of the *bārû* diviner”) has previously been considered as a scribal mistake¹⁵⁴⁰. The reason is that *bārûtu* is much better documented than *nārûtu* in the 1st millennium¹⁵⁴¹. However, that proposal has some problems concerning the epigraphy¹⁵⁴². In the same way, it overlooks some important aspects about *nārûtu* and *bārûtu*¹⁵⁴³.

First, it is true that *bārûtu* is quite well-documented in the cuneiform texts¹⁵⁴⁴. Nevertheless, we do not have many allusions to that term together with the other terms mentioned in our Text 70: *āšipûtu*¹⁵⁴⁵ and, specially, *kalûtu*¹⁵⁴⁶. In addition, all those references come from the Neo-Assyrian Period. However, in the Seleucid textual documentation contemporary to our Text 70, the *bārû* diviner is mainly related to the dream interpreter (*šā’ilu*)¹⁵⁴⁷. However, said *bārû* is not professionally related with the *āšipu* sorcerer or the *kalû* priest as in our text.

Then, against the suppositions about the **nar/nāru** as an illiterate people¹⁵⁴⁸, we need to remember the existence of a library in Aššur, the iC6III-iB6III, belonging to a family of *nargallu* from the 8th century onward¹⁵⁴⁹. In that library we find tablets belonging to

¹⁵³⁹ Stevens, 2019: 188 n. 183 just says that *nārûtu* here is a textual *corpus* but there is no translation of this term, just a transcription of the Akkadian text. For her part, Fincke, 2003: 130 n. 152 talked about some texts belonging to *nārûtu*, defined as “musician’s lore”. Nevertheless, that author does not make any additional comment about possible texts belonging to that “musician’s lore”.

¹⁵⁴⁰ Frahm, 2005: 46 n. 9.

¹⁵⁴¹ Frame and George, 2005: 276.

¹⁵⁴² Frame and George, 2005: 276 compared signs BA and NA of the entire tablet for confirming that the first sign is NA (for *na-ru-tu₂*) and not BA (for *ba-ru-tu₂*). Frahm, 2005: 46 n. 9 talked about a confusion of the Assyrian shapes of signs BA and NA. However, according to their shapes in MEA 5 and 70 and MZL 14 and 110, we would not consider them so similar in Assyrian script as Eckart Frahm thought.

¹⁵⁴³ Thanks to Andrew R. George and Grant Frame for their feedback on our interpretations.

¹⁵⁴⁴ See AHW I, p. 110 and CAD B, p. 131–133 in addition to SAAo and CAMS/GKAB for evidence.

¹⁵⁴⁵ SAA 7 51 = ADD 1053 [BM 1882-5-22,533], o. i 9’, b. e. i 15’, b. e. ii 2’ (*bārûtu*) and b. e. ii 6’ (*āšipûtu*) (SAAo); SAA 10 160 = CT 54, pl. 57 + 106 [K. 7655], r. 13–14 (*āšipûtu*) and r. 17 and 31 (*bārûtu*) (SAAo). Moreover, *Compendium*, Incantation 5, 15 (Schramm, 2008) mentions a *bārû* diviner and *āšipu*.

¹⁵⁴⁶ SAA 7 49 = ADD 943 (+) 944 [BM 80-7-19,262], o. i 17’ (reference to *bārûtu*) and 19’ (reference to *kalûtu*), o. ii 11’ (reference to *āšipûtu*) (SAAo).

¹⁵⁴⁷ *Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi*, I 52 and SpTU 2 22 [W 22666,1 + 22666,2], o. i 27 (CAMS/GKAB).

¹⁵⁴⁸ Shulgi3Hymns, p. 19.

¹⁵⁴⁹ Pedersén, 1986: 34–41; Mirelman, 2008: 103; Fahdil, 2012: 34. In addition, keep in mind SAA 13 95 = ABL 13 440 [K. 493], r. 1, where the *nargallu* is writing a letter.

hymns, mythological narrations or incantations in addition to some daily administrative texts. That says that, at least¹⁵⁵⁰, those *nargallu* were literate, participated in a scribal education¹⁵⁵¹ and, why not, could have a sort of text *corpus* for their work.

Finally, Seleucid ritual¹⁵⁵² texts make references to the *āšipu*, the *kalû* and the *nāru*¹⁵⁵³ (normally mentioned in this same order¹⁵⁵⁴, just as in our Text 70¹⁵⁵⁵) as “scholars” (*ummânû*)¹⁵⁵⁶. In those texts, the three professionals (sometimes just two of them¹⁵⁵⁷) perform exactly the ritual tasks. That fact, which has its precedents in the Neo-Assyrian period (where the original version of our Text 70 should have been written)¹⁵⁵⁸, was possible because of their common condition as “cultic experts”¹⁵⁵⁹. Moreover, we should recall their common musical abilities, since, as we have already seen, the *āšipu* also knew how to sing and to use some musical instruments¹⁵⁶⁰. On the contrary, we do not know of

¹⁵⁵⁰ Fahdil, 2012: 34 suggested that these texts fit with the profession of the *nāru*. However, he is mixing two different figures: the *nāru* and the *nargallu*. As we have previously said, the *nargallu* was just a chief musician in charge of the organizational aspects of the musical performance, not a performer like the *nāru*.

¹⁵⁵¹ Mirelman, 2008: 103 and personal communication of Andrew George.

¹⁵⁵² Similar observations concerning magic are available on Ambos, 2011: 5.

¹⁵⁵³ KAR 132 [VAT 7849], o. i 18', 22' and 26' (Linssen, 2004: 201); TCL 6 41 [AO 6460], o. 33' (Linssen, 2004: 239); TCL 6 42 [AO 7439], o. 25' and r. 6' (Linssen, 2004: 246).

¹⁵⁵⁴ TCL 6 42 [AO 7439], r. 6' (Linssen, 2004: 239) mentions these professions in the inverse order: *nāru*, *kalû* priests and *āšipu* sorcerers.

¹⁵⁵⁵ In this sense, we might have a case of intertextuality between those Seleucid ritual texts and our Text 70, and not a scribal mistake as Eckart Frahm (2005: 46 n. 9) suggested.

¹⁵⁵⁶ TCL 6 38 [AO 6451], r. 45 (Linssen, 2004: 175).

¹⁵⁵⁷ TCL 6 39 [AO 6459], o. 12 (Linssen, 2004: 185) mentions the performance of songs (*zimirî*) by the *kalû* lamenter and the *nāru*. For a mention of *āšipu* sorcerers and *nāru* without the *kalû* lamentation priests, see TCL 6 39 [AO 6459], o. 35 (Linssen, 2004: 185).

¹⁵⁵⁸ *Aššarhaddon* 53, 13'–15' (RINAP 4 Q003282), *Aššarhaddon* 105, vi 25–27 (RINAP 4 Q003334), and *Aššarhaddon* 110, i' 3'–5' (RINAP 4 Q003339). There, *āšipu*, *kalû* and *nāru* are “those who have mastered the(ir) entire craft” (*ša gimir ummânûti ḥammu*).

¹⁵⁵⁹ Farber, 1995: 1903; Ambos, 2008: 501 and 2011: 5. In the Neo-Assyrian text SAA 20 31 = BBR pl. 56 [K. 8380], the *nāru* performs some tasks more typical of a priest: o. 24' (washing of the hands), r. 16 (to bring honey, oil and water to the pail of a bed), r. 20 (performance of some blessings). That clearly contrasts with the Ur III Period. There, the **nar(-nita₂)** was a professional of the entertainment usually connected with the bear trainers (**u₄-da-tuš**) and the snake charmers (**muš-laḥ_{4/5}**).

¹⁵⁶⁰ SpTU 2 16 [W 22758/1] about the ritual to be executed by the *āšipu* for the building a house (as we can see in r. ii 16) mentions the use of the **kuš-gu₄-gal** and **urudu-niḫ₂-kalag-ga** instruments (o. ii 14'–15'). We have not found evidence for the *šerkugû* songs in the Seleucid Period. However, an Achaemenid

any textual record about the hypothetical musical abilities of the *bārû* diviner. That complicates the defence of the presence of the term *bārûtu* instead of *nārûtu* in our literary letter—Text 70.

Therefore, in our opinion, the presence of *nārûtu* in our Text 70 is not at all as strange as Eckart Frahm believed¹⁵⁶¹. Furthermore, we can use this text for a new definition of the **kešda nam-nar** of our Text 67 to be delineated right now.

6.4.4.3. A new definition for **kešda nam-nar**

In light of the previous considerations, we might define **kešda nam-nar** as “group of tablets (**kešda/riksu**)¹⁵⁶² of the text *corpus* of the **nar (nam-nar)**”¹⁵⁶³. That text *corpus* would contain at some point the text **Saṅ-gig-ga-meš**, IV, Incantation 1 mentioned in our Text 67. Furthermore, as a part of that text *corpus*, that incantation might be recited by the **nar/nāru**, perhaps with the use of some musical instruments.

This recitation of an incantation by a musician would be possible because the *āšipū* and the *nāru* collaborated together as “scholars” (*ummânū*) in ritual activities according to the 1st-millennium ritual texts. The origin of that collaboration, as we have also previously noted, might be based on the musical knowledge possessed not only by the *nāru*, but also by the *āšipu*. Certainly, that figure was able to perform some types of chants (like the *šerkugū* songs) and to play some musical instruments, like the “Big Bull Skin” (**kuš-gu4-gal**) and the “Mighty Copper” (**urudu-niṅ2-kalag-ga**).

That fact might cause occasional overlaps between the texts and the activities of those professions¹⁵⁶⁴. We are in face of one of those situations. In this case, an incantation (usual domain of the *āšipū*) would actually be performed by the *nāru* as if it were, for instance, a royal praise hymn.

manuscript for *Exorcist's Manual*, 28, SpTU 5 231 [W 23293/04], still mentions in r. 7 those songs. Therefore, we suspect that they might still have been performed by the *āšipu* during the Seleucid Period.

¹⁵⁶¹ Frahm, 2005: 46 n. 9.

¹⁵⁶² For this meaning, see CAD R, p. 351 4e.

¹⁵⁶³ Or, perhaps better, “music(al) text *corpus*” since we have **kešda nam-nar**, not **kešda nam-nar-ra**. This procedure is similar to the one we have done with **s/šer3 nam-nar**. There, **nam-nar** acts as an adjective of **s/šer3**, not as a *nomen rectum*. Otherwise, we would have **s/šer3 nam-nar-ra**.

¹⁵⁶⁴ For some comments, also common to other disciplines at that time, see Geller, 2018: 295–296.

6.5. General Conclusions of the Chapter

It is complicated to make any conclusion about **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* in the 1st millennium BCE for two reasons.

First, pay attention to our Neo-Assyrian texts, that is, those texts occupying approximately the first part of the 1st millennium. In those texts, the presence of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* is sometimes merely hypothetical, as in our Text 59. In other cases that presence has been only proved recently. That is the case of our Text 60, where we have read an allusion to **šer₃ nam-nar** for the first time in the research on this text. In this sense, our considerations about **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* in the 1st millennium mainly concern just to the second half of the millennium in an uncertain extension. We say “uncertain extension” since our Text 70 is between the Late Seleucid and the Parthian Period without a precise date.

Secondly, as we saw in the introduction of this chapter, we do not have yet any reference to **nam-nar** and/or *nārūtu* in any Middle Babylonian/Assyrian text. In this sense, it is more difficult to establish any continuity or innovation regarding our many texts with **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* from the Old Babylonian Period and from earlier times.

In any case, we can establish the following conclusions concerning **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* in the 1st millennium BCE:

- The meaning of **nam-nar** (and, by extension *nārūtu(m)*), since we are actually dealing with a Sumerogram **NAM.NAR**) as “music” persisted until the last stages of cuneiform culture. We find that in our Text 68, an astral-mythological commentary from the early Seleucid Period, one of our last texts of a certain date. Certainly, that text has in its final lines a reference to a “musical (**NAM.NAR**) festival (**IZIN**)” without any possible reference to other abstract musical terms like, for instance, *nigûtu*. We might keep in mind also the Neo-Assyrian evidence (as fragmentary it is) discussed at the beginning of this chapter. Certainly, our Text 58 referred to an “instrument of music” (*enûtu ša nārūti*). Moreover, our Texts 59 and 60 referred to a “musical (**nam-nar**) text to be sung (**šer₃**)”, that is, the term **šer₃ nam-nar**.
- Like in Old Babylonian legal texts and in spite of some relatively controversial cases (mainly our Texts 62 and 64, and perhaps also 66), Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid texts mention *nārūtu* as the office/condition of the *nāru*. This office or condition knew

some specializations in those texts according to the deity worshipped. This is the case of our Texts 64 (about a *nāru* “in” (*ina*) the Ebabbar temple), 65 (about a *nāru* of the god Bēl) and 66 (about a *nāru* “in front” (*pāni*) of the goddess Išhara). However, we also know of other specializations according to the instrument or, as in this case, songs performed by the *nāru*. Such is the case of our Text 61, where an individual, Nabī-Ellil, is going to learn the “office of the *nāru* of the *zimru* songs” (*nārūtu ša zimrī*).

- Our Texts 67 and 70 referred to a meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* unknown until the 1st millennium: the text *corpus* of the **nar/nāru**. It is true that the notion of this text *corpus* has been much debated. The origin of this debate might be in the reference to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* with incantations instead of royal/divine praise hymns or other “more typical” texts of those musically performed by the musicians. In any case, beyond the particularities of both of these texts, we should remember, in defence of this “text *corpus* of the **nar/nāru**”, that our Seleucid ritual texts often show the *nāru* and *āšipu* (besides the *kalû*) interacting with each other in the same ritual tasks. As we have said before, that fact was possible because these three professionals had a certain expertise in cultic activities. In addition, they could each play some instruments or intone several chants.

Therefore, although the meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu* as “music” is much “eroded” in our 1st-millennium texts vis-à-vis earlier times, we might still maintain for this 1st-millennium our hypothesis that the main meaning of both terms was “music”. However, some secondary meanings (“office of the **nar/nāru**” and “text *corpus* of the **nar/nāru**”) also existed for these two terms at that time.

In any case, these conclusions should definitely change with the publication of new texts, not only from the 1st millennium, but also from the second half of the previous millennium. Certainly, any reference from that period will be useful in the establishment of connections with the Old Babylonian (and earlier) evidence for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu*.

7. CONCLUSIONS

7.1. Introduction

As we said in the introduction to this study, there is a scientific agreement nowadays about the non-existence of a word for “music” in Sumerian or Akkadian. In the same way, according to the main researchers on Mesopotamian music, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* would make reference to many musical aspects. However, they would not be related to the idea of music as calculated sound like in our modern Western World.

In the introduction, we noted problems with each of the previous positions about this topic, and we offered some counter-arguments for minor aspects of those positions. As a consequence of that, we made reference, among others, to the possible notion of “music” as sound in some excerpts from *Šulgi B* or the existence of words for “music” in several ancient and modern non-Indoeuropean languages around the world. However, the most important problem we detected in that analysis of the previous research is that very few texts containing **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* had been used for those conclusions.

Therefore, we found it convenient to perform an in-depth analysis of all the references to these two terms, including those new references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* published after the last reflections on this topic. Our objective with that was trying to see if that scientific statement was still consistent and how much.

7.2. Problems for any type of conclusion

After having performed said analysis, the first idea we should highlight is that there are many difficulties for saying anything about **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* according to our current number of texts, and their preservation state, in addition, of course, to the inherent problems of each one of those texts individually.

Certainly, concerning the Old Akkadian Period (Texts 1–2), we saw how the chains traditionally understood as **lugal-nam nar** and **sipa-nam nar** (that is, two persons who would work as musicians) could be also understood as **lugal-nam-nar** and **sipa-nam-nar**. That would make sense with other personal names from that time. However, since both names were contained in mere personnel lists, it is difficult for us to say anything else about the possible meaning (or not) of that **nam-nar** as “music”.

A similar thing happened concerning the 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš since, beyond the *Gudea Cylinders* (= Text 4), our possible references to **nam-nar** in other texts (= Text 3) were uncertain. Concerning the Ur III Period, it is astounding that, while we have a large textual *corpus* in general with many references to the **nar**, we have only a single sure reference to **nam-nar** (= Text 5). Beyond that, we have a sole possible (but uncertain) reference to **nam-nar** (= Text 6). At the end of this 3rd millennium, we find our earliest *nārūtu(m)* (= Text 7–8). We have chronologically situated them in the transition to the 2nd millennium BCE, but there have been many debates about their exact chronology.

The Old Babylonian Period, by the 2nd millennium BCE, contains many references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*. However, these are problematic in several senses, especially for southern Mesopotamia. Certainly, we cannot know many basic things about our (many and complex) literary references to **nam-nar**—such as their (approximate) creation date, region, or author—. In this sense, we cannot contextualize them properly. A more precise context would help us, among other things, to distinguish how realistic are those allusions to **nam-nar** in light of the references to that same term in the contemporary legal documentation. Certainly, in those texts, **nam-nar** does not mean anything beyond “office/prebend of the **nar**”. In any case, as an exception, in our Text 28, *nārūtu* as “music” fits very well in the context described in that text.

This aporia could be solved keeping in mind the case of the Old Babylonian Mari, where all our references to *nārūtu(m)* are contained in a single type of text (letters). That remains in contrast to southern Mesopotamia, where we had not only literary and legal texts, but also texts from the scribal elementary curriculum.

In any case, we should keep in mind the geographical distance between Mari (in northern Mesopotamia) and Nippur (where most of our texts with references to **nam-nar** come from) and other cities in southern Mesopotamia. In the same way, Mari represents an *unicum* in northern Mesopotamia. Certainly, we saw how, in the Old Assyrian texts, we only find references to *narūtum*, a type of malt. In the same way, concerning Neo-Assyrian times, already by the 1st millennium BCE, our references to **nam-nar** and/or *nārūtu(m)* were usually uncertain. That is certainly a pity considering how rich the Neo-Assyrian textual documentation is in general.

The transition between the 2nd and 1st millennia is the biggest problem we have currently. Certainly, there is no Middle Assyrian or Babylonian text with **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* yet known, despite our attempts to find such terms in that corpus. The unpublished texts we surveyed only referred, unfortunately, to the *nāru*. In any case, since

the musical world in those texts has still been very little explored, we do not rule out that future research on that corpus might be able to find some references to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*, probably in connection with other musical terms.

Finally, in 1st-millennium southern Babylonia, our legal documentation (mainly from Achaemenid times) is more or less uniform in talking about *nārūtu(m)* as “office of the *nāru*”. That documentation distinguishes specializations of that office according to the deity worshipped or the instruments played by said musician. It is in our literary texts where, however, we find more problems. Among them, the different readings and interpretations of EZEN NAM-LUL (**šir₃ nam-nar**, ***šir₃ nam-lul** and **kešda nam-nar**) in our Text 67, the NAM.NAR in the Akkadian astral-mythological commentary Text 69, or the epigraphic problems with signs BA (= *bārūtu*) and NA (= *nārūtu*) in our Text 70. In addition, as a general remark, we should remember the late and somewhat vague chronology of these texts. This late chronology might have something (possible) consequences on the meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*.

7.3. **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* as “music”

In any case, according to our previous analysis, our two terms might make reference to music *lato sensu* in many of the texts studied here. It is important to stress that **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* seem to have this meaning—“music”—in our Texts 4 (from the 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš) and 69 (from the Early Seleucid Period). In other words, **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* might mean “music” in our earliest (sure) reference to **nam-nar** and one of the latest ones to *nārūtu(m)*. Other meanings for these two terms only appeared in the middle of that chronological span.

Sometimes, we have established “music” as the meaning for a reference to **nam-nar** or *nārūtu(m)* since our context is not precise enough for establishing a different meaning for those terms. This is the case of our Texts 5, 6 and 28 of a legal-administrative nature. However, it is also the case of our Text 41, a literary text where **nam-nar** is mentioned in an uncertain context. In those cases, we thought that the translation “music”, instead of the more concrete translation “office of the **nar/nāru(m)**”, was convenient in order to not dismiss *a priori* any possibility for **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)*.

At other times, this meaning as “music” fits well since we deal with a reality concerning several types of instruments and/or musicians. This is the case of some Sumerian texts, as our Text 12. That text was a model contract about the teaching of the

asila₃ of the **tige**_x and **a-da-ab** chants besides the “music(al sounds) (**nam-nar**)” of the **ṁeštigidla**_x (an instrument never played by the **nar**). We might recall also our Text 22 (an excerpt from *Enkihejal and Enkitalu*) where different vocal and instrumental elements are mentioned together in connection with **nam-nar**. There also some Akkadian texts where the meaning of *nārūtu(m)* as “music” comes from a similar fact. This is the case of our Texts 44–52 from Mari.

However, there are some texts where **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* definitely have the meaning of “music”. Let us, at this moment, make reference to these:

- In our Text 4, from the 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš (that is, 3rd millennium), **nam-nar** describes the perfect (**šū du7-a**) activity of three musical instruments. Those instruments were the **se-em** cymbals, the **a2-la2** (giant) drum and the **balan** lyre, more concretely, the beloved Ninjirsu’s **balan** called **ušumgal kalam-ma**.
- In our Texts 33 and 39, already in the Old Babylonian Period, Šulgi and Išmē-Dagān claim to have devoted themselves to music (**nam-nar**). In those claims, they make reference to the different instruments and chant(s) (techniques) they mastered. It is important to highlight that those musical elements also referred to the world of lamentations. That is the case of our Text 40, where Išmē-Dagān claims to have mastered the “difficult aspects of music” (**nam-nar-a ki bal-bal-la-bi**) and, at that moment, he makes reference to the **šag4 ser3 še11(LUL)-da**, the action of “soothing” (**še11**) the heart (**šag4**) with the **ser3** songs. The activity of those kings also included some more theoretical aspects of music. Certainly, in our Text 35, Šulgi talks about his familiarity with the “(deep) sense of music” (**šag4 nam-nar-ra**). That term should designate a quite abstract concept/entity keeping in mind the description of that **šag4 nam-nar-ra** in our Text 25 (an excerpt from *The Father and his rude Son*). In that text, this term is described as something “distant” (**su3-ud**) from the human understanding as the ocean shores.
- In our Texts (22), 23, and 52, some people are described as “not fit” (**nu-ub-du7** in the Sumerian Text 22, *ul redī* in our Akkadian Text 52) for “music”. That implies that these people were neither ready/sufficient to perform (some) musical tasks. However, that would also imply that could not do other less musical activities but still relevant

in terms of the behaviour and “manners” of a good musician. We can see that in our Text 23, where we find references to the respect/greeting of other people.

We should remember also those texts where **nam-nar** and *nārūtum* acted like an adjective (“musical”) describing an instrument (Texts 13, 55–58) or a sung text (Texts 37–38 and 59–60, about the expression *s/šer₃ nam-nar*) during the 2nd millennium BCE. In addition, our Texts 67 and 69 from the 1st millennium describe, respectively, a “musical” group of tablets (**kešda nam-nar**, expression which we see also as “group of tablet of the text *corpus* of the **nar**” in line with our Text 70) and a music festival (**IZIN NAM.NAR**). However, the most important texts to be considered here are the following:

- In our Text 34 (= *Šulgi B*, 157), the expression **nam-nar šu du₇-a** might describe the perfect sound of the **tige₂** and **a-da-ab** drums. Perhaps that expression was a (literary) elaboration of the meaning of that same expression contained in our Text 4 (= *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20–22), an excerpt where **nam-nar šu du₇-a** designated the perfect music(al action) of the **se-em**, **a₂-la₂** and **balaj** instruments. In any case, this meaning of **nam-nar** as “musical sound” would not be an exception in southern Mesopotamia. Certainly, we can also find it in our Text 12, where <**nam**>-**nar** ^{neš}**tigidla_x** cannot designate the profession of the **nar** of the ^{neš}**tigidla_x** since that instrument was never played by the **nar**. In addition, a reference to the musical sound (**nam-nar**) of the ^{neš}**tigidla_x** might make sense with the reference, in the same text, to the **asila₃** cry of the **tige_x** and **a-da-ab** songs.
- Our Text 48, from Mari, is also very relevant. Certainly, Rîšīya said in that text to have made music (*nārūtam epēšum*) with the sons of Muḥaddum. Until this point, we might translate that expression as “to perform the office of the *nārum*” as we have, for instance, in our Text 42. In that text, said expression referred to a musician of the god Āmûm. However, Muḥaddum’s answer (*šūma ittikama ēpuš*, “make it with yourself”) is interesting for our hypothesis. Certainly, it makes reference to something which could be “performed” with other people or with oneself, as music.
- Finally, our Text 49, also from Mari, contains the sentence *u nārūtam ana lâ’im īpeš* (“and he performs music for Lâ’ûm”) where, as we noted in our Section 5.2.2.6, the

name Lâ'ûm can be hardly applicable to a city. In that section we noted, among other things, that we have the preposition *ana* (“for”) and not *ina* (“in”) in this excerpt.

Therefore, in our opinion, **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)* not only designated the music *lato sensu*, but also the music as something pertaining to the musical sounds and their use, just as in our word for “music”. Some people have defined **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)* just as “ceremonial music”, while **nam-gala/kalûtu(m)** would designate the music used for the lamentations. That would be in line with the main professional occupations of the **nar/nāru(m)** and the **gala/kalû(m)**. However, we have argued in several parts of this study that **nam-gala/kalûtu(m)** never meant something like “lamentation music”. Certainly, that term only referred to the office of the **gala/kalû(m)** priest (not musician) or to a group of those priests. Moreover, in the 1st millennium, this term referred also the text *corpus* of the *kalû(m)*. In fact, we already find in *nigûtu(m)* a term for “joyful music”. In this sense, there was no reason for having another reference to that type of music in **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)*. In any case, as we have previously seen, *nigûtu(m)* should be mainly understood as a consequence (“make music/merry”) of a contextual mood (“to be happy”) and not something specifically musical, as **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)*.

7.4. About other meanings for **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)*

In any case, as a part of the changes occurring throughout the Mesopotamian world during its long history, the meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)* underwent some changes. Certainly, it is possible that the meaning as “music” that we are defending for these two terms were already a bit “eroded” in the 1st millennium BCE. Certainly, for instance, we found some (reasonable) doubts about reading the Sumerogram **NAM.NAR** of our Text 68 as *nārûtu*. However, the main change we have detected regarding our terms **nam-nar** and *nārûtu(m)* seems rather to concern to their transformation from an original nature as words with a single meaning to a final stage where they pertained to three different (musical) things more or less at the same time.

Thus, by the 3rd millennium, **nam-nar**, and perhaps *nārûtu(m)*, would mean “music”, the main example of that being our Text 4, *Gudea Cylinders*, B15.20–22. By the end of that millennium, we already find our first references to these terms as “office of the **nar/nāru(m)**”, just as in our Text 7–8. That meaning would consolidate its presence in our documentation by the Old Babylonian Period. At that moment, that meaning would

become frequent in our legal texts and some letters, as in the case of Mari. Elementary scribal curriculum texts and literary texts, in addition to those letters from Mari, would make reference, on the contrary, to **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* as “music” with different scopes. Finally, by the 1st millennium, we find three different meanings for **nam-nar/nārūtu(m)**: “music” (as in our Text 69 besides our Neo-Assyrian Texts 58–60), “office of the **nar/nāru(m)**” (our Neo-Babylonian and Achaemenid legal Texts 61–66) and “text *corpus* of the **nar/nāru(m)**”. This last meaning is found in our Text 70 besides our Text 67. In any case, the condition of **nam-nar** in that text as an adjective (“musical”) would fit better with the grammar (we have **kešda nam-nar**, not **kešda nam-nar-ra**).

7.5. Final statement

The main meaning of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* was “music” throughout most of the long history of Mesopotamia, at least from the middle 3rd millennium until the final centuries of the 1st millennium BCE. Other meanings for these words appeared later in our texts: “office of the **nar/nāru(m)**” (from the 2nd millennium onward) and “text corpus of the **nar/nāru(m)**” (by the 1st millennium BCE). In addition, some of these meanings appear only in a specific type of text. This is the case of **nam-nar** and *nārūtu(m)* as “office of the **nar/nāru(m)**”, a meaning appearing mainly in our legal texts.

Therefore, contrary to the previous, commonly held understanding, there was actually a word for “music” in ancient Mesopotamia in line with other modern and ancient cultures and their languages around the world. In this way, Assyriologists in the future will be able to study the conceptualizations of music in Mesopotamia.

8. INDICES

8.1. Terminological index

8.1.1. Common People

Akšaya	189 n. 1295
Aplāya	206
Arbītum	65 n. 471, 66 n. 476
Atimatum	66 n. 476
Damiq-ilīšu	99
Dudu-Kalla	91
Du-iliam	69 n. 508
Egibi	211
Ellil-šumu-ibni	206
Ellil-īpuš	194
Enkiheḡal	103
Enkitalu	103
Geme-Dumuzida	57–61
Geme-Iškur	55
Gumul-Dagān	179
Ḥaṣrī-Āmîm	172
Ḥitte	191
Ilī-ippalsam	83 n. 599
Ilī-šummid	67, 71, 172
Ilšu-ibbīšu	179, 187–190, 194–195
Imgur-Šamaš	189–190
Inaya-Šamaš	187
Ipatum	98 n. 691
Išar-Lîm	191
Kinibši	65 n. 471, 66 n. 476
Ku-Enlila	166
Kulpen-dayyān	172 n. 1195

Kulpi-Atal	172
Lipit-Ellil	189–190
Lu-diņira	161
Lugal-gabari-nutuku	91
Lugal-ḥeņal	99
Lugal-nam	38–39
Lugal-namdag	39
Lugal-namdu	39
Lugal-namgusu	39
Lugal-namme	39
Lugal-nammes	39
Lugal-nammuru'e	39
Lugal-namtare	39
Lugal-namzitar(a)	39
Lu-Ninurta I	91, 93
Marduk-bān-zēri	211
Muḥaddum	184–185
Nabī-Ellil	206–207, 230
Nannā	161
Nanna-manšum	178–179
Nappāḥu	212
Nin-Ezem	56–61
Nūr-Sîn	211
Pāpā	55 n. 393, 58, 62
Rišīya	175, 177, 179, 181–182, 184–185, 187, 190, 192–193, 197
Samim (<i>^Psa-mi-im</i>)	109–110
Sudduštu	208
Šalim-nūrī	65 n. 473
Šamaš-magir	187
Šarrum-bāni	70 n. 508
Šēlebi	213 n. 1443
Šešmakal	166
Šinunutum	125

Šu-Amurru	126 n. 879
Šulgi-tūrī	65 n. 471, 66 n. 476
Tablazu	59, 62
Tir-Ea	190–191
Ubārum	95, 97–98
Ugubi	90
Ur-Pabilsaḡ	94 n. 672, 95, 97–99
Wirri	68, 172
Zababa-iqīša	211
Zittāya	208 n. 1402

8.1.2. Deities and other mythological characters

Āmûm	172, 174, 196 n. 1334, 235
Anu	213
Bēl	211-212, 230
Bēltu	212
Dumuzi	152 n. 1080
Dagān	189 n. 1297
Enki	100, 102, 121–123, 128–129, 147, 220 n. 1487
Enlil	42, 135, 145, 162 n. 1148
Eštar	174 n. 1213
Deštinanna	121
Inanna	102, 128, 132-133, 152 n. 1080, 153, 203 n. 1375
Išhara	213, 230
Nanna	100 n. 702, 122
Nergal	145 n. 1022, 172, 174, 196 n. 1334
Ninḡirsu	42, 49, 52, 130, 234
Ninmaḡ	102, 123, 125
Suen	122
Šara	55–57, 59, 63
Zababa	201 n. 1363

8.1.3. Rulers

Aššurbānipal	225
Gudea	42, 44–46, 47 n. 341, 49–50, 124 n. 862
Ibbī-Suen	50, 56–57
Išbī-Erra	106–107 n. 736, 162 n. 1147
Išmē-Dagān	130, 162, 163, 165, 183 n. 1262, 234
Lā'ûm	186–187, 235
Lipit-Ištar	162 n. 1148
Sargon of Akkad	201
Šamši-Addu	13, 172, 175–176, 179–180, 182, 184, 187, 193–194, 196
Šu-Suen	59
Šulgi	5, 43, 56–57, 59, 65, 102, 130, 143, 145–148, 156, 157 n. 1113, 159, 161, 163, 165, 169, 201, 234
Ur-Namma	101, 134, 136–137, 160
Ur-Zababa of Kiš	201
Urukagina	41 n. 280
Yaḥdun-Līm	187
Yasmaḥ-Addu	172, 179, 187, 189
Zimrī-Līm	178, 189 n. 1297, 192–194, 196

8.1.4. Toponyms

Adab	40
Assyria	199
Awal	67, 172
Babylon	212, 214, 225
Babylonia	199
Baneh	177 n. 1230
Dilmun	19
Dūr-Yaḥdun-Līm	194
Ebla	2 n. 10, 23 n. 160, 45 n. 320, 78 n. 560
Ekallātum	176

Elam	19–20, 85, 189 n. 1297
Eridu	90, 128
Dirsu	38–39, 41 n. 280
Ḫubšalum / Ḫubšil	172
Isin	87, 90, 161–163
Kaniš	81, 171
Lagaš	36, 41–42, 44, 231, 233–234
Larsa	90, 161, 162 n. 1147
Mari	2 n. 10, 12–14, 17, 19, 33, 51 n. 370, 53 n. 381, 64, 67, 86, 109–110, 125–126, 139, 171–172, 174, 176–181, 183, 186–190, 193–194, 196–197, 205, 209, 232–233, 235–236
Marḫaši	19, 85 n. 612
Mesopotamia (South)	1, 2 n. 10, 17, 19 n. 139, 20, 23 n. 160, 51 n. 370, 67 n. 485, 73, 126, 171, 170, 185 n. 1272, 187 n. 1288, 197, 232, 235
Mesopotamia (North)	67, 126, 171, 205, 232
Mišlan	174 n. 1213
Nineveh	186 n. 1279, 200 n. 1355, 203 n. 1377, 204 n. 1384, 225
Nippur	39–40, 73–74, 76 n. 545, 79–80, 89 n. 646, 94–95, 102 n. 707, 105 n. 721, 118 n. 818, 122 n. 845, 124 n. 864, 126, 134 n. 934 and 939, 141 n. 999, 143 n. 1007, 144 n. 1016, 156 n. 1107, 158 n. 1119, 160 n. 1141, 162 n. 1153, 164 n. 1164, 166, 206, 232
Puzriš-Dagān	65
Šubat-Ellil	172, 176, 189
Šuprum	174 n. 1213
Sabum	19, 177 n. 1230, 201 n. 1361
Samānum	186
Samim	110
Sippar	203 n. 1377, 208–210
Susa	40 n. 276, 134 n. 934
Ugarit	1
Umma	40 n. 275 and 278, 39, 54, 56–58, 63, 65

Uprabum	187
Ur	73, 76 n. 545, 77 n. 546, 143 n. 1007, 144 n. 1016, 156 n. 1107, 158 n. 1119, 162 n. 1153, 164 n. 1164
Ur-Zababa	19, 201
Uruk	48 n. 345, 98 n. 692, 128–129, 132, 213, 222

8.1.5. Terms in Ancient languages

8.1.5.1. Sumerian

a-da-ab	78, 84, 101, 113, 122 n. 850–851, 136, 138–140, 143 n. 1011, 144 n. 1014, 145–149, 154–155, 169, 174, 233, 235
a-ga	49
a-la-la	28
a-nir	134 n. 936, 135, 136 n. 956
a-ra₂	84
a-u₃-a	140
a-zu	217
a₂	88, 163 n. 1155
a₂ šum₂	163, 183 n. 1262
a₂ tarah₇	126
(kuš)a₂-la₂	12 n. 84, 26, 44 n. 309, 45–47, 51–53, 62, 132, 148, 151– 152, 154
ab₂ hi nun	107
ab₍₂₎ za₃-mi₂	107–109, 111 n. 783
ad	105–106, 145
ad ša₄	28, 105–106, 145
aga₃-us₂	59 n. 423, 70 n. 511
ak	69, 88
azlag₇	66 n. 476
al-ḡar	49 n. 353, 51, 94 n. 666, 190 n. 1303
ḡeš-al-ḡar-sur₉	28, 135, 163 n. 1156, 190 n. 1303
aga	76

aga šu-si	130
agrun	205 n. 1386
akkil	106
anše	60
asila₃	84–85, 101, 233, 235
bal	165
bal-bal-e	63, 122 n. 850, 135 n. 952
balan	18–19, 28, 47–53, 58, 79, 94 n. 666, 124 n. 861, 130, 136 n. 961, 148, 150–153, 162 n. 1148, 210, 214, 220, 234– 235
balan-di	27, 49 n. 353, 135 n. 952
bar	217
buru₃	147–149, 154
daṅal	120, 147–149, 154
dal	149
dar	151 n. 1066
dim₃-ma mar-ḥa-a-ši	19 n. 139
du-bu-ul	157
du₃	88
du₇	104 n. 719, 214 n. 1456
du₁₂	86
du₁₄	166 n. 1183
dub-sar	39–40, 115
dug₃	155
dul	165
e-ne-eṅ₃-ṅa₂	217
e-ne-di	86
e₂-ba ge₄	139
e₂-balan	63
e₂-gal	138
e₂-ṅar₈	136–137
e₂-mar-ru₁₀	138 n. 971
e₂ nam-nar-ra	90, 130, 135, 137–140, 169

e2 nar-ra	90
e2 nar-gal-la	90
e2 sumur-ra	138
e2 tige(2)	140
e2 uš-bar	61
e2 uš-bar-ra	61
e2/ki umun2	139, 167
e2 zu2-ra-aḥ-a	138
eden	216
eme	105
eme-gi7	105
en3-du	28, 63, 64 n. 465, 105, 120, 131, 136 n. 954, 145 n. 1022
er2	50, 135, 136, 153 n. 1087
er2 balaḥ-ḥa2	136 n. 960
er2 gi-di(-da)	115 n. 808, 136 n. 960
er2 pad3	161
er2 s/šem3-ma	136 n. 960, 153, 210
er2 ub3-a	136 n. 960 and 962
ezem/izin	224 n. 1522
gal	131 (especially n. 920)
gal-(an)-zu	126 n. 875
gala	29, 50, 79, 114–115, 153, 161, 203 n. 1375, 210, 235– 236
gala maḥ	100 n. 702, 153 n. 1087
gašam	118
ge4	78 n. 552
ge17	118–119
geme2 kinkin2	66 n. 476
geme2 uš-bar	57, 61 n. 445, 66 n. 476
gen6	5, 131
GI×TAK4	41
gi-di	114–115, 136 n. 960, 143 n. 1011, 149
gi-gid2	114–115, 135, 136, 138, 139, 140

gi₁₆	165
giri₁₇	108
gid₂-i	5, 131
gu-uš	5
gu₂	141, 146 n. 1029, 163
gu₂ šum₂	141, 163
ḡešgu₂	201
gu₃ nun dug₄	12 n. 84, 152
gu₄ gu₃ nun di	49
gu₄-ud / gud₂	183
gudu₄	91–94
gud^dgud₁₀	48
ḡešgur₂	152
ḡarza	128
ḡen	70
ḡeš	19 n. 139, 45, 51 n. 370, 47, 151, 201
ḡeš ḡur	5
ḡeš tag	138
DEŠ×TAK₄	41
ḡeš-gid₂-da	115 n. 815
ḡeš-gu₃-di	5, 28 n. 212, 47, 106, 129–132, 134 n. 937, 136–138, 140, 163 n. 1156, 165, 195–196
ḡeš-nu₁₁ ge₄ ge₄	124
na⁴ḡeš-nu₁₁-gal	124 n. 865
ḡeš₂	159
ḡešbun	122 n. 851, 140 n. 990
ḡeštug₂	154
ḡešḡeštug za₃-mi₂	107
ḡiri₃	66
ḡiri₃-se₃-ga	57
ḡuruš uš-bar	62
ḡešḡar-ḡar	110, 163 n. 1156
ḡu-luḡ	221

ia⁽²⁾	159 n. 1128
i-lu	105, 122 n. 850, 135-136
igi	154
išib	52
izi šu ḥu-uz	217
KA-us₂-sa₂	59 n. 423
ka ḥal₂ taka₄	105
ka₅-a	217
kad₄	165 n. 1172
kam-ma sa₆-ga	5, 111
kaš	100 n. 703
ke-ze₂-er	86
keše₂/ kešda	64 n. 465, 91 n. 656, 215, 219, 221, 228
ki	146
ki aḥ₂	49
ki-bal	164
ki dul-dul-la	164
ki-ezem	223 n. 1521
ki nam-dub-sar-ra	118
ki-ru-gu₂	146 n. 1029
kiḥ₂-ge₄-a	118
kinkin⁽²⁾	61
ku₃	152
ḡeškul	85
kur₉	56–57
kuš-gu₄-gal	48, 220, 227-228
la₂	46, 158
lamma	121 n. 845
LIL₂	120 n. 837
li-li-is_{2/3} , liliz	48, 63, 94 n. 666, 132
lu₂ a₂-la₂	27
lu₂ al-ḥar-su-ra	27–28, 115 n. 812, 163 n. 1156
lu₂ balaḥ(-di)	27, 115

lu₂-^{ŋeš}ban	70–71 n. 511
lu₂ bur₂-balaŋ	27
lu₂ gi-di-da	27, 114–115
lu₂ gi-gid₂	27, 114–115
lu₂ i-lu (di)	28, 115
lu₂ mu₇-mu₇	115, 220 n. 1492
lu₂ ser₃(-ra)	28
lu₂ ^{ŋeš}tigidla	27, 63 n. 463, 86 n. 619
lu₂ u₆-e	124
*lu₂ za-na-ru	27
lugal	39, 122, 128 n. 894
lukur	57–58
lukur-gal	57
lul	217
ma-al-ga-tum	145
ma₂-ri₂-tum;	19, 49 n. 353, 51, 201 n. 1361
mi-ri₂-tum	
ma₂-la₂	64 n. 465
me	15, 128
me ŋar	81
me-lam₂	221
me-ze₂	132
meli₂	28, 119
min	85
mu	147
mu šid-bi	147
mu₇-mu₇	12
munus-nar-balaŋ	26 n. 186
muš-lah_{4/5}	71 n. 516, 227 n. 1559
nam	25 n. 173, 124–125, 169
nam-ab-ba	77 n. 547, 131–132
nam-agar₄-niŋin₂	54 n. 387
nam-^{lu₂}azlag₂	54 n. 387

nam-bur-ra	153
nam-e2-ge4-a	54 n. 387
nam-egir-erin-na	54 n. 387
nam-enku	54 n. 387
nam-gab2-us2	54 n. 387
nam-gal	78 n. 550
nam-gala	15, 70-71, 77 n. 547, 203 n. 1375, 153, 235–236
nam-gu2	38 n. 253
nam-gudu4	98 n. 694
nam-ḡeš2	159
nam-ia	159
nam-kalag-ga	78 n. 550
nam-kisal-luḡ	98 n. 694
nam-lu2-(ulu3)	38 n. 253, 118
nam-lu2-bappir	98 n. 694
nam-lu2-gi-na-ab-tum	54 n. 387
nam-lu2-la-ga	54 n. 387
nam-lu2-pi-lu5-da	54 n. 387
nam-lugal	76
nam-lul	217
nam-maḡ	38 n. 253, 78 n. 550
nam-mi2-us2-sa2	54 n. 387
nam-muḡaldim	87–88
nam-nar-a	164–165, 168, 234
ki bal-bal-la-bi	
nam-nar	<i>passim</i>
nam-nar-sa	79, 99–100
nam-niḡir-si	54 n. 387
nam-sa6-ga	78 n. 550
nam-tur	38 n. 253
nam-u4-da-tuš	54 n. 387
nam-ugula	98 n. 694
nam-um-ma	98 n. 689

nam-uru₄(-a)	54 n. 387
nam-ušbar	61 n. 439
nar	7, 15, 26, 28, 38, 40, 41, 46, 50, 57–58, 65–66, 78, 84–85, 90, 92–94, 96–100, 105, 108, 113–114, 119, 125, 129, 138, 152, 160, 167, 174, 204, 212–213, 227
nar a₂-na₂	26 n. 189
nar eš₃-a	26 n. 189
nar gu₃ dug₃-ga	26 n. 184
nar gu₃ nu-dug₃-ga	26 n. 184
nar gu₃ silim-ma	26 n. 184
nar ḫal-la-tuš-a	26 n. 187
nar igi lugal	26 n. 189, 212
nar igi suḫur-la₂	26 n. 189, 212
nar inim bala-bala	26 n. 184
nar keše₂-da	26 n. 188
nar pad₃-da	26 n. 188
nar ze₂-za	26 n. 184
nar balaḡ	29, 50 n. 367, 76, 78, 99–100, 196, 219
nar gal	12, 26 n. 188, 89, 124, 125–126, 130, 140 n. 996
nar munus	55, 56 n. 492, 57, 58, 63
nar ni₂a₂	63
nar sa	26 n. 185, 100
nar tur	26 n. 187
niḡ₂	95 n. 677
niḡ₂-me-ḡar	81
niḡ₂-na-me	165
niḡ₂-sakar	82 n. 581
buru₃-buru₃	
niḡ₂-SAR(-SAR)	82
niḡ₂-umun	120 n. 837
niḡ₂-zu	120 n. 837
niḡin₃	205
niḡin₃-ḡar	132, 205

ninda	100 n. 703
nu-banda₃	141
nu-ge₁₇	132
nu₂	138
pad₃	5, 131
pe-el-la₂	114
ri	146 n. 1029, 214 n. 1456
sa	130, 214
ᶯešsa-eš₍₅₎	156, 163 n. 1156
sa-gid₂-da	105 n. 726
sa₍₃₎-bi₍₂₎-tum	163 n. 1156, 177 n. 1230, 201 n. 1361
sag₃	151
saᶯ-tuku	98 n. 692
se-em	44–46, 49 n. 357, 52–53, 148, 234–235
si-EZEN	130, 163
si sa₂	20 n. 144, 153
sipa	40–41
su₃-ud	120, 234
sukkal	40, 59 n. 423
šag₄	85, 120, 156, 165, 234
šag₄ ᶯul₂	155
šag₄ nam-nar-ra	120, 156–157, 163, 165, 170, 234
še₁₁	75, 165, 234
šeg₁₁	105, 145
šeg_{12/1} ge₄	46, 152
s/šem_{3/5}	43–45
s/šer₃	63, 75–76, 84, 165, 177 n. 1233, 202, 204–205, 215–216, 228–229, 234
ser₃ gid₂-da	75, 113, 145 n. 1022, 157 n. 1115
s/šer₃ ku₃	64 n. 465, 94 n. 667, 140, 219
s/šer₃ nam-erim₂-ma	75
*šer₃ nam-lul	205, 216
s/šer₃ nam-gala	74 n. 526, 76, 160–161

s/šer₃ nam-nar	31, 74–76, 101, 160–161, 168, 202, 204–205, 217, 219, 221, 228 n. 1563, 229, 234
s/šer₃ nam-šub	122 n. 850, 135 n. 952
šid	147
šim-mu₂	217
šir₃-da	15 n. 112
šu	60, 151 n. 1067, 158–159
šu dar	151
šu du₇-a	51–52, 148–149, 234–235
šu nam-nar-ra	158–159, 169
šu nam-sa₆-ga	159
šu nam-uš₂	60, 159
ḡeššu-kar₂	5, 88, 146, 163
šu₂-šu₂	5, 146
šum₂	141, 163, 178 n. 1234, 183 n. 1262
tar	85
ti-ge₄, tige₍₂₎	50, 78–79, 83–84, 101, 108, 113, 132, 135–136, 138–140, 145–150, 152–155, 157, 169, 174, 233, 235
ḡeššitigidla_(x)	63, 85–86, 101, 149–150, 233, 235
ḡeššitigidla elam-ma	19 n. 135, 85
ḡeššitigidla kaskal-la	19 n. 135, 85, 150
ḡeššitigidla sa eš₅	85
tu-lu	5, 131
u₃-kul	70 n. 511
u₃-lu-lu-ma-ma	122 n. 850
u₄	46
u₄-da-tuš	71 n. 516, 227 n. 1559
u₈[!]-u_x(PA)-a	28
um-mi-a	113 n. 791, 125
(ḡeš)ur-za-ba-bi₍₂₎-tu(m)₍₂₎	19, 143 n. 1011, 201–202
ur-gu-la	19
ub_{3/5}	63, 132, 136 n. 962, 152 n. 1082
ḡu^uugu₄-bi	90

ugula	40, 98 n. 694
uku₂	98 n. 692
umun₂	120 n. 837
unu₂	110, 122 n. 851, 140 n. 990
urudu	154 n. 1099
urudu-niŋ₂-kalag-ga	106, 220, 227 n. 1560, 228
ušum(-)gal	42 n. 288, 42 n. 288, 50, 124 n. 862
uš₂/ug₇	59
uš-bar	55, 61–62
^{tug₂}(saŋ-)uš-bar	61
za-am-za-am	135–136, 140, 146, 152 n. 1082, 157, 159
za-na-ru	23 n. 160, 27 n. 196, 28 n. 212, 49 n. 353, 106 n. 735 and 729, 163 n. 1156
za-pa-aŋ₂	28, 105–106
za₃-mi₂	5, 20, 106-111, 134 n. 934, 143-144 n. 1011, 165, 190 n. 1303, 191
zabar	151 n. 1070
zag e₂-ŋar₈-e us₂	137
zi-zi	5, 146
zu	154, 156

8.1.5.2. Akkadian and Sumerograms in Akkadian texts

<i>agû(m)</i> ¹⁵⁶⁵	150 n. 1061
<i>aḥāzu(m)</i>	178 n. 1238
<i>aḥu(m)</i>	183 n. 1262
<i>aḥû(m)</i>	215
<i>akītu(m)</i>	213
<i>alû(m)</i>	27 n. 196, 45 n. 318
<i>algasurrû(m)</i>	191
<i>ana</i>	69 n. 496, 174, 186, 194 n. 1322, 235
<i>ana mārûti(m) nadānu(m)</i>	210 n. 1425
<i>apālu(m)</i>	193
<i>apu(m)</i>	150
<i>appu(m)</i>	108
<i>āšīpu(m)</i>	208–209
<i>āšipūtu(m)</i>	225–226
<i>ašnugallu(m)</i>	124 n. 865
<i>aššu(m)</i>	178 n. 1238, 218 n. 1473
<i>aštalû(m)</i>	114 n. 798, 175, 190, 194
<i>baddû(m)</i>	181–182
<i>balaggu(m)</i>	18
<i>bašû(m)</i>	10
<i>batultu(m)</i>	208
<i>bārû(m)</i>	226, 228
<i>bārûtu(m)</i>	226, 228
<i>bištu(m)</i>	185 n. 1276
<i>bīt mummi(m)</i>	12 n. 89, 139 n. 988
<i>bīt tegêti(m)</i>	139
<i>dagālu(m)</i>	211 n. 1432
lu²DUMU.NID₂.LA.LA	212
<i>elammakku(m)</i>	189 n. 1297

¹⁵⁶⁵ As a matter of coherence, the mimation is put as optional in all the Akkadian terms of this list independently of their chronology.

<i>ebbubbu(m)</i>	221 n. 1501
<i>ēnu(m)/īnu(m)</i>	196
<i>enûtu(m)</i>	11, 193–197, 201–202, 229
<i>epēšu(m)</i>	88, 173, 185, 197, 235
DIRI3.SAG10.GA	174
<i>ḫalāqu(m)</i>	180 n. 1247, 197
<i>ḫalḫallatu(m)</i>	11 n. 79
<i>ḫasīs sammī(m)</i>	107
<i>ḫasīru(m)</i>	172 n. 1196
<i>ḫišeḫtu(m)</i>	194
<i>ḫubûru(m)</i>	12–13, 177 n. 1231
<i>ḫuppû(m)</i>	126 n. 879, 183
<i>ikrību(m)</i>	81–82
<i>inûtu(m)</i>	195 n. 1326
<i>ina</i>	186, 235
<i>isinnu(m)</i>	224 n. 1522
<i>išdu(m)</i>	223 n. 1517
<i>itti</i>	223 n. 1521
<i>ittinnûtu(m)</i>	223
KA5.A	212 n. 1438
<i>kalû(m)</i>	2 n. 10, 10–11, 15 n. 108, 29, 98 n. 691, 174–175, 210, 225–227, 230, 235–236
<i>kalûtu(m)</i>	10–11, 67 n. 485, 225–226, 235–236
<i>kammu(m)</i>	205, 217
<i>kamû(m)</i>	205, 215, 217–218
<i>kaw/mû(m)</i>	217
<i>kaššāptu(m)</i>	216
<i>kirru(m)</i>	109
<i>kummu(m)</i>	205 n. 1386
KU3.SI22	109, 193 n. 1319, 195 n. 1326
<i>lā illu(m)</i>	212 n. 1439
<i>lē'u(m)</i>	189–190
<i>le'û(m)</i>	181 n. 1250

<i>lilisu(m)</i>	11 n. 79, 48, 136 n. 962, 210
LU2.DEŠTIN	222 n. 1516
LU2.KU3.DIM2	195 n. 1326
<i>malsûtu(m)</i>	218
<i>mandîtu(m)</i>	111
<i>mārîtu(m)</i>	201 n. 1361
<i>martu(m)</i>	149
<i>mašmaššu(m)</i>	220 n. 1490
<i>mimma</i>	194 n. 1322
<i>mummu(m)</i>	12 n. 89, 13, 185 n. 1277, 193
<i>mušāḥizu(m)</i>	189–190
<i>nabû(m)</i>	10
<i>nakāpu(m)</i>	214 n. 1456
<i>nadû(m)</i>	183 n. 1262
<i>nargallatu(m)</i>	180 n. 1249
(^{munus} NAR.GAL, ^{munus} NAR3.GALA7)	
<i>nargallûtu(m)</i>	180
<i>nāru(m)</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>nārûtu(m)</i>	<i>passim</i>
<i>narûtu(m)</i>	81–82, 171, 232
<i>nārtu(m)</i>	64 n. 466, 86, 114 n. 798, 174 n. 1213, 178, 183, 208
<i>nasāsu(m)</i>	105 n. 727
<i>ni'u(m)</i>	181–182 n. 1261, 220 n. 1489
<i>nīd qabli(m)</i>	1
<i>nigkalagû(m)</i>	220 n. 1490
<i>nigûtu(m)</i>	11 n. 79, 78, 224, 229, 236
<i>*nu'artu(m)</i>	208
<i>nūru(m)</i>	212 n. 1439
<i>para(ḥ)š(ī)u(m)</i>	19, 85 n. 612
<i>puršum(t)u(m)</i>	98–99
<i>qaqqadu(m)</i>	210
<i>qaštu(m)</i>	177 n. 1230

<i>qūlatu(m)</i>	81
<i>qullu(m)</i>	110
<i>raqādu(m)</i>	183 n. 1269
<i>riksu(m)</i>	219, 221, 228
<i>rikis zamārī</i>	221–222
<i>rīmtu(m)</i>	111 n. 783
<i>riqdu(m)</i>	183 n. 1269
<i>rīšātu(m)</i>	81
<i>sadādu(m)</i>	188 n. 1291
<i>sammû(m)</i>	10 n. 73, 11 n. 79, 20, 106–111, 191
<i>sibūtu(m)</i>	68 n. 488
<i>sibûtu(m)</i>	68 n. 488
<i>siddu(m)</i>	188, 195
SUĦUŠ	20 n. 146
<i>šā'ilu(m)</i>	226
<i>sabītu(m)</i> or <i>šebītu(m)</i>	19, 64, 177, 201 n. 1361
<i>šalam bīti(m)</i>	210
<i>šamallû(m)</i>	208–209
(^{lu2} ŠAMAN ₂ .LA ₂)	
<i>šanīta(m)</i>	191
<i>šēlebu(m)</i>	213 n. 1443
<i>šemû(m)</i>	218 n. 1473
<i>šerkugû(m)</i>	219–220, 227 n. 1560, 228
<i>šēru(m)</i>	177 n. 1233
<i>šiptu(m)</i>	216
<i>šitru(m)</i>	64, 94 n. 669, 193
ŠU.II₂.LA₂	212
<i>šabātu(m)</i>	195
<i>šābu(m)</i>	179
<i>šarāḥu(m)</i>	216
<i>šinnatu(m)</i>	221 n. 1501
<i>tigû(m)</i>	139, 150, 177
<i>tikittallû(m)</i>	150

<i>tikittallî api(m)</i>	150
<i>ṭābiḥu(m)</i>	210
<i>ṭābiḥūtu(m)</i>	210
<i>usukku(m)</i>	110
<i>zakāru(m)</i>	10
<i>zamāru(m)</i>	1, 15 n. 112, 29, 76, 206 n. 1396, 216
<i>zamāru(m)</i> (III)	191 n. 1308
<i>zammārūtu(m)</i>	10 n. 73
<i>zâqu(m)</i>	214 n. 1456
<i>zimru(m)</i>	191 n. 1308, 207, 214, 230
<i>zimru(m)</i> (III)	191 n. 1308

8.1.5.3. Other Ancient Languages

8.1.5.3.1. Aramaic

<i>zmār(ā)</i>	23 n. 163, 25
----------------	---------------

8.1.5.3.2. Biblical Hebrew

<i>šemeš</i>	172 n. 1199
<i>zimrah</i>	23 n. 163, 25

8.1.5.3.3. Chinese

<i>yuè</i> (樂)	24
----------------	----

8.1.5.3.4. Eblaite

<i>gi-na-ru₁₂-um</i>	23 n. 160
NAR	23 n. 161

	8.1.5.3.5.	Egyptian
<i>iḥy</i>		24–25
<i>ḥn</i>		24–25
<i>ḥst</i>		24–25
<i>knnr</i>		19 n. 137
	8.1.5.3.6.	Elamite
<i>ka₄-si-ik-ki ba-ak-ki-ra</i>		24 n. 165
<i>šu-ku-ri</i>		24 n. 165
	8.1.5.3.7.	Greek
αὐλός		22
φόρμιγξ		6
μουσική (τέχνη)		2, 5–6, 22, 24
	8.1.5.3.8.	Hittite
<i>iḥamai-</i>		25 n. 175
<i>kuleššar</i>		67 n. 485
<i>siuna-, siunis-</i>		xxiii
<i>zinar</i>		21 n. 146, 23 n. 160, 25, 27 n. 196
	8.1.5.3.9.	Hurrian
<i>eni-</i>		xxiii
<i>kul-</i>		172 n. 1195
<i>šenni</i>		67
<i>weri</i>		68

	8.1.5.3.10.	Latin
<i>musica</i>		22
	8.1.5.3.11.	Phoenician
<i>šmš</i>		172 n. 1199
	8.1.5.3.12.	Proto-Semitic
<i>*šamš</i>		172 n. 1199
	8.1.5.3.13.	Sanskrit
<i>saṅgīta</i>		24
	8.1.5.3.14.	Ugaritic
<i>ḏmr</i>		23 n. 162, 25
<i>knr</i>		111 n. 783
<i>r²imt</i>		111 n. 783
<i>špš</i>		172 n. 1199

8.1.6. Mesopotamian Cuneiform Signs

A	162 n. 1162
AB	212 n. 1440
AB _{gunû}	173 n. 1203
AL	155 n. 1105
AN	xxiii, 142 n. 1005
BA	122 n. 849, 226 n. 1542, 233
BAD	54–55 n. 391, 60–61
BALAD	47, 48 n. 345, 50, 144 n. 1014

BI	123 n. 857, 150 n. 1061, 176 n. 1224, 222 n. 1515
BU	114 n. 803, 134 n. 935
BULUD	83 n. 592
DA	87 n. 632, 142 n. 1005
DI	212 n. 1442
DU	212 n. 1440, 223 n. 1517
E ₂	90
EZEN	83 n. 591, 84, 204-205, 215, 216, 218-219, 221, 224 n. 1522, 233
EZEN×A	83 n. 591, 84
EZEN×LAL ₂	83 n. 591
GAB	168 n. 1191
GAL	124 n. 862, 173 n. 1203, 180 n. 1248
GI	23 n. 160, 114 n. 801 and 803
GL ₄	78 n. 552, 167 n. 1188
GU ₄ ×KUR	95 n. 677
DAR	80 n. 567, 222 n. 1513
DEŠ	123 n. 857
ĤU	117 n. 817
IG	144 n. 1015, 167 n. 1188
IŠ	209 n. 1415
KA	108, 134 n. 938
KEŠDA	91 n. 656
KI	122 n. 849, 173 n. 1204, 212 n. 1442
KIŠ	173 n. 1203
KUR	95 n. 677, 209 n. 1417
LA	155 n. 1106, 164 n. 1162
LIŠ	83 n. 592
LUL	50, 165 n. 1172, 173 n. 1202 and 1206, 180 n. 1248, 210 n. 1424 and 1425, 222 n. 1514 and 1516
MI	155 n. 1106
MU	144 n. 1015
NA	121 n. 844, 216 n. 1467, 226 n. 1542, 233
NA ₂	117 n. 817

NAM	78
NE	113 n. 791, 166 n. 1183
NI	83 n. 599, 167 n. 1187
NU	200 n. 1351
NU ₁₁ /ŠIR	123 n. 857
NUN	90
PI	176 n. 1224
PIRID	173 n. 1203
RA	162 n. 1152
RU	209 n. 1417
SA	110
SAD	223 n. 1517
SAL	106 n. 736
SAR	65 n. 474, 81, 82 n. 580, 204
SI	15 n. 112, 68 n. 488, 173 n. 1204
SUD	114 n. 803, 134 n. 935
SUM	178 n. 1234
ŠAG ₄	85, 200 n. 1353, 222 n. 1514
ŠER ₃	91 n. 656
ŠIM	210 n. 1424
ŠU	200 n. 1354
TA	160 n. 1139, 209 n. 1415
TAB	160 n. 1140
TU	206 n. 1394
TUM	69 n. 498, 180 n. 1248, 200 n. 1354
U	83 n. 587
UB	212 n. 1442
UD	200 n. 1351
UŠ ₂	59
ZA	110
ZAG	124 n. 862
ZI	186 n. 1282
ZU	122 n. 849

8.2. Edited and Commented Texts

Titles of the different sections have normally tried to show the title of the text to be commented at each time. In any case, as a sort of clarification, here is an index of the different texts edited and commented here. We indicate only the page of their transliteration and translation, not the one for other comments, whether in the main text, whether in the footnotes.

Text 1	CT 50, pl. 168 [BM 86313] (00-00-00), o. 5–9	38
Text 2	Adab 652 [OIM A652] (00-00-00), o. 6–9	40
Text 3	MVN 6 309 [Ist. L 7319] (00-00-00), o. i 12–15	41
Text 4	<i>Gudea Cylinders</i> , B15.20–22	42
Text 5	Nisaba 11 33 [BM 104768] (Šulgi 36-11-00), r. i 3–10	54–55
Text 6	TRU 41 [ICP 41] (Šulgi 41-08-00), o. 1–r. 7	65
Text 7	al-Rawi, 1992:185 [IM 85455/as-Sulaima 410] (00-00-00)	68
Text 8	al-Rawi, 1992: 185 [IM 85456/as-Sulaima 411] (00-00-00)	69
Text 9	<i>Proto-lu₂</i> , 590–591 (score)	74
Text 10	Proto- izi , II 227–231 (score)	76–77
Text 11	Niḡ₂-ga (monolingual version), 73–75	80
Text 12	Geller, 2003: 109–111 [MS 2951]	83
Text 13	Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534], r. iii 1’–19’	87
Text 14	<i>Proverbs</i> 3.150 (score)	89
Text 15	ARN 4 [Ist. Ni 9201] (Būr-Sîn 00-12-10), o. ii 1’–o. ii 14’’	91
Text 16	ARN 58 [Ist. Ni 2182] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00), o. 1–r. 10	92
Text 17	Kraus, 1951: 200–201 [Ist. Ni 2181] (Būr-Sîn 00-00-00), o. 1’–o. 10’	93
Text 18	ARN 35 [Ist. Ni 1922] (Rīm-Sîn I 37-10-00), o. 1–r. 2	95
Text 19a	TMH 10 58a [HS 2072] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00), o. 1–r. 5	96
Text 19b	TMH 10 58b [HS 2116] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00), o. 1–r. 5	96
Text 20a	TMH 10 59a [HS 2081] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00), o. 1–r. 6	97
Text 20b	TMH 10 59b [HS 2350 (case)] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00), o. 1’–r. 7’’	97

Text 21	TMH 10 55 [HS 2396] (Rīm-Sîn I 35-10-00), o. 1–o. 11	99
Text 22	<i>Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu</i> , 94–99 (score)	103–105
Text 23	<i>Enkiheḡal and Enkitalu</i> , 110–113 (score)	111–113
Text 24	<i>The Father and his rude Son</i> , 107–110 (score)	116–118
Text 25	<i>The Father and his rude Son</i> , 111–112 (score)	119
Text 26	<i>Šulgi E</i> , 162–163 (score)	121–122
Text 27	<i>Enki and Ninmaḡ</i> , b 26–29 (score)	123–124
Text 28	TJA, p. 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna, 23-10-02 (?)), o. 1–o. 6	125
Text 29	<i>Inanna and Enki</i> , PBS 1/1 1 [CBS 13571 + 13602 + 13617 + 13623 + 13629], I v 33–34	128
Text 30	<i>Inanna and Enki</i> , Farber-Flüge, 1973: pl. 1 [CBS 15283], II v 47–52	129
Text 31	<i>Ur-Namma A</i> , 187–188 (score)	134
Text 32	<i>Šulgi E</i> , 155 (score)	141
Text 33	<i>Šulgi B</i> , 154–156 (score)	142–143
Text 34	<i>Šulgi B</i> , 157 (score)	144
Text 35	<i>Šulgi B</i> , 162 (score)	155–156
Text 36	<i>Šulgi B</i> , 277–279 (score)	157–158
Text 37	<i>Šulgi CC</i> , UET 6/3 522 [U. 7774], o. i 1–o. i 4	160
Text 38	<i>Death of Nannā</i> , 19 (score)	160
Text 39	<i>Išmē-Dagān A + V</i> , A 367	162
Text 40	<i>Išmē-Dagān A + V</i> , A 373–374	164
Text 41	UET 6/3 721 [U. ---]	166–167
Text 42	ARM 1 78 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	173
Text 43	FM 9 24 [M.5160] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 7–13	175
Text 44	ARM 1 64 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)	176–177
Text 45	ARM 5 73 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 2’–7’	178
Text 46	FM 9 13 [M.6851] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 1–r. 2	179–180
Text 47	FM 9 26 [M.14611] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 1–lo. e. 1	182
Text 48	FM 9 27 [M.13050] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 1–r. 9	184
Text 49	FM 9 30 [M.7321] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 5–r. 2	186
Text 50	FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 1–13	187–188

Text 51	FM 9 55 [A.905] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 12–19	189
Text 52	FM 9 62 [M.7281] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), r. 6’–10’	190
Text 53	FM 9 5 [A.4377] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), lo. e. 1–r. 6	191–192
Text 54	FM 9 18 [A.903] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 1–lo. e. 1	192–193
Text 55	FM 9 3 [A.4202] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 23–24	194
Text 56	FM 9 48 [M.6900] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00), o. 8–13	194
Text 57	FM 9 44 [M.8181] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00), o. 1–10	195
Text 58	Mur-gu₄ = <i>imrû</i> = <i>ballu</i> , B II [= Urs-ra = <i>hubullu(m)</i> VII B], 169 (score)	200
Text 59	<i>Examination Text A</i> , 24 (score)	203
Text 60	<i>Nabnītu</i> , IVa, 329 (score)	204
Text 61	BE 8/1 98 [CBS 3579] (Cambyses II 14+-01-00), o.1–r.6	206–207
Text 62	MacGinnis, 2002: 234, text n. 12 [BM 64026] (Cyrus 07-10-06), o. 1–4	208
Text 63	VS 6 169 [VAT 1180] (Darius I 00-00-00), o. 1–8	209
Text 64	MacGinnis, 1991–1992: 83, text n. 3 [BM 70463] (00-00-00), o.4’–8’	210–211
Text 65	Wunsch, 2003: 106, text n. 33 [BM 30515] (Nabonidus, 10-11-15), r. 2–4	211
Text 66	<i>Dar.</i> 463 [BM 77393] (Darius I (x)+3-1-18), o. 1–r. 2	212–213
Text 67	CT 17, pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+], iv 18’–19’	214
Text 68	VS 15 19 [VAT 8552] (Seleucid Era 109-09-24), o. 1–7	222–223
Text 69	Koch, 2004: 106–108 [BM 55466 + 55486 + 55627], r. 25–26	223
Text 70	Frame and George, 2005: 270–277 [BM 28825], o. 8–10	225

8.3. Cited Texts

8.3.1. Mesopotamian Texts

8.3.1.1. Uruk Period

ATU 5 89 [VAT 15061]

ii 3 48 n. 345

8.3.1.2. Early Dynastic IIIa

CUSAS 11 18 [CUNES 50-03-188]

o. 2 38 n. 253

AWEL 1 [Erm. 14001] (Urukagina 02-00-00)

r. iii 3 71 n. 515

IAS 54 + 56 [IM 70293+]

o. v 17 27 n. 191

o. v 18 27 n. 197

o. v 19 27 n. 193

IAS 60 [IM 70171]

o. vi 2' 28 n. 204

IAS 326 + 342 [IM 70169 + 70297?]

passim 70 n. 502

SF 47 [VAT 12619]

57_(22) 28 n. 204

58_(23) 27 n. 193

60_9 27 n. 197

SF 70 [VAT 12617]

o. i 8 49 n. 353

8.3.1.3. Early Dynastic IIIb

DP 588 [AO 13796] (Urukagina 04-00-00)

o. i 6 41 n. 280

DP 590 [AO 13798] (Urukagina 04-00-00)

o. i 5 41 n. 280

ED Practical Vocabulary A

207–208 19 n. 134, 51 n. 370

210–212 41 n. 281

ED Lu₂ E

98 49 n. 353

101 27 n. 191

102 27 n. 197

103–105 27 n. 193, 41 n. 281

107 28 n. 204

TSA 7 [MRAH O.653] (Urukagina 00-00-00)

r. i 3 41 n. 280

8.3.1.4. Ebla

ARET 5 6 [TM.75.G.2421 + 75.G.5511]

passim 70 n. 502

ARET 9 107 [TM75.G.576]

o. i 3 27 n. 191

MEE 3 8 + 9 + unpublished fragment [TM.75.G.11651+]

o. vi 2 28 n. 204

MEE 4 2 + 3 + 61 [TM.75.G.15301]

r. ii 4' 23 n. 160

MEE 4 76 [TM.75.G.1445]

r. iii 15 45 n. 320

8.3.1.5. Old Akkadian

Adab 658 [OIM A658] (00-00-00)

o. 11 39 n. 259

Adab 1209 [OIM A1209] (00-00-00)

o. ii 10 39 n. 264

CDLI P270837 [Anonymous 270837] (00-00-00)

o. ii 3 40 n. 275

CDLI P390448 [Kress 150] (03-00-00)

o. i 2 39 n. 267

CUSAS 13 2 [CUNES 47-12-177] (00-00-00)

r. 8 39 n. 259

r. 11 39 n. 259

CUSAS 19 97 [CUNES 48-10-76] (00-00-00)

o. 4' 39 n. 259

o. 7' 39 n. 259

r. 1 39 n. 259

r. 5 39 n. 259

CUSAS 20 136 [CUNES 48-7-97] (00-00-00),

o. 4 39 n. 259

CUSAS 20 164 [CUNES 48-6-173] (00-00-00)

o. 2 39 n. 259

o. 7 39 n. 266

CUSAS 20 168 [CUNES 48-10-115] (00-00-00)

r. 1 39 n. 265

CUSAS 20 194 [CUNES 50-1-10] (00-00-00)

o. 5–6 49 n. 353

r. 4 49 n. 353

CUSAS 20 339 [CUNES 47-11-47] (00-00-00)

o. 3 39 n. 259

CUSAS 35 360 [MS 4206] (Naram-Sîn 01-00-00[?])

o. ii 18 39 n. 259

Farber and Walter, 2003: 66 n. 1 [Anonymous 499911] (00-00-00)

r. 8 39 n. 261

ITT 1 1100 [Ist. L 1100] (00-00-00)

o. 7 39 n. 262

ITT 2 4409 [Ist. L 4409] (00-00-00)

r. 2 39 n. 260

MDP 14 19 [Sb 1819] (00-00-00)

r. 9 40 n. 276

OSP 1 24 [N 281] (00-00-00)

o. iii 2 39 n. 269

OSP 2 100 [UM 29-15-202] (Šar-kali-šarrī 02-00-00)

r. i 15 39 n. 270

OSP 2 120 [CBS 6225] (00-00-00)

o. 5 39 n. 268

OSP 2 133 [N 433 + 581] (00-00-00)

r. 12 23 n. 160, 27 n. 195, 49 n. 353

OSP 2 134 [N 526] (00-00-00)

o. 5 39 n. 268

OSP 2 136 [N 278] (00-00-00)

o. 3 39 n. 268

r. 5 23 n. 160, 27 n. 195, 49 n. 353

OSP 2 149 [CBS 6223 + N 611] (00-00-00)

o. 2 39 n. 268

OSP 2 154 [N 275] (00-00-00)

o. 8 39 n. 268

RTC 96 [AO 31324] (00-00-00)

o. 10' 39 n. 263

STTI 1 20 [Ist. L 1176] (00-00-00)

o. 5 39 n. 259

STTI 1 182 [Ist. L 9336] (00-00-00)

r. 5 47 n. 340

TCBI 1 212 [BdI 1,180] (00-00-00)

r. 1 39 n. 259

TCBI 1 231 [BdI 1,86] (00-00-00)

r. 2 39 n. 259

TMH 5 186 + 202 [HS 936 + 952 + 994 + 1000] (00-00-00)

r. i 22 40 n. 277

USP 26 [NMS A.1927.421] (00-00-00)

r. 6 40 n. 278

Westenholz, 1974: 78, text 4 [NMC 10071] (00-00-00)

r. 2 40 n. 275

8.3.1.6. 2nd Dynasty of Lagaš

Çiğ, 1976: 87 text 7 [Ist. L 40470] (Gudea 03-00-00)

r. 4' 50 n. 360

Gudea Cylinders

A1.14 52 n. 376

A2.15 52 n. 375

A6.24 42 n. 288, 49 n. 358, 50 n. 360

A6.25 47 n. 341, 49 n. 358, 130 n. 904 and 907

A7.24 49 n. 358, 50 n. 360

A7.25 47 n. 341, 49 n. 358

A10.17–18 52 n. 375

A18.7 52 n. 376

A18.18 44 n. 303, 309, 45 n. 321

A20.13 52 n. 375

A28.17	49 n. 355
A28.18	44 n. 303, 309, 45 n. 321, 46 n. 322, 49 n. 357
B4.20–21	50 n. 363
B5.23	52 n. 375
B7.4–10	52 n. 376
B10.9	77 n. 551, 78 n. 560, 150 n. 1056
B10.11	49 n. 353, 51 n. 371
B10.14	15 n. 111, 51 n. 369
B11.1	50 n. 362
B14.25–B15.16	42 n. 284
B16.4	52 n. 375
B18.19	52 n. 376
B18.22	50 n. 360 and 366, 78 n. 552, 79 n. 561, 150 n. 1056

Gudea Statue B [E3/1.1.7.StB]

iv 3 50 n. 368

Gudea Statue L [E3/1.1.7.StL]

a 41' 46 n. 329

MVN 7 458 [Ist. L 8065] (Gudea 02-00-00)

r. 1 50 n. 360

RTC 247 [AO 3432] (00-00-00)

o. i 10' 49 n. 359

Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 82 [AO 3324] (Gudea 02-00-00)

o. 7' 50 n. 360

Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 86 [AO 3367] (00-00-00)

o. i 3 44 n. 303

o. ii 7 44 n. 303

Thureau-Dangin, 1902: 88 [AO 3368] (00-00-00)

- o. i 1 44 n. 303
- o. iii 1 44 n. 303
- r. ii 1 44 n. 303
- r. ii 5 45 n. 316

8.3.1.7. Ur III Period

AAICAB 1/1, pl. 20 [Ashm. 1911-160] (Šu-Suen 02-09-00)

- o. 1 60 n. 433

AAICAB 1/2, pl. 105 [Ashm. 1937-68] (Šulgi 48-04-00)

- o. 2 43 n. 295

AAICAB 1/1, pl. 166 [Ashm. 1911-480] (Šulgi 42-00-00)

- o. ii 15 57 n. 415
- r. i 13 57 n. 415
- r. i 6 57 n. 415
- r. ii 14–15 57 n. 415

AAICAB 1/2, pl. 166 [Ashm. 1975-293] (Amar-Suena 02-09-00)

- o. ii 14 57 n. 415
- o. ii 17 57 n. 415
- r. ii 5 57 n. 415

AAICAB 1/4, pl. 262 [Bod. S 379] (Šu-Suen 02-04-12)

- r. 1–4 59 n. 423

AIHA 4, p. 40 [IM 92363] (00-00-00)

- passim* 67 n. 483

Amherst 17 [Amherst ---] (Šulgi 25-00-00)

- o. ii 18 50 n. 360

Amorites 20 (pl. 9) [OIM A4218] (Šu-Suen 04-09-02)

r. 6–8 70 n. 506

AnOr 7 285 [MM 188] (00-00-00)

o. iii' 7' 66 n. 476

o. iii' 24' 66 n. 476

AnOr 7 296 [MM 190] (00-00-00)

o. ii 16 57–58 n. 415

r. ii 9 57–58 n. 415

Atiqot 4 7–9 [IMJ 90.24.61] (Amar-Suena 05-04-00)

o. ii 9 63 n. 460

AUCT 1 942 [AUAM 73.724] (Amar-Suena 02-00-00)

o. 8 63 n. 462

AUCT 3 42 [AUAM 73.851] (Šu-Suen 01-12-00)

o. 1–3 70 n. 508

BIN 3 262 [NBC 2176] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-01)

o. 3 50 n. 367

BIN 5 301 [NBC 1424] (00-00-00)

r. 31 57 n. 410

BPOA 2 2318 [BM 112068] (Šu-Suen 04-00-00)

o. 1 60 n. 433

BPOA 6 137 [YBC 13653] (Šu-Suen 02-10-00)

o. 1 60 n. 433

BPOA 6 1190 [NBC 618] (Šulgi 45-00-00)

r. 1 27 n. 199

BPOA 7 1559 [NBC 1516] (Amar-Suena 04-00-00)

r. 4–5 63 n. 458

BPOA 7 2401 [NBC 3641] (Amar-Suena 07-01-00)

o. 1–2 58 n. 417

o. 5–r. 2 58 n. 417

BPOA 10 558 [YBC 13384] (00-00-00)

o. 3' 65 n. 465

CDLI P218067 [WAM 2000.47] (Amar-Suena 05-00-00)

o. i 32 63 n. 457

CDLI P235573 [USC 6763 = L.63] (Šu-Suen 03-00-00)

r. 12 27 n. 197

CST 189 [JRL 189] (Šulgi 47-10-14)

o. 1–3 70 n. 510

CST 442 [JRL 442] (Šu-Suen 07-11-18)

o. 1–2 70 n. 510

Delaporte, 1911: 192 text 14 [NME H94673] (Amar-Suena 08-11-00)

o. 3 64 n. 465

Fish, 1958: 84–87 [BM 106055] (Šulgi 45-01-00)

r. i 12' 106–107 n. 736, 107 n. 741

Fish and Lambert, 1963: 96 18 [BM 105348] (00-00-00)

r. 12 43 n. 295

r. 15 43 n. 295
r. 17 43 n. 295
r. 20 43 n. 295

George, 1987: 35 text 317 [B1 44.317] (Amar-Suena 09-09-00)
o. 1–2 70 n. 509

Gomi, 1980: 33 text 92 [BM 17810] (Amar-Suena 06-02-00)
o. 1 50 n. 367

Mirelman, 2010c: 33 [U. 18857] (Šu-Suen 01-06-00)
o. 1 43 n. 295

MVN 3 136 [FLP 157] (Šulgi, 33-04-00)
o. 4 201 n. 1359

MVN 5 116 [Pinches 13] (Amar-Suena 07-03-09)
o. 8–10 71 n. 512

MVN 6 300 [Ist. L 7309] (00-00-00)
o. ii 16 27 n. 197

MVN 7 235 [Ist. L. 7836] (00-00-00)
r. 2 43 n. 295

MVN 8 122 [AO 19603] (Amar-Suena 01-08-20)
o. 8–10 70 n. 507

MVN 10 96 [AO 10391] (Šulgi 42-11-00)
o. ii 20 27 n. 197

MVN 12 112 [FLP 592] (Šulgi 47-10-25)
r. 13–14 70 n. 507

MVN 12 547 [FLP 2527] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-02)

o. 3 50 n. 367

MVN 15 142 [Cornell 30] (Šulgi 00-00-00)

r. 22–23 70 n. 504

MVN 20 81 [Erm. 4040] (Ibbī-Suen 02-00-00)

r. 1 57 n. 409

r. 6–7 57 n. 409

MVN 21 238 [Erm. 14487] (Amar-Suena 08-06-00)

o. 4 58 n. 416

o. 7 58 n. 416

MVN 21 240 [Erm. 8087] (Šu-Suen 05-05-00)

o. 4 58 n. 417

r. 1–3 58 n. 417

Mycenaean, p. 217 no. 7 [Ashm. 1924-668] (Šu-Suen 02-00-00)

o. ii 20 57–58 n. 415

r. i 16 57–58 n. 415

r. ii 7 57–58 n. 415

Nebraska 45 [OPL ---] (00-00-00)

o. ii 34 57 n. 410

Nebraska 49 [OPL 45] (00-00-00)

o. 4 57 n. 407

Nisaba 6 12 [BM 106051] (0000-00-00)

o. iv 12 59 n. 422

o. v 6 56 n. 401

Nisaba 6 27 [BM 106043] (Šulgi 32-05-00)

- o. vi 21 57 n. 412
- o. vi 32 57 n. 412
- o. viii 9 57 n. 412
- r. iv 12 55 n. 402
- r. v 1 57 n. 412
- r. v 9–15 56 n. 404

Nisaba 11 18 [BM 104752] (Ibbī-Suen 03²-03- 00)

- o. i 14 57 n. 408

Nisaba 15/2 97 [Anonymous] (Amar-Suena 08-04-17)

- o. 10–r. 1 70 n. 505

Nisaba 15/2 342 [Adra 15] (Šu-Suen 05-12-00)

- o. 4 43 n. 295

Nisaba 15/2 462 [Anonymous 388020] (Šu-Suen 08-00-00)

- o. 4 43 n. 295

Nisaba 15/2 668 [Private owner] (Ibbī-Suen 01-00-00)

- o. i 4 66 n. 476
- o. ii 22 56 n. 403
- o. ii 30 66 n. 476
- o. iii 38 66 n. 476
- o. iv 23 66 n. 476

Nisaba 15/2 1031 [Unknown] (00-00-00)

- o. ii' 15' 56 n. 403

Nisaba 15/2 1032 [Unknown] (00-00-00)

- o. ii 24 56 n. 403

Nisaba 23 24 [BM 110237] (Amar-Suena 05-06-00)

o. ii 12 57–58 n. 415

o. ii 18 57–58 n. 415

r. ii 16 57–58 n. 415

Nisaba 23 36 [BM 110272] (Amar-Suena 06[?]-00-00)

o. ii 7 57–58 n. 415

o. ii 14 57–58 n. 415

r. ii 12 57–58 n. 415

Nisaba 24 28 [BM 110122] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00)

o. ii 23–25 58 n. 417

o. ii 37–o. iii 2 57 n. 408

Nisaba 26 10 [BM 110149] (Amar-Suena 05-06-00)

o. ii 9–10 57–58 n. 415

o. ii 16 57–58 n. 415

r. ii 11 57–58 n. 415

Nisaba 26 80 [BM 110247] (Amar-Suena 05-00-00)

o. i 1–2 59 n. 425

o. i 4 58 n. 421

o. ii 17 59 n. 425

r. ii 1–2 59 n. 425

Nisaba 30 23 [Owen ---] (Šulgi 47-08-18)

r. 2–3 70 n. 504

NYPL 120 [NYPLC 205] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00)

o. i 9 57 n. 408

r. i 12 57–58 n. 415

r. i 23 57 n. 408

Ontario 2 488 [ROM 925.62.8] (Šulgi 25-00-00)

o. 8 57 n. 411

OrSP 18 5 17 [Schneider ---] (Šulgi 48-09-09)

o. 16–17 70 n. 511

OrSP 47–49 21 [VAT 6966] (Amar-Suena 02-09-24)

o. 1-2 70 n. 507

Owen and Wasilewska, 2000: 15, text 57 [ASM 12054] (Šulgi 32-09-00)

o. v 14' 57 n. 412

r. ii 12 57 n. 412

r. iv 4 57 n. 412

PDT 1 464 [Ist. PD ---] (Šu-Suen 01-09-06)

o. 1–2 70 n. 509

PDT 1 525 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 05-12-00)

o. i 6 66 n. 466

o. i 14 66 n. 466

PDT 2 1120 [Ist. PD ---] (Amar-Suena 04-02-02)

o. 7 63 n. 463, 86 n. 619

Princeton 1 90 [PTS 540] (Amar-Suena 02-06-09)

o. 6 70 n. 511

Princeton 2 435 [PTS 1357] (Ibbī-Suen 02-09-00)

o. 4 50 n. 367

Rochester 159 [Crozer 76] (Ibbī-Suen 03-04-00)

o. i 17 57 n. 408

r. ii 17–18 57 n. 408

Rochester 166 [Crozer 83] (Šulgi 44-00-00)

o. 4 56 n. 405

RTC 399 [AO 2444] (Ibbī-Suen 03-00-00)

r. i 24 50 n. 367

Rudik, 2013: 481–482 [HS 1556]

o. 2–4 134 n. 937

SANTAG 6 178 [Erm. 18768] (Amar-Suena 07-07-00)

o. 4 60 n. 433

SAT 2 189 [YBC 11209] (Šulgi 38-00-00)

o. 4 56 n. 403

SAT 2 724 [YBC 8255] (Amar-Suena 02-10-30)

o. iii 15–19 70 n. 507

o. iv 31–34 70 n. 507

o. vi 15–16 70 n. 507

r. i 22–23 70 n. 507

SAT 3 1708 [YBC 1166] (Šu-Suen 06-00-00)

o. 3 57 n. 408

SET 274 [RC 929] (Amar-Suena 02-00-00)

r. ii 5 58 n. 417

SNAT 533 [BM 106111] (00-00-00)

r. 4 27 n. 197

Snell, 1982: pl. 4 3 [CUL 2] (Amar-Suena 04-00-00)

r. i 9 82 n. 580

STA 4 [PUL Ex. 183] (Amar-Suena 01-05-00)

r. i 19 63 n. 460

STA 14 [PUL Ex. 835] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00)

o. i 12 57 n. 408

r. ii 4 57 n. 408

STA 15 [PUL Ex. 833] (Ibbī-Suen 02-12-00)

r. ii 15 56 n. 405

STA 16 [PUL Ex. 665] (Ibbī-Suen 02-02-00)

o. i 9 57 n. 408

r. i 22 57 n. 408

TCBI 2/2 50 [BI C 11] (Šu-Suen 07-04-00)

r. 2–4 70 n. 508

TCNU 702 [MAT 702] (Šulgi 35-01-00)

o. ii 3 56 n. 403

o. ii 23 59 n. 424

r. ii 19–21 59 n. 424

TCL 5 6038 [AO 6038] (Amar-Suena 07-00-00)

r. iv 11 27 n. 197

TRU 350 [ICP 350] (Šu-Suen 02-09-07)

r. 1–2 70–71 n. 511

TUT 159 [VAT 2330] (Amar-Suena 01-05-00)

o. v 25 63 n. 460

UDT 97 [NBC 97] (Amar-Suena 04-09-19)

o. 8–9 70 n. 509

r. 21 27 n. 198, 86 n. 619

UET 3 15 [U. 4864 (IM envelope) + U. 7002 (BM tablet)] (Šulgi 47-00-00)

o. 8 27 n. 198, 86 n. 619

UET 3 1449 [U. 3600] (Ibbī-Suen 07-10-00)

r. ii 16 62 n. 449

UET 3 1070 [U. 4841] (Ibbī-Suen 08-09-00)

o. 2 27 n. 197

UET 3 1265 [U. 4611] (00-00-00)

o. i 4 27 n. 191

UET 9 821 (Ibbī-Suen 06-05-00)

o. 3 27 n. 191

UET 9 830 (Ibbī-Suen 06-11-00)

r. 4 27 n. 191

UTI 4 2849 [Ist. Um 2849] (Šu-Suen 02-00-00)

o. 6 58 n. 418

UTI 5 3152 [Ist. Um 3152] (Amar-Suena 09-00-00)

r. 3 64 n. 465

YOS 15 115 [PM 19] (Amar-Suena 05-01-00)

o. ii 10–15 59 n. 425

o. ii 21 59 n. 425

o. iii 31 57 n. 414

o. iv 16 57 n. 414

YOS 15 118 [Private owner] (00-00- 00)

o. i 5 56 n. 401

r. ii 3 56 n. 401

YOS 15 119 [Missouri 8] (00-00-00)

o. 13 63 n. 464

YOS 18 100 [CUL 9] (00-05²-00)

o. 3 56 n. 403

8.3.1.8. Old Assyrian

TCL 14 47 [AO 8717]

o. 7 81 n. 579, 171 n. 1194

VS 26 75 [VAT 13516]

r. 7' 81 n. 579, 171 n. 1194

8.3.1.9. Old Babylonian southern Mesopotamian texts

A uru₂-ġu₁₀ im-me, Cohen, 1988: 647–649 [YBC 9862]

43 153 n. 1092

AbB 9 193 [NBC 5309] (Ḫammu-rāpi 31+)

r. 1 126 n. 879

AbB 14 137 [AO 6907] (00-00-00)

o. 1 110 n. 771

Aba-taḥ-lugalḥa to his brothers

3 120 n. 839

11 120 n. 839

Asalluḥi A

16–17 147 n. 1035

BIN 9 213 [NBC 7594] (00-10-03)

o. 1 150 n. 1069

BIN 9 185 [NBC 8416] (Išbī-Erra 22-12-00/23-01-00)

o. 5–r. 1 108–109 n. 757

BIN 9 312 [NBC 7172] (00-00-00)

o. 8 151 n. 1070

BIN 9 352 [NBC 5684] (Išbī-Erra 13-08-00)

o. 5 109 n. 760

BIN 10 104 [NBC 10075] (Išbī-Erra 13-02-00)

o. 1–8 108–109 n. 757

r. 4 109 n. 759

BPOA 9 16 [N 4838]

passim 128 n. 891

BPOA 9 17 [N 5730]

passim 128 n. 891

CDLI P231749 [YBC 2127]

d i 16 108–109 n. 757

CDLI P247861 [IB 1612b]

r. i 7 43 n. 298

CDLI P277029 [N 1915 + N 6268]

passim 162 n. 1151

CDLI P355702 [Haddad 2]

KXXIV.16 43 n. 297

Civil, 1987a: 14–15 [IM 58336] (Išbī-Erra 00-00-00)

o. 7 162 n. 1148

Copper and Silver

A 33 139 n. 986

CT 4, pl. 8 [BM 78210] (Šamšu-ditāna 07-12-20)

r. 13 100 n. 703

CT 15, pl. 18 [BM 15821]

r. 14 115 n. 808

CT 36, pl. 41–42 [BM 96940]

o. 19 43 n. 298

o. 21 115 n. 808

o. 22 134 n. 937

CT 45, pl. 84 [BM 78284] (00-00-00)

r. 15–16 100 n. 702

Cursing of Agade

35	86 n. 623
36	115 n. 810, 135 n. 948, 153 n. 1088
198–199	153 n. 1087
200	152 n. 1085, 153 n. 1087
201	43 n. 297
260	12 n. 84, 155 n. 1101

CUSAS 12 3.1.1 [MS 3214]

b iv 7	107 n. 738
b iv 11	19 n. 135
b iv 14	162 n. 1148
b vi 21	23 n. 160
c iv 28–31	152 n. 1079

CUSAS 12 7.1.A [MS 4135]

o. i 6'–8'	27 n. 196
------------	-----------

CUSAS 12, 7.1 B [MS 4158]

r. i 11'–15'	106 n. 735
--------------	------------

Death of Nannā

66–67	60 n. 432, 159 n. 1133
-------	------------------------

Death of Nawirtum

59	131 n. 919
----	------------

Diatribes C

12	147 n. 1037
----	-------------

Dumuzi and Inanna F

37	153 n. 1087
----	-------------

Dumuzi and Inanna H

17 28 n. 213, 105 n. 727

Dumuzi-Inanna T

22 124 n. 865

EEN, p. 303 Ni II-075 [UM 29-16-294]

r. i 6'–7' 151 n. 1072

Edubba'a A

41 159 n. 1127

62 165 n. 1170

Edubba'a C

48 159 n. 1132 and 1134

Enki and the World Order

50 139 n. 986

447 43 n. 297

448 79 n. 559, 139 n. 985, 154 n. 1098

Enki and Ninmah

a 13–14 147 n. 1041

Enki's Journey to Nippur

62 111 n. 784, 151 n. 1068, 190 n. 1303

63 51 n. 370, 145 n. 1026

64–65 106 n. 730, 145 n. 1026

66 94 n. 666, 145 n. 1026

67 145 n. 1026

122 152 n. 1085

Enlil A

34 131 n. 919

58 93 n. 664

Enkihegal and Enkitalu

227 166 n. 1181

Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta

265 49 n. 356

373–374 137 n. 966

Eridu Lament

A 61 43 n. 97

Er₂ na-mu-ma-al

12 134 n. 937

Fish, 1955: 115, text 1 [Wahbi 1] (Išbī-Erra 13-02-00/13-10-00)

o. 4–7 108–109 n. 757

Flood Story

D 7 147 n. 1038

Gilgameš and Aga

7 147 n. 1040

13 147 n. 1040

22 147 n. 1040

Gilgameš and the Bull of An

A 1–6 105 n. 724

D 28 142 n. 1002

Gilgameš and the Netherworld

264 114 n. 796

Ur₆ r. 6–7 98 n. 692

Ur₆ r. 12–13 98 n. 692

Goetze, 1957: 106 [CUA 57] (00-00-00)

16–19 98 n. 691

Grain and Sheep

110–112 93 n. 664

Heron and Turtle

17 131 n. 919, 147 n. 1039

Ḫendursarḫa A

207 98 n. 692

Hymn to Nannā for Šamšu-ilūna, VAS 10 215 [VAT 598]

r. 16 78 n. 555

Hoe and Plough

28 152 n. 1077

52 147 n. 1038

Ibbī-Suen A

38 122 n. 850

Ibbī-Suen B

A 29 147 n. 1040

C 13 160 n. 1137

Ibbī-Suen C

71 121 n. 850

Ibbī-Suen D

16 122 n. 850

Iddin-Dagān A

35-40 94 n. 666
41 94 n. 666, 151 n. 1066, 152 n. 1084
42-43 94 n. 666
70 43 n. 298
79 12 n. 84, 152 n. 1076
99-100 98 n. 693
204 130 n. 911, 137 n. 970
205 130 n. 911, 137 n. 970
206-207 111 n. 785, 130 n. 911, 137 n. 970

Inanna B

33 153 n. 1087

Inanna G

61 28 n. 213, 105 n. 727

Inanna and Bilulu

145 81 n. 576

Inanna and Ebiḫ

86 147 n. 1040

Inanna and Enki

I iii 2 128 n. 891
I iii 10 128 n. 891
I iv 32-41 128 n. 891
II iv 47 152 n. 1082
II iv 48 43 n. 297, 152 n. 1082 and 1084, 153 n. 1089, 155 n. 1101
II vi 24 94 n. 666, 132 n. 927

Inanna's Descent

223	185 n. 1272
335	63 n. 454
353	115 n. 810

Instructions of Šuruppak

29	147 n. 1037
156	137 n. 966
214	147 n. 1037
264	81 n. 576

Išmē-Dagān A + V

A 37–50	162 n. 1151
A 333	125 n. 873
A 338	126 n. 875
A 360	147 n. 1034
A 368–369	75 n. 536, 164-165 n. 1169, 165 n. 1175
A 370	130 n. 905 and 910, 162 n. 1154, 164-165 n. 1169
A 371	162 n. 1154, 163 n. 1167, 164-165 n. 1169, 165 n. 1175
A 372	162 n. 1154, 163 n. 1167
A 373–374	15 n. 113, 75 n. 536
A 375	15 n. 111
C 6–7	125 n. 873
C 8	105 n. 726

Išmē-Dagān Z, Text D = TRS 27 [AO 5392]

o. 11	142 n. 1003
-------	-------------

Karpeles 1, CUSAS 12 13 [PAS 27]

r. i 25	88 n. 636
---------	-----------

Keš Temple Hymn

115a 152 n. 1077

116a 79 n. 558

Kramer, 1981: 2–6 [BM 29616]

o. 21–23 185 n. 1272

Lerberghe, 1986: text 4 [CBS 50] (Abī-ešuḫ 28-03-25)

o. 7 100 n. 703

Lipit-Ištar E

31 160 n. 1137

Lu₂-azlag₂ B–C

Segment 2, 167 88 n. 639

Lugalbanda in the mountain cave

251–253 98 n. 694

Lugal u₄ me-lam₂-bi nir-ḡal

514 124 n. 865

617 114 n. 804

Man and his god

4 151 n. 1068

Martu's Marriage

60 43 n. 298

Mayer, 2005: pl. 35–36 [IB 211] (Rīm-Sîn I 38-11-00)

r. 4–5 126 n. 881

“Monkey” to his mother

6 90 n. 649, 125 n. 872, 185 n. 1272

MSL 7, p. 211 V₁₆ [N 5056 + UM 29-16-391]

o. ii 18–19 151 n. 1073

MSL 7, p. 211 V₂₄ [3N-T649]

c i' 2'–4' 151 n. 1073

MSL 12, p. 28 A [CBS 2241 + 9850 + 9851 + 11394 + N 4631 + 5222]

r. ii 26–28 219 n. 1483

MSL 12, p. 30 S' [Ni 5169]

o. ii' 6' 218 n. 1483

MSL 12, p. 157 A [IM 58433 + 58496]

242 27 n. 197

243 27 n. 199

244 27 n. 197

245–246 28 n. 205, 115 n. 811

247 27 n. 191, 115 n. 811

248 28 n. 200, 115 n. 811, 163 n. 1156

249–253 27 n. 194, 115 n. 811

MSL 12, p. 203–211 [NBC 9830]

r. i 27 27 n. 197

r. i 28 27 n. 199

r. i 31 27 n. 194

r. i 32 27 n. 191

r. i 33–34 28 n. 205

MSL 14, p. 18 B₄ [UM 55-21-347]

r. iv 37 114 n. 801

MSL 14, p. 19 B_g [CBS 15221]

o. 10 114 n. 801

MSL 14, p. 29 L_e [HS 1756]

o. 5 114 n. 801

MSL SS 1, p. 96 [Ashm. 1923-402]

a ii 37'–38' 152 n. 1079

Nanna A

6 122 n. 850

34–36 122 n. 850

Nanna I

42 122 n. 850

Nanna K

28 122 n. 850

Nanna L

53 160 n. 1137

Nanna N

23 153 n. 1089 and 1094, 155 n. 1101

26 153 n. 1094, 155 n. 1101

27 153 n. 1094

Našše A

40 107 n. 744

41 126 n. 876, 152 n. 1083

42–44 126 n. 876, 151 n. 1081

Nergal C

57 174 n. 1216

75 174 n. 1215

Nergal E

passim 174 n. 1215

Niḫ₂-ga

145 82 n. 581

Niḫ₂-ga = makkūru (bilingual version)

61 81 n. 574

Nippur Lament

38 43 n. 298

83 155 n. 1101

109 28 n. 205

117 28 n. 204

Nuska A

D 1 147 n. 1036

OECT 4 153 [Ashm. 1923-400]

c 2-4 150 n. 1057

Old Babylonian Catalogue possibly from Sippar

A 8 151 n. 1069

OIP 11 201 [CBS 6398 + 6522 + 6997]

o. ii 5 43 n. 298

PBS 5 149 [CBS 10466]

o. 10 115 n. 808

PBS 8/1 27 [CBS 13947] (00-00-00)

o. 3 166 n. 1778

PBS 8/1 92 [CBS 10888] (00-00-00)

r. 2 166 n. 1778

PBS 8/2 194 [CBS 345]

o. i 20 109 n. 762

Peterson, 2015a: 46–47 [N 2821a]

passim 145 n. 1022

Proto-aa

757:1 15 n. 112, 76 n. 541

Proto-Ea

275 178 n. 1234

327 28 n. 206

423 106 n. 736

460 114 n. 801

461 78 n. 552

757 15 n. 112

Proto-izi

II 218–220 78 n. 550

II 235 78 n. 550

II 397 76 n. 538

Proto-ka2-gal

370 136 n. 960

371 136 n. 960

372–373 136 n. 960

374 115 n. 808, 136 n. 960

Proto-lu2

59 167 n. 1185

593 75 n. 534

600–606 106 n. 726

638–640 106 n. 735

641 26 n. 183

642 26 n. 183, 127 n. 882

643 26 n. 183, 79 n. 563, 100 n. 701

644 26 n. 183, 79 n. 557, 100 n. 701

646–647 26 n. 183, 213 n. 1452

648–650 26 n. 183

Proverbs 1.15

passim 120 n. 838

Proverbs 2.39

passim 28 n. 207 and 211, 105 n. 725, 106 n. 734, 120 n. 842, 131 n. 921

Proverbs 2.41

passim 28 n. 209, 106 n. 733

Proverbs 2.43

passim 28 n. 206, 119 n. 827

Proverbs 2.54

passim 27 n. 197 and 199, 114–115, 139 n. 982

Proverbs 2.57

passim 28 n. 209, 106 n. 733

Proverbs 3.87

passim 28 n. 208

Proverbs 5.124

passim 85 n. 614

Proverbs 8.b33

passim 217 n. 1471

Proverbs 13.8

passim 147 n. 1037

MSL 11, p. 56–59 [IM 51143 + 51153]

131 201 n. 1360

196 201 n. 1360

SLT 175 [CBS 8164]

o. i 1'–2' 151 n. 1072

Sigrist, 1977: 169–183 [CBS 8550 + 14217] (Ḫammu-rāpi 35-00-00)

r. viii 19 100 n. 703

Sjöberg, 1975: 322 [CBS 10222]

r. 3' 63 n. 456

r. 6' 63 n. 456

Sumer and Ur Lament

436 140 n. 994, 152 n. 1082 and 1084

437 140 n. 994

441 152 n. 1082 and 1084

Summer and Winter

235 130 n. 906, 137 n. 970

236 137 n. 970

Šu-ilīšu A

68 174 n. 1215

Šu-Suen to Šarrum-bāni

17 147 n. 1040

Šulgi A

47 148 n. 1045

49 122 n. 851

50 122 n. 851, 152 n. 1082

51 122 n. 851, 152 n. 1082, 153 n. 1089 and 1094, 155 n. 1101

78 15 n. 111, 131 n. 914, 152 n. 1085, 153 n. 1094

Šulgi B

18–19 148 n. 1044

128 182 n. 1270

156 164 n. 1169

158 163 n. 1160

159 88 n. 640, 130 n. 911, 163 n. 1160

160 5 n. 35, 130 n. 911, 147 n. 1030

161 5 n. 37, 106–107 n. 736, 111 n. 787, 143 n. 1011, 163 n. 1159

163 51 n. 370

165 143–144 n. 1011, 200 n. 1356

166 19 n. 139

167 15 n. 111, 130 n. 910

168 129 n. 901, 137 n. 968, 129 n. 909

171 5 n. 39, 28 n. 212, 106 n. 729, 131 n. 915, 163 n. 1159

172 143 n. 1011, 149 n. 1050

173–174 29 n. 217, 165 n. 1174

196	133 n. 930
272	145 n. 1022
350	114 n. 796

Šulgi C

A 115	148 n. 1044
B 75	133 n. 930
B 76	133 n. 930, 145 n. 1023
B 77–82	133 n. 930
B 90	94 n. 666, 152 n. 1084
B 95	148 n. 1044

Šulgi D

15	148 n. 1044
37	148 n. 1044
62	148 n. 1044
217	148 n. 1043
224	148 n. 1045
295	148 n. 1045
333	148 n. 1043
366	43 n. 296
396	148 n. 1045

Šulgi E

14–15	145 n. 1022
16–33	145 n. 1022, 161 n. 1146
34	146 n. 1028, 161 n. 1146
35–37	160 n. 1144, 161 n. 1146
38	115 n. 810, 161 n. 1146
51	133 n. 930
53–55	136 n. 954
56	115 n. 810, 136 n. 954
57–58	136 n. 954

101	43 n. 296
249–251	116 n. 815
242–254	133 n. 929
255–257	133 n. 929, 140 n. 993
258–259	133 n. 929, 139 n. 992

Šulgi G

21	148 n. 1045
70	145 n. 1022

Šulgi N

45	79 n. 564, 136 n. 961, 151 n. 1066
----	------------------------------------

Šulgi R

5	148 n. 1044
50	114 n. 803
52	148 n. 1045

Šulgi T

2	148 n. 1045
10	124 n. 862
14	148 n. 1044
22	148 n. 1044

Šulgi X

120	114 n. 803
156	148 n. 1045

Takil-ilissu 2 [E4.11.2.2]

52	177 n. 1231
54	177 n. 1231

TCL 11 146 [AO 8430] (Ḫammu-rāpi 33-09-06)

r. 3–4 100 n. 702 and 704

Temple Hymns

107 43 n. 298, 122 n. 851, 140 n. 990, 154 n. 1096

183 27 n. 196, 28 n. 212, 106 n. 729 and 735

206 132 n. 925

313–314 63 n. 455

316 132 n. 925

513 132 n. 925

The Raging Sea

a+38 115 n. 808

The Slave and the Scoundrel

24 86 n. 620

TMH NF 4 1 [HS 1475 + 1476 + 1502]

r. vi 18 154 n. 1098

TMH 10 8 [HS 2077] (Šamšu-ilūna 15-02-01)

o. 8–9 126 n. 881

TMH 10 13a [HS 2352 + Ist. Ni 9207 + N unnumbered] ([...]-[...]-[...])

ii 14” 166 n. 1179

TMH 10 25 [HS 2205] (Šamšu-ilūna 12-07-03)

r. 4 28 n. 203, 79 n. 562

TMH 10 26 [HS 2390] (Sumu-el 22-10-00)

r. 6 166 n. 1179

UET 3 282 [U. 6708] (00-00-00)

o. 15 151 n. 1070

UET 5 170 [U. 7795a + U. 7786d] (Sumu-El 07-10-00)

r. 6' 166 n. 1180

UET 5 191 [U.31352] (Rīm-Sîn I 54-01-00)

r. 22–23 100 n. 705

UET 6/1 140 [U. 16881]

r. 19 144 n. 1014

UET 6/2 217 [U. 17207,92]

passim 217 n. 1471

UET 6/2 258 [U. 17207,27]

passim 120 n. 840

UET 6/2 267 [U. 17207,21]

o. 7–8 114 n. 804

UET 6/2 268 [U. 17207,88]

o. 6 28 n. 207 and 211, 105 n. 725, 106 n. 734, 131 n. 921

UET 6/2 290 [U. 17207,55]

o. 1 131 n. 921

UET 7 74 [U. 7/80]

o. 4–7 5, 94 n. 668, 111

Ugu-ḡu₁₀

147 43 n. 297

284 131 n. 916

Ur Lament

4	139 n. 986
86	153 n. 1087
356	43 n. 297, 153 n. 1091
360	136 n. 956
436	140 n. 994, 152 n. 1082
437	140 n. 994
483–485	139 n. 986

Ur-Namma A

40–41	138 n. 978
42	138 n. 974
48	138 n. 974
88	138 n. 971
91	138 n. 973
96	138 n. 973
105	138 n. 973
109	138 n. 973
113	138 n. 973
119	138 n. 973
128	138 n. 973
149–150	148 n. 975
194	135 n. 952
199	138 n. 976
201–202	138 n. 976
212	138 n. 976
224	138 n. 972

Ur-Namma B

72	135 n. 951
----	------------

Ur-Namma C

89	139 n. 986
----	------------

Ur-Namma E-F

52 135 n. 952

Ur-Namma G

28 135 n. 952

Ur₅-ra

I 606 19, n. 139

I 614 19, n. 135

I 616 19, n. 135

II 565 43 n. 298

Uruk Lament

H 16 12 n. 84, 152 n. 1076 and 1082

H 17 151 n. 1080, 155 n. 1101

H 27 126 n. 874

Utu Incantation

19–20 147 n. 1034

Veldhuis, 2017: 363–373 1 [BM 85983]

r. ii 30 43 n. 297

VS 2 29 [VAT 1339]

o. 6–7 153 n. 1093, 203 n. 1375

Wilcke, 1987: 106–107 [IB 1515a + 1515b + 1534]

r. ii' 9 88 n. 635

Winter and Summer

165 87 n. 632

236 43 n. 297

237 155 n. 1102
261 87 n. 632

YOS 5 163 [YBC 5418] (Warad-Sîn 10-10-00)

r. 2 100 n. 702–703

YOS 10 59 [Smith College 12]

r. 6 (9th omen) 149 n. 1052, 150

YOS 15 35 [University of Michigan 849–469] (Ḫammu-rāpi 31+-00-00)

o. 5 186 n. 1286

YOS 15 44 [YBC 13339] (00-00-00)

o. 10 187 n. 1288

r. 1 187 n. 1288

8.3.1.10. Old Babylonian northern Mesopotamia

ARM 1 103 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

r. 21 110 n. 772

ARM 10 126 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 8–r. 5 64 n. 466, 94 n. 669

ARM 10 125 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 4–r. 4 64 n. 466

ARM 13 142 (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

r. 17 110 n. 771

ARM 18 9 (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 8 177 n. 1230

ARM 21 106 (Zimrī-Līm 03-08-25)

r. 5 110 n. 771

ARM 23 375 (Zimrī-Līm 13-01-10 = Zimrī-Līm 8)

15 179 n. 1244

ARM 32, p. 421–422 (= earlier ARM 25 752) [M.10449] (00-07-10)

lo. e. 1 109 n. 766

Charpin, 1984: 69 [TH 82.67] (Ṭab-ṣilli-Aššur eponym 196-09-11)

o. 5 110 n. 771

Dossin, 1955: 4–11 [M. 2802]

iii 4–5 187 n. 1286

FM 3 2 [A.3165]

r. i 12 177 n. 1233

ii 17' 174 n. 1213

FM 3 8 [ARM 22/1 205] (Zimrī-Līm 05-00-00)

o. i' 9'–10' 178 n. 1242

FM 9 9 [M.7618+M.14609] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

r. 3 174 n. 1211

lo. e. 1 174 n. 1211

FM 9 10 [A.93+A.94] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 5 174 n. 1211

lo. e. 1 174 n. 1211

FM 9 11 [ARM 13 20] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

r. 1–4 88 n. 642

FM 9 12 [ARM 10 137] (Zimrī-Līm 13-00-00)

r. 4 109 n. 764

lo. e. 5 193 n. 1319, 195 n. 1326

FM 9 17 [A.2806] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

o. 18' 177 n. 228 and 1232

FM 9 23 [A.4336] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

l. e. 7–8 177 n. 1231

FM 9 31 [A.3683] (Šamšī-Addu, 00-00-00)

o. 6–10 64 n. 466

FM 9 36 [A.2521] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

o. 10–16 189 n. 1295

FM 9 38 [A.78] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 5–r. 5 174 n. 1213, 177 n. 1230

FM 9 41 [M. 14663] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

r. 1 177 n. 1230

FM 9 43 [A.1185] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

o. 5–o. 9 195 n. 1326

lo. e. 2–le. e. 3 189–190 n. 1297

FM 9 48 [M.6900] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

r. 2–4 195 n. 1325

FM 9 49 [A.3925] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

o. 18 188 n. 1292

FM 9 51 [A.3115] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

r. 2–5 185 n. 1277

FM 9 57 [ARM 1 63 + M.11322] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

o. 5–8 189 n. 1296

FM 11 180 [M.10447] (Šamšī-Addu 00-00-00)

r. 2 110 n. 771

FM 16 12 [A.309] (Zimrī-Līm 00-00-00)

r. 1–2 179 n. 1243

FM 16 41 [ARM 24 6 + M.6473 + M.12387] (Zimrī-Līm 00-07-10)

o. i 28 179 n. 1241

PIHANS 117 80 [L. 87-627] (00-00-00)

r. 2 110 n. 772

Ziegler, 1996: 479–480 [M.8426+9046]

o. 6' 86 n. 621

8.3.1.11. Middle Assyrian

KAR 158 [VAT 10101]

passim 198 n. 1336

Middle Assyrian Coronation Ritual text, KAR 135 + 137 + 216 + 217

[VAT 9583 + 9936 +? 10113 (+) 9978]

r. iii 2 29 n. 219

r. iii 10–11 10 n. 73, 20 n. 143

Tukultī-Ninurta's epic Lambert, 1957–1958: 44–47 [BM 98730]

r. 32 20 n. 143

Weidner, 1931–1932: pl. 7–8 [VAT 5744]

o. ii 33 196 n. 1333

8.3.1.12. Middle Babylonian

An = *anum*

I 264	48 n. 347
I 267–268	48 n. 347
I 270	48 n. 347
I 272–273	48 n. 347
I 362	27 n. 194, 48 n. 347
II 311	48 n. 347
II 313	48 n. 347
III 157–158	48 n. 347
III 260–262	48 n. 347
III 264	48 n. 347

Emar 6/1, p. 240 [Msk 7498f]

r. ii 17	19 n. 139
r. ii 18	107 n. 739

Emar 6/1, p. 285 [Msk 74114d]

r. 1	107 n. 739
r. 3	19 n. 139
r. 7	19 n. 135

Emar 6/1, p. 376 [Msk 74148k]

r. i' 13'	43 n. 300
-----------	-----------

Emar 6/2, p. 508–515 + 730 [Msk 74209a + 7526]

r. ii 1 107 n. 739

r. ii 6–9 201 n. 1361

r. ii 20 19 n. 139

r. ii 24 19 n. 135

CBS 7826

o. 2 198 n. 1339

CBS 8500

o. i 24 198 n. 1340

PBS 1/1 11 [CBS 11341]

r. 10 121 n. 845

passim 198 n. 1336

RS 15.30 + 15.49 + 17.387

passim 1

Syllabary B

II 348 15 n. 112

UM 29-15-72

r. 4 198 n. 1341

UM 29-15-211

r. ii 18 198 n. 1342

8.3.1.13. Neo-Assyrian

Abusch and Schwemer, 2016: 110 [W 22316]

2' 216 n. 1466

Aššurbānipal 6

vii 53 11 n. 79, 186 n. 1279, 197 n. 1335, 224 n. 1523

Aššurbānipal 7

vi 11”–12” 11 n. 79, 186 n. 1279, 197 n. 1335, 224 n. 1523

Aššurbānipal Assyrian Tablet 2 [K. 2694 + 3050]

o. iii 3’–4’ 20 n. 145, 29 n. 221

BID, Hauptritual A

IIa 66–67 221 n. 1501

Bezold, 1887–1888: pl. 3 [K. 4603]

o. i’ 2’ 216 n. 1464

Compendium

Incantation 1, 52–57 220 n. 1492

Incantation 1, 78 220 n. 1492

Incantation 1, 79 221 n. 1497

Incantation 2, 1’–25’ 219 n. 1494, 221 n. 1497 and 1498

Incantation 2, 34’–37’ 221 n. 1499

Incantation 9, 24–26 220 n. 1492 and 1493

Incantation 5, 15 226 n. 1545

Incantation 10, 41 221 n. 1499

CT 11, pl. 14–18 [K. 110]

iv 58 43 n. 301

CT 11, pl. 20 [K. 7671]

r. ii’ 2 15 n. 112

CT 12, pl. 40–41 [K. 39]

o. i 1 216 n. 1464

o. i 14 216 n. 1465

o. i 17 216 n. 1465

CT 14, pl. 8 [K. 4330]

o. i 26'–27' 154 n. 1099

CT 14, pl. 47 [BM 42339]

o. 4 110 n. 773 and 775

CT 17, pl. 19–20 [K. 3169 + 7848]

o. 1 216 n. 1467

o. 2 216 n. 1467

CT 19, pl. 23 [Rm. 344]

r. i 38' 27 n. 194

CT 58, pl. 64 [BM 54981 + 69265 +?]

o. 12' 203 n. 1376

Enūma Eliš

I 1–2 10 n. 74

VI 5 185 n. 1272

Exorcist's Manual

28 220 n. 1487, 227-228 n. 1560

Im-ma-al gu3-de2-de2

c+201 28 n. 204

KAR 132 [VAT 7849]

o. i 18'	213 n. 1444, 227 n. 1553
o. i 22'	213 n. 1444, 227 n. 1553
o. i 26'	213 n. 1444, 227 n. 1553
r. i 14	213 n. 1444

Langdon, 1931: 128 [K. 4547]

r. ii 9–10	136 n. 962
------------	------------

LKA 66 [VAT 10843]

r. 4a	134 n. 937
-------	------------

Lu₂ Short 1

205	29 n. 222, 220 n. 1488
-----	------------------------

Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi

I 52	226 n. 1547
------	-------------

Maqlû

VII 155	29 n. 221, 181–182 n. 1260, 220 n. 1489
---------	---

Maul *Ershahunga*, p. 252–253, **er₂ ša₃ ħun-ŋa₂** n. 49 [K. 9608]

o. 2	11 n. 77, 203 n. 1375
------	-----------------------

Meek, 1920: 119 [K. 945]

o. 3	106 n. 736
------	------------

MSL 6, p. 81 [K. 2028]

r. i' 2'	19 n. 135
r. i' 19'	201 n. 1364
r. i' 27'	19 n. 139

Mur-gu₄ = *imrû* = *ballu*

B, I 47	20 n. 144
B, II 117	196 n. 1332
B, II 162–170	202 n. 1368

Nabnītu IVa

333	205 n. 1386
-----	-------------

SAA 3 37 = CT 15, pl. 43–44 [K. 3476]

o. 21'	29 n. 219
--------	-----------

SAA 3 39 = KAR 307 [VAT 8917]

o. 3	20 n. 146
------	-----------

SAA 7 49 = ADD 943 (+) 944 [BM 80-7-19,262]

o. i 17'	226 n. 1546
o. i 19'	226 n. 1546
o. ii 11'	226 n. 1546

SAA 7 51 = ADD 1053 [BM 1882-5-22,533]

o. i 9'	226 n. 1545
b. e. i 15'	226 n. 1545
b. e. ii 2'	226 n. 1545
b.e. ii 6'	226 n. 1545

SAA 10 160 = CT 54, pl. 57 + 106 [K. 7655]

r. 13-14	226 n. 1545
r. 17	226 n. 1545
r. 31	226 n. 1545

SAA 10 226 = ABL 1 2 [K. 183]

o. 16–18	99 n. 696
----------	-----------

SAA 13 95 = ABL 13 440 [K. 493]

r. 1 226 n. 1549

SAA 20 7 = KAR 215 [VAT ---] + PKT 16 [VAT 10464]

o. ii 51' 29 n. 219

r. iii 2 29 n. 219

SAA 20 16

[K. 3455 + 5660 + 9937 + 17525 + 17648 + 18029 + 18117 + 18309 + 18440]

o. i 12' 29 n. 219

r. iv 13 29 n. 219

r. iv 23 29 n. 219

SAA 20 17 = PKT 19 [VAT 13597 + 13999] + OrSP 23, p. 115 [VAT 13830]

r. 8 29 n. 219

r. 11 29 n. 219

SAA 20 18 [K. 9923]

o. 14–15 29 n. 219

SAA 20 19 = KAR [VAT 10112]

o. ii 6–9 29 n. 219

r. i 13' 29 n. 219

r. ii 1' 29 n. 219

r. ii 16' 29 n. 219

r. ii 28' 29 n. 219

SAA 20 20 = CA, pl. 6 [Ist. A 127]

o. i 22 29 n. 219

SAA 20 21 = PKT 12–13 [VAT 13717]

r. 1 29 n. 219

r. 7 29 n. 219

SAA 20 31 = BBR pl. 56 [K. 8380]

o. 6'	29 n. 219
o. 15'–17'	29 n. 219
o. 22'	29 n. 219
o. 24'	227 n. 1559
r. 2	29 n. 219
r. 8	29 n. 219
r. 16	227 n. 1559
r. 20	227 n. 1559

SAA 20 32 = KAR 141 [VAT 13003]

o. 20	29 n. 219
r. 1	29 n. 219
r. 3	29 n. 219

SAA 20 52 = CA, pl. 1–2 [BM 121206]

r. i 31'–32'	29 n. 219
--------------	-----------

SAA 20 51 [Ass 13956cf]

r. ii 11'–14'	10 n. 73
---------------	----------

SAA 20 53 = PKT 14–15 [VAT 13596]

o. i 16'	29 n. 219
r. vi 1'	29 n. 219

Saṅ-gig-ga-meš

A, Incantation 1, 20	220 n. 1490 and 1492
A, Incantation 1, 36	220 n. 1492
A, Incantation 2, 1	221 n. 1497
A, Incantation 2, 7	220 n. 1494
A, Incantation 2, 17	221 n. 1499
C, Incantation 3, 27–29	220 n. 1492 and 1493

D, Incantation 1, 47 221 n. 1499

Sēnnaḥērib 37

r. 11' 186 n. 1280

TDP, pl. 48–49 [AO 6680]

r. 33 208 n. 1404

Ur₅-ra (1st Millennium)

XII, Segment 1, 114 43 n. 301

Udug ḥul / Utukkū Lemnūtu

I 7' 220 n. 1485

II 46 220 n. 1486

IV 125 60 n. 431

VII 15–17 106 n. 732, 221 n. 1500

VII 18–20 106 n. 732

VII 47–48 106 n. 732, 220 n. 1496

VII 87–88 106 n. 732

VII 131 220 n. 1486

IX 48' 221 n. 1500

XVI 120'–122' 221 n. 1496 and 1500

XVI 147'–148' 221 n. 1496

Uru am₃-ma-ir-ra-bi

XIX 38 222 n. 1505

XIX 47 11 n. 77, 203 n. 1375

XIX 48 203 n. 1375

Volk, 1989: pl. Ia–III [BM 38593]

r. iv 24 222 n. 1506

8.3.1.14. Neo-Babylonian

Baker, 2004, text no. 233 [BM 77544]

o. 3 213 n. 1443

Erim-ḫuš

III Seg. 2, 40 196 n. 1332 and 1333

GCCI 2 24 [GCBC 389] (Nabopolassar 17-08-27[?])

1 110 n. 779

MSL 17, p. 6 [OIM A1595]

o. i 2 15 n. 112

Volk, 1989: 74 text H [K. 7598 + 19304 + Sm. 1294]

o. 4' 221 n. 1504

Veldhuis, 1996: 233 [UM 29-15-134]

r. ii 1' 134 n. 937

YOS 6 62 [YBC 7388] (Nabonidus 06-12-06)

r. 7 30 n. 223

YOS 6 192 [YBC 7536] (Nabonidus 15-09-07)

r. 1 111 n. 780

8.3.1.15. Achaemenid

Sadowicz, 2018: 48–51, text n. 3 [BM 16996]

r. 5 206 n. 1393

SpTU 1 72 [W 22307/12]

r. 10–11 111 n. 781

SpTU 5 231 [W 23293/04]

r. 7 227–228 n. 1560

TCL 6 47 [MRAH O.175]

reverse 48 n. 350

8.3.1.16. Seleucid

CT 17 pl. 15–18 [BM 34223+]

iv 20' 216 n. 1468

Çağırğan and Lambert, 1991–1993: 93–100

[BM 32206 + 32237 + 34723 (S+ 76-11-17,1933+1964 + Sp II 213) (+) F 220]

o. ii 2 212 n. 1435

o. ii 15–16 212 n. 1436

o. iii 24–25 212 n. 1436

George, 1992: pl. 29, n. 18e [BM 38413]

o. 2–3 215 n. 1461, 217, 218 n. 1473 and 1474

le. e. 19'–20' 215 n. 1461, 217, 218 n. 1473 and 1477

Langdon, 1919: 73–84 [Bod. S 302]

o. 14 224 n. 1522

Linssen, 2004: 215–224 [DT 15 + DT 109 (+ BM 32485) + DT 114, MNB 1848]

338–342 220 n. 1490

SBH 1 [VAT 269 + 272 + 285 + 417 + 438 + 1774 + 1705]

o. 54–57 217 n. 1470

SBH 2 [VAT 247 + 1815]

o. 10'–12' 217 n. 1470

SBH 5 [VAT 427]

o. 6–7 217 n. 1470

SBH 13 [VAT 214]

o. 7' 217 n. 1469

SBH 14 [VAT 248 + 396]

r. 9' 217 n. 1469

SBH 21 [VAT 288 + 318 + 553 + 1828 + 1858]

o. 10 217 n. 1469

SBH 22 [VAT 283 + 401]

r. 8 217 n. 1469

SBH 25 [VAT 406 + 1782]

o. 11 217 n. 1469

SBH 26 [VAT 298 + 1736 + 1748 + 1791 + 1825 + 2178]

o. 20' 217 n. 1469

SBH 44 [VAT 555]

r. 21'–28' 217 n. 1469

SpTU 2 16 [W 22758/1]

o. ii 14'–15' 227 n. 1560

r. ii 16 227 n. 1560

SpTU 2 22 [W 22666,1 + 22666,2]

o. i 27 226 n. 1547

SpTU 3 111 [W 23289]

o. iii 9 43 n. 301

TCL 6 38 [AO 6451]

r. 45 227 n. 1556

TCL 6 39 [AO 6459]

o. 3 213 n. 1446

o. 7 213 n. 1445

o. 12 213 n. 1447, 227 n. 1557

o. 35 213 n. 1447, 227 n. 1557

TCL 6 41 [AO 6460]

o. 33' 227 n. 1553

r. 31 224 n. 1526

TCL 6 42 [AO 7439]

o. 25' 227 n. 1553

r. 6' 227 n. 1554

TCL 6 44 [AO 6479]

i 1–6 48 n. 351

8.3.2. Hittite texts

The Siege of Uršu, CTH 7/ KBo 1, 11 [VAT 7679]

r. 13 67 n. 485

r. 17–18 67 n. 485

8.3.3. Elamite texts

Böhl, 1933: 30 [LB 1003]¹⁵⁶⁶

o. 5 24 n. 165

LB 1004

lo. e. 1 24 n. 165, 32 n. 233

8.3.4. Ugaritic texts

Baal's Myth, CAT 1.101

17–18 111 n. 783

8.3.5. Classical Antiquity

Diodorus Siculus, *Bibliotheca historica*

Book I, 18, 4 24 n. 170

Book I, 81, 7 24 n. 170

Iamblichus' *Pythagoras' Life*

4, 19 6 n. 44

Pindar, *Olympian Odes*

1st Ode, 21–24 6

¹⁵⁶⁶ Actually, both texts of this list are bilingual Elamite-Akkadian.

Plato, *Cratylus*

439a 10 n. 75

Plato, *Laws*

II, 656e 24 n. 170

Plutarch, *Isis and Osiris*

13 A-B 24 n. 170

Augustine of Hippo, *De Musica*

I, 1, 2 22 n. 154

8.3.6. Other Texts

Book of Odes (*Shijing*, 詩經)

Poem n. 141 24 n. 171

Śārṅgadeva, Saṅgīta Ratnākara

I, v, 21c–24b 24 n. 172

9. BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abusch, T. (2015), *The Magical Ceremony Maqlû. A Critical Edition*, Brill, Leiden, AMD 10.
- Abusch, T. and Schwemer, D. (2016), *Corpus of Mesopotamian Anti-Witchcraft Rituals: Volume Two*, Brill, Leiden, AMD 8/2.
- al-Faruqi, L. I. (1981), *An Annotated Glossary of Arabic Musical Terms*, Greenwood, London.
- al-Rawi, F. (1992), “Two Old Akkadian Letters concerning the offices of kala’um and nārum”, *ZA* 82, 180–185.
- al-Rawi, F. and D’Agostino, F. (2005), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Texts from Umma kept in the British Museum, Part One (NATU I)*, DiScAM, Messina, Nisaba 6.
- al-Rawi, F. and Verderame, L. (2006), *Documenti Amministrativi Neo-sumerici da Umma conservati al British Museum (NATU II)*, DiScAM, Messina, Nisaba 11.
- al-Rawi, F. and Verderame, L. (2009), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Texts from Umma kept in the British Museum. Part Three (NATU III)*, DiScAM, Messina, Nisaba 23.
- al-Rawi, F.; D’Agostino, F. and Taylor, J. (2009), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Texts from Umma kept in the British Museum, Part Four (NATU IV)* [In collaboration with Francesca Goello], DiScAM, Messina, Nisaba 24.
- al-Rawi, F.; Gorello, F. and Notizia, P. (2013), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Texts from Umma kept in the British Museum. Part Five (NATU V)*, DiScAM, Messina, Nisaba 26.
- Allotte de la Fuÿe, M. F. (1908–1920) *Documents présargoniques*, 4 volumes, Ernest Leroux, Paris.
- Alster, B. (1974), *The Instructions of Suruppak. A Sumerian Proverb Collection*, Akademisk Forlag, Copenhagen, Mesopotamia 2.
- Alster, B. (1975), “On the Sumerian Composition «The Father and his Disobedient Son»”, *RA* 69, 81–84.
- Alster, B. (1997), *Proverbs of Ancient Sumer. The World’s Earliest Proverb Collection*, Two Volumes, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Alster, B. (2005), *Wisdom of Ancient Sumer*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Alster, B. and Geller, M. J. (1990), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets. Part 58*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.

- Altenmüller, E. (2004), “Singen - die Ursprache? Zur Evolution und Hirnphysiologie des Gesangs”, en Hickmann, E. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 4*, Leidorf, Rahden, 3-9.
- Álvarez-Mon, J. (2017), “The Elamite Royal Orchestra from Madaktu (653 BC)”, *Elamica 7*, 1-34.
- Ambos, C. (2008), “Sänger, Sängerin. A. Philologisch”, *RIA 11 7–8*, 499–503.
- Ambos, C. (2011), “Magie (Alter Orient)”, *Wissenschaftliche Bibellexikon im Internet*, [Online document], <<https://www.bibelwissenschaft.de/stichwort/25322/>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Ambos, C. (2012), “Tanz. A. I. In Mesopotamien. Philologisch”, *RIA 13 5/6*, 445–447.
- Andrés Toledo, M. A. (2016), “Indo-Iranian Weavers of Old and New Hymns”, in: Fanfani, G., Harlow, M. and Nosch, M. L. (ed.), *Spinning Fates and the Song of the Loom*, Oxbow, Oxford and Philadelphia, 17–23.
- Archi, A. (2003-2005), “Palast. A. II. Ebla (Ibla*)”, *RIA 10*, 204–205.
- Archi, A. (ed.), *Tradition and Innovation in the Ancient Near East. Proceedings of the 57th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale at Rome, 4-8 July 2011*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana).
- Archi, A. and Pomponio, F. (1995), *Testi Cuneiformi Neo-Sumerici da Umma. NN. 0413-0723*, Museo Egizio di Torino, Turin, Torino 8.
- Arkhipov, I. (2012), *Le Vocabulaire de la Métallurgie et la Nomenclature des Objets en Métal dans les Textes de Mari. Matériaux pour le Dictionnaire de Babylonien de Paris. Tome III*, Peeters, Leuven, Paris and Walpole (Massachusetts), ARM 32.
- Arkhipov, I. (2019), “Zimri-Lim offers a throne to Dagan of Terqa”, in: Evans, J. M. and Rossberger, E. (ed.), *Ancient Near Eastern Temple Inventories in the Third and Second Millennia BCE: Integrating Archaeological, Textual, and Visual Sources. Proceedings of a Conference held at the LMU Centre for Advanced Studies, November 14-15, 2016*, PeWe-Verlag, München, Münchener Abhandlungen zum Alten Orient 4, 131-137.
- Arnaud, D. (1985a), *Recherches au Pays d'Aštata. Emar VI. Tome 1. Textes sumériens et accadiens. Textes*, Paris, Editions Recherche sur les Civilisations.
- Arnaud, D. (1985b), *Recherches au Pays d'Aštata. Emar VI. Tome 2. Textes sumériens et accadiens. Planches*, Paris, Editions Recherche sur les Civilisations.

- Arroyo Cuadra, S. (2018), *Los Kudurru Babilónicos. Función y Simbolismo en su Contexto Histórico y Cultural*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Universidad Nacional de Educación a Distancia.
- Attinger, P. (1993), *Eléments de linguistique sumérienne. La construction de du₁₁/e/di "dire"*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, OBO Sonderband.
- Attinger, P. (2005), "A propos de AK "faire" (II)", *ZA* 95, 208–275.
- Attinger, P. (2009), "Review of: Ebeling, Jarle/Graham Cunningham (ed.), *Analysing Literary Sumerian: Corpus based Approaches*. London, Oakville: Equinox Publishing Ltd, 2007. XIV, 412 p. 23,4 × 15,6 cm. ISBN 1-84553-229-5. Preis: £ 75,00/\$ 135,00", *ZA* 99, 127–134.
- Attinger, P. (2011), "/ug/ versus uš₂", *NABU* 2011/1, n. 5, 6–7.
- Attinger, P. (2014), "Iddin-Dagan A", Koslova, N.; Vizirova, E. and Zólyomi, G. (ed.), *Studies in Sumerian Language and Literature. Festschrift für Joachim Krecher*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), *Babel und Bibel* 8, 11–82.
- Attinger, P. (2015), *Enlil A (4.5.1)*, [Online document]
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2600235#.XSpEC-gzZPY>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Attinger, P. (2018), *Choix de Proverbes (6.1-6.2)*, [Online document]
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2667755#.XXZMrSgzZPY>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Attinger, P. (2019a), *Bilgames, Enkidu et le monde infernal (1.3.1)*, [Online document]
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2600245#.XXZNJygzZPY>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Attinger, P. (2019b), *Dumuzi Inanna H (4.08.08)*, [Online document]
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2599581#.XSpD6egzZPY>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019]
- Attinger, P. (2019c), *La Descente d'Inanna dans le Monde Infernal*, [Online document].
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2599619#.XYOYoSgzZPY>>
[Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Attinger, P. (2019d), *Lexique sumérien-français*, [Online document].
<<https://zenodo.org/record/2585683#.XSpFY-gzZPY>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019].

- Attinger, P. (2019e), “Našše A”, in: Chambon, G.; Ghichard, M. and Langlois, A.-I. (ed.), *De l'Argile au Numérique. Mélanges Assyriologiques en l'Honneur de Dominique Charpin* (with the collaboration of Thomas Römer and Nele Ziegler), 2 volumes, Peeters, Leuven, Paris and Bristol (Connecticut), Publications de l'Institut du Proche-Orient Ancien 3.
- Attinger, P. (2019f), *Šulgi X (2.4.24.)*, [Online document]
 <<https://zenodo.org/record/2600006#.XSpDy-gzZPY>>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Attinger, P. and Krebernik, M. (2005), “L’Hymne à Ḫendursaġa (Ḫendrusaġa A)”, in: Rollinger, R. (ed.), *Von Sumer bis Homer. Festschrift für Manfred Schretter zum 60. Geburtstag am 25. Februar 2004*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 325, 21–91.
- Averbeck, Richard E. (1987), *A preliminary study of ritual and structure in the Cylinders of Gudea*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Dropsie College, University of Pennsylvania, Merion (Pennsylvania), [Online document].
 <https://www.academia.edu/14523225/The_Cylinders_of_Gudea>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Baker, H. D. (2002), “Approaches to Akkadian Name-Giving in First-Millennium BC Mesopotamia”, in: Wunsch, C. (ed.), *Minining the Archives. Festschrift for Christopher Walker on the Occasion of His 60th Birthday*, Islet, Dresden, 1–24.
- Baker, H. D. (2004), *The Archive of the Nappāḫu Family*, Institut für Orientalistik der Universität Wien, Vienna, BAfO 30.
- Balke, Th. E. (2006), *Das sumerische Dimensionalkassensystem*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 331.
- Bar-Moshe, A. (2016), *The Function of Preverbal Markers in Jewish-Baghdadi Arabic*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem, [Online document]
 <https://www.academia.edu/34929842/The_Functions_of_Preverbal_Markers_in_Jewish-Baghdadi_Arabic> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Barahona, A. (1997), “Reflexiones sobre la posibilidad de una notación musical en el Antiguo Egipto”, *Boletín de la Asociación Española de Egiptología* 7, 229–248.
- Barahona, A. (2000), “Aproximación al concepto de música del Egipto Antiguo”, in: M. A. Molinero and D. Sola (eds) *Arte y sociedad del Egipto antiguo*, Encuentro, Madrid, 37–65.

- Barahona, A. (2002), “Two lexicological notes related to the concept of music in Ancient Egypt”, *Papers on Ancient Egypt - Trabajos de Egiptología* 1, 11–15.
- Barahona, A. (2005), “El concepto de música del Egipto antiguo: una aproximación metodológica”, in: Cervelló, J.; Díaz de Cerio, M., and Ribó, D. (eds.), *Actas del Segundo Congreso Ibérico de Egiptología: Bellaterra, 12-15 de marzo de 2001*, Bellaterra, Barcelona, 41–53.
- Bardet, G.; Joannès, F.; Lafont, B.; Soubeyran, D. and Villard, P. (1984), *Archives Administrative de Mari I*, Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, Paris, ARM 23.
- Bartash, V. (2016), *Sumerian Administrative and Legal Documents ca. 2900-2200 BC in the Schøyen Collection*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 35.
- Barth, J. (1894), *Die Nominalbildung in den semitischen Sprachen*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Bauer, J. (1970), “Ein Nachtrag zu Edmond Sollberger, Le syllabaire présargonique de Lagaš”, *RA* 64, 188–189.
- Bauer, J. (1992), “Der “Leierspieler””, *AoN* 51, 4–5.
- Bauer, J. (1998), “Der Vorsargonische Abschnitt der Mesopotamischen Geschichte”, in: Bauer, J.; Englund, R.; and Krebernik, M. (ed.), *Mesopotamien: Späturuk-Zeit und Frühdynastische Zeit*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, OBO 160/1, 431–585.
- Beaulieu, P.-A. (2010), “The Afterlife of Assyrian Scholarship in Hellenistic Babylonia”, in: Stackert, J., Porter, B. N. and Wright, D. P. (eds.), *Gazing on the Deep: Ancient Near Eastern and Other Studies in Honor of Tzvi Abusch*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), 1–18.
- Beaulieu, P.-A. (2017), “Assyria in Late Babylonian Sources”, in: Frahm, E. (ed.), *A Companion to Assyria*, Wiley Blackwell, 549–555.
- Beekes, R. (2010), *Etymological Dictionary of Greek* [with the assistance of Lucien van Beek]. Two Volumes, Brill, Leiden and Boston, Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series 10/1+2.
- Belli, O. (2007), “Urartularda Kadın Müzisyen ve Dansçılar”, in: Alparslan, M.; Doğan-Alparslan, M. and Peker, H. (ed.), *Belkis Dinçol ve Ali Dinçol'a Armağan VITA. Festschrift in Honor of Belkis Dinçol and Ali Dinçol*, Yayinlari, Istanbul, 87–103.
- Benito, C. A. (1969), ‘*Enki and Ninmah*’ and ‘*Enki and the World Order*’, Graduate School of Arts and Sciences, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), [Online document].

<https://repository.upenn.edu/dissertations/AAI7016124/>>

[Last search on 12/10/2019].

- Bezold, Ch. (1887–1888), “A New Text Concerning the Star KAK-SI-DI”, *PSBA* 10, 265–280.
- Biggs, R. D. (1974), *Inscriptions from Tell Abū Šalābīkh*, Chicago University Press, Oriental Institute of Chicago, OIP 99.
- Black, J. (1991), “Eme-sal Cult Songs and Prayers”, in: Michalowski, P.; Steinkeller, P.; Stone, E. C. and Zettler, R. L. (ed.), *Velles Paraules: Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Honor of Miguel Civil on the Occasion of his Sixty-Fifth Birthday*, AUSA, Sabadell, *AuOr* 9, 23–36.
- Black, J.; George, A.; Postgate, N. (2000), *A Concise Dictionary of Akkadian*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, SANTAG 5.
- Bleibtreu, E.; Hirsch, H.; Hunger, H. and Stola, R. (1988), “Assyriologie. Register. 1. Realien, 2. Wörter. 3. Textstellen (1986 - Februar 1988)”, *AfO* 35, 261–398.
- Böck, B. A. (2000), *Die babylonisch-assyrische Morphoskopie*, Institut für Orientalistik der Universität Wien and Berger & Söhne GmbH, Vienna, BAfO 27.
- Böhl, F. M. Th. (1933), *Mededeelingen uit de Leidsche verzameling van spijkerschrift-inscripties II. Oorkonden uit de periode van 2000-1200 v. Chr.*, Noord-Hollandsche Uitgevers-Maatschappij, Amsterdam, Mededeelingen der Koninklijke Nederlandsche Akademie van Wetenschappen, Afd. Letterkunde, 78/2.
- Bongenaar, A. C. V. M. (1997), *The Neo-Babylonian Ebabbar Temple at Sippar: its Administration and its Prosopography*, Leiden, Peeters, PIHANS 80.
- Borger, R. (2004), *Mesopotamisches Zeichenlexikon*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 305.
- Borkowski, S. (2018), “Visualizing the Provenance of Sumerian Literary Texts”, *BaF-Online. Proceedings of the Berner altorientalisches Forum 2*, [Online document] <https://doi.org/10.22012/baf.2017.05> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Bottéro, J. and Kramer, S. (ed.) (1989), *Lorsque les dieux faisaient l'homme*, Éditions Gallimard, Paris.
- Bowen, J. A. (2017), *A Preliminary Study of the Sumerian Curricular and Lamentational Texts from the Old Babylonian City of Kish*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, John Hopkins University, [Online document] <https://jscholarship.library.jhu.edu/handle/1774.2/40851>>

[Last search 04/09/2019].

- Brinkman, J. A. (1980), “Forced Laborers in the Middle Babylonian Period”, *JCS* 32/1, 17–22.
- Brinkman, J. A. (2004), “Administration and Society in Kassite Babylonia”, *JAOS* 124/2, 283–304.
- Buccellati, G. (1966), *The Amorites of the Ur III Period*, Istituto Orientali di Napoli, Naples.
- Burke, A. (2018), *Walled Up to Heaven: The Evolution of Middle Bronze Age Fortification Strategies in the Levant*, Brill, Leiden.
- Bush, F. W. (1964), *A Grammar of the Hurrian Language*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Brandeis University, Waltham (Massachusetts), [Online document] <<http://pubman.mpg.de/pubman/faces/viewItemFullPage.jsp?itemId=escidoc%3A400906%3A2>> [Last search on 14/08/2018].
- Calvot, D.; Pettinato, G.; Picchioni, S.A.; Reshid, F. (1979), *Textes économiques du Selluš-Dagan du Musée du Louvre et du Collège de France* (D. Calvot); *Testi economici dell'Iraq Museum Baghdad* (G. Pettinato - S.A. Picchioni - F. Reshid), Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 8.
- Casey, R. A. (1998), *Inanna and Enki in Sumer: An Ancient Conflict Revisited*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Faculty of the Division of Humanities and Social Sciences, San Francisco (California).
- Castellino, G. (1969), “Incantion to Utu”, *OrAnt* 8, 1–57.
- Castellino, G. (1972), *Two Šulgi Hymns (B, C)*, Istituto di Studi del Vicino Oriente. Università di Roma, Rome, StSem 42.
- Caubet, A. (2016), “Terracotta Figurines of Musicians from Mesopotamia and Elam”, in: Bellia, A. and Marconi, C. (ed.), *Musicians in Ancient Coroplastic Art: Iconography, Ritual Contexts, and Functions*, Istituti Editoriali Poligrafici Internazionali, Pisa and Rome, 35–43.
- Cavigneaux, A. (1978), “L’Essence Divine”, *JCS* 30/3, 177–185.
- Cavigneaux, A. (1996), “Notes Sumérologiques”, *ASJ* 18, 27–45.
- Cavigneaux, A. and al-Rawi, F. N. H. (2000), *Gilgameš et la Mort. Textes de Tell Haddad VI avec un appendice sur les textes funéraires sumériens*, Styx, Groningen, CM 19.
- Cavigneaux, A.; Güterbock, H. G.; Roth, M. T.; Farber, G. (1985), *The Series Erim-ḫuš = anantu and An-ta-gál = šaqû*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 17.

- Ceccarelli, M. (2012), “Enkis Reise nach Nippur”, in: Mittermayer, C. and Ecklin, S. (ed.), *Altorientalische Studien zu Ehren von Pascal Attinger, mu-ni u₄ ul-li₂-a-aš ġa₂-ġa₂-de₃*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, OBO 256, 89–118.
- Ceccarelli, M. (2016), *Enki und Ninmah: eine mythische Erzählung in sumerischer Sprache*, Tübingen, Mohr Siebeck, Oriental Religions in the Antiquity 16.
- Ceccarelli, M. (2018), “Der Umgang mit streitenden Schülern im Edubba’a nach den sumerischen Schulstreitgesprächen *Enkiġeġal und Enkitalu* und *Ġirinisa und Enkimanšum*”, *AoF* 45/2, 133–155.
- Ceccarelli, M. (forthcoming), The *editio princeps* of *Enkiġeġal and Enkitalu*. We do not know more details about this publication.
- Chambon, G. (2009), *Les Archives du vin à Mari*, Societé d’Études du Proche-Orient Ancien, Paris, FM 11.
- Charpin, D. (1984), “Inscriptions Votives d’Époque Assyrienne”, *MARI* 3, 31-81.
- Charpin, D. (1986), *Le clergé d’Ur au siècle d’Hammurabi (XIXe-XVIIIe siècles av. J.-C.)*, Librairie Droz, Paris and Geneva, HEO 22.
- Charpin, D. (1995), “The History of Ancient Mesopotamia: An Overview”, *CANE* 2, 807-829.
- Charpin, D. (2006), “Louange des dieux et des rois”, *Dossiers d’Archéologie* 310 (*La Musique au Proche-Orient Ancien*), 56–60.
- Charpin, D. (2014), *Comment peut-on être assyriologue? Leçon inaugural prononcée le jeudi 2 octobre 2014*, Collège de France, Paris, [Online document] <<https://books.openedition.org/cdf/4175>> [Last search the 14/10/2019].
- Charpin, D. (2018), “Chroniques Bibliographiques. 21. À l’Occasion des Dix Ans du Project Archibab”, *RA* 112/1, 177–208.
- Cheng, J. (2012), “The Horizontal Forearm Harp: Assyria’s National Instrument”, *Iraq* 74, 75–87.
- Chiera, E. (1914), *Legal and Administrative Documents from Nippur Chiefly from the Dynasties of Isin and Larsa*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), PBS 8/1.
- Chiera, E. (1922a), *Old Babylonian Contracts*, University of the Museum of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia, PBS 8/2.
- Chiera, E. (1922b), *Selected temple accounts from Telloh, Yokha and Drehem. Cuneiform Tablets in the Library of Princeton University*, Philadelphia.

- Chiera, E. (1929), *Sumerian Lexical Texts from the Temple School of Nippur*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), OIP 11.
- Chiera, E. (1934a), *Sumerian Epics and Myths*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), OIP 15.
- Chiera, E. (1934b), *Sumerian Texts of Varied Content*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), OIP 16.
- Colonna d'Istria, L. (2011), "Pièces tissées et musiciens: à propos d'ARM XIX 321", *NABU* 2011/4, n. 78, 94.
- Crisostomo, C. J. (2019), *Translation as Scholarship. Language, Writing, and Bilingual Education in Ancient Babylonia*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin/Boston, SANER 22.
- Civil, M. (1969), *The Series lú = ša and Related Texts* [with the collaboration of R. D. Biggs, H. G. Güterbock, H. J. Nissen and E. Reiner], Pontificum Institutum Biblicum, Rome, MSL 12.
- Civil, M. (1971), *Izi = išātu, Ká-gal = abullu and Níg-ga = makkūru*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 13.
- Civil, M. (1979), *Ea A = nâqu, Aa A = nâqu, with their Forerunners and Related Texts*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 14.
- Civil, M. (1987a), "An inscription of Išbi-Erra", *NABU* 1987/2, n 28, 14–15.
- Civil, M. (1987b), "The *Tigidlu* Bird and a Musical Instrument", *NABU* 1987/2, n. 48, 26–27.
- Civil, M. (1992), "Education (Mesopotamia)", in: Freedman, D. N. *et al.* (ed.), *The Anchor Bible Dictionary*, volume 2, Doubleday, London, Toronto, Sydney and Auckland, 301–305.
- Civil, M. (1994), *The Farmer's Instructions. A Sumerian Agricultural Manual*, AUSA, Sabadell.
- Civil, M. (1995), "Ancient Mesopotamian Lexicography", *CANE* 4, 2305–2314.
- Civil, M. (2008), *The Early Dynastic Practical Vocabulary A (Archaic HAR-ra A)*, Rome, Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, ARES 3.
- Civil, M. (2010), *The Lexical Texts in the Schøyen Collection*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 12.
- Civil, M. (2011), "The Law Collection of Ur-Namma", in: George, A. R. (ed.), *Cuneiform Royal Inscriptions and Related Texts in the Schøyen Collection*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 17, 221–286.

- Civil, M. (2013), “Remarks on AD-GI₄ (A.K.A “Archaic Word List C” or “Tribute””, *JCS* 65, 13–68.
- Civil, M., Gurney, O. R., and Kennedy, D. A. (1986), *The Sag-Tablet, Lexical Texts in the Ashmolean Museum, Middle Babylonian Grammatical Texts, Miscellaneous Texts*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL SS 1.
- Clay, J. S. (1988), “What the Muses Sang: Theogony 1-115”, *Greek, Roman, and Byzantine Studies* 29/4, 323–333.
- Clines, D. J. A. (ed.) (2009), *The Concise Dictionary of Classical Hebrew*, Sheffield, Sheffield Phoenix Press.
- Clifton, Th. (1983), *Music as Heard: A Study in Applied Phenomenology*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut) and London.
- Cocquerillat, D. (1972–1975), “Handwerker, spätbabylonisch”, *RIA* 4, 98–105.
- Cohen, M. E. (1981), *Sumerian Hymnology: The Ershemma*, Hebrew Union College and Jewish Institute of Religion, Cincinnati, HUCA 2.
- Cohen, M. E. (1974), *Balag-Compositions: Sumerian Lamentation Liturgies of the Second and First Millennium B.C.*, Undena, Malibu, SANE 1.2.
- Cohen, M. E. (1988), *The Canonical Lamentations of Ancient Mesopotamia*, Potomac (Maryland), Capital Decisions Limited.
- Cohen, Y. and Kedar, S. (2011), “Teacher-Student Relationships: Two Case Studies”, in: Radner, K. and Robson, E. (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 229–247.
- Colburn, J. (2009), “A New Interpretation of the Nippur Music-Instruction Fragments”, *JCS* 61, 97–109.
- Collon, D. (2003), “Dance in Ancient Mesopotamia”, *Near Eastern Archaeology* 66/3, 96–102.
- Collon, D. (2010), “Playing in concert in the Ancient Near East”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2008), The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008*, ICONEA Publications, London, 47–65.
- Collon, D. (2013), “The Social Status of Musicians based on their Depictions in Mesopotamian Art”, in: Emerit, S. (ed.), *Le statut du musicien dans la Méditerranée ancienne: Égypte, Mésopotamie, Grèce, Rome: actes de la table ronde internationale tennue à Lyon, Maison de l’Orient et de la Méditerranée, les*

- 4 et 5 juillet 2008, Institut Français d'Archéologie Orientale, Cairo, IFAO Bibliothèque d'Étude 159, 17–30.
- Collon, D. and Kilmer, A. D. (1980), “The Lute in Ancient Mesopotamia”, in: Mitchell, T. C. (ed.), *Music and Civilisation. The British Museum Yearbook 4*, British Museum, London, 13–27.
- Corò, P. (2005), *Prebende Templari in Età Seleucide*, S.A.R.G.O.N, Padua, History of the Ancient Near East. Monographs 8.
- Cook, S. B. (1995), *Unity and Diversity in the Musical Thought of Warring States China*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, University of Michigan.
- Cooper, J. S. (1997), “Gendered Sexuality in Sumerian Love Poetry”, in: Finkel, I. L. and Geller, M. J. (ed.), *Sumerian Gods and Their Representations*, Styx, Groningen, CM 7, 85–97.
- Cooper, J. S. (2006), “Genre, Gender, and the Sumerian Lamentation”, *JCS* 58, 39–47.
- Cooper, J. S. (2017), ““Enlil and Namzitara” Reconsidered”, in: Feliu, L.; Karahashi, F. and Rubio, G. (eds.), *The First Ninety Years. A Sumerian Celebration in Honor of Miguel Civil*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, SANER 12, 37–53.
- Correa Pabón, G. L. (2009), *Numerus-Proportio en el De Musica de San Agustín (Libros I y VI). La Tradición Pitagórico-Platónica*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Universidad de Salamanca, Departamento de Filosofía y Lógica y Filosofía de la Ciencia, [Online document]
https://gredos.usal.es/bitstream/handle/10366/76465/DFLFC_CorreaPabonGL_MusicadeSanAgustin.pdf;jsessionid=5362FAFBD4DAFE600D2174ED4554779E?sequence=1 > [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Correll, Ch. (1990), “Zum adjektivischen “Abstraktplural” des Akkadischen”, *Linguistische Berichte* 128, 332–337.
- Couto Ferreira, É. (2009): *Etnoanatomía y partonomía del cuerpo humano en sumerio y acadio. El léxico Ugu-mu*, Departament d'Humanitats, Universidad Pompeu i Fabra, Barcelona, [Online document]
<http://www.tdx.cat/bitstream/handle/10803/7473/TECF.pdf?sequence=1> > [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Crawford, V. E. (1954), *Sumerian Economic Texts from the First Dynasty of Isin*, New Haven (Connecticut), Yale Universtiy Press, BIN 9.
- Crocker, R. L. (1997), “Mesopotamian Tonal Systems”, *Iraq* 59, 189–202.

- Crocker, R. L. (2011), “No Polyphony before A.D. 900!”, in: Heimpel, W. and Frantz-Szabó, G. (ed.), *Strings and Threads. A Celebration of the Work of Anne Draffkorn Kilmer*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 45–58.
- Çağırğan, G. and Lambert, W. G. (1991–1993), “The Late Babylonian *Kislīmu* Ritual for Esagil”, *JCS* 43, 89–106.
- Çavuşoğlu, R.; Işık, K. and Göcke, B. (2014), “Women and Their Status in Urartu: A Critical Review”, *ANES* 51, 235–261.
- Çig, M. (1976), “New Dates Formulas from the Tablet Collection of the Istanbul Archaeological Museums”, in: Eichler, B. L., et al. (eds.), *Kramer Anniversary Volume. Cuneiform Studies in Honor of Samuel Noah Kramer*, Verlag Butzon & Bercker and Neukirchener Verlag, Kevelaer and Neukirchen Vluyn, AOAT 25, 75–82.
- Çiğ, M. I.; Kızılyay, H.; Kraus, F. (1952), *Eski Babil zamanına ait Nippur hukukî vesikalari = Altbabylonische Rechtsurkunden aus Nippur*, Istanbul, Millî Eğitim Basımevi.
- Çiğ, M. I., Kızılyay, H., and Kramer S. N. (ed.) (1969), *İstanbul Arkeoloji Müzelerinde bulunan Sumer edebî tablet ve parçaları (= Sumerian Literary Tablets and Fragments in the Archaeological Museum of Istanbul) 1*, Türk Tarih Kurumu Yayınları, Ankara.
- Çiğ, M. I., Kızılyay, H., and Kramer S. N. (ed.) (1976), *İstanbul Arkeoloji Müzelerinde bulunan Sumer edebî tablet ve parçaları (Sumerian Literary Tablets and Fragments in the Archaeological Museum of Istanbul) 2*, Türk Tarih Kurumu Yayınları, Ankara.
- Çig, M.; Kızılyay, H. and Salonen, A. (1954), *Die Puzriš-Dagan-Texte der Istanbul Archäologischen Museen Teil I: Nrr. 1-725*, Helsinki 1954, AASF 92.
- Černý, M. K. (1988), “Probleme der Musikaufzeichnung aus Ugarit - Versuch einer Neuen Interpretation des "Hymns h 6”, Vavroušek, P. and Souček, V. (ed.), Šulmu. Papers on the Ancient Near East Presented at International Conference of Socialist Countries (Prague, Sept. 30 - Oct. 3, 1986), Charles University, Prague, 49–62.
- Černý, M. K. (2004), “Another Look at the Mesopotamian “Tonal” System - Ascending or Descending?”, *ArOr* 72, 25–32.
- D’Agostino, F. (1997), *Testi amministrativi della III Dinastia di Ur dal Museo Statale Ermitage San Pietroburgo - Russia*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 20.

- D'Agostino, F. (2012), "Some considerations on u₄-da-tuš (bear tamer?) and jugglery in Ur III", *RA* 106, 89–99.
- D'Amico, L. and Kaye, A. (2004), *Musica dell'Africa Nera*, L'epos, Palermo.
- Dahl, J. L. (2007), *The Ruling Family of Ur III Umma, A Prosopographical Analysis of an Elite Family in Southern Iraq 4000 Years Ago*, Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten (NINO), Leiden, PIHANS 108.
- Darlene, L. (1976), *Economic Texts from the Third Dynasty of Ur*, Trustees of the British Museum, London, UET 9.
- de Boer, R. (2014), *Amorites in the Early Old Babylonian Period*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Universiteit Leiden, Leiden, [Online document] <<https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/handle/1887/25842>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- de Maaijer, R. (2001), "Late Third Millennium Identifying Marks", in: van Soldt, W. H., Dercksen, J. G.; Kouwenberg, N. J. C. and Krispijn, Th. J. H. (eds.), *Veenhof Anniversary Volume. Studies Presented to Klaas R. Veenhof on the Occasion of his Sixty-Fifth Birthday*, Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten (NINO), Leiden, 301–324.
- de Schauensee, M. (2002), *Two Lyres from Ur*, University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, Philadelphia.
- Deimel, A. (1923), *Schultexte aus Fara*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, WVDOG 43.
- Delaporte, L. (1911), "Tablettes de Draham", *RA* 8, 183-198.
- Delnero, P. (2006), *Variation in Sumerian Literary Compositions: A Case Study Based on the Decad*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, University of Pennsylvania, Pennsylvania (Philadelphia) [Online document] Available from ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. (305256016) [Last search on 26/01/2019].
- Delnero, P. (2010), "Sumerian Extract Tablets and Scribal Education", *JCS* 62, 53-69.
- Delnero, P. (2015), "Texts and Performance: The Materiality and Function of the Sumerian Liturgical Corpus", in: Delnero, P. and Lauinger, J. (ed.), *Texts and Contexts: The Circulation and Transmission of Cuneiform Texts in Social Space*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, SANER 9, 87–118.
- Démare-Lafont, S. (2011), "L'adoption à l'époque paléo-babylonienne", *Annuaire de l'École Pratique des Hautes Études. Résumés des Conférences et Travaux 142 (2009-2010)*, 14-16.

- Démare-Lafont, S. (2016–2017), “Adoption and apprenticeship in the Old Babylonian period”, *JEOL* 46, 45–57.
- Deubner, L. (1937), *Iamblich. De Vita Pythagorica Liber*, Lipsiae, B. G. Teubner, Bibliotheca Scriptorum Graecorum et Romanorum Teubneriana.
- Dietrich, M. (1979), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 54. Neo-Babylonian Letters from the Kuyunjik Collection*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Dietrich, M.; Loretz, O. and Sanmartín, J. (1976), *Die keil-alphabetischen Texte aus Ugarit*, Butzon & Bercker and Neukirchener Verlag, Kevelaer and Neukirchen-Vluyn, AOAT 24/1.
- Dilley, R. (1992), “Dreams, inspiration and craftwork among Tukolor weavers”, in: Jedrej, M. M. Ch. and Shaw, R. (ed.), *Dreaming, Religion, and Society in Africa*, Brill, Leiden, New York and Köln, 71–85.
- Donbaz, V. and Foster, B. (1982), *Sargonic Texts from Telloh in the Istanbul Archaeological Museums I*, University Museum, Philadelphia, OPBF 5.
- Dossin, G. (1946), *Archives royales de Mari*, Vol. 1, *Lettres*, Geuthner, Paris, TCL 22.
- Dossin, G. (1950), *Correspondance de Šamši-Addu et de Ses Fils*, Imprimerie Nationale, Paris, ARM 1.
- Dossin, G. (1951), *Lettres*, Geuthner, Paris, ARM 5, TCL 26.
- Dossin, G. (1955), “L’Inscription de Fondation de Iahtun-Lim, roi de Mari”, *Syria* 32/1, 1–28.
- Dossin, G. (1978), *Correspondance Féminine Transcrite et Traduite*, Geuthner, Paris, ARM 10.
- Dossin, G.; Bottéro, J.; Birot, M.; Burke, M. L.; Kupper, J.-R., and Finet, A. (1964), *Textes Divers Transcrits, Traduits et Commentés à l'Occasion du XXXe Anniversaire de la Dévoucerte de Mari*, Geuthner, Paris, ARM 13.
- Doty, L. T. (1977), *Cuneiform Archives from Hellenistic Uruk*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Yale University.
- Dougherty, R. Ph. (1923), *Records from Erech. Time of Nabonidus (555-538 B.C.)*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut), YOS 6.
- Dougherty, R. P. (1933), *Archives from Erech, Neo-Babylonian and Persia Periods*, Yale University Press, New Haven, GCCI 2.
- Duchesne-Guillemain, M. (1975), “Les Problèmes de la Notation Hourrite”, *RA* 69, 159–173.

- Duchesne-Guillemain, M. (1980), “Sur la restitution de la musique hourrite”, *Revue de Musicologie* 66 n. 1, 5–26.
- Dumbrill, R. J. (2005), *The Archaeomusicology of the Ancient Near East*, London, Tadmora Press.
- Dumbrill, R. J. (2010), *Rediscovering the Silver Lyre of Ur British Museum 121199*, ICONEA Publications, London.
- Dumbrill, R. J. (2014), “Glues, Hides and Guts in Mari Organology during the Last Dynasties (1787 - 1762 B.C.) and under the reigns of Yasmah-Addu and Zimri-Lim”, *ARAM* 26 1&2, 309–325.
- Dumbrill, R. J. (2017), “The Truth about Babylonian Music”, *NEMO* 4/6, 91–121 [Online document] <<http://nemo-online.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/08/INTERNET-6-02.-Article-NEMO-no.-4-6-2-Richard-Dumbrill-Truth-170822S.pdf>> [Last search on 12/10/2019]
- Dumbrill, R. J. (2019), *Semitic Music Theory (from its earliest sources till the dawn of Christianity)*, ICONEA Publications, London.
- Durand, J.-M. (1983), *Textes administratifs des salles 134 et 160 du Palais de Mari*, Geuthner, Paris, *ARM* 21, *MARI* 5.
- Durand, J.-M. (1989), “*kirrum* = ÁBxŠÀ (kír)”, *NABU* 1989/2, n. 30.
- Durand, J.-M. (1991), “Baddum = devin fantôme”, *NABU* 1991/2, n. 53, 36.
- Durand, J.-M. (1993a), “Le dieu des Enfers à Mari”, *NABU* 1993/2, n. 60, n. 49-50.
- Durand, J.-M. (1993b), “Mythologèmes d'époque amorrite”, *NABU* 1993/4, n. 114, 96–97.
- Durand, J.-M. (1997), *Les documents épistolaires du palais de Mari*, vol. 1, Éditions du Cerf, Paris, *LAPO* 16.
- Durand, J.-M. (1998), *Les documents épistolaires du palais de Mari II*, Éditions du Cerf, Paris, *LAPO* 17.
- Durand, J.-M. and Guichard, M. (1997), “Les rituels de Mari”, in: Charpin, D. and Durand, J.-M. (ed.), *Recueil d'études à la mémoire de Marie-Thérèse Barrelet*, Société d'Études du Proche-Orient Ancien, Paris, *FM* 3, 19–78.
- Ebeling, E. (1931), *Tod und Leben nach den Vorstellungen der Babylonian. I Teil: Texte*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin and Leipzig.
- Ebeling, E. (1948), “Ein Gebet an einen “verfinsterten Gott” aus neuassyrischer Zeit”, *OrNS* 17, 416–422.
- Ebeling, E. (1953), *Literarische Keilschrifttexte aus Assur*, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin.

- Edzard, D. O. (1963), “(Review Article) H. Limet, *Le travail du metal au pays de Sumer au temps de la III^e dynastie d’Ur (1960)*”, *OLZ* 58, 28–34.
- Edzard, D. O. (1976), “„Du hast mir gegeben“, „ich habe dir gegeben“ Über das sumerische Verbum sum”, *WO* 8/2, 159–177.
- Edzard, D. O. (1976–1980), “Išme-Dagān von Isin”, *RIA* 5, 194–195.
- Edzard, D. O. (1984), *Hymnen, Beschwörungen und Verwandtes aus dem Archiv L. 2769*, Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Roma, *ARET* 5.
- Edzard, D. O. (1997), *Gudea and His Dynasty*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto, Buffalo and London, *RIME* 3/1.
- Edzard, D. O. (2003), *Sumerian Grammar*, Brill, Leiden, HdOr 1.21.
- Eichmann, R. (2011), “Extant Lutes from the New Kingdom and the Coptic Period of Ancient Egypt”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. (ed.), *ICONEA 2011. Proceedings of the International Conference of Near-Eastern Archaeomusicology held at Senate House, Institute of Musical Research University of London. December, 1, 2 and 3, 2011*, ICONEA Publications, London, 25–38.
- Eidem, J. (2011), *The Royal Archives from Tell Leilan. Old Babylonian Letters and Treaties from the Lower Town Palace East*, Peeters, Leuven, Paris and Walpole (Massachusetts), *PIHANS* 117.
- Elli, A. (2015), *La costruzione del Tempio di Ningirsu. I cilindri A e B di Gudea di Lagash* [Online document], Digital Magazine di egittologia.net et mediterraneoantico.it,
https://www.mediterraneoantico.it/wp-content/uploads/2016/06/SpecialeMA_Elli_Gudea_Ningirsu_def.pdf
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Emerit, S. (2013), “Music and Musicians”, in Wendrich, W. (ed.), *UCLA Encyclopedia of Egyptology*, University of California Los Angeles, Los Angeles, [Online document]
<http://digital2.library.ucla.edu/viewItem.do?ark=21198/zz002h77z9>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Emerit, S. (2017), “Harpe angulaire”, in in: Emerit, S.; Guichard, H.; Jeammet, V.; Perrot, S.; Thomas, A.; Vendries, Chr.; Vincent, A. and Ziegler, N. (ed.), *Musiques! Échos de l’Antiquité*, Musée du Louvre-Lens and Snoeck Publishers, Lens and Ghent, 132.

- Englund, R.K. (1991), “Hard work - Where will it get you? Labor management in Ur III Mesopotamia”, *JNES* 50, 255–280.
- Englund, R. K. (1994), *Archaic Administrative Texts from Uruk. The Early Campaigns*, Gebr. Mann Verlag, Berlin, ATU 5, ADFU 15.
- Englund, R. K. (2002), “Notes on SET 274”, *CDLB 2002: 2*, [Online document] <https://cdli.ucla.edu/files/publications/cdlb2002_002.pdf> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Englund, R. K. (2003), “Worcester Slaughterhouse Account”, *CDLB 2003:1*, [Online document] <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdlb/2003/cdlb2003_001.html> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Erman, A. and Grapow, H. (1926–1961), *Wörterbuch der ägyptischen Sprache*, 3 volumes, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin.
- Espak, P. (2010), *The God Enki in Sumerian Royal Ideology and Mythology*, Tartu University Press, Tartu, Dissertationes Theologiae Universitatis Tartuensis 19.
- Fagoaga, L. (1975), “Alboka”, *Cuadernos de etnología y etnografía de Navarra*, 7/19, 45–50.
- Fahdil, A. A. F. (2012), *Eine kleine Tontafelbibliothek aus Assur (Ass. 15426)*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Heidelberg Universität, [Online document] <<https://archiv.ub.uni-heidelberg.de/volltextserver/17610/>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Falkenstein, A. (1949), *Grammatik der Sprache Gudeas von Lagaš I: Schrift- und Formenlehre*, Pontificum Institutum Biblicum, Rome, AnOr 28.
- Falkenstein, A. (1950), *Grammatik der Sprache Gudeas von Lagaš II. Syntax*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, AnOr 29.
- Falkenstein, A. (1952), “Sumerische religiöse Texte”, *ZA* 50, 61–91.
- Falkenstein, A. and Matouš, L. (1922), “Zur 3. Tafel der Serie diri = DIR = *sijaku = watru*” *ZA* 34, 144–151.
- Farber, W. (1977), *Beschwörungsrituale an Ištar und Dumuzi. Atti Ištar ša Ḫarmaša Dumuzi*, Franz Steiner Verlag, Wiesbaden.
- Farber, G. (1991), “Konkret, Kollektiv, Abstrakt?”, *ArOr* 9, 81–90.
- Farber, W. (1995), “Witchcraft, Magic, and Divination in Ancient Mesopotamia”, *CANE* 3, 1895–1910.
- Farber, G. (1997), “Sumerian Canonical Compositions. A. Divine Focus. 1. Myths: Inanna and Enki (1.161)”, *COS I*, 522–526.

- Farber, G. and Walter, F. (2003), “Wer kennt die Zahlen, nennt die Namen”, in: Selz, G. J. (ed.), *Festschrift für Burkhart Kienast zu seinem 70. Geburtstage dargebracht von Freunden, Schülern und Kollegen*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 274, 67–78.
- Farber-Flüge, G. (1973), *Der Mythos «Inanna und Enki» unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Liste der me*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, StPohl 10.
- Feliu, Ll. and Millet Albà, A. (2009), “An Old Babylonian text concerning acrobats and wrestlers”, in: Barreyra Fracaroli, D. A. and Del Olmo Lete, G. (eds.), *Reconstructing a Distant Past. Ancient Near Eastern Essays in Tribute to Jorge R. Silva Castillo*, AUSA, Sabadell, Aula Orientalis Supplementa, 97–102.
- Feliu, L. and Millet, A. (2017), “Text and Workers”, in: Feliu, L.; Karahashi, F. and Rubio, G. (eds.), *The First Ninety Years. A Sumerian Celebration in Honor of Miguel Civil*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, SANER 12, 110–114.
- Figulla, H. H., Forrer, E. and Weidner, E. F. (1923), *Keilschrifttexte aus Boghazkoi. Erstes bis Viertes Heft*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Figulla, H. H. and Martin, W. J. (1953), *Letters and Documents of the Old-Babylonian Period*, Trustees of the British Museum and University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, UET 5.
- Finn, J. (2017), *Much Ado about Marduk: Questioning Discourses of Royalty in First Millennium Mesopotamian Literature*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston and Berlin, SANER 16.
- Fincke, J. C. (2000), *Augenleiden nach keilschriftlichen Quellen: Untersuchungen zur altorientalischen Medizin*, Königshausen & Neumann, Würzburg, Würzburger medizinhistorische Forschungen 70.
- Fincke, J. C. (2003-2004), “The Babylonian Texts of Nineveh: Report on the British Museum’s “Ashurbanipal Library Project””, *AfO* 50, 111–149.
- Fincke, J. C. (2017), “Assyrian Scholarship and Scribal Culture in Kalhu and Nineveh”, in: Frahm, E. (ed.), *A Companion to Assyria*, Wiley Blackwell, 378-397.
- Finkel, I. L. and Civil, M. (1982), *The Series SIG7.ALAN = Nabnītu*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 16.
- Fish, T. (1932), *Catalogue of Sumerian Tablets in the John Rylands Library*, Manchester University Press, Manchester.
- Fish, T. (1955), “Kuš Texts of the Isin Period”, *MCS* 5, 115–124.

- Fish, T. (1958), “A Copy of the Umma-Tablet BM 106055 and Copies of Other Tablets Relating to its subject Matter”, *MCS* 8, 84–98
- Fish, T. and Lambert, M. (1963), “‘Vérification’ dans la bureaucratie sumérienne”, *RA* 57, 93-97.
- Flückiger-Hawker, E. (1999), *Urnamma of Ur in Sumerian Literary Tradition*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, OBO 166.
- Forde, N.W. (1967), *Nebraska Cuneiform Texts of the Sumerian Ur Dynasty*, Coronado Press, Lawrence (Nebraska).
- Foster, B. (1982), *Umma in the Sargonic Period*, Archon Books, Hamden (Connecticut), MCAAS 20.
- Fournet, A. (2013), *Hurrian and Kassite Glossary*, The Book Edition, La Garenne-Colombes.
- Foxvog, D. A. (1995), “Sumerian Brands and Branding-Irons”, *ZA* 85, 1–7.
- Foxvog, D. A. (2011), “Aspects of Name-Giving in Presargonic Lagash”, in: Heimpel, W. and Frantz-Szabó, G. (ed.), *Strings and Threads. A Celebration of the Work of Anne Draffkorn Kilmer*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 59–97.
- Foxvog, D. A. (2014), *Old Sumerian Occupations. A Handlist of Terminology Found in the Presargonic Lagash Texts*, [Online document]
 <[https://www.academia.edu/9481488/Old_Sumerian_Occupations. A Handlist of Terminology Found in the Presargonic Lagash Texts](https://www.academia.edu/9481488/Old_Sumerian_Occupations._A_Handlist_of_Terminology_Found_in_the_Presargonic_Lagash_Texts)>
 [Last search 12/10/2019].
- Foxvog, D. A. (2016a), *Elementary Sumerian Glossary (after M. Civil, 1967)*, University of California, Berkeley, Cuneiform Digital Library Preprints 3. [Online document],
 <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdli/cdli0003_20160104.pdf>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Foxvog, D. A. (2016b), *Introduction to Sumerian Grammar*, University of California, Berkeley, Cuneiform Digital Library Preprints 2. [Online document],
 <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdli/cdli0002_20160104.pdf>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Frahm, E. (2005), "On Some Recently Published Late Babylonian Copies of Royal Letters", *NABU* 2005/2, n. 43, 43–46.

- Frahm, E. (2011), *Babylonian and Assyrian Text Commentaries. Origins of Interpretation*, Ugairt-Verlag, Münster, Guides to the Mesopotamian Textual Record 5.
- Frahm, E. (2013), “The Sources of Commentarial Explanations”, *CCP*, [Online document]
 <<https://ccp.yale.edu/introduction/sources-commentarial-explanations>>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Frame, G. (1993), “Nabonidus and the History of the Eulmaš Temple at Akkad”, *Mesopotamia* 28, 21–50.
- Frame, G. and George, A. R. (2005), “The Royal Libraries of Nineveh: New Evidence for King Ashurbanipal’s Tablet Collecting”, *Iraq* 67/1, 265–284.
- Franklin, J. C. (2013), “Divinized Instruments and Divine Communication in Mesopotamia”, in: Jiménez, R.; Till, R. and Howell, M. (ed.), *Music & Ritual. Bridging Material & Living Cultures*, Ekho Verlag, Berlin, Publications of the ICTM Study Group on Music Archaeology 1, 43–62.
- Franklin, J. C. (2015), *Kinyras: The Divine Lire*, Harvard University Press, Washington DC, Hellenic Studies 70.
- Frayne, D. (1990), *Old Babylonian Period (2003-1595 BC)*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto, Buffalo and London, RIME 4.
- Frayne, D. (1997), *Ur III Period (2112-2004 BC)*, University of Toronto Press, Toronto, Buffalo and London, RIME 3/2.
- Freedman, R. D. (1977), “Cuneiform Texts from the Piepkorn Collection, III”, *JANES* 9, 11–25.
- Gabbay, U. (2003), “Dance in Textual Sources from Ancient Mesopotamia”, *Near Eastern Archaeology* 66/3, 104–105.
- Gabbay, U. (2007), *The Sumerian-Akkadian Prayer “Eršema”: A Philological and Religious Analysis*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Hebrew University of Jerusalem, Jerusalem.
- Gabbay, U. (2010), “The ancient Mesopotamian sistrum and its references in cuneiform literature: the identification of the šem and meze”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2008), The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008*, ICONEA Publications, London, 23–28.

- Gabbay, U. and Mirelman, S. (2011), “Two Summary Tablets of Balag Compositions with Performative Indications from Late-Babylonian Ur”, *ZA* 101, 274–293.
- Gabbay, U. (2014a), *Pacifying the Hearts of the Gods. Sumerian Emesal Prayers of the First Millennium BCE*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, Heidelberger Emesal Studien 1.
- Gabbay, U. (2014b), “The Balaĝ Instrument and Its Role in the Cult of Ancient Mesopotamia”, in: Westenholz, J. G., Maurey, Yossi and Seroussi, E. (ed.) *Music in antiquity: the Near East and the Mediterranean*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin, Studies of the Jewish Music Research Centre 8, 129–147.
- Gabbay, U. (2014c), “The *kalû* Priest and *kalûtu* Literature in Assyria”, *Orient* 49, 115–144.
- Gabbay, U. (2016), *The Exegetical Terminology of Akkadian Commentaries*, Brill, Leiden, CHANE 82.
- Gabbay, U. (2017), “Chants et instruments du culte, histoire d’un changement”, en Emerit, S.; Guichard, H.; Jeammet, V.; Perrot, S.; Thomas, A.; Vendries, Ch.; Vincent, A. and Ziegler, N. (ed.), *Musiques! Échos de l’Antiquité*, Musée du Louvre and Snoeck Publishers, Lens and Ghent, 46–47.
- Gadd, C. J. (1921), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part XXXVI*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Gadd, C. J. (1957), “Fragments of Assyrian Scholastic Literature”, *BSOAS* 20 n. 1/3, 255–265.
- Gadd, C. J. and Kramer, S. N. (1963), *Literary and Religious Texts. First Part*, British Museum, London, UET 6/1.
- Gadd, C. J. and Kramer, S. N. (1966), *Literary and Religious Texts. Second Part*, British Museum, London, UET 6/2.
- Gadotti, A. (2010), “The Nar and Gala in Sumerian Literary Texts”, in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, Vienna, LIT Verlag, Wiener Offene Orientalistik 8, 51–66.
- Gadotti, A. (2014), “*Gilgamesh, Enkidu, and the Netherworld*” and the Sumerian *Gilgamesh Cycle*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston and New York, UAVA 10.
- Gardiner, A. (2007), *Egyptian Grammar. Being an Introductory to the Study of Hieroglyphs*, Griffith Institute, Oxford.

- García López, J.; Pérez Cartagena, F. J. and Redondo Reyes (2012), *La Música en la Antigua Grecia*, Editum Murcia.
- García Ventura, A. (2012a), *El trabajo y la producción textil en la Tercera Dinastía de Ur*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Institut Universitari d'Historia "Jaume Vicens Vives", Universitat Pompeu i Fabra, Barcelona, [Online document] <<https://repositori.upf.edu/handle/10230/20037>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- García Ventura, A. (2012b), "Tejedor@s en la Tercera Dinastía de Ur: nuevas perspectivas de estudio", *Claroscuro. Revistas del Centro de Estudios sobre Diversidad Cultural* 11, 13–31.
- Garraghan, G. J. (1946), *A Guide to Historical Method*, Fordham University Press, New York.
- Garrison, M. B. (2012), "Antiquarism, Copying, Collecting", in: Potts, D. T. (ed.), *A Companion to the Archaeology of the Ancient Near East. Volume I*, Wiley-Blackwell, 27–47.
- Gelb, I. (1976), "Homo Ludens in Early Mesopotamia", *StOr* 46, 43–76.
- Geller, M. J. (1985), *Forerunners to Uduĝ-hul. Sumerian Exorcistic Incantations*, Franz Steiner, Stuttgart, FAOS 12.
- Geller, M. J. (1995–1996), "(Review) *Spätbabylonische Texte aus Uruk. Teil III* (ADFU 12), by Egbert von Weiher", *AfO* 42/43, 245–248.
- Geller, M. J. (2003), "Music Lessons", in: Selz, G. J. (ed.), *Festschrift für Burkhard Kienast zu seinem 70. Geburtstage dargebracht von Freunden, Schülern und Kollegen*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 274, 109–111.
- Geller, M. J. (2007), *Evil Demons. Canonical Utukkū Lemnutū Incantations. Introduction, Cuneiform Text, and Transliteration with a Translation and Glossary*, Institute for Asian and African Studies, University of Helsinki, Helsinki, State Archives of Assyria Cuneiform Texts 5.
- Geller, M. J. (2011), "(Review) W. Schramm, Ein Compendium sumerisch-akkadischer Beschwörungen. 355 pp. Göttingen, Universitätsverlag Göttinger, 2008 (= GBAO 2). € 30,-.", *AfO* 52, 252–257.
- Geller, M. J. (2015), *Healing Magic and Evil Demons: Canonical Uduĝ-hul Incantations*, De Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, BAM 8.
- Geller, M. J. (2018a), "A Babylonian Hippocrates", in: Steinert, U. (ed.), *Assyrian and Babylonian Scholarly Text Catalogues. Medicine, Magic and Divination*, De Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, BAM 9, 42–54.

- Geller, M. J. (2018b), “The Exorcist’s Manual (KAR 44)”, in: Steinert, U. (ed.), *Assyrian and Babylonian Scholarly Text Catalogues. Medicine, Magic and Divination*, De Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, BAM 9, 292–312.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1909) *Tablettes sumériennes archaïques*, Ernest Leroux, Paris.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1910), *Textes de l’époque d’Agadé et de l’époque d’Ur*, Ernest Leroux, Paris, ITT 2.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1922), *Textes Cunéiformes Tome V. Textes Économiques d’Oumma de l’Époque d’Our*, Geuthner, Paris, TCL 5.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1924), “Choix de textes économiques de la Collection Pupil”, *Babyloniaca* 8, 37–40.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1930a), *Textes Religieux Sumériens du Louvre I*, P. Geuthner, Paris, TCL 15.
- Genouillac, H. d. (1930b), *Textes Religieux Sumériens du Louvre II*, P. Geuthner, Paris, TCL 16.
- George, A. R. (1992), *Babylonian Topographical Texts*, Departement Oriëntalistiek and Uitgeverij Peeters, Leuven, OLA 40.
- George, A. R. and Spada, G. (2019), *Old Babylonian Texts in the Schoyen Collection. Part 2. School Letters, Model Contracts, and Related Texts*, Eisenbrauns and University Park, Pennsylvania, CUSAS 43.
- George, L. C. (1987), “Clay Tablets and Cones in the New Brunswick Museum, Saint John”, *ARRIM* 5, 31–42.
- Glassner, J.-J. (1992), “Inanna et les me”, in: Ellis, M. d. J. (ed.), *Inanna at the centennial. 35. Comptes-Rendus des Rencontres Assyriologiques Internationales*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), 55–86.
- Glenn, A. and Peterson, J. L. (2018), “The Lulal *širgida* Composition CBS 12590 (HAV 5, pl. 7, VIII)”, *AoF* 45/2, 168–181.
- Glenn, A. (2018), “Towards a Definition of the Sumerian *Širgida*”, *BaF-Online. Proceedings of the Berner altorientalisches Forum 2*, [Online document] <<https://doi.org/10.22012/baf.2017.05>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Glenn, A. (2019), *Praise of Kingship: Širgida Hymns in the Old Babylonia Liturgical Tradition*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, John Hopkins University, Baltimore (Maryland).
- Goldstein, R. (2010), “Late Babylonian Letters on Collecting Tablets and Their Hellenistic Background - a Suggestion”, *JNES* 69/2, 199–207.

- Gomi, T. (1980), “Neo-Sumerian Administrative Tablets in the British Museum. I”, *ASJ* 2, 1–36.
- Gomi, T. and Sato, S. (1990), *Selected Neo-Sumerian Administrative Texts from the British Museum*, Chuo-Gakuin University, Chiba.
- Gomi, T. and Yildiz, F. (1997), *Die Umma-Texte aus den Archäologischen Museen zu Istanbul. Band IV (Nr. 2301-3000)*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Goddeeris, A. (2016), *The Old Babylonian Legal and Administrative Texts in the Hilprecht Collection Jena* [with a contribution by Ursula Seidl], 2 Volumes, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, TMH 10.
- Goddeeris, A. (2018), “Fields of Nippur. Irrigation Districts and Lexicography in Old Babylonian Nippur”, in: Tavernier, J.; Gorris, E.; Abraham, K. and Boschloos, V. (ed.), *Topography and Toponymy in the Ancient Near East. Perspectives and Prospects*, Peeters, Université Catholique de Louvain, Louvain-la-Neuve, Publications de l'Institut Orientaliste de Louvain 71, 97–112.
- Goetze, A. (1947a), “Historical Allusions in Old Babylonian Omen Texts”, *JCS* 1, 253–265.
- Goetze, A. (1947b), *Old Babylonian Omen Texts*, New Haven (Connecticut), Yale University Press, YOS 10.
- Goetze, A. (1957), “Old Babylonian Letters in American Collections: I. Catholic University of America (Washington, D.C.)”, *JCS* 11/4, 106–109.
- Goetze, A. (ed.), (2009), *Cuneiform Texts from Various Collections*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut) and London, YOS 15.
- Gordon, C. H. (1952), *Smith College Tablets. 110 Cuneiform Texts Selected from the College Collection*, Smith College Northhampton (Massachusetts), Smith College Studies in History 38.
- Gordon, E. I. (1959), *Sumerian Proverbs. Glimpses of Everyday Life in Ancient Mesopotamia*, University Museum, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia.
- Gordon, E. I. (1960), “Some General Remarks on the Wisdom Literature of Mesopotamia”, *BiOr* 17, 123-152.
- Grandpierre, V. (1997), “Bruit et silence dans les villes de Mésopotamie antique”, *Sources. Travaux Historiques* 49-50, 53–72.
- Grégoire, J.-P. (1981), *Inscriptions et Archives Administratives Cunéiformes - 1e Partie*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 10.

- Grégoire, J.-P. (1996), *Contribution à l'Histoire Sociale, Économique, Politique et Culturelle du Proche-Orient Ancien. Archives Administratives et Inscriptions Cunéiformes de l'Ashmolean Museum et de la Bodleian Collection d'Oxford (AAICAB). I. Les Sources*, P. Geuthner, Paris.
- Grégoire, J.-P. (2000), *Contribution à l'Histoire Sociale, Économique, Politique et Culturelle du Proche-Orient Ancien. Archives Administratives et Inscriptions Cunéiformes de l'Ashmolean Museum et de la Bodleian Collection d'Oxford (AAICAB). II. Les Sources*, P. Geuthner, Paris.
- Grégoire, J.-P. (2004), *Contribution à l'Histoire Sociale, Économique, Politique et Culturelle du Proche-Orient Ancien. Archives Administratives et Inscriptions Cunéiformes de l'Ashmolean Museum et de la Bodleian Collection d'Oxford (AAICAB). IV. Les Sources*, P. Geuthner, Paris.
- Grice, E. M. (1919), *Records from Ur and Larsa Dated in the Larsa Dynasty*, Yale University Press, Humprey Milford and Oxford University Press, New Haven (Connecticut), London and Oxford, YOS 5.
- Grimal, P. (2008), *Diccionario de Mitología griega y romana*, Paidós, Barcelona.
- Groß, M. M. (2014), *The Structure and Organisation of the Neo-Assyrian Royal Household*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Universität Wien, [Online document] <<http://othes.univie.ac.at/34056/>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Groneberg, B. (1989), “Reduplications of Consonants and “R”-Stems”, *RA* 83/1, 27-34.
- Gragg, G. B. (1973), *Sumerian Dimensional Infixes*, Butzon & Bercker and Neukirchener Verlag, Kevelaer and Neukirchen-Vluyn, AOATS 2.
- Gurney, O. (1973), *Middle Babylonian Legal Documents and Other Texts*, Trustees of the British Museum and University of Pennsylvania Museum of Archaeology and Anthropology, UET 7.
- Hackl, J. (2007–2010), “Neue spätbabylonische Lehrverträge aus dem British Museum und der Yale Babylonian Collection”, *AfO* 52, 1–21.
- Hackman, G. G. (1937), *Temple Documents of the Third Dynasty of Ur from Umma*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut), BIN 5.
- Hagel, S. (2005), “Is *nīd qabli* Dorian? Tuning and modality in Greek and Hurrian Music”, *BagM* 36, 287–348.
- Hagel, S. (2018), “An Alphabet of Sound. The First Known Melodic Notation”, in: De Angeli, S., Both, A. D., Hagel, S., Holmes, P., Jiménez Pasalodos, R.; Lund, C. S. (ed.), *Music and Sounds in Ancient Europe. Contributions from the European*

- Music Archaeology Project*, European Music Archaeology Project (EMAP) and Regione Lazio, Roma, 108–109.
- Hallo, W. W. (2008), “Day dates in texts from Drehem”, in: Garfinkle, S. and Johnson, J. C. (ed.), *In The Growth of an Early State in Mesopotamia: Studies in Ur III Administration: Proceedings of the First and Second Ur III Workshops at the 49th and 51st Rencontre assyriologique internationale, London July 10, 2003 and Chicago July 19, 2005*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 5, 99–118.
- Handcock, P. S. P. (1910), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 28*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Handley, E. W. (1985), “Comedy”, in: Easterling, P. E. and Knox, B. M. W. (ed.), *The Cambridge History of Classical Literature I. Greek Literature*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 355–425.
- Handley, E. W. (1985), “Historiography”, in: Easterling, P. E. and Knox, B. M. W. (ed.), *The Cambridge History of Classical Literature I. Greek Literature*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 426–455.
- Harper, R. F. (1892–1914), *Assyrian and Babylonian Letters*, 14 volumes, University of Chicago Press, Chicago (Illinois).
- Harris, R. (1975), *Ancient Sippar. A Demographic Study of an Old-Babylonian City (1894-1595 B.C.)*, Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten (NINO), Leiden, PIHANS 36.
- Hartmann, H. (1960), *Die Musik der sumerischen Kultur*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Philosophische Fakultät, Johann Wolfgang Goethe-Universität, Frankfurt am Main.
- Hecker, K. (1990), *Rückläufiges Wörterbuch des Akkadischen*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, SANTAG 1.
- Heeßel, N. P. (2002), *Pazuzu. Archäologische und philologische Studien zu einem altorientalische Dämon*, Brill/Styx, Leiden and Boston, AMD 4.
- Heidel, A. (1948), “The Meaning of Mummu in Akkadian Literature”, *JNES* 7, 98–105.
- Heilmann, A. (2007), *Boethius’ Musiktheorie und das Quadrivium: eine Einführung in den neuplatonischen Hintergrund von "De institutione musica"*, Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, Göttingen, Hypomnemata. Untersuchungen zur Antike und zu ihren Nachleben 171.

- Heimerdinger, J. W. (1979), *Sumerian Literary Fragments from Nippur*, University of Pennsylvania Museum, Philadelphia, OPBF 4.
- Heimpel, W. (1998–2000), “Nanše. A. Philologisch”, *RIA* 9, 152–160.
- Heimpel, W. (2003), *Letters to the King of Mari: A New Translation, with Historical Introduction, Notes and Commentary*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), MC 12.
- Heimpel, W. (2015), “Balang Gods”, in: Franklin, J. C., *Kinyras: The Divine Lire*, Harvard University Press, Washington DC, HS 70, 571–632.
- Henkelman, W. (2002), “Exit der Posaunenbläser. On lance-guards and lance-bearers in the Persepolis Fortification archive”, *Achaemenid Research on Texts and Archaeology 2002/007*, 1–35.
- Hickmann, H. (1961), *Ägypten*, Deutscher Verlag für Musik, Leipzig, Musikgeschichte in Bildern, Musik des Altertums II/1.
- Hidemi, I. (1987), “An Introduction to Musical Thought in Ancient China - Sound, Order, Emotion”, *Contemporary Music Review* 1/2, 75–84.
- Hilgert, M. (2002), *Akkadisch in der Ur III-Zeit*, Rhema, Münster, IMGULA 5.
- Hinz, W., Koch, H. (1987), *Elamisches Wörterbuch*, 2 volúmenes (I A-H, II I-Z), Dietrich Reimer, Berlin.
- Holladay, W. L. (ed.) (1988), *A Concise Hebrew and Aramaic Lexicon of the Old Testament*, Brill, Leiden.
- Hübner, B. and Reizammer, A. (1985), *Inim Kiengi. II. Sumerisch-Deutsches Glossar in zwei Bänden (Bd. 1: A-L, Bd. 2: M-Z mit Anhang)*, Albert Reizammer’s Auto-Publication, Marktredwitz.
- Huehnergard, J. (2011), *A Grammar of Akkadian (Third Edition)*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana).
- Hunger, H. (1968), *Babylonische und assyrische Kolophone*, Butzon & Kevalaer, Neukirchen-Vluyn, AOAT 2.
- Hunger, H. (1976), *Spätbabylonische Texte aus Uruk. Teil 1*, Gebr. Mann, Berlin, ADFU 9.
- Hunger, H. and De Jong, T. (2014), “Almanac W22340a from Uruk: the Last Datable Cuneiform Tablet”, *ZA* 104/2, 182–194.
- Hutter, M. (1996), *Religionen in der Umwelt des Alten Testaments I.: Babylonier, Syrer, Perser*, Stuttgart, Kohlhammer, Studienbücher Theologie 4/1.

- Izre'el, Sh. (2001), *Adapa and the South Wind: Language Has the Power of Life and Death*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), MC 10.
- Jacobsen, Th. (1987), *The Harps that Once... Sumerian Poetry in Translation*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut).
- Jagersma, A. H. (2010), *A Descriptive Grammar of Sumerian*, Universiteit Leiden, Leiden [Online document].
 <<https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/bitstream/handle/1887/16107/Binnenwerk-jagersma.pdf>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Jáka-Sövegjártó, S. (2019), “Local identities and the Old Babylonian literary curriculum in Nippur and Ur”, in: Friesen, M. and Hesse, Ch. L. (ed.), *Antike Kanonisierungsprozesse und Identitätsbildung in Zeiten des Umbruchs. Tagungsband zur internationalen Nachwuchstagung in Münster (26.-27. Mai 2017)*, Westfälische Wilhelms-Universität, Münster, Reihe X. Band 28, 43-56.
- Jakob, S. (2003), *Mittlassyrische Verwaltung und Sozialstruktur. Untersuchungen*, Brill - Styx, Leiden and Boston, CM 29.
- Jaques, M. (2004), *Le vocabulaire des sentiments dans les textes sumériens*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 332.
- Jiménez, E. (2013a), *La Imagen de los Vientos en la Literatura Babilónica*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, [Online document]
 <<https://eprints.ucm.es/26391/1/T34781.pdf>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Jiménez, E. (2013b), “Three Colophons”, *NABU* 2013/4, n. 92, 152–154.
- Jiménez, E. (2016a), “Commentary on Sagig 7 (CCP 4.1.7.C.a)”, *CCP*, [Online document] <<https://ccp.yale.edu/P461244>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Jiménez, E. (2016b), “May the Reader not Withhold the Tablet! On a Formula in Late Babylonian Colophons”, *Babel und Bibel* 9, 227–239.
- Jiménez Zamudio, R. (2017), *Nueva gramática de sumerio*, Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Alcalá de Henares, Alcalá de Henares.
- Joannès, F. (2013), “The Economic Role of Women in Neo-Babylonian Temples”, *Carnet de REFEMA 08/10/2013*, [Online document]
 <<https://refema.hypotheses.org/745>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Joannès, F. (2016), “Women and Palaces in the Neo-Assyrian Period”, *Orient* 51, 29–46.
- Johns, C. H. W. (1898–1923), *Assyrian Deeds and Documents*, Deighton, Cambridge.
- Johnson, J. C. (2006), “The Ur III Tablets in the Valdosta State University Archives”, *CDLB 2006:2*, [Online document]

https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdlj/2006/cdlj2006_002.html

[Last search on 12/10/2019].

- Johnson, H. (1999), “The sounds of *Myūjikkū*. An exploration of concepts and classifications in Japanese Sound Aesthetics”, *Journal of Musicological Research* 18/4, 291–306.
- Jones, T. B. and Snyder, J.W. (1961), *Sumerian Economic Texts from the Third Ur Dynasty. A Catalogue and Discussion of Documents from Various Collections*, University of Minnesota Press, Minneapolis.
- Journeau, V. A. (2008), “Musique de l’Antiquité en Chine: Quand ‘soies et bambous’ (cordes et vents) sont accordés sur les cloches”, in: Both, A. A. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 6. Herausforderungen und Ziele der Musikarchäologie: Vorträge des 5. Symposiums der Internationalen Studiengruppe Musikarchäologie im Ethnologischen Museum der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, 19. - 23. September 2006 = Challenges and objectives in music archaeology*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 22, 487–507.
- Jursa, M. (1995), *Die Landwirtschaft in Sippar in neubabylonischer Zeit*, Institut für Orientalistik der Universität Wien, Vienna, BAfO 25.
- Kaneva, I. T. (1966), “A New Clay Tablet with a Fragment from the Sumerian Poem "The Scribe and His Perverse Son" (in Russian), *Journal of Ancient History* 1966/2 n. 96, 68–78.
- Karahashi, F. (2000), *Sumerian Compound Verbs with Body-Parts Terms*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Civilizations, University of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois).
- Kedar, S. (2014), “Apprenticeship in the Neo-Babylonian Period: A Study of Bargaining Power”, in: Marti, L. (ed.), *La famille dans le Proche-Orient ancien: réalités, symbolismes, et images. Proceedings of the 55th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale at Paris 6-9 July 2009*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 537–546.
- Keiser, C.E. (1971), *Neo-Sumerian Account Texts from Drehem*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut) and London, BIN 3.
- Kelly, N. (1997), *Spinning the Thread, Weaving the Web. Images of Women Spinning and Weaving in Western Art*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor.

- Kessler, K. (2008), “Gott – König – Tempel. Menschliches Recht und göttliche Gerechtigkeit in neu- und spätbabylonischer Zeit”, in: Heinz, B.; Rollinger, R. and Lang, M. (ed.), *Recht und Religion: Menschliche und göttliche Gerechtigkeitsvorstellungen in den Antiken Welten*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, Philippika. Marburger altertumskundliche Abhandlungen 24, 73–92.
- Kettnerová, V., Lopatková, M., and Bejček, E. (2012), “The syntax-semantics interface of Czech verbs in the valency lexicon”, in: Fjeld, R. V. and Torjusen, J. M. (ed.), *Proceedings of the 15th EURALEX International Congress*, Department of Linguistics and Scandinavian Studies, University of Oslo, 434–443.
- Kienast, B. (1994), *Glossar zu den altakkadischen Königsinschriften*, Franz Steiner, Stuttgart, FAOS 8.
- Kikawada, Isaac (1994), “The Double Creation of Mankind in Enki and Ninmah, Atrahasis I 1-351, and Genesis 1-2”, in: Hess, R. S. and Tsumura, D. T. (eds.), *I Studied Inscriptions from Before the Flood: Ancient Near Eastern, Literary, and Linguistic Approaches to Genesis 1-11*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), Sources for Biblical and Theological Study 4, 169–174.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1971), “The Discovery of an Ancient Mesopotamian Theory of Music”, *PAPS* 115, 131–149.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1974), “The Cult Song with Music from Ancient Ugarit: Another Interpretation”, *RA* 68, 69–82.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1980–1983a), “Laute. A. Philologisch”, *RIA* 6, 512–515.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1980–1983b), “Leier. A. Philologisch”, *RIA* 6, 572–576.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1993–1995), “Musik. A.I. In Mesopotamien”, *RIA* 8, 463–482.
- Kilmer, A. D. (1995), “Music and Dance in Ancient Western Asia”, *CANE* 4, 2601–2613.
- Kilmer, A. D. (2000), “Continuity and Change in the Ancient Mesopotamian Terminology for Music and Musical Instruments” in: Hickmann, E.; Laufs, I. and Eichmann, R. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 2. Musikarchäologie früherer Metallzeiten: Vorträge des 1. Symposiums der International Study Group on Music Archaeology (ICTM), Kloster Michaelstein, 18. - 24. Mai 1998*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, Orient Archäologie 7, 113–119.
- Kilmer, A. D. (2003-05), “Pauke und Trommel. A. In Mesopotamien”, *RIA* 10, 367–371.
- Kilmer, A. D. (2014), “Mesopotamian Music Theory since 1977”, in: Westenholz, J. G.; Maurey, Y. and Seroussi, E. (ed.) *Music in antiquity: the Near East and the*

- Mediterranean*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin, Studies of the Jewish Music Research Centre 8, 92–101.
- Kilmer, A. D. and Civil, M. (1986), “Old Babylonian Musical Instructions Relating to Hymnody”, *JCS* 38/1, 94–98.
- Kilmer, A. D. and Tinney, S. (1997). “Correction to Kilmer/Tinney “Old Babylonian Music Instruction Texts” “JCS” 48 (1996)”, *JCS* 49, 118.
- Kilmer, A. D. and Tinney, S. (1996), “Old Babylonian Music Instruction Texts”, *JCS* 48, 49–56.
- Kilmer, A. D. and Peterson, J. L. (2009), “More Old Babylonian Music-Instructions Fragments from Nippur”, *JCS* 61, 93–96.
- King, L. W. (1902a), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part XV*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- King, L. W. (1902b), *The Seven Tablets of Creation, or the Babylonian and Assyrian Legends Concerning the Creation of the World and of Mankind*, Vol. 2. Supplementary Texts, etc., Luzac and Co., London.
- Klein, E. (1987), *A Comprehensive Etymological Dictionary of the Hebrew Language for Readers of English*, Carta Jerusalem, University of Haifa, Jerusalem.
- Klein, J. (1981), *Three Šulgi Hymns. Sumerian Royal Hymns Glorifying King Šulgi of Ur*, Bar-Ilan University Press, Ramat-Gan.
- Klein, J. (1989), “From Gudea to Šulgi: Continuity and Change in Sumerian Literary Tradition”, *Studies Sjöberg*, 289–301.
- Klein, J. (1990), “Šulgi and Išmedagan: Originality and Dependency in Sumerian Royal Hymnology”, in: Klein, J. and Skaist, A. (eds.), *Bar-Ilan Studies in Assyriology Dedicated to Pinhas Artzi*, Bar-Ilan University Press, Ramat-Gan, 65–136.
- Klein, J. (1997), “Sumerian Canonical Compositions. A. Divine Focus. 1. Myths: Enki and Ninmah (1.159)”, *COS I*, 516–522.
- Klein, J. (2005), “The Independent Pronouns in the Šulgi Hymns”, *ASJ* 22, 135–152.
- Klein, J. (2014), “From Agade to Samaria: The Inflationary Price of Barley in Situations of Famine”, in: Csabai, Z. (ed.), *Studies in Economic and Social History of the Ancient Near East in Memory of Péter Vargyas*, Department of Ancient History, University of Pécs, L'Harmattan Kiadó, Budapest, Ancient Near Eastern and Mediterranean Studies 2, 167-180.
- Klein, J. and Sefati, Y. (2013), “The ‘Stars (of) Heaven’ and Cuneiform Writing”, in: Sassmannshausen, L. (ed.), *He Has Opened Nisaba’s House of Learning: Studies*

- in Honor of Åke Waldemar Sjöberg on the Occasion of His 89th Birthday on August 1st 2013*, Brill, Leiden and Boston, CM 46, 85–102.
- Kleinerman, A. (2011), *Education in Early 2nd Millennium BC Babylonia. The Sumerian Epistolary Miscellany*, Brill, Leiden, CM 42.
- Koch, J. (2004), “Ein astralmythologischer Bericht aus der Zeit der Diadochenkämpfe”, *JCS* 56, 105–128.
- Koch, J. (2006), “Neues vom astralmythologischen Bericht BM 55466+”, *JCS* 58, 123-135.
- Koitabashi, M. (1998), “Music in the Texts from Ugarit”, *UF* 30, 363-396.
- Köpp-Junk, H. (2018), “Textual, Iconographical, and Archaeological Evidence for the Performance of Ancient Egyptian Music”, in: García-Ventura, A., Tavolieri, C. and Verderame, L. (ed.), *The Study of Musical Performance in Antiquity. Archaeology and Written Sources*, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, 93-120.
- Korczynski, M., Pickering, M. and Robertson, E. (2013), *Rhythms of Labour. Music at Work in Britain*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Koslova, N. (2000a), *Neusumerische Verwaltungstexte aus Umma aus der Sammlung der Ermitage zu St. Petersburg - Rußland*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 21.
- Koslova, N. (2000b), *Ur III- Texte der St. Petersburger Eremitage*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, SANTAG 6.
- Koubková, E. (2016), *Washing the mouth of a kettledrum*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Univerzita Karlova v Praze, Ústav filozofie a religionistika, Prague.
- Krahmalkov, Ch. (2000), *Studia Phoenicia XV. Phoenicia-Punic Dictionary*, Peeters, Leuven, OLA 90.
- Kramer, S. N. (1952), *A “Fullbright” in Turkey (Background and Purpose - Work Done - Law and Love, a Hymn, a Prayer and a Word to the Wise - Anatolian Archaeology [Alaca; Karatepe])*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), University Museum Bulletin 17/2.
- Kramer, S. N. (1956), *From the tablets of Sumer: twenty-five firsts in man’s recorded history*, Falcon’s Wing Press, Indian Hills (Colorado).
- Kramer, S. N. (1960), *Two Elegies on a Pushkin Museum Tablet: A New Sumerian Literary Genre*, Oriental Literature Publishing House, Moscow.

- Kramer, S. N. (1961), *Sumerische literarische Texte aus Nippur, Band 1. Mythen, Epen, Weisheitsliteratur und andere Literaturgattungen*, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin, TMH NF 3.
- Kramer, S. N. (1963), *The Sumerians, Their History, Culture and Character*, Chicago University Press, Chicago (Illinois).
- Kramer, S. N. (1967a), “Shulgi of Ur: A Royal Hymn and a Divine Blessing”, *The Jewish Quarterly Review* 57, 369–380.
- Kramer, S. N. (1967b), “The Death of Ur-Nammu and His Descent to the Netherworld”, *JCS* 21 (Fs Goetze), 104–122.
- Kramer, S. N. (1967c), *Sumerische literarische Texte aus Nippur, Band 2. Hymnen, Klagelieder, Weisheitstexte und andere Literaturgattungen*, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin, TMH NF 4.
- Kramer, S. N. (1981), “BM 29616: The Fashioning of the Gala”, *ASJ* 3, 1–11.
- Kramer, S. N. (1991), “The Death of Ur-Nammu”, in: Mori, M., Ogaea, H. and Yoshikawa, M. (eds.), *Near Eastern Studies. Dedicated to H.I.H. Prince Takahito Mikasa on the Occasion of His Seventy-Fifth Birthday*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, 193–214.
- Kramer, S. and Maier, J. (1989), *Myths of Enki, the Crafty God*, Oxford University Press, New York and Oxford.
- Kraus, F. R. (1951), “Nippur und Isin nach altbabylonischen Rechtsurkunden”, *JCS* 3, iii-xiv+1-228.
- Kraus, F. R. (1990), “Einige Kleine Urkunden aus der Zeit der III. Dynastie von Ur”, *RA* 84, 151–156.
- Krebernik, M. (1992), “Mesopotamian Myths at Ebla: ARET 5,6 and ARET 5,7”, in: Pelio, F. (ed.), *Literature and Literary Language at Ebla*, Dipartimento di linguística, Università di Firenze, Florence, QuadSem 18, 63–149.
- Krebernik, M. (1998), “Die Texte aus Fāra und Tell Abū Ṣalābīḥ”, in: Bauer, J.; Englund, R.; and Krebernik, M. (ed.), *Mesopotamien: Späturuk-Zeit und Frühdynastische Zeit*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, OBO 160/1, 237–427.
- Krecher, J. (1966), *Sumerische Kultlyrik*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- Krecher, J. (1985), “Die /m/-Präfixe des sumerischen Verbums”, *OrNS* 54, 133-181.
- Krecher, J. (1987), “Morphem[e]less syntax in Sumerian as seen on the background of word-composition in Chukchee”, *ASJ* 9, 67–88.

- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (1990), “Beiträge zur altorientalischen Musikforschung: 1. Šulgi und die Musik”, *Akkadica* 70, 1–27.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (1998), *Woordenlijst op de inscripties van Gudea van Lagaš* (4th revised edition), Unpublished manuscript, Leiden.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2002), “Musik im Keilschrift. Beiträge zur altorientalischen Musikforschung 2”, in: Hickmann, E.; Kilmer, A. D. and Eichmann, R. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie* 3, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 10, 465–479.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2008), “Music and Healing for someone far away from home HS 1556, A Remarkable Ur III Incantation, revisited”, in: Spek R. J. van der (ed.), *Studies in Ancient Near Eastern World View and Society presented to Marten Stol on the occasion of his 65th birthday*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), 173–193.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2010a), “Music in the Syrian city of Ebla in the Late Third Millennium B.C.”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2009-2010)*, Université de la Sorbonne, Paris, and Senate House, School of Musical Research, University of London, November 2009 and December 2010, ICONEA Publications, London, 55–61.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2010b), “Musical Ensembles in Ancient Mesopotamia”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2008)*, The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008, ICONEA Publications, London, 125–150.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2011), “The acceptance of Pop music in Mesopotamia: The Mesopotamia lute of the Second Millennium B.C. and its socio-cultural context”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. (ed.), *ICONEA 2011. Proceedings of the International Conference of Near-Eastern Archaeomusicology held at Senate House, Institute of Musical Research University of London. December, 1, 2 and 3, 2011*, ICONEA Publications, London, 113-128.
- Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2017), “Music in Nineveh”, in: Petit, L. P. and Morandi Bonacossi, D. (eds.), *Nineveh the Great City. Symbol of Beauty and Power*, Leiden, Sidestone Press, Papers on Archaeology of the Leiden Museum of Antiquities 13.
- Krul, J. (2018), *The Revival of the Anu Cult and the Nocturnal Fire Ceremony at Late Babylonian Uruk*, Brill, Leiden, CHANE 95.

- Kümmel, H. M. (1972–1975), “Horn (Musikinstrument). A. Philologisch”, *RIA* 4, 469–470.
- Kupper, J.-R. (1983), *Documents administratifs de la salle 135 du Palais de Mari*, Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, Paris, ARM 22/1.
- Kutzer, E. R. (2017), *The Socio-Cultural Value and Function of Music: On musical instruments and their performances in Mesopotamia of the 3rd millennium BCE from archaeological, iconographical and philological perspective*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Faculty of Archaeology, Leiden Universiteit, Leiden, [Online document]. <<https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/handle/1887/59625>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Labat, R. (1951), *Traité Akkadien de Diagnostics et Pronostics Médicaux*, Two volumes, Académie Internationale d’Histoire des Sciences and Brill, Paris and Leiden.
- Labat, R. and Malbran-Labat, F. (1988), *Manuel d’Épigraphie Akkadienne. Signes, Syllabaire, Idéogrammes*, Geuthner, Paris.
- Lacambre, D. and Millet, A. (2008), “Les musiciennes de Chagar Bazar”, *NABU* 2008/2 n. 51, 69–70.
- Læssøe, J. (2014), *People of Ancient Assyria: Their Inscriptions and Correspondence*, Routledge, New York.
- Lafont, B. (1985), “Relecture des tablettes de L. Legrain”, *ASJ* 7, 165–188.
- Lafont, B. (2009), “The Army of the Kings of Ur: The Textual Evidence”, *CDLJ* 2009:5, [Online document] <https://cdli.ucla.edu/files/publications/cdlj2009_005.pdf> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Lafont, B. (2016), “Women at Work and Women in Economy and Society during the Neo-Sumerian Period”, in: Lion, B. and Michel, C. (ed.), *The Role of Women in Work and Society in the Ancient Near East*, Walter de Gruyter, New York and Berlin, SANER 13, 149–173.
- Langdon, S. (1917), *Sumerian Grammatical Texts*, University of Pennsylvania Museum, Philadelphia, PBS 12/1.
- Langdon, S. (1919), “A Bilingual Tablet from Erech”, *RA* 12, 73–84.
- Langdon, S. (1931), “Assyrian Syllabaries and Other Texts”, *RA* 28, 117–141.
- Lambert, W. G. (1957–1958), “Three Unpublished Fragments of the Tukulti-Ninurta Epic”, *AfO* 18, 38–51.
- Lambert, W. F. (1959), *Babylonian Wisdom Literature*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana).

- Lambert, W. G. (2013), *Babylonian Creation Myths*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), MC 16.
- Lämmerhirt, W. (2010), *Wahrheit und Trug. Untersuchungen zur altorientalischen Begriffsgeschichte*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 348.
- Lamphere, L. (1992), “Gladys Reichard among the Navajo”, *Frontiers: A Journal of Women Studies* 12/3, 78–115.
- Landsberger, B. (1957), *The Series ḪAR-ra = ḫubullu. Tablets I - IV*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 5.
- Landsberger, B. (1958), *The Series ḪAR-ra = ḫubullu. Tablets V - VII*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 6.
- Landsberger, B. (1959), *The Series ḪAR-ra = ḫubullu. Tablets VIII - XII*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 7.
- Laroche, L. (1971), *Catalogue des Textes Hittites*, Klincksieck, Paris.
- Laroche, E. (1980), *Glossaire de la langue hourrite*, Editions Klincksieck, Paris.
- Larsen, M. T. (2002), *The Aššur-nādā Archive*, Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten (NINO), Leiden, OAAs 1.
- Lawergren, B. (2000), “Extant Silver Pipes from Ur, 2450 BC”, in: Hickmann, E. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 2*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, 121–132.
- Lawergren, B. (2010), “Bull Lyres, Silver Lyres, Silver Pipes and Animals in Sumer”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2008), The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008*, ICONEA Publications, London, 83–88.
- Lawergren, B. (2018), “Music”, in: Álvarez-Mon, J., Basello, G. P. and Wicks, Y. (ed.), *The Elamite World*, Routledge, London and New York, 781–800.
- Lawergren, B. and Gurney, O. R. (1987), “Sound Holes and Geometrical Figures. Clues to the Terminology of Ancient Mesopotamian Harps”, *Iraq* 49, 37–52.
- Ledent, D. (2009), “L’institutionnalisation des concerts publics. Enjeux politiques et esthétiques”, *Appareil 3 (Concerts publics et formes de la sensibilité musicale)*, [Online document] <<http://appareil.revues.org/809>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Legrain, L. (1912), *Le temps des rois d’Ur, recherches sur la société antique, d’après des textes nouveaux*, Honoré Champion, Paris, Bibliothèque de l’École des Hautes Études 199.
- Legrain, L. (1947), *Business documents of the Third Dynasty of Ur*, London, British Museum, UET 3.

- Levitin, D. J. (2006), *This is your Brain on Music. The Science of a Human Obsession*, Dutton, London.
- Levy, S. and Artzi, P. (1965), *Sumerian and Akkadian Documents from Public and Private Collections in Israel*, Israel Antiquities Authority, Jerusalem, Atiqot, English Series 4.
- Lieberman, S. J. (1977), *The Sumerian Loanwords in Old-Babylonian Akkadian*, Missoula (Montana), Scholars Press, HSS 22.
- Limet, H. (1986), *Textes Administratifs Relatifs aux Metaux*, Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, Paris, ARM 25.
- Linssen, M. J. H. (2004), *The Cults of Uruk and Babylon. The Temple Ritual Texts as Evidence for Hellenistic Cult Practice*, Brill and Styx, Leiden and Boston, CM 25.
- Linton, D. (1975), *The Series Sag.gig.ga.meš and Related Incantations*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, University of Birmingham.
- Lippman, E. A. (1964), *Musical Thought in Ancient Greece*, Columbia University Press, New York and London.
- Litke, R. (1998), *A Reconstruction of the Assyro-Babylonian God-Lists AN: ^dA-un-um and AN: Anu šá amēli*, Yale Babylonian Collection, New Haven (Connecticut), TBC 3.
- Liverani, M. (1992), *Studies on the Annals of Ashurnasirpal II. Band 2: Topographical analysis*, Centro Stampa d'Ateneo, Roma, Quaderni di Geografia Storica 4.
- Livingstone, A. (1986), *Mystical and Mythological Explanatory Works of Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana).
- Livingstone, A. (1989), *Court Poetry and Literary Miscellanea*, Helsinki University Press, Helsinki, SAA 3.
- Löhnert, A. (2008), "Scribes and Singers of Emesal Lamentations in Ancient Mesopotamia in the Second Millennium BCE", in: Cingano, E. and Milano, L. (ed.), *Papers on Ancient Literatures: Greece, Rome and the Near East. Proceedings of the "Advanced Seminar in the Humanities" Venice International University 2004-2005*, S.A.R.G.O.N. Editrice e Librería, Padova, Quaderni del Dipartimento di Scienze dell'Antichità e del Vicino Oriente 4, 421–447.
- Löhnert, A. (2009), "*Wie die Sonne tritt heraus!*": eine Klage zum Ausflug Enlils mit einer Untersuchung zu Komposition und Tradition sumerischer Klagelieder in altbabylonischer Zeit, Ugarit-Verlang, Münster, AOAT 365.

- Löhnert, A. (2016), “Copping with Death according to the “Elegy on the Death of Nannā””, in: Felli, C. (ed.), *How to Cope with Death: Mourning and Funerary Practices in the Ancient Near East. Proceedings of the International Workshop Firenze, 5th-6th December 2013*, ETS Editorial, Pisa, 49–66.
- Luce, J. V. (1969), “Plato on Truth and Falsity in Names”, *The Classical Quarterly* 19/2, 222–232.
- Ludwig, M.-C. (1990), *Untersuchungen zu den Hymnen des Išme-Dagan von Isin*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, SANTAG 2.
- Ludwig, M.-C. and Metcalf, Ch. (2017), “The Song of Inanna and Išme-Dagan: An Edition of BM 23820+23831”, *ZA* 107/1, 1–21.
- Maaijer, R. d. (2001), “Late third millennium identifying marks”, in: Soldt, W. H. v., Dercksen, J.G.; Kouwenberg, N. J. C. and Krispijn, Th. J. H. (ed.), *Veenhof Anniversary Volume. Studies Presented to Klaas R. Veenhof on the Occasion of his Sixty-Fifth Birthday*, Nederlands Instituut voor het Nabije Oosten (NINO), Leiden, PIHANS 89, 301–324.
- Maiocchi, M. (2009), *Classical Sargonic Tablets chiefly from Adab in the Cornell University Collection*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 13.
- Maiocchi, M. and Visicato, G. (2012), *Classical Sargonic Tablets chiefly from Adab. Part II*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 19.
- Marcetteau, M. (2008), *Vie Musicale à Mari sous les Dernières Dynasties Amorrites (1787 - 1762 avant J.C.)*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, [Abstract online] <<http://lettres.sorbonne-universite.fr/article/mme-myriam-marcetteau-vie-musicale>> [Last search 11/10/2019].
- Marcetteau, M. (2010), “A Queens’s Orchestra at the Court of Mari: A New Perspective on the Archaic Instrumentarium in the Third Millennium BC”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2008), The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008*, ICONEA Publications, London, 67–76.
- Mayer, W. R. (2005), “Die altbabylonischen Keilschrifttexte in der Sammlung des Päpstlichen Bibelinstituts”, *OrNS* 74/4, 317–351.
- MacGinnis, J. (1991-1992), “Neo-Babylonian Prebend Texts from the British Museum”, *AfO* 38/39, 74–100.
- MacGinnis, J. (2002), “The Use of Writing Boards in the Neo-Babylonian Temple Administration at Sippar”, *Iraq* 64, 217–236.

- Machinist, C. (1997), *Letters from Priests to the Kings Esarhaddon and Assurbanipal*, Helsinki University Press, Helsinki, SAA 13.
- Maidman, M. P. (2010), *Nuzi Texts and Their Uses as Historical Evidence*, Society of Biblical Literature, Atlanta (Georgia), WAW 18.
- Maekawa, K (1980), “Female Weavers and Their Children in Lagash - Pre-Sargonic and Ur III - “, *ASJ* 2, 81–125.
- Manniche, L. (1988), “The erotic oboe in Ancient Egypt”, in: Hickmann, E. and Hughes, D. W. (ed.), *The Archaeology of Early Music Cultures. Third International Meeting of the ICTM Study Group on Music Archaeology*, Bonn, Verlag für systematische Musikwissenschaft GmbH, 189–198.
- Manniche, L. (1991), *Music and musicians in ancient Egypt*, British Museum Press, London.
- Mathiesen, Th. J. (1984), “Harmonia and Ethos in Ancient Greek Music”, *The Journal of Musicology* 3/3, 264–279.
- Matthews, V. H. (1977), *Pastoral Nomadism in the Mari Kingdom (ca. 1830-1760 B. C.)*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Brandeis University, Waltham (Massachusetts).
- Matuszak, J. (2018), “Assessing Misogyny in Sumerian Disputations and Diatribes”, in: Budin, S. L. Budin, Cifarelli, García Ventura, A. and Millet Albà, A. (eds.), *Gender and methodology in the Ancient Near East: Approaches from Assyriology and beyond*, Editions de la Universitat de Barcelona, Barcelona, BMO 10, 259-272.
- Maul, S. M. (1988), “*Herzberuhigungsklagen*”: die sumerisch-akkadischen Eršahung-Gebete, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- Maul, S. M. (1999), “Gottesdienst im Sonnenheiligtum zu Sippar”, in: Böck, E., Cancik-Kirschbaum, E. and Richter, Th. (ed.), *Munuscula Mesopotamica. Festschrift für Johannes Renger*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 267, pp. 285–316.
- Maul, S. M. (2000), “Die Frühjahrsfeierlichkeiten in Assur”, in: George, A. R. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Wisdom, Gods and Literature: Studies in Honour of W. G. Lambert*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 389-420.
- Maul, S. M. (2002), “Eine neubabylonische Kultordnung für den 'Klagesänger' (*kalû*)”, in: Richter, T.; Prechel, D. and Klinger, J. (ed.), *Kulturgeschichten. Altorientalische Studien für Volkert Hass zum 65. Geburtstag*, Saarbrücker Druckerei und Verlag, Saarbrücken, 255-265.

- Mayer, W. R. and van Soldt, W. H. (1991), “Akkadische Lexikographie: CAD S”, *OrNS* 60/2, 109-120.
- McDermott, J. H.; Schultz, A. F.; Undurraga, E. A.; Godoy, R. A. (2015), “Indifference to dissonance in native Amazonians reveals cultural variation in music perception”, *Nature* 535, 547–550.
- McEwan, G. J. P. (1981a), “Agade after the Gutian Destruction: the Afterlife of a Mesopotamian city”, in: Hirsch, H. and Hunger, H. (ed.), *Vorträge gehalten auf der 28. Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale in Wien 1981*, RAI 28, Vienna, BAfO 19, 8–15.
- McEwan, G. J. P. (1981b), *Priest and Temple in Hellenistic Babylonia*, Franz Steiner Verlag, Wiesbaden, FAOS 4.
- Meek, Th. J. (1920), “Some Explanatory Lists and Grammatical Texts”, *RA* 17/3-4, 117–206.
- Meeks, D. (1997), “Les emprunts égyptiens aux langues sémitiques durant le Nouvel Empire et la Troisième Période Intermédiaire. Les aléas du comparatisme”, *BiOr* 54, 32–61.
- Meier, G. (1966), “Studien zur Beschwörungssammlung Maqlû. Zusammengestellt nach hinterlassenen Notizen”, *AfO* 21, 70–81.
- Meissner, B. (1898), *Supplement zu den Assyrischen Wörterbüchern*, Brill, Leiden.
- Michalowski, P. (1989), *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Sumer and Ur*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), MC 1.
- Michalowski, P. (2004), “Sumerian”, in: Woodward, R. D. (ed.), *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of the World’s Ancient Languages*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 19–59.
- Michalowski, P. (2006), “Love or Death? Observations on the Role of the Gala in Ur III Ceremonial Life”, *JCS* 58, 49–61.
- Michalowski, P. (2010a), “Learning Music: Schooling, Apprenticeship, and Gender in Early Mesopotamia”, in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, Berlin and Münster, LIT Verlag, Wiener Offene Orientalistik 8, 199–240.
- Michalowski, P. (2010b), “Traveler’s tales: observations on musical mobility in Mesopotamia and beyond”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA*

- 2008), *The British Museum, London, December 4–6, 2008*, ICONEA Publications, London, 117–124.
- Michalowski, P. (2011), *The Correspondence of the Kings of Ur. An Epistolary History of an Ancient Mesopotamian Kingdom*, Winona Lake (Indiana), Eisenbrauns, MC 15.
- Michalowski, P. (2013), “From the collections of an Old Babylonian Literary Connoisseur”, *RA* 107, 15–22.
- Michalowski, P. (2017), “Literary Journeys from Babylonia to Assyria: Second Millennium Copies of a Bilingual Poem Concerning Ninurta”, in: Feliu, L., Karahashi, F. and Rubio, G. (ed.), *The First Ninety Years: A Sumerian Celebration in Honor of Miguel Civil*, De Gruyter, Boston and Berlin, SANER 12, 205–230.
- Michel, C. (2001), *Correspondance des marchands de Kanis au début du Iie millénaire avant J.-C.*, Les Éditions du Cerf, Paris, LAPO 19.
- Michel, C. (2016), “Quelques remarques sur les bullae inscrites de la ville basse de Kültepe”, in: Perello, B. and Tenu, A. (ed.), *Parcours d'Orient. Recueil de textes offert à Christine Kepinski*, Archaeopress Archaeology, 175–184.
- Milano, L. (1990), *Testi Amministrativi: Assegnazioni di Prodotti Alimentari (Archivio L. 2712 - Parte I)*, Università degli Studi di Roma "La Sapienza", Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Roma, ARET 9.
- Mirelman, S. (2008), “Contrafactum in the Ancient Near East”, in Both, A. A.; Eichmann, R.; Hickmann, E.; Koch, L.-C. (eds.), *Herausforderungen und Ziele der Musikarchäologie, Vorträge des 5. Symposiums der Internationalen Studiengruppe Musikarchäologie im Ethnologischen Museum der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, 19.-23. September 2006, Studien zur Musikarchäologie 6*; Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 22, 99–110.
- Mirelman, S. (2010a), “Performative Indications in Late Babylonian Texts”, in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, LIT Verlag, Berlin and Münster, *Wiener Offene Orientalistik* 8, 241–264.
- Mirelman, S. (2010b), “The Definition of ‘Music’ in Music Archaeology. The Contribution of Historical Ethnomusicology”, in: Eichmann, R. and Koch, L.-Chr., (eds.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 7*. Marie Leidorf, Rahden, 115–118.

- Mirelman, S. (2010c), “The Gala Musician Dada and the si-im Instrument”, *NABU* 2010/2, n. 33, 40–41.
- Mirelman, S. (2011), “(Review) Monika Schuol, Hethitische Kultmusik: Eine Untersuchung den Instrumental- und Vokalmusik anhand hethitischer Ritualtexte und von archäologischen Zeugnissen. VII + 260 pp. 40 Fn. Radhen/Westf. Verlag Marie Leidorf, 2004 (= *Orient-Archäologie*, Band 14). € 71,50 ISBN 3-89646-644-5. ISSN 1434-162X”, *AfO* 51/1, 299–301.
- Mirelman, S. (2014), “The Ala-Instrument: Its Identification and Role”, in: Westenholz, J. G.; Maurey, Y. and Seroussi, E. (ed.) *Music in antiquity: the Near East and the Mediterranean*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin, *Studies of the Jewish Music Research Centre* 8, 148–171.
- Mirelman, S. (2018a), “Mesopotamian Magic in Text and Performance”, in: Panayotov, S. V. and Vacín, L. (ed.), *Mesopotamian Medicine and Magic. Studies in Honor of Markham J. Geller*, Brill, Leiden and Boston, *AMD* 14, 343–378.
- Mirelman, S. (2018b), *Text and Performance in the Mesopotamian Liturgical Tradition*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, ISAW (CUNY) and Universität Heidelberg, New York and Heidelberg.
- Mirelman, S. and Krispijn, Th. J. H. (2009), “The Old Babylonian Tuning Text UET VI/3 899”, *Iraq* 71, 43–52.
- Mirelman, S. and Sallaberger, W. (2010), “The Performance of a Sumerian Wedding Song (CT 58, 12)”, *ZA* 100, 177–196.
- Mittermayer, C. (2006), *Altbabylonische Zeichenliste der sumerisch-literarischen Texte* (with Attinger, P.), Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen.
- Mittermayer, C. (2009), *Enmerkara und der Herr von Arata. Ein ungleicher Wettstreit*, Academic Press Fribourg and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, Fribourg and Göttingen, *OBO* 239.
- Mittermayer, C. (2019), *‘Was sprach der eine zum anderen?’. Argumentationsformen in den sumerischen Rangstreitgesprächen*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin/Boston, *UAVA* 15.
- Molina, M. (2008), “The Corpus of Neo-Sumerian Tablets: an Overview”, in: Garfinkle, S. J. and Cale Johnson, J. (ed.), *The Growth of an Early State in Mesopotamia: Studies in Ur III Administration. Proceedings of the First and Second Ur III Workshops at the 49th and 51st Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale, London*

- July 10, 2003 and Chicago July 19, 2005*, Madrid, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), 19–53.
- Molino, J. (1975), “Fait musical et sémiologie de la musique”, *Musique en Jeu* 17, 37–62.
- Monroe, M. W. (2016), *Advice from the Stars: The Micro-zodiac in Seleucid Babylonia*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of Egyptology and Assyriology, Brown University, [Online document]
<<https://repository.library.brown.edu/studio/item/bdr:674191/PDF/>>
[Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Müller, K. Fr. (1937), *Das Assyrische Ritual. Teil I. Texte zum Assyrischen Königsritual*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, MVAG 41/3.
- Murai, N. (2018), *Studies in the aklu documents of the Middle Babylonian Period*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Leiden Universiteit, [Online document]
<<https://openaccess.leidenuniv.nl/handle/1887/60263>>
[Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Myhrman, D. W. (1911), *Babylonian Hymns and Prayers*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), PBS 1/1.
- Nies, J. B. (1920), *Ur Dynasty Tablets. Texts Chiefly from Tello and Drehem Written during the Reigns of Dungi, Bur-Sin, Gimil-Sin and Ibi-Sin*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Nissinen, M. (1998), *References to Prophecy in Neo-Assyrian Sources*, Helsinki University Press, Helsinki, SAA 7.
- Nettl, B. (1983), *The Study of Ethnomusicology. Thirty-one Issues and Concepts*, University of Illinois Press.
- Neumann, H. (2004), “Sumerische und akkadische Texte des 3. Jt. V. Chr.” in: Janowski, B. and Wilhelm, G. (ed.), *Texte zum Rechts- und Wirtschaftsleben*, Gütersloher Verlaghaus, Gütersloh, TUAT-NF 1, 1–24.
- Oberhuber, K. (1991), “Sänger/Musiker oder Sängerin/Musikerin? Zu einer Streitfrage der altmesopotamischen Bildkunst und Epigraphik”, in: Fink, M.; Gstrein, R. and Mössmer, G. (ed.), *Musica Privata: Die Rolle der Musik im privaten Leben, Festschrift zum 65. Geburtstag von Walter Salmen*, Heibling, Innsbruck, 339–343.
- Oelsner, J. (1980-1983), “Klageverzicht(sklausel)”, *RIA* 6, 6–15.
- Olmo de Lete, G. and Sanmartín, J. (2003), *A Dictionary of the Ugaritic Language in the Alphabetic Tradition*, Two volumes (*Part One: [(a/i/u - k)]* and *Part Two: [l - z]*), Brill, Leiden, HdOr 16.

- Oppenheim, A. L. (1948), *Catalogue of the Cuneiform Tablets of the Wilberforce Eames Babylonian Collection in the New York Public Library, Tablets of the Time of the Third Dynasty of Ur*, American Oriental Society, New Haven (Connecticut), AOS 32.
- Oppenheim, A. L. (1952), “The Archives of the Palace of Mari: A Review Article”, *JNES* 11/2, 129–139.
- Oppenheim, A. L., Reiner, E., *et al.* (eds.), (1956–2010), *The Assyrian Dictionary of the University of Chicago*, 27 Volumes, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois).
- Oshima, T. (2015), *Babylonian Poems of Pious Sufferers: Ludlul Bēl Nēmeqi and the Babylonian Theodicy*, Mohr Siebeck, Tübingen, Oriental Religions in Antiquity 14.
- Owen, D. I. (1975), *The John Frederick Lewis Collection*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 3.
- Owen, D. I. (1991), *Neo-Sumerian Texts from American Collections*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 15.
- Owen, D. I. (2013), *Cuneiform Texts Primarily from Iri-Saġrig / Āl-Šarrākī and the History of the Ur III Period. Volume 2. Catalogue and Texts*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), Nisaba 15/2.
- Owen, D. I. (2016), *The Nesbit Tablets* [With the assistance of Alexandra Kleinerman], Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, Nisaba 30.
- Owen, D. I. (2019), “New Iri-Saġriġ Ration Distribution and Related Texts”, in: Avetisyan, P. S.; Dan, R. and Greykan, Y. H. (ed.), *Over the Mountains and Far Away. Studies in Near Eastern History and Archaeology presented to Mirjo Salvini on the Occasion of his 80th Birthday*, Archaeopress Archaeology, Oxford, 389–398.
- Owen, D. I. and Wasilewska, E. (2000), “Cuneiform texts in the Arizona State Museum, Tucson”, *JCS* 52, 1–53.
- Ozaki, T. and Sigrist, M. (2006), *Ur III Administrative Tablets from the British Museum. Part Two*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 2.
- Panayotov, S. (2013), “A Copper Bell to Expel Demons in Berlin”, *NABU* 2013-3: 80–87.

- Paoletti, P. (2012), *Der König und sein Kreis. Das Staatliche Schatzarchiv der III.Dynastie von Ur*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 10.
- Park, S. J. (2013), “Musical Thought in the Zhuangzi: A Criticism of the Confucian Discourse on Ritual and Music”, *Dao* 12/3, 331–350.
- Parpola, S. (1993), *Letters from Assyrian and Babylonian Scholars*, Helsinki University Press, Helsinki, SAA 10.
- Parpola, S. (2017), *Assyrian Royal Rituals and Cultic Texts*, Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project and Finnish Assyriological Research, Helsinki, SAA 20.
- Parpola, S., et al. (2007), *Assyrian-English-Assyrian Dictionary*, The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, Helsinki.
- Pearce, L. (1995), “The Scribes and Scholars of Ancient Mesopotamia”, *CANE* 4, 2265–2278.
- Pedersén, O. (1986), *Archives and Libraries in the City of Assur: A Study of the Material from the German Excavations. Part II*. Uppsala Universitet, Uppsala, Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis. Studia Semitica Upsaliensia 8.
- Peiser, F. E. (1890), *Babylonische Verträge des Berliner Museums in Autographie, Transcription und Übersetzung*, Berlin, Wolf Peiser Verlag.
- Peled, I. (2010), “Expelling the Demon of Effeminacy: Anniwiyani's Ritual and the Question of Homosexuality in Hittite Thought”, *JANER* 10/1, 69–81.
- Peled, I. (2014), “*assinnu* and *kurgarrû* Revisited”, *JNES* 73/2, 283–297.
- Peled, I. (2015), “*kula'ūtam epēšum*: Gender Ambiguity and Contempt in Mesopotamia”, *JAOS* 135/4, 751–764.
- Peterson, J. L. (2007), *A Study of Sumerian Faunal Conception with a Focus on the Terms Pertaining to the Order Testudines*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, University of Pennsylvania, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), [Online document] <https://repository.upenn.edu/dissertations/AAI3260966/> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Peterson, J. L. (2011), *Sumerian Literary Fragments in the University Museum, Philadelphia*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 9.
- Peterson, J. L. (2015a), “An Adab Composition of Nergal/Meslamtaea at Lagaš and Ĝirsu for Šulgi”, *JCS* 67, 45–63.

- Peterson, J. L. (2015b), *Examestext A: Composite Translation and Line Bibliography*, [Online document]
 <https://www.academia.edu/11912097/Examenstext_A_Composite_Translation_and_Line_Bibliography> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Peterson, J. L. (2019a), *The Literary Sumerian of Old Babylonian Ur: UET 6/1-3 in Transliteration and Translation with Select Commentary. Part I: UET 6/1*, CDLI, Cuneiform Digital Library Preprints 15.0, [Online document].
 <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdlp/cdlp0015_20190416.pdf>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Peterson, J. L. (2019b), *The Literary Sumerian of Old Babylonian Ur: UET 6/1-3 in Transliteration and Translation with Select Commentary. Part II: UET 6/2*, CDLI, Cuneiform Digital Library Preprints 16.0, [Online document].
 <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdlp/cdlp0016_20190416.pdf>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Peterson, J. L. (2019c), *The Literary Sumerian of Old Babylonian Ur: UET 6/1-3 in Transliteration and Translation with Select Commentary. Part III: UET 6/3*, CDLI, Cuneiform Digital Library Preprints 16.0, [Online document].
 <https://cdli.ucla.edu/pubs/cdlp/cdlp0017_20190416.pdf>
 [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Petschow, H. P. H. (1980–1983), “Lehrverträge”, *RIA* 6, 556–570.
- Pettinato, G. (1977), *Testi economici di Lagaš del Museo di Istanbul. Parte I: La. 7001-7600*, *Unidade Accademica Nazionale*, Rome, MVN 6.
- Pettinato, G. (1981), *Testi lessicali monolingui della Biblioteca L. 2769*, Università degli Studi di Napoli L’Orientale, Naples, MEE 3.
- Pettinato, G. (1982), *Testi Lessicali Bilingui della Biblioteca L. 2769. Parte I: Traslitterazione dei testi e ricostruzione del VE*, Istituto Universitario Orientale di Napoli. Seminario di Studi Asiatici, MEE 4.
- Pettinato, G. and Picchioni, S. A. (1978), *Testi Economici di Lagas del Museo di Istanbul. Parte II: La. 7601-8200*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 7.
- Pinches, Th. G. (1898), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part IV*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Pinches, Th.G. (1908), *The Amherst Tablets. Part I: Texts of the Period extending to and including the reign of Bur-Sin*, Bernard Quaritch, London.

- Pinches, Th. G. (1964), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part XLV. Old-Babylonian Business Documents*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Pirngruber, R. and Waerzeggers, C. (2011), “Prebend Prices in First Millennium BC Babylonia”, *JCS* 63, 111–144.
- Pitts, A. (2015), *The Cult of the Deified King in Ur III Mesopotamia*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Graduate School of Arts & Sciences, Harvard University, Cambridge (Massachusetts), [Online document] <https://dash.harvard.edu/handle/1/17467243> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Poebel, A. (1914), *Historical and Grammatical Texts*, University Museum, Philadelphia, PBS 5.
- Pohl, A. (1935), *Vorsargonische und Sargonische Wirtschaftstexte. Autographiert und mit Inventarverzeichnis und Namenlisten versehen*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, TMH 5.
- Pomponio, F. (2006), *Tavolette cuneiformi di Adab delle collezioni della Banca d'Italia*, Centro Stampa della Banca d'Italia, Rome.
- Pomponio, F. and Visicato, G. (2015), *Middle Sargonic Tablets chiefly from Adab in the Cornell University Collections*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 20.
- Pomponio, F.; Stol, M. and Westenholz, A. (2006), *Le tavolette cuneiformi delle collezioni della Banca d'Italia. II. Tavolette cuneiformi di varia provenienza delle collezioni della Banca d'Italia*, Centro Stampa della Banca d'Italia, Rome.
- Pozzer, K. M. P.; da Silva, S. S. and Cerqueira, F. V. (2012), “Música e iconografia entre os assírios”, *Clasica. Revista brasileira de estudos clássicos* 25 1/2, 43-60.
- Prechel, D. (1996), *Die Göttin Išhara. Ein Beitrag zur altorientalischen Religionsgeschichte*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, ALASPM 11.
- Price, I. M. (1927), *The great cylinder inscriptions A [and] B of Gudea, copied from the original clay cylinders of the Telloh Collection preserved in the Louvre, autographed, signs listed, tentatively transliterated and translated, with commentary and notes*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Pruzinszky, R. (2007), “Beobachtungen zu den Ur III-zeitlichen königlichen Sängern und Sängerinnen”, in: Kohbach, M.; Procházka, S.; Selz, G. J. and Lohlker, R. (ed.), *Festschrift für Hermann Hunger zum 65. Geburtstag gewidmet von seinen Freunden, Kollegen und Schülern*, Institut für Orientalistik, Vienna, WZKM 97, 329–352.

- Pruzsinszky, R. (2010a), “Die königlichen Sänger der Ur III-Zeit als Werkzeug politischer Propaganda”, in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, LIT Verlag, Berlin and Münster, Wiener Offene Orientalistik 8, 95–118.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2010b), “Singer, musicians and their mobility in Ur III Period Cuneiform Texts”, in: Dumbrill, R. J. and Finkel, I. L. (ed.), *Proceedings of the International Conference of Near Eastern Archaeomusicology (ICONEA 2009-2010)*, Université de la Sorbonne, Paris, and Senate House, School of Musical Research, University of London, November 2009 and December 2010, ICONEA Publications, London, 31–39.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2013), “The Social Positions of NAR-Musicians of the Ur III Period at the End of the IIIrd Millennium BC”, in: Emerit, S. (ed.), *Le statut du musicien dans la Méditerranée ancienne: Égypte, Mésopotamie, Grèce, Rome: actes de la table ronde internationale tennue à Lyon, Maison de l’Orient et de la Méditerranée, les 4 et 5 juillet 2008*, Institut Français d’Archéologie Orientale, Cairo, IFAO Bibliothèque d’Étude 159, 31–46.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2015), “Vielseitig und kreativ. Musikerinnen im Alten Orient”, *Frauen im Alten Orient*, *Antike Welt* 201/02, 26–31.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2016), “Musicians and Monkeys: Ancient Near Eastern Clay Plaques Displaying Musicians and Their Socio-Cultural Role”, in: Bellia, A. and Marconi, C. (ed.), *Musicians in Ancient Coroplastic Art: Iconography, Ritual Contexts, and Functions*, Istituti Editoriali Poligrafici Internazionali, Pisa and Rome, 23–34.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2018a), “Las mujeres y el universo musical en el Próximo Oriente Antiguo”, in: Justel, J. J. and García-Ventura, A. (ed.), *Las mujeres en el Oriente cuneiforme*, Servicio de Publicaciones de la Universidad de Alcalá, Alcalá de Henares, 89–116.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (2018b), “‘The Poor Musician’ in Ancient Near Eastern Texts and Images”, in: García-Ventura, A., Tavolieri, C. and Verderame, L. (ed.), *The Study of Musical Performance in Antiquity. Archaeology and Written Sources*, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, 39–58.
- Pruzsinszky, R. (forthcoming), *Sänger und Sängerinnen im Alten Orient, Eine diachrone Studie (3.-1. Jt. v. Chr.) zur Stellung der Berufsgruppe der Sänger unter wirtschaftlichen und gesellschaftlich-kulturellen Gesichtspunkten*.

- Raman, C. V. (1922), “The acoustical knowledge of the ancient Hindus”, *Asutosh Mookerjee Silver Jubilee 2*, 179–185.
- Rašīd, F. (1981), *The Ancient Inscriptions in Himrin Area: Results of the Salvage Excavations at Himrin Reservoir* (in Arabic), Baghdad, Himrin 4.
- Rašīd, Ş. A. (1984), *Mesopotamien*, VEB Deutscher Verlag für Musik, Leipzig, Musikgeschichte in Bildern, Musik des Altertums II/2.
- Rawlinson, H. C. (1866), *A Selection from the Miscellaneous Inscriptions of Assyria*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Reculeau, H. (2018), *L’Agriculture Irriguée au Royaume de Mari: Essai d’Histoire des Techniques*, 2 volumes, Société d’Études du Proche-Orient Ancien, Paris, FM 16.
- Redondo Reyes, P. (2002), *La Harmónica de Ptolomeo. Edición Crítica con Introducción, Traducción y Comentario*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Universidad de Murcia.
- Reichard, G. A. (1997), *Spider Woman: A Story of Navajo Weavers and Chantes* [With an introduction by Louise Lamphere], University of New Mexico Press, Albuquerque (New Mexico).
- Reiner, E. and Civil, M. (1974), *The Series HAR-ra = ħubullu, Tablets XX - XXIV*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, MSL 11.
- Reisner, G. (1896), *Sumerisch-babylonische Hymnen nach Tontafeln griechischer Zeit*, W. Spemann, Berlin.
- Reisner, G. (1901), *Tempelurkunden aus Telloh, königliche Museen zu Berlin*, Mittheilungen aus den orientalischen Sammlungen 16, Spemann, Berlin.
- Rendu Loisel, A.-C. (2011), *Bruit et Emotion dans la Littérature Akkadienne*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Université de Genève, [Online document] <<https://tel.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-00770955/document>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Rendu Loisel, A.-C. (2015), “The Voice of Mighty Copper in a Mesopotamian Exorcistic Ritual”, in: Pongratz-Leisten, B. and Sonik, K. (eds.), *The Materiality of Divine Agency*, De Gruyter, Berlin, SANER 8, 211–227.
- Rendu Loisel, A.-C. (2016), *Les chants du monde. Le paysage sonore de la Mésopotamie ancienne* (avec un appendice d’Ariane Thomas), Press Universitaires du Midi and Musée du Louvre.
- Renger, J. (1967), “Untersuchungen zum Priestertum der altbabylonischen Zeit 1. Teil”, *ZA* 58, 110–118.

- Renger, J. (1969), “Untersuchungen zum Priestertum der altbabylonischen Zeit 2. Teil”, *ZA* 59, 104–230.
- Richter, Th. (1999), *Untersuchungen zu den lokalen Panthea Süd- und Mittelbabyloniens in altbabylonischer Zeit*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 257.
- Richter, Th. (2012), *Bibliographisches Glossar des Hurritischen*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- Robson, E. (1999), *Mesopotamian Mathematics 2100-1600 BC: Technical Constants in Bureaucracy and Education*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, OECT 14.
- Robson, E. (2001), “The tablet House: a scribal school in Old Babylonian Nippur”, *RA* 93/1, 39-66.
- Robson, E. (2007), “The long career of a favourite figure: the *apsamikku* in Neo-Babylonian mathematics”, in: Ross, M. (ed.), *From the banks of the Euphrates: studies in honor of ALice Louise Slotsky*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 209-224).
- Rocconi, E. (2012), “The Aesthetic Value of Music in Platonic Thought”, in: Sluiter, I and Rosen, R. M. (ed.), *Aesthetic Value in Classical Antiquity*, Brill, Leiden, Mnemosyne 350.
- Rochberg-Halton, F. (1987), “The Assumed 29th *ahû*-tablet of *Enūma Anu Enlil*”, in: Rochberg, F. (ed.), *Language, Literature, and History: Philological and Historical Studies presented to Erica Reiner*, American Oriental Society, New Haven (Connecticut), AOS 67, 327–350.
- Rodin, Th. (2014), *The World of the Sumerian Mother Goddess. An Interpretation of her Myths*, Uppsala Universitet, Uppsala, Acta Universitatis Upsaliensis. Historia Religionum 35.
- Rodríguez Adrados, F. (1989), “Sobre Nombre y Cosas en Platón”, in: Borrego Nieto, J. (ed.), *Philologica: Homenaje a Antonio Llorente*, 2 volumes, Universidad de Salamanca, Salamanca, 415–418.
- Römer, W. H. Ph. (1990), “Weisheitstexte” und Texte mit Bezug auf den Schulbetrieb in sumerischer Sprache, in: Kaiser, O. (ed.), *TUAT* III/1, 17–109.
- Römer, W. H. Ph. (1993), “Mythen und Epen in sumerischer Sprache”, *TUAT* III/3, 351–559.
- Römer, W. H. Ph. (1999), *Die Sumerologie. Einführung in die Forschung und Bibliographie in Auswahl*, Ugarit Verlag, Münster, AOAT 262.

- Römer, W. H. Ph. (2010), *Die Zylinderinschriften von Gudea*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 376.
- Roth, M. Th. (1987), “Age at Marriage and the Household: A Study of Neo-Babylonian and Neo-Assyrian Forms”, *Comparative Studies in Society and History* 29/4, 715–747.
- Roth, M. Th. (1989), *Babylonian Marriage Agreements 7th - 3rd Centuries B.C.*, Neukirchener Verlag, Neukirchern, AOAT 222.
- Rouault, O. (1977), *Mukannisum. L'Administration et l'Économie Palatiales à Mari. Transcription, Traduction et Étude Historique*, Geuthner, Paris, ARM 18.
- Rowell, L. (1981), “Early Indian Musical Speculation and the Theory of Melody”, *Jornal of Music Theory* 25/2, 217–244.
- Rowell, L. (1992), *Music and Musical Thought in Early India*, University of Chicago Press, Chicado and London.
- Rubio, G. (2002), “On a recent volume of Mari letters”, *AuOr* 20, 239–243.
- Rubio, G. (2009), “Sumerian Literature”, in: Ehrlich, C. S. (ed.), *From an Antique Land. An Introduction to Ancient Near Eastern Literature*, Rowman & Littlefield Publishes Inc., Plymouth, 11–76.
- Rudik, N. (2013), *Die Entwicklung der keilschriftlichen sumerischen Beschwörungsliteratur von den Anfängen bis zur Ur III-Zeit*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Philosophischen Fakultät, Friedrich-Schiller-Universität Jena, Jena [Online document] <<https://d-nb.info/1074139194/34>> [Last search on 14/08/2018].
- Sacks, O. (2007), *Musicophilia. Tales of Music and the Brain*, Alfred A. Knopf, New York and Toronto.
- Sallaberger, W. (1993), *Der kultische Kalender der Ur III - Zeit*, Two Volumes, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin and New York, UAVA 7/1+2.
- Sallaberger, W. (2006), *Leipzig-Münchner Sumerischer Zettelkasten*, Institut für Assyriologie und Hethitologie, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität München, München, [Online document] <https://www.assyriologie.uni-muenchen.de/forschung/forschungsprojekte/sumglossar/zettelkasten2006_09.pdf> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Sallaberger, W. (2011), “Sumerian Language Use at Garšana. On Ortography, Grammar and Akkado-Sumerian Bilingualism”, in: Owen, D. I. (ed.), *Garšana Studies*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 6.

- Sallaberger, W. (2011–2013), “Šulgi”, *RIA* 13, 270–280.
- Sallaberger, W. (2013), “The Management of Royal Treasure. Palace Archives and Palatial Economy in the Ancient Near East”, in: Hill, J. A.; Jones, Ph. and Morales, A. (ed.), *Experiencing Power, Generating Authority. Cosmos, Politics, and the Ideology of Kingship in Ancient Egypt and Mesopotamia*, University of Pennsylvania Press, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), 119–255.
- Sallaberger, W. (2014–2015), “Ur-Namma”, *RIA* 14, 422–431.
- Sallaberger, W. and Huber Vulliet, F. (2003-2005), “Priester. A. I. Mesopotamien”, *RIA* 10, 617–640.
- Salvini, M. (2018), *Corpus dei testi urartei. Volume V. Revisione delle epigrafi e nuovi testi su pietra et roccia (CTU A). Dizionario Urarteo. Schizzo grammaticale della lingua Urartea*, De Boccard, Paris.
- Samet, N. (2014), *The Lamentation over the Destruction of Ur*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake, MC 18.
- San Nicolò, M. (1947), “Zum *atru* und anderen Nebenleistungen des Käufers beim neubabylonischen immobiliarkauf”, *OrNS* 16, 273-302.
- San Nicolò, M. and Ungnad, A. (1937), *Neubabylonische Rechts- und Verwaltungsurkunden. Übersetzt und Erläutert. Band I: Rechts- und Wirtschaftsurkunden der Berliner Museen aus Vorhellenistischer Zeit*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Sandowicz, M. (2018), “Before Xerxes: The Role of the Governor of Babylonia in the Administration of Justice under the First Achaemenids”, in: Waerzeggers, C. and Seire, M. (eds.), *Xerxes and Babylonia. The Cuneiform Evidence*, Peeters, Leuven/Paris/Bristol (Connecticut), OLA 277.
- Sánchez Muñoz, D. (2016), “Una reflexión sobre el origen de la importancia de la música en la antigua Mesopotamia a partir de los Cilindros de Gudea A y B”, *Antigüedad Religión y Sociedades (ARYS)* 14 (*Verenda Numina: Temor y Experiencia Religiosa en el Mundo Antiguo*), 193-222.
- Sánchez Muñoz, D. (2017), “The south face of the Helicon: Ancient Egyptian musical elements in ancient Greek music”, in: Rosińska-Balik, K.; Dębowska-Ludwin, J. and Chyla, J. M. (ed.), *Current Research in Egyptology 2016 Proceedings*, Oxbow, Oxford and Philadelphia, 173-185.
- Sánchez Muñoz, D. (*forthcoming* - a), “**e2 nam-nar-ra**: A Musical Royal Space in Ancient Mesopotamia”, in Bellia, A. (ed.), *Musical and Choral Performance*

- Spaces in the Ancient World*, Istituti Editoriali e Poligrafici Internazionali, Pisa and Rome, Telestes 5.
- Sánchez Muñoz, D. (forthcoming - b) “**tigi2 a-da-ab nam-nar šu du7-a...** hymnes ou instruments à percussion en *Šulgi B*, 157” *Pallas: Revue des Études Antiques*.
- Saporetti, C. (1993), “Alcune Note in Margine ad un Volume di Assiriologia Recentemente Riproposto in Traduzione Italiana”, *EVO* 16, 117-121.
- Sassmannshausen, L. (2001), *Beiträge zur Verwaltung und Gesselschaft Babyloniens in der Kassitenzeit*, Philipp von Zabern, Mainz am Rhein, BagF 21.
- Sasson, J. M. (2012), “‘Nothing So Swift As Calumny’: Slander and Justification at the Mari Court”, in: Boiy, T.; Brestschneider, J.; Goddeeris, A.; Hameeuw, H.; Jans, G. and Tavernier, J. (eds.), *The Ancient Near East, A Life! Festschrift Karel van Lerberghe*, Peeters, Leuven, Paris and Walpole (Massachusetts), OLA 220, 525-542.
- Sauren, H. (1978), *Les tablettes cunéiformes de l'époque d'Ur des collections de la New York Public Library*, Institut Orientaliste de Louvain, Louvain, PIOL 19.
- Sauren, H. (1993), “Nammu and Enki”, in: Cohen, M. E.; Snell, D. C. and Weisberg, D. B. (ed.), *The Tablet and the Scroll: Near Eastern Studies in Honor of William W. Hallo*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), 198–208.
- Scheil, V. (1913), *Textes Élamites-Sémitiques. Cinquième Série*, Ernest Laroux, Paris, MDP 14.
- Schipper, J. (2006), *Disability Studies and the Hebrew Bible: Figuring Mephibosheth in the David Story*, Bloomsbury Publishing, New York and London.
- Schneider, N. (1925), *Das Drehem und Djoha-Archiv*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, OrSP 18.
- Schneider, N. (1930), *Die Geschäftsurkunden aus Drehem und Djoha in den Staatlichen Museen (VAT) zu Berlin in Autographie und mit systematischen Wörterindices herausgegeben*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, OrSP 47–49.
- Schneider, N. (1932), *Die Drehem- und Djohatexte im Kloster Montserrat (Barcelona) in Autographie und mit systematischen Wörterverzeichnissen*, Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, AnOr 7.
- Schneider, Th. (1992), *Asiatische Personennamen in ägyptischen Quellen des Neuen Reiches*, Universitätsverlag and Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht, Fribourg and Göttingern, OBO 114.

- Schramm, W. (2008), *Ein Compendium sumerisch-akkadischer Beschwörungen*, Universitätsverlag Göttingen, Göttingen, Göttinger Beiträge zum Alten Orient 2.
- Schramm, W. (2010), *Akkadische Logogramme*, Universitätsverlag Göttingen, Göttinger, Göttinger Beiträge zum Alten Orient 5.
- Schretter, M. K. (1990), *Emesal-Studien: Sprach- und literaturgeschichtliche Untersuchungen zur sogenannten Frauensprache des Sumerischen*, Verlag des Instituts für Sprachwissenschaft der Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Kulturwissenschaft Sonderheft 69.
- Schroeder, O. (1916), *Kontrakte der seleukidenzeit aus Warka mit einer Zeichenliste und Tafel*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, VS 15.
- Schuol, M. (2004), *Hethitische Kultmusic. Eine Untersuchung der Instrumental- und Vokalmusik anhand hethitischer Ritualtexte und von archäologischen Zeugnissen*, Marie Leidorf, Radhen, Orient Archäologie 14.
- Schwemer, D. (2001), *Die Wettergottgestalten Mesopotamiens und Nordsyriens im Zeitalter der Keilschriftkulturen*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- Sciandra, R. (2011), *Aspects of Local Power in Neo and Late Babylonian Mesopotamia: the Case of Assemblies*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, [Online document] <<https://core.ac.uk/download/pdf/14703035.pdf>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Seidl, U. (2012), “Tanz. B. In der Bildkunst”, *RIA* 13, 4/5, 448–451.
- Seidl, U. (2009), “Musik und Tanz in Urartu”, in: Sağlamtimur, H.; Abay, E.; Dein, Z.; Erdem, A. Ü.; Batmaz, A.; Dedeoğlu, F.; Erdalkıran; Baştürk, M. B. and Konakçı, E. (ed.), *Altan Çilingiroğlu'na Armağan. Yukarı Denizin Kıyısında Urartu Krallığı'na Adanmış Bir Hayat / Studies in Honour of Altan Çilingiroğlu. A Life Dedicated to Urartu on the Shores of the Upper Sea*, Arkeoloji ve Sanat Yayınları, 607–617.
- Selz, G. J. (1989), *Die altsumerischen Wirtschaftsurkunden der Ermitage zu Leningrad*, Franz Steiner Verlag Wiesbaden GmbH, Stuttgart, FAOS 15/1.
- Selz, G. J. (1997), “The holy Drum the Spear and the Harp. Towards an understanding of the problems of deification in the third millennium Mesopotamia”, in: Finkel, I. L. and Geller, M. J. (ed.), *Sumerian Gods and their Representation*, Styx, Groningen, CM 7, 167–213.
- Selz, G. J. (2003), “Die Spur der Objekte. Überlegungen zur Bedeutung von Objektivierungsprozessen und Objektmanipulationen in der mesopotamischen Frühgeschichte”, in: Wenzel, U., Bretzinger, B. and Holz, K. (ed.), *Subjekte und*

- Gesellschaft. Zur Konstitution von Sozialität. Fs Günter Dux*, Velbrück Wissenschaft, Weilerswist, 233-258.
- Selz, G. J. (2018), "Aesthetics", in: Gunter, A. C. (ed.), *A Companion to Ancient Near Eastern Art*, Wiley & Sons, 359–382.
- Shaffer, A. and Ludwig, M.-C. (2006), *Literary and Religious Texts. Third Part*, British Museum, London, UET 6/3.
- Shehata, D. (2002), "Contributions to the Music Theory System of Mesopotamia", in: Hickmann, E.; Kilmer, A. D. and Eichmann, R. (ed.) *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 3*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden and Westphalen, *Orient Archäologie* 10, 487–496.
- Shehata, D. (2006), "Some Observations on the /alġarsur/", in: Hickmann, E.; Both, A. A. and Eichmann, R. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 5. Music Archaeology in Contexts. Papers from the 4th Symposium of the International Study Group on Music Archaeology at Monastery Michaelstein, 19-26 September 2004*, Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 20, 367–378.
- Shehata, D. (2007), "Privates Musizieren in Mesopotamien?", in: Kohbach, M.; Procházka, S.; Selz, G. J. and Lohlker, R. (ed.), *Festschrift für Hermann Hunger zum 65. Geburtstag gewidmet von seinen Freunden, Kollegen und Schülern*, Institut für Orientalistik, Vienna, WZKM 97, 521–529.
- Shehata, D. (2008), "On the Mythological Background of the Lamentation Priest", in: Both, A. A. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 6. Herausforderungen und Ziele der Musikarchäologie: Vorträge des 5. Symposiums der Internationalen Studiengruppe Musikarchäologie im Ethnologischen Museum der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, 19. - 23. September 2006 = Challenges and objectives in music archaeology*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 22, 119–127.
- Shehata, D. (2009), *Musiker und ihr vokales Repertoire. Untersuchungen zu Inhalt und Organisation von Musikerberufen und Liedgattungen in altbabylonischer Zeit*, Universitätsverlag Göttingen, Göttingen, *Göttinger Beiträge zur Altem Orient* 3.
- Shehata, D. (2010), "Klagesänger und ihr Gesangsrepertoire. Überlegungen zu den Überlieferungswegen altbabylonischer Kultliturgie", in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, LIT Verlag, Berlin and Münster, *Wiener Offene Orientalistik* 8, 171–198.

- Shehata, D. (2013), “Status and Organisation of the Babylonian Lamentation Priests”, in: Emerit, S. (ed.), *Le statut du musicien dans la Méditerranée ancienne: Égypte, Mésopotamie, Grèce, Rome: actes de la table ronde internationale tennue à Lyon, Maison de l’Orient et de la Méditerranée, les 4 et 5 juillet 2008*, Institut Français d’Archéologie Orientale, Cairo, IFAO Bibliothèque d’Étude 159, 69–86.
- Shehata, D. (2014), “Sounds from the Divine: Religious Musical Instruments in the Ancient Near East”, in: Westenholz, J. G.; Maurey, Y. and Seroussi, E. (ed.) *Music in antiquity: the Near East and the Mediterranean*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin, Studies of the Jewish Music Research Centre 8, 102–128.
- Shehata, D. (2017a), “Eine mannshohe Leier im altbabylonischen Ištar-Ritual aus Mari (FM 3, no. 2)”, *AoF* 44/1, 68–81.
- Shehata, D. (2017b), “La théorie musicale mésopotamienne et le système de “notation””, in: Emerit, S.; Guichard, H.; Jeammet, V.; Perrot, S.; Thomas, A.; Vendries, Chr.; Vincent, A. and Ziegler, N. (ed.), *Musiques! Échos de l’Antiquité*, Musée du Louvre-Lens and Snoeck Publishers, Lens and Ghent, 44–45.
- Shehata, D. (2017c), “Naturgewalt und (Un)heilsmacht. Strukturelle und inhaltliche Überlegungen zum akkadischen Anzû-Mythos”, in: Kertai, D. and Niewenhuyse, O. (ed.), *From the Four Corners of the Earth. Studies in Iconography and Cultures of the Ancient Near East in Honour of F. A. M. Wiggermann*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 441, 181-204.
- Shehata, D. (2018a), *Der Anzu-Vogel. Bedeutung und Wandel eines mesopotamischen Mischwesens in Literatur und Ikonographie. Mit einer Neuedition und Analyse der Anzu-Erzählungen*, Unpublished *Habilitationschrift*, Universität Würzburg.
- Shehata, D. (2018b), “Singing and Singers in the 2nd Millennium Babylonia: A New Look at Selected Texts and Images”, in: García-Ventura, A., Tavolieri, C. and Verderame, L. (ed.), *The Study of Musical Performance in Antiquity. Archaeology and Written Sources*, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, 59–92.
- Shehata, D. (2019), “Religious Poetry and Musical Performance under King Hammurāpi of Babylon and His Successors”, in: Eichmann, R., Howell, M. and Lawson, G. (ed.), *Music and Politics in the Ancient World. Exploring Identity, Agency, Stability and Change Through the Records of Music Archaeology*, Topoi Excellence Cluster, Berlin, Berlin Studies of the Ancient World 65, 159–182.

- Shringy, R. K. (1978), *Saṅgīta Ratnākara of Śārṅgadeva: Sanskrit Text and English Translation with Comments and Notes*, 2 volumes, Motilal Banarsidass, Delhi, Varanasi and Patna.
- Sibbing Plantholt, I. (2014), “A New Look at the Kassite Medical Letters, and an Edition of Šumu-libši Letter N 969”, *ZA* 104/2, 171–181.
- Sigrist, M. (1977), “Offrandes dans le temple de Nusku à Nippur”, *JCS* 29, 169–183.
- Sigrist, M. (1984), *Neo-Sumerian Account Texts in the Horn Archaeological Museum*, Andrew University Press, Berrien Springs, AUCT 1.
- Sigrist, M. (1990), *Tablettes du Princeton Theological Seminary. Époque d’Ur III*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), OPSNKF 10.
- Sigrist, M. (1991), *Documents from Tablet Collections in Rochester - New York*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Sigrist, M. (1992), *Drehem*, Bethesda (Maryland), CDL Press.
- Sigrist, M. (2000a), *Texts from the Yale Babylonian Collections I*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), SAT 2.
- Sigrist, M. (2000b), *Texts from the Yale Babylonian Collections II*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), SAT 3.
- Sigrist, M. (2004), *Neo-Sumerian Texts from the Royal Ontario Museum. II. Administrative Texts Mainly from Umma*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Sigrist, M. (2005), *Tablets from the Princeton Theological Seminary. Ur III Period. Part 2*, University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania), OPSNKF 18.
- Sigrist, M.; Gavin, C. E. S.; Stein, D.; Menard, C. (1988), *Neo-Sumerian Account Texts in the Horn Archaeological Museum*, Andrews University Press, Berrien Springs, AUCT 3.
- Sigrist, M. and Ozaki, T. (2009a), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Tablets from the Yale Babylonian Collection. Part One*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 6.
- Sigrist, M. and Ozaki, T. (2009b), *Neo-Sumerian Administrative Tablets from the Yale Babylonian Collection. Part Two*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 7.
- Sigrist, M.; Owen, D. I. and Young, G. D. (1984), *The John Frederick Lewis Collection-Part II*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 12.
- Sjöberg, Å. (1973), “Der Vater und sein missratener Sohn”, *JCS* 25, 105–169.
- Sjöberg, Å. (1974), “Der Examenstext A”, *ZA* 64, 137–176.

- Sjöberg, Å. (1976), “The Old Babylonian Eduba”, in: Lieberman *et al.* (ed.), *Sumerological Studies in Honor of Thorkild Jacobsen on his seventieth birthday, June 7 1974*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), AS 20, 159–179.
- Sjöberg, Å. (1983), “The First Pushkin Museum Elegy and New Texts”, *JAOS* 103/1, 315–320.
- Sjöberg, Å. (ed.) (1984–1998), *The Sumerian Dictionary of the University Museum of the University of Pennsylvania*, 4 volumes, Babylonian Section of the University Museum, Philadelphia (Pennsylvania).
- Skelton, D. A. (2017), *Singers of Wisdom: Hymnody and Pedagogy in Ben Sira and the Second Temple Period*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Florida State University, [Online document] <<https://fsu.digital.flvc.org/islandora/object/fsu:552131/datastream/PDF/view>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Slobodzianek, I. (2012), *Acquérir, exprimer et transmettre les “pouvoirs” divins : une comparaison entre Aphrodite et Inanna-Ištar*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Université Toulouse le Mirail - Toulouse II, Toulouse, [Online document] <<https://tel.archives-ouvertes.fr/tel-00802105/document>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Smith, M. S. and Pitard, W. T. (2009), *The Ugaritic Baal Cycle. Volume II. Introduction with Text, Translation and Commentary of KTU/CAT 1.3-1.4*, Brill, Leiden and Boston, VTS 114.
- Snell, D. C. (1982), *Ledgers and Prices: Early Mesopotamian Merchant Accounts*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut) and London, YNER 8.
- Snell, D. C. and Lager, C. (1991), *Economic Texts from Sumer*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut), YOS 18.
- Sollberger, E. (1978), *The Pinches Manuscript*, Multigrafica Editrice, Rome, MVN 5.
- Sommerfeld, W. (1982), *Der Aufstieg Marduks. Die Stellung Marduks in der babylonischen Religion des zweiten Jahrtausends v. Chr.*, Butzon & Bercker and Neukirchener Verlag, Kevelaer and Neukirchen-Vluyn, AOAT 213.
- Spada, G. (2018), *Sumerian Model Contracts from the Old Babylonian Period in the Hilprecht Collection Jena*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, TMH 11.
- Spycket, A. (1972), “La musique instrumentale mésopotamienne”, *Journal des savants*, 1972/3, 153–209.

- Stauder, W. (1970), “Die Musik der Sumerer, Babylonier und Assyrer”, in: Hickmann, H. and Stauder, W. (ed.), *Orientalische Musik*, Brill, Leiden and Köln, HdOr 1.4, 171–244.
- Steiner, G. (1972), “Die Bezeichnung von ‘Gruppen’ und ‘Klassen’ durch Abstrakta in Sprachen des Alten Orients”, in Edzard, D. (ed.), *Gesellschaftsklassen im Alten Zweistromland und in den angrenzenden Gebieten: XVIII. Rencontre assyriologique internationale, München 29. Juni bis 3. Juli 1970*, Beck, München, 191–208.
- Steinkeller, P. (1979), “Notes on Sumerian Plural Verbs”, *OrNS* 48, 54–67.
- Steinkeller, P. (1981), “Studies in Third Millennium Palaeography, I: Signs TIL and BAD”, *ZA* 71, 19–28.
- Steinkeller, P. (1982), “The Question of Marḥaši: A Contribution to the Historical Geography of Iran in the Third Millennium B.C.”, *ZA* 72, 237–265.
- Steinkeller, P. (1984), “Old Akkadian Miscellanea: 3. *isqam nadā’um* in Old Akkadian”, *RA* 78 (1984), 83–88.
- Steinkeller, P. (2001), “New Light on the Hydrology and Topography of Southern Babylonia in the Third Millennium”, *ZA* 91, 22–84.
- Steinkeller, P. (2006), “New Light on Marhashi and its Contacts with Makkan and Babylonia”, *JMS* 1, 1–17.
- Steinkeller, P. (2010), “On the Location of the Towns of Ur-Zababa and Dimat-Enlil and on the Course of the Arahtum”, in: Fincke, J. (ed.), *Festschrift für Gernot Wilhelm anlässlich seines 65. Geburtstages am 28. Januar 2010*, Islet-Verlag, Dresden, 369–382.
- Steinkeller, P. (2015), “On the Reading of the Pre-Sargonic Personal Name DI-(d)Utu and Related Matters”, *JNES* 74, 39–44.
- Steinkeller, P. (2017), *History, Texts and Art in Early Babylonia: Three Essays*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston and Berlin, SANER 15.
- Still, B. (2019), *The Social World of the Babylonian Priest*, Brill, Leiden, CHANE 103.
- Stępień, M. (2006), *Animal Husbandry in the Ancient Near East. A Prosopographic Study of Third-Millennium Umma*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Stock, J. (1993), “A Historical Account of the Chinese Two-Stringed Fiddle Erhu”, *The Galpin Society Journal* 46, 83–113.
- Stol, M. (1981), *Letters from Yale*, Brill, Leiden, AbB 9.
- Stol, M. (1998–2000), “Nippur. A. II. Altbabylonisch”, *RIA* 9, 539–544.

- Stol, M. (2000), *Birth in Babylonia and the Bible: Its Mediterranean Setting* [with a Chapter by F.A.M. Wiggermann], Styx, Groningen, CM 14.
- Stol, M. (2006–2008), “Sabum. B. Old Babylonian and later”, *RIA* 11, 479–480.
- Stol, M. (2012), “(Review) SHEHATA, D. — Musiker und ihr vokales Repertoire. Untersuchungen zu Inhalt und Organisation von Musikerberufen und Liedgattungen in altbabylonischer Zeit. (Göttinger Beiträge zum Alten Orient, Band 3). Universitätsverlag Göttingen, Göttingen, 2009. (24,5 cm, IX, 479). ISBN 978-3-941875-13-5. ISSN 1866-2595. / € 40,-.”, *BiOr* 69, 547–550.
- Stol, M. (2015), “(Review) SVÄRD, S. — Women and Power in Neo-Assyrian Palaces. (State Archives of Assyria Studies, 23). The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, Helsinki, 2015. (25 cm, XIV, 286). ISBN 978-952-10-1346-1. ISSN 1235-1032. \$ 79.50.”, *BiOr* 72 5/6, 699-702.
- Stol, M. (2016), *Women in the Ancient Near East* [translated by Helen and Mervyn Richardson], Walter de Gruyter, Berlin and New York.
- Stone, E. C. (1987), *Nippur Neighborhoods*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), SAOC 44.
- Stone, E. C. and Owen, D. I. (1991), *Adoption in Old Babylonian Nippur and the Archive of Mannum-mesu-lissur*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), MC 3.
- Streck, M. P. (2001), “Keilschrift und Alphabet”, in: Borchers, D., Kammerzell, F.; Weninger, S. (ed.), *Hieroglyphen, Alphabete, Schriftreformen: Studien zu Multiliteralismus, Schriftwechsel und Orthographieneuregelungen*, Seminar für Ägyptologie und Koptologie, Göttingen, *Lingua Aegyptia-Studia Monographica* 3, 77–97.
- Streck, M. P. (2018), *Supplement to the Akkadian Dictionaries. Vol. 1: B, P* (with the collaboration of Nadezda Rudik), Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden, LAOS 7,1.
- Sultan, N. (1988), “New Light on the Function of “Borrowed Notes” in Ancient Greek Music: A Look at Islamic Parallels”, *The Journal of Musicology* 6/3, 387–398.
- Suter, C. E. (2000), *Gudea's Temple Building. The Representation of an Early Mesopotamian Ruler in Text and Image*, Styx, Groningen, CM 17.
- Svärd, S. (2018), “Women in Neo-Assyrian Temples”, in: Yamada, Sh. (ed.), *Neo-Assyrian Sources in Context. Thematic Studies of Texts, History, and Culture*, Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project and Foundation for Finnish Assyriological Research, Helsinki, State Archives of Assyria Studies 28, 117-133.

- Szjártó, I. M. and Magnússon, S. G. (2013), *What is Microhistory? Theory and Practice*, Routledge, London and New York.
- Szlechter, E. (1963), *Tablettes juridiques et administratives de la III^e Dynastie d'Ur et de la I^{re} Dynastie de Babylone conservées au Musée de l'université de Manchester et, à Cambridge, au Musée Fitzwilliam, à l'Institut d'études orientales et à l'Institut d'égyptologie*, Two volumes, Publications de l'Institut de Droit Romain de l'Université de Paris and Sirey, Paris.
- Talon, Ph. (1985), *Texts administratifs de salles Y et Z du Palais de Mari. Planches*, Éditions Recherche sur les Civilisations, Paris, ARM 24.
- Talon, Ph. (2005), *The Standard Babylonian Creation Myth. Enuma Elis. Introduction, Cuneiform Text, Transliteration, and Sign List with a Translation and Glossary in French*, The Neo-Assyrian Text Corpus Project, Helsinki, State Archives of Assyria Cuneiform Texts 4.
- Tanos, B. (2007), "The polysemy and productivity of the formative element *nam* in Old Babylonian literary Sumerian", in: Cunningham, G. and Ebeling, J. (ed.), *Analysing Literary Sumerian: Corpus-based Approaches*, Equinox, London, 250–272.
- Taylor, J. (2001), "A New OB Proto-Lu-Izi Combination Tablet", *OrNS* 70, 209–234.
- Taylor, J. (2005), "The Sumerian Proverb Collections", *RA* 99/1, 13-18.
- Tenney, J. S. (2011), *Life at the Bottom of Babylonian Society. Servile Laborers at Nippur in the 14th and 13th Centuries B.C.*, Brill, Leiden, CHANE 51.
- Terada, Y. (2008) "Tamiḷ Isai as a Challenge to Brahmanical Music Culture in South India", *Senri Ethnological Studies* 71, 203–226.
- Teppo, S. (2007), "Agency and the Neo-Assyrian Women of the Palace", *StOr* 101, 381–420.
- Thomas, A. (2017), "Tablette: mythe sumérien de la création de l'homme dont les musiciens", in in: Emerit, S.; Guichard, H.; Jeammet, V.; Perrot, S.; Thomas, A.; Vendries, Chr.; Vincent, A. and Ziegler, N. (ed.), *Musiques! Échos de l'Antiquité*, Musée du Louvre-Lens and Snoeck Publishers, Lens and Ghent, 153.
- Thompson, R. C. (1900), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 11*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Thompson, R. C. (1901), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 12*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.

- Thompson, R. C. (1902), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 14*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Thompson, R. C. (1903), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 17*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Thompson, R. C. (1904a), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 18*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Thompson, R. C. (1904b), *Cuneiform Texts from Babylonian Tablets in the British Museum. Part 19*, Trustees of the British Museum, London.
- Thomsen, M.-L. (1984), *The Sumerian Language. An Introduction to its History and Grammatical Structure*, Akademisk Forlag, Copenhagen, Mesopotamia 10.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1902), “Notice sur la troisième collection de tablettes découvertes par M. de Sarzec à Tello”, *RA* 5, 67–102.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1903), *Recueil de Tablettes Chaldéennes*, Ernest Leroux, Paris.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1907), *Die sumerischen und akkadischen Königsinschriften*, Hinrichs, Leipzig.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1910), *Texts de l'époque d'Agadé*, Ernest Leroux, Paris, ITT 1.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1922), *Tablettes d'Uruk à l'usage des prêtres du Temple d'Anu au temps des Séleucides*, Geuthner, Paris, TCL 6.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1925), *Les Cylindres de Goudéa*, Paul Geuthner, Paris, TCL 8.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1926), *Tome I. Lettres et Contrats de l'Époque de la Première Dynastie Babylonienne*, Paul Geuthner, Paris, TCL 11.
- Thureau-Dangin, F. (1928), *Tablettes Cappadociennes*, Paul Geuthner, Paris, TCL 14.
- Tischler, J. (2001), *Hethitisches Handwörterbuch. Mit dem Wortschatz der Nachbarsprachen*, Institut für Sprachen und Literaturen der Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck.
- Tischler, J. (2016a), *Hethitisches Etymologisches Glossar* (mit Beiträgen von Günter Neumann und Erich Neu), Teil IV. Lieferung 16 W-Z, Institut für Sprachen und Literatur der Universität Innsbruck, Innsbruck, Innsbrucker Beiträge zur Sprachwissenschaft 20.
- Tischler, J. (2016b), *Vocabulaire Hittite y compris Louvite, Palaïte, Akkadien et Sumérien*, Peeters, Leuven, *Lettres Orientales et Classiques* 20.
- Tonietti, M. V. (1988), “La figura del nar nei testi di Ebla. Ipotesi per una cronologia delle liste di nomi presenti nei testi economici”, *QuadSem* 15, 79–119.
- Tonietti, M. (1989), “Aggiornamento alla cronologia dei nar”, *QuadSem* 16, 117–129.

- Tonietti, M. V. (1997a), “Musik. A. II. In Ebla”, *RIA* 8 7/8, 482–483.
- Tonietti, M. V. (1997b), “NAR directly connected to a temple in Ebla”, *NABU* 1997/2, 37–38.
- Tonietti, M. V. (2010), “Singers in the Ebla Texts: a Third Millennium local source for Northern Syria”, in: Pruzsinszky, R. and Shehata, D. (ed.), *Musiker und Tradierung: Studien zur Rolle von Musikern bei der Verschriftlichung und Tradierung von literarischen Werken*, Vienna, LIT Verlag, Wien Offene Orientalistik 8, 67–93.
- Tonietti, M. V. (2018), “The First Ancient Near Eastern Written Sources on Musician’s Activity and Performance: the Ebla Archives - A Glance at the 3rd Millennium BCE Syrian Evidence”, in: García-Ventura, A., Tavolieri, C. and Verderame, L. (ed.), *The Study of Musical Performance in Antiquity. Archaeology and Written Sources*, Cambridge Scholars Publishing, Newcastle upon Tyne, 9–38.
- Tsouparopoulou, Ch. (2013), “Killing and Skinning Animals in the Ur III Period: The Puzris-Dagan (Drehem) Office Managing of Dead Animals and Slaughter By-Products”, *AoF* 40/1, 150–182.
- Turnbull, H. (1972), “The Origin of the Long-Necked Lute”, *GSJ* 25, 58–66.
- Uchitel, A. (1985), *Mycenaean and Near Eastern Economic Archives*, PhD. Dissertation, University College of London, London.
- Vacín, L. (2011), *Šulgi of Ur: Life, Deeds, Ideology and Legacy of a Mesopotamian Ruler as Reflected Primarily in Literary Texts*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of the Languages and Cultures of Near and Middle East, School of Oriental and African Studies, University of London, London [Online document] <https://www.academia.edu/1122531/%C5%A0ulgi_of_Ur_Life_Deeds_Ideology_and_Legacy_of_a_Mesopotamian_Ruler_As_Reflected_Primarily_in_Literary_Texts_PhD_diss._SOAS_University_of_London_2011_329_pp_> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- van de Mierop, M. (2016), *Philosophy before the Greeks: the pursuit of truth in Ancient Babylonia*, Princeton University Press, Princeton.
- van der Meer, P. E. (1938), *Syllabaries A, B¹ and B with Miscellaneous Lexicographical Texts from the Herbert Weld Collection*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, OECT 4.
- van Dijk, J. J. A. (1987), *Literarische Texte aus Babylon*, Akademie Verlag, Berlin, VS 24.

- van de Mieroop, M. (1987), *Sumerian Administrative Documents from the Reigns of Išbi-Erra and Šū-ilisu*, Yale University Press, New Haven (Connecticut) and London, BIN 10.
- van Driel, G. (1998), “The Care of the Elderly: The Neo-Babylonian Period”, in: Stol, M. and Vleeming, S. P. (eds.), *The Care of the Elderly in the Ancient Near East*, Brill, Leiden, *Studies in the History and Culture of the Ancient Near East* 14, 161–197.
- van Driel, G. (2003–2005), “Pfründe (Prebends)”, *RIA* 10, 518–524.
- van Lerberghe, K. (1986), *Old Babylonian Legal and Administrative Texts from Philadelphia*, Peeters, Louvain, OLA 21.
- van Wyk, S. (2018), “Inheritance Feuds in the Ur-Pabilsaga Archive from Old Babylonian Nippur”, *Journal for Semitics* 27/2, 1–27.
- Vanstiphout, H. L. J. (1999), “De Enki-Administratie, of waarom de wereld zo in elkaar zit”, *Revue belge de philologie et d’histoire* 77/1, 5–51.
- Vedeler, H. T. (2002), *The HAR.GUD Commentary and its Relationship to the HAR-ra = hubullu Lexical List*, Unpublished Master Thesis, Graduate School, Yale University, New Haven (Connecticut), [Online document] https://www.academia.edu/7307832/THE_HAR.GUD_COMMENTARY_AND_ITS_RELATIONSHIP_TO_THE_HAR-RA_HUBULLU_LEXICAL_LIST [Last search on 05/10/2018].
- Velázquez Muñoz, J. (2013), “Guarniciones y Escoltas Militares. La Seguridad en los Caminos Reales Aqueménidas”, *Studia* 19, 13–29.
- Veldhuis, N. C. (1996), “A Nippur Emesal Vocabulary”, *ASJ* 18, 229–235.
- Veldhuis, N. Ch. (1997), *Elementary Education at Nippur. The Lists of Trees and Wooden Objects*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Groningen Universiteit, [Online document] [https://www.rug.nl/research/portal/publications/elementary-education-at-nippur-the-lists-of-trees-and-wooden-objects\(d7539f72-9851-4b83-841f-886ef19cb1be\).html](https://www.rug.nl/research/portal/publications/elementary-education-at-nippur-the-lists-of-trees-and-wooden-objects(d7539f72-9851-4b83-841f-886ef19cb1be).html) [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Veldhuis, N. Ch. (1997/1998), “The Sur₉-Priest, the instrument ^{giš}Al-gar-sur₉, and the Forms and Uses of a Rare Sign”, *AfO* 44/45, 115–128.
- Veldhuis, N. Ch. (2000), “Sumerian Proverbs in Their Curricular Context”, *JAOS* 120/3, 383–399.
- Veldhuis, N. Ch. (2014), *History of the Cuneiform Lexical Tradition*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, *Guides to the Mesopotamian Textual Record* 6.

- Veldhuis, N. (2017), “Words and Grammar: Two Old Babylonian Lists”, in: Feliu, L.; Karahashi, F. and Rubio, G. (eds.), *The First Ninety Years. A Sumerian Celebration in Honor of Miguel Civil*, Walter de Gruyter, Boston/Berlin, SANER 12, 363–395.
- Veenhof, K. R. (2005), *Letters in the Louvre. Transliterated and Translated*, Brill, Leiden and Boston, AbB 14.
- Veenhof, K. R. (2012), “On the Old Babylonian texts in YOS 15”, *NABU* 2012/2, n. 28, 38-31.
- Visicato, G. (1995), *The Bureaucracy of Šuruppak. Administrative Centres, Central Offices, Intermediate Structures and Hierarchies in the Economic Documentation of Fara*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, ALASPM 10.
- Visicato, G. and Westenholz, A. (2010), *Early Dynastic and Early Sargonic Tablets from Adab in the Cornell University Collections*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS 11.
- Vitale, R. G. (1980), “La Tablette ‘Musicale’ H 6 (RS 15.30+15.49+17.367)”, *Annales Archéologiques Syriennes* 29–30, 41–62.
- Vitale, R. G. (1982), “La Musique Suméro-Accadienne”, *UF* 14, 241–263.
- Volk, K. (1989), *Die Balag-Komposition úru àm-ma ir-ra-bi*, Harrasowitz, Wiesbaden, FAOS 18.
- Volk, K. (1994), “Improvisierte Musik im alten Mesopotamien?”, in: Fähndrich, W. (ed.), *Improvisation II*, Winterthur, 160–202.
- Volk, K. (1995), *Inanna und Šukaletuda. Zur historisch-politischen Deutung eines sumerischen Literaturwerkes*, Harrasowitz, Wiesbaden, SANTAG 3.
- Volk, K. (2000), “Musik: Alter Orient”, *Der Neue Pauly* 8, 516–517.
- Volk, K. (2006), “Musikalische Praxis und Theorie im Alten Orient”, in: Volk, K.; Zamminer, F.; Floros, C.; Harmon, R.; Richter, L. and Haas, M. (ed.), *Von Mythos zur Fachdisziplin: Antike und Byzanz*, Wissenschaftliche Buchgesellschaft, Darmstadt, 3–46.
- Volk, K. (2011), “Über Bildung und Ausbildung in Babylonien am Anfang des 2. Jahrtausends v. Chr.”, *OrNS* 80/3, 269-299.
- Volk, K. (2011–2013), “Streitgespräch”, *RIA* 13, 214–222.
- Volk, K. (forthcoming), *Sumerische literarische Texte in der Schøyen Collection*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), CUSAS XX.

- von Lieven, A. (2008), “Native and Foreign Elements in the Musical Life of Ancient Egypt”, in Both, A. A.; Eichmann, R.; Hickmann, E.; Koch, L.-C. (eds.), *Herausforderungen und Ziele der Musikarchäologie, Vorträge des 5. Symposiums der Internationalen Studiengruppe Musikarchäologie im Ethnologischen Museum der Staatlichen Museen zu Berlin, 19.-23. September 2006, Studien zur Musikarchäologie 6*; Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 22, 155–160.
- von Soden, W. (1959–1981), *Akkadisches Handwörterbuch*, 3 volumes, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- von Soden, W. (1988), “Musikinstrumente in Mari”, *NABU* 1988/3, n. 59, 42–43.
- von Soden, W. (1995), *Grundriss der akkadischen Grammatik, 3., ergänzte Auflage* (unter Mitarbeit von Werner R. Mayer), Pontifical Biblical Institute, Rome, *AnOr* 33.
- von Weiher, E. (1983), *Spätbabylonische Texte aus Uruk. Teil II*, Gebr. Mann Verlag, Berlin, *ADFU* 10.
- von Weiher, E. (1988), *Spätbabylonische Texte aus Uruk. Teil III*, Gebr. Mann Verlag, Berlin, *ADFU* 12.
- Waetzoldt, H. (1972), *Untersuchungen zur neusumerischen Textilindustrie*, Centro per le Antichità e la Storia dell’Arte del Vicino Oriente, Rome, *Studi Economici e Tecnologici* 1.
- Waetzoldt, H. (1975), “(Review) Gertrud FARBER-FLÜGE, *Der Mythos Inanna und Enki unter besonderer Berücksichtigung der Liste der me*. Rome, Biblical Institute Press, 1973 (8vo. XV + 256 S.) = *Studia Pohl* 10. Preis: Lit. 2.800; Doll. 4.00”, *BiOr* 32, 382-384.
- Waetzoldt, H. (1989), “Der Schreiber als Lehrer in Mesopotamien”, in: Prinz von Hohenzollern, J. G. and Liedtke, M. (eds.), *Schreiber, Magister, Lehrer: Zur Geschichte und Funktion eines Berufsstandes*, Bad Heilbrunn, *Schriftreihe zum Bayerischen Schulmuseum in Ichenhausen*, 833–50.
- Waley, A. (1960), *The Book of Songs. The Ancient Chinese Classic of Poetry*, Grove Press, New York.
- Walls, N. (2007), “The Origins of the Disabled Body. Disability in Ancient Mesopotamia”, in Avalos, H.; Melcher, S. J. and Schipper, J. (eds.), *This Aabled Body. Rethinking Disabilities in Biblical Studies*, Society of Biblical Literature, Atlanta, *SBLSS* 25, 13–30.

- Wee, J. Z. (2017), “Pan-astronomical Hermeneutics and the Arts of the Lamentation Priest”, *ZA* 107/2. 236–260.
- Weidner, E. F. (1951–1952), “Das Vokabular Martin A”, *Afo* 7, 271–275.
- Weidner, E. (1967), *Gestirn-Darstellungen auf babylonischen Tontafeln*, Böhlau in Kommission, Vienna.
- Weissmann, J. S. (1964), “Hungary: Recent Advances in Folk Music Research”, *Ethnomusicology*, 8/1, 49–53.
- Wegner, I. (2007), *Hurritisch. Eine Einführung 2., überarbeitete Auflage*, Harrassowitz, Wiesbaden.
- West, M. L. (1994), “The Babylonian Musical Notation and the Hurrian Melodic Texts”, *Music & Letters* 75 n. 2, 161–179.
- Westenholz, A. (1974), “Old Sumerian and Old Akkadian Texts in the National Museum of Copenhagen”, *JCS* 26, 71–80.
- Westenholz, A. (1975), *Old Sumerian and Old Akkadian Texts in Philadelphia Chiefly from Nippur*, Undena Publications, Malibu, BiMes 1.
- Westenholz, A. (1987), *Old Sumerian and Old Akkadian Texts in Philadelphia, Part II: The ‘Akkadian’ Texts, the Enlilemaba Texts, and the Onion Archive*, The Carsten Niebuhr Institute of Ancient Near Eastern Studies, Copenhagen, Carsten Niebuhr Publications 3.
- Westenholz, A. (2010), “Enki and Ninmah: An Interpretation”, in: Horowitz, W.; Gabbay, U. and Vukosavović, F. (eds.), *A woman of valor: Jerusalem Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Honor of Joan Goodnick Westenholz*, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Madrid, BPOA 8, 201–204.
- Westenholz, J. G. (2005), “Sing a Song for Šulgi”, in: Sefati, Y.; Artzi, P.; Cohen, C.; Eichler, B. and Hurowitz, V. A. (ed.), *“An experienced scribe who neglects nothing”*. *Ancient Near Eastern Studies in Honor of Jacob Klein*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland), 343–373.
- Westenholz, J. G. (2013), “In the service of the gods: the ministering clergy”, in: Crawford, H. (ed.), *The Sumerian World*, Routledge, London, 246–276.
- Wilcke, C. (1976a), “Formale Gesichtspunkte in der sumerischen Literatur”, in: Lieberman, S. J. (ed.), *Sumerological Studies in Honor of Thorkild Jacobsen*, Oriental Institute of Chicago, Chicago and London, AS 20, 205–316.
- Wilcke, C. (1976b), *Kollationen zu den sumerischen literarischen Texten aus Nippur in der Hilprecht-Sammlung Jena*, Akademie-Verlag, Berlin, ASAW 65/4.

- Wilcke, C. (1987), “Die Inschriftenfunde der 7. und 8. Campagne” in: Hrouda, B. (ed.), *Isin – Išān Baḫrīyāt III. Die Ergebnisse der Ausgrabungen 1983-1984*, Akademische Verlag, München, BAW NF 94.
- Wilcke, C. (1988), “Anmerkungen zu Konjugationspräfix /i/- und zur These vom silbischen Charakter der sumerischen Morpheme anhand neusumerischer Verbalformen, beginnend mit ì-ib-, ì-im- und ì-in-”, *ZA* 78, 1–48.
- Wilcke, C. (1998), “Care of Elderly in Mesopotamia in the Third Millennium B.C.”, in: Stol, M. and Vleeming, S. P. (ed.), *The Care of the Elderly in the Ancient Near East*, Brill, Leiden, Boston and Köln, SHCANE 14, 23–58.
- Wilcke, C. (2002), “Konflikte und ihre Bewältigung in Elternhaus und Schule im Alten Orient”, in: Lux, R. (ed.), *Schau auf die Kleinen... Das Kind in Religion, Kirche und Gesellschaft*, Evanelische Verlagsanstalt, Leipzig, 10–31.
- Wilcke, C. (2005), “The Verb si - sa2: A Diachronic List of Datable Occurrences Grouped according to the Number of Participants to the Action”, *ASJ* 22, 279–301.
- Wilcke, C. (2007), “Vom altorientalischen Blick zurück auf die Anfänge”, Angehrn, E. (ed.), *Anfang und Ursprung. Die Frage nach dem Ersten in Philosophie und Kulturwissenschaft*, Walter de Gruyter, Berlin and New York, 3–59.
- Wilson, J. (1996), *The Cylinders of Gudea. Transliteration, Translation and Index*, Butzon & Bercker Kevelaer, Neukirchen-Vluyn, AOAT 244.
- Willson Aedo, A. (1992), *Textilería mapuche, arte de mujeres*, Centro de Estudios para el Desarrollo de la Mujer, Santiago de Chile.
- Winnington-Ingram, R. P. (1985), “The origins of tragedy”, in: Easterling, P. E. and Knox, B. M. W. (ed.), *The Cambridge History of Classical Literature I. Greek Literature*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 258–262.
- Wiseman, D. J. and Black, J. A. (1996), *Literary Texts from the Temple of Nabû, British School of Archaeology in Iraq*, CTN 4.
- Witzel, M. (1922), *Der Gudea-Zylinder A: in neuer uebersetzung. Mit Kommentar. Anhang: Eridu-Hymnus*, Heinrichs, Leipzig.
- Wolfe, J. N. (2015), *ZU: The life of a Sumerian Verb in Early Mesopotamia*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Department of Near Eastern Languages and Cultures, University of California, [Online document]
<<https://escholarship.org/uc/item/6cr2r7kn>> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Woods, B. (2015), *Bodhrán: The Basics*, Fenton (Missouri), Mel Bay Publications.

- Woods, Ch. (2006), “Bilingualism, Scribal Learning, and the Death of Sumerian”, in: Sanders, S. L. (ed.), *Margins of Writing, Origins of Cultures*, Oriental Institute of the University of Chicago, Chicago (Illinois), OIS 2, 91-120.
- Woods, Ch. (2008), *The Grammar of Perspective. The Sumerian Conjugation Prefixes as a System of Voice*, Brill, Leiden, CM 32.
- Wossink, A. (2009), *Challenging Climate Change: Competition and Cooperation Among Pastoralist and Agriculturalist in Northern Mesopotamia (c. 3000-1600 BC)*, Sidestone Press, Leiden.
- Wright, J. W. (2007), ““Those Doing the Work for the Service in the House of the Lord”: 1 Chronicles 23:6-24:31 and the Sociohistorical Context of the Temple of Yahweh in Jerusalem in the Late Persian/Early Hellenistic Period”, in: Lipschits, O., Knoppers, G. N. and Albertz, R. (ed.), *Judah and the Judeans in the Fourth Century B.C.E.*, Eisenbrauns, Winona Lake (Indiana), 361–384.
- Wulstan, D. (1971), “The Earliest Musical Notation”, *Music & Letters* 52 n. 4, 365–382.
- Wunsch, C. (1997), “Die Jugensünden eines Babyloniers aus gutem Hause”, *AoF* 24/2, 231-241.
- Wunsch, C. (2003), *Urkunden zum Ehe-, Vermögens- und Erbrecht aus verschiedenen neubabylonischen Archiven*, Islet, Dresden, BA 2.
- Wunsch, C. (2003-2004), “Findelkinder und Adoption nach neubabylonischen Quellen”, *AfO* 50, 174–244.
- Yildiz, F. and Gomi, T. (1988), *Die Puzriš-Dagan-Texte der Istanbuler Archäologischen Museen II: Nr. 726-1379*, Franz Steiner, Stuttgart, FAOS 16.
- Yildiz, F. and Ozaki, T. (2000), *Die Umma-Texte aus den Archäologischen Museen zu Istanbul. Band V (Nr. 3001-3500)*, CDL Press, Bethesda (Maryland).
- Zemp, H. (1978), ““Are’are Classification of Musical Types and Instruments”, *Ethnomusicology* 22/1, 37–67.
- Zgoll, A. (1997), *Der Rechtsfall der En-ḫedu-Ana im Lied nin-me-šara*, Ugarit-Verlag, Münster, AOAT 246.
- Zgoll, A. (2012), “Welt, Götter und Menschen in der Schöpfungsentwürfen des antiken Mesopotamien”, in: Schmid, K. (ed.), *Schöpfung*, Mohr Siebeck, Stuttgart, Themen der Theologie 4, 17–70.
- Zhi, Y. (1989), *Sargonic Inscriptions from Adab*, Institute for the History of Ancient Civilizations, PPAC 1.

- Ziegler, N. (1996), “Ein Bittbrief eines Händlers”, in: Ambros, A. A. and Köhbach, M. (eds.), *Festschrift für Hans Hirsch zum 65. Geburtstag gewidmet von seinen Freunden, Kollegen und Schülern*, WZKM 86, 479–488.
- Ziegler, N. (1999), *La Population Féminine des Palais d'après les Archives Royales de Mari. Le Harem de Zimrî-Lîm*, SEPOA, Paris, FM 4, Mémoires de NABU 5.
- Ziegler, N. (2005), “Les vaisseaux sanguins et *Enûma eliš* VI: 5”, *JMC* 5, 4–5.
- Ziegler, N. (2006a), “Die ‚internationale‘ Welt der Musik anhand der Briefe aus Mari (Syrien, 18. Jh. V. Chr.)”, in: Hickmann, E.; Both, A. A. and Eichmann, R. (ed.), *Studien zur Musikarchäologie 5. Musikarchäologie im Kontext. Archäologische Befunde, historische Zusammenhänge, soziokulturelle Beziehungen*, Marie Leidorf, Rahden, *Orient Archäologie* 20, 345-354.
- Ziegler, N. (2006b), “Les musiciens aveugles”, *Dossiers d'Archéologie. La Musique au Proche-Orient Ancien* 310, 39.
- Ziegler, N. (2007), *Les musiciens et la musique d'après les archives de Mari*, Société d'Études du Proche-Orient Ancien, Paris, FM 9; Mémoires de NABU 10.
- Ziegler, N. (2011), “Music. The Work of Professionals”, in: Radner, K. and Robson, E. (ed.), *The Oxford Handbook of Cuneiform Culture*, Oxford University Press, Oxford, 288–312.
- Ziegler, N. (2012), “Les rois et leurs musiciens en Mésopotamie”, in: Schettino, M. T. and Pittia, S. (ed.), *Les sons du pouvoir dans les mondes anciens: actes du colloque international de l'Université de La Rochelle: 25-27 novembre 2010*, Presses Universitaires de Franche-Comté, Besançon, 25–46.
- Ziegler, N. (2013), “Le statut social des musiciens à l'époque paléo-babylonienne”, in: Emerit, S. (ed.), *Le statut du musicien dans la Méditerranée ancienne: Égypte, Mésopotamie, Grèce, Rome: actes de la table ronde internationale tenue à Lyon, Maison de l'Orient et de la Méditerranée, les 4 et 5 juillet 2008*, Institut Français d'Archéologie Orientale, Cairo, IFAO Bibliothèque d'Étude 159, 47–68.
- Ziegler, N. (2015), “Femmes inspiratrices en Mésopotamie: les musiciennes de cour”, *Journal asiatique* 303, 197–204.
- Ziegler, N. (2017), “Savoirs et Traditions Musicales de l'Orient ancien“, in: Emerit, S.; Guichard, H.; Jeammet, V.; Perrot, S.; Thomas, A.; Vendries, Chr.; Vincent, A. and Ziegler, N. (ed.), *Musiques! Échos de l'Antiquité*, Musée du Louvre-Lens and Snoeck Publishers, Lens and Ghent, 30–43.

- Ziegler, N. and Langlois, A.-I. (2017), *Les toponymes paléo-babyloniens de la Haute-Mésopotamie. La Haute-Mésopotamie au I^{er} millénaire av. J.-C. - MTT I/1 / Obermesopotamien im 2. Jt. v. Chr. - MTT I/1*, Collège de France, Paris.
- Zimmern, H. (1912), *Sumerische Kultlieder aus altbabylonischer Zeit. Erste Reihe*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, VS 2.
- Zimmern, H. (1913), *Sumerische Kultlieder aus altbabylonischer Zeit. Zweite Reihe*, Hinrichs, Leipzig, VAS 10.
- Zimmermann, L.-S. (2017), “What was life like as a female singer 3400 ago?”, *Journal of the History of Ideas*, [Online document] <<https://jhiblog.org/2017/09/20/what-was-life-like-as-a-female-singer-3400-years-ago/>> [Last search the 12/10/2019].
- Zorzi, N. d. (2011), *Divinazione e Intertestualità. La serie divinatoria Shumma izbu e il suo orizzonte culturale*, Unpublished PhD Dissertation, Università Ca’Foscari Venezia, [Online document] <http://dspace.unive.it/bitstream/handle/10579/1117/tesi_de-zorzi_venezia.pdf?sequence=2> [Last search on 12/10/2019].
- Zólyomi, G. (2003), “Five newly identified literary fragments from various publications”, *NABU* 2003/3, 97–99.

10. ABSTRACTS AND CONCLUSIONS IN OTHER LANGUAGES

10.1. Resumen en Castellano

Se conocen¹⁵⁶⁷ muchos términos en los textos en sumerio y acadio designando los instrumentos, músicos, composiciones y algunos aspectos de la interpretación musical en Mesopotamia. Sin embargo, ¿hubo alguna vez un término en aquella cultura que designara todas aquellas facetas musicales en su totalidad? ¿Hubo alguna palabra para “Música” en Mesopotamia como, por ejemplo, en nuestra cultura occidental?

De acuerdo a los principales investigadores sobre Música en Mesopotamia, no hay ningún término sumerio o acadio para “Música”. Especialmente, no existió ningún término referido a una combinación de sonidos como sí pasa con nuestro término “Música”. Los términos más cercanos a dicho término de “Música” serían el sumerio **nam-nar** y el acadio *nārūtu(m)*. Sin embargo, designarían tan solo algunos aspectos musicales como la profesión de un músico o la habilidad para hacer Música. En todo caso, tan solo una pequeña parte de los textos conteniendo **nam-nar** o *nārūtu(m)* han sido estudiados en el pasado por quienes hicieron las afirmaciones comentadas anteriormente.

En consecuencia, este estudio pretende analizar todas las alusiones conocidas hasta hoy en los textos mesopotámicos a los términos **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* a fin de probar o desmontar este consenso científico. La hipótesis de esta Tesis Doctoral es que **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* significaron “Música” y, por lo tanto, existiría realmente una palabra para “Música” en Mesopotamia. Esto tendría importantes consecuencias para las (posibles) futuras investigaciones acerca del concepto mesopotámico de la Música. Ciertamente, de acuerdo al pensamiento mesopotámico, ninguna cosa o idea que no tuviera un nombre existía realmente. Esto se puede comprobar acudiendo a las primeras líneas del Poema Babilónico de la Creación, el *Enūma Eliš*. Allí se puede leer que, en el origen del Universo, los Cielos y la Tierra aún no habían recibido un nombre. La acción de darles un nombre al Cielo y la Tierra es, como se puede imaginar, una forma de referirse al momento en el que comenzaron a existir dentro del Universo.

¹⁵⁶⁷ El siguiente texto intenta cumplir con los requisitos establecidos para toda Tesis Doctoral de la Universidad de Granada no redactada principalmente en lengua castellana.

A priori **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* podrían significar “Música” debido a su composición en dos partes. Por una parte, ambos términos poseen una partícula (el sumerio **nam-**, el acadio *-ūtu*) para crear sustantivos abstractos. Por otra parte, ambos términos hacen referencia a un músico (el **nar/nāru(m)**), esto es, alguien que podía tocar varios tipos de instrumentos y/o entonar varios tipos de cantos. En otras lenguas del Antiguo Oriente (tales como el hitita, el hebreo o el egipcio) los términos para “Música” no tienen ninguna partícula que les permita ser considerados como abstractos. Por otra parte, dichos términos suelen estar referidos solo a un tipo de instrumento o canto. Este es el caso del vocablo hitita *zinar*, quien podría haberse referido solo a la música de una lira. Además, Grecia y Roma no fueron las únicas culturas de la Antigüedad que tuvieron un término para “Música”, sino que otras culturas antiguas también los tuvieron, como India o China.

Para demostrar la hipótesis de este estudio, se presentan aquí 70 textos comprendidos entre el Período Paleo-acadio y el Período Selúcida Tardío con una transliteración, traducción y notas filológicas, así como son analizados mediante un comentario. Para las transliteraciones de esas ediciones se han consultado las copias y fotos de las tablillas cuneiformes originales. Algunas de ellas han sido, además, colacionadas en sus actuales museos de acogida. Cuando se tenían varias variantes para una misma línea, dichas variantes se presentan en las ediciones como en una partitura musical siguiendo convenciones asiriológicas. Los comentarios son principalmente filológicos, pero también hay comentarios musicales, puesto que **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)*, además de otros términos musicales de los textos estudiados, tienen una naturaleza musical. En este sentido, se combinan tres disciplinas en este estudio: la Asiriología (para el marco histórico-cultural y la metodología filológica), la Musicología (para el tema y los comentarios) y la Historia, puestos todos los fragmentos son presentados aquí según su procedencia cronológica y geográfica.

Después de una introducción, la cual se ha resumido brevemente aquí, el análisis de los 70 textos se extiende a lo largo de cinco capítulos. El primer capítulo lidia con ocho textos del Tercer Milenio a. n. e.: dos listas paleo-acadias de raciones con inseguras referencias a **nam-nar** (Texto1–2), un texto administrativo muy fragmentado de la Segunda Dinastía de Lagaš (Texto 3), un fragmento de los *Cilindros de Gudea* (Texto 4), dos textos sobre músicas-tejedoras de Ur III (Textos 5–6) y dos cartas de Awal (Tell al-Sulaima) situadas en la transición al Período Paleobabilónico que hablan sobre *nārūtum* y *kala'ūtum* (Textos 7–8).

El segundo capítulo trata, por una parte, de **nam-nar** en los textos del *curriculum* elemental de los escribas. Los textos de dicho currículo comentado aquí son, en primer lugar, algunos extractos de las listas léxicas *Proto-lu2* (líneas 590–591 = Texto 9), *Proto-izi* (líneas II 227–231 = Texto 10) y *Niḫ2-ga* (versión monolingüe, líneas 73–75 = Texto 11). Más tarde se presentan dos contratos-modelo (textos para aprender la práctica administrativa) (Textos 12–13) y *Proverbios* 3.150 (Texto 14). Este último texto es un ejemplo de los textos que los escribas utilizaban para iniciarse en los (más complejos) textos literarios sumerios. Por otra parte, este capítulo lidia con varios documentos de compraventa de prebendas de templos (Textos 15–21). Algunos de ellos (Textos 19a–21) han sido publicados hace poco.

El tercer capítulo analiza el término **nam-nar** en los textos literarios sumerios. Los primeros extractos de aquel capítulo proceden del texto de disputa llamado *Enkiheḡal* y *Enkitalu* (líneas 94–99, 110–113¹⁵⁶⁸ = Textos 22–23). Luego se comenta un extracto del texto sapiencial *El Padre y su hijo maleducado* (líneas 107–112 = Textos 24–25). Las narraciones mitológicas *Enki y Ninmaḡ* (líneas b 26–29 = Texto 27) e *Inanna y Enki* (líneas I v 33–34 y II v 47–52 = Textos 30–31) se comentan en tercer lugar. En el análisis de *Enki y Ninmaḡ* se presenta también una pequeña edición y comentario del texto administrativo llamado aquí TJA, p. 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna 23.10.02 (?)) (Texto 28). En cuarto lugar se analizan fragmentos de los siguientes textos de la poesía de alabanza real: *Ur-Namma A* (Texto 31), *Šulgi B* (Textos 33–36), *Šulgi E* (Textos 26 y 32), *Šulgi CC* (Texto 37, con un comentario sobre la *Elegía por la muerte de Nannā* = Texto 38) e *Išmē-Dagān A + V* (Textos 39–40). Finalmente se estudia aquí el Texto 41. Este texto ha sido publicado hace muy poco y su subtipología literaria es desconocida.

Las referencias a *nārūtum* en las cartas de Mari durante el Período Paleobabilónico son comentadas en el Cuarto Capítulo. Los textos son ordenados de acuerdo a su procedencia del reinado de Šamšī-Addu (Textos 42–52) o Zimrī-Līm (Textos 53–54). Sin embargo, una última sección de este capítulo reúne textos de ambos reinados que tienen la expresión *enūt narutim* (Textos 55–57). Este *enūt narutim* (“instrumento de Música”) es identificado en este estudio con un tipo de laúd en Mari en el Período Paleobabilónico.

¹⁵⁶⁸ Con la cortesía de Manuel Ceccarelli, quien actualmente está preparando la *editio princeps* completa de este texto. En todo caso, el material que nos ha cedido ha sido revisado con los métodos usuales en este estudio, incluyendo las colaciones de algunos manuscritos conteniendo nuestros pasajes.

No se ha encontrado por el momento ningún texto mesobabilónico o asirio con **nam-nar** o *nārūtu(m)*. Hemos estudiado algunos textos inéditos (CBS 7826 y 8500, UM 29-15-21 y 29-15-211) con el fin de encontrar alguna posible nueva referencia a *nārūtu*. Sin embargo, esas tablillas están solo referidas al músico (*nāru*). En este sentido, el último capítulo trata sobre el Primer Milenio a. C.

En primer lugar se estudian tres textos neo-asirios: un texto lexical que contiene la expresión *enūtu ša nārūti* (“instrumento de Música”) y dos referencias a **šer₃ nam-nar** (literalmente “composición musical para ser cantada”, un tipo de canción) (Texto 59–60). Luego se analizan algunos textos de compraventa del oficio del músico y sus prebendas procedentes de época neobabilónica y aqueménide (Textos 61–66). Finalmente se analizan varios textos seléucidas: una referencia indirecta a una prebenda con *nārūtu* (Texto 68), un comentario astrológico (Texto 69) que contiene la expresión “festival musical” (**IZIN NAM.NAR**) y dos referencias a **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* como “*corpus* de textos del músico” (Texto 70 y posiblemente el 67).

Después de haber realizado este análisis, la primera conclusión de este estudio es que es complicado decir algo concreto y/o seguro sobre **nam-nar** o *nārūtu(m)*. Esto concierne tanto a los argumentos a favor de la hipótesis de este estudio aquellos como en contra. Las causas de esto son el número actual de textos que tienen **nam-nar** o *nārūtu(m)*, así como su estado de conservación además de los problemas particulares que tiene cada uno de los textos de este estudio. Se hace una explicación para cada período a continuación.

En el período paleoacadio (textos 1–2) **lugal-nam nar** (“Lugalnam el músico”) y **sipa-nam nar** (“Sipanam el músico”) también se podían leer como **lugal-nam-nar** (“rey (de la) Música”) y **sipa-nam-nar** (“pastor (de la) Música”). La segunda opción tiene sentido de acuerdo a algunos otros nombres personales documentados en textos de la época (por ejemplo, Lugal-namzitara). Sin embargo, puesto que **lugal-nam(-)nar** y **sipa-nam(-)nar** son conocidos tan solo por meras listas de raciones, es complicado decir algo sobre posibles referencias (o no) a **nam-nar** como “Música” en aquellos textos.

En la Segunda Dinastía de Lagaš los *Cilindros de Gudea* (Text 4) hacían referencia a **nam-nar** como “Música” pero otras referencias a aquel término en textos de la época (Texto 3) eran mucho más inciertas. Con respecto al Período de Ur III, hay muchos textos con referencias a los músicos (**nar**) pero solo una referencia segura a **nam-nar** (Texto 5). Otras referencias a **nam-nar** en el Período de Ur III (Texto 6) son meramente hipotéticas. Nuestras primeras referencias a *nārūtum* (Textos 7–8) podrían proceder del momento de

tránsito al Segundo Milenio, pero su datación precisa ha sido reiteradamente discutida en el pasado.

Los textos paleobabilónicos del Segundo Milenio contienen muchas referencias a **nam-nar** y *nārūtum*, pero son problemáticos para nosotros en varios sentidos, especialmente en el caso de los textos de la Baja Mesopotamia. Por ejemplo, en referencia a los textos literarios que tienen **nam-nar**, desconocemos su fecha y proveniencia originales así como sus autores por el momento. Un contexto más preciso nos ayudaría a comparar estos textos con los textos contemporáneos de tipo legal con **nam-nar**. Ciertamente, en aquellos textos **nam-nar** no significa “Música” sino “profesión del músico (**nar**)”, aunque el significado de “Música” para la referencia a *nārūtum* en el Texto 28 (otro texto legal) podría tener sentido.

Esta dicotomía podría resolverse examinando los textos paleobabilónicos de Mari, puesto que todas las referencias a *nārūtum* en los textos de aquella ciudad son contenidas en cartas. Esto contrasta con la situación del Sur de Mesopotamia, donde las referencias a **nam-nar** están contenidas en textos de hasta tres tipologías distintas: legales, literarios y escolares. En todo caso, hay una larga distancia entre Mari (Norte de Mesopotamia) y el Sur de Mesopotamia. Además, Mari es un *unicum* en el Norte de Mesopotamia, porque los textos paleo-asirios solo hacen referencia al término *narūtum* (que designa un tipo de malta) y los textos neo-asirios con **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* son a menudo fragmentarios.

Nuestro mayor problema por el momento es, sin embargo, la transición del Segundo al Primer Milenio, puesto que no se ha encontrado ningún texto meso-asirio o babilónico. El análisis de algunos textos inéditos tampoco ha dado los resultados esperados, pues esos textos solo contienen referencias a los músicos (*nāru*).

Los textos legales neobabilónicos y aqueménides del Primer Milenio hacen referencia a *nārūtu* como “profesión del Músico” en dos sentidos: por una parte, como músico de una divinidad, por otra parte, aunque menos frecuentemente, como músico que domina un tipo de instrumento o canto. La lectura e interpretación de los textos literarios es, no obstante, mucho más compleja en varios aspectos.

En primer lugar, las diferentes lecturas e interpretaciones de EZEN NAM-LUL en nuestro Texto 67 (**šer₃ nam-nar**, ***šer₃ nam-lul** o **kešda nam-nar**). Luego, ¿podemos leer el sumerograma NAM.NAR del comentario astrológico aquí denominado Texto 69 ciertamente como *nārūtu*? ¿Podría ser realmente una referencia a *nigūtum*? Finalmente, hay varios problemas en nuestro Texto 70. Por una parte, se puede leer el signo BA o NA para obtener *bārūtu* o *nārūtu*. Por otra parte, es complicado definir *nārūtu* como “corpus

textual del *nāru*” puesto que ningún texto por el momento pertenece oficialmente a dicho *corpus*. Hay que prestar atención también a la fecha de estos textos. El significado de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* podría haber cambiado con respecto a épocas anteriores.

En todo caso, el significado de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* en la mayoría de los textos podría ser “Música”. A veces ese significado es adecuado ya que no tenemos suficiente información acerca de los músicos mencionados en dichos textos. En ese sentido, no se puede proponer ninguna traducción más concreta para ambos términos. Este es el caso de nuestros textos administrativos 5–6 y 28, pero también el 41, que tiene una referencia a **nam-nar** en un contexto muy incierto. En esos textos una traducción de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* por “Música” puede ser mejor que una más específica.

En otros casos la traducción de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* como Música es apropiada porque esos términos hacen referencia a varios instrumentos, cantos o músicos. Ese es el caso de nuestro Texto 12, un contrato-modelo. Como parte de los contenidos de ese texto, una persona aprenderá varios aspectos musicales: el **asila**₃ (una especie de grito de alegría o júbilo) de los himnos **tige**_x y **a-da-ab** y cómo aprender a tocar el ^{neš}**tigidla**_x (un tipo de laúd). Se puede hacer también referencia al Texto 22, un extracto de *Enkihegal* y *Enkitalu* (líneas 94–99). Allí se refieren junto con **nam-nar** varios elementos de la Música vocal (por ejemplo, los cantos **en**₃-**du**) e instrumental (por ejemplo, el arpa angular **za**₃-**mi**₂). La traducción de *nārūtu* como “Música” es interesante por similares razones para los Textos 44–52 de Mari.

Otros textos sitúan **nam-nar** y *nārūtu* en un contexto donde aún podríamos usar la palabra “Música”. Un ejemplo son los textos 33 y 49, en los cuales los reyes Šulgi e Ismē-Dagān se jactan de haberse dedicado a la Música. En nuestro Texto 41, un hipotético estudiante dice que quiere estudiar Música. También puede ser el caso del Texto 46 procedente de Mari. En aquel texto, el rey Šamšī-Addu dice que la Música (*nārūtum*) ha sido “destruida” en Mari puesto que se ha nombrado al incapaz músico Rīšīya como nuevo Jefe de la Música (*nargallum*) de Mari. La Música parece ser un estilo de vida en los Textos 24–25, en los cuales un hijo se quiere convertir en músico, y en nuestro Texto 27 la Música (**nam-nar**) es el destino (**nam**) de Enki para un ciego. Gracias al mismo, dicha persona ciega será el nuevo Jefe de la Música (**nar-gal**) del reino.

Hay, sin embargo, varios textos donde **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* significan definitivamente “Música”:

- En el Texto 4 de la Segunda Dinastía de Lagaš (Tercer Milenio a. C.), el cual describe la perfecta (**šu du7-a**) acción musical de tres instrumentos: los címbalos (**se-em**), el tambor gigante (**a2-la2**) y la lira (**balan**), más concretamente, el apreciado **balan** de Ninjirsu llamado **ušumgal kalam-ma**.

- En los Textos 33 y 39, ya del Período Paleobabilónico, los reyes Šulgi e Išmē-Dagān dicen haberse dedicado a la música y hacen referencia a varios de los instrumentos y cantos que dominaron. Algunos de esos instrumentos o cantos también concernían a la “música elegíaca” y no solo a la “música ceremonial”. Este es el caso del Texto 40. Allí el rey Išmē-Dagān se refiere, como uno de los aspectos difíciles de la Música (**nam-nar-ra ki bal-bal-la-bi**), a la expresión **šag4 ser3 se11(LUL)-da**: la acción de calmar (**se11**) el corazón (**šag4**) con las canciones **ser3**. Estos reyes también dominaron aspectos más intelectuales de la Música que los instrumentos o los cantos. Esto se puede ver en nuestro Texto 35, donde Šulgi afirma haber dominado el “sentido (profundo) de la Música” (**šag4 nam-nar-ra**). Esta expresión (**sag4 nam-nar-ra**) se refería a un aspecto musical bastante intelectual, tal y como se puede ver en nuestro Texto 25. En aquel fragmento la expresión **šag4 nam-nar-ra** designa algo musical que está muy alejado (**su3-ud**) del entendimiento humano. La distancia entre dicho entendimiento y el **šag4 nam-nar-ra** se comprara en aquel texto con la distancia entre las dos orillas de un océano.

- En los Textos 22–23 y 52, algunas personas son consideradas como “no aptas” (**nu-ub-du7** en el Texto sumerio 22, *ul redī* en nuestro Texto 52, en acadio) para la Música. Esas personas no podrían, por lo tanto, realizar ciertas actividades musicales, pero posiblemente tampoco otras actividades extra-musicales. Por ejemplo, en las dos primeras líneas de nuestro Texto 23 se dice “él no es apto para la Música, él no es adecuado para sus contenidos. Cuando va hacia la casa de otra persona, no es respetuosa con ella”. Esos aspectos no musicales podían ser, en todo caso, importantes para un músico. Esa situación podría explicarse teniendo en cuenta que los músicos en Mesopotamia trabajaban para diversas instituciones (templos, palacio, etc.) y, por lo tanto, debían ser respetuosos con el funcionamiento de aquellas instituciones.

Se pueden recordar también las referencias a **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* de algunos textos como un adjetivo. En los Textos 55–58 describía algunos instrumentos (*enūtu*) como “de

Música” (*nārūtīm/ša nārūti*) y **nam-nar** describía en nuestros Textos 9, 37–38, 59–60 una composición para ser cantada (*s/šer*₃) como “musical”. Hay que prestar atención también al uso de **NAM.NAR** para calificar un festival en nuestro texto 69 como “musical”. Finalmente, **nam-nar** era una referencia a la condición “musical” de un grupo de textos litúrgicos (**kešda**). Esos textos podían ser un conjunto de textos (litúrgicos) que el músico (**nar**) dominaba y utilizaba para sus actividades.

Finamente **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* se pudieron referir a la Música como una combinación de sonidos en el sentido actual de “Música” en algunos de nuestros textos:

- Este es el caso, por ejemplo, del Texto 34 (*Šulgi B*, 157), donde **nam-nar šu du7-a** podía describir el perfecto sonido musical de los tambores **tige**₂ y **a-da-ab**.
- Este significado pudo ser una variación literaria de la misma expresión **nam-nar šu du7-a** de nuestro Texto 4, un fragmento de los *Cilindros de Gudea*. En aquel texto **nam-nar šu du7-a** se refería a la perfecta acción musical obtenida con tres instrumentos musicales (**se-em**, **a2-la2** y **balan**). Esta expresión no designaba en los *Cilindros de Gudea*, sin embargo, nada de los sonidos musicales de aquellos instrumentos como en nuestro Texto 34. En todo caso, **nam-nar** como “Música” en tanto que combinación de sonidos no fue ninguna excepción en la Baja Mesopotamia concerniente solo a nuestro Texto 34. La expresión **<nam>-nar** ^{ueš}**tigidla**_x de nuestro Texto 12 es ciertamente una referencia al sonido musical del laúd ^{ueš}**tigidla**_x, puesto que el **nar** nunca utilizó aquel instrumento. No se puede, en consecuencia, traducir aquella expresión como “profesión del músico del ^{ueš}**tigidla**_x”. En ese Texto 12 se encuentra una referencia al **asila**₃ (un grito de alegría/júbilo) de los cantos **tige**_x y **a-da-ab**. La traducción de **<nam>-nar** ^{ueš}**tigidla**_x como “sonidos musicales del laúd ^{ueš}**tigidla**_x” podría tener sentido en consecuencia en aquel Texto 12.
- El Texto 48 de Mari es también muy relevante para la hipótesis de este estudio. El *nargallum* Rîšīya dice una persona llamada Muḥaddum que él, Rîšīya, había hecho (*epēšum*) Música (*nārūtum*) con los hijos de aquel Muḥaddum. Esa expresión, *nārūtam epēšum*, se podría entender como “desempeñar el oficio del músico” como en nuestro Texto 42. En aquel Texto 42 *nārūtum* se refería al oficio de un *nārum* consagrado al dios Āmûm. La respuesta de Muḥaddum a Rîšīya (*šūma ittikama ēpuš* “¡hazla contigo mismo!”) nos ayuda, sin embargo, a proponer una definición distinta

para aquel *nārūtum*. Aquel término podría designar en aquel Texto 48 algo que se podía realizar con o para otra gente, como hacer Música para alguien.

- Finalmente el Texto 49 de Mari hace referencia a la expresión *u nārūtam ana lâ'ûm ippeš* (“y el hace música para Lâ'ûm”). Como se ha expuesto en la sección 5.2.2.6 de este estudio, Lâ'ûm no es ningún nombre de ciudad, sino un nombre personal. Del mismo modo, para tener “y él hace Música en Lâ'ûm”, el texto debería de tener *u nārūtam ina lâ'ûm ippeš*. Esto es, el texto debería tener *ina* (“en”) y no *ana* (“para”).

En ese sentido, **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* no solo designaron “Música” *lato sensu*, sino también “Música” en tanto que combinación de sonidos como en nuestro término “Música”. No hubo nunca una oposición del tipo “música ceremonial” (**nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)*) vs. “música elegíaca” (**nam-gala/kalûtu(m)**) como algunos investigadores han propuesto. El término **nam-gala/kalûtu(m)** nunca significó “música elegíaca” solo designó “oficio del **gala/kalû(m)**”, “grupo de sacerdotes **gala/kalû(m)**” y “*corpus* textual del **gala/kalû(m)**” (solo en el 1er Milenio a. C.)

En todo caso ya había una palabra en Mesopotamia para “música alegre”, *nigûtu(m)*, por lo que no había razón para que **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* designaran aquello o algo similar. El término *nigûtu(m)* no solo designó “música alegre” sino también “alegría” o un tipo de festival puesto que procede de la palabra *nagû(m)* (“ser feliz”). En ese sentido, sus connotaciones musicales fueron minoritarias. Si **nam-gala/kalûtu(m)** y *nigûtu(m)* no hicieron referencia a tipos concretos de Música, **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* serían en consecuencia las únicas palabras para designar toda las actividades musicales en Mesopotamia, tanto las ceremoniales como las elegíacas.

En cualquier caso, el significado de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* experimentó algunos cambios durante la historia de Mesopotamia. Así, **nam-nar** significaría originalmente “Música” en el Tercer Milenio como se puede ver, por ejemplo, en nuestro Texto 4. Del final de ese Milenio provienen las primeras referencias a *nārūtu(m)*, término que designa el “oficio del músico (*nāru(m)*)” en dos cartas (Textos 7–8) de esa época. La acepción de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* como “oficio del músico” sería especialmente común durante el Segundo Milenio en los textos administrativos del Sur de Mesopotamia. Los textos del *curriculum* de los escribas y los textos literarios de aquella época, sin embargo, se referirán a **nam-nar** como “Música”. En el Norte de Mesopotamia, en Mari, *nārūtu(m)* significa “oficio del músico” en algunas cartas y en otras cartas “Música”.

Finalmente **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* harían referencia a tres aspectos musicales distintos hacia el Primer Milenio a. C. El primero de esos significados es “Música”, a encontrar en nuestros textos 58–60 y 69. El segundo significado, “oficio del músico” se encontrará en los textos legales neobabilónicos y aqueménides (Textos 61–66). Finalmente, **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* hicieron referencia a un grupo de textos que el músico conocía y/o utilizaba (Textos 67 y 70). En todo caso es mejor traducir el **nam-nar** de nuestro Texto 67 como “musical” con respecto a la gramática, puesto que el texto tiene **kešda nam-nar** y no **kešda nam-nar-ra**.

“Música” es por tanto, el principal significado de **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* en nuestros textos cuneiformes, ya que hay textos de la mayoría de períodos de la Historia de Mesopotamia con esos términos significando “Música”. Otros significados de esos términos son secundarios en los textos. Por una parte, nuestras referencias más antiguas a **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* como “oficio del músico” provienen tan solo del final del Tercer Milenio. Por otra parte, **nam-nar** y *nārūtu(m)* como referencia a un grupo de textos dominados por el músico solo son conocidos en los Textos del Primer Milenio.

En ese sentido, al contrario que en la investigación anterior, se puede hablar efectivamente de la existencia de una palabra para “Música” en la antigua Mesopotamia. Como se ha dicho anteriormente, esto tiene importantes consecuencias para las posibles y futuras investigaciones sobre el concepto de la Música en la Antigua Mesopotamia, el cual no ha sido bien explorado hasta ahora con respecto a otras culturas antiguas.

10.2. Zusammenfassung auf Deutsch

Viele *Termini* in den sumerischen und akkadischen Texten, die Instrumente, Musiker, Kompositionen oder einige Facetten der musikalischen „Performance“ des alten Mesopotamien bezeichnen, sind bekannt. Gab es jedoch jemals ein Wort in dieser Kultur, um diese musikalischen Aspekte in ihrer Gesamtheit zu benennen? Gab es ein Wort für „Musik“ in Mesopotamien wie z. B. in unserer westlichen Kultur?

Den heutigen Hauptforschern in der mesopotamischen Musik zufolge ist ein sumerischer oder akkadischer *Terminus* für „Musik“ nicht vorhanden. Insbesondere würde kein Wort existieren, mit der die Kombination von Klängen gemeint ist, wie in unserem westlichen Verständnis. Die *Termini*, die dem Wort „Musik“ am nächsten kommen, würden im Mesopotamien **nam-nar** (sumerisch) und *nārūtu(m)* (akkadisch) sein. Sie würden jedoch lediglich auf einige musikalische Aspekte, wie der Beruf eines Musikers oder die Fähigkeit zum Musizieren, bezogen sein. In jedem Fall wurden nur wenige Texte, in denen **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* erscheinen, von diesen Forschern, die diese Aussagen tätigten, analysiert.

Daher wurden in dieser Studie alle bis heute bekannten mesopotamischen Texte analysiert, in denen **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* erscheinen, um diese wissenschaftliche Übereinstimmung zu verifizieren bzw. zu falsifizieren. Die Hypothese dieser Promotionsarbeit ist, dass **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* tatsächlich „Musik“ bedeuten, und somit dieses Wort, „Musik“ wirklich in Mesopotamien existierte. Dies implizierte wesentliche Konsequenzen für die (mögliche) zukünftige Forschung über das mesopotamische Konzept von Musik. Sicherlich existierte keine Sache oder Idee für die Mesopotamier, wenn es dafür kein Wort gab. Man kann dies aus den ersten Zeilen des Schöpfungsmythos *Enūma Eliš* ersehen, aus denen hervorgeht, dass im Ursprung der Welt Himmel und Erde noch keinen Namen, also noch kein Wort dafür existierte hatten. Himmel und Erde einen Namen zu geben ist die Weise dieses Textes, um über dem Beginn ihrer Existenz im Universum zu sprechen.

Die Substantive **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* könnten *a priori* „Musik“ bedeuten, weil sie aus zwei Teilen bestanden. Einerseits haben sie eine Partikel (das sumerisch **nam-**, das akkadisch *-ūtu*), um abstrakte Substantive zu erschaffen. Andererseits bezeichnen **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* einen Musiker (der **nar/nāru(m)**), der mehrere Instrumente spielen und verschiedene Lieder singen konnte. In anderen Sprachen im alten Orient (i. e. Hethitisch, Hebräisch oder Altägyptisch) weisen die *Termini* für „Musik“ einerseits

keine Partikel für abstrakte Substantive auf. Andererseits beziehen sie sich nur auf eine Art Instrument oder Lied. Dies ist der Fall von der hethitisch Wort *zinar*, das sich nur auf der Musik der Lyra (*zinar*) bezog. Außerdem hatte man nicht nur im alten Griechenland und Rom Ausdrücke für ‚Musik‘, sondern es gibt sie auch in anderen alten Kulturen wie China und Indien.

Um die Hypothese dieser Studie zu beweisen, wurden in dieser Untersuchung insgesamt 70 Texte von der altakkadische Periode bis in die späte Seleukidenzeit mit einer Transliteration, einer Übersetzung, philologischen Anmerkungen und einem Kommentar vorgestellt und analysiert. Für die Transliterationen, die der Verfasser in dieser Edition vorlegt, benutzte er Kopien und Fotos der originalen Tontafeln aus anderen Publikationen. Einige Tontafeln wurden ferner in Museen, in denen sie sich derzeit befinden, kollationiert. Wenn mehrere Varianten für den gleichen Text bekannt sind, sind sie in dieser wie in einer musikalischen „Partitur“ (wie in anderen altorientalischen Studien) wiedergegeben und geordnet. Die Kommentare sind hauptsächlich philologisch, doch sind auch einige musikalische vorhanden, da **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* und andere wichtige *Termini* in diesen Texten musikalischer Natur sind. In diesem Sinne sind drei Disziplinen in der vorliegenden Untersuchung kombiniert: Assyriologie (für den kulturgeschichtlich Rahmen und die philologische Methodologie), Musikwissenschaft (für das Thema und einige Kommentare) und Geschichte, weil alle Exzerpten hier gemäß ihrer chronologischen und geografischen Herkunft präsentiert sind.

Nach der Einleitung, die in dieser Zusammenfassung kurz vorgestellt wird, erfolgt die Analyse der 70 Texte in fünf Kapiteln. Das erste Kapitel behandelt acht Texte aus dem 3. Jt. v. Chr.: zwei altakkadische Lebensmittelverteilungslisten, in denen **nam-nar** in unklarem Kontext genannt wird (Text 1–2), ein sehr fragmentarischer administrativer Text aus der zweiten Dynastie von Lagaš (Text 3), ein Exzerpt der *Zylinderinschriften von Gudea* (Text 4), zwei Texte über Musikerinnen/Weberinnen aus der Dritte Dynastie von Ur (Text 5–6) und zwei Briefe von Awal (Tell al-Sulaima) aus dem Übergang zur altbabylonischen Zeit, die *nārūtum* und *kala'ūtum* thematisieren (Text 7–8).

Das zweite Kapitel befasst sich zum einen mit Nennungen von **nam-nar** in einigen altbabylonischen Texten aus dem Grundcurriculum der Schreiber. Die Texte des Curriculums, die in dieser Studie kommentiert wurden, sind in erster Linie einige Extrakte der lexikalischen Listen *Proto-luz* (Zeilen 590–591 = Text 9), *Proto-izi* (Zeilen II 227–231 = Text 10) und **Niḫ₂-ga** (einsprachige Version, Zeilen 73–75 = Text 11). Ferner wurden zwei Musterverträge (Texte zum Erlernen der Verwaltungspraxis) (Texts 12–13)

und *Proverbs* 3.150 (Text 14) analysiert. Dieser letzter Text ist ein Beispiel für Texte, die Schreibern als Einführung in die sumerische Literatur dienten. Zum anderen werden in diesem Kapitel mehrere Texte über den Verkauf einiger Tempelpfründe (Texte 15–21) kommentiert, von denen einige (Texte 19a–21) relativ kürzlich publiziert wurden.

Das dritte Kapitel dient der Analyse des *Terminus nam-nar* in den altbabylonischen sumerischen literarischen Texten. Die ersten Extrakte dieses Kapitels stammen aus dem Rangstreitgespräch namens *Enkihegal und Enkitalu* (Zeilen 94–99 und 110–113¹⁵⁶⁹ = Texte 22–23). Dann wird ein Auszug aus dem Weisheitstext *Der Vater und sein missratener Sohn* (Zeilen 107–112 = Texte 24–25) analysiert. Die mythischen Erzählungen *Enki und Ninmah* (Zeilen b 26–29 = Text 27) und *Inanna und Enki* (Zeilen I v 33–34 und II v 47–52 = Texte 30–31) werden anschließend präsentiert. In der Analyse von *Enki und Ninmah* befindet sich auch eine kurze Edition nebst Kommentar des administrativen Textes TJA, S. 151 [UMM G 40] (Ammī-ditāna 23.10.02 (?)) (Text 28). Darüber hinaus werden Auszüge der folgenden Königshymnen kommentiert: *Ur-Namma A* (Text 31), *Šulgi B* (Texte 33–36), *Šulgi E* (Texte 26 und 32), *Šulgi CC* (Text 37, mit einem Kommentar zu der *Elegie auf den Tod des Nannā* = Text 38) und *Išmē-Dagān A + V* (Texte 39–40). Anschließend wird der Text 41 untersucht, der erst kürzlich publiziert wurde und dessen präzise literarische Subtypologie nicht bekannt ist.

Die Erwähnungen von *nārūtu(m)* in den Briefen aus dem altbabylonischen Mari sind im vierten Kapitel kommentiert. Die Texte sind entsprechend ihrer Zugehörigkeit zur Regierungszeit von Šamšī-Addu (Texte 42–52) oder Zimrī-Līm (Texte 53–54) gruppiert. Im letzten Teil dieses Kapitels werden Texte beider Regierungszeiten zusammen kommentiert, weil sie den Ausdruck *enūt nārūtīm* aufweisen (Texte 55–57). Dieses *enūt nārūtīm* („Musikinstrument“) wird in dieser Studie als eine Art Laute definiert.

Es wurden keine mittel-babylonischen oder mittel-assyrischen Texte mit **nam-nar** und/oder *nārūtu* bisher gefunden. Der Verfasser hat einige unpublizierte Tontafeln studiert (CBS 7826 und 8500, UM 29-15-72 und 29-15-211), um einen möglichen Verweis auf *nārūtu* zu finden. Diese Tontafeln beziehen sich jedoch nur auf Musiker (*nāru*). Daher beschäftigt sich das letzte Kapitel dieser Studie mit Texten des 1. Jt. v. Chr. Darin wurden zunächst drei neuassyrische Texte untersucht: ein lexikalischer Text, der

¹⁵⁶⁹ Mit freundlicher Genehmigung von Manuel Ceccarelli, der gerade an einer Gesamtausgabe dieses Textes arbeitet. Seine Edition von Zeilen 94–99 und 110–113 wurde für die vorliegende Untersuchung überarbeitet und einige Tontafeln dieses Textes für die Edition von dieser Studie kollationiert.

den Ausdruck *enûtu ša nārūti* („Musikinstrument“) beinhaltet, und zwei Verweise auf das Wort **šer₃ nam-nar** (wörtlich „musikalische Komposition, die gesungen wird“, eine Art Lied) (Texte 59–60). Anschließend werden einige Verkaufstexte von Tempelpfründen, die im Zusammenhang mit Musikern stehen (*nārūtu*), aus der neubabylonischen und achämenidischen Perioden (Texte 61–66) kommentiert. Schließlich werden einige seleukidische Texte untersucht: ein indirekter Verweis auf die *nārūtu*-Pfründe (Text 68), ein astrologischer Kommentar (Text 69), der den *Terminus* „Musikfest“ (**IZIN NAM.NAR**) beinhaltet, und zwei Verweise auf **nam-nar** und *nārūtu* als „Texte, die Musiker benutzten werden“ (Text 70 und möglicherweise auch Text 67).

Nach dieser Analyse ist der erste Eindruck, dass es in vielerlei Hinsicht schwierig ist, konkret etwas über **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* zu sagen, was sowohl für als auch gegen die Hypothese des Verfassers sprechen mag. Dies ist durch die aktuelle Anzahl der Texten, die **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* beinhalten, bedingt, sowie ihren Erhaltungszustand und die spezifischen Probleme in Bezug auf jeden dieser Texte.

Im Folgenden sei auf verschiedene Probleme innerhalb der einzelnen Zeitperioden eingegangen.

In der altakkadischen Periode (Texte 1–2) könnten **lugal-nam nar** („Lugalnam, der Musiker“) und **sipa-nam nar** („Sipanam, der Musiker“) als **lugal-nam-nar** („König (der) Musik“) und **sipa-nam-nar** („Hirte (der) Musik“) transkribiert werden. Wir haben anderen Namen mit *lugal* + ein Abstraktum mit *nam-* (z.B. *Lugal-namzitara*) in Texten aus der gleichen Zeit belegt. Da **lugal-nam(-)nar** und **sipa-nam(-)nar** jedoch aus einfachen Lebensmittelverteilungslisten bekannt sind, ist es schwierig, etwas zur möglichen Bedeutung von **nam-nar** als „Musik“ in diesen Texten zu sagen.

In der zweiten Dynastie von Lagaš bezog sich **nam-nar** in den *Zylinderinschriften von Gudea* (Text 4) eindeutig auf „Musik“, während andere Verweisen auf **nam-nar** aus der gleichen Periode (Text 3) weniger eindeutig sind. In Bezug auf die Ur III-Zeit gibt es viele Verweise auf den Musiker (**nar**), aber nur einen sicheren Beleg für **nam-nar** (Text 5). Andere Hinweise auf **nam-nar** aus der Ur III-Zeit (Text 6) sind nicht eindeutig, da nur **nar** explizit erwähnt ist und der Rest des Wortes aus dem Kontext ergänzt wird. Die ersten Nennungen von *nārūtum* (Text 7–8) könnten aus dem Übergang zum 2. Jt. v. Chr. stammen, doch wird ihre präzise Datierung diskutiert.

Die altbabylonischen Texte aus dem zweiten Jahrtausend enthalten viele Verweise auf **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)*, doch sind sie in verschiedener Hinsicht problematisch, insbesondere solche aus dem Süden Mesopotamiens. Zum Beispiel sind in Bezug auf die

literarischen Texte, in denen **nam-nar** genannt wird, ihr Entstehungsdatum, die Herkunft oder der Verfasser nach bisherigem Stand der Forschung unbekannt. Ein präziser Kontext für die literarischen Texte mit **nam-nar** ist wichtig, um diese literarischen Texte mit den zeitgenössischen juristischen Texten mit **nam-nar** zu vergleichen. Sicherlich bedeutet **nam-nar** in diesen juristischen Texten zumeist nicht „Musik“, sondern nur „Beruf des Musikers (**nar**)“, obwohl „Musik“ die korrekte Bedeutung für *nārūtum* in Text 28 sein könnte.

Diese Dichotomie könnten wir lösen, indem wir uns die altbabylonischen Texte aus Mari ansehen, weil alle Verweise auf *nārūtu(m)* in Mari nur in Briefen belegt sind. Hingegen wurde **nam-nar** in Südmesopotamien in Texten dreier verschiedener Typologien erwähnt: juristische, literarische und Schultexte. In jedem Fall gibt es eine große geografische Distanz zwischen Mari (in Nordmesopotamien) und Südmesopotamien. Außerdem ist Mari ein Unikum in Nordmesopotamien, weil nur die altassyrischen Texte Verweise auf *narūtum* (eine Art Malz) machen und die neuassyrischen Texte mit Erwähnungen von **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu* meistens fragmentarisch sind.

Unser wichtigstes Problem ist im Moment der Übergang vom zweiten zum ersten Jahrtausend, weil keine mittelassyrischen oder babylonischen Text belegt sind, in denen **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* vorkommt. Zwar wurden einige unpublizierte Texte in dieser Untersuchung analysiert, doch wird in diesen nur auf Musiker (*nāru*) Bezug genommen.

Die neubabylonischen und achämenidischen juristischen Texte des 1. Jt. v. Chr. erwähnen den Begriff *nārūtu(m)* im Sinne von „Beruf des Musikers (*nāru*)“ in zweierlei Hinsicht: zum einen als Musiker eines Gottes oder einer Göttin, zum anderen, wenn auch seltener, als Musiker, der ein bestimmtes Instrument bzw. Lied spielt. Die Lesung und Interpretation von literarischen Texten ist jedoch in Bezug auf mehrere Aspekte komplizierter als die der Verwaltungstexte.

Zunächst einmal gibt es verschiedene mögliche Lesungen und Interpretationen von EZEN NAM-LUL (**šer₃ nam-nar**, ***šer₃ nam-lul** und **kešda nam-nar**) in Text 67. Ferner stellt sich die Frage, ob das Sumerogramm NAM.NAR in dem astrologischen Kommentar in Text 69 tatsächlich *nārūtu(m)* zu lesen ist? Könnte es ein Verweis auf *nigūtum* sein? Schließlich gibt es in unserem Text 70 zwei Probleme. Zum einen kann man ein Zeichen als BA oder NA identifizieren, um *bārūtum* oder *nārūtu* zu lesen. Zum anderen ist es schwierig, *nārūtu* als „Texte, die vom Musiker (*nāru*) gelernt/benutzt wurden“ zu definieren, weil kein mesopotamischer Text im Moment zu dieser „Gruppe“ gehört.

Ferner ist die späte Datierung dieser Texte zu beachten. Die Bedeutung von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* könnte in dieser Zeit im Vergleich zu Nennungen in älteren Perioden sehr unterschiedlich gewesen sein.

In jedem Fall ist davon auszugehen, dass in den meisten der hier vorgelegten Texte die Bedeutung von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* „Musik“ ist. Mitunter ist diese Deutung anzuwenden, weil wir nicht genug Informationen über die Musiker haben, auf die in diesen Texten Bezug genommen wird. In diesem Sinne kann man keine konkretere Übersetzung für **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* in diesen Texten vorschlagen. Dies ist bei den juristischen und administrativen Texten 5–6 und 28 der Fall, aber ebenso in Text 41, wo **nam-nar** in einem fragmentarischen Kontext genannt ist. Bei diesen konkreten Textbelegen kann „Musik“ für **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* eine bessere Übersetzung sein als eine spezifische Bedeutung.

An anderen Stellen ist die Übersetzung „Musik“ für **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* geeignet, weil sich diese *Termini* in bestimmten Texten auf mehrere Instrumente, Liedern oder Musiker beziehen. Dies ist in unserem Text 12 der Fall, bei dem es sich um einen Mustervertrag handelt. Unter anderem beinhaltet dieser Text, dass eine Person einige musikalische Aspekte erlernt: das **asila₃** (ein Art-Freudenschrei oder Jubel) von den **tige_x** und **a-da-ab** Hymnen und wie man das ^u**tigidla_x** (eine Art Laute) spielt. Ferner ist auf Text 22, einem Auszug Extrakt aus *Enkiheṅal und Enkitalu* (Zeilen 94–99), hinzuweisen. Verschiedene Elemente der Vokalmusik (i.e den **en₃-du** Liedern) und Instrumentalmusik (i.e der **za₃-mi₂** Winkelharfe) werden dort mit **nam-nar** bezeichnet. Die Übersetzung von *nārūtu(m)* als „Musik“ ist aus einem ähnlichen Grund in den Texten 44–52 aus Mari interessant.

Andere Texte stellen **nam-nar** oder *nārūtu(m)* in einen Kontext, in dem man immer noch das Wort „Musik“ benutzen könnte. Ein Beispiel bilden die Texte 33 und 49, in denen die Könige Šulgi und Išmē-Dagān behaupten, sich der Musik gewidmet zu haben. In dem Text 41 sagt ein angeblicher Student, dass er Musik studieren möchte. In Bezug auf die Texte aus Mari ist insbesondere der Text 46 zu erwähnen. König Šamšī-Addu konstatiert in diesem Text, dass die Musik (*nārūtum*) in Mari „zerstört“ wurde, weil der unfähige Musiker Rīšīya zum Hauptmusiker von Mari ernannt wurde. Musik erscheint als Lebensziel in den Texten 24–25, in denen ein Sohn ein Musiker sein möchte, in dem Text 27 ist Musik das von Enki (**nam**) für eine Blinde vorgesehene Schicksal. Dank dieses Schicksals wird diese blinde Person zum Hauptmusiker (**nar-gal**) des Königreichs.

Es gibt jedoch einige Texte, in denen **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* zweifellos „Musik“ bedeutet:

- Text 4 aus der zweiten Dynastie von Lagaš (3. Jt. v. Chr.) beschreibt die perfekte (**šudu7-a**) musikalische Fähigkeit von drei Musikinstrumenten nämlich den Cymbeln (**se-em**), der (Riese)Trommel (**a2-la2**) und der Lyra (**balaj**), genauer gesagt, der von Ninjirsu geliebten **balaj** namens **ušumgal kalam-ma**.
- In den Texten 33 und 39 aus altbabylonischer Zeit behaupten Šulgi und Išmē-Dagān, sich der Musik gewidmet zu haben, und führen diverse von ihnen beherrschte Instrumente und Gesänge an. Einige dieser Instrumente oder Gesänge sind der „elegischen Musik“ und nicht allein der „Festmusik“ zuzuordnen. Das ist der Fall in unserem Text 40. Dort bezeichnet der König Išmē-Dagān als einen der schwierigsten Aspekte der Musik (**nam-nar-ra ki bal-bal-la-bi**), den er gelernt hat, den Ausdruck **šag4 ser3 še11(LUL)-da**: eine Handlung, um das Herz (**šag4**) mit den **ser3** Liedern zu beruhigen (**se11**). Diese Könige beherrschten auch Aspekte der Musik, die „immaterieller“ als Instrumente oder Liedern waren. Dafür ist der Text 35 anzuführen, in dem Šulgi behauptet, „den (tiefen) Sinn der Musik“ (**šag4 nam-nar-ra**) gemeistert zu haben. Dieser Ausdruck (**šag4 nam-nar-ra**) verweist auf eine sehr intellektuelle musikalische Facette, wie man in Text 25 sehen kann. In diesem Exzerpt bezeichnet **šag4 nam-nar-ra** etwas musikalisches, das sehr fern (**su3-ud**) vom menschlichen Verständnis ist. Die Distanz zwischen diesem menschlichen Verständnis und **šag4 nam-nar-ra** wird in dem Text mit der zwischen den zwei Ufern eines Ozeans verglichen.
- In den Texten 22–23 und 52 werden einige Personen als „nicht geeignet“ (**nu-ub-du7** in dem sumerischen Text 22, *ul redī* in unserem akkadischen Text 52) für die Musik beschrieben. Diese Personen konnten deshalb nicht gut musikalische Aktivitäten ausführen, aber möglicherweise auch keine anderen außermusikalischen Tätigkeiten. So heißt es zum Beispiel in den ersten zwei Zeilen von Text 23 „er ist nicht geeignet für die Musik, er ist nicht geeignet für ihre Inhalte (= die der Musik). Wenn er zum Hause einer anderen Person geht, so ist er dieser gegenüber respektlos“. Diese andere nicht musikalische Facette könnte in jedem Fall wichtig für die Musiker sein. Man könnte diese Situation so erklären, dass Musiker in Mesopotamien bestimmten

Institutionen (Tempel, Palast) dienten und sie deshalb die Arbeitsweisen dieser Institutionen beachten mussten.

Man könnte außerdem die Nennungen von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* in einigen Texten als Adjektive interpretieren. In den Texten 55–58 werden einige Instrumente (*enūtu*) mit „von Musik“ (*nārūtīm/ša nārūti*) näher bestimmt, während **nam-nar** in unseren Texten 9, 37–38, 59–60 mit einer musikalischen Komposition, die gesungen wird, gleichgesetzt wird (**s/šer₃**)“. Zu beachten ist auch der Gebrauch von **NAM.NAR**, um ein Fest (**IZIN**) in unserem Text 69 als „musikalisch“ zu kennzeichnen. Schließlich war **nam-nar** ein Hinweis auf einer ‚Gruppe von (liturgischen) Texten‘ (**kešda**), die der Musiker (**nar**) zu beherrschen hatte und für seine Tätigkeiten benutzte.

Schließlich könnten sich **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* auf Musik als eine Kombination von Klängen wie in unserer modernen Definition für „Musik“ beziehen:

- Dies ist z. B. in unserem Text 34 (*Šulgi B*, 157) der Fall, in dem sich der Ausdruck **nam-nar šu du₇-a** auf den perfekten musikalischen Klang der Trommeln **tige₂** und **a-da-ab** bezieht.
- Diese Bedeutung könnte eine (literarische) Variation des gleichen Ausdrucks **nam-nar šu du₇-a** in Text 4 sein, einem Exzerpt der *Zylinderinschriften von Gudea*. In diesem Text bezog sich **nam-nar šu du₇-a** auf das perfekte musikalische Ergebnis, das mit drei Instrumenten (das **se-em**, **a₂-la₂** und **balaj**) erzeugt wurde. Dieser Ausdruck bezog sich in den *Zylinderinschriften von Gudea* jedoch dort nicht auf den musikalischen Klang dieser Instrumente wie in unserem Text 34. In jedem Fall war nicht dieser Verweis auf **nam-nar** als „Musik“ als eine Kombination von Klängen eine Ausnahme in Südmesopotamien. Der Ausdruck **<nam>-nar ʾeš₇tigidla_x** in Text 12 ist sicherlich ein Hinweis auf den musik(alischen Klang) der ʾeš₇tigidla_x Laute, weil der Musiker (**nar**) noch nie die ʾeš₇tigidla_x Laute spielte. Man kann deshalb nicht **<nam>-nar ʾeš₇tigidla_x** mit „Berufs des Musikers des ʾeš₇tigidla_x“ übersetzen. In diesem Text 12 findet man einen Hinweis auf den **asila₃** (Freudenschrei/Jubel) von den **tige_x** und **a-da-ab** Liedern. Die Übersetzung von **<nam>-nar ʾeš₇tigidla_x** als „musik(alischen Klang) der ʾeš₇tigidla_x Laute“ würde deshalb in diesem Text 12 Sinn ergeben.

- Text 48 aus Mari ist ebenfalls sehr relevant für die Hypothese dieser Studie. Der *nargallum* Rîšīya sagt zu einer Person namens Muḥaddum, dass er (Rîšīya) Musik (*nārūtum*) mit den Söhnen des Muḥaddum gemacht hatte (*epēšum*). Dieser Ausdruck, *nārūtam epēšum*, könnte als „den Beruf des Musikers ausführen“ wie in unserem Text 42 verstanden werden. In diesem Text 42 würde *nārūtum* auf den Beruf eines *nārum* des Gottes Āmûm verweisen. Die Antwort des Muḥaddum zu Rîšīya (*šūma ittikama ēpuš*, „mache es mit Dir!“) hilft uns in dem Text 48, um eine andere Bedeutung für *nārūtum* vorzuschlagen. Der *Terminus nārūtum* könnte in diesem Text 48 auf etwas, das man für/mit anderen Leuten machen kann (wie ein Musikstück für jemanden spielen), verweisen.
- Schließlich beinhaltet Text 49 aus Mari den Ausdruck *u nārūtam ana lâ'ûm ippeš* („und er macht Musik für Lâ'ûm“). Wie in Teil 5.2.2.6 dieser Studie dargelegt, handelt es sich bei Lâ'ûm nicht um einen Ortsnamen, sondern nur ein Personennamen. Um „und er macht Musik in Lâ'ûm“ zu finden, sollte der Text *u nārūtam ina lâ'ûm ippeš* haben. Das heißt, der Text müsste *ina* („in“) und nicht *ana* („für“) haben.

In diesem Sinne benannten **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* nicht nur ‚Musik‘ im weiteren Sinne, sondern sie bedeuteten auch ‚Musik‘ als Kombination von Klängen wie das Wort ‚Musik‘ unseres heutigen Sprachgebrauchs. Es gab nie eine Opposition vom Typ „zeremonielle Musik“ (**nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)*) gegen „elegische Musik“ (**nam-gala/kalûtu(m)**), wie einige Forscher gesagt haben. Der *Terminus nam-gala/kalûtu(m)* bedeutete tatsächlich nie „elegische Musik“. Es bedeutet nur „Beruf des **gala/kalû(m)**-Priesters“, „Gruppe von **gala/kalû(m)**-Priesters“ und „Gruppe von Texte, die vom **gala/kalû(m)** gelernt/benutzt waren“ (nur im 1. Jt. v. Chr.)

In jedem Fall existierte bereits in Mesopotamien ein Wort für die ‚Jubelmusik‘, *nigûtu(m)*. Es deshalb keinen Grund, **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* mit ‚fröhlicher Musik‘ oder ähnlichem gleichzusetzen. *nigûtu(m)* bedeutete nicht nur ‚Jubelmusik‘, sondern auch ‚Freue‘ oder eine Art Festival, weil *nigûtu(m)* von *nagû(m)* („glücklich sein“) kommt. In diesem Sinne waren die musikalischen Konnotationen von *nigûtu(m)* in der Minderheit. Wenn **nam-gala/kalûtu(m)** und *nigûtu(m)* keine Verweise auf verschiedene Arten von Musik bildeten, waren **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* die einzigen Wörter, um alle musikalischen Aktivitäten (zeremonielle oder elegische) in Mesopotamien zu bezeichnen.

In jedem Fall würde die Bedeutung von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* innerhalb der historischen Entwicklung Mesopotamiens einige Veränderungen erfahren.

Somit bedeutete **nam-nar** ‚Musik‘ im dritten Jahrtausend, wie man es z. B. in unserem Text 4 sehen kann. Aus der Ende dieses Jahrtausends kommen die ältesten Verweise auf *nārūtu(m)*, dem Wort, das ‚Beruf des Musikers (**nar/nāru(m)**)‘ in zwei Briefen (Texte 7–8) aus dieser Zeit bedeutet. Der Sinn von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* als ‚Beruf des Musikers‘ wird dann während des zweiten Jahrtausends gewöhnlich in den juristischen Texten aus Südmesopotamien bekannt sein. In den Texten über das Curriculum der Schreiber und den literarischen Texten bedeutet **nam-nar** jedoch Musik. In Nordmesopotamien bedeutet *nārūtu(m)* in einigen Briefen ‚Beruf des Musikers‘, aber ‚Musik‘ in anderen.

Schließlich würden drei verschiedene Bedeutungen für **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* in den Texten aus dem 1 Jahrtausend erkennbar werden. Die erste wäre ‚Musik‘, wie aus unserem Texten 58–60 und 69 hervorgeht. Die zweite Bedeutung ist ‚Beruf des Musikers‘ und erscheint in neubabylonischen und achämenidischen juristischen Texten (Texten 61–66). Schließlich kann sich in unseren Texten 67 und 70 **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* auf eine ‚Gruppe von Texten, die vom Musiker gelernt/benutzt waren‘, beziehen. In jedem Fall ist es in Bezug auf die Grammatik, besser, **nam-nar** im Text 67 als ein Adjektiv (‚musikalisch‘) zu übersetzen, weil der Text **kešda nam-nar** und nicht **kešda nam-nar-ra** aufweist.

‚Musik‘ ist deshalb in unseren keilschriftliche Quellen die Hauptbedeutung von **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)*, weil es Texte aus den meisten Perioden der Geschichte Mesopotamiens mit diesen zwei *Termini* mit dieser Bedeutung ‚Musik‘ gibt. Andere Bedeutungen dieser *Termini* sind in den Texten sekundärer Natur. Einerseits kommen die ältesten Verweise auf **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* als ‚Beruf des Musikers‘ aus dem Ende des dritten Jahrtausends. Andererseits sind **nam-nar** und *nārūtu(m)* in Bezug auf eine Gruppe von Texten, die vom Musiker gelernt wurden, nur in Texten aus dem ersten Jahrtausend bekannt.

In diesem Sinne kann man daher, anders als in der früheren Forschung, von der Existenz eines Wortes für ‚Musik‘ im alten Mesopotamien sprechen. Wie bereits angemerkt, ist das sehr wichtig für mögliche zukünftige Studien über das Konzept der

Musik im alten Mesopotamien, das in Bezug auf anderen antiken Kulturen noch nicht sehr gut untersucht ist¹⁵⁷⁰.

¹⁵⁷⁰ Herzlichen Dank zu Heidi Köpp-Junk für ihre Korrekturen von unserem Deutsch Text.